

IASTA National Conference 2023

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Conference Proceedings of IASTA 2023

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Preface

The Indian Aerosol Science and Technology Association (IASTA) is hosting the National Conference (IASTA 2023) during 12-14, December 2023 at Vivanta, Navi Mumbai, Maharashtra, India. IASTA 2023 focuses on range of topics covering aerosol fundamentals, aerosol modelling, instrumentation, aerosol characterization, air quality, nuclear & radioactive aerosols, bio aerosols and aerosol health effects.

The aim of IASTA 2023 is to provide a platform to researchers, technocrats, policy-makers and students for presenting their ideas, research work and views. IASTA 2023 will give an excellent opportunity to participants to interact, collaborate and contribute towards the growth of aerosol science and engineering. The conference will also offer a unique opportunity for industries to showcase their technologies, products and innovations.

Scientific programme of conference includes Key Note address, Plenary Lectures, Invited Talks, Proffered Papers & Posters (71 platform, 60 lightning, and more than 140 poster presentations), and Technical Exhibition of different products and systems related to aerosol research, technology and allied areas. The conference also includes Panel Discussion on the topic “Air Quality in Mumbai”.

The technical programme committee thank all the invited speakers, panellists, authors of proffered papers, and reviewers who have supported in finalising the scientific and technical programmes. The committee thank all the persons involved in bringing out the proceedings, well in time for the IASTA 2023. We take this opportunity to wish all the delegates interactive and fruitful discussions during the conference.

(Technical Programme Committee)

IASTA 2023

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AEROSOL TRANSPORT MECHANISMS OVER THE CENTRAL HIMALAYAN REGION

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CRUISING THROUGH COMMUTES: CHARACTERIZATION AND DEPOSITION MODELING OF SIZE-SEGREGATED PM EXPOSURE

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EVALUATION OF SODIUM AEROSOL TRANSPORT EFFICIENCY IN CIRCULAR TUBE

RESUSPENSION DYNAMICS OF THERMOPHORETICALLY DEPOSITED PARTICLES VIA SHOCKWAVE INTERACTION

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QUANTIFYING THE IMPACT OF CROP RESIDUE BURNING ON AMBIENT PM_{2.5} MASS CONCENTRATION OVER THE INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN USING THE WRF-CHEM MODEL

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EVALUATION OF PM₁₀ AND PM_{2.5} MODEL DATA THROUGH CAMS BIAS CORRECTION

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MODELING OF AEROSOL FORMATION UNDER RAPID THERMAL TRANSIENTS

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VARIATION OF GROSS ALPHA AND GROSS BETA ACTIVITY CONCENTRATION IN AIR PARTICULATE MATTER AT NAPS NARORA SITE DURING 2012-2022

⁷Be ACTIVITY IN AIR AND MEAN RESIDENCE TIME AT KAIGA SITE

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STUDY OF IODINE OXIDE AEROSOLS IN CONTEXT OF SEVERE NUCLEAR REACTOR ACCIDENTS

GRAPHITE AEROSOL GENERATION AT DIFFERENT HEATING CONDITIONS

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HEALTH EFFECTS AND BIOAEROSOLS

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CARBONACEOUS AEROSOLS

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SEASONAL VARIATION OF AEROSOL OPTICAL DEPTH OVER INDIA UNDER FUTURISTIC CLIMATE SCENARIOS: AN IMPLICATION OF CARBONACEOUS AEROSOLS

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GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION OF BLACK CARBON FROM SATELLITE RETRIEVAL

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SOURCES OF FINE CARBONACEOUS AEROSOLS OVER A SEMI-ARID URBAN CITY OF WESTERN INDIA USING DUAL CARBON ISOTOPES

THE SMOG-INDIA_{COALESC} EMISSIONS INVENTORY

CHARACTERISTICS, TEMPORAL VARIATION, AND SOURCE IDENTIFICATION OF FINE CARBONACEOUS AEROSOLS OVER INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN IN INDIA

HIGH-RESOLUTION AEROSOL EMISSIONS FROM CROP RESIDUE BURNING: A COMPONENT OF SMOG-India_{COALECE}

OPTICAL PROPERTIES OF PM_{2.5} FROM LIGHT-DUTY GOODS AND HEAVY-DUTY VEHICLES IN INDIAN ON-ROAD CONDITIONS

DECADAL TREND OF BLACK CARBON AEROSOLS AT A SEMI-URBAN LOCATION IN THE CENTRAL IGP

VERSATILE SOURCE SAMPLING SYSTEM (VS3): TRACKING ON-FIELD RESIDENTIAL COOKING ACTIVITY EMISSIONS IN INDIA.

CONFERENCE SPONSORS

KEYNOTE ADDRESS

FROM AEROSOL SYNTHESIS OF MATERIALS AND DEVICES TO A NEW VALUE FOR THE MEAN FREE PATH OF AIR

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The lecture will start with a fascinating overview of flame aerosol technology from ancient times in Asia, to the bible printing by Gutenberg and to the current manufacture of nanostructured commodities (carbon black, fumed SiO₂, pigmentary TiO₂ and nanosilver, among many others). Recent advances in understanding of combustion and aerosol formation and growth through multiscale process design, allow now inexpensive synthesis of nanoparticles with sophisticated composition, size and morphology by flame spray combustion at kg/h even at an academic institution [1] with such units now all over the world (UK, Spain, India etc.). These have led to synthesis of single noble atom heterogeneous catalysts, highly porous self-assembled lace-like or cauliflower-like gas sensing films and biomaterials.

These advances and community's keen interest on nanoscale phenomena have motivated a closer look to the fundamentals of aerosol dynamics in the free molecule regime. The mean free path (MFP) dictates when gas-phase nanoparticle transport takes place in the free molecule or continuum regime. This distinction is crucial in process design of gas phase processes (laser, plasma, hot wall, ultrasonic and flame) in material synthesis (films and nanoparticles). For eons, the kinetic theory of gases [2] has been used to determine the MFP assuming elastic collisions between spherical gas molecules. However, is this so with what we know about molecular shape and force fields today? Having reached a state of maturity now, molecular dynamics (MD) simulations can elucidate the fundamentals of basic gas-phase (aerosol) processes that lead to understanding of natural phenomena and accelerating process scale-up [3]. Here the mechanics of gas collisions are elucidated for plain air at room temperature by thoroughly-validated atomistic MD treating O₂ and N₂ as true diatomic molecules accounting for their shape and force field, for the first time to our knowledge.

The MD simulations were conducted for air in the NVE ensemble at 300 K & 1 atm. Treating O₂ and N₂ as hard spheres led to the straight trajectories (Fig. 1a) and collision frequencies, in perfect agreement with classic kinetic theory. Accounting, however, for the molecular shape and force field, trajectories were no longer straight, and collision frequencies were much higher due to the attractive part of the force field and the diatomic, thus more voluminous, shape of N₂ and O₂ (Fig. 1b) as will be shown by the respective videos.

Fig. 1: Collision trajectories by a) classic kinetic theory and b) detailed accounting of attractive and repulsive forces between diatomic gas molecules (like N₂ and O₂). The reference (stationary) molecule is in white, and the colliding one in blue. The bold line shows the trajectory followed by the moving molecule before & after collision while the thin one helps to determine the collision parameter b .

Detailed analysis of the latter trajectories revealed that molecular collisions involve strong interactions between colliding molecules. Frequently, colliding molecules were split from each other but soon return to collide again and again without interacting with any other molecule in between resulting in orbiting collisions (Fig. 2a) as had been envisioned 70 years ago (Fig. 2b) by Hirschfelder et al. [4]. Such collisions are termed spurious and were systematically removed from the analysis to avoid overcounting collisions. These complex collision patterns were never observed by treating O₂ & N₂ as hard spheres!

Fig. 2: (a) Seven spurious collisions within 17.1 ps by a pair of colliding molecules during a single otherwise collision event. This is an orbiting collision (b) as had been envisioned by Hirschfelder et al. [4].

A direct result of the enhanced interactions between air molecules when treated as true diatomic molecules is that their MFP comes out to be considerably smaller than that from the classic kinetic theory. The new value of the MFP for air is 38.5 nm, almost 43% smaller than the currently known and widely used value in textbooks of 67.3 nm at 300 K and 1 atm. Aside from its fundamental value, such a result is significant in gas-phase synthesis of tiny (< 5 nm) nanoparticles where asymptotic (self-preserving) particle size distributions and (fractal-like) structure have not been attained yet to simplify the corresponding process design [5].

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PLENARY LECTURES

EMERGING CHALLENGES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF AIR CLEANING TECHNOLOGIES: FROM INDOOR AIR PURIFIERS TO OUTDOOR SMOG TOWERS

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The recognition of the overwhelming ill-effects on human health posed by exposure to air particulate matter has brought in a paradigm shift in defining the quality of life among large sections of world's populations. Indoor air purifiers are increasingly being used by urban populations as necessary gadgets for living a healthier life-style. The recent experience of the global outbreak of COVID-19 and the potential threat of emergence of newer forms of airborne diseases are further reinforcing the perception of indoor air purifiers as risk reduction devices. Air purifiers make up a multi-billion dollar industry at present and are poised to reach much higher levels as the demand is expected to increase among the urban populations in populous developing countries. In order to bring down the cost and improve performance, constant search is on for technologies using different principles of filtration and ionization. Future technologies could include hybrid concepts involving ESPs, electrospays and filtration principles. Certain basic physics and engineering challenges have to be overcome before these ideas could be implemented competitively with existing technologies.

On the other side, rising levels of outdoor air pollution in cities has been a matter of great concern in recent years. It is well recognized that outdoor air pollution can only be mitigated by controlling emissions at the sources and ensuring strict regulatory compliance. Unfortunately, these measures have largely remained elusive as of now. In Delhi and in large parts of Gangetic plains, episodes of hazardous levels of PM concentrations are seen to occur regularly in winter, year after year. To combat such episodes, equipping the society with a suitable clean air delivery technology will be a helpful step, among a portfolio of measures. In this context, the conception of a design of outdoor air cleaners began to be discussed in scientific circles since 2015 (Cao et al. 2015). It was quite clear from engineering and mathematical considerations that high-throughput clean air delivered into ambient domain, could travel significant distances to supply purified air to general public. This amounts to creation of a clean air zone by technological means. In view of the acute air pollution events faced in the city of Delhi and other places during winter, there were ongoing efforts by central agencies to explore the outdoor air cleaning technologies. Upon careful examination of the engineering basis of various proposals, it was clear that the system proposed by the group of aerosol scientists from the University of Minnesota, had the suitable Clean Air Delivery Rate (CADR), following as it were, from established filtration principles. Hence it was considered suitable for a pilot study for assessing its performance in ambient domain of Delhi. The design concept was provided by the Clean Air Care CCL set up by the University of Minnesota faculty, and the systems were installed by Tata Projects Limited with technical support from IIT Bombay. The two units, one at Anand Vihar and another at Connaught place were funded by the Central Pollution Control Board and the Delhi Pollution Control Committee, respectively. IIT Bombay conducted the detailed evaluation of the intrinsic performance of the system as well as its impact in the ambient domain at various distances. The objective was clear: Evaluate the range of impact and the air cleaning efficiency for $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} at different distances from the installed facility, in the ambient domain.

In this backdrop, the talk will highlight the development of ideas on Indoor air cleaning technology. Also, the rationale for setting up outdoor air cleaners (smog towers), the challenges faced in the installing them, the complex task of performance evaluation and the conclusions arising from the vast data collected, will also be presented. An attempt will be made, in the light of the experimental observations, to clarify certain misconceptions existing in the public domain on this study.

AEROSOLS, NUCLEAR ENERGY AND ENVIRONMENT

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Imagine a “worst-case scenario” when all nuclear reactors worldwide are shut-down and replaced by coal/gas plants. It is for sure that the aerosol and CO₂ emissions will have distinct effect on climate change, which in fact is the most difficult challenge the world is facing today. On the contrary, nuclear power can reduce greenhouse gas and aerosol emissions while ensuring firm supply of energy for economic growth. However, there is public fear of radiation, which originates from Linear No-Threshold (LNT) model i.e. even a single radiation has an excess risk of cancer. In this talk, we present an overview of radiation, which is an integral part of the civilisation. The LNT model does not consider the adoptive response of biological systems, and has created unnecessary fear of radiation in public. We will try to analyse the past studies, scientific biases, ethical and moral challenges, nuclear fallout, and the development of international policies. It is emphasized that there is a need to carry out extensive scientific studies (especially at low doses) and to move away from LNT model to a more realistic Hormesis model that considers adoptive responses. However, for this quantum biology studies on DNA repair mechanisms at low doses should be conducted to ensure any beneficial effects at low doses.

**THE COALESCE NETWORK: UNRAVELLING AEROSOL EFFECTS ON
CLIMATE AND AIR POLLUTION IN INDIA**

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There are examples of network projects in India over the last two decades, which have examined the role of aerosols in climate change. Important gaps remain, however, in understanding human activities influencing emissions, aerosol thermodynamic and optical properties, and atmospheric processes, specifically related to carbonaceous aerosols, vis-à-vis their impacts on the country's climate and air quality. The COALESCE network (<https://ncapcoalesce.iitb.ac.in/>) involves 22 institutions, working in coordination with the Indian Ministry for Environment, Forests, and Climate Change, under the National Carbonaceous Aerosols Programme. It involves more than 40 investigators, in consultation with representatives from government agencies, with expertise in aerosols, air pollution, radiation, and monsoons, among others, and over 80 researchers. In this talk I will present science highlights from the project that relate to new knowledge on intrinsic aerosol properties and aerosol impacts on regional air quality and climate. I will reflect on intrinsic composition and optical properties of aerosols, including spectral absorption and first field measurements illustrating the black-brown carbon continuum. In regard to air pollution, a weight of evidence approach will be illustrated to estimate quantitative source apportionment of PM-2.5, from emission strengths of sources and sectors from a new emissions inventory (at a high resolution of 5x5 km all over India), top-down receptor modelling from detailed measurements (including advanced receptor modelling methods) and bottom up chemical transport modelling using the new emission inventory for India. COALESCE is envisaged as a first step toward building an integrated aerosol, air pollution, and climate research community in South Asia, with links to India's national plans regarding air quality and international climate change commitments.

INVITED TALKS

SOURCE APPORTIONMENT AND OXIDATIVE POTENTIAL OF PARTICULATE MATTER IN INDIA, CHINA AND EUROPE

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INTRODUCTION AND METHODS

Most mitigation measures regarding air quality are tackling particulate matter. However, such strategies do not take into account the variability in the toxicity of different components or sources of particles in the air. Oxidative potential (OP) is a reasonably easy way to measure the toxicity particles using DTT, ascorbic acid, DCFH or other assays. In several projects in Asia (India, China, and Europe) we measured oxidative potential together with sophisticated aerosol instrumentation including off-line/on-line OP, aerosol mass spectrometry (Daellenbach et al., 2016), extractive electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (Lopez-Hilfiker, 2019; Qi et al., 2020), on-line x-ray fluorescence (Furger et al., 2017) and off-line inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry.

CONTENT OF PRESENTATION

We discuss here the concentrations of oxidative potential in different regions in the world with a focus on India including multiple cities. We statistically relate the oxidation potential to different sources that were obtained by state-of-the art off-line and on-line source apportionment using the instrumental methods mentioned above. We will discuss the comparison of the toxicity for different sources/components of the measured aerosol concentrations. We will show significant differences in the OP concentration that are

correlated to aerosol mass concentrations but are also strongly influenced by different sources present and varying source toxicity at different sites. Our baseline for comparison was presented by Daellenbach et al. (2020). In that study, secondary organic aerosols and vehicular wear were found to be the most dominant contributors to OP in Europe. In India and also in China, other components are important which is crucial for the evaluation of cost-effective measures to mitigate health impacts on the population.

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MEASURING AEROSOL ABSORPTION FOR SOURCE APPORTIONMENT AND QUANTIFICATION OF CLIMATE CHANGE

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Keywords: aerosol absorption coefficient, black carbon, light absorbing aerosols, filter absorption photometer.

INTRODUCTION

Measuring the aerosol absorption coefficient is central for the determination of the aerosol influence on the climate (Bond *et al.*, 2013) and for the determination of sources of carbonaceous aerosol, especially black carbon (BC; Sandradewi *et al.*, 2008). Different methods can be used to determine or measure the aerosol absorption coefficient. Filter absorption photometers (such as Aethalometers; Drinovec *et al.*, 2015) are most easy to deploy and use in varying field conditions, while more sophisticated methods may be more suitable for laboratory studies. Lately, photoacoustic instruments (Arnott *et al.*, 2005) and photothermal interferometers (Visser *et al.*, 2020; Drinovec *et al.*, 2022) have bridged the lab-to-field divide.

METHODS

Filter absorption photometers such as the Aethalometer (Hansen *et al.*, 1984, Drinovec *et al.*, 2015) or PSAP (Bond *et al.*, 1999) and CLAP (Ogren *et al.*, 2017) collect the airborne particles continuously on the filter and measure the transmission of light through the sample-laden filter. Making several assumptions allows black carbon concentration or particle absorption coefficient to be calculated from the attenuation of the light due to the collected sample between consecutive measurements. The method is simple and the instruments can be easily operated in challenging environments, such as the South Pole or the Arctic. However, while the filter increases the sensitivity, it also perturbs the sample and causes systematic artefacts that need to be accounted for (Bond *et al.*, 1999; Weingartner *et al.*, 2003). Two major effects impacting the measurement – the loss of sensitivity due to the accumulation of the sample (the loading or “shadowing” effect) and the cross-sensitivity to scattering, are usually treated separately. The former is measured in the Aethalometer AE33 (Drinovec *et al.*, 2015), while the latter is sometimes neglected. There is a lack of standardized calibration procedures for the optical measurement in filter photometers and there is no traceable calibration.

The photoacoustic instruments measure the pressure fluctuations as the heat is transferred from the heated aerosols into the surrounding air, the effect is amplified in acoustic resonator enhancing the signal nonlinearly (Arnott *et al.*, 2005). The transfer of heat is affected by coating of the absorbing aerosol core, water adsorbed onto aerosol and by relative humidity of the sample, resulting in a negative artefact (Langridge *et al.*, 2013).

A photothermal interferometer similarly measures the change of the refractive index caused by light absorption in (and the subsequent heating of) the sample – the change of phase in the interferometer is proportional to the aerosol absorption coefficient (Moosmüller & Arnott, 1996; Sedlacek, 2006). The detection is linear and can be traced to first principles. Since the laser-sample interaction region is monitored continuously, the method does not suffer from artefacts. The interferometric measurement can be calibrated to first principles (Drinovec *et al.*, 2022).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

We present different methods outlining the principles and relevant details impacting their sensitivities. We show that robust quality control procedures improve the results not just on the scale of an individual filter photometer, but on a scale of very large instrumental networks (Cuesta-Mosquera *et al.*, 2021). We show how source apportionment can be validated using C^{14} measurements (Zotter *et al.*, 2017) and how source-specific parameters can be estimated in their absence (Tobler *et al.*, 2021). Using results of measurements performed in contrasted environments, we show the limits of the filter photometer measurements due to the cross-sensitivity to scattering and different sensitivities of different aerosol types and size distributions, and parametrize the calibration as a function of single-scattering albedo (Yus-Díez *et al.*, 2022).

We present the new two-wavelength (532 and 1064 nm) photothermal aerosol absorption monitor (PTAAM-2) uses a folded Mach-Zender interferometer (Drinovec *et al.*, 2022). The two pump lasers at 532 and 1064 nm are modulated at different respective frequencies and focused in the sample chamber using an axicon for simultaneous measurement. Measurement at two wavelengths results in the absorption Ångström exponent (AAE), crucial for source apportionment. We show the traceable calibration to primary standards of the measurement at 532 nm using $\sim 1 \mu\text{mol/mol}$ NO_2 using a permeation NO_2 source; and how the calibration is transferred to the IR using aerosolized nigrosin (Drinovec *et al.*, 2022). Instrumental uncertainties are quantified. We show how filter photometers (CLAP, AE33) were calibrated in green and near infrared with soot, and determined their cross-sensitivity to scattering for ammonium sulfate particles, resulting in wavelength and size dependent calibration parameters.

Laboratory and ambient campaigns have shown similar filter photometer calibration parameter values for ambient aerosols and laboratory experiments. The spectral dependence of these parameters resulted in somewhat biased AAE values from Aethalometers. We have also determined the absorption enhancement by coating BC with non-absorbing secondary organic matter in laboratory (Kalbermatter *et al.*, 2022) and ambient campaigns in contrasted environments in a traffic dominated urban background and a rural wood-burning hotspot (both Slovenia), regional background impacted by a mega-city (Paris). Mass absorption cross-section increase due to coatings were determined using different mass metrics – elemental carbon (EN 16909:2017, using Sunset off line OC/EC analyzers) or refractory black carbon (using SP2).

We finish with a description of the standardization efforts in Europe, describing how measurements of the aerosol absorption coefficient and black carbon mass-absorption cross-section will be standardized and calibrated to the primary standards, and how filter photometer calibration will be performed using standard operating procedures, which will allow these efforts to be conducted in any aerosol laboratory.

CONCLUSIONS

Measuring aerosol absorption for climate and source apportionment studies is not easy due to various instrumental measurement artefacts. The calibration, traceable to primary standards, is crucial for the quantification of the anthropogenic impact on the environment. While filter photometers are easy to use, the data they produce is difficult to interpret in environments with high single-scattering albedo. The linearity & traceable calibration position multi-wavelength PTI as an excellent candidate for the reference method to measure the aerosol absorption coefficient, as illustrated by laboratory & ambient measurements in contrasting environments.

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PM_{2.5} AND AIR POLLUTANTS OBSERVATIONS FOR STUDYING CROP RESIDUE BURNING IN A TARGET REGION OF NORTHWEST INDIA

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Keywords: CROP RESIDUE BURNING, PUNJAB, DELHI, PM_{2.5} AIR POLLUTION.

INTRODUCTION

Intensification of agriculture around the world during the green revolution was the key to support present day human population on the Earth. However, exposure to particulate matter less than 2.5 μm in diameter (PM_{2.5}) has become a cause of concern in cities and major emission regions of northern India due the crop residue burning (CRB) in the past 2-3 decades. The existing ground network of air quality measurements in India focuses on urban areas, where the population density is high. This type of ground network and data gaps in satellite remote sensing due to clouds have failed to capture the linkages between peak CRB emissions in rural areas and the hazardous air pollution events in the neighbouring cities. The RIHN initiated project AAKASH entitled "An Interdisciplinary Study toward Clean Air, Public Health and Sustainable Agriculture: The Case of Crop Residue Burning in North India", in collaboration with various institutions in India. One of the overarching goals of the project is to elucidate the origin and effects of CRB-related air pollution on Delhi NCR in the post-monsoon season using a dense network of low-cost Compact and Useful PM_{2.5} Instrument with Gas sensors (CUPI-Gs; Nakayama et al., 2018).

METHODS

An intensive field campaign involving the states of Punjab, Haryana and Delhi national capital region (NCR) was conducted in Sep-Nov 2022 using 29 CUPI-Gs. The measurement network is shown in Fig. 1 (map). The CUPI-Gs also measure carbon monoxide (CO), ozone (O₃) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x), which are serving as important elements for estimation of secondary PM_{2.5} production in the downwind regions of the CRB on event basis. We tested the CUPI-Gs before the campaign for calibration and scaling factors for PM_{2.5} sensors are determined, and various other QA/QC checks are performed during the campaign.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Continuous observations show that the PM_{2.5} in the region increased gradually from < 60 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in 6–10 October to up to 500 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ on 5–9 November, which subsequently decreased to about 100 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in 20–30 November (Fig. 1). Two distinct plumes of PM_{2.5} over 500 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ are tracked from crop residue burning in

Punjab to Delhi NCR on 2–3 November and 10–11 November with delays of 1 and 3 days, respectively. Experimental campaign demonstrates the advantages of source region observations to link agricultural waste burning and air pollution at local to regional scales (details in Singh et al., 2023).

Figure 1. Daily mean PM_{2.5} concentrations over different regions, i.e., Punjab (a: source), Haryana (b: intermediate) and Delhi NCR (c) during the intensive field campaign (1 September -30 November 2022) along with daily VIIRS-based fire counts and over Punjab and Haryana and Global Satellite Mapping of Precipitation (GSMaP) based rainfall (d). PM_{2.5} concentrations along with aerosol optical depth (AOD) at individual sites are

shown in Fig. S1.

CONCLUSIONS

A dense and strategically positioned measurement network over NW-IGP in September-November 2022 provided a unique and valuable dataset that helped in understanding the impact of crop (paddy) residue burning in the Punjab-Haryana region on the air quality of Delhi NCR. Our results highlighted that PM_{2.5} has spatial and temporal variabilities that are of serious concerns for air pollution exposure to the rural population. Measurements covering wider regions of the IGP at a network of sites must be established and sustained for tracking the overall improvements in air quality relating to the governmental policies.

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HEALTH EFFECTS OF ATMOSPHERIC AEROSOL DRIVEN PARTICULATE MATTER AND ITS COMPONENTS: STUDIES FROM INDIA

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Air pollution has been a major public health issue in India, causing a range of health problems, including respiratory illnesses, cardiovascular diseases, and cancer. In 2019, 1.67 million deaths in India were attributable to air pollution, accounting for 17.8% of the total deaths in India. Lost output from premature deaths and morbidity attributable to air pollution accounted for economic losses of US\$28.8 billion and \$8.0 billion, respectively, in India in 2019; 1.36% of India's gross domestic product (GDP). Though global data base on air pollution and health effects are quite strong, but very limited evidence is from studies in India. Recently, a cohort of southern India (APCAPCS) observed negative associations between ambient PM_{2.5} and household air pollution and lung function in young adults. They also reported the association between ambient and household air pollution and carotid intima-media thickness (CIMT), a marker of atherosclerosis. Two of the recent mother child cohorts in South Indian (TAPHE & HAPIN) reported 4gm and ~2gm reduction in birth weight for 10µg/m³ increase in PM_{2.5} exposure of mother during pregnancy. Another study reported 7.23% increase in odds of anemia of adult women for 10 µg/m³ increase in ambient PM_{2.5} exposure and among PM_{2.5} species, sulfate and black carbon revealed stronger association with anemia. A very recent study published in Nature communication reported that the cumulative effect of PM_{2.5} components is larger than the effect of PM_{2.5} mass on child health in India. A study from the CARRS cohort (Chennai & Delhi) recently reported 1.22 times increase in T2DM risk for every 10 µg/m³ increase in long term PM_{2.5} exposure. Though sparse, but there are now strong growing evidence of air pollution and health effects across the ranges of health issues in India which could be sufficient for designing a sector specific mitigate plan for air pollution and health effects. But yet to focus on collecting evidence for few more important endpoints such as neurological disorder among children and elderly, Cardiovascular illness including premature CAD, Metabolic disorder, kidney disorder, cancer etc.

AEROSOL-RADIATION VERSUS AEROSOL-CLOUD INTERACTIONS OVER THE SOUTH ASIAN REGION

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Atmospheric aerosols exert a broad influence on climate through two distinct pathways: (i) direct interaction with radiation, known as aerosol radiation interaction (ARI), and (ii) modification of cloud properties, referred to as aerosol cloud interaction (ACI). Radiative forcing is commonly used as an index for quantifying such imbalances in the Earth's radiation budget by any factor. Quantifying aerosol effective radiative forcing (ERF) is an initial step towards understanding the response of the Earth's climate system to changes in emissions of aerosols from anthropogenic sources from pre-industrial to present day. A positive ERF implies warming effect, and a negative ERF implies cooling effect of aerosols on the climate system of our planet. Global Climate models with interactive atmospheric chemistry are the best tools available with the scientific community for quantifying the radiative forcing due to aerosols as well as the climate responses to this important driver of climate change at various scales.

A global chemistry-climate model named CAM6 is used to understand implications of changing emissions of aerosols and its precursors over the historical period (1900-2014) on the evolution of aerosol and cloud radiative forcing on a global scale with special focus on the South Asian region. Our results show that although the overall effect of changing emissions aerosols and their precursors from anthropogenic sources is to produce a net (longwave plus shortwave) negative radiative forcing at the top of atmosphere (TOA) thereby resulting in cooling over the south Asian region, we find that while ARI alone leads to warming but ACI results in cooling over the same region. Results of our simulations further show that while the annual mean net ERF_{ARI} averaged across the Indian land mass due to all major aerosol species is around $+0.39 \text{ W/m}^2$ but the annual mean net ERF_{ACI} is -2.61 W/m^2 thereby signifying an overall cooling effect due to aerosols. More results with greater details regarding the contribution of individual aerosol species towards the temporal evolution of ERF_{ARI} and ERF_{ACI} will be presented. Further, results of our systematically designed model sensitivity simulations to understand the influence of different aerosol types on cloud cover, cloud vertical structure, cloud droplet number concentrations, ice-crystal number concentration, other cloud microphysical parameters and ACI sensitivities over the south Asian region will be presented.

ATMOSPHERIC CHEMISTRY MODELING IN THE ERA OF CLIMATE CHANGE

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The atmospheric Chemistry, where aerosols is one of the many components, was paid least attention by meteorologist and climate scientists in India but, lately, it has registered a central place when its importance is realized. It is clear from the emerging science and satellite views that while local action has to gather momentum, bigger solutions need regional scale action because air pollution moves across boundaries. In the era of fast changing climate, extreme events are more frequent than ever and we need to understand the underlining processes for abrupt variability for which solutions will emerge only from high resolution chemical transport models. In recent time, La Nina, which lasted in its third consecutive year, disturbed global weather and the Indian monsoon pattern. However, the linkages of such changes to regional air quality have yet to be explored. Recently, the winter of 2022-23 that coincided with retreating phase of the unprecedented triple dip La-Niña, was marred by a mysterious trend in air quality in different climatological regions of India, not observed in recent decades. model simulation tend to suggest that, beyond just influencing the meteorology, the interactions between the ocean and the atmosphere during the retreating phase of the La-Niña produced secondary results that significantly influenced the normal mechanism of the distribution of air quality through disturbed large-scale wind patterns. While La Niña is a natural phenomenon, in the context of global warming, more moisture gets concentrated in the atmosphere, resulting in a colder winter season and the sudden emergence of extreme events, which points toward climate change.

AEROSOL FUNDAMENTALS – PHYSICS, CHEMISTRY, AND BIOLOGY

**UNDERSTANDING THE MUTUAL RESPONSE BETWEEN NEAR SURFACE
TEMPERATURE AND AEROSOL (BC AND NON-BC PM_{2.5}) MASS CONCENTRATION IN AN
URBAN ENVIRONMENT**

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Keywords: aerosol fundamentals, surface temperature, mutual response

INTRODUCTION

The mutual response between near surface aerosol concentration and surface temperature is complex in nature and is still not sufficiently discussed in literatures (Sand et al., 2019). In order to analyze the aerosol environment over a region it becomes very significant to understand its mutual response with its ambient meteorology. A recent work by Talukdar and Ratnam (2021) had put efforts to understand the mutual response between surface temperature and aerosol using observational data of black carbon (BC) aerosols and surface temperature over Gadanki, a rural location in peninsular India and the outcome of that study led to a hypothesis. The hypothesis states that ‘more fall in morning hour surface temperature (T) contributes to the enhancement of BC aerosols fumigation peak after the sunrise which positively impacts the extra rise in mid-day temperature’. The original study was performed mainly for a rural location. However, regarding different aerosol environments, the statement of this BC-T hypothesis is much relevant to an urban environment which was not thoroughly tested in the original study. Further, the original study worked on BC aerosols and did not test the mutual response hypothesis for non-BC PM_{2.5} aerosols. The probability of the high loading of both BC and Non-BC PM_{2.5} aerosols over an urban site may make the mutual response more complicated which needs to be investigated. These aspects motivated us to conduct the present work of methodically testing the validity of the BC-T hypothesis for both BC and non-BC fraction of PM_{2.5} over Kolkata, a densely-populated city in the Eastern India, using the suite of measurements at Kolkata Camp Observatory of NARL (KCON) along with other supporting data.

METHODS

A prominent fumigation peak in the diurnal pattern of BC surface mass concentration is observed during the morning hours well after the sunrise (between 0600 and 0800 LT (LT=UT+05:30 h). All the daily fumigation peak values are normalized with respect to its upper limit and grouped proportionally in four classes as low (BCP1 < 0.25), average (0.25 ≤ BCP2 < 0.5), above average (0.5 ≤ BCP3 < 0.75), and high (0.75 ≤ BCP4). To calculate the degree of temperature fall, the minimum value of surface temperature (between 0500-0600 LT) is subtracted from the mean value of temperature during 0100 to 0600 LT and the mid-day temperature rise is calculated by subtracting the minimum value of surface temperature in the morning from the mean value of temperature during 1100 to 1300 LT. Then, applying the necessary boundary conditions of total cloud cover, wind speed and specific humidity on the total data set, the dates meeting these boundary conditions are considered and the morning hour temperature fall and mid-day temperature rise values of those dates are grouped corresponding to the four classes of fumigation peak values (i.e., BCP1, BCP2, BCP3, BCP4) and are separated out for different seasons.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The present study has confirmed that more falls in morning hour surface temperature (T) is linked to the enhancement of the morning hour BC fumigation peak which positively influences the extra rise in mid-day temperature during the day time and clearly supports the statement of the previously mentioned hypothesis. For the non-BC fraction of PM_{2.5}, as has been examined statistically and then introspectively

with case studies, it is observed that the first part of the hypothesis is equally valid for non-BC fraction of $PM_{2.5}$ which means more fall in morning hour surface temperature (T) contributes to enhance the morning fumigation peak of non-BC fraction of $PM_{2.5}$ along with BC. This happens possibly because more fall in morning hour temperature is the indicator of the stronger nocturnal inversion which causes an additional amount of aerosol to remain trapped in the residual layer from the previous night. The analysis also shows that for the non-BC fraction of $PM_{2.5}$, the second part of the hypothesis which tells about the impact of the enhanced peak concentration on the mid-day temperature rise is valid in other way that ‘the enhancement of non-BC $PM_{2.5}$ (mostly scattering) aerosols peak after the sunrise can negatively influences the mid-day temperature rise over a region during the day time’ as non-BC $PM_{2.5}$ is likely to exert cooling effect.

Figure 1. (Top to bottom) Total cloud cover (TCC), early morning surface temperature fall, corresponding morning BC peak concentration levels and corresponding hike in surface temperature during mid-day in (a) pre-monsoon and (b) post monsoon seasons for different BC categories, (c) and (d) same as (a) and (b) for corresponding morning peak categories of $PM_{2.5}$ during pre-monsoon and post monsoon.

CONCLUSIONS

The present observation over Kolkata for both BC and non-BC fraction of $PM_{2.5}$ aerosols evidently supports the statement of the previously reported BC-T hypothesis. This study also indicated a significant aspect in the original hypothesis that even a high BC condition with a background of enhanced non-BC $PM_{2.5}$ may show apparent weak response of surface temperature. Thus, the actual BC-T mutual response should be considered under a given range of background non-BC $PM_{2.5}$ concentration and the vice-versa.

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RADIATIVE FORCING DUE TO BLACK CARBON AT AN URBAN LOCATION IN INDIA

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Keywords: BLACK CARBON, AETHALOMETER, AEROSOL OPTICAL DEPTH, RADIATIVE FORCING

INTRODUCTION

Carbonaceous aerosol is ubiquitous in troposphere and other than being a pollutant plays an important role in global climate. It can be classified as visible light absorbing black carbon (BC) and light scattering organic carbon (OC). BC is an operationally defined aerosol species based on its optical properties. It absorbs light throughout the visible spectrum and exhibits absorption angstrom exponent around 1 (Moosmüller et al., 2011). BC aerosol radiative forcing refers to the impact of black carbon aerosols on the earth's radiation balance. It is influenced by different factors such as its aerosol optical depth, mass concentration, size distribution, as well as atmospheric setting in which it is present. The magnitude of the direct radiative forcing ($+1.1 \text{ W m}^{-2}$) indicates BC to be the second most important component of global warming after CO₂ (Bond et al., 2013). However, this radiative impact is poorly constrained and is masked by large uncertainties. Consequently, in recent years, the impact of BC on the earth radiative balance has been extensively studied in many regions. Most investigations on BC radiative forcing in South Asia have concentrated on the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP), which is considered a hotspot for biomass-burning emissions (Bisht et al., 2015). However, very few studies on BC radiative forcing have been documented on the west coast of India (Babu et al., 2002; Kumar and Devara, 2012). In the present study, the clear sky short wave radiative forcing due to BC at an urban location in Mumbai is investigated.

METHODS

The observation period for BC in the present study is from September 2017 to May 2018. The optical properties of aerosols were estimated using OPAC (Optical properties of aerosols and clouds) model (Hess et al., 1998). We have used the BC concentration (obtained using Aethalometer, Model AE-33), water soluble and water insoluble mass to estimate their number densities using size distribution listed in the OPAC. These number densities were used as an anchoring point to formulate the composite aerosol model. The number density of mineral dust species was iteratively varied until agreement (within 2 %) was reached between modeled and satellite (AQUA) observed aerosol optical depth at 550 nm. The optical properties obtained for this composite aerosol model (single scattering albedo SSA, asymmetry parameter ASY and AOD) were used in SBDART model along with other inputs like atmosphere type, surface reflectance (8-day L3 Global 500 m MODIS), water vapour (Atmospheric InfraRed Sounder) and ozone (Ozone monitoring instrument). SBDART is a software tool that computes plane-parallel radiative transfer in clear and cloudy conditions within the earth's atmosphere and at the surface. The model provided the radiative fluxes at surface and top of atmosphere (100 km). Similarly, the calculations were repeated for the composite aerosol model without the inclusion of BC and no aerosol case. The difference between these computed fluxes provided the radiative forcing (short wave: 0.2 – 4 μm) due to BC at the surface (SUR) and the top of the atmosphere (TOA). Further, within the atmosphere forcing (ATM) was estimated as the difference between the surface and the top of the atmosphere forcing.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The SSA, ASY and AOD for the composite aerosol and BC were obtained from OPAC. The SSA gives the measure of absorbance by the aerosol model. SSA for the composite aerosol ranged from 0.65 to 0.89 for the sampling duration. It was observed that with the increase in BC concentration resulted in the decrease in the SSA of the composite aerosol and thus were negatively correlated. This is due to increase in absorption by the composite aerosol as a result of increase in BC concentration. The BC AOD ranged from 0.04 to 0.16 during the sampling period and it contributed around 22 % to composite aerosol AOD. These optical properties were used in SBDART to compute the radiative forcing potential of BC. The monthly averaged variations of shortwave clear sky BC aerosol radiative forcing (ARF) at TOA,

SUR and ATM over Mumbai for the period September, 2017 to May 2018 obtained in this study is shown in Fig. 1. The BC ARF range from 1 to 16, -4 to -62 and 7 to 66 $W m^{-2}$ at TOA, SUR and ATM, respectively. The BC ARF at TOA was positive for all the months signifying heating effect produced by the BC aerosol. The BC ARF at TOA was highest in the winter months which is characterised highest atmospheric BC concentration at the sampling location. The negative BC ARF at the surface indicates a net cooling effect at the surface.

Figure 1. Black carbon shortwave direct radiative forcing over Mumbai at top of atmosphere (TOA), surface (SUR) and atmosphere (ATM).

CONCLUSIONS

The aerosol measurements along with the OPAC and SBDART model provided the estimates for BC radiative forcing. For the entire observation period the mean values of BC ARF were $4.8 \pm 2.8 W m^{-2}$, $-19 \pm 10 W m^{-2}$, $24 \pm 10 W m^{-2}$ at TOA, SUR and ATM respectively. The positive radiative forcing values of BC at the TOA underscores the substantial impact of BC on radiative balance, with implications for local climate dynamics and broader discussions on climate change.

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**INFLUENCE OF AEROSOL COLUMNAR AND VERTICAL DISTRIBUTION ON THE
MODULATION OF ATMOSPHERIC AND SURFACE SOLAR HEATING**

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Keywords: Aerosol-Radiation Interaction, Aerosol Radiative Forcing, Heating Rates, Atmospheric State, Aerosol extinction coefficient.

INTRODUCTION

The atmospheric aerosols interact with incoming solar radiation, altering Earth's radiation budget by scattering and absorbing shortwave (SW: 0.25 to 4 μm) and longwave (LW: 4 to 50 μm) radiation and is referred to as direct aerosol radiative effect (DARE) (IPCC, 2021). The quantification of DARE under clear-sky conditions typically involves determining aerosol radiative forcing (ARF) and heating rates (HRs) through a combination of aerosol observations and radiative transfer (RT) calculations. These calculations necessitate precise characterization of aerosol-related properties, involving measurements either integrated over the atmospheric column or with vertical profiling. The properties of aerosols at various altitudes have a direct impact on radiative forcing and heating rates. While metrics like column-integrated Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD), Single Scattering Albedo (SSA), and asymmetry parameter (ASY) offer a simplified way to represent aerosols in radiative transfer calculations, their effectiveness diminishes when vertical distribution shows significant variations in extinction (both scattering and absorption). Moreover, when dealing with scenarios such as elevated aerosol layers or volcanic aerosols, the complexity of aerosol extinction and scattering properties becomes more pronounced. These aerosols exhibit distinct characteristics due to their unique sources and transport mechanisms. Additionally, many previous studies consistently highlighted the importance of accurate aerosol profile representation in DARE impact estimations (e.g. Feng et al., 2016). Considering these aspects, the current study aims to investigate the impact of two aerosol descriptions: namely, Columnar Properties (CP) and Vertical Distribution (VD) on the estimation of DARE over a tropical location Gadanki (13.48° N, 79.18° E, 375 m above mean sea level) in South India using ground-based and satellite-based aerosol measurements.

METHODS

Long-term (December 2013 to November 2020) collocated ground-based measurements of column-integrated aerosol optical properties (AOD, SSA, ASY) from the Sky Radiometer, CALIPSO aerosol extinction profiles, and in-situ atmospheric profiles (from balloon-borne sondes) available from Gadanki are used to define the CP and VD aerosol descriptions and atmospheric state in the radiative transfer calculations. The ARF and HRs were calculated in SW and net (SW + LW) spectral regions using the SBDART (Santa Barbara DISORT (Discrete Ordinate Radiative Transfer) Atmospheric Radiative Transfer model) (Richiazzi et al. 1998).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

We found that the column-integrated properties (CP) of aerosols resulted in a significant underestimation of Aerosol Radiative Forcing (ARF) compared to those with vertical distribution (VD) of aerosol properties. On comparing the SW ARF estimates at the TOA, SUR, and in the ATM for the column-integrated descriptions of aerosol parameters (CP), we found that they have slight seasonal dependency at the TOA (-5 to -12 W m^{-2}), SUR (-4 to -15 W m^{-2}), and in the ATM (+10 to +20 W m^{-2}). The inclusion of vertical profiles of aerosol extinction coefficient with VD description of aerosol properties resulted in a significantly large ARF in SW region differing with seasons (Figure 1). It is noteworthy that the LW forcing plays a considerable role in compensating for the impact of SW forcing in this instance. Among the different seasons, higher warming in the ATM prevailed during pre-monsoon,

followed by the monsoon, winter, and post-monsoon. Despite showing lower values of ARFs, the description CP retains the ability to preserve the sign of ARF and capture the pattern of HRs along altitudes.

Figure 1. Aerosol Radiative Forcing (ARF) at the top-of-the-atmosphere (TOA), surface (SUR), and atmosphere (ATM) in different spectral regimes (SW, LW, and Net) obtained for CP and VD aerosol descriptions during the winter (a), pre-monsoon (b), monsoon (c), and post-monsoon (d) seasons. The black vertical lines on each of the bars correspond to $\pm 1\sigma$ standard deviation of the respective forcing component for the entire study period.

CONCLUSIONS

The column-integrated properties (CP) of aerosols resulted in a significant underestimation of ARF compared to the potentially more accurate vertical distribution (VD) of aerosol properties.

The net ARF is dominated by the SW region.

The estimated radiative impacts were found to vary with season with higher warming in the pre-monsoon over Gadanki.

Accurate information of aerosol vertical profiles are necessary for quantifying the radiative impacts.

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MOLECULAR FINGERPRINTS OF MONOCARBOXYLIC ACIDS IN ATMOSPHERIC
AEROSOLS: SOURCES AND FORMATION PROCESSES

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INTRODUCTION

Organic aerosols (OAs) are made up of a complex mixture of different chemicals. Water-soluble monocarboxylic acids (MCAs) can alter the hygroscopic and cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) properties of atmospheric aerosols. Low-molecular-weight MCAs are more prevalent in the gas phase than in the particle phase (Andreae *et al.* 1988). Yu (2000) claims that their concentration levels in atmospheric aerosols are adequate to activate particles as CCN. Biomass burning has been identified as the prime source of OAs in eastern central India. However, the region is a receptor site for transported aerosols from the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP), where aerosols are enriched with biomass burning products and industrial emissions. Moreover, the intense solar radiation during the summer may induce enhanced production of secondary OAs in the atmosphere of eastern central India.

We collected fine aerosols (PM_{2.5}) during March to June 2017 at the forest site in eastern central India. The samples were analyzed for water-soluble MCAs and levoglucosan. The purpose of this research is to assess the molecular fingerprints of water-soluble MCAs and examine their sources and formation processes in the atmosphere of eastern central India. The results from this research are expected to improve the understanding of atmospheric processing and the impacts of water-soluble OAs of PM_{2.5} in the atmosphere of eastern central India.

METHODS

The location of the campaign site (Ambikapur: 23.1°N and 83.2°E) and its surroundings are shown in Fig. 1. The site is located in an upland region at an elevation of 623 m above sea level. The site is represented by enormously rich vegetation. Therefore, the region represents a unique rural location in eastern central India with low anthropogenic emissions. The mean ambient air temperature and relative humidity during the campaign were 29°C and 33%, respectively. The prevailing wind direction was westerly and northwesterly, with a mean wind speed of 4.5 km h⁻¹. The total amount of rainfall was 385 mm during the campaign.

PM_{2.5} samples were collected at the campaign site on a terrace of an observatory about 15 m above ground level using a Thermo Andersen (USA) high-volume (1.1 ± 0.1 m³ min⁻¹) on pre-baked (500°C for 6 h) quartz fiber filters from March 01 to June 25, 2017. The sampling duration was 24 h for each sample. We collected a total of 30 PM_{2.5} samples and 3 field blanks. We analyzed the samples for water-soluble MCAs and levoglucosan using a gas chromatograph equipped with a flame ionization detector (GC-FID) and mass detector (Deshmukh *et al.* 2019; Kawamura *et al.* 2023).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

We detected a homologous series of MCAs (C₁-C₁₀), including normal-chain saturated and aromatic compounds in PM_{2.5} samples. Their mean molecular fingerprints show the predominance of formic acid (C₁), followed by acetic acid (C₂). Both C₁ and C₂ acids contributed on average 85% of the total measured MCAs in PM_{2.5} during the campaign. High abundances of C₁ and C₂ acids in aerosols in eastern central India perhaps show that they are the product of photochemical chain reactions in the atmosphere. Interestingly, nonanoic acid (C₉) is the next abundant species, followed by benzoic acid. It is reported that higher terrestrial plants and biomass burning emit unsaturated fatty acids (FAs) such as oleic acid (C_{18:1}), which are subsequently photochemically decomposed into C₉ acid in the atmosphere (Kawamura *et al.* 2023). This result suggests that the photochemical alteration of unsaturated FAs is substantial in eastern central India.

Figure 1. Location of the sampling site Ambikapur (23.1°N and 83.2°E) in eastern central India

Figure 2. Molecular distribution of water-soluble monocarboxylic acids in PM_{2.5} at a forest site in eastern central India

Temporal changes in the concentrations of major MCAs are higher during early to late April than early to late March and then continuously decrease from early May to late June. We presume the substantial contribution of locally produced aerosols to transported aerosols at a forest site in eastern central India. The emission strength of biomass burning and meteorology might be critical factors that influence the atmospheric levels of MCAs in PM_{2.5} over eastern central India.

Massive biomass burning from forest fires was seen in April during the campaign (Deshmukh *et al.* 2019), which implies that MCAs are closely linked with biomass burning in eastern central India. We found that C₁-C₆, C₉ and benzoic acid present a strong positive correlation with levoglucosan ($r = 0.78-0.97$), a tracer of biomass burning (Deshmukh *et al.* 2019), implying biomass burning as a prime source of MCAs in PM_{2.5} over eastern central India. The positive correlations ($r = 0.53-0.99$) among detected MCAs suggest that they have common sources and formation processes in the atmosphere of eastern central India. The mass ratio of C₁ to C₂ acid in PM_{2.5} samples during the campaign ranged from 0.82-1.4 (avg. 1.1), indicating that both secondary and primary sources are crucial for the formation of MCAs over eastern central India. Benzoic to C₉ acid ratio is on average 0.32 (0.13-0.66), denoting that PM_{2.5} at a forest site in eastern central India experienced more atmospheric processing of unsaturated FAs than aromatic hydrocarbons.

CONCLUSIONS

We measured water-soluble MCAs in PM_{2.5} aerosols to understand their sources and atmospheric behaviour at a forest site in eastern central India. We found formic and acetic acid as the most abundant species in PM_{2.5} samples. Severe biomass burning emissions and photochemical processing of biomass burning-derived organic precursors over the observation site increased the atmospheric burden of water-soluble MCAs in eastern central India and may have an impact on the regional climate. Biomass burning in eastern central India not only determines the high loading of water-soluble OAs but also affects the air quality and climate in the outlay region.

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HYGROSCOPICITY-DRIVEN AEROSOL LIGHT-SCATTERING ENHANCEMENT OVER A TROPICAL COASTAL STATION

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Keywords: Aerosol hygroscopicity, light-scattering enhancement factor, humidified Nephelometer.

INTRODUCTION

The regional and global climate impact of atmospheric aerosols through their direct (scattering and absorption of incoming solar radiation) and indirect (by acting as cloud condensation nuclei and modifying the cloud microstructure and lifetime) are well recognized. The aerosol characteristics of relevance to their climate effects are largely influenced by their water-uptake ability (hygroscopicity) (Rosenfeld *et al.*, 2014). Aerosol hygroscopicity is a key parameter required for understanding alterations to their physical, optical, and chemical properties during their atmospheric lifetime due to aging processes and resulting changes in their mixing state and chemical composition (Alonso-Blanco *et al.*, 2019). Specifically, aerosol scattering properties, critical for aerosol radiative forcing estimations, strongly depend on ambient relative humidity (RH). Alterations to aerosol scattering can be described by the scattering enhancement factor $f(RH)$, which is defined as the aerosol light scattering coefficient at a defined RH (typically 85%) divided by its dry value (RH <40%). Globally, aerosol hygroscopicity-driven light-scattering enhancement is a widely investigated topic (Titos *et al.*, 2016); however, studies quantifying $f(RH)$ are virtually non-existent over the Indian region with diverse aerosol sources and atmospheric conditions. This study presents the results on aerosol light-scattering enhancement based on in situ observations over a coastal site in Southern peninsular India.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The measurements were carried from a tropical coastal, semi-urban location, Thumba (8.5° N, 77° E, 5 m amsl) (Figure 1), on the southwest coast of India. The data covered different synoptic air mass conditions (seasons) during 2019-2021. The observational site is 500 m due east of the Arabian Sea and characterized by highly humid conditions (seasonal mean RH is > 80 % in all the seasons) with significant atmospheric water vapor content. Further synoptic scale features are modulated over this coastal site by mesoscale sea-land breeze circulation, which brings contrasting air masses and aerosol systems within a day.

Figure 1: The measurement site and the experimental setup.

The experimental setup (schematic is shown in the right panel of Figure 1) consists of an aerosol humidity conditioning system and two identical well-calibrated integrating Nephelometer units. The ambient air was aspirated through a PM₁₀ impactor, and this sample flow was split into two branches using an isokinetic flow-splitter and passed through Nafion-based dryer modules for preconditioning the incoming aerosol flow to a desired low RH state (i.e., < 45%). The dry sample was passed through one branch to a Nephelometer (termed as ‘dry Neph.’), while the other sample stream passed through a humidifier module where the sample RH was varied between 60% to typically 85% (in steps of 5% RH and each RH level was maintained for a duration of 10 min) and fed to another Nephelometer (termed as

‘wet Neph.’). The Nephelometers provide aerosol total and backscattering coefficients at three wavelengths with a 1-min temporal resolution. Here we report aerosol light scattering enhancement factor - $f(RH)$ at the wavelength of 550 nm.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The descriptive aerosol hygroscopic growth factors calculated from the observations during different seasons revealed that $f(RH=85\%, 550 \text{ nm})$ values varied from 1.3 to 1.8. Higher $f(RH)$ values (mean ~ 1.55) were seen during the daytime (sea-breeze) compared to the night (mean ~ 1.40) (land-breeze) (Figure 2), highlighting the distinct hygroscopicity of the aerosol system. The measured humidographs of $f(RH)$ were parameterized using an empirical two-parameter fit, and the association between the hygroscopicity parameters and aerosol chemical composition was examined to ascertain the relative contribution of different species. The results highlighted the influence of organic aerosols apart from inorganics on aerosol hygroscopic growth under varying RH regimes. These results have implications for aerosol optical and radiative properties over the regions with significant organic aerosol loading and higher RH conditions.

Figure 2: Typical diurnal pattern of aerosol total scattering coefficient and $f(RH)$ during this study.

CONCLUSION

This study presents the quantitative description of aerosol hygroscopic growth factors and associated parameters and elucidates the role of various chemical species in controlling aerosol hygroscopicity.

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IMPACT OF COATING ON BLACK CARBON ABSORPTION ENHANCEMENT OVER DELHI DURING WINTER

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Keywords: RADIATIVE FORCING; ABSORPTION COEFFICIENT; ANGSTROM EXPONENT

INTRODUCTION

Black carbon (BC) is a well-known climate-forcing agent with direct radiative forcing (DRF) of around $0.71 \pm 0.17 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ (Bond et al., 2013). There are still some uncertainties in estimating BC radiative impacts due to their internal/or external mixing with other chemical species. The coating of other chemical species internally/or externally over BC aerosols may enhance their absorption. Recent studies including field measurements, modelling, and laboratory studies have estimated BC absorption enhancement (E_{abs} ; Zhang et al., 2018). However, there is ambiguity in E_{abs} value, as a few studies have shown no enhancement (for instance, Cappa et al., 2012), and some have shown an enhancement of around 50 % (i.e. $E_{\text{abs}} \sim 1.5$, Liu et al., 2015) to 100 %, specifically at short wavelength range, where the BrC is contributing largely to E_{abs} (for example, Chen et al., 2020). Studies on BC absorption enhancement are still lacking in the literature, especially over the Indian subcontinent. In this context, we estimated the BC absorption enhancement (E_{abs}) over a megacity, Delhi, during winter.

METHODS

The present study is conducted from 1st January to 28th February 2018 in Delhi, located in northern India. During study. Black carbon (BC) was measured in real-time utilizing a multi-channel aethalometer (Magee Scientific Model AE33; Drinovec et al., 2015). In parallel to BC measurements, total 19 PM_{2.5} samples were collected in day/night pair using a high-volume air sampler for off-line carbonaceous aerosols analyses using Sunset OC/EC analyzer (Sunset Laboratory Inc.). The sampling time was 06:30–17:30 IST for day-time sampling and 17:30–06:30 IST for night-time sampling, respectively. Further, BC absorption enhancement (E_{abs}) is derived as per the method reported by Zhang et al. (2018).

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

In the present study, absorption coefficients (b_{abs}) were estimated using AE33 observation at seven wavelengths (370, 450, 571, 615, 660, 880, 950), which showed the highest magnitude (210 Mm^{-1}) at 370nm and it decreased exponentially with increasing wavelengths, i.e., 157, 134, 117, 100, 76 and 71 Mm^{-1} at 470, 520, 590, 660, 880 and 950 nm, respectively. A similar variation in spectral b_{abs} is reported by several studies worldwide. Further b_{abs} is utilized to calculate the Absorption angstrom exponent (AAE), a well-known parameter to visualize the wavelength dependence of the absorption and the sources, as the magnitude of AAE varies for different sources. The period average value of $\text{AAE}_{370-520}$ is higher than unity (1.28 ± 0.12) which indicates a significant presence of BrC over the study region.

BC absorption enhancement (E_{abs}) values are calculated by assessing the ratio between the observed mass absorption cross section (MAC in m^2g^{-1}) to the theoretical uncoated MAC of absorbing aerosol. Here for calculation, AAE for uncoated pure BC (1.08) was used from the reported work (Roy et al., 2023). The E_{abs} estimated from the ratio of coated BC, using Elemental carbon (EC) from offline analysis represented as MAC_{EC} in m^2g^{-1} to uncoated BC calculated from theoretical calculations represented as $\text{MAC}_{\text{uncoatedBC}}$ which was found as 5.82 ± 0.70 at 880 nm wavelength.

Figure 1. Temporal trends of E_{abs880}

The temporal variation of BC absorption enhancement at 880 nm ($E_{abs-880}$) during the study period is shown in Fig. 1. It varied from 0.70 to 5.8 with a period average of 2.76 ± 1.35 ($avg \pm 1\sigma$). The observed value in the present study is in line with the previous studies by Roy et al (2023) $E_{abs-880}$ (3-6) and by Zhang et al (2018) $E_{abs-880}$ (2.07 ± 0.49).

CONCLUSION

Significant absorption enhancement was observed during the study period. Overall, it is likely that coating had a significant impact on the optical properties of aerosols during various pollution periods, in addition to the combined effects of emissions and complex microphysical properties of particles. This encourages research into how chemical species affect secondary formation during various pollution periods as well as the effects of chemical composition on AAE, SAE, MAC, and E_{abs} .

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EVOLUTION OF CHEMICAL SPECIATION IN MIXED MALONIC ACID - UREA AEROSOLS

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Keywords: intermolecular interaction in aerosol, malonic acid-urea interaction, aerosol reactivity.

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols comprise of several classes of organics that originate from natural or anthropogenic sources, or are formed *in-situ* due to various atmospheric processes. Low molecular weight water-soluble dicarboxylic acids in aerosols are products of photochemical oxidation. Malonic acid is one such commonly found dicarboxylic acid in aerosols. Also present in the atmosphere in abundant measure are a wide range of nitrogen-based compounds, such as ammonia, amines, amides etc. Due to several atmospheric processes, *viz.* volatile gas uptake, these two categories of organics co-exist in aerosols, eventually forming a new particle. (Kumar *et. al.*, 2018). Urea is one such nitrogen-rich compound found in the atmosphere, its prevalence is largely due to the widespread use of fertilizers worldwide. The impact on global nitrogen cycle due to ammonia release into the atmosphere through urea hydrolysis is well studied. Being a diamide, urea has distinctly high reactivity towards acids compared to its amine analogue. In this study, the inter-molecular interactions and humidity mediated evolution of chemical identities in mixed MA-urea aerosol have been investigated using *in-situ* micro-Raman spectroscopy.

METHODS

Aqueous solutions of malonic acid (MA, 0.2M), urea (0.2M) and MA-urea mixture (1:1) were prepared using Milli-Q water (18.2 M Ω cm resistivity). Freshly prepared aqueous solutions were sprayed onto a silver substrate and placed immediately into an environment cell maintained at ~85% relative humidity. The desired humidity inside the cell was obtained by controlled mixing of wet and dry nitrogen gas flow. The cell was placed onto a motorized stage of micro-Raman spectrometer. After deposition, the particles were first subjected to dehumidification followed by humidification, at a step of 5%RH. At each RH point, after sufficient equilibration period, *in-situ* Raman spectra were collected from the individual particles.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

RH mediated Raman spectral changes during hygroscopic growth cycle of MA, urea and 1:1 mixed MA-urea aerosol particles are shown in figure 1. The abrupt changes in Raman spectra, coupled with the concurrent acquisition of particle images, provide compelling evidence of aqueous-to-solid (efflorescence) or solid-to-aqueous (deliquescence) phase transitions. During dehumidification, the pure MA and urea showed efflorescence RH (ERH) at 20% and 46%, respectively, while the mixed system dried at 49%RH. Conversely, during humidification, the pure MA and urea showed deliquescence RH (DRH) at 70% and 77%, respectively, while the mixed MA-urea system deliquesced early at 68%RH. Thus, during drying process, the mixed MA-urea behaves like urea whereas in the humidification process it resembles the other component, MA. The contrasting physical behaviours exhibited by the mixed system under varying ambient humidity strongly suggest the presence of intricate solute-solute interactions. This emphasizes the need for detailed Raman spectral analyses to unveil their underlying chemical identities.

In pure state, at 87%RH, MA molecules remain in fully hydrated state as indicated by the appearance of $\nu_s(C=O)$ at 1724cm⁻¹. However, on drying till 24%RH, the 1690 cm⁻¹ band intensifies at

the expense of 1724cm^{-1} . This indicates the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ groups undergo intermolecular H-bonding and formation of MA dimer. MA solidifies at 20%RH; the appearance of 1635 and 1660 cm^{-1} bands corresponding to two different types of intermolecular H-bonded $\text{C}=\text{O}$ groups support this argument. (Saha and Mathi, 2023) During humidification, particularly after deliquescence, the reversal of Raman spectral changes indicates dissociation of MA dimers into hydrated monomers.

Figure 1. Raman spectral changes for MA (A-B), urea (C-D) and 1:1 mixed MA-urea (E-F) aerosols during hygroscopic cycle.

Raman spectra of urea aerosols (figure 1.C, D) show characteristic amide vibrations (I, II) in the range $1500\text{-}1800\text{ cm}^{-1}$. In liquid state, such bands ($1586, 1661\text{ cm}^{-1}$) appear very broad in nature, which become distinctly narrower accompanied with change in peak positions ($1538, 1576, 1620, 1646, 1674\text{ cm}^{-1}$) upon solidification. At the end of the hygroscopic cycle, all the spectral changes are reversed.

The Raman spectra of 1:1 mixed MA-urea aerosols (figure 1.E, F) are different from either of the pure MA or urea aerosol from the very beginning of the hygroscopic cycle. Although the $\nu_s(\text{C}=\text{O})$ band of carboxyl appears at 1724 cm^{-1} but its width (60 cm^{-1}) becomes almost half of the pure MA (120 cm^{-1}). Moreover, unlike MA, with drying, this band blue-shifted to a very narrow and sharp band at 1740 cm^{-1} . These spectral changes not only confirm prevention of MA dimer formation upon drying, but also provide compelling evidence for presence of a distinct environment around MA molecules. The relative intensities of bands in amide regions as well as appearance of new band at 1500 cm^{-1} upon drying also indicates perturbed molecular environment of urea in mixed system. The combined spectral changes in carbonyl group of MA and amide group of urea indicate intermolecular interaction between MA and urea in mixed state. Interestingly, unlike pure aerosols, in mixed system, although little but permanent spectral changes persist after the completion of the hygroscopic cycle.

CONCLUSIONS

In mixed state, MA and urea are involved in intermolecular interactions. The inter-molecular interactions are expected to affect their individual atmospheric reactivity, such as urea hydrolysis, decarboxylation of MA, bulk pH of aerosols, optical properties of particles or new particle formation *etc.*

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OBSERVATION OF PHYSICO-CHEMICAL TRANSFORMATION IN GLUTARIC ACID-METAL NITRATE AEROSOLS

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Keywords: ion-molecular Interactions, solid-solid phase separation

INTRODUCTION

Water soluble organic acids are generated *in-situ* during aerosol photo-oxidation processes. Their interactions with the inorganic constituents significantly alters the physico-chemical behaviour of aerosols. For instance, mixed aerosols comprising of malonic acid and metal nitrates have been reported to undergo metal-organic salt formation/complexation accompanied with release of HNO₃. (Saha and Mathi, 2023)) Glutaric acid (GA), a 5-carbon water soluble dicarboxylic acid (DCA), has also been detected in rain water sample, with concentration ranging between 2-15 µg L⁻¹ which is 10-40 times lower than that of other short chain DCAs. (Sempéré and Kawamura, 1996) Despite its very low concentration, GA, having a higher ratio of hydrophobic-to-hydrophilic groups tends to undergo phase separation and in-turn can act as nucleation seed. It will be interesting to dissect the behaviour of GA in the presence of potentially reactive inorganics. In this work, the humidity mediated aerosol hygroscopic behaviour of GA in presence of nitrates of monovalent (Na⁺) and divalent (Mg²⁺) metal ions has been explored using micro-Raman spectroscopy.

METHODS

Milli-Q water (18.2 MΩ cm resistivity) was used to prepare aqueous solutions of GA, NaNO₃ (SN) and Mg(NO₃)₂ (MN). Stock solutions were used to prepare the mixed 1:1 GA-SN and 1:1 GA-MN solutions. The aqueous solutions were sprayed onto a silver substrate and placed immediately into a humidity controlled environment cell maintained at ~85% relative humidity. Controlled mixing of dry-to-wet nitrogen gas was used to maintain the desired humidity inside the cell. The deposited particles were first subjected to dehumidification followed by humidification and *in-situ* Raman spectra were collected from the individual particles at each RH point after sufficient equilibration period.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

GA-monovalent metal nitrate (SN) system:

Figure 1.(a,b) shows the Raman spectral changes corresponding to the fingerprint region (900-1000 cm⁻¹ and 1500-1800 cm⁻¹) of DCA. At the onset of dehumidification (86%RH), broad bands seen at 1660 and 1715 cm⁻¹ correspond to overtone of $\nu_3(\dot{C})$ and the $\nu_s(C=O)$ band of GA, respectively. With further drying, the $\nu_s(C=O)$ band blue shifted by 8 cm⁻¹. Finally, the mixed aerosol system dried at 36%RH exhibiting solid-solid phase separation as can be seen from the characteristic red shift of the $\nu_s(C=O)$ band to 1646 cm⁻¹ and blue shift of overtone of $\nu_3(\dot{C})$ band to 1666 cm⁻¹. The effect of phase change can be confirmed from the blue shift of characteristic GA skeletal carbon band from 927 to 944 cm⁻¹. No further changes were observed till 4%RH. On humidification, the particle deliquesced at 73%RH; the GA skeletal carbon band as well as the carbonyl band shapes and intensities resemble the starting particle. In other words, the GA- did not exhibit any permanent chemical transformation at the end of the hygroscopic cycle.

Figure 1. Raman spectral changes for 1:1 mixed (a, b) GA-SN and (c, d) GA-MN aerosols during hygroscopic cycle.

GA-divalent metal nitrate (MN) system:

In contrast to organic-monovalent metal system, i.e., GA-SN, the organic-divalent metal system, GA-MN did not exhibit any phase change during the hygroscopic cycle (Figure 1.c,d). Interestingly, the deliquesced particle has a lower ratio of $\nu_s(C=O)$ band of GA to $\nu_3\delta$ overtone band. The spectral signature corresponding to the carbon skeleton of GA, seen as a single band at 930 cm^{-1} splits into a strong band at 937 cm^{-1} and a weak band at 954 cm^{-1} with their relative intensities become comparable at the end of the hygroscopic cycle. The significant change in the carbon skeleton as well as the accompanying changes in the $C=O$ band intensities strongly suggests the prevalence of ion-molecular interactions between GA and the divalent metal Mg^{2+} . This observation is in contrast with the mixed GA-monovalent metal (Na^+) nitrate (GA-SN) system.

CONCLUSIONS

GA has been found to interact with divalent metal ion (Mg^{2+}) present in the mixed aerosol. No such interaction has been observed for mixed GA-monovalent metal ion (Na^+) aerosol. The identity of the metal ions shapes the physico-chemical transformations in aerosols during their hygroscopic cycle.

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VARIATION OF AEROSOL OPTICAL PROPERTIES OVER WESTERN HIMALAYAN REGION (PALAMPUR) USING REMOTE SENSING TECHNIQUES

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Keywords: Aerosol Optical Properties, Raman Lidar, MODIS, Western Himalayan Region.

INTRODUCTION

The effects of atmospheric aerosols on the earth's climate system are significant, still they are not fully known. The greater spatial-temporal variability of aerosols and their complex interactions with the gases in the atmosphere, radiation, and clouds are to account for these uncertainties. We can study the properties of aerosols with the help of ground based and satellite-based observations. Accurate estimation of aerosol climatic effect is extremely difficult due to the highly heterogeneous and area-specific physico-chemical and optical properties of aerosols. Satellite measurements can provide fruitful information about atmospheric constituents over any geolocation especially over the remote places where ground-based observations are not feasible due to the geographical, climatic, and economical challenges. They can also help to validate and corroborate the ground-based measurements. The aim of this work is to investigate the aerosol optical properties such as aerosol optical depth (AOD), angstrom exponent (AE) over Palampur in Western Himalayan region, obtained from ground-based and satellite-based measurements during 2017 to 2022.

METHODS

A Raymetrics Raman Lidar system is installed at the National Physical Laboratory's remote monitoring station at the campus of CSIR-Institute of Himalayan Bioresource Technology (IHBT), Palampur, Himachal Pradesh, India (32.11°N, 76.53°E and 1347m amsl). The technical specifications of the Raman lidar system are given in Table 1. In this study, the Raman Lidar measurements over Palampur from Feb 2017 to Dec 2019 during clear sky days has been used. The Raman channel was operated only during night time (non-cloudy condition) in the observation period due to its low signal strength. The lidar data was processed using the methodologies discussed in (Jaswant et al., 2020; Singh et al., 2022). The AOD measurements obtained by Raman lidar are compared with the satellite-based AOD obtained from level 3 MODIS. AOD data for Palampur was obtained from the MODIS Terra (MOD08_D3 v6.1) satellite as a daily mean gridded average in $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ spatial resolutions and is downloaded from <https://giovanni.gsfc.nasa.gov/giovanni/>.

Specifications of Raman Lidar	
Pulsed Laser Source	Nd:YAG (Quantel ULTRA100 Series)
Wavelength	355 nm
Energy / Pulse	32.8 mJ
Repetition Rate	20 Hz
Laser Beam Divergence	<0.8 mrad
Telescope Type	Cassegrain
Primary Diameter	200 mm
Secondary Diameter	48 mm
Transmitter–Receiver Distance	212 mm
Field of View	2.3 mrad (adjustable from 0.5 to 3mrad)
Detectors	3 PMTs

Table 1. Specifications of Raman Lidar System

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The Raman lidar measurements taken during 2017 to 2019 and MODIS observations during 2017 to 2022 have been used for the study. The monthly variation of lidar derived AOD and MODIS AOD is shown in the figure 1. As it can be seen that lidar derived AOD and MODIS AOD are following the similar trend throughout the observation period. We observed the correlation coefficient (0.76) between

Lidar AOD and MODIS AOD. The monthly variation of aerosol optical properties and angstrom exponent are shown in figure 2. The climatological annual mean AOD is 0.19 ± 0.18 and ranges from 0.02 to 0.97 which indicates that the region's atmospheric condition varies between clean and moderately polluted condition.

Figure 1. Variation of aerosol optical depth from Raman Lidar and MODIS during 2017 to 2019

Figure 2 (a-b). Monthly variation of aerosol optical depth and angstrom exponent during 2017-22 from MODIS

CONCLUSIONS

This study elucidates about the aerosol properties (aerosol optical depth, angstrom exponent) derived from MODIS and Raman lidar. The results suggest that aerosol optical depth shows the order as Monsoon> Summer>Winter>Post-monsoon in MODIS. The dominance of coarse mode particles during summer and monsoon while fine mode particles during post-monsoon and winter is also observed.

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CHARACTERISTICS OF NEW PARTICLE FORMATION EVENTS AT A RURAL LOCATION,
 MAHABUBNAGAR, IN INDIA

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Keywords: NEW PARTICLE FORMATION EVENT, SHORT-LIVED NPF EVENT, FORMATION RATE, GROWTH RATE, RURAL

INTRODUCTION

It is a well-known fact that atmospheric aerosols influence the climate directly and indirectly. The largest source of aerosol numbers in the terrestrial atmosphere is new particle formation (NPF), which is a non-linear and dynamic process that occurs ubiquitously in the Earth’s atmosphere (Kulmala et al., 2012). While NPF can have a natural origin (biogenic), human activities, including the release of pollutants and aerosols, can also influence the NPF processes. Therefore, it is crucial to study the characteristics of NPF in diverse geographical environments. Further, atmospheric NPF, its characteristics, the chemistry driving NPF, and its impacts on air quality have been largely unexplored in the Indian context. With this motivation, this study aims to study the characteristics of NPF at a rural location, Mahabubnagar, in India (Varghese et al. 2016).

METHODS

In this study, we have used particle number size distribution data from the Cloud Aerosol Interaction and Precipitation Enhancement Experiment (CAIPEX) campaign (Kulkarni et al., 2012; Prabha et al., 2011), ranging from 5 nm to 34 µm measured by the Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS). Ambient measurements were taken from 1st September to 28th October of 2011 at Mahabubnagar (16.699°N, 77.94°E; ~460 m above mean sea level), which is a rural location in the South Indian state of Andhra Pradesh. The observation day was classified into NPF event, short-lived NPF event, non-event, and undefined event by visually inspecting the contour plot of particle number size distribution following the methodology given by Dal Maso et al. (2005), with further modifications. We have also used tropospheric nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) data with a resolution of 0.25° × 0.25° retrieved from the Ozone Monitoring Instrument (OMI) on board the Aura satellite to infer the nature of the location and major anthropogenic emission sources in the vicinity of the site.

Fig. 1. Time-evolution of meteorological and aerosol properties for a typical NPF event on the left (October 24, 2011), and a typical non-event on the right (October 25, 2011). Starting from the top, air temperature (T), relative humidity (RH), wind speed (WS), wind direction (WD), contour plot of particle number size distribution (dN/dlogDp), particle number concentrations in the particle diameter range of 5 to 25 nm (NNUC) and 5 to 1000 nm (NTOT), total condensation sink (CSTOT) and coagulation sink (CoagSTOT).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Out of a total of 53 valid observation days, NPF events occurred on 8 days (15.1%), short-lived NPF events on 4 days (7.5%), and non-events on 22 days (41.5%). The observation days which we could not classify into any of the above classes were referred to as undefined event days (19 days, 35.8%). An

NPF event displays a burst of nucleation mode particles (particles of diameter less than 25 nm), and this distinct new mode of particles steadily grows for at least 6 hours such that the particle number size distributions display a “banana-shaped” aerosol growth, as shown in the figure. A short-lived event displays a burst of nucleation mode particles, but this new mode did not show banana-shaped aerosol growth. Overall, NPF events occurred infrequently in Mahabubnagar. We further examined various NPF characteristics (formation and growth rate, condensation sink, influence of meteorological parameters) for the observed types of event days (NPF, short-lived NPF, and non-events).

CONCLUSIONS

The following are the major conclusions drawn from this study.

Mahabubnagar, a rural location in India, showed a sporadic occurrence of NPF, unlike rural locations in Europe and the USA. It seemed to us that the unavailability of precursor vapors and cloudy conditions during monsoon (therefore less photochemically active atmosphere) leads to the suppression of NPF events in Mahabubnagar.

The derived formation and growth rates in Mahabubnagar were well within the observed ranges across the globe.

These results highlight that NPF has site and season-specific characteristics and patterns, and therefore, it warrants long-term continuous measurements of particle number size distributions in diverse geographical locations in India to deduce the intricate relationship between human activities, atmospheric processes, and the environment, so that NPF can be addressed in the context of the changing climate.

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**SEISMIC REINFORCING OF PHTHALATES AND BENZO (A) PYRENE ON WOMEN
HEALTH: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS IN INDOOR AND OUTDOOR AIR OF LUCKNOW**
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Keywords: INDOOR, OUTDOOR AIR POLLUTANTS, PM_{2.5}, PHTHALATES, PYRENE

INTRODUCTION

Particulate matter (PM), especially PM_{2.5}, poses a serious risk to human health and is still a major global public health issue. Phthalates (phthalates esters, PAEs) have been used as plasticizing agent in polymer such as polyvinyl chloride (PVC) and consumer products (as in personal care products, food packaging, varnishes, and coatings) [1]. As the PAEs are not chemically linked to the products, their use can slowly release PAEs into the environment (air, water and soil). Through ingestion, inhalation, and cutaneous channels, humans are exposed to PAEs. PAEs have been found to be endocrine disruptors, causing endocrine disruption and reproductive toxicity, they are toxic to humans [2]. Numerous epidemiological studies have shown a strong link between PAE exposure and reproductive disorders, obesity, diabetes, respiratory diseases, coronary heart disease, liver toxicity, endometriosis, ovarian dysfunction. Di (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate, one of the most common phthalate plasticizers, has been categorised as a suspected carcinogen (1B) by the European Union as well as a possible human carcinogen (Group B2) by the US EPA. As a result, the widespread usage of PAEs has a negative impact on public health. Recent studies have looked into PAEs in the environment, including in the air, dust, soil, food, water, skin surface, and personal care items [3].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

SITE SELECTION

The study was conducted in summer season in capital city of the most polluted state of India i.e., Lucknow, which has been recently listed in the top 50 most polluted cities of the world.

QUESTIONNAIRE SURVEY

A questionnaire study was done to learn more about the state of indoor air pollution and its effects on health, particularly in women because women spending more than 90% of their time in indoor chores are at an elevated risk of deadly chemicals. In the present study, in the questionnaire the location of the home, the number of rooms, the timing and frequency of respiratory symptoms, as well as indoor and outdoor characteristics, were all questioned. Women's eating habits and routines were also taken into consideration because they may affect respiratory function either directly or indirectly. The selection of the households for monitoring was done based on the responses. On the basis of the questionnaire survey, six locations were selected in Lucknow for monitoring.

SAMPLING OF PM_{2.5}

Filter-based PM_{2.5} samples from each sampling site were collected with APM 557 (dry gas sampler) on a PTFE filter which are Whatman make, pore 2 μ m, diameter 46.2mm with a flow rate of 16.67l/m. All samplers were operated at a flow rate of 16.17l/m and for 24 hrs. The PTFE filters were pre-heated at 500 C for 4 hours before sampling to eliminate any volatile elements. Each loaded filter was kept in a refrigerator below 0⁰ C after sampling in preparation for gravimetric and chemical examination.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

On the basis of survey consequence six households were selected for both outdoor and indoor monitoring of PM_{2.5}, derivatives of phthalates (PAEs), pyrene (BaP) associated with PM_{2.5}, Using organic compounds (derivatives of phthalates and pyrene), DEP was the highest reported concentration in PM_{2.5} collected in May 2023 (554 - 4139 ng/m³ of particles with mean and max value of 1.93 and 6.50). Among Pyrenes, B(a)P had remarkably higher concentration in indoors indicating towards major indoor sources which were further studied via. Principal Component Analysis. The results obtained were high as compared to the USEPA standard prescribed for ILCR, however, women were evaluated to be most vulnerable among all. The findings of this research will be the initial step towards giving better insight

into the air quality in a variety of small-scale environments. This would help us better understand the negative effects of sub-micron particles and provide new parameters for potential restrictions. In the Table (1) the comparison of indoor and outdoor the concentration of derivatives of Phthalates and pyrene associated with PM_{2.5} are given below-

Table-1 Concentrations of Phthalates and Pyrene associated with PM_{2.5}

Households	Indoor Concentration PM _{2.5}	Outdoor Concentration PM _{2.5}	DMP		DEP		BbP		DEHP		B(a)P	
			Indoor	Outdoor								
House1	95.8333	116.6667	1.8	2.3	6.5	7.1	2.5	7.9	6.9	11.4	0.1	0.1
House2	76.25	100	1.2	3.5	11.9	12.5	4.5	7.4	2.1	9.1	0.1	0.1
House3	87.5	104.167	1.5	5.1	12.9	13.7	0.4	2.9	2.4	9.6	10.2	0.1
House4	104.1667	129.1667	3.5	9.4	11.8	13.7	6.9	7.5	9.3	11.7	0.1	0.1
House5	62.5	87.5	1.3	4.7	4.6	5.4	0.2	2.1	1.4	3.1	0.1	0.1
House6	91.66667	104.1667	2.1	6.0	7.1	10.2	1.7	12.5	2.3	6.2	0.1	0.1

CONCLUSION

Conclusively, the study is first of its kind in India give an all around figurative assessment of noxious organic pollutant specially in indoor environment, which have been prominently overlooked by the governing authorities round the globe. The study gives a clear view of source and possible health risk associated with the major indoor pollutants and aim to assist the professional in the field for better mounting of guidelines in future.

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INVESTIGATIONS ON LEVITATION, PATTERN FORMATION, INSTABILITIES AND BREAKUP OF CHARGED DROPLETS

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Keywords: Electrohydrodynamics, levitation, charged drops, Rayleigh instability, nanoparticle generation.

INTRODUCTION

Electrosprays are increasingly used in applications such as nanoparticle generation and air cleaning, apart from more commonly known applications of mass spectrometry, spray painting, and particle deposition amongst others. This has brought back into focus, several not-so-well-understood aspects of the dynamics of charged drops, generated by electrosprays, that are relevant in technological advancement. These include the mechanism of generation of charged droplets, and the estimates of mass and charge on progenies generated by fission of charged droplets. An important question of interest in the aerosol context is the generation of nanometer sized droplets, recorded by SMPS positioned downstream, when micron sized droplets are ejected from an electrospray. This understanding is critical in electrospray based air cleaning technologies. In this context, in this presentation we discuss a myriad of phenomenon exhibited by charged droplets: Levitation, Coulombic crystals, Shape and positional oscillations of the charged droplets when suspended in quadrupolar potentials, and their coupling leading to a atleast two different modes of Rayleigh break.

METHODS

The numerical calculations were conducted using an in-house Boundary integral method in the group, with features of analysis in both, the viscous and inviscid limits. The code has provision to correctly incorporate the charge balance and its accurate conservation at the interface. The experiments were carried out in an in-house quadrupole trap, designed to levitate charged droplets, and investigate pattern formation, shape and center of mass oscillations, and breakup using high-speed imaging.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1. Droplet levitation and pattern formation, center of mass oscillations and breakup of a charged droplet levitated in a quadrupole trap

A charged droplet when placed in a quadrupolar potential, given in the simplest form as $\phi = \Lambda \frac{(z^2 - r^2)}{2}$ is levitated and the dynamics is governed by the Mathieu equation. This is really due to a restoring force that acts on the droplet towards the center of mass, due to the correlation of the oscillatory position of the droplet with the oscillatory applied field. When multiple droplets are levitated, there is a competition between the restoring force of the trap and the coulombic repulsive interaction between the levitated droplets. Our study, both experimental and numerical indicates the admittance of degenerate states in the multidroplet systems.

A droplet levitated in a quadrupolar trap without a DC feedback, is a “loose trap” that leads to not just shape oscillations, but an off-center levitation of the droplet within the trap, which admits low amplitude center of mass motion. We recently showed that this coupling leads to a nontrivial upward breakup of droplets if levitated in “loose traps”.

The droplet eventually undergoes breakup. Numerically, the charge on the droplet progenies can be obtained by both perfect conductor and finite conductivity analysis. Our simple study indicates that there at least two modes of breakup, which are determined by the conductivity of the droplet phase. While low conductivity leads to tip streaming type of breakup, much higher conductivity leads to jet detachment. Both these observations were shown separately in experiments as well as numerical calculations.

CONCLUSIONS

Charged droplets can be levitated using a very ordinary quadrupole trap without the more complex mechanism of DC feed back control, resulting in “loose” levitation of charged droplets that show center of mass motion and pattern formation of Coulombic crystals. The charged droplets undergo fission when the critical Rayleigh charge is realised. The results indicate that the complex physics of multiple breakup of charged droplets due to Rayleigh fission, can be systematically investigated using a combination of experimental and theoretical techniques. The charge and mass of the progenies formed in the Rayleigh breakup are shown to be critically dependent on the electric field distribution, but more importantly on the conductivity of the droplet solution. This has direct implications in the particle-charged droplets and has relevance in wet electrostatic scrubbers and electrospray based air cleaners.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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CHARACTERISTICS OF NEW PARTICLE FORMATION EVENTS OVER HIGH ALTITUDE
LOCATION IN INDIA

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Atmospheric new particle formation (NPF, via gas-to-particle conversion) occurs commonly in the troposphere which has implications for air quality, weather, and climate. Here, we comprehensively characterize NPF events at High Altitude Cloud Physics Laboratory (HACPL) in a mountain semi-rural location, Mahabaleshwar using 2.5 years of semi-continuous measurements of ion and particle number size distributions. The occurrence frequency of NPF events was the highest in March through May (pre-monsoon season) (22.9%) compared to other seasons. Considering all seasons at HACPL, the particle growth rates in the size range from 1 – 3 nm, 3 – 7 nm, 7 – 25 nm, and 5 – 25 nm varied from 0.7 to 5.8 nm h⁻¹, 0.5 to 6.9 nm h⁻¹, 1.3 to 10.2 nm h⁻¹, and 1.5 to 16.4 nm h⁻¹, respectively. The formation rate of charged clusters (J_3^{+ii} and J_3^{-ii}) are reported for the first time from India, which were at least three orders of magnitude higher at HACPL (3.1 – 294.4 cm⁻³ s⁻¹) than in many locations in Europe (0.07 – 0.16 cm⁻³ s⁻¹). The general absence of a positive correlation between the particle formation rate and the growth rate indicates that dissimilar vapors might have contributed to the formation and growth of particles. Further, the role of ions in particle formation was also reported for the first time in India, which indicates an insignificant contribution of ions to particle formation at HACPL. The formation rates of neutral/charged particles are the highest at higher temperatures and lower relative humidity conditions. Overall, our results provide new insights into NPF event characterization in the Indian context which have critical importance to an improved process-level understanding of secondary aerosol formation processes globally.

Keywords: Neutral and charged clusters, new particle formation, particle formation rate, growth rate

**A NEW APPROACH FOR UNRAVELLING THE ORGANIC SIGNATURE OF ATMOSPHERIC
AEROSOL PARTICLES: COUPLING THERMAL-OPTICAL CARBON ANALYSIS TO LASER
PHOTO-IONIZATION MASS SPECTROMETRY**

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Keywords: Ambient particulate matter, Photo Ionization Mass Spectrometry (PIMS), Elemental Carbon/Organic Carbon (EC/OC), Thermal Optical Carbon Analysis (TOCA), Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAH)

INTRODUCTION

Carbonaceous material in airborne particulate matter (PM) is often characterized by sum parameters (organic and elemental carbon, OC and EC). Thermal-optical carbon analysis (TOCA) is one important approach in atmospheric research and monitoring and environmental health research in this context. In hundreds of air quality monitoring station worldwide routinely PM is sampled on quartz fiber filters. From those filters different OC-fractions can be analyzed in the TOCA process by stepwise heating of a small punch of the PM-loaded quartz filter sample and analysis of the released carbon after catalytic oxidation by IR analysis of CO₂. Elemental carbon (EC) can be analyzed likewise. The yield of information from TOCA can be extended by evolved gas analysis (EGA) techniques, such as photo-ionization mass spectrometry (PIMS, Grabowsky et al., 2011; Diab et al., 2015, Miersch et al. 2019a/b). For example, health-relevant polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) are detectable by resonance-enhanced multiphoton ionization (REMPI) Time-of-Flight mass spectrometry simultaneously to OC and EC by guiding a fraction of the evolved gases before catalytic conversion to the MS.

METHODS

A concept of an improved TOCA-based instrument for analyzing filter samples is presented. The quasi-simultaneous EI and REMPI detection by high-resolution TOFMS, enabling detection of PAH and the oxidation state of organic PM similar to the high-resolution AMS approach, is described.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

A quadrupole mass spectrometry (qMS) approach with electron ionization (EI) was previously introduced by Riggio et al. (2018) to provide quantitative results on organic matter, nitrate, and sulfate, aiming to transfer fragmentation tables from online aerosol mass spectrometry (AMS, Canagaratna et al., 2007) to offline filter analysis. However, no information on carbon oxidation state can be derived because the qMS cannot provide sufficient mass resolution to distinguish between key isobaric ions, such as C₃H₇⁺ and C₂H₃O⁺ at m/z 43. In this work EGA was done via on-line sampling from a modified TOCA quartz oven. Ions were generated alternating by EI and REMPI (KrF laser with 248 nm pulses). Detection of the ions was performed by a reflectron-TOFMS with a mass resolution of ~2,800 at m/z 43. The benefits of this instrument are demonstrated. For example, for fresh and aged spruce combustion

emissions, a decrease in hydrocarbon-like fragments (e.g., $C_3H_7^+$) can be observed, whereas ions of oxygenates (e.g. $C_2H_3O^+$ and CO_2^+) are noticeably increased by atmospheric ageing. The high mass resolution thus allows separation of many hydrocarbon- and oxygenate-isobars. Simultaneously, the selective REMPI detection of PAH addresses the very important substance class of the PAH and thus allow an indirect estimation of the carcinogenicity of the organic PM fraction (Miersch *et al.*, 2019b).

CONCLUSIONS

The organic signature of atmospheric aerosol particles can be analyzed by a new approach by coupling thermal-optical carbon analysis to laser photon-ionization mass spectrometry. Using a high resolution mass spectrometer allows the separation of many hydrocarbon- and oxygenate-isobars. With the selective REMPI ionization of the PAH also an estimation of the carcinogenicity of the organic PM fraction is possible.

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OBSERVATION OF NEW PARTICLE FORMATION EVENTS OVER HIGH-ALTITUDE SITE IN WESTERN GHATS, INDIA

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Keywords: New particle formation, growth rate, CCN, Aerosol

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric new particle formation (NPF, via molecular clusters formation and their subsequent growth to larger sizes) occurs frequently in diverse environments, from remote polar to urban locations, around the world (Kanawade et al., 2022; Kerminen et al., 2018;). NPF event can take place over a spatial scale of hundreds of kilometers and a temporal scale of 1-2 days and is only observed when specific atmospheric conditions are met (Kulmala et al., 2014). Previous studies based on observations and modeling approaches suggest that NPF events produce about half of the present-day cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) (Pierce and Adams, 2007) and thereby affecting cloud processes and radiative forcing. But, the fraction of newly formed particles that contribute to CCN formation remains poorly examined in diverse locations across the globe.

METHODS

An NPF event is generally identified by the visual inspection of the shape characteristic of particle number size distributions and characteristic properties such as formation rate and growth rate of particles (Dal Maso et al., 2005). Here, we classified events into three different types: NPF, non-events, and undefined (Table 1). The time evolution of particle number size distribution shows the temporal change in concentrations throughout the observations time period.

Table 1. Classification of different events considered in this study.

NPF	An abrupt increase in sub-3 nm ions and nucleation mode particles (sub-25 nm) with evidence of steady growth in the ion and particle size, thus appearing as conventional banana-shaped ion and aerosol growth. Ion and particle mode diameter is less than 3 nm and 25 nm, respectively, so that the growth rate and formation rate of ions and particles can be calculated.
Non-event	No increase in sub-3nm ions and nucleation mode particles (sub-25nm) and ion and particle mode diameter (absence of growth) during the day
Undefined	All the remaining valid observation days which doesn't satisfy either of the above two criteria,

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Overall, out of 540 valid observation days, NPF events occurred on 79 days (14.6%) and non-events were observed on 353 days (65.4%) at HACPL. A total of 108 undefined days (20%) were categorized as the days which could not be classified as NPF event or non-events days due to mixed features such as broken banana-shaped aerosol growth, ion/particle bursts without evidence for growth (volcano/apple), or Aitken mode growth or tail events (Kanawade et al., 2014). A recent study in India showed that more than half of events days with particle bursts (volcano/apple) in the sub-3nm size range did not show banana-shaped aerosol size growth during summer (March through May) (Sebastian et al., 2021). The frequency of occurrence of NPF events was the highest in MAM months (22.9%), mainly due to the high solar radiation (typically higher oxidation extent of the atmosphere enhancing the production of low volatile organic compounds responsible for particle growth) and relatively low pollution loading close to the surface (owing to dilution effect from elevated boundary layer resulting lower condensation sink for condensable vapors).

CONCLUSIONS

Here, we comprehensively characterized the atmospheric new particle formation at the HACPL site in Mahabaleshwar to provide new insights into the frequency of occurrence of NPF events, the formation and growth rates of charged and neutral clusters and particles, the role of ions in particle formation, and meteorological influence on NPF events.

At HACPL in Mahabaleshwar, the frequency of occurrence of NPF events was the highest in MAM months (22.9%) and the lowest in DJF months (16.9%), which is analogous to previous studies in India and globally except in a few locations wherein NPF event frequently occurred in DJF months.

Figure 1. Time evolution of averaged particle number size distributions in the size range from 5 to 680 nm from WRAS (top panel) and 1 – 47 nm from NAIS (bottom panel) for observed (a) NPF events (79 days).

On average, about 20% of days were categorized as undefined event days showing irregularities in particle number size distributions possibly associated with the abrupt mixing of different air masses or the rapid change in meteorological conditions.

We then quantified the strength of the observed NPF event days by calculating the formation and growth rates of clusters and particles. The median growth rates of particles in the size range of 1-3 nm, 3-7 nm, 7-25 nm, and 5-25 nm when averaged over all seasons were 2.2, 2.9, 4.6, and 4.5 nm h⁻¹, respectively. The size-segregated growth rates of particles were the highest during MAM months as compared with ON and DJF months, replicating the observed seasonal variation in the NPF event frequency.

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**PHOTOCATALYTIC INACTIVATION OF AEROSOLIZED MYCOBACTERIUM
SMEGMATIS IN A CONTINUOUS FLOW REACTOR**

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Keywords: Bioaerosol disinfection, Electrostatic precipitator, Photocatalysis, *Mycobacterium smegmatis*.

INTRODUCTION

Recently, indoor air quality is considered with utmost priority, since the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) has impacted in most countries around the world. Millions of positives cases have been reported, resulting in hundreds of thousands of deaths. Many studies have shown the association between indoor bioaerosols and health problems associated with it such as, sick building syndromes, infectious diseases, respiratory problems, airborne transmission of tuberculosis, asthma, etc. (Lu et al., 2021; Zacarías et al., 2020; Zacarías et al., 2021). Due to poor maintenance in many cases, excessive dirt may be collected in heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC) systems and serve as a breeding ground for the microorganisms. Therefore, development of air purification systems effective for disinfecting airborne microorganisms is attracting worldwide attention. There is need for developing cost effective disinfection technology for inactivation of bioaerosols. In this work, a continuous-flow reactor for photolytic and photocatalytic inactivation of aerosolized bacterium *Mycobacterium smegmatis* is demonstrated and the inactivation performance is evaluated. In addition, Electrostatic precipitator (ESP) was designed and installed in the reactor setup to check the capturing performance of the bioaerosols.

METHODS

In this study, a continuous flow reactor was used to evaluate both photolytic and photocatalytic (TiO₂-mediated) inactivation of an aerosolized Gram-positive bacterium, *Mycobacterium smegmatis*. UV-A light was used with intensity (0.05-0.25 J/cm²) and photocatalyst loading (950 to 1500 mg/m²) at a flow rate of 1LPM. The bacteria were collected on filter fixed on single cascade impactor and plated on nutrient agar plate. In addition, ESP was installed for evaluating the capture efficiency. To generate a continuous flow of bacterial aerosols, purified air was blown through bioaerosol nebulizing generator. Flows of bioaerosols and fresh air were adjusted using mass flow controller. The bacteria were collected onto eosin methylene blue (EMB) agar plates using a single stage cascade impactor having filter paper. The reactor was sealed with aluminium foils and black papers to minimize influence of external light sources as well as for restricting the light from coming out of the reactor. All sampling plates were carefully sealed and placed in an incubator at 37°C. Bacteria colonies were counted after 48hr of incubation for four consecutive days to examine potential regrowth of the colonies.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

From the preliminary studies, the results can be summarized as follows :

a) The inactivation rate of *M. Smegmatis* increased with an increase in TiO₂ loading and UV-intensity. A UV-A dose of 0.05-0.25 J/cm² at a residence time of 15 min, is sufficient to inactivate *M. Smegmatis*.

- b) Disinfection study using plate counting method revealed that maximum disinfection is achieved in a photocatalytic process (94.12%) as compared to photolytic process (58.82%) because of the oxidising nature of ROS (i.e., $\text{OH}\cdot$, $\text{OOH}\cdot$, $\text{O}_2\cdot^-$) generated in the photocatalytic processes.
- c) From the preliminary studies, it was found that the designed ESP with respect to the number concentration showed capture efficiency of 95.47%, 97.99% and 98.12% of particles for voltages 6 kV, 8 kV, and 10 kV respectively.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of experimental setup

Figure 2. Comparison between bacterial disinfection efficiency under photolytic and photocatalytic processes

CONCLUSIONS

This study indicates the higher potential of photocatalytic disinfection over photolysis alone and the integration of ESP for the capture of disinfected bacterium *Mycobacterium smegmatis* with an average size of $4.0\ \mu\text{m}$. Thus, the study reveals the possibility of scaling up of the photocatalytic inactivation process for bioaerosol disinfection and capture. A translation of this technology is proposed based on the promising initial results and most importantly it can provide safe environment by disinfecting in various occupational settings.

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AEROSOL INSTRUMENTATION AND MEASUREMENT TECHNIQUES

**A NOVEL ON-LINE SINGLE PARTICLE MASS SPECTROMETER: RAPID SIMULTANEOUS
DETECTION OF HEALTH-RELEVANT POLYCYCLIC AROMATIC HYDROCARBONS (PAH),
SOOT AND METALS FROM INDIVIDUAL AIRBORNE AEROSOL PARTICLES**

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Keywords: AEROSOL PARTICLES, SINGLE PARTICLE MASS SPECTROMETRY (SPMS), LASER
DESORPTION/IONIZATION (LDI), LASER DESORPTION-PHOTO IONIZATION, MULTIPLEXED
IONIZATION, POLYCYCLIC AROMATIC HYDROCARBONS (PAH)

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution by inhalable fine dust represents the most severe environmental health-risk worldwide. The chemical composition of the dust particles is highly relevant for the PM-toxicity. In particular, the content of toxic compounds/fractions such as soot, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) or redox-active transition metals (e.g., Fe or Cu) is of concern. A detailed analysis of the PM composition can be performed by chemical analysis of filter samples, giving integral values on the pollutant mass concentrations. However, no information on the mixing state of toxicants, i.e., the distribution of toxicants in the particle ensemble can be obtained. The mixing state, however, is one crucial parameter to assess health effects: the toxicants may either be equally distributed over many particles (internally mixed) or could be highly concentrated within a specific, small sub-population (externally mixed). In the latter case, the few particles with a very high concentration of toxicants can induce stronger cellular effects at the lung-deposition site due to overwhelming defence mechanisms locally at individual lung-cells/macrophages or due to DAMP signalling, if necrotic cell death is induced. Consequently, novel on-line analysis techniques which can address the mixing state of health relevant PM-chemicals on a single-particle level are required.

METHODS

A new approach for on-line single dust particle analysis bases on bipolar laser mass spectrometry (i.e. the “classical” single particle mass spectrometer approach, SPMS) but with novel, tailored laser ionisation processes. The aerosol is directly on-line sampled from the air via an aerodynamic lens. The airborne dust particles are size-characterized by laser velocimetry in the instrument and the organic coating of individual particles is desorbed by intense IR-laser pulses on the fly. Subsequently the relevant toxicants (transition metals, PAH and soot) are ionized particle-by-particle using a novel combined UV-laser ionization scheme and are detected in the bipolar single particle mass spectrometer (Schade et al., 2019).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The novel SPMS dust particle characterisation system is offering the characterisation of the most relevant dust particle-borne toxicants on a sized-resolved, single particle basis.

Thus in addition classifying sources and quantifying main aerosol compound it gives insight into the mixing state of the relevant air toxicants (PAH/metals/soot) and other compounds (nitrate, sulfate etc.). First results for PAH, e.g., show that, depending on the conditions, PAH may either concentrate on a very small fraction

of the particles or may rather uniformly distributed over all dust particles. Future application concepts in air monitoring and research are discussed (Passig et al. ACP 22, 2022). Furthermore, the system enables a new approach in source apportionment of the detected by using ab Fe atomic transition to enhance the detectability of iron and other transition metals in dust particles. The PAH and metal fingerprinting capability of the approach was applied for the detection of e.g. ship emission plumes over larger distances and determine the fuel type used by the vessel (Heavy Fuel Oil or Marine Gas Oil). The new SPMS system was also applied on board of a reserch vessel in order to check the emissions of individual ships at sea. This demonstrates the selectivity of the approach.

CONCLUSIONS

A novel single particle mass spectrometer allows to on-line analyse the composition of aerosol particles in real-time. In particular, toxic substances such ae elemental carbon (EC, soot) transition metals and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) can be addressed. A particular important capability is the determinability of the mixing state (internal vs. external mixture) for these pollutants. This is very important for accessing the cause of the adverse health effects of ambient aerosols.

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EVOLUTION OF PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF PLASMA TORCH GENERATED AEROSOLS IN A CLOSED CHAMBER

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Keywords: Number size distribution, ELPI

INTRODUCTION

In the case of severe nuclear accidents, a huge amount of aerosols is expected to be released in the environment. Several studies have been performed in recent past on reactor containment system in order to simulate various aerosol processes. Effect of turbulence in context of aerosol codes has been studied by Sapra et al. 2008. In a study by Slama et al. (2014), coagulation and deposition was simulated using models. Effect of humidity in context of severe accident condition was studied by Mishra et al. (2019). In order to characterize depositional effects of aerosols in nuclear accident condition, size characteristics needs to be known. This study is aimed to study evolution of aerosols during accidental releases.

METHODS

Experiments were performed in a test facility of Plasma torch aerosol generator (PTAG). PTAG system consists of a plasma based aerosol generator, a plenum chamber and a 10m³ mixing chamber. Detailed description of the facility is provided in a study by Sapra et al., (2008). Aerosols of Zinc metal powder were generated. Number concentration measurements were performed using Electrical Low Pressure Impactor (ELPI). ELPI can be used for charge measurements also. Number concentration is obtained by keeping the charger continuously ON. Mass concentration measurements were performed using gross filter paper samples throughout the experiment. Homogeneous aerosols were sampled through 10m³ mixing chamber.

Figure 1. Experimental setup

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Plasma torch generated aerosols of zinc metal powder were continuously sampled by Electrical low pressure impactor. Figure 2 below shows, variation of total concentration with time, in Torch On condition and Torch off condition. Total number concentration reached maximum 1.75E6 No./cc in Torch off condition. It can be observed that mean size of Zinc particles increased upto 700nm which could be attributed to coagulation of particles inside the chamber. Geometric mean size got saturated at ~170nm after 6 minutes of Torch On. The

geometric mean observed at maximum number concentration was ~200nm, which got increased by almost 70% due to coagulation of aerosols inside the chamber.

(a) (b)
 Figure 2. Variation of total concentration and geometric mean with time
 (a) Torch On condition, (b) Torch Off condition

As can be seen from Figure 3, the mode of the particle size distribution got shifted from 129 nm to 734 nm. After 32 mins of Torch off condition, still mode of particle size distribution was observed to be the same as in Torch On condition i.e. 129nm.

Figure 3. Evolution of particle size distribution

Results obtained from mass concentration measurements depicted that during Torch On condition, mass concentration was initially ~12-16mg/m³ which increased to 29mg/m³. The airborne particle concentration was observed to be in the range of 26mg/m³ even after 60mins of Torch off.

CONCLUSIONS

Aerosol processes play vital roles in governing the dynamics of aerosols. Coagulation of particles is critical phenomena which leads to change in the properties of aerosols.

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COMPARISON OF PM_{2.5} GROUND-BASED MEASUREMENT AND NASA'S MERRA-2 REANALYSIS CONCENTRATION OF PM_{2.5} OVER INDIA

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Keywords: Aerosol instrumentation and measurement, MERRA-2, Ground-measurement, PM_{2.5}.

INTRODUCTION

The concentration of PM_{2.5} (particulate matter with a diameter $\leq 2.5 \mu\text{m}$), an important component of air pollution, plays a crucial role in the evaluation of the overall air quality. However, the scarce PM_{2.5} surface measurement and absence of monitoring with adequate spatial resolution delimits the studies related to air quality. The objective of the present study is to evaluate Modern-Era Retrospective Analysis for Research and Applications, Version 2 (MERRA-2) reanalysis fine PM concentration data against surface measurements to understand their strengths and weaknesses, with the help of several performance statistics (correlation coefficient, mean bias, standard deviation of bias) which were applied on seasonal and monthly temporal scales.

METHODS

The present work is related to aerosol instrumentation and measurement techniques as they appear on the classification form. In this study, we compared PM_{2.5} concentration by two measurement techniques- NASA's MERRA-2 reanalysis data and ground-based measurements across India between 2015-2019 cited from published literature at 27 sampling locations. It is important to note that MERRA-2 PM_{2.5} values at specific latitude and longitude coordinates were selected, corresponding to the coordinates of ground monitoring stations, in order to get spatially accurate data. Since ground PM_{2.5} sampling durations varied in different studies, only those ground stations/cities are selected for which at least one month of continuous data is available, for better comparison with satellite data. The total mass concentration of PM_{2.5} retrieved from satellite data can be evaluated applying mass reconstruction method as shown in the equation below (Chow et al., 2015):

$$(\text{MERRA-2 PM}_{2.5}) = \text{DU}_{2.5} + \text{BC} + \text{SS}_{2.5} + (\text{OC} \times 1.6) + (\text{SO}_4 \times 1.375) \quad (1)$$

where, $\text{DU}_{2.5}$, BC, $\text{SS}_{2.5}$, OC and SO_4 stand for dust (size $\leq 2.5 \mu\text{m}$), black carbon, sea salt (size $\leq 2.5 \mu\text{m}$), organic carbon and sulfate concentration, respectively.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Fig. 1 shows the spatial pattern of MERRA-2 reanalysis PM_{2.5} mass concentration throughout India for different seasons. The observed trends show that MERRA-2 data in different seasons reasonably conform to that of ground-based measurements. However, when comparing the observed concentration (from ground data) and reanalysis concentration (from MERRA-2) an apparent deviation is evident in mass concentration of PM_{2.5}. High mean bias between ground and reanalysis data over IGP ($-28 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) as compared to IHR ($-7 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and southern region ($-3 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) is observed, and the corresponding underestimation by MERRA-2 is 29%, 15% and 8%, respectively. Hence, PM underestimation by MERRA-2 especially in regions showing very high pollution levels is observed. This point is further supported by scatter plot between the MERRA-2 and ground-based data for monthly PM_{2.5} mass concentrations (Fig. 2). The scatter becomes wider for higher ground-based concentrations implying underestimation of PM concentration.

Fig. 1. Location of measurement sites along with corresponding Ground PM_{2.5} and MERRA-2 PM_{2.5} concentration during the time period 2015-2019 in India, where (a) winter, (b) summer, (c) monsoon, and (d) post-monsoon. The upper values in the boxes indicate ground PM_{2.5} values and lower values show MERRA-2 reanalysed PM_{2.5} concentration for each site.

Fig. 2 Scatter plot for monthly mean ground-based and MERRA-2 reanalysis PM_{2.5} mass concentration

CONCLUSIONS

MERRA-2 PM_{2.5} exhibited seasonal variation with high mass loading in winter and low in monsoon, similar to that in ground-based observations.

MERRA-2 mostly underestimated PM_{2.5} mass concentration relative to corresponding ground measurement, which was even higher during pollution episodes

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UNCERTAINTY ESTIMATES OF SUOMI-NPP VIIRS V1 DEEP BLUE AEROSOL OPTICAL DEPTH AND ÅNGSTRÖM EXPONENT OVER SOUTH ASIA

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KEYWORDS: ACCURACY, AOD, PRECISION, SOUTH ASIA, VIIRS.

INTRODUCTION

To help construct global distribution of aerosols, many satellite sensors and retrieval algorithms are in use. Deep Blue has now been applied on Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite (VIIRS) retrievals on board S-NPP satellite. The DB applied on VIIRS is better equipped in measuring land surface reflectance, dust model and smoke mask to isolate thick smokes from clouds (Hsu et al., 2019). Performance of VIIRS DB AOD over South Asia is challenging due to prevailing high aerosol loading, varying aerosol sub-types and variations in surface reflectance which affect retrieval accuracy. Here, accuracy, precision and uncertainty were assessed for VIIRS V1 DB AOD and AE against AERONET.

DATASET AND METHODS

In this study, VIIRS V1 DB AOD was retrieved for year 2012 to 2021 over landmasses of South Asia, for all the months except during monsoon due to moisture-related uncertainties. Further, AE at 412–490 nm was retrieved to find the size of the prevailing aerosols. AERONET Version 3 Level 2.0 direct-Sun AOD at 500 nm was interpolated to 550 nm using AE at 440 nm and 675 nm wavelength pair. Ten AERONET stations across South Asia were chosen.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

We note, DB was able to identify the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) of South Asia with highest AOD compared to the rest of South Asia (Fig. 1). Spatial variations in dominance of fine and coarse-mode aerosols were also recognized. Annual mean VIIRS AOD over South Asia averaged in between 2012 to 2021 was 0.37. This was well comparable with reported AOD both from MAIAC (0.39) and MISR (0.36) sensors by Mhawish et al. (2021) for year 2000 to 2019. Spatial mean AOD over the IGP was however, much higher (0.57) compared to rest of the South Asia (0.19).

Fig. 1. Spatial nature of VIIRS retrieved AOD and AE over South Asia averaged in between 2012 and 2021. White dots indicate AERONET stations considered for analysis.

Figure 2 indicates the sample statistics of these evaluation parameters for VIIRS AOD and AE against AERONET retrievals averaged over 10 stations. The accuracy and precision of VIIRS AOD was 0.187 and 0.491 respectively, which were indicative of associated error in VIIRS AOD retrievals over South Asia. For AE, such matrices were comparatively higher as its accuracy and precision was 0.651 and 0.411, respectively. For both AOD and AE, uncertainty associated with respect to AERONET observation was computed as 0.004. However, it should be noted that AE is a semiquantitative indicator of optical prevalence of fine and coarse-mode aerosols and is now not reported in the DT algorithm.

Fig. 2. Time series of VIIRS and AERONET AOD averaged seasonally over all AERONET stations.

Considerable spatial variations in MB between different AERONET cities can be evident (Fig. 3). Maximum positive MB in VIIRS AOD retrievals was noted in Lahore and Pokhara (0.06), followed by Karachi (0.1). AERONET stations located in these cities are having either very bright (Lahore and Karachi) or dark

vegetated surfaces (Pokhara) with DB underestimating the surface reflectance resulting in overestimation of AOD. DB underestimated AOD across South Asia with varying degree, as also reported by Aditi et al. (2023), due to overestimation of surface reflectance and assumption related to aerosol SSA. For all the stations, positive MB was noted for VIIRS AE varying from 0.09 to 0.83.

Fig. 3. Spatial variations in mean bias in VIIRS AOD and AE over South Asia.

Fig. 4. Spatial variations in RMSE of VIIRS AOD and AE over South Asia.

Fig. 4(a-b) shows inconsistent RMSE patterns for AOD and AE in South Asia. AOD RMSE peaks at 0.42-0.47 in Lumbini, Kathmandu Bode, and Dhaka, aligning with AOD MB, while lower RMSE is seen in Lahore (0.08), Karachi (0.17), Pune (0.15), Kanpur (0.24), and Gandhi College (0.27). Differences in VIIRS AOD and AERONET RMSE could be due to aerosol load, surface reflectance, and terrain variations. VIIRS DB AE RMSE varies spatially with peaks in Karachi (0.88) and Dhaka (0.54), similar to VIIRS AE MB. Higher VIIRS AE MB correlates with higher RMSE in AERONET, possibly due to AOD differences at specific sites (Sayer et al., 2019).

VIIRS V1 DB AOD and AE performance was evaluated at ten AERONET stations in South Asia. Statistical parameters, including RMSE, bias, accuracy, precision, and uncertainty, were computed against AERONET data. VIIRS AOD aligned with AERONET, capturing high aerosol loading in the IGP and India's east coast. Seasonal VIIRS AOD time series matched AERONET, with an accuracy (precision) of 0.187 (0.491), indicating minor retrieval errors. Both AOD and AE uncertainty was 0.004. VIIRS DB mostly underestimated AOD, with exceptions in Lahore and Pokhara, and higher RMSE in Kathmandu Bode and Lumbini (0.45-0.47). Improved aerosol models and surface reflectance measurements are needed for precise aerosol characterization in South Asia using VIIRS.

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NEW 9λ AETHALOMETER MODEL AE36s - PERFORMANCE AND ADVANCED
CHARACTERIZATION OF AEROSOL SOURCES

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Keywords: Aethalometer AE36s, Black Carbon, Brown Carbon, absorption Ångström exponent.

INTRODUCTION

The Aethalometer is a widely used filter photometer capable of measuring the light-absorbing properties of aerosol particles. In this study, we present the performance of the new Aethalometer model AE36s (Aerosol Magee Scientific) and show equivalence with its predecessor AE33. The new model addresses two crucial areas that have emerged in the scientific community in recent years: (1) the sensitivity of filter photometers to rapid changes of relative humidity, (2) the need for improved characterization of the absorbing part of organic aerosols in blue and UV region, the so-called brown carbon (BrC). Despite technical changes and improvements of the instrument, continuity of data of absorption measurements is essential; thus, in this study, we demonstrate the equivalence with AE33 through a series of laboratory and ambient measurement campaigns.

Additionally, to improve the characterization of BrC share of absorption in blue and UV regions, two additional wavelengths were introduced in the new Aethalometer model AE36s with respect to the older models: the 400 nm increases the resolution of absorption in a large gap of AE33 channels between 370 nm and 470 nm, and 340 nm extends the measurement range in the UV spectrum.

METHODS

Long-term measurements with the AE36s were conducted at an urban background site in Ljubljana (Slovenia) in winter – spring period in 2021/22 and 2023, and compared with results obtained in the EUPHORE simulation chamber for different fuel types, burning condition and ageing state. AAE was analyzed for the long (AAE₅₉₀₋₉₅₀; 590-660-880-950 nm) and short spectral range (AAE₄₀₀₋₅₂₀; 400-470-520 nm) separately, which allowed us to distinguish between different absorption fingerprints.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The performance of AE36s with improvements mentioned above was evaluated and compared to its predecessor AE33 during a long-term field campaign at an urban background site in Ljubljana, Slovenia (winter-spring 2022 and winter 2023), and laboratory tests with an artificial soot generator. Slopes of the orthogonal regression for all common wavelengths are within 5% range relative to the unity with $R^2 > 0.99$. Signal to noise ratio in the AE36s is also significantly improved, which results in more stable determination of the absorption Ångström exponent.

Chamber experiments have revealed significant absorption of BrC at 340 nm for fresh BrC emitted during the smouldering phase of biomass burning. Soon after emission the absorption at 340 nm decreases relative to the absorption in the short range (400 – 520 nm). In the first part of the aging phase, when the aerosol is exposed to sunlight, significant increase of absorption was observed in the middle wavelength range (470 – 660 nm), thus decreasing short range AAE₄₀₀₋₅₂₀ and increasing long range AAE₅₉₀₋₉₅₀. A slow decrease of absorption in the middle wavelength range follows with further photochemical ageing. Freshly emitted diesel exhaust and the flaming phase of biomass burning are characterized by lower BrC contribution and about 20% lower absorption at 340 nm than expected if AAE₄₀₀₋₅₂₀ would be extrapolated to 340 nm (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Comparison of AE33 and AE36s measurements for high BrC fraction condition.

Results from ambient Ljubljana campaign presented in the form of dual AAE resolution revealed several specific events, which could be distinguished from the urban aerosol absorption fingerprint: e.g. industrial fire emission, open fire burning and fresh BrC emission (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Example of dual AAE plot to distinguish between different aerosol sources.

CONCLUSIONS

Validation of the new Aethalometer model AE36s has revealed significant improvement of signal to noise ratio and reduced sensitivity to rapid changes of relative humidity in comparison to its predecessor AE33. Additional wavelengths, 340 nm and 400 nm can be efficiently used to enhance the resolution of absorption spectral dependence and improve the characterization of Brown Carbon.

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METHOD FOR ON-SITE INTERMEDIATE QUALITY CHECK (IQC) OF BETA GAUGE SYSTEM USED FOR PARTICULATE MATTER SAMPLING

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Keywords: Beta gauge system, absorption coefficient, calibration, intermediate checks

INTRODUCTION

The near real-time particulate matter (PM) monitors provide continuous measurements with minimal human intervention. The prevailing near real-time methods for PM measurement are primarily the Tapered-Element Oscillating Microbalance (TEOM) and the Beta Attenuation Monitor (BAM) technique. Continuous PM monitoring holds immense value as it furnishes real-time data on ambient concentrations over short durations. Globally, BAM technique stands out as a widely used real-time air quality monitoring method. However, Shukla and Aggarwal (2021) studied the effect of RH and high particle mass loading on the performance of beta gauge method and suggested for obtaining appropriate regional correction factors to enhance the accuracy of beta gauge measurements under variable meteorological conditions. The calibration of beta gauge system is performed using a film of known mass density (x) to ascertain the absorption efficiency (μ) of beta-rays. Due to diverse particle compositions and fluctuating meteorological conditions, there is a need for a calibration device traceable to primary standards, facilitating intermediary assessments of measurement data. To the best of our knowledge there is no device available for calibration verification of beta gauge system. As per ISO 17025, intermediate checks to validate the sampled data are an important part of maintaining accurate measurements. Therefore, a simple and precise method (with traceability to SI) is needed to fulfil this requirement. Developing a device tailored to intermediate checks of PM measurements will improve the existing calibration protocol of beta gauge system and the quality of data generated. Diverse regions exhibit distinct sources of PM, resulting in variations in surface density and particle composition, thereby impacting the value of μ . This highlights the significance of conducting on-site calibrations. In the view of above concern, the objective of present research is to provide an apparatus and method for on-site intermediate check method which is traceable to SI unit.

METHODS

Figure 1. Samples deposited on filter

A device is developed for calibration verification of beta gauge system. This device consists of a Carbon-14 beta-rays source and a PMT with scintillation device as the detector and a display unit. It helps in the determination of x and then μ to perform field calibration and intermediate checks of the on-site beta gauge monitors. To verify the effect of attenuation coefficient on beta gauge measurements, series of 1-hour samples of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} particles of organic source (from burning cow dung cakes) and inorganic source (ammonium sulphate) were collected on 47 mm Teflon filters (see scheme 1). For intermediate checks of beta gauge measurement data, sampled filter tape was unrolled from the beta gauge system and deposited spots were punched and weighed using 1 μ g readability microbalance. PM mass of each sampling spot were

calculated by subtracting blank values (unexposed punches taken between sampled spots). Similarly, ambient samples were collected as spot deposit for low volume sampler (flow rate -16.7 lpm) and initial and final mass of filter were measured to calculate the mass difference. Compared the PM mass of beta gauge and gravimetric sampling (m_g) for ambient samples (see scheme 2).

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Our results show that different composition of PM attenuates the beta rays differently. Recorded attenuation coefficient (mostly $> 0.3 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mg}^{-1}$) is different from range specified in literature ($0.25 - 0.27 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mg}^{-1}$). Thus, different values of absorption coefficient are recoded confirming its dependency on particle composition and size (PM_{10} or $\text{PM}_{2.5}$). Therefore, for on-site calibration of beta gauge systems it is important to calculate and input absorption coefficient measured by above described method for different seasons.

Our comparison results of intermediate checks for PM concentration (wide range tested $8.7 - 314 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) derived by beta gauge instrument and weighing method shows an excellent agreement within 10% deviation (U.S. EPA, 2017). However, detailed uncertainty study is in progress to further quantify these approaches.

Fig. 2 Plot of $\ln(Io/I)$ vs $x \text{ (mg cm}^{-2}\text{)}$ for (a) PM_{10} and (b) $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ particles generated in laboratory

CONCLUSION

Data reliability is the matter of concern and inappropriate method can affect the accuracy of measurement due to unavailability of accurate calibration equipment. This highlights the significance of maintaining a reliable beta gauge calibration configuration that incorporates comprehensive correction. As a consequence of the mass absorption coefficient's reliance on different PM sources, it is imperative to exercise caution during calibration and particle measurement. The developed device is capable of improving the existing calibration protocol of beta gauge system to enable intermediate checks of measurement data and improve the quality of data generated.

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HARMONIZED MEASUREMENTS OF AMBIENT PARTICLES AND DEDICATED SOLUTIONS FOR PARTICLE NUMBER CONCENTRATIONS AND SIZE DISTRIBUTIONS

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Keywords: AMBIENT PARTICLES, ULTRAFINE, MEASUREMENT, NUMBER CONCENTRATION

INTRODUCTION

Until about 70 years ago, the world did not have any air quality regulations. It was the deadly fog in the city of London (UK) in 1953 that led to the introduction of mass-based particulate matter measurements and eventually PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} standards. It has only been in the past decade that also the subset of ambient ultrafine particles (UFP) has gained importance. In 2021, the World Health Organization (WHO) published their Global Air Quality Guidelines (WHO, 2021). For the first time, these guidelines stated the need to include the continuous measurement of particle number concentration (PNC) and particle size distributions (PSD) in addition to other airborne pollutants. On a European level, the Committee for Standardization (CEN) published technical specification CEN/TS 16976:2016 for PNC measurements in ambient air using a Condensation Particle Counter (CPC). In addition, the CEN/TS 17434 technical specification for measuring the particle size distribution of ambient air by Scanning Mobility Particle Sizers (SMPS, or ‘Mobility Particle Sizer Spectrometer’, MPSS, in regulatory terms) was published in 2019. Finally, the efforts of the ‘‘Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure’’ (ACTRIS) have to be mentioned.

METHODS

Measurement instruments should provide reproducible sampling, conditioning, measurement and data handling. The complete solution from TSI (Fig. 1) enables the continuous monitoring of ambient particles compliant with all current requirements. A full-flow butanol-based CPC with a 10 nm detection limit (Model 3750-CEN10, TSI Inc., Shoreview, USA) was calibrated independently at the World Calibration Center for Aerosol Physics (WCCAP) in Leipzig. The same was done for the new wide-range SMPS (Model 3938W50-PP-CEN10, TSI Inc.), so it fully complies with the CEN/TS 17434 guideline. This ambient monitoring SMPS also starts its measurement at 10 nm and covers the range up to 800 nm in one scan.

Figure 1. Harmonized technical solution for the measurement of ambient ultrafine particles.

An optimized sampling inlet system with dryer, RH/T control and an optional diluter are used to enable standardized measurements. Another advantage of this complete monitoring solution for ambient UFP is its data output, which permits the transfer to a standardized database as well as the use of other data protocols.

MEASUREMENT RESULTS

We will share and discuss exemplary results from several weeks of measurements of the urban aerosol in a light industrial area in the city of Aachen, Germany, as well as of ambient air at the location of the World Calibration Center for Aerosol Physics (WCCAP) at TROPOS in Leipzig, Germany (Fig. 2). As an important quality check, a standalone CPC was operated alongside the SMPS. The integrated total number concentration from the SMPS needs to be within $\pm 10\%$ of the average PNC determined by the standalone CPC. Stability in the aerosol population is required for a valid SMPS scan. We can show a valid closure between both measurements for our dataset when considering highly fluctuating aerosol concentrations by application of the coefficient of variation on the 1 Hz time resolution dataset of the CPC measurements.

Figure 2. Comparison of a SMPS 3938W50 to the TROPOS reference MPSS for ambient air in Leipzig, Germany. The deviation in the 20 to 200 nm range is well below the permissible $\leq 10\%$.

CONCLUSIONS

This work illustrates current developments in improving and harmonizing the measurement of submicrometer aerosol number concentrations and particle size distributions in ambient air. While the regulatory activities reported here have their origin and focus in Europe, they are considered on a global level by institutions like the WHO as well as by atmospheric measurement networks in the United States and elsewhere. We have shown that high precision instrumentation from TSI has been adapted to the latest requirements. Good agreement to the World Calibration Center of Aerosol Physics standards within specified levels has been shown.

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A DUAL-WAVELENGTH PHOTOTHERMAL AEROSOL ABSORPTION MONITOR: DESIGN, CALIBRATION, PERFORMANCE AND MEASUREMENTS OF COATED SOOT

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Keywords: aerosol absorption coefficient, black carbon, light absorbing aerosols, aerosol mixing state.

INTRODUCTION

Direct measurement of aerosol light absorption is conceptually preferable over indirect methods. Using filter photometers is challenging due to systematic artifacts (Weingartner et al., 2003) and the lack of standardized calibration procedures. A photothermal interferometer probes the change of the refractive index caused by light absorption in (and the subsequent heating of) the sample – the detection is linear and can be traced to first principles. Measurement at two wavelengths allows the determination of its wavelength dependence and the Ångström exponent (AAE).

METHODS

A photothermal interferometer probes the change of the refractive index caused by light absorption in the sample – the detection is linear and can be traced to first principles. Measurement at two wavelengths allows the determination of its wavelength dependence and the Ångström exponent (AAE). The photothermal aerosol absorption monitor (PTAAM-2) uses a folded Mach-Zender interferometer (similar to Moosmüller and Arnott, 1996; Sedlacek, 2006, Visser *et al.*, 2020). Two pump lasers at 532 and 1064 nm are modulated at different frequencies and focused in the sample chamber using an axicon (patent granted) for simultaneous measurement. The interferometer signal is detected by two photodiodes and resolved by a dual-channel lock-in amplifier measuring at the two respective frequencies.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The green channel (532 nm) is calibrated traceably to primary standards using ~1 µmol/mol NO₂ using a permeation NO₂ source. The calibration is transferred to the IR using aerosolized nigrosin (Drinovec *et al.*, 2022). The instrument was characterized and its uncertainties quantified (Table 1).

$b_{\text{abs},532\text{nm}}$	4%
$b_{\text{abs},1064\text{nm}}$	6%
AAE	9%

Table 1. Uncertainties of the measured parameters.

We calibrated filter photometers (CLAP, AE33) in green and near infrared with soot, and determined their cross-sensitivity to scattering for ammonium sulfate particles, resulting in wavelength and size dependent calibration parameters. A winter ambient campaign has shown similar multiple scattering parameter values for ambient aerosols and laboratory experiments. The spectral dependence of these parameters resulted in AE33 reporting somewhat biased AAE values. We have also determined the absorption enhancement by

coatings of BC with non-absorbing secondary organic matter (SOM) dependent on the coating thickness-to-core diameter ratio, see Figure 1 (Kalbermatter *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 1. Absorption enhancement due to coating of BC with SOM vs. wavelength using PTAAM-2.

CONCLUSIONS

The calibration traceable to primary standards and the direct linearity make the multi-wavelength PTI an excellent candidate for the reference method for the determination of the aerosol absorption coefficient.

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OPTIMIZING REFERENCE CO-LOCATION SITES FOR IMPROVED TRANSFERABILITY OF CALIBRATION MODELS WITHIN A LOW-COST SENSOR NETWORK IN NCT-DELHI, INDIA

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Keywords: Low-cost sensors, Calibration, Transferable models, Machine-learning

INTRODUCTION

Low-cost sensor networks (LCSNs) are enlarging worldwide to collect high spatiotemporal data due to their economic feasibility and compact size. However, their major limitation is the low data quality and inherent biases in their measurements due to the estimation of mass and number concentrations from light scattering data. Additionally, the effect of external factors on sensor performance, such as relative humidity (RH) and temperature (T) are well established in the literature (Kumar & Sahu, 2021). The most common practice to develop calibration models for LCS is through collocation in the ambient environment with a reference monitor (Levy Zamora et al., 2023). Conducting collocation studies is especially difficult in regions with a sparse network of monitors, such as rural and semi-urban areas. In this study, we introduce the concept of developing a reference map as a collocation guide to achieve maximum transferability of the calibration models within a network of LCS. The methodology discussed can be used for other LCS networks. It will benefit the monitoring agencies to develop calibration models through field collocation in regions with a sparse network of reference monitors.

METHODS

A dense network of APT-MAXIMA sensors were collocated with the reference monitor Beta Attenuation Monitor (BAM) at 22 sites in NCT-Delhi. We assessed the spatial transferability of the site-specific calibration models by testing the model performance at each site. The performance of a model trained using the data from sites $S_1, S_2, \dots, S_{n-1}, S_n$ is tested on all sites $[S_1, S_2, \dots, S_{n-1}, S_n]$ using four ML algorithms namely, MLR, kNN, RF, and GB. To evaluate the spatial variation of the model performance, we assessed their performance using the R^2 and RMSE values with respect to the distance between the sites. Representative locations were identified for collocation using k-Means clustering (kMC) on the performance metric R^2 . Clusters were used to find the transferability scores to arrange the sites from low to high suitability for co-locating LCS with a reference monitor. Three clusters (0: low R^2 , 1: medium R^2 , and 2: high R^2) were found which were then used to calculate the transferability scores. We calculated the inter-site dependency of each site pair using the average of inter-site transferability score. Then we added this score for all the possible site pairs corresponding to each site. Since the variance in the score was too low, the total added-up score represented the overall transferability. This “transferability score” quantified the transferability performance of the trained models across sites. The sites with high transferability scores are more likely to produce a transferable calibration model with good performance at most sites and vice-versa.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Transferability of the calibration models was assessed, and the sites were classified into high, medium, and low, based on the site suitability for conducting LCS collocation and calibration studies. Figure 1 shows the most suitable locations identified for collocating LCS with reference monitors to develop calibration within the network. A site with high suitability for LCS calibration, presented as green zones, implies that the correction models developed at that site are transferable to the maximum sites in the network. On the other hand, the sites with low suitability, presented as red zones, can only be used to develop site-specific calibration models with poor performance when transferred to the other sites in the network. The major hotspots identified for collocating LCS and developing calibration models are S2, S3, S4, S6, S9, S10, S11, S12, S15, S16, and S20. Mundka (S10) and Punjabi Bagh (S16) were found to be the “most suitable” sites for developing LCS calibration models and transferring them to the other sites in the network. On the contrary, PGDAV (S17) site is the “least suitable” site and therefore needs a site-specific calibration model.

Figure 1. Locations identified for LCS collocation with the reference monitors for development of calibration models to achieve best transferability within the monitoring network in Delhi.

CONCLUSIONS

This type of reference map (presented in Figure 1) for assessing the spatial transferability of LCS calibration models can be developed for any network of LCS, and representative locations can be identified to conduct LCS collocation studies. It is especially useful for monitoring agencies to install reference monitors which will serve as a collocation platform for LCS and calibrate the networks of low-cost sensors.

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**SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF ZINC OXIDE BASED THIN FILMS FOR
DEVELOPMENT OF LOW COST SENSORS FOR DETECTION OF MICROBIAL
COMPONENTS IN AMBIENT ENVIRONMENT**

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Keywords: ambient environment, bioaerosols, biosensors, nanomaterial

INTRODUCTION

Bioaerosols, or biological aerosols, consist of airborne particles of biological origin including bacteria, fungi, archaea, viruses, pollen, their fragments, components, and byproducts, such as DNA, endotoxin, and mycotoxins. (Cox and Wathes, 1995; Ghosh et al., 2015; Lindsley et al., 2017) They infect humans, plants, and animals and are estimated to be responsible for more than 15 million deaths worldwide each year. Detection of biological components in ambient air is a difficult challenge as the methods are cumbersome and time taking. Hence, the development of fast and accurate methods of detection and identification systems for biological components in the environment is of paramount importance in the current scenario of the infection and spread of pathogens. Nanomaterials have a great impact when used in biosensing applications because of their unique properties at nanoscale. Metal oxide based thin films of ZnO may have great potential because of its chemical stability and low cost. ZnO based thin film has been prepared and characterized to see the biosensing properties to fabricate the biosensors for monitoring and measurements of bioaerosols in the environment. These films have been prepared using sol-gel method and characterization of thin films were done by various techniques using FE SEM, UV-VIS and XRD. ZnO electrode has also been prepared to see the biosensing application.

METHODS

2.4 gm of Zinc acetate dehydrate was dissolved in 30 ml of Ethanol and 7 ml of Glycerol was added as sol stabilizer and binder and kept for stirring for 20 minutes at 80°C on Magnetic stirrer. Then the solution was allowed to stir for 6 hr. at room temperature and kept for ageing for 24 hours. 100 microliter of prepared sol was placed on $1.1 \times 1.3 \text{ cm}^2$ Indium tin oxide substrate and homogeneously coated for 2-layers using a spin-coating unit (MILMAN) at 2000 rpm for 30 sec. 2-layer deposition was achieved by successive deposition of the same amount of sol over the previously deposited layer. The thickness of deposited films was controlled by spin coater rotation speed and rotation time. After each deposition, the thin film of precursor sol was dried on the hot plate at 80°C for 10 min. Finally, the dried films were sintered at 500°C for 2 hours in a tubular furnace. (Biswas, et al., 2023)

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Structural characterization XRD patterns were acquired with a Bruker AXS D8 Advance X-ray Diffractometer using Cu Ka radiation. 2θ scan range of the samples was 20-80 with scan speed of 5 s/step. The XRD outcome spectrum shows predominantly zinc and oxygen peaks, showing nature's crystallinity as shown in figure 1. The ZnO nanostructures obtained are homogeneous and similar in volume, which is consistent with the XRD test. which shows fine crystalline. (Ramzuz et al., 2020) The size of the particle was determined using the Scherrer equation ($0.9\lambda/\beta\cos\theta$) and was found to be 209.34 nm.

Optical absorbance spectra were obtained from UV-Visible spectrophotometer (PerkinElmer Lambda 365, USA) in 200-800 nm range. By extrapolating the linear portion of Tauc plots, the values of the bandgaps

were estimated and is found to be 3.7eV. (Fig. 2) Morphology of metal oxide was investigated by field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM) using FEI Quanta 200 FE-SEM. (Fig 3.) Diameter distribution of particle was obtained from Image J software. The size of the sphere was in found to be 74.09 nm as shown in Fig.3. Results of the characterization from EDAX indicates that the ZnO nanostructures have strong sterling 62% amount of zinc content and 23%. of oxygen content, rest being Na and Si. The photoelectrochemical performance of the electrodes was measured in a three-electrode cell configuration comprising of the reference electrode (Saturated Calomel electrode, SCE), counter electrode (Pt mesh), and working electrode by Electrochemical workstation. (Zahner, Germany) Photocurrent density (J_{ph}) of the samples was calculated from the difference of light current and dark current per square centimeter of the illumination area. The Potential was found to be 2.014 RHE and the corresponding current was 1.042 mA/cm².

CONCLUSION

We confirm the structure of Zinc oxide by XRD data. UV-VIS analysis confirmed the band gap of ZnO which is in range from 3.2eV to 3.8eV. FE SEM analysis was performed and ZnO structure was found to be in nanometer scale size and was spherical in shape. We further did the elemental analysis which further confirms the presence of Zinc and Oxygen in the structure. Later on, ZnO photoelectrode was prepared which shows the fluctuation in current and voltage. Hence it is proved that the prepared ZnO thin film will be used to fabricate the biosensors for monitoring and measurements of bioaerosols in the environment.

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COMPARATIVE STUDY OF SUB-MICRON PARTICLE REMOVAL USING AIR FILTERS AND ELECTROSTATIC PRECIPITATOR

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Keywords: Air purification, Sub-micron particles, Air filters, Electrostatic precipitators

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution has emerged as a critical global concern, significantly affecting human health and environment. With increasing urbanization, industrialization and population growth, the release of hazardous particles and gases into the atmosphere has increased. Particularly, in developing countries like India, numerous cities are ranked among the most polluted globally. To address this pressing issue, innovative air pollution control technologies are essential for both indoor and outdoor environments. In this study, a systematic investigation is conducted for characterizing removal efficiencies of filtration and ionization-based technologies. Various locally available air filter medias were evaluated for overall and size-dependent efficiency and pressure drop. Their performance results are compared with ionization technology such as electrostatic precipitator (ESP).

METHODS

The experimental setup is followed ISO-16890 standard test aerosols to evaluate the removal efficiency of air filters and ESP. A Collison nebulizer (CH Technologies Inc, USA) having a 6-jet nozzle was used to generate microdroplets from KCl salt solution. These microdroplets were carried by nitrogen gas (99.997%) at a flow rate of 8.6 LPM. Further, microdroplets were passed through a diffusion dryer to reduce moisture content below 40% relative humidity (Sebastian et al., 2021), so as to produce theoretically one dry aerosolized particle. Subsequently, the aerosol stream was diluted (50%) with highly pure nitrogen gas in a cylindrical chamber. These diluted particles were challenged to evaluate filter media performance in a specially designed custom-built Air Filter Holder (AFH) to ensure uniform particle collection. With a maintained flow rate (17.17 LPM) and face velocity (0.5 m/s), the isokinetic sample was drawn to aerosol measuring research-grade instrument for characterization of particle concentration. The filter media were tested with a SMPS instrument, specifically a long-differential mobility analyzer (long-DMA, Model 3938L50, TSI Inc., MN, USA) at 0.59 LPM, was used to classify the mobility diameter of particles in the range of 13 nm to 420 nm. Similarly, for evaluation of indigenously designed lab-scale ESP (Designed configuration: single-pass axial flow; cross-section: square; full width: 43 mm; length: 150 mm; central discharge electrode radius: 0.1 mm), the AFH was replaced with ESP and the remaining setup was kept similar as it was done for the air filter testing. The ESP with an axial aerosol velocity of 0.15 m/s was used for the evaluation.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The efficiencies of different air filters (i.e., HEPA, fine and pre-filter) were studied to check the removal of salt particles generated from the 0.2M KCl solution and results are shown in Figure 1. The study was performed at a flow rate of 17.17 LPM and face velocity of 0.5 m/s using 6-jet Collison nebulizer. The generated particles were challenged on various filter media for detecting particle removal efficiency. The removal efficiency of different filters was found to be 99.997%, 60-90% and <30% for HEPA, fine and Pre-filters, respectively (shown in Figure 1). Similarly, the initial pressure drops were 2346, 168 and 45 Pa for HEPA, fine and Pre-filters, respectively. Different efficiencies and corresponding pressure drop might be mainly due to characteristics of the individual filter. HEPA filters often are densely packed, fine filters with fibres are medium packed, whereas pre-filters are loosely packed. Effective fiber diameter in the range of 1-10 μm , 10-30 μm and 30-60 μm for HEPA, fine and Pre-filters, respectively. Also, HEPA filters are less porous compared to fine filters and pre-filters are highly porous. Further, literature suggested that particle collection efficiency of the ESP is as high as 95% for minimum flow rate of 10 m^3/min at an ionization voltage of 8 kV with collection plates at 7 kV (Kim et al., 2013). The performance of an Electrostatic

Precipitator (ESP) was evaluated by varying applied voltage (8, 9, and 10 kV) to assess its efficiency. It was found that, the highest efficiency of 74% was achieved at 10 kV, specifically within the particle size range of 13 to 400 nm. This outcome can be attributed to the ESP's filtration efficiency, which relies on factors such as migration velocity, residence time, and the voltage applied across the discharge electrode and collection plate.

Figure 1. Particle removal efficiency for tested filters and ESP using KCl salt (Experimental conditions: Salt concentration = 0.2 M, Face velocity = 0.5 m/s, for ESP discharge electrode at 8, 9 and 10 kV).

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a comparison between air filtration and ionization technologies was performed to identify suitable technology for mitigating indoor air pollution. Based on five different flat air filter media testing, it is concluded that fine filters should be used in air filtration systems. The HEPA filter showed a removal efficiency of 99.997% for particles ranging from 13 nm to 400 nm but the pressure drop was very high. Whereas, for a similar size range the ESP was capable to remove with an efficiency of 74% when the discharge electrode potential is 10 kV. Therefore, the removal efficiency of HEPA filters are much higher in comparison to ESP. This study provides evidence that the air filters are better than ESP for removing submicron particles and should be used for closed indoor environment.

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**OVERVIEW OF MICROPULSE LIDAR OBSERVATIONS OF BOUNDARY LAYER, AEROSOLS
AND CLOUDS OVER KATTANKULATHUR: INSIGHT INTO COUPLING PROCESSES**

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Keywords: Micro pulse lidar, aerosol optical depth, Atmospheric Boundary layer, Coupling processes,
Clouds

INTRODUCTION

The Earth's lower troposphere is mainly divided into two layers based on turbulence characteristics: the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL), dominated by the turbulence processes, and the free troposphere (FT), which is relatively free from such turbulence (Kakkanattu et al., 2023). The ABL is directly influenced by the surface forcings such as the convective turbulence during the daytime and wind shear turbulence during the nighttime, among several other processes, which mixes the properties at a response scale of about an hour or less (Reddy et al., 2021), resulting in the properties different from the FT. Such forcings develop barriers between the ABL and FT that inhibit the exchange of mass, momentum, and energy. The ABL is known as a gateway for the exchange between the surface and FT; however, exchange mainly occurs during the preferred times of diurnal evolution and during the timings of the strong convection and advection activities (Ananthavel et al., 2021). The aerosols within the ABL play a crucial role in determining the lower tropospheric thermal structure, atmospheric stability, sensible and latent heat fluxes, changes in the surface wind speed, pollution dispersion, and vertical mixing. On the other hand, the FT aerosols significantly affect the surface energy balance due to their interaction with incoming solar radiation, regional rainfall patterns, monsoon strength, and boundary layer dynamics. The entrainment of aerosols from the ABL significantly alters the thermal structure of the atmosphere both directly by absorbing solar radiation and indirectly by the formation of clouds (Ali et al., 2022). The processes of forming the elevated aerosol layer (EAL) are mainly by the strong convection that pushes the surface aerosol layer to the FT and the advection that causes the transport of transboundary aerosols from one region to another (Mehta et al., 2023). Aerosols are one of the essential meteorological variables that affect weather and climate via their interactions mainly with radiation and clouds and their complex coupling with atmospheric dynamics. For example, the formation of cirrus clouds provides the means to trap the aerosols deep into the troposphere, which is susceptible to being transported into the lower stratosphere. Cirrus clouds also play a crucial role in the Earth's radiation budget by reflecting the incoming solar radiation (albedo effect) and trapping the outgoing longwave radiation (greenhouse effect) (Ali et al., 2022).

METHODS

This paper presents an overview of micropulse lidar (MPL) observations at coastal station Kattankulathur (12.82°N, 80.04°E) is carried out under network projects supported by Earth Science and Technology Cell (ESTC) under the Ministry of Earth Sciences, India. Three years- long continuous MPL observations were carried out almost every day between 15:00 IST on day one to 11:00 IST on day two on all clear sky days except on holidays during 2016-2018. MPL observations simultaneous to cloud aerosol lidar with orthogonal polarization (CALIOP) and regulation radiosonde observations from Indian Meteorological Department (IMD) Chennai located at Meenambakkam (13.0°N, 80.06°E). This study identifies ABL using the fuzzy logic method and different mixing lines using conserved variable analysis. The elevated aerosols and cirrus cloud layers are identified using zeros crossing methods.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The ABL over Kattankulathur is generally characterized by the double mixed layer providing an extra barrier to exchange between ABL and FT. The pollutants and aerosols escaping to the free troposphere either get advected and deposited to the transboundary region or convectively transported to higher altitudes, resulting in the nucleation of the clouds at various levels. Under the deep convection boundary layer, pollutants even reach the upper troposphere, providing surface to high-level cirrus cloud formations. The knowledge of the spatiotemporal cirrus clouds occurrence is vital in quantifying the radiation budget of the Earth-atmosphere system. The MPL observation over Kattankulathur shows a robust diurnal pattern with frequent occurrence of single-layer cirrus in the late evening and multi-layer cirrus clouds in the early

morning. The maximum occurrence of cirrus clouds during the southwest (SW) monsoon and northeast (NE) monsoon, and the minimum occurs during winter. The vertical extent of the occurrence is ~ 8-17 km, with frequent occurrence of cirrus clouds above the cold point tropopause (CPT) during May, July, and August. The occurrence of the cirrus top above the CPT indicates the transport of water vapor into the lower stratosphere. Such water vapor transport by means of the formation of cirrus clouds can radiatively affect stratospheric ozone chemistry. Further, to understand the role of the cirrus clouds on the thermal structure of the tropical tropopause layer (TTL), the subvisible (SVC) optically thin and thick clouds occurring at the CPT and within the TTL are segregated. The temperature profiles in the presence of the SVC, optically thin and optically thick clouds concerning clear sky temperature profiles show cooling between the cirrus top and CPT while warming below the cirrus top in the upper troposphere and above the CPT in the lower stratosphere.

Figure 1. (a) Percentage contribution of the ABL and FT to the total AOD. Interannual variation of AOD in total, within ABL, and within EAL using (b) MPL and (d) CALIPSO and the contribution of ABL and EAL to the total AOD using (c) MPL and (e) CALIPSO. (f-h) Cirrus clouds occurrence above CPT.

CONCLUSIONS

Contribution of the AOD from ABL and Free Troposphere

Contribution of AOD from ABL and EAL during pre-monsoon season

The thermodynamic structure of the ABL, the mixing lines, and the multiple mixing lines provide an extra barrier to exchange processes.

Diurnal variations of the cirrus clouds and their role in the exchange of water vapor into the lower stratosphere

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THE NATION-FIRST SUN-SKY-MOON-POLARIZED MULTISPECTRAL RADIOMETER FOR AEROSOL AND PRECURSOR GAS STUDIES AT AUH, GURUGRAM, INDIA

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Keywords: PRISTINE LOCATION, AEROSOLS, OPTICAL DEPTH, MICROPHYSICS, POLARIZATION, WATER VAPOR, RADIATIVE FORCING.

INTRODUCTION

Studies relating to the effects of atmospheric aerosols and precursor gases at regional and global scales on climate change, environmental evolution and health are sparse over pristine locations, and are critical for the future of our planet sustainability challenges that balance economic growth, social well-being, and ecological stewardship. To better manage their impacts and end products, observers and decision / policy makers need to monitor and diagnose the nature and concentration of aerosols in both space and time, forecast and alert. Despite the high temporal and spectral resolution provided by different aerosol networks, the sun photometry yields aerosol information limited to the daylight period and column-averaged. Moreover, polarization measurements that provide composition and shape of aerosols are scarce. These important limitations hamper our understanding of aerosols and gases for climate studies, particularly over high-latitude regions where we encounter extended periods of darkness at wintertime. To acquire this vital information, as a part of the ongoing long-term research collaboration program which is in progress between NASA-AERONET, GSFC, USA and Amity University Haryana (AUH), India, a sun-sky-lunar-polarized multiband photometer has been installed at AUH, Panchgaon, a pristine location in the Haryana State. In this communication, we briefly describe and present some salient features of this new system together with some preliminary results and future studies that merit over the earlier conventional network systems (Holben *et al.*, 1998) for air quality and human health (Bayat *et al.*, 2013), global warming, and climate sustainability studies (for example, Vijayakumar *et al.*, 2020).

METHODS

A new NASA-AERONET photometer system (CE318-T) (Fig. 1) that has been presented in this paper involves basically the standard instrument, CE318-AERONET, coupled with the principles behind the lunar/star photometry, light polarization (Li *et al.*, 2021) and associated calibration procedures. Thus, it performs daytime and night-time measurements and provides additional and enhanced operational functionalities including the lidar ratio, LR (ratio between backscattering and extinction coefficients) and depolarization ratio, DR (ratio between peak intensity of parallel and perpendicular component).

Figure 1. Schematic of CE318-T

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The sun-sky photometric observations using the CE 318-AERONET have been in progress at AUH since August 2017. The new Cimel sun-sky-lunar-polarized multiwavelength photometer (CE318-T) has been installed and observations during day and night, as per the protocol, have been in progress since 18 June 2023. Some sample (first) results of AOD, AE, PWV, LR, DR and SSA, amongst many others, are displayed in Fig. 2 (A), (B), (C), (D), (E) and (F), respectively. It is clear from the figure that diurnal variations in AOD and AE show larger mean daytime AOD as compared to its nocturnal counterpart, while the water vapour exhibits lower values during daytime and higher values during night-time, which is consistent. As the 1.0 level data were used here, the larger AOD values could be due to multiple scattering

effects from clouds. The variations in LD and DR (at two elevation angles) portray inverse relationship with wavelength.

Figure 2. Diurnal variation of (a) Aerosol optical depth (AOD), (b) precipitable water vapor (PWV), (c) Angstrom Exponent (AE), and Spectral variation of (d) Lidar Ratio, (e) Depolarization Ratio and (F) Single Scattering Albedo (SSA) during 0235 h – 2355 h of 31 July 2023.

CONCLUSIONS

The new sun-sky-moon-polarized multiband photometer, installed at AUH, Gurugram, is described, and the salient features observed and future programs that highlight the potentiality of the new system for better understanding of the integrated impact of aerosol and gas constituents on climate, under different environmental and meteorological conditions, are presented.

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APPLICABILITY AND VALIDATION OF INSAT-3D AEROSOLS MEASUREMENTS FOR INDIAN REGION

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Keywords: INSAT, Satellite, Validation, Aerosol Measurements.

INTRODUCTION

India is home to various types of aerosols from both natural and anthropogenic sources. To understand their interactions with the climate as well as the resultant implications, one needs continuous measurements of aerosols at high spatial and temporal resolutions. The advanced Indian meteorological geostationary satellite INSAT-3D provides such measurements of the aerosol optical depth (AOD) from space since its launch in 2013. The data is available at every 30min interval and has a spatial resolution of 10km x 10km. These high resolution aerosol observations are useful for understanding the aerosol characteristics and their effects associated with various atmospheric phenomenon. Earlier studies such as Kumar et al. 2016 have validated the INSAT-3D AOD data by comparing it with other satellite and ground based observations. Mishra et al. (2018) have also estimated the uncertainty in observations from INSAT-3D Imager and performed the validation of its algorithm over land and ocean. However, the current study performs a more precise comparison with the MODIS Terra and Aqua satellites to bring out further insights with the intention to understand its applicability for various types of studies.

DATA & METHODS

In this work, long time INSAT-3D Level 2 data of AOD is analysed for the period 2014-2022. It has been compared with the combined Dark Target and Deep Blue combined AOD from both MODIS Aqua (1:30 am, local time) and Terra (10:30 am, local time) datasets. Further, the INSAT-3D AOD observations are also validated with five different surface AERONET stations available over India. Different statistical analysis such as correlations have been performed and the results are presented.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

In the present work, we analyse the long-time aerosol observations by INSAT-3D for the Indian region and validate the mean and variability with other satellite and ground observations with the intention to better understand its advantages and applicability for different types of studies.

The annual AOD pattern in INSAT-3D show large differences in comparison with the MODIS. (Fig. 1). The range of AOD is approximately half of the MODIS values. Although, the Indo-Gangetic Plains show a similar pattern that of MODIS, the values of INSAT-3D AOD ranges between 0.3 to 0.4 (MODIS AOD range is 0.6-1.0). A large is particularly observed over Eastern India that could have significant impact on our current understanding of aerosols on systems like the Indian monsoon. Similarly, the seasonal distribution of AOD also continues to show differences between the two datasets with the maximum difference during the Monsoon (JJAS) and least difference during the Pre-Monsoon (MAM) season.

Fig 1. Long-time mean Aerosol Optical Depth over India from (a) INSAT-3D and (b) MODIS (combined Aqua and Terra)

CONCLUSIONS

Despite showing significant differences in the aerosol optical depth with other satellite datasets such as MODIS, the INSAT-3D data is highly useful for studying the temporal variability and spatial variability of aerosol loading, calculating the radiative forcing, data assimilation and process understanding studies among other applications that the study highlights with the case studies.

Main conclusions are that clearly the spatial distribution show differences in the annual, seasonal and as well as monthly scales. A similar, differences exist between the INSAT-3D and AERONET stations also.

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MASS ABSORPTION CROSS SECTION OF AETHALOMETER BLACK CARBON IN THE ARCTIC

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Keywords: MASS ABSORPTION CROSS-SECTION, BLACK CARBON, AETHALOMETER, ARCTIC.
INTRODUCTION

Long-term measurements of the mass concentration of black carbon (BC) in the atmosphere (M_{BC}) with well-constrained accuracy are indispensable to quantify its emission, transport, and deposition. The aerosol light absorption coefficient (b_{abs}), usually measured by a filter-based absorption photometer, including an Aethalometer (AE), is often used to estimate M_{BC} . The measured b_{abs} is converted to M_{BC} by assuming a value for the mass absorption cross section (MAC). Previously, we derived the MAC for AE (MAC (AE)) from measured b_{abs} and independently measured M_{BC} values at two sites in the Arctic. M_{BC} was measured with a filter-based absorption photometer with a heated inlet (COSMOS). The accuracy of the COSMOS-derived M_{BC} (M_{BC} (COSMOS)) was within about 15%. Here we obtained additional MAC (AE) measurements to improve understanding of its variability and uncertainty. We measured b_{abs} (AE) and M_{BC} (COSMOS) at Alert (2018–2020), Barrow (2012–2021), Ny-Ålesund (2012–2019), and Pallas (2019–2022). At Pallas, we also obtained four-wavelength photoacoustic aerosol absorption spectrometer (PAAS-4λ) measurements of b_{abs} . b_{abs} (AE) and M_{BC} (COSMOS) were tightly correlated; the average MAC_{cor} (AE) at the four sites was $11.4 \pm 1.2 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ (mean $\pm 1\sigma$) at 590 nm and $7.76 \pm 0.73 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ at 880 nm. The spatial variability of MAC_{cor} (AE) was about 11% (1σ), and its year-to-year variability was about 18%. We compared MAC_{cor} (AE) in the Arctic with values at mid-latitudes measured by previous studies, and also with values obtained by using other types of filter-based absorption photometer.

OBSERVATION SITES AND METHODOLOGY

Simultaneous measurements of M_{BC} (COSMOS, $\lambda = 565 \text{ nm}$) and b_{abs} (AE, λ) were carried out at Alert in Canada (82.5°N, 62.5°W, 210 m ASL), Barrow (NOAA, Barrow Observatory) in Alaska (71.3°N, 156.6°W, 10 m), Sammaltunturi in Finland (68.0°N, 24.1°E, 560 m ASL; hereafter Pallas), and Ny-Ålesund (Zeppelin station) in Svalbard (78.9°N, 11.9°E, 472 m). More detailed descriptions of these sites are provided in Ohata et al. (2021a).

RESULTS

We define the year-to-year variation as the ratio of the yearly mean M_{BC} (COSMOS) to the mean M_{BC} (COSMOS) over the whole observation period. The year-to-year variation in AAE (MAC, 470 and 950 nm) ranged from 2% to 6.3% at the different sites. These AAE (MAC, 470 and 950 nm) values closely resembled AAE (MAC, λ) values, with mean values of 0.93, 0.88, 0.87, 0.86, and 1.2 at Alert, Barrow (AE 31), Barrow (AE 33), Ny-Ålesund, and Pallas, respectively. The weak spectral variation in MAC (AE, λ) at Arctic sites suggests that the contribution of non-BC or light-absorbing aerosols like dust or BrC was relatively small, although this wasn't quantitatively assessed. Additionally, BC particle characteristics, including size distribution, refractive index, shape, and mixing state, can influence AAE. BC in the Arctic is often thickly coated, with a shell/core ratio of about 1.4 and a median diameter of around 0.1 μm . Coated

Figure 1: Time series of yearly averaged MAC_{cor} (AE, 590 nm) and MBC (COSMOS) for the four sites in the Arctic. The dashed line show the mean

BC tends to exhibit decreasing AAE as the geometric mean diameter (GMD) increases. The observed AAE of approximately 1.0 at a GMD of 0.1 μm aligns reasonably with the average AAE seen at the four sites. However, specific factors affecting AAE differences at Pallas require further investigation, especially considering different aerosol properties and higher biogenic aerosol levels during the summer. To gain more insights into the higher AAE at Pallas, detailed measurements of BC size distribution and mixing state at that location are necessary. Across the entire study period, the average MAC_{cor} (AE, 590 nm) and MAC_{cor} (AE, 880 nm) at the four sites showed limited spatial variability, about 11%. Annual mean MAC_{cor} (AE, 590 nm) and MAC_{cor} (AE, 880 nm) remained relatively stable, with variations between 10.1 to 12.8 $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$ and 7.2 to 9.0 $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$, respectively. Year-to-year MAC_{cor} (AE) variability averaged about 15%, except at Barrow, where it reached up to 18%. The relative year-to-year variability of MAC_{cor} (AE, 590 nm) ranged from 1.8% to 18.2% at Alert, Barrow, Ny-Ålesund, and Pallas over the entire study period.

CONCLUSIONS

We initially derived babs (AE) with $C_0 = 3.5$, finding strong correlations ($r^2 = 0.74\text{--}0.96$) between babs (AE) and MBC (COSMOS) at all four sites throughout the study period. This indicates that BC dominates light absorption in submicron particles. The high correlations validate the reliability of MAC (AE) estimation via the babs (AE)–MBC (COSMOS) correlation method. At Barrow, MAC (AE 31) and MAC (AE 33) values were similar, suggesting C_0 independence from the AE model. MAC_{cor} (AE) estimated using this method at 590 nm ranged from 10.1 to 12.8 $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$ (1-h data) and 10.2 to 12.9 $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$ (24-h data) across the four sites. The annual average MAC_{cor} (AE) at these sites was $11.3 \pm 1.24 \text{ m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$ (590 nm) and $7.76 \pm 0.73 \text{ m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$ (880 nm), displaying a slight 11% spatial variability—a novel Arctic finding. Yearly MAC_{cor} (AE) variation at 590 nm reached 18%, contributing to an overall MAC (AE) variability of approximately 21% during the study. Our $11.4 \pm 1.2 \text{ m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$ (590 nm) MAC (AE) value in the Arctic aligns closely (within 3%) with previously published data using $AAE = 1$ and C_0 correction, endorsing C_0 's importance in AE data correction for MAC (AE) reproducibility. We further compared MAC values of BC among Arctic instruments, adjusted to 590 nm. The mean $\pm 1\sigma$ MAC (590 nm) value among instruments was 11.9 ± 0.70 , indicating a minimal 6% variation, reinforcing the $C_0 = 3.5$ choice for AE.

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EFFECT OF VENTILATION ON INDOOR AIR QUALITY OF RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS

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Keywords: Indoor Air Quality (IAQ), indoor and outdoor PM_{2.5}, I/O ratios and ventilation.

INTRODUCTION

Most of the research around the world has been on outdoor air pollution, but majority of people spend more than 90% of their times indoor, thus fine particles (PM_{2.5}) generated during various activities like cooking, smoking, cleaning, etc., becomes important for health assessment studies (Abbatt and Wang, 2020). The concentration and chemical composition of indoor air depends not only on its indoor emission rate, but also on the rate at which it is being transported from outdoors to indoors, and the rates at which it is scavenged by indoor surfaces, consumed by indoor chemistry, and removed by ventilation or filtration. Although these pollutants are often present in low concentrations in buildings, long-term exposure can cause significant risks to human health (Tran *et al.*, 2020). In this regard, the objective of this study is to estimate the extent to which outdoor-originating particles and indoor-emitted particles contribute to the residential indoor PM_{2.5} concentration.

METHODS

The study was conducted at a residential area in the city Agra (27°10' N, 78°05' E), Uttar Pradesh in India from the period between May 2022 and April 2023. The city generally experiences high atmospheric pollution load in which 60% is mainly due to vehicular pollution (Pipal *et al.*, 2022). The study site represents an urban residential area (near Kendriya Hindi Sansthan). Simultaneous indoor (living room) and outdoor (rooftop) PM_{2.5} were collected at 5 residential homes for 24 h using Envirotech APM 821 on quartz fibre filter with a flow rate of 3L/min. The samples were collected five times a week. A total of 240 samples for both indoor and outdoor were collected for each home, for field blanks, filter cassette were loaded with a filter paper and left at both indoor and outdoor sites individually for 24 hours. The infiltration of particles as a result of ventilation was then studied using I/O ratios and the infiltration factor model.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Overall, the levels of PM_{2.5} reported in this work were comparable to the previous studies. The average mean 24 h PM_{2.5} concentration when the windows are open and closed was found to be $82.9 \pm 17.2 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $76.1 \pm 13.6 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ respectively, whereas that of outdoor was $69.8 \pm 8.7 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ during the study period. On comparing the annual averages of PM_{2.5} concentrations with the National Ambient Air-Quality Standards of India ($40 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ annual average), they were found to be 1.5-2 times higher both in indoors as well as outdoors. Figure 1 represents the mean average concentration of indoor and outdoor PM_{2.5} along with the meteorological parameters (temperature and relative humidity). It can be clearly seen that the concentration were higher when the windows are kept open (higher than outdoor) indicating transport of outdoor generated particles to indoor (Ji and Zhao, 2015). Similar results have been reported in both rural and urban residential houses with high indoor concentrations by (Talbot *et al.*, 2017; Massey *et al.*, 2012).

Meteorological conditions also have predominant effect on PM_{2.5} concentrations. Therefore, the effect of meteorological parameters: temperature and relative humidity was also examined, both indoors and outdoors. The average temperature, indoors and outdoors, was $28.6 \pm 2.2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $32.6 \pm 3.6 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively, whereas RH was $45 \pm 8.5\%$ and $41 \pm 7.2\%$, indoors and outdoors, respectively. Low temperature and high RH may be responsible for enhanced PM concentrations during winter season. Meteorological parameters such as, wind speed and direction had a significant impact on the concentration of particles. The influence of wind direction was more than that of wind speed, more the wind speed higher will be the infiltration of particles (PM_{2.5}) from outdoor to indoor (Li *et al.*, 2023).

The indoor/outdoor ratio (I/O) is a tool for assessing the disparity between indoor and outdoor concentration levels as well as a sign of indoor sources and outdoor particle infiltration (Abdel Salam, 2021). In our study, the mean I/O ratio when windows were kept closed and opened came out to be 1.15 and 1.20 respectively. It was observed that the I/O ratios were higher than 1 during the whole study period indicating the dominance indoor sources. This means that outside penetration of PM_{2.5} dominated the overall exchange, owing to the relatively severe air pollution. Although indoor and outdoor have different sources, their strength is similar therefore the I/O ratio is similar.

Figure 1: Average mean 24 h concentration of Indoor PM_{2.5} when windows are open and closed along with the meteorological parameters temperature (Temp) and relative humidity (RH) indoor (I) and outdoor (O).

CONCLUSIONS

The present study showed that the contribution of outdoor-originating PM_{2.5} to the indoor PM_{2.5} concentration dominates. When the windows are open, the indoor particle source contribution is lower than when the windows are closed, and it varies little with the strength of the indoor source emission, as outdoor-originating particles contribute the most to indoor PM_{2.5} concentration.

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IMPROVEMENT OF A GC-MS PROTOCOL FOR DETECTING AND ANALYSING
DICARBOXYLIC ACIDS (DCAS) IN AMBIENT AEROSOLS IN INDIA

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Keywords: Dicarboxylic acids; Organic molecular markers; Water-soluble organic compounds; Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry

INTRODUCTION

Global climate change is a serious problem, and increasing concentrations of hygroscopic aerosols play a major role in the changing precipitation patterns and changes in radiative forcing. Dicarboxylic acids (DCAs) have been known to act as cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) and ice nuclei (IN), which can alter rainfall patterns due to their propensity to absorb moisture and hygroscopic properties. As byproducts of the ozonolysis and photochemical oxidation of hydrocarbons, DCAs are predominantly secondary processes that contribute to their presence in the atmosphere (Sempéré & Kawamura, 2003). Dicarboxylic acids are valuable organic molecular markers for a variety of anthropogenic and biogenic sources. Hence, their study in ambient aerosol samples has attracted growing interest.

METHODS

Dicarboxylic Acids (DCAs) are now more easily extracted from aerosol samples that were gathered using quartz filters. A variety of organic solvents with different levels of polarity were used for this optimisation. Using an innovative extraction device called the Energised Dispersive Guided Extractor (EDGE), by CEM Corporation, USA, we performed extraction experiments under various temperature and pressure conditions to evaluate the efficacy of these solvents.

A derivatization step was required before performing a Gas Chromatography (GC) study because of the compound's strong polarity and the low amounts (about 1 ng/m³) of dicarboxylic acids. We used TMCS (trimethylchlorosilane) + BSTFA (N, O-bis-(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide) as the derivatizing reagent for this purpose. In order to achieve the best conversion rates, we extensively optimised the reaction parameters, such as temperature and the ratio of BSTFA to TMCS.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Dicarboxylic acids (DCAs) were extracted from quartz filters using three distinct solvents at various temperatures and times. The derivatization reagent BSTFA + TMCS was chosen for the procedure in this study. At 50 °C, 75 °C, and 100 °C with hold times of 30, 60, and 90 minutes, the derivatization reaction was carried out. According to the findings, the reaction's best results were obtained when it was carried out at 75 °C for 90 minutes. Additionally, two distinct compositions of BSTFA + 1% TMCS and BSTFA + 10% TMCS were used to carry out the reaction. Notably, it was shown that using 10% TMCS resulted in better conversions when BSTFA (10 µL or 20 µL) was added in lesser amounts. However, the impact of a higher percentage of catalyst on the reaction diminished as the amount of BSTFA increased (30 µL and 40 µL).

This proposed protocol's extraction efficiency was determined to be reliable and equivalent to the outcomes of other investigations. As shown in Figure 1, this procedure was effectively used to assess DCAs in actual aerosol ambient air samples.

Figure 1. DCAs concentration was analysed from the ambient aerosol samples by applying the proposed detection method.

CONCLUSIONS

An improved method for identifying lower homologues of saturated aliphatic diacids (C_3 – C_{10}) in aerosol samples. Our enhanced Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GCMS) method in Selected Ion Monitoring (SIM) mode yields accurate and symmetrical peaks for these diacids, allowing their identification in 43 minutes with great resolution. Using the CEM Edge instrument and properly selected solvents, all targeted C_3 - C_{10} diacids have been extracted with above 80% efficiency. This standardised GCMS approach for dicarboxylic acid detection makes it easier to evaluate aerosol samples quickly and reliably.

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ANALYSIS OF CHARGING PARAMETERS OF ELECTROSTATIC AEROSOL NEUTRALISER (EAN) AT DIFFERENT CHARGED CONDITIONS

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INTRODUCTION

Electrostatic Aerosol Neutralizer (Make: TOPAS, Model: EAN581) is used to condition the pre-charges of aerosols by exposing the aerosols to bipolar ion field in the mixing chamber generated from two independent ionization heads operated at high voltages of opposite polarity. EAN581 is also be used as a unipolar charger if operated with one ionization head at a time and as a bipolar charger if used two ionisation heads created with certain possible asymmetry in bipolar ion concentrations. The charge level of aerosol obtained from EAN is highly depend on the charging parameter for the given size distribution of particles. This study is conducted to derive the unknown charging parameters of EAN i.e., bipolar ion asymmetry ratio and n_i*t product in the selected bipolar and unipolar charged conditions, respectively. This study presents the methodology of deriving the unknown charging parameters of EAN using the aerosol charge measurements of Electrical Low-Pressure Impactor (ELPI®) and its limitations. This study shows the sensitivity of charging parameters on the charge level of particles in different charged conditions.

METHODS

PAO (Poly Alpha Olefin) aerosols are used to characterise the EAN. PAO aerosols are generated using Laskin nozzle generator (M/S ATI instruments, USA). The aerosols are passed through EAN581 (M/S Topas, Germany) to get them charged. The charged aerosols are simultaneously measured using ELPI® as shown in schematic Fig.1. EAN is operated with 4 different voltage pairs in separate tests to arrive at different charged conditions with distinct net charge levels of aerosols (Pujala et al., 2023a). The voltage pairs (in kV) are (3.25, -6.7) and (3.7, -4) for two different bipolar charged conditions and (0, -6.5) and (6, 0) for two different unipolar charged conditions.

Fig. 1. Schematic of characterisation of EAN charger.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The PAO aerosol consists of polydisperse sub-micrometre size spherical particles with insignificant net charges ~ 0.02 per particle acquired during generation (Pujala *et al.*, 2023b). The ELPI has 13 impactor stages spanning the size range of 0.007 to 10 μm . The ELPI measures the mean charge–size distributions of particles (i.e. j_i Vs d_i) during its internal charger OFF condition. ELPI charger voltage and currents are 4.7 ± 0.1 kV and 1 μA , respectively, and operated at 10 lpm flow rate. The positive ion concentration of ELPI internal charger n_i is $\sim 1.9 \times 10^{14} /\text{m}^3$, and the residence time t is ~ 0.44 s. So, the n_i*t product is $\sim 8.36 \times 10^{13}$ s/m^3 (Moisio, 1999). The PAO aerosol generation rate is $\sim 1 \times 10^{10} /\text{m}^3\text{s}$, which is less than the n_i*t product of ELPI charger by nearly four orders. The ELPI charger produces sufficient positive current to neutralize the existing charges and redefine the charges as per the ELPI charger efficiencies in the tested conditions. The uncertainty in measured net charge levels is

within $\pm 3\%$.

Initial charge size distribution: The measured mean charge-size distributions of PAO aerosols in 4 selected voltage pair conditions are shown in Fig. 2. In unipolar charged conditions, the charge level j_i increases with particle size d_i and reaches up to -42.8 ± 1.7 and $+34.1 \pm 1.06$ for the particles of size $2.26 \mu\text{m}$ at the voltage pairs of (0, -6.5) and (6, 0), respectively as depicted in Fig. 2 (blue and orange bars). In case of bipolar voltage pairs and (3.25, -6.7) and (3.7, -4), the particles have a net negative and positive charges respectively as shown in Fig. 2 (grey and yellow bars). This represents the bipolar ion ASR < 1 at (3.25, -6.7) and ASR > 1 at (3.7, -4) as shown in Fig. 3. In both bipolar charging cases, the j_i reaches up to -29.9 ± 0.62 and 14.2 ± 0.4 for $2.26 \mu\text{m}$ particles at the voltage pairs of (3.25, -6.7) and (3.7, -4), respectively. The j_i values of bipolar-charged aerosols are considerably lesser than the unipolar-charged conditions due to the cancellation of the opposite charges.

Fig. 2. The charge size distributions.

Fig. 3. Charging parameters.

Derived charge parameters of EAN: In the mixing chamber of EAN, the aerosol gets charged by diffusion charging in both bipolar and unipolar charged conditions. As the mixing chamber is grounded, field charging process is absent. Harrison equation is used for bipolar charged conditions to derive the bipolar ion asymmetry ratio. The diffusion charging theory equation is used to derive n_i*t product in unipolar charged conditions (Pujala *et al.*, 2022). The charge parameters are derived from each j_i and particle size d_i values as shown in Fig. 3. The bipolar ion ASR is observed to be varying with size ranges from 0.67 to 0.83 at (3.25, -6.7), resulting in a net negative charge. The ASR ranges from 1.1 to 1.2 at (3.7, -4), resulting in a positive net charge. The unipolar charging parameter n_i*t derived from different size particles is varied considerably in the range 1.54×10^{11} to $1.12 \times 10^{12} \text{ s/m}^3$ at (0, -6.5) & 5.4×10^{11} to $4 \times 10^{10} \text{ s/m}^3$ at (6, 0).

CONCLUSIONS

The measured charge parameters in both bipolar and unipolar charged conditions are observed to have significant spread varying with particle size. The diffusion charging phenomenon is primarily depends on particle size. A particle of a particular size can carry different quantities of charges if inhomogeneity in ion concentration prevails inside the mixing chamber of EAN. However this issue may not be significant at the tested flow rates of aerosol though EAN. This could be majorly due to the polydisperse nature of PAO aerosols and resolution of ELPI with 13 size classes. Each stage gets deposited with particles of a specific size range and hence has spread in mean charge levels where as specified cut-off sizes are used to estimate the charging parameter. Further study using the series based DMA and ELPI technique is under progress.

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**AEROSOL PROFILING OF UTLS REGION USING A PASSIVE REMOTE SENSING
TECHNIQUE**

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Keywords: Aerosol, UTLS, Twilight sounding, aerosol vertical distribution

INTRODUCTION

The twilight photometry is a passive remote sensing technique, involving ground-based photometry of the twilight sky brightness, is used to derive the vertical distribution of atmospheric aerosols in the Earth's atmosphere up to stratospheric altitudes. Twilight is the optical phenomena in the earth's atmosphere appear when the sun is near the horizon. The main factor controlling the course of the twilight phenomena is sunlight scattering of sunlight in the earth's atmosphere. The most important circumstance, which gives an altitudinal sounding ability to the twilight event is that only a comparatively thin layer of air above the earth's shadow contributes maximum to the sky brightness at every given moment. The logarithmic gradient of twilight sky intensity (q , also known as scattering coefficient) at a fixed angle above the horizon where the earth's shadow traverses different layers of the atmosphere, gives information about the vertical distribution of aerosols in the atmosphere (Padma Kumari et al. 2008). The scattered radiation received from any part of the sky is primarily due to the light scattered by illuminated molecules and aerosols. Any rapid change in their concentration with height will lead to a corresponding change in illumination at the ground. Thus the scattered intensity is assumed to be proportional to the particle number density.

METHODS

The instrument twilight photometer has been designed and developed indigenously at IITM (Padma Kumari et al., 2018). The observations were taken during morning and evening twilight period at Pune. Each twilight sky-brightness record contains information on scattered light intensity at a height corresponding to the lowest layer above the Earth's shadow boundary. The observation time is converted to solar zenith angle Z , which in turn is used in the computation of shadow height of the earth. The q parameter provides information about aerosols. Thus, the earth's shadow height and the q are the important parameters of twilight sounding method (Padmakumari et a., 2006, 2008).

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Using twilight photometer, aerosol vertical profiles are derived in terms of logarithmic gradient of intensity (q). Figure 1 shows the aerosol vertical profiles up to 50 km during the clear sky periods of March, April and May 2021. It is noticed from the figure that the value of q decreases with increasing height, implying decrease of aerosol concentration with height. In the lower troposphere sharp decrease is observed up to 10 km. Above 10 km the scattering intensity seems to be changing very little, showing almost constant concentration up to the tropopause. From the tropopause to about 30 km (lower stratosphere), the subsequent increase in q value is observed due to the presence of stratospheric aerosol layer. This stratospheric aerosol layer is also well known as Junge layer. Thus, q is the most effective parameter for distinguishing the aerosol layers or to reveal the stratified structure of the atmospheric aerosols.

Figure 1: Vertical distribution of atmospheric aerosols (upper troposphere (UT) and lower stratosphere (LS)).

CONCLUSIONS

The instrument twilight photometer has been designed and developed indigenously for monitoring the vertical distribution of atmospheric aerosols up to stratospheric altitudes. The system is simple and inexpensive based on passive remote sensing technique and hence can be operated continuously for monitoring the day-to-day variability of the aerosol profiles. The most effective way of retrieving the aerosol layer is by logarithmic gradient of scattered intensity (q). Thus, the twilight sounding method is the most efficient passive technique used to study the aerosol vertical distribution in UTLS region and the variability of stratospheric aerosol layer.

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ASSESSING BIASES AND UNCERTAINTIES IN BLACK CARBON MEASUREMENTS OVER INDIA: AN EVALUATION OF COMMONLY USED PHOTOMETER IN INDIA

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Keywords: Black Carbon, Mass Absorption Cross-Section, Aethalometer, COSMOS

INTRODUCTION

Accurate measurement of black carbon (BC), a significant air pollutant, is essential for a thorough understanding of its impacts on both human health and the environment. There are three main approaches to measuring BC: optical absorption, evolved carbon, and the laser-induced incandescent method. When it comes to continuous and long-term BC assessment, real-time photometers based on the optical absorption technique, such as COSMOS and Aethalometer, are the preferred choice due to their ease of use and high temporal resolution. However, it is important to note that the optical absorption approach is not a direct method; it involves converting optical absorbance data from photometers into BC mass using a calibration constant known as the mass absorption cross section (MAC). The MAC value can vary significantly between different locations and is influenced by the composition and structure of the aerosol particles. Historically, all BC investigations in Delhi relied on data obtained from different version of a specific photometer i.e., Aethalometer. Furthermore, all BC measurements in Delhi have used the manufacturer-recommended MAC value for the Aethalometer, which has the potential to introduce inaccuracies. Given these considerations, the current research conducted at an urban site (CSIR-NPL) in Delhi aims to determine the MAC value for the Aethalometer model AE-31, which has been commonly utilized in previous studies.

METHODS

In a typical optical photometer used for BC measurement, the light absorption due to aerosol (denoted by coefficient β_{abs}) is converted into BC mass concentration (M_{BC} in units of $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) using following equation.

$$M_{\text{BC}} = \beta_{\text{abs}} / \text{MAC}$$

In current study, above equation is used to derive the MAC value by using simple linear regression analysis between β_{abs} of AE-31 and BC mass derived parallelly using a reference instrument. The MAC value of instrument under test can be derived as the slope of linear regression between β_{abs} of instrument under test and M_{BC} of reference instrument. The photometer COSMOS, which is incredibly accurate, serves as the reference device for the current investigation. In COSMOS, incoming aerosol is heated up to 300°C to remove interferences due to non-refractory aerosol. As a result, the mass absorption cross section (MAC value, a calibration constant used to convert BC of COSMOS remains relatively stable despite change in site and emission sources. Therefore, COSMOS has been used as a reference instrument of calibrating MAC values of different photometers in previous studies (Ohata et al., 2020).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1 displays the linear regression graph illustrating the relationship between β_{abs} of AE-31 and M_{BC} concurrently measured by COSMOS throughout the entire month of March 2023. The slope of the linear

regression is determined using hourly averaged data from this one-month period. The strong correlation observed between the datasets of both instruments is a crucial prerequisite for calculating the MAC value. The derived value of MAC for the AE-31 (590) is $49.2 \text{ m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$, 50% higher than the manufacturer's recommended value of $24.8 \text{ m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$.

Figure 1. Regression plot between β_{abs} measurements of AE-31 and simultaneously measured M_{BC} using COSMOS

CONCLUSIONS

Initial examination indicates that the measurements of BC concentrations in Delhi, as determined by the Aethalometer, may have been overestimated. This overestimation is likely attributed to the heightened aerosol absorption resulting from the presence of other light absorbing aerosols. To fully understand the influence of change in emission sources, it is imperative to conduct more comprehensive research into the behaviour of the MAC value.

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ASSESSMENT OF RESIDENTIAL OUTDOOR PARTICULATE MATTER CONCENTRATIONS DURING DIWALI USING LOW-COST SENSORS IN MUMBAI, INDIA

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Keywords: Diwali, PM_x, LCS, regulatory stations, urban area

INTRODUCTION

Diwali, the festival of lights, is celebrated in almost all parts of India. Several cities in India witnessed a significant rise in air pollution levels during the Diwali festival due to the use of firecrackers. However, most of our understanding of the impact of firecrackers on atmospheric air quality is based on regulatory stations' data. Little data on firecrackers' impact on residential outdoor air quality in urban areas is available. During festive periods, such as Diwali, people spend most of their time at home, hence, it is essential to estimate household-level particulate matter (PM) exposures due to firecrackers used during such festivals.

METHODS

The air quality assessment during pre- and post-Diwali days was done on 5 consecutive days in October 2022. 24-hour PM_x was measured outside 7 homes distributed in different neighbourhoods in Mumbai using low-cost PM sensors (LCS) deployed in their outdoor surrounding such as balconies. Atmos (Respirer Living Sciences, Pune, India) devices were used, and the collected one-minute data was aggregated hourly and further used for analysis.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The mean \pm SD outdoor PM₁ (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀) levels during Pre-Diwali and Post Diwali days were 54.1 ± 20.2 (79.6 ± 29.9 , 110.3 ± 36.7) & 85.1 ± 34.5 (132.1 ± 60.6 , 144.2 ± 63.4) respectively, whereas on the day of Diwali, the PM₁ (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀) levels were 98.8 ± 36.3 (154.9 ± 66.6 , 174.3 ± 70.9) exhibiting significant differences among pre-, during and post- Diwali days ($p < 0.05$) (see Figure 1). However, no significant difference was observed in PM_x during and post-Diwali days, likely due to residual firecrackers burning and meteorological differences. The average PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀ ratios on pre- and post-Diwali days were 0.72, 0.88 & 0.91, respectively, indicating a higher fraction of smaller particles due to festive firecrackers use. The average PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ concentrations exceeded the CPCB permissible limits (60 and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively) on all the days.

On Diwali day, the average PM_x concentration during the night, when most of the firecrackers are burst, was 56% higher than the daytime average PM_x concentration, whereas on the pre-and post-Diwali days it was 36% & 37% higher than the daytime average levels, respectively.

The average PM_{2.5} concentration varied significantly between traffic-exposed and urban background homes during Diwali and Non-Diwali days with, traffic-exposed homes showing ~ 1.5 times higher average PM_{2.5} than background homes on Diwali & Pre-Diwali days and ~ 1.8 times on the post-Diwali days.

The average PM_{2.5} concentration measured by LCS was ~ 1.5 times higher than the concentration measured by CPCB monitors ($p < 0.05$). However, no significant difference was observed in average PM₁₀ concentration between LCS and CPCB monitors. The differences can be attributed to the differences in measurement principles as well as the spatial differences and effect of local sources.

Figure 1. Variation in Particulate matter concentrations during pre- and post-Diwali 2022

CONCLUSIONS

The higher PM_x levels outside residences in Mumbai on Diwali day are due to the burning of firecrackers. The increment in PM_x concentration on the post-Diwali days is likely due to the residual firecracker activity and accumulation of the surrounding air from the previous Diwali day. The higher fraction of the PM_{2.5} in PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀ ratio and the increment in night-time PM_x indicate the release of fine particulate matter from the firecrackers burning. While the measurements from regulatory fixed-site stations and low-cost sensors cannot be directly compared, significant differences between the LCS and CPCB monitors are likely to indicate that the regulatory monitoring stations may not represent the true individual household exposure to particulate matter.

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RESULTS FROM EARLY PERFORMANCE TESTS OF A NEW PORTABLE AND NETWORKABLE BLACK CARBON MONITOR

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Keywords: BLACK CARBON, HEALTH AEROSOL, INSTRUMENTATION

INTRODUCTION

Black carbon (BC) is an aerosol produced primarily through anthropogenic combustion activities at a global rate of around 4-8 Tg/yr (Xu et al. 2021), representing an estimated 15% - 50% of global PM_{2.5} (Klimont et al. 2017). About 1 Tg/yr comes from Indian energy activities alone (IEA 2021). BC is strong a climate forcing agent (~ 0.88 W/m² or a 100-year GWP ~ 900x greater than CO₂) (Bond et al. 2013), but it is also short-lived in the atmosphere with residence time estimates on the range of a few days to weeks. This imbues BC with important implications for climate policy in India and abroad. The health effects and policy implications of exposure to BC are also substantial, with BC posing a potentially greater per-unit health risk than total PM_{2.5} (Li et al. 2016). About 60 million people live in BC hotspots in the Indo-Gangetic plain alone. In these megacities, approximately 62% of cardiovascular disease mortality is attributable to BC exposures (Verma et al. 2022). The needs for BC measurements and action-oriented quantification of actual personal exposures to BC by location and microenvironment are thus great.

To help address these needs, AethLabs has produced a lower-cost portable single-wavelength, SingleSpot™ microAethalometer: the AL30. The AL30 facilitates stationary, mobile, and personal monitoring with size and form factor similar to a deck of cards; built-in WiFi and remote data & device management; internal battery; temperature, relative humidity, pressure, and accelerometry sensors; and sample rate setpoints ranging from 1 – 300 seconds. The AL30 can operate between 25 – 250 mL/min to accommodate high concentration measurements and extended deployments. This work outlines key results from early internal performance testing, and includes data and results from limit of detection (LoD) testing and soot exposure experiments at various concentrations in a soot exposure chamber while collocated with several larger multi-wavelength BC monitors from the AethLabs MA-series, which employs standard attenuation-based BC measurement and has been characterized and validated in the literature.

METHODS

Preliminary LoD testing was conducted under stationary use at 250 mL/min flow for 1 AL30 device, which was allowed to operate for an extended duration in a climate-controlled room with a Whatman 6722-5000 VACU-GUARD near-HEPA filter attached to its inlet. LoD values are reported using overlapping Allan deviation (1 σ), as used in previous BC monitor detection limit work (e.g., Asmi et al. 2021), for data collected at 1s, 60s, and 300s. Performance of an AL30 device was assessed during 3 concentration-ramping tests in our internal soot exposure chamber (Shlipak et al. 2023). Collocated performance is reported for 1 AL30, 3 MA200 units, and 3 MA350 units (AethLabs, San Francisco, CA) operating at 100 mL/min (~ 68- 80 mL/min through the SingleSpot™). AL30 SingleSpot™ performance was compared to SingleSpot™ and DualSpot® performance of the MA instruments to evaluate relative filter loading effects.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Preliminary LoD (1 σ) values were 0.004, 0.024, and 0.544 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for 300s, 60s, and 1s, respectively. LoD stability was reached between ~ 4 - 7.5 min (Fig. 1). Allan deviation estimates noise-related effects; the LoD increase after ~ 450s in Fig. 1 is likely a product of systematic effects or drift and is not expected to represent a true increase in LoD at higher sample rates. 1hr LoD was assessed from 300s data at < 0.001 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Data used for LoD at 60s, 300s, and 1hr are shown in Fig. 1. Collocation data are shown in Figure 2. For SingleSpot™, AL30 showed strong agreement with MA units under low to moderate filter loading, with relatively smaller filter loading effects overall. Fig. 2 demonstrates sustained inter-device agreement prior to the onset of filter loading effects. During the middle peak (relevant to Indian BC concentrations), the AL30 reported a mean BC concentration of 12.0 (0.6) $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ while MA device means ranged from 11.2 –12.5 (0.5-0.7) $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for SingleSpot™ BC and from 10.0 – 12.3 (0.8-1.0) $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for filter-loading- compensated BC. The AL30's mass absorption cross-section value (σ_{MAC}) was preliminary at the time of analysis. σ_{MAC} represents the relationship between

measured attenuation and BC mass. There is no reference for optical BC measurement; τ_{MAC} is typically calculated experimentally by collocation with a validated instrument, such as an AethLabs microAeth. The preliminary nature of the AL30 τ_{MAC} value represents an important limitation of this analysis and, as such, bias could not be properly assessed at the time of analysis.

Fig. 1. Data (left) used for LoD calculations for the AL30 (e.g., right), and 1s Allan deviation plot (middle; log₁₀ axes).

Fig. 2. Collocation data for MA200, MA350, and AL30 instruments during soot exposure testing.

CONCLUSIONS

Early performance testing of the AL30 – a lower-cost, portable, and networkable BC monitor – demonstrates a low limit of detection and performance on par with its larger multi-wavelength counterpart, the MA-series, and with potential improvement over the MA-series in terms of a reduced rate of accrual of filter loading effects under typical operating conditions.

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DYNAMIC POLLUTION DETECTION AND CALIBRATION OF LOW-COST SENSORS FOR LOW AND HIGH CONCENTRATION REGIONS USING MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES

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Keywords: Air Quality Monitoring, Low-Cost Sensor, Local Air Quality Variation, Calibration Factor.

INTRODUCTION

Timely and accurate air quality monitoring is of paramount importance for assessing environmental health risks and enabling effective pollution management strategies. Traditional monitoring approaches like the Environmental Beta Attenuation Monitor (E-BAM) and High-Volume Sampler provide accurate measurements, but their deployment is limited due to high costs often results in spatial data gaps (Le et al., 2020). In contrast, low-cost sensors offer an economical solution for wider coverage, but their data quality necessitates validation. This study presents a comprehensive approach that combines the strengths of high-temporal-resolution low-cost sensors (PurpleAir- Plantower PMS 5003) and machine learning-based calibration using co-located E-BAM data in ambient condition.

METHODS

The low-cost sensor (LCS) was installed alongside the E-BAM at two distinct locations: one at Anand Vihar, Delhi, a highly polluted area, and the other near Powai CAQMS located at IIT Bombay, Mumbai, which is characterized as a low-pollution zone. The data was collected from February 2023 to August 2023 for both sites. The data were analysed using time series plot to understand the sudden change in pollution captured by LCS vs E-BAM. The Z-score method was used to remove the outlier prior to performing the machine learning modelling. The calibration study was performed using multiple machine learning algorithm for both sites using PM_{2.5} concentration obtained from E-BAM (reference) and LCS, also included the relative humidity (RH) and temperature (T) obtained from LCS. The previous studies found that RH & T are the crucial parameters for the LCS calibration (Lee et al., 2020; Liang, 2021; Aix et al., 2023). The algorithms used are Multiple Linear Regression (MLR), Random Forest (RF), K-Nearest Algorithm (KNN), Gradient boosting regression (GBR), and Support vector regression (SVR).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The result of time series plot showed that LCS very well captured the small period episodic event because of the high temporal resolution data (2-minutes). The PM_{2.5} concentration obtained from E-BAM did not capture the such events because of the low temporal resolution (1-hr average) data as shown in the Figure . The descriptive analysis of air quality data from both monitoring sites, indicates noteworthy differences shown in the Table 1 The mean concentration obtained by E-BAM & LCS for Delhi site (117.60±90.18 & 66.50±58.86 respectively) are significantly high as compared to Mumbai site (34.03±32.86 & 39.36±44.27 respectively). The result suggests that LCS are able to capture the trend nicely. However significant difference in the mean concentration observed at Delhi site compared to Mumbai site, which emphasize the requirement of different calibration factor for both the sites.

The various machine learning models were applied for developing calibration factors for both the sites as shown in Figure 2 for Mumbai site. The result showed that the Random Forest (RF) algorithm (R²-0.86 & RMSE-10.93) and Gradient Boosting Regression (GBR) algorithm (R²-0.85 & RMSE-10.92) perform better compared to all four considered model for Mumbai site. The Delhi site result showed that the Gradient Boosting Regression (GBR) algorithm (R²-0.64 & RMSE-25.00) performed better. The GBR

algorithm was found to more descriptive because of the lesser difference in the training and testing score, which avoids the overfitting of the model.

Table 1. Descriptive analysis of the reference instrument (BAM) & LCS (PurpleAir) for both site

Statistics	Powai, Mumbai		Anand Vihar, Delhi	
	PM _{2.5} E-BAM	PM _{2.5} LCS	PM _{2.5} E-BAM	PM _{2.5} LCS
Mean	34.03	39.36	117.60	66.50
Standard Deviation	32.86	44.27	90.18	58.86
Minimum	4.27	1.00	1.00	1.60
Maximum	214.84	473.74	780.50	489.43
Count	4433	4433	4077	4077

Figure 1. Time series plot of LCS (2-min & 1-hr) & BAM (1-hr).

Figure 2. Calibration result of LCS using multi machine learning model.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the integration of low-cost sensors (LCS) and reference instruments like the Environmental Beta Attenuation Monitor (E-BAM) showcased their complementary roles in air quality monitoring. LCS exhibited a unique capacity to capture the episodic pollution events due to their high temporal resolution. Moreover, machine learning-based calibration models were applied to correct the LCS data with reference measurements, enhancing their accuracy. The study's findings underline the potential of LCS in supplementing traditional monitoring networks, while the calibration process highlights the necessity of accurate calibration models. These insights contribute to advancing the field of air quality assessment, enabling more informed decision-making and proactive pollution management strategies.

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**DEVELOPMENT OF A NOBEL DEVICE TO ENHANCE AEROSOL REMOVAL EFFICIENCY
OF ANY NON-CONDUCTING AIR FILTER**

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Keywords: AEROSOL REMOVAL, AIR PURIFICATION, AIR QUALITY, AIR FILTRATION.

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution has become a major threat to human health as well as global climate. Estimated one out of 6 premature deaths are caused by pollution. In the 2015, 6.67 million premature deaths were caused by air pollution worldwide, which is almost 3.8 times higher than deaths caused by other types of pollutions (Fuller et al., 2022). Air pollution can cause various health problems including asthma, acute respiratory infection, cardiovascular & cardiopulmonary diseases, and lung cancer etc. Each increase of PM_{2.5} by 10 µg/m³ can be associated with increment of 24% cardiovascular diseases, 6% cardiopulmonary diseases and 8% lung cancer mortality. (Chen & Kan, 2008).

Present commercial air purifiers mainly consist of a high-efficiency particulate air (HEPA) filter to capture dust and submicron particles. HEPA filter is generally made up of glass fibers or polyester fibers, which are non-biodegradable. Whereas other biodegradable filters (like cotton fiber filter) are not as efficient as HEPA filters. The present work relates to a technology which can enhance the filtration efficiency of any filter it is used with. In this way, we can use not only cheap but biodegradable filters with almost comparable efficiency to HEPA filters. Also, this invention can enhance efficiency of already available air filters to achieve extremely purified air.

METHODS

The present invention essentially includes a conductive net that is sandwiched between filters, a negative air ionizer, a voltage multiplier, and an insulating covering. The material chosen for the conductive net was a metal net/mesh. All the open ends of metal net/mesh were sealed by plastic sealant. The metal net/mesh was sandwiched between two layers of cotton filters. Three types of filters were homemade using medical grade cotton wool. Before making the filters, the cotton wool was washed and dried. After drying, layers of cotton wool were taken out and compressed using a cloth iron. Filters were given the name F1, F2 & F3 with decreasing filter thickness. The conductive net/mesh was connected to the positive end of a voltage multiplier. The other (negative) end of the voltage multiplier is grounded for a continuous positive voltage supply. Figure 1(A) shows the arrangement for testing the effectiveness of present invention which includes a negative air ionizer upstream, the filter assembly constructed as described above, an aerosol spectrometer (GRIMM model 1.108), a flow meter and a suction pump. This assembly was manufactured in Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur. The testing was done for 7 days in 28 number of sets for each condition. Also, the variation of PM reading within each set was very small and hence can be ignored. Test was done under ambient atmospheric conditions.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The idea behind the filter assembly was to hold the static electric charge for long time with least losses so that it can transfer the electric static charge to the cotton (non-conductive) filter. The holding and transferring of electric static charge were confirmed using an electrostatic polarity detector. The intention behind the invention is to enhance the aerosol capturing efficiency of the low cost, biodegradable cotton filter. Figure 1(B) shows the increase in aerosol removal efficiency of filter F1 by using the above-described filter assembly. An increment in aerosol removal efficiency can be seen for

all size range of aerosol from 0.3 to

20 μm . The change in increase in efficiency for different particle size range might be caused by difference in the ability to hold charge by particle of each size, along with the difference in inertia of different sized particles to deviate from original path to be collected on filter fibre due to electrostatic attraction. The device is supposed to be worked with the voltage multiplier 'on', hence longevity of charge on filter was not tested. But in future while optimising the technology, the charge retention will surely be tested.

Figure 1: (A) Test setup for aerosol removal efficiency. (B) Test results of filter F1 @ 20 LPM flow rate.

CONCLUSION

In the present work, a successful development of a new technology to enhance the aerosol removal efficiency of a low cost, biodegradable and less efficient filter was achieved. The filter F1 with the presented assembly at 20 LPM has achieved more than 90% efficiency for particle size up to 0.8 μm with a simple cotton filter having a pressure drop of only 0.5mm H₂O (at 20 LPM air flow rate). This head loss is 4 times lesser than HEPA filter. This technique can be used to manufacture indoor or outdoor air filters using cheap filter material which are also biodegradable. Which will be helpful in removing aerosols from air to provide a cleaner and healthier environment.

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AEROSOL CHARACTERIZATION

CHANGING PATTERNS IN THE AEROSOLS OPTICAL, PHYSICAL, MORPHOLOGICAL AND CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OBSERVED USING MULTI-SENSOR MEASUREMENTS

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Keywords: AOD, MULTIVARIATE LINEAR REGRESSION, LONG-TERM TRENDS, MULTI-SENSOR DATASETS

INTRODUCTION

With the rapidly changing aerosol emissions due to the increase in urbanization, energy consumption, population density, and industrialization in the past two decades, there is an evolution of different aerosol properties that are yet not quantified properly. In this regard, numerous studies have been carried out to examine the trends in the rapidly changing aerosol loading using the total Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) parameter. But so far, no study has acknowledged its long-term implications through the combined Optical (Absorbing/ Scattering), Physical (Fine/ Coarse), Morphological (Non-spherical), and Chemical (Black carbon/ Dust/ Organic carbon /Sea salt/ Sulfate/ Polluted Dust/ Elevated Smoke) properties of the aerosols on a global scale. Not only the columnar but the presence of Elevated Aerosol Layers has also impacted the cloud dynamics and air quality by stabilizing the atmosphere (Wang et al., 2013). Therefore, a detailed analysis of a complete three-dimensional perspective of the long-term changes in all the aerosol properties still remains missing and hence is attempted in this study using multi source long-term data.

METHODOLOGY

The main aspect of this study involves the global estimates of long-term trends of all the aerosol properties using the multivariate linear regression trend model (Randel and Cobb, 1994), which separates the trend contributions from naturally occurring oscillations such as Semi-Annual Oscillations (SAO), Annual Oscillations (AO), Quasi-Biennial Oscillations (QBO), El-Niño southern oscillations (ENSO), and Solar Cycle (SC). The general expression for the model equation applied to the time-series of monthly averaged variables is given below:

$$T(t) = \alpha(t) + \beta(t)t + \gamma(t)QBO(t) + \delta(t)Solar(t) + \epsilon(t)ENSO(t) + residual_{fit}(t) \quad (1)$$

where, the coefficients α , β , γ , δ , and ϵ are determined at each grid using the harmonic expression. A detailed explanation of this equation is given by Gupta et al. (2022).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Before using the multi-source (i.e., ground-based (AERONET), space-borne (MODIS, MISR, CALIOP), and reanalysis (MERRA-2)) datasets, a detailed statistical comparison was made by estimating the correlation coefficient, root mean square error, mean absolute error and relative mean bias. After obtaining medium to high correlation values between ground-based and space-borne/ reanalysis AOD datasets, we could identify 8 hotspot Regions of Interest (RoI) where statistically significant increases or decreases in the total AOD values are observed, as shown in Figure 1. The major findings of these identified RoIs are discussed as follows:

- The major decrease (increase) in the total AOD values over North-Eastern America or NEA, South America or SAM, Europe or EU, North-Western Africa or NWA, and Eastern and Central China or ECC (Indian) regions are mainly in connection with the decrease (increase) in the fine-mode and scattering aerosols.
- A major increase in the total AOD values over the South African (SAF) region is the increase in absorbing and scattering aerosols. The highest percentage of aerosols contributing to an overall increase in total AOD values over the Middle East (ME) region are the coarse-mode and scattering aerosols.
- Interestingly, despite the overall increase in the total AOD values over the Indian region, we observed a slight decrease in the coarse-mode (Indo-Gangetic Plain or IGP and the Arabian Sea or AS), non-spherical (IGP, Central India or CI, South India or SI, AS, and Bay of Bengal or BoB), and absorbing (IGP and CI) aerosols, in recent years.

Figure 1. Region-wise long-term trends in the aerosol (a). Optical, Physical and Morphological, and (b) columnar and vertically distributed Chemical properties.

(d). The detailed analysis showed that there exists an overall higher contribution of aerosols persisting in the free troposphere region which in turn can have a long-term effect on climate due to their higher residence time, particularly absorbing aerosols.

CONCLUSIONS

This study has made serious efforts in understanding the changing patterns in columnar and vertical distribution of aerosol properties using two decades (i.e., 2001-2020) of multi-source datasets globally. Here, we could analyse that the overall reason behind the decrease in the total AOD values over the developed countries such as NEA is exactly the cause of the overall increasing trend in the total AOD values over the developing country like India i.e., increase in sulfate aerosols. Also, there exists increase in the contribution of anthropogenic aerosols at the EAL altitudes as well. From this, we can anticipate that the developing regions like South-East Asia (with high population density) and the South Africa (which exhibited increasing trends due to increasing aerosols) regions can also call for similar kinds of mitigation strategies, which can lead to a drastic improvement in the air quality and can also lower the risks of premature deaths and serious health effects as well.

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AEROSOL DISTRIBUTION OVER THE NORTHERN INDIAN OCEAN THROUGH SHIP-BORNE MEASUREMENTS AND MODEL-DERIVED OUTCOMES

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Keywords: Aerosols, CAMS, MEERA-2, Chemical composition, North Indian Ocean

INTRODUCTION

Natural and anthropogenic processes in South and Southeast Asia strongly influence the North Indian Ocean (NIO), however, studies combining observations and modelling of climate-forcers remain very few in this part of the world's ocean. To fill this gap, we performed ship-borne aerosol measurements during different months from October 2015 to September 2021 in part of ocean either side of the Indian peninsula (Arabian Sea and Bay of Bengal) and evaluated results from the global reanalysis models (Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) and Modern-Era Retrospective Analysis for Research and Applications, Version 2 (MERRA-2)) (Chutia et al., 2022).

METHODS

Aerosol samples were collected on cruise campaigns over the Arabian sea (AS) and Bay of Bengal (BoB) on pre-baked Tissu-quartz filters using a high-volume sampler with PM₁₀ inlet at a flow rate of 1.1 m³/min. This filter piece was leached with Milli-Q water and used for the analyses of water-soluble cations and anions (Kaushik et al., 2021). Also, in this study, MERRA-2 and CAMS reanalyses data set have been used which are not validated with near-surface observations in the North Indian Ocean (NIO). These global reanalysis models (CAMS and MERRA-2) assimilate and blend observations from satellite and ground-based instruments to provide a consistent 2d/3d/4d state. Several satellite datasets including bias-corrected AOD, aerosol species profile, species concentration is assimilated along with ground-based aerosol measurements to produce the reanalysis products (Jin et al., 2022).

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The distributions of PM₁₀, sulfate and dust are seen to be qualitatively similar between CAMS and MERRA-2 over the Indian Ocean, but the concentrations exhibit substantial differences. In addition, the variability in sulfate, dust, and PM₁₀ concentrations over the Bay of Bengal (BoB) was reasonably captured (e.g., $r \sim 0.8$ for sulfate). However, the sulfate concentrations were typically underestimated by CAMS but overestimated by the MERRA-2. Notably, the model also shows a stronger limitation in reproducing high-dust ($> 10 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) conditions over this region. Similar pattern was also reported in AS region for MERRA-2 ($r = 0.39$) but the correlation was not that good in AS region as compared to BoB. Cams showed poor correlation with the measured dust in all the scenarios ($r = -0.16$). Further analyses using air mass trajectories over the region are being conducted. The study would serve as a reference for future applications of reanalysis datasets over this region and will help understand the impacts of aerosols on the climate and biogeochemical cycle over the Indian Ocean.

CONCLUSIONS

MERRA-2 and CAMS performed poorly in estimation of PM₁₀ in the oceanic region of both AS and BoB. Both the model also performed poor in estimating various parameters including Dust, Sea salt for the AS region. Moreover, relatively comparative results were reported for the BoB region than AS. Our study suggests that reanalyses data from MERRA-2 and CAMS require further more rigorous validation with online monitoring stations over the oceanic region before taking into use in the estimation of air quality monitoring.

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IDENTIFICATION AND PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF MICROPLASTICS IN MARINE AEROSOLS OVER THE NORTHEAST ARABIAN SEA

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Keywords: AEROSOLS, MICROPLASTICS, ARABIAN SEA.

INTRODUCTION

Microplastics (MPs) in the atmosphere (Pandey *et al.*, 2022) can get transported from their source/emission regions to remote continental and ocean ecosystems (Materić *et al.*, 2021; Allen *et al.*, 2022). Despite the increased scientific interest, fundamental questions and issues remain unresolved, particularly in the field of aerosols. Due to the inconsistencies in the sampling and processing of MPs, it is difficult to analyze the spatial and temporal patterns of these contaminants. Hence, there is a need to develop a comprehensive sampling and processing methodology for future investigations. The current study is to demonstrate a robust methodology for extracting MPs from depth filters and characterizing those MPs by using stereo-zoom microscopes, fluorescence spectroscopy, and micro-Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (μ -FTIR). Moreover, this is the first study focusing on MP distribution and characterization in the atmosphere, particularly in marine aerosols over the Arabian Sea.

METHODS

In this study, aerosols were collected on quartz fibre filters by using total suspended particulate sampler at a constant flow rate. The sampler was set up on the terrace of CSIR-National Institute of Oceanography, Goa (15.45°N, 73.20°E) building at the height of ~56 m from the ground level by operating the sampler for 24-hours. Four samples from two different years (March 2016 and November 2020) were processed to extract MPs from depth filters. For the physical characterization of MPs, stereo-zoom and fluorescence microscopy were used. Polymeric composition was confirmed by μ -FTIR.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The observed MPs were classified into three distinct morphotypes, namely fibres, fragments and films. Furthermore, the abundance of all morphotypes was found higher for density separation (DS) in comparison to without density separation (WDS). The average total abundance of MPs was found to be 1.30 ± 0.12 n/m³ in 2016 and 1.46 ± 0.14 n/m³ in 2020 samples. During this study, fibres were found to be the dominant species with a contribution of 40-41% among all the MPs, followed by fragments and films with 31% and 28%, respectively, in 2016 and 35% and 25%, respectively in 2020. Maximum number of fibres was found in the range of 401-800 μ m (33%) followed by films 81-160 μ m (36%) and fragments 0-40 μ m (36%) for both the years. This study showed the dominance of black 28%, transparent 22%, and blue 17% coloured

MPs, irrespective of the years. In total, 10 types of polymers were observed during 2016 and 2020. MPs consist of Polyvinyl chloride (PVC) 31%, Polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) 24%, Polyester (PES) 15%, Styrene butyl methacrylate (SBMA) 11%, Polyacetal (POM) 9%, Polyarylate (PAR) 3%, Polyurethane (PUR) 2%, Acrylonitrile (AN) 2%, Epoxy resin (ER) 2% and Polyvinyl alcohol (PVAL) 1%.

CONCLUSIONS

Fibres, films and fragments are the three types of morphotypes observed in this study with the dominant contribution of fibres from during both years 2016 and 2020. Higher abundance of MPs observed for DS subsamples in contrast to WDS subsamples suggests density separation technique is a better and more robust methodology for MPs extraction for aerosol samples. This study shows the dominance of black and transparent (50%) coloured MPs among all detected MPs. Chemical characterization of MPs indicates the dominance of PVC and PMMA among various polymers present in this study which might have an implication towards the surface water biogeochemical processes.

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EFFECT OF TITANIA NANO-ADDITIVES ON THE PARTICULATE MATTER INCLUDING ULTRA-FINE PARTICLE EMISSIONS OF A COMPRESSION IGNITION ENGINE

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Keywords: Diesel Engine, Nano-additives, Particulate Matter, Ultra-fine Particulate Matter.

INTRODUCTION

Particulate matter (PM) emissions from diesel engines pose severe environmental and health issues, necessitating comprehensive understanding and effective mitigation techniques (Sher, E. 1998). Most of the transportation sector runs on diesel engines, and their emissions contribute significantly to ambient PM levels. The health implications of exposure to particulate matter, including ultra-fine particles, are profound (HEI Review 2013). Using Diesel Particulate Filter (DPF) helps reduce PM emissions; nevertheless, the PM concentration during the regenerative events of DPF is neither environmentally friendly nor economical (Giechaskiel, B. 2020). Many researchers have experimentally investigated that adding nanoparticles to diesel fuel reduces the PM emissions of an automobile engine (Kegl, T. 2021). However, none of the prior studies have focused on the effect of nanoparticles on PM emissions in the ultra-fine range (1–100 nm).

The present study focuses on the impact of Titania-laden nanofuel on the particulate emissions of a compression ignition (CI) engine. The mechanical method of ultra-sonication helps to modify the particle size distribution (PSD) of the dispersed nano-additives. The effect of Titania (TiO₂) nano-additives on PM, including ultra-fine particles (UFPs), is studied experimentally.

METHODOLOGY & EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

The experimental study involves the preparation of stable nanofuel suspension, testing the dispersibility of nano-additives in diesel, and measurement of PM emissions using a Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS). The 100 ppm TiO₂ nano-additives (purchased from Sigma-Aldrich) were blended with diesel fuel to improve the thermo-physical properties of the suspension. Span 80 surfactant was added to provide steric stabilization, and the nanofuel sample was ultra-sonicated for 1 hour using a 'BRANSON CPX300H' bath sonicator (BS). The PSD analysis of the dispersed nanoparticles is done using the Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) technique. The sample naming is done in the following ways: **(a)** Ti100: 100 ppm TiO₂ + 0.02% wt. Span80 + Diesel, and **(b)** Ti100 BS: 100 ppm TiO₂ + 0.02% wt. Span80 + Diesel + 1 hour BS.

The engine experiments were performed on a 4-stroke, single-cylinder, water-cooled engine with a rated power output of 5 HP. The experimental measurements were done in the CRDI mode at an engine speed of 1100 RPM. The exhaust emissions were sent to SMPS for the number concentration analysis of PM, through a dilution system that intakes air at a flow rate of 1.0 l/min for dilution. The aerosol flow rate (AFR) and sheath flow rate (SFR) in SMPS were defined as 0.3 l/min and 3.0 l/min, respectively.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The stability of nanofuel is essential as the benefits of adding nanoparticles will nullify due to settling. Figure 1 shows the DLS measurement of TiO₂ nano-additives dispersed in diesel, with and without ultra-sonication, after one day. Ultra-sonication helps in the breakdown of weak aggregates; hence, there is a shift in intensity peak plots towards the smaller size range in the case of the 'Ti100 BS' sample, which aids in the improvement of the shelf-life of nanofuel.

After the preparation of nanofuel suspension, the engine experiments for the measurement of PM emissions are carried out using SMPS. Figure 2 shows the plot of the number concentration of PM as a function of the mobility diameter (D_m). There is a reduction in PM emissions with the addition of TiO₂ nanoparticles at distinct engine loads (0%, 50%, and 100%). At first instance, it appears that there is an overall reduction in the total

number concentration (TNC) of PM emissions for the entire size range (15.7 – 637.8 nm) with the addition of TiO₂ nanoparticles; however, the mathematical analysis for the lower size range (< 100 nm), shows that there is an increment in the TNC of UFPs for TiO₂-laden nanofuel, as given in Table 1. The addition of nano-additives led to the reduction of soot and other PM, but TiO₂ nanoparticles may have evolved in the exhaust of the engine, which increases the TNC in the ultra-fine range. Thus, detailed investigations are required to understand the effect of nano-additives on UFPs.

Figure 1. Size analysis of dispersed TiO₂ nanoparticles after one day, using DLS

Figure 2. PM emissions measurement for Diesel and Ti100 BS [@1100 RPM, CR 20]

Table 1. Percentage change in the TNC of PM emissions at various engine loading conditions

Load (%)	All sizes (15.7 – 637.8 nm)	< 23 nm	23 – 50 nm	50 – 100 nm	100 – 150 nm	> 150 nm
0	- 45.9	- 80.4 %	6.0 %	- 20.0 %	- 40.3 %	- 65.1 %
50	- 9.0	- 10.4 %	- 20.4 %	- 27.1 %	- 11.9 %	- 6.0 %
100	- 33.5	- 37.1 %	- 55.3 %	21.0 %	- 23.9 %	- 32.4 %

CONCLUSIONS

The stability of nanofuel is a crucial aspect that helps to understand its shelf-life for better improvement of the engine characteristics. The concept of adding TiO₂ nanoparticles to diesel fuel is a promising way for the reduction of PM emissions. There is a decrement of 45.9%, 9.0%, and 33.5% in TNC at 0%, 50%, and 100% engine loads, respectively. However, the TNC of UFPs increases with the addition of nano-additives. There is an increment of 6% (size: 23 – 50 nm) and 21 % (50 – 100 nm) in TNC at 0% and 100 % engine loading conditions, respectively. Therefore, a comprehensive study is required in this direction to understand the effect of nano-additives on PM, including UFPs.

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EFFECT OF COVID-19 RESTRICTIVE MEASURES ON AEROSOLS IN THE INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN REGION

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Keywords: AOD, BC, COVID-19, IGP, SATELLITE REMOTE SENSING

INTRODUCTION

Severe acute Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) has been considered one of the major health disasters of the 20th century (WHO, 2020), which has led to unprecedented challenges to socio-economic reform worldwide. The COVID-19-induced lockdown provided a unique opportunity to investigate the changes in aerosol loading over heavily aerosol-laden regions like the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP). During the initial phases of the lockdown period, nearly all human-related sources of pollution in India were notably diminished (Srivastava, 2020; Pratap et al., 2021). This resulted in a temporary enhancement of air quality, attributed to the decrease in emissions of anthropogenic aerosols and other pollutants originating from industries, transportation, and various human activities. The present study emphasizes the variability in columnar aerosol properties at 10 different cities of the IGP during pre-lockdown (Pre-LD: 1st March – 24th March), lockdown (LD: 25th March – 31st May) and post-lockdown (Post-LD: 1st June – 30th June) period of 2020, and further compared with respect to the same period of 2015 – 2019. In addition, the actual change in aerosol levels during the total lockdown period is estimated by eliminating the impact of seasonal variations.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

To assess the impact of lockdown measures on aerosols in the IGP, we have categorized the IGP into three regions: Western IGP represented by Amritsar, Patiala, Delhi and Agra; Central IGP represented by Kanpur, Gorakhpur, Varanasi and Patna; and Eastern IGP represented by Asansol and Kolkata. For the present study, Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) level3 combined DB-DT retrieved daily AOD from Terra and Aqua satellite, and Modern MERRA-2 reanalysis hourly averaged BC mass concentration data are used. The LD period is considered LD(A) and LD(B) depending on the implementation of four phases of the lockdown. LD(A) represents the initial two phases of the lockdown from 25th March to 14th April 2020, while LD(B) represents the latter two phases of the lockdown from 15th April to 31st May 2020. The percentage change (PC) was calculated to quantify changes that occurred during the lockdown phases (i.e. Pre-LD, LD(A), LD(B) and Post-LD) in 2020 with respect to the same phases of 2015–2019, using the following relation:

$$PC = \left[\frac{(Phase)_{2015-2019} - (Phase)_{2020}}{(Phase)_{2015-2019}} \right] \times 100$$

In order to remove the seasonal biases and ascertain the absolute change in AOD and BC levels due to the COVID-19-induced lockdowns, the seasonal influences during the period of 2015 – 2019 were taken as a reference. To eliminate the seasonal influences, we have calculated the percentage change during the lockdown period of 2015 – 2019 with respect to Pre-LD period of 2015 – 2019. Further, the estimated percentage change and the Pre-LD of 2020 is used to normalize the lockdown period of 2020 to ascertain the changes that occurred during this period were only due to the COVID-19 induced lockdown. Based on this an estimation of the absolute percentage change (APC) during the lockdown period was done.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

As the lockdown progressed, all IGP cities witnessed a gradual decline in AOD and BC, which suggests the significant impact of lockdown measures on aerosol loading. During the first two phases of the lockdown i.e., LD(A), the central IGP witnessed a maximum decrease in AOD and BC of 30% and 14.5% followed by the eastern (25.4% and 10.4%) and western IGP (25.3% and 7.5%) (Table 1). During the third and fourth phases of lockdown i.e., LD(B), a further decline in AOD was observed over all the cities, indicating reduced anthropogenic activities. During LD(B), the maximum drop in BC was observed over the central IGP (14.5%) followed by the eastern IGP (10.4%) and the western IGP (7.5%). During this period, the maximum decline in BC concentration occurred at Gorakhpur, Varanasi and Kolkata. During Post-LD period restrictions on public and private transport, industries, and other anthropogenic activities were lifted. It was reflected in the BC measurements where an increase of 6 – 9% throughout the IGP was observed.

Table 1: Percentage change (PC) in AOD and BC concentration over different regions/cities of the IGP during Pre-LD, LD phases and Post-LD period of 2020 with respect to the same period of 2015 – 2019.

Region/Cities of the IGP	Percentage Change in AOD (%)				Percentage Change in BC (%)			
	Pre-LD	LD(A)	LD(B)	Post-LD	Pre-LD	LD(A)	LD(B)	Post-LD
West IGP	11.6	-25.3	-28.4	-3.0	4.02	-7.5	-4.2	6.0
Amritsar	-2.1	-33.7	-37.1	-0.8	1.27	-3.4	-20.2	-5.0
Patiala	13.5	-23.9	-27.3	-2.3	1.65	-10.2	4.1	12.6
Delhi	15.5	-21.0	-22.8	-1.6	6.70	-9.5	-3.6	10.1
Agra	19.4	-22.5	-26.3	-7.1	6.46	-6.6	3.2	6.0
Central IGP	20.4	-30.0	-23.7	-6.1	8.76	-14.5	-7.2	8.2
Kanpur	31.7	-26.6	-24.2	-0.7	12.15	-12.0	-1.6	2.3
Gorakhpur	5.8	-33.7	-25.7	-3.8	5.89	-17.9	-11.6	11.0
Varanasi	30.8	-25.0	-19.2	-10.6	8.44	-15.3	-8.2	10.2
Patna	13.2	-33.8	-25.6	-9.4	5.7	-12.7	-7.4	9.3
East IGP	3.6	-25.4	-21.8	3.4	6.79	-10.4	0.4	8.7
Asansol	8.1	-27.8	-18.9	5.5	6.47	-5.7	3.0	18.0
Kolkata	-1.0	-22.9	-24.6	1.3	7.11	-15.0	-2.2	-0.7

Figure 1. Percentage change (PC) and absolute percentage change (APC) in (a) AOD and (b) BC during total lockdown (LD) period with respect to the same time frame of 2015 – 2019.

During the total lockdown period, both PC and APC show a maximum reduction in AOD in central IGP (26.5% and 38.5%), followed by western IGP (24.9% and 34.6%), and eastern IGP (23.2% and 25.9%). According to APC, the cities of western and central IGP show a large absolute decrease in AOD of 30 – 40% during the lockdown period with the maximum decrease observed in the central IGP cities of Kanpur (43.2%), Varanasi (40%) and Patna (37.5%). The estimated APC indicates a major reduction in BC was observed in the central IGP (18.2%), where Gorakhpur and Varanasi showed a maximum decrease of 19.6% and 18.8%, respectively.

CONCLUSIONS

This study presents a comprehensive analysis of COVID-19 lockdown impact on aerosol properties over the IGP and highlights unprecedented reductions in AOD (~ 40 %) and BC (~ 20 %), due to the imposition of lockdown and subsequent cessation of aerosol sources, by removing seasonal influences. Following the lockdown, most of the cities of the IGP experiences substantial build-up of aerosols as a result of the lifting of restrictions on public and private transports, industries and other anthropogenic activities.

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SEASONAL VARIATION AND ISOTOPIC COMPOSITION OF ATMOSPHERIC AEROSOLS
COLLECTED OVER THE NORTHEAST ARABIAN SEA

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Keywords: ATMOSPHERIC DUST, CHARACTERIZATION, RADIOGENIC ISOTOPES, SOURCES, ARABIAN SEA

INTRODUCTION

Arabian Sea receives substantial amount of mineral dust annually via wet (Suresh et al., 2021) and dry deposition from various surrounding arid and semi-arid sources (Kumar et al., 2020). The transport and deposition of the mineral dust can modulate the climate system in various ways particularly by supplying the essential macro (N, P) and micro (especially Fe) nutrients to the open ocean, thus can impact surface water biogeochemical processes including primary productivity (Guieu et al., 2019). In case of Arabian Sea, the transport of atmospheric mineral dust largely depends on the seasonal reversal of winds i.e. SW monsoon during Summer (June-September) and NE monsoon during winter (November-February). The nutrients associated with atmospheric mineral dust largely depends on the sources from where it is being originated. Thus, the identification of dust sources and quantification of associated nutrients are important to constrain the impact of dust deposition over the Arabian Sea.

METHODOLOGY

We report a two-year time series of aerosols deposit collected using high volume sampler at a coastal station in Goa (15.45° N, 73.80° E), spanning the Winter (Jan-Feb), Pre-monsoon (Mar-May) and Post monsoon (Oct-Nov) seasons for 2018-2019 period. The samples were leached to remove sea salt Sr and carbonate fraction using MQ water and Na acetate buffered acetic acid solution respectively. The samples were further digested using a mixture of HF-HNO₃. The analyses of Sr and Nd isotope of samples were carried out throughout the period. Using the radiogenic isotopic ratio (Sr and Nd) corroborated with Air-mass back trajectories and Aerosol index map, we were able to record how the different wind patterns throughout the year affected the seasonal pattern of dust deposition in this region.

RESULTS

We observed a significant seasonal variation in the isotopic composition of samples collected during different periods. An increase in the Sr ⁸⁷Sr/⁸⁶Sr value (0.7163-0.7289) during winter period was noticed which tend to decrease during pre-monsoon period (0.7136 to 0.7228) and again increases during post monsoon period (0.728601). Whereas ϵ_{Nd} values shows an opposite trend, with a decrease observed during winter period (-8 to -17) which continue to increase during pre-monsoon period (-7 to -14) and again decline or become less radiogenic during post monsoon period (-16). These observations are also well supported with the HYSPLIT retrieved air mass back trajectory and UV-Aerosol index map providing a synoptic view of wind regimes and active dust sources respectively, during study period.

Figure 1. Seasonal variation in the isotopic composition observed over the Northeast Arabian Sea.

CONCLUSION

The large variation in the isotopic composition indicate the contribution of various dust sources active during these periods. This seasonal variation in the sources of dust is capable of supplying variable amount of nutrients and thus influencing biogeochemistry of the Arabian sea.

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UNVEILING AEROSOL MORPHOLOGY THROUGH GROUND-BASED OBSERVATIONS AND OPTICAL PROPERTIES VIA REMOTE SENSING TECHNIQUES

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Keywords: PARTICULATE MATTER, AEROSOL OPTICAL THICKNESS, MORPHOLOGY, OPTICAL PROPERTIES.

ABSTRACT

The study of aerosol particles comprehends a crucial aspect of atmospheric science, providing insight into their complex interactions with the environment and their consequential ramifications for climate and human health. This study investigated the variability in the morphological and optical properties of aerosol particles, highlighting their profound influence on aerosol behavior in atmospheric dynamics. This study has been carried out at Jaipur and Ajmer cities of Rajasthan, an arid region of northwest India. We used ground-based (high volume sampler and microtop-sunphotometer) and satellite (MODIS, OMI, and AIRS) observation data. We use SEM, EDX, FTIR, and XRD for morphology to characterize morphological variability of the diverse physical characteristics encompassing variations in size, shape, and structural arrangements of aerosol (particulate matter). These morphological characteristics of aerosol formation show how aerosols disperse, interact, and evolve within the atmosphere. The interplay of morphological traits significantly influences optical properties by scattering, absorbing, and radiative transfer characteristics. The optical properties (AOT, AE, AI, and SSA) were analyzed by hand-held microtop-sunphotometer and satellite observations. The most dominating particles had a maximum contribution by C, O, Na, and Cl elements, while aerosol optical properties, AOD, and AE were observed >0.3 and >0.8 . This represents the coarser particles are dominating in the study region. The comprehensive analysis of these optical properties elucidates aerosol behavior and clarifies their role in altering atmospheric radiative fluxes and influencing climate patterns. This study unravels aerosol morphological diversity and optical behavior within aerosol dust particles. By explaining the morphological variations and optical properties, a comprehensive understanding of aerosol behavior emerges, transcending the boundaries of atmospheric science and extending its implications to diverse spheres, including climate modeling and public health assessment.

METHODS

We did the sampling at the Central University of Rajasthan campus using a respirable dust sample (morphology) and MICROTUPS-11 sunphotometer (optical properties). The methodology flow chart is mentioned in the figure (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Representing the flow chart of methodology

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

This study has been conducted at Jaipur and Ajmer cities of Rajasthan, an arid region of northwest India. This region has a complex characteristic of aerosols due to their elemental and mineral composition (Figure 2). This might be due to the complex chemistry of aerosols, and this region influences mixed aerosol emitted from various industries, biomass burning, desert dust, etc. (Tiwari et al., 2015a; Kumar et al., 2020; Sharma and Mandal, 2023).

Figure 2. Representing the morphology of atmospheric dust with the mineral compositions by EDX and SEM image.

CONCLUSIONS

This study represented the interrelationship between particle size, shape, and optical characteristics and played a pivotal in influencing aerosol dispersion, light interactions, and radiative effects. The outcomes of this research transcend fundamental scientific inquiries reverberating across disciplines.

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HETEROGENEITY IN THE AEROSOL VERTICAL PROFILE AND ITS INTERACTION WITH THE ATMOSPHERIC BOUNDARY LAYER AS OBSERVED BY TETHERED BALLOON PAYLOADS ALONG THE BRAHMAPUTRA VALLEY OF NORTH EAST INDIA

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Keywords: BLACK CARBON, ATMOSPHERIC BOUNDARY LAYER, TETHERED BALLOON, NORTH EAST INDIA.

INTRODUCTION

Absorbing aerosols constituting of black carbon (BC) influences our atmosphere the most by absorbing most of the solar radiation coming to the earth's surface. The existence of this bulk of aerosol or atmospheric pollutants within the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) has always been a critical source in determining global as well as regional aerosol dispersion and distribution in the atmosphere. Previous studies over North East India (NEI) have extensively explored spatio-temporal behaviour of aerosols. However, understanding of the ABL characteristics and the vertical distribution of aerosol is still lacking over the region. Therefore, for the first time a tethered balloon field campaign was conducted over three locations along the Brahmaputra valley of Assam in NEI from west to east viz., Dhubri (26.02°N, 89.97°E, 31 metres), Guwahati (26.10°N, 91.60°E, 55 metres), and Dibrugarh (27.47°N, 94.91°E, 108 metres) during the winter (WN) and pre monsoon (PM) seasons of the year 2021 to characterize ABL and the vertical distribution of BC up to a height of 1 km from the surface.

METHODOLOGY

A kytoon/tethered balloon manufactured by TIFR with dimensions 25×11×5 feet approximately is used as an instrument platform for elevating Dr. Pisharoty Radiosonde for vertical profiling of meteorological parameters (Temperature, Pressure, Relative Humidity, Wind Speed and Wind Direction) and Microaethalometer (MA) for airborne aerosol measurements. The tethered balloon was deployed 4 times a day at 6 hourly intervals. Meteorological balloons were also launched simultaneously 4-5 times per day in each of these 3 stations for one day during the time of tethered balloon launch. The maximum gradient of virtual potential temperature (θ_v) can be used to determine ABLH which indicates atmospheric static stability and effects pollutant diffusion. ABLH can also be estimated by the minimum vertical gradient of specific humidity with a significant reduction in atmospheric moisture.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Distinct diurnal variability has been observed in the vertical profiles of BC and meteorological parameters throughout the day. In the absence of incoming solar radiation or weak turbulence during the morning, evening and night time, ABLH varied between 50 – 150 m and 75 – 250 m over Dhubri during WN and PM respectively as measured by the radiosonde. Whereas, Guwahati recorded ABLH varying between 100 – 275 m and 125 – 250 m and Dibrugarh recorded 50 – 225 m and 50 to 250 m during WN and PM seasons respectively. Figure 1, depicts the vertical profiles of θ_v , q and black carbon concentration (BCC) during morning, evening and night time of WN and PM seasons over Dhubri where it can be clearly seen that low height of the ABL during morning, evening and night time suppresses of the BCC near to the surface. Maximum BCC of 23.5 μgm^{-3} , 17.30 μgm^{-3} , 13.01 μgm^{-3} during WN and 9.5 μgm^{-3} , 11.79 μgm^{-3} , 9.65 μgm^{-3} during PM was recorded within the ABL during the morning, evening and night time respectively over Dhubri. High BCC alters the thermal radiation processes, reducing the sensible heat flux responsible for the evolution of the ABL and at the same time reducing the entrainment of dry air into the ABL from the free troposphere amplifying ABL suppression and leading to more moisture in the ABL. This increases the relative humidity (RH) in the atmosphere which in turn increases hygroscopic growth of aerosols augmenting the scattering of

solar radiation. Increasing RH also favors the formation of secondary aerosols. The aerosol and ABL has bidirectional feedback effects which results in intensifying detrimental health impacts caused by the aerosol-ABL interaction. BCC recorded a maximum of $27.10 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, $16.26 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, $20.24 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$ and $13.68 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, $5.31 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, $10.59 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$ during morning, evening and night time respectively over Guwahati during WN and PM seasons respectively near to the surface. While Dibrugarh observed a maximum BCC of $13.01 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, $5.39 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, $12.27 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$ during winter and $4.45 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, $4.78 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, $6.48 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$ during morning, evening and night time respectively. ABLH goes above 1 km during day time, where the rapid development of a well-mixed vertical profile of BC was observed during the day over all the three locations where a maximum BCC of $5.4 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, $12.25 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, $3.88 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$ was recorded during WN and $5.39 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, $4.54 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, $2.96 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$ during PM over Dhubri, Guwahati and Dibrugarh respectively. The vertical profiles of BC closely followed the vertical profiles of the meteorological parameters.

Figure 1. Vertical profile of θ , q and BCC during morning, evening and night time during WN and PM seasons over Dhubri.

CONCLUSIONS

During the morning, evening and night time the ABL height (ABLH) measured by sonde varied from 50 – 150 m, 100 – 275 m and 50 – 225 m during WN season over Dhubri, Guwahati and Dibrugarh respectively. While during PM season, ABLH varied from 75 – 250 m, 125 – 250 m and 50 to 250 m respectively over the 3 stations. Near surface BCC was found to be high within the ABL during morning, evening and night time over all the stations. During winter and pre monsoon, maximum BCC reached up to approximately $30.98 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, $27.10 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, $13.01 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$ and $9.65 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, $13.68 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$, $6.48 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$ respectively over Dhubri, Guwahati and Dibrugarh near to the surface. A well-mixed vertical profile of BC was observed over all the study sites as the ABLH crosses 1 km during the day. The vertical profile BCC was in good correlation with the meteorological parameters within the ABL that has reciprocating response upon its interaction.

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CARBON CHEMISTRY OF PM_{2.5} OVER A SEMI-URBAN REGION AT IGP: A STUDY UNDER DIFFERENT METEOROLOGICAL DISPERSION CONDITIONS

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Keywords: PM_{2.5}, IGP, CARBONACEOUS AEROSOLS, NAAQS

INTRODUCTION

The major components of fine-mode aerosols have adverse health and climatic effects. Acceleration of urbanization, industrialization, emissions from the energy-related sectors, and growing usage of petrol-driven vehicles are among the prime sources of PM_{2.5} leading to high mortality rates as per the Global Energy Organization reports, 2016. The chemical nature of PM_{2.5} is highly complex which includes different types of organic as well as inorganic components having primary and secondary origins. Amongst all of the components, the carbonaceous part is of major importance, usually comprising 20 % to 50 % of the total aerosol mass (Kanakidou *et al.*, 2005). The massive anthropogenic activities in the Indo-Gangetic Plain region which is considered to be a significant hotspot region in the Indian subcontinent as well as the meteorological conditions (frequent temperature inversion, shallow boundary layer, stagnant winds, etc.) are favorable for the high accumulation of air pollutants over this region (Dumka *et al.*, 2017). The variations of carbonaceous aerosols in high and low pollution periods with respect to dispersion conditions can help us understand the meteorological dependency on carbonaceous aerosol formations.

METHODS

This year-long study (Jan-Dec 2019) has been conducted over a semi-urban atmosphere called Shyamnagar (22°50'N, 88°23'E, 8 m asl) in the eastern part of IGP. 24-hour samples of PM_{2.5} were collected using a 5-channel aerosol sampler (SASS, Met-One, USA) on every alternate day covering all the seasons. Teflon filters were used for the collection of aerosols and the concentrations were determined using gravimetric measurement. Nylon filters were used for the collection of samples for the analysis of water-soluble ionic species using ion chromatography whereas pre-heated quartz filters were used for the analysis of carbonaceous components using a thermal optical carbon analyzer. Sampling events were divided into three dispersion classes based on the ventilation co-efficient which is the product of the main dispersion parameters viz. wind speed and mixing layer depth.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The NAAQS of India for 24-hr PM_{2.5} is 60 µgm⁻³ and about 44% of our sampling days have been above the limit (implying high pollution events). The PM_{2.5} concentrations were observed to be decreased significantly with higher dispersion classes thus evidently implying the dominance of local emissions. PM_{2.5} concentrations increased about 3.2 times during LFD (Least favorable meteorological condition for dispersion) for events with higher NAAQS days than lower NAAQS days, whereas it increased about 2.6 times during MFD (Moderately favorable meteorological condition for dispersion) and 2.1 times during HFD (Highly favorable meteorological condition for dispersion). The increase in the secondary components from low to high pollution events was significantly low under the meteorological conditions favorable for pollutant dispersion. The increase in SOC under LFD conditions was 10.1 µgm⁻³ whereas it was only 1.6 µgm⁻³ under HFD conditions. On the contrary, the increases in POC and EC were 5.8 and 6.1 µgm⁻³ under LFD which were not significantly reduced when the conditions favored dispersion (Under HFD conditions, 1.53 µgm⁻³ for POC and 2.24 µgm⁻³ for EC) indicating that primary local emissions were less dependent on meteorological conditions.

Figure 1: Mean (and standard deviation) of total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations, POC, SOC, EC, and TCA under different dispersion conditions and during $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ within and exceeding NAAQS.

CONCLUSIONS

The higher increase in secondary components under LFD conditions compared to HFD conditions strongly indicates that the formation mechanisms of secondary aerosols from their respective precursors were favored under stable and calm atmospheric conditions. Identifying and curbing the primary emissions would significantly reduce $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations in this region. This region is a good representative of the semi-urban IGP region. Therefore, such mitigation policies are also applicable to all semi-urban IGP regions.

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**CHEMICAL CHARACTERISATION AND SOURCE APPORTIONMENT OF FINE
ATMOSPHERIC AEROSOLS OVER THE SEMI-URBAN ATMOSPHERE OF EASTERN INDO-
GANGETIC PLAIN: COMPARISON WITH MEGACITY**

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Keywords: STACKED FILTRATION UNIT, SUB-MICRON AEROSOLS, WATER-SOLUBLE
INORGANIC IONS, SOURCE APPORTIONMENT.

INTRODUCTION

Knowledge of aerosol chemical composition provides essential information about sources and processes that can affect the aerosol concentration at a particular place. The chemical composition of aerosols has an important role in determining their relative efficiency to absorb and scatter the solar radiation. Though the atmospheric abundance of aerosol constituents is known in general, the chemical composition would exhibit temporal and spatial heterogeneity owing to the short residence time of aerosol species, influence from the source- and region-specific emission sources and meteorological effects. This heterogeneity thereby leads to uncertainty in the prediction of aerosols induced climatic impacts, and therefore, necessitates examining temporal features of aerosol chemical species on a regional to local scale, and that distinctly for fine and coarse aerosols. Unlike coarse particles, fine aerosols can penetrate deep into the respiratory system and are often associated with cardiovascular disease, cardiovascular mortality (Verma et al., 2022) and respiratory mortality. Thus, investigating fine aerosols on regional scale is crucial for an accurate quantification of their atmospheric and health effects. The studies delineating aerosol particle chemical composition of water-soluble inorganic ions (WSII) or carbonaceous aerosols (CA) are mostly over the urban agglomerates, often characterising PM_{2.5} or PM₁₀ mass and lacking simultaneous yet discrete measurement of WSII and CA. There is still a scarcity of information on the fine aerosols and the sources contributing to their mass in the Eastern Indian region.

METHODS

Ambient fine aerosol sampling was carried out over the semi-urban atmosphere (KGP), at the rooftop of the civil engineering department, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur (KGP: 22.33°N, 88.33°E) from January to December 2018 using a devised submicron aerosol sampler (SAS) (Priyadharshini et al., 2019). The Quartz filter and PTFE filters were used for the collection of respectively the carbonaceous and WSII species. Discrete sampling using separate substrates is helpful for a better characterization of WSII and CA; e.g., PTFE for WSII and Quartz for CA. The analysis of WSII species and CA were carried using Metrohm 761 Compact Ion chromatography (IC) and carbon analyzer (Model 4-semi continuous) following National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) thermal optical transmittance (TOT) 5040 protocol. The sampled fine aerosol (PM<1.6 µg m⁻³) chemical concentration and the associated uncertainties are provided as input to the PMF model Version 5.0. The model has been run for six factors (number of sources) decided on basis of the minimum value of Q (goodness of fit parameters) and scaled residuals. Factor profiles obtained from the PMF model are identified through insights from source profiles and emission inventories, and the physical interpretability of resolved factors.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Chemical Composition of Fine Aerosols at Kharagpur

The monthly mean concentration of total WSII (T_{WSII}: sum of analysed WSII species) is highest during February (132 µg m⁻³) followed by November (111 µg m⁻³); these being twice as large as the annual mean T_{WSII} concentration. The lowest monthly mean of T_{WSII} concentration is observed during June (53 µg m⁻³) which is twice lower than the annual mean. The annual mean concentration of WSII revealed Ca²⁺ as the most abundant ion followed by Cl⁻ and Mg²⁺. The analysis of chemical composition revealed abundance of Ca²⁺, Cl⁻, Mg²⁺, Na⁺ and SO₄²⁻ as compared to NH₄⁺, K⁺, NO₃⁻ and F⁻ in the semi-urban atmosphere. The relative abundance is found to be similar to that of the megacity atmosphere. Remarkably, the monthly mean SO₄²⁻ concentration is consistently higher (twice) than NO₃⁻ throughout the study period at the semi-urban atmosphere of KGP. A pronounced peak in the monthly mean concentration of K⁺ is observed during the summer month of May. Annually, nss-K⁺ amounts to 91% of the total K⁺ concentration; however, low monthly mean fractional contribution of nss-K⁺ to total K⁺ during April (69%) and October (74%) is

observed. The mean ionic ratio (the ratio of the sum of cations to the sum of the anions) for the study period is estimated as 2.9 suggesting highly alkaline aerosols. The largest contribution for the neutralization results from the high concentrations of Ca^{2+} in this region. The highest monthly mean OC (EC) concentration was observed in December (November) while the lowest was observed in September for OC and March for EC.

PMF Source profiles for Kharagpur and Kolkata

The sources contributing to the fine aerosols over KGP are resolved using PMF 5.0. For the semi-urban location, six factors are identified based on the marker elements present in each source profile. Among the factors determined, emissions from brick kilns constituted 21% followed by marine aerosols (18%), crustal elements (17%), secondary aerosols (16%), biomass burning (14%) and fugitive dust (14%). Among the obtained factors, emission from the brick kiln and coal combustion had the most significant contribution to submicron aerosol mass at KGP and KOL, respectively. Multiple small-scale local brick kilns surround the semi-urban location. The apportioned source profiles indicated biomass burning and marine aerosol as the common sources between KGP and KOL with nearly equivalent percentage contributions attributed to similar region types (coastal cities) surrounded by extensive agricultural activities throughout the year. Other factors determined at megacity are resuspended paved road dust (19%), marine aerosols (17%), emission from waste burning (14%), biomass burning (13%) and vehicular emissions (13%).

Figure 1. Monthly mean concentration of T_{WSII} at KGP (a), the annual mean value is presented by a black dashed line. Annual mean composition of WSII (b-c) and PMF derived source contributions (d-e) at KGP and KOL.

CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, the daytime sampled fine aerosol particles (cut-off size of $1.6 \mu\text{m}$) were chemically characterized to evaluate the relative abundance of ambient aerosol species and their sources at semi-urban and megacity atmospheres. A comparison of fine aerosols at KGP with KOL showed a relative dominance of Ca^{2+} followed by Cl^- , Mg^{2+} and Na^+ at both the sites. The fractional contribution of secondary aerosols to T_{WSII} was larger at KOL (25%) than at KGP (16%). The annual mean concentration of SO_4^{2-} was higher than NO_3^- at KGP while it was vice versa at KOL. A predominance of the stationary source was observed at KGP contrary to the mobile sources at KOL. The annual mean concentration of OC was three times EC at both study sites. The influence of biomass burning at both sites was discerned from the monthly mean trend of nss-K^+ which corroborated the biomass burning (crop residue and forest burning) information over India. The assessment of sources as quantified using Positive Matrix Factorization (PMF) revealed brick kilns, crustal elements and secondary aerosols as the primary sources contributing to fine aerosol mass in the semi-urban atmosphere. In contrast, it was coal combustion, paved road dust and marine aerosols in the megacity atmosphere.

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ESTIMATION OF REALTIME BROWN CARBON ABSORPTION PROPERTIES OVER A HIGH ALTITUDE STATION IN ESTERN HIMALAYA, INDIA.

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INTRODUCTION

Light-absorbing aerosols strongly impact the radiative balance of the earth influencing regional as well as global climate change. Brown Carbon (BrC) a fraction of organic carbon absorbs solar radiation preferably in the UV-vis region range (200-400 nm) efficiently. Due to its light absorbing nature which makes it capable of affecting the oxidizing capacity of photochemically active gases by restraining their photolysis rates (Laskin et al., 2015). The sources of BrC can be of primary origin like Biomass Burning emissions and fossil fuel combustion but also of secondary origin through oxidation of VOCs (Zhang et al., 2007). They are a group of compounds with specific physical properties but versatile chemical components making them difficult to characterize. They are emitted as complex mixtures containing BC, BrC and other non-absorbing organic aerosols as well as inorganic compounds in varying proportions making estimation of emission factors and attributing sources extremely difficult. Reports are made showing that the Global radiative forcing by BrC is one-fourth of that of BC. In regions with intense combustion activities, the regional radiative forcing by BrC was found to be much more than the global average thereby signifying its influence on regional climate change. Thus, the characterization of BrC in an urban Eastern Himalayan region which shows significant combustion activities can be useful for understanding the aerosol climate interaction.

METHODS

In the present study the absorption coefficient ($b_{abs,BrC,370}$) of Brown Carbon at 370 nm was derived from continuous monitoring of light absorption properties of ambient aerosol at seven wave-lengths (ranging from UV to IR) by an Aethelometer over an eastern Himalayan hill station Darjeeling (altitude 2200 m). Simultaneous measurement of carbonaceous aerosol concentration was conducted using an online OC-EC analyzer (Sunset laboratories). Both these measurement were conducted during the month Mar-May in the year 2019. The wavelength dependent improved AAE method (following the work by Wang et al., 2018) was used to derive the absorption coefficient of BrC ($b_{abs,BrC,370}$) using the following equation.

$$b_{abs,BrC,370} = b_{abs,370} - b_{abs,BC,880} \times \left(\frac{660}{880}\right)^{-AAE_{660/880}} \times \left(\frac{370}{660}\right)^{-AAE_{660/880} \times AAE_{ratio}} \quad \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

The contribution of BrC to the total absorption were calculated using the equation

$$\% b_{abs,BrC,370} = \frac{b_{abs,BrC,370}}{b_{abs,370}} \times 100 \quad \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

And the Mass Absorption Cross section (MAC) at 370 nm was calculated using the equation

$$MAC_{BrC,370} = b_{abs,370}/OC \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

The AAE represents the Absorption Angstrom Exponent at different wavelength.

AAE_{ratio} is the ratio of AAE of BC at the wavelength range (370-660) and (660-880)nm. In the present study the AAE_{ratio} was value used was 0.64 following the previous work by Kapoor et al., 2022.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

A high altitude location like Darjeeling shows a unique feature in terms of pollutant concentration variation which is markedly different from the plan land regions. During the night due to shallow mixing layer the pollutants get tapped in the valley region and the concentration of the pollutants remains low at the high altitude location showing low OC-EC/BC concentration (figure 1a).

Figure 1: Showing the diurnal variation of (a) carbonaceous aerosol concentration (OC, EC, BC) and (b) the absorption properties of BrC

As the sun rises in the morning the nocturnal boundary layer breaks and pollutants transported to the high altitude location creating a morning peak of OC and EC/BC. However as the day progress the concentration slightly decreases and again takes a peak in the afternoon and then slowly decreases and becomes minimum in the night. The afternoon peak could be explained by the transport of polluted air mass by up valley wind. The BrC absorption coefficient ($b_{\text{abs_BrC}_{370}}$) which denotes the total absorption by BrC follow the similar diurnal pattern with the OC-EC/BC concentration variation indicating majority of BrC is of similar source of OC and EC which might be from primary anthropogenic origin. However diurnal features somewhat different for %BrC and MAC_{BrC,370}. The %BrC and MAC which is indicator of the nature of BrC aerosol both showed a consistent high value during the late night. The MAC reaches its maxima just before the sun rise when the concentration of the pollutants was minimum. This is a very interesting observation as this indicates the BrC present in the atmosphere during the night is highly absorbing in nature. As the day begins the photochemical process leads to bleaching of the night time BrC hence MAC_{BrC,370} decreases. Also during the evening period when the solar radiation flux decreases, a prominent peak of MAC_{BrC,370} of BrC was observed which coincides with the OC concentration peak. This might be the result of transportation of absorbing brown carbon from the low land region when the solar intensity was low.

CONCLUSIONS

This study is one of the very few studies which shows the formation and transformation of atmospheric brown carbon using real time observation over a high altitude Himalayan site. This study indicates that the solar radiation intensity and night time chemistry may play a complex role on the nature and absorbing properties of BrC aerosol.

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MORPHOLOGICAL AND COMPOSITIONAL ANALYSIS OF AEROSOLS DURING BIOMASS AND NON BIOMASS BURNING PERIODS IN AGRA, INDIA INSIGHTS FROM ADVANCED ANALYTICAL TECHNIQUES

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Keywords: BIOMASS BURNING, FTIR, XRD, FESEM.

INTRODUCTION

Recurrent biomass burning-induced smoke haze has been a persistent issue in Southeast Asia since the late 1990s due to uncontrolled land-clearing activities. Biomass burning produces fine particulate matter, with around 90% of these particles being smaller than 2.5 μm , allowing them to travel long distances and remain suspended (Adam et al., 2021). The escalating impacts of these particles on the environment are driven by factors such as population growth, anthropogenic activities, land use changes, and urbanization. Among various anthropogenic activities, biomass burning is a major contributor to atmospheric pollutants, especially in regions like India, where it is prevalent. Consequently, comprehending the composition and characteristics of aerosols emitted during biomass burning episodes is essential for evaluating their environmental and health repercussions. A comparative analysis of aerosol characterization, with a focus on $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} particle sizes, during both biomass burning (BB) and non-biomass burning (NBB) periods in India, employing advanced analytical techniques has been conducted in this study.

METHODS

Air sampling was conducted using a low-volume sampler at a precise flow rate of 16.6 L/min. Sampling took place during two distinct periods: December 2022 to February 2023, representing a non-biomass burning period, and March 2023 to May 2023, signifying a biomass burning period. Samples were collected at two sites in Agra, Rambagh (urban site) and Dayalbagh (suburban site). Concentration of the metals K, Mg, Na, Ca, Al, Ba, Fe, Cr, Cd, Mn, Zn, Co, Pb, Cu, and Ni were analysed in the PM samples using Inductively-Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES). Organic and Elemental Carbon in the PM samples was estimated through Thermo Gravimetric Analyzer (TGA). Advanced techniques such as Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), X-ray Diffraction (XRD), and Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FESEM) were employed for PM sample.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The 24 h mean concentration of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ was $151.5 \pm 33.4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and $140.5 \pm 32.0 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, while for PM_{10} it was $185.7 \pm 42.3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and $139.2 \pm 46.9 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, at Rambagh and Dayalbagh, respectively during BB period. During the NBB period concentration of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ was $143.2 \pm 64.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and $109.7 \pm 22.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and of PM_{10} was $178.3 \pm 43.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and $127.8 \pm 23.7 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at Rambagh and Dayalbagh, respectively. The concentration of crustal metals, such as K, Na, Ca, Fe and Zn ranged from 0.4 to $26.8 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the BB samples. Notably, K exhibited the highest concentration at $26.8 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, signifying the generation of aerosols associated with biomass burning as K is a prominent biomass tracer (Yang et al., 2022). However, carcinogenic metals like Cd, Cr and Ni were also found in a prominent range of 0.1 to $5.0 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ during BB period, suggesting the severe health impacts. The FTIR analysis (Figure 1) revealed the prominent peaks at the wavenumbers 800, 1000, 1300, 1400, 1600, 2100 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of C-H (alkanes and aliphatic compounds), C=O (carbonyl groups), and O-H (hydroxyl groups) functional groups during BB periods. The prominent peak for O-H group indicates the presence of organic compounds like diacids and sugars that are considered as significant biomass tracers. In the samples of NBB period, instead of O-H, Si-O (siloxane groups) was dominant. The XRD was employed to decipher their mineral composition and confirmed the presence of minerals such as quartz, calcite, feldspar, illite, mascagnite, kaolinite, augite during BB period while minerals like quartz, gypsum, halite, albite, and montmorillonite were prevailing during NBB period.

Figure 1. FTIR analysis of PM_{2.5} sample of (a) BB and (b) NBB period

Additionally, FESEM revealed morphological features of aerosol, with EDX analysis indicating higher concentrations of elements, primarily C > O > Ca > Al > S > Si > Na in BB samples. Elevated ambient carbon levels result from incomplete combustion of fuels and biomass, signifying soot particles from activities like agricultural burning, wood combustion, and burning of organic fuels (Ramli et al., 2021).

CONCLUSIONS

During periods of BB, particulate matter emerges as a prominent pollutant, showing slightly higher concentrations than NBB periods. The study reveals that 24-hour mean concentrations of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ during BB are 1.15 and 1.17 times higher than in NBB, surpassing the recommended limits of 60 and 100 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ set by the National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQS). Additionally, BB significantly elevates levels of various metals, including carcinogenic elements such as Cr, Ni, and Pb. Advanced analytical techniques like FTIR and XRD emphasize distinct compound profiles in BB and NBB samples, accentuating their unique aerosol characteristics. Furthermore, FESEM and EDX analyses substantiate differences in particle morphology and composition between BB and NBB, enhancing the grasp of aerosol behavior and its potential impacts on air quality, climate, and human health.

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SOURCE PROFILE OF CARBONACEOUS PM_{2.5} EMISSIONS FROM DIFFERENT PRIMARY SOURCES IN THE COAL CAPITAL CITY DHANBAD, INDIA

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Keywords: aerosol-characterization, carbonaceous-aerosols, OC/EC

INTRODUCTION

The escalation of fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) levels in Indian urban areas, driven by various anthropogenic activities, has prompted urgent air quality concerns. PM_{2.5} comprises various chemical species, of which carbonaceous fraction is of utmost importance. Carbonaceous fraction encompasses organic carbon (OC) and elemental carbon (EC). These are released into the atmosphere as aerosols due to various activities, including traffic, construction, biomass burning, and coal combustion emissions. In this study, we have attempted to make a carbonaceous source profile of nine primary emission sources, primarily categorised under traffic and combustion sources present in the coal capital city of India - Dhanbad.

METHODS

Source-specific sampling is carried out primarily for traffic emissions, combustion sources, and construction-related activity in Dhanbad city. Traffic samplings were done for urban traffic (UT) and Mine traffic (MT). A diesel concrete mixer (DCM) was sampled for construction emissions in an active construction site. For combustion sources, locally burned sources were sampled. Since coal is not burned individually, it was combined with other sources and sampled. The sampled sources are - Garbage Burning (GB), Wood Burning (WB), Cow Dung Burning (CDB), Mixed Fuel 1 (MF1) - soft coke and wood burning, Mixed Fuel 2 (MF2) - soft coke and cow dung burning, Mixed Fuel 3 (MF3) - raw coal and cow dung burning. The samples were collected on 47mm Quartz Filter paper using a dual-channel sampler consisting of a Wins impactor capable of collecting PM_{2.5}. The Quartz filter papers were then analysed for carbonaceous matter using the procedure described in earlier published works (Izhar et al., 2020a).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1 summarises the variation of the carbonaceous fraction of PM_{2.5} in different sources. Among the carbonaceous fractions of PM_{2.5}, OC was found to be in relatively higher concentration in combustion sources when compared to traffic and constructional sources, ranging from 92.8% (MF2) to 97.1%(CDB) in combustion emissions and 60%(UT) to 84.5%(DCM) in traffic emissions. Diagnostic ratios, including OC/EC and CharEC/SootEC (Figure 1 B), showed similar trends for different sources, with combustion sources having higher values relative to traffic and construction emissions. The EC fraction concentration determines Char-EC (CEC= EC1) and Soot-EC (SEC= EC2+EC3) levels. We found that OC is majorly contributed from low-temperature combustion sources while EC primarily comes from relatively higher-temperature engine exhaust. EC2 and OC4 are a marker of traffic emissions, while OC1 and EC2 are primary source markers for combustion sources. On the other hand, OC1 and OC3 are markers of GB, and OC1 and EC1 are markers for WB, CDB as well as MF3. Coal combustion showed different markers when burned with different mixtures.

Figure

re 1: A) Relative Distribution of carbonaceous fraction present in different sources. B) Diagnostics (OC/EC vs CEC/SEC) ratios in different sources present in the study.

MF1 had OC1 and EC2 while EC2 and OC3 for MF2. It is often used for identification sources (Izhar et al., 2020b). Higher levels of EC2 were found in traffic sources compared to combustion sources. Notably, CDB showed the highest ratios for both diagnostic ratios. Other local sources, such as GB and WB, also had higher diagnostic ratios than the reported literature (Sheesley et al., 2003). The combination of different fuels has a significant role in their emission as well as source markers. Relative source markers are used for source apportionment studies, and having a local emission profile is much more crucial.

CONCLUSIONS

The study has generated the thermal carbon profile of the emissions obtained from traffic (urban and Mine), construction, and combustion (garbage, wood, cow dung, soft coke and wood, soft coke and cow dung, and raw coal and cow dung burning) sources present, which contribute substantially to PM_{2.5} mass in Dhnabad. Carbon fractions showed distinct heterogeneity across source emission types and will be useful in resolving combustion sources. OC/EC and CEC/SEC ratios show contrasting patterns for traffic and combustion emissions, which can be used for source identification. These findings are significant for the Indian environmental database, enriching our understanding of the intricate interplay between emission sources and carbonaceous profile.

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AEROSOL MORPHOLOGY AND ITS ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OVER A TROPICAL SEMI-ARID REGION, KADAPA (14.47°N, 78.71°E, 138m asl)-INDIA.

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Keywords: Aerosol Characterization, SEM-EDS, Particle Morphology, Elemental Composition.

INTRODUCTION

Aerosols are important atmospheric trace constituent that interacts with solar and terrestrial radiation and influence the energy balance of the Earth-Atmosphere system. The role of aerosols in atmospheric radiation budget and a possible climatic impact has been recognized for a long time. Atmospheric aerosols play an important role in the global climate system through modifications of the global radiation budget: directly, by Scattering and Absorption of radiation; indirectly, by the Modification of cloud properties; and abundance via the modification of the thermal structure of the atmosphere and the surface energy budget. The impact of aerosol Morphology on Radiative properties has been a vital component to better understand the Earth-Climate System. For accurate estimation of aerosol radiative properties, deeper insight into the origin, transport, Morphological characteristics and Elemental compositions of individual particles is crucial because these particles are constantly restructured through coagulation, humidification, scavenging by precipitation and gas to particle conversion which modify the aerosol system. The radiative properties of an aerosol population depend further on the aerosol mixing state, that is the degree to which the chemical components occur as independent particles (external mixing) as compared to a component mixture in each individual particle (internal mixing). A number of factors complicate the understanding of aerosol absorption, even at the local scale. This arises mainly because of the large heterogeneity (spatial and temporal) in their properties (physical and chemical composition). Near the surface, where the boundary layer process is active, the variabilities in aerosol characteristics are considerably higher, primarily because of the large diversity in the sources and sinks of aerosols, their short atmospheric residence-time and also due to transport processes.

MONITORING SITE

In the southern portion of peninsular India, the monitoring site is a tropical semi-arid rural station located next to the highway, about 10 miles (15 km) west of the city of Kadapa. The actual measurements have been carried out on the roof of Sir C.V. Raman Science block, Department of Physics, situated in the premises of Yogi Vemana University (YVU: Latitude:14.47°N, Longitude:78.71°E, 138 m asl) campus, Kadapa. Being far away from east and west coasts, this region is deprived of the full benefits of both the monsoons and consequently droughts are frequently experienced here. This region endowed with rich mineral wealth, is one of the important and fairly well studied geological units in peninsular India. There are many mining centers and cement industries in and around this proposed study region. Twenty-five percent of the world's barite resources are present within the basin. Electrical instruments industries are also established in the region. Several cement industries are located here because of the availability of limestone in the region.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Ambient Sampling

Through Gravimetric analysis, TSPM samples were collected by using a High volume air Sampler (DFHV-1E) on Whatman Quartz fibre filter(47mm) for a period of one year (2021) over a Tropical Semi-arid Environment (14.47°N, 78.71°E, 138m asl), Kadapa in Southern Peninsular India. Over the last two decades, SEM-EDS technique has become an extensive tool to characterize the Morphology and Chemical Composition of single aerosol particles which are one among the crucial parameters. Since a detailed investigation is required to understand the connections and dependencies between the Morphology and Radiative properties of aerosols for accurate understanding of their Health, Climate and Radiative effects. In this study, SEM (Model: JSM-IT500) coupled with EDS has been used for investigating Morphology and Elemental Composition of Total Suspended Particulate Matter (TSPM). Over the sampling period all the TSPM samples were statistically analysed from which the samples with Maximum and Minimum TSPM concentration were selected for SEM-EDS analysis. The Elemental analysis was carried-out using EDS system, capable of collecting spectrum of the sample with a 60s of capture time.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The TSPM samples were investigated for Particle Morphology and Relative abundance of elements. The SEM-EDS results displayed variation in Morphology and Mineralogy due to Varied sources and prevailing provincial climatic conditions and pollution levels. The Morphology varied from Regular to Irregular structures with several agglomerates and a few spherical particles. Fig.1 (a), (b) shows the Particle Morphology during high and low concentration sample periods with Grossular(Ca rich), Rod like(Si rich), Spherical(C rich), Chain like(C rich) and agglomerates structures. The Elemental Analysis(figure2) illustrated during pre-monsoon (high concentration)season it was found to have major contributing particle groups of aluminium-silicates(Al-Si-O) along with Ca rich(Ca-C-O), Si rich(Si-O-Al-Mg) and Irregular Agglomerate particles(C-S-Ca-Fe-O) with a few other structures possessing mineral elements and during Monsoon (low concentration) a very low abundance of particles was seen as shown in Fig1.(b) with Aluminium-silicates(Al-Si-O) and Ca rich(Ca-C-O) added to that a few other mineral particles were contributed as shown. In Fig.2 (a) EDS spectra of blank quartz fiber filter is presented so as to analyze the influence of loaded particles and its Elemental Composition. From Fig 2(b) it is depicted that during the pre-monsoon season the influence of particles with Si, O (~50%) presence was majorly due to particle abundance and after which C(~10%), and Ca, Mn, Mg, Al, Pb, Na, Fe, Cl, and N equally likely contributing. From Fig 2(c), sample witnessed the presence of Si, O(83%), with high percentage contribution due to fiber filter constituents while Ca, C(~4), N, S(3%), Al, Cu(2%), Mg, Na, Fe was having negligible contribution during Monsoon. It is crucial to understand that during both the sampling events elements such as Si, O were due to either particle abundance or filter constituents and other elements were quite common but the contribution has huge variation over the periods. All the analyzed samples were associated with 'O', since there exists a strong probability that these elements are present in the form of Oxides, Sulphates and Carbonates. Simultaneously 'Si' is quite common in the samples mainly due to soil crust and anthropogenic activities. The other elements like Al, Na, Ca, may be originated from the burning of agricultural residuals.

CONCLUSION:

The Morphology and Elemental composition studies revealed that TSPM had varied shapes, and Sizes. While EDS spectra indicated major particle groups i.e., Si rich(Si-O) particles, Ca rich(Ca-Si-O) and Aluminium-silicates (Al-Si-O) with others elements like C, Ca, Mn, Mg, Al, Na, Fe, Cl on the basis of their percentage contribution.

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**EXCEEDANCE AND METEOROLOGICAL IMPACT ON PM_{2.5} OVER A SEMI-ARID REGION
KADAPA- INDIA.**

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Keywords: Fine Particulate Matter (PM_{2.5}), NAAQS, Optical Particle Counter, ECMWF.

INTRODUCTION

Particle pollution, a subset of air pollution, is of major concern due to its deleterious effects. Particulate Matter (PM) is a mixture of Solid and Liquid Particles in air that varies in size, shape and Composition. The size distribution of PM provides important information of their effect on atmospheric processes and radiative forcing estimation. PM may be classified on the basis of Aerodynamic diameter: PM₁₀ ($D_p < 10\mu\text{m}$) as Coarse mode, and PM_{2.5} ($D_p < 2.5\mu\text{m}$) as fine mode. Due to their tiny size, PM_{2.5} particles are more readily inhaled and have the ability to penetrate the alveoli of the respiratory system, leading to a variety of health problems. On global and regional level, PM_{2.5} is the leading risk factor which needs particulate monitoring to analyze the pollution levels in both urban and rural atmosphere. PM_{2.5} pollution is mainly responsible for environmental degradation, an array of health disorders like respiratory and cardiovascular symptoms, visual impairment, mortality and morbidity. Air Pollution is currently India's the second-largest public health threat after child and maternal malnutrition. Based on yearly average population-weighted PM_{2.5} values, India was rated third and fifth most polluted countries in the world in 2020 and 2021, respectively (IQAir 2020,2021). Due to India's growing population and fast urbanization, PM_{2.5} concentrations will be expected to substantially degrade air quality in the future decades. The major objective of the present research work is to get a better understanding of the features of regional atmospheric aerosols utilizing an optical particle counter.

STUDY AREA

The present analysis was carried out at Yogi Vemana University, Kadapa (YVU; 14.47°N, 78.82°E, 138 m above sea level), for two winter seasons i.e., Winter 2019-20 and Winter 2020-21. The observational site, Kadapa is a tropical semi-arid station located in the southern part of India in the state of Andhra Pradesh. It is an active station under the Aerosol Radiative Forcing over India (ARFI) network of stations. Kadapa is situated about 8 km to the south of Penna River and is surrounded by the Nallamala (40 km) and the Palakonda hills (25 km) on its three sides. The University is situated adjacent to the highway and is about 15 km west of the main city of Kadapa, where automobile and vehicular emissions are the principal sources of air pollution. In addition, there are several brick kilns and some small-scale cement and electrical industries around the observational site within a 30 km radius.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Continuous PM measurements were done at Kadapa tropical semi-arid region in southern Peninsular India to explore the temporal aspects. The instrument utilized in this study is a Lightweight Lighthouse Handheld 3016-IAQ Optical Particle Counter, featuring Mass Concentration Mode that approximates density in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ providing up to 6 particle size channels (0.3, 0.5, 1.0, 2.5, 5.0, 10.0 μm) of simultaneous counting having 0.1 CFM (2.83 LPM) flow rate. The instrument uses a laser-diode light source and collection optics for particle detection. The rapport between PM_{2.5} concentrations and the meteorological parameters has been examined for better understanding the influence of these meteorological parameters on PM_{2.5} mass concentrations. The hourly averaged meteorological data was obtained from the ECMWF (European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Variation and Exceedance analysis of PM_{2.5} concentration.

The variation of PM_{2.5} concentration between winter 2019-20 (December 2019 to February 2020) and winter 2020-21 (December 2020 to February 2021) is shown in figure 1 (a). When compared to the average PM_{2.5} concentration of winter 2019-20 ($27.7\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), we observed that the average PM_{2.5} concentration of winter 2020-21 ($44.6\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) had increased by 61%. The local emission sources such as Agriculture residue burning activities, vehicular and industrial activities and the yearly variability in the impact of meteorological parameters on fine particulate matter may be the reason for this significant increase in PM_{2.5} pollution. And also, we investigated the daily mean PM_{2.5} concentration of these two winter seasons to study how many days PM_{2.5} pollution exceeded the NAAQS standard value ($60\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ -24 hour mean) (NAAQS, 2019). From figure

1(b), we have identified that only one day during winter 2019–20 exceeded the NAAQS standard value, but during winter 2020–21, a total of 16 days exceeded the NAAQS standard value.

Impact of Meteorological parameters on PM_{2.5} concentration.

The impact of meteorological parameters such as Temperature, Relative Humidity, Wind Speed, and Boundary Layer Height on PM_{2.5} concentration during winter 2019-20(December 2019 to February 2020) and winter 2020-21(December 2020 to February 2021)is shown in Figure 2(a) and 2(b). These two figures 2(a) and 2(b) clearly show that temperature, wind speed, and boundary layer height have a negative impact and relative humidity has a positive impact on PM pollution during the two winter periods.The correlation coefficients between PM_{2.5} and the meteorological parameters across Winter 2019-20 and Winter 2020-21 are listed in Table 1.

Table.1 Correlation analysis between PM_{2.5}and Meteorological parameters.

Seasons	PM _{2.5} µg/m ³	Correlation Coefficient - R ²			
		Temperature (°C)	Relative Humidity (%)	Wind Speed (m/s)	Boundary Layer Height (m)
Winter 2019-20	27.7	-0.76	0.78	-0.26	-0.54
Winter 2020-21	44.6	-0.87	0.9	-0.61	-0.68

CONCLUSIONS

This study presents theanalysis of the variability in PM_{2.5} concentration, exceedance analysis and the impact of meteorological parameters on PM_{2.5}pollution across winter 2019-20 and winter 2020-21 over the Kadapa region. According to these observations we have concluded that the during Winter 2020-21 period PM_{2.5} pollution was highly emitted compared to the Winter 2019-20 period PM_{2.5}pollution and meteorological parameters also more strongly related to the PM_{2.5} during Winter 2020-21 period compared to Winter 2019-20 period.

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PHYSICAL AND OPTICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF AEROSOLS OVER ASIA: AERONET, MERRA-2 AND CAMS

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Keywords: Aerosol characterization, AERONET Observations, MERRA-2 and CAMS simulations, Asia.

INTRODUCTION

The recent observations revealed a significant decrease in aerosol optical depth (AOD) over East Asia and a persistent increase in AOD over South Asia during the last two decades, which created an Asian aerosol dipole (Samset et al., 2019; Ramachandran et al., 2020). These recent aerosol trends over Asia are not well captured by the latest climate models (Ramachandran et al., 2022). The simulation and future prediction of aerosol impact on climate may not be highly accurate over Asia due to rapidly changing aerosol emissions, inefficiency in capturing the aerosol trends, and the non-availability of regional distribution of columnar aerosol parameters based on high-quality observational datasets on a seasonal scale. For the first time, this study examines the spatial variation of columnar aerosol optical and physical characteristics on a seasonal and annual scale over a total of 41 Aerosol Robotic Network (AERONET) observational sites covering a large extent of Asia, e.g., South, South-East, and East Asia, during the recent 5-year (2015-2019, before COVID-19 lockdowns). The seasonal and annual validation of Modern-Era Retrospective Analysis for Research and Applications-2 (MERRA-2) and Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) simulated AOD with AERONET measured AOD is also performed over each observational site to examine the model performance over Asia.

METHODS

This study utilizes the most updated level 2, version 3 cloud-screened, quality-assured, and calibrated AERONET measured all data points of AOD, Ångström exponent (AE), fine mode fraction (FMF), and volume size distribution (VSD) (Holben et al., 2001) over Asia during 2015-2019. A total of 41 sites in Asia are included, where all optical and physical aerosol parameters are available, covering all four seasons with ≥ 9 months in at least a year. MERRA-2 ($0.5^\circ \times 0.625^\circ$) simulated 1-hourly and CAMS ($0.75^\circ \times 0.75^\circ$) simulated 3-hourly AODs are utilized for the collocated comparison with AERONET measured AOD over Asia.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The spatial distribution of AERONET and model simulated AODs reveal that AOD is relatively higher (>0.4) over South Asia, especially over the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP), compared to other regions on annual and seasonal scale due to high anthropogenic activities and transport of dust aerosols (Fig 1a-1c). During winter and post-monsoon, higher local anthropogenic activities and intense crop-residue burning lead to an increase in AE and FMF, and during pre-monsoon and monsoon, transport of coarse mineral dust and sea salt particles results in a decrease in AE and FMF over South Asia. Over East Asia, North China Plain (NCP) is the major source of anthropogenic aerosols due to higher fossil-fuel combustion and biomass burning. Dust is transported over East Asia during pre-monsoon, leading to lower AE. During monsoon, AOD (>0.5) is observed to be higher over East China due to the hygroscopic growth of fine aerosols. In South-East Asia, AOD (>0.5) is relatively higher during the biomass burning period, e.g., over Indochina Peninsula and Maritime continent during pre-monsoon and post-monsoon, respectively. The performance of CAMS in simulating AOD is better over East Asia and South-East Asia ($R^2 > 0.7$). MERRA-2 AOD underestimates ($\sim 20\%$) AERONET AOD over South Asia (Fig. 1d), whereas CAMS is less biased ($< 10\%$) (Fig. 1i). The probability distribution reveals that the underestimation in MERRA-2 AOD is higher for higher AOD (>0.75) conditions (Fig. 1e-1h), whereas CAMS performs better for higher AOD conditions (Fig. 1j-1m).

CONCLUSIONS

The seasonal and annual scale analysis of columnar aerosol properties clearly reveals the significant spatial and seasonal variation in AOD, AE, and FMF over Asia, with a relatively higher AOD over South Asia. Fine mode aerosols dominate over South-East Asia, followed by East Asia. The collocated comparison of model

Figure 1: Annual mean (a) AERONET observed aerosol optical depth ($AOD_{0.55}$), (b) MERRA-2 and (c) CAMS simulated AOD over Asia. (d) The error (in %) in MERRA-2 AOD with respect to AERONET AOD, and the probability distribution of difference between MERRA-2 and AERONET AOD (e-h) over Central, South, South-East Asia, and East Asia. (i) The error (in %) in CAMS AOD with respect to AERONET AOD, and the probability distribution of difference between CAMS and AERONET AOD (j-m) over Central, South, South-East Asia, and East Asia.

AOD with AERONET observed AOD clearly reveals that the performance of CAMS is better than MERRA-2 over Asia. For higher AOD conditions, the underestimation of MERRA-2 AOD is higher compared to CAMS AOD. The seasonal-scale analysis of columnar aerosol characteristics over an aerosol hotspot region with the validation of two highly spatially resolved models will help to improve aerosol processes and parameterization in models, which has significant radiative and climatic implications of aerosols over Asia.

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**HEAVY METALS AND OXIDATIVE POTENTIAL OF PM_{1.0} AND PM_{2.5} IN DIFFERENT
REGIONS OF AGRA, INDIA**

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KEYWORDS: Oxidative Potential, Heavy metal concentration, Ambient air, Particulate matter

INTRODUCTION

Fine particulate matter PM_{2.5} and PM_{1.0} in the ambient atmosphere are of significant research interest due to their inimical effects on humans. A prolonged exposure to fine particulate matter can lead symptoms ranging from mild respiratory difficulties to severe issues. Particulate matter compositions such as organic carbon (OC), element carbon (EC), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAHs), and toxic metals are strongly associated with reactive oxygen species (ROS) (a major indicator for oxidative potential) generation in human cells (Brook et al., 2010). The highest attention has been concentrated on the metals, especially for heavy metals such as Hg, Ni, Cu, Pb, Cd, Zn, Cr, As, V, and Mn (Santo Signorelli et al., 2019, Moradi et al., 2020). The ability of PM to induce oxidative stress in target molecules is defined as the Oxidative potential(OP) (Fang et al., 2016). The excessive production of ROS leads to oxidative stress, destroys the normal physiological redox regulation function of cells, and causes cell death and genotoxic effects (Fu, Xia, Hwang, Ray, & Yu, 2014; Kramer et al., 2021). Oxidative potential induced oxidative stress is one of the most plausible pathophysiological mechanisms to explain the association of PM exposure and occurrence of respiratory infections, lung cancer, and chronic cardiopulmonary diseases. Mediated by excess ROS including hydroxyl radicals (OH[•]), hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), and superoxide (O₂⁻) oxidative stress can result in injury to cells and tissues in the respiratory tract (Fang et al., 2019). This study may be helpful for evaluating the potential health risks of PM_{1.0} & PM_{2.5}, providing a scientific basis for the management and control of atmospheric particulate matters.

METHODOLOGY

Sampling was carried out in winter season in Agra city at three different locations urban, roadside and rural site. Particulate matter samples were collected by Sioutas cascade impactor using low-volume air samplers operating at a flow rate of 9 L/min. the duration of sampling was 6 hours in a day. The mass of the PM_{1.0} and PM_{2.5} were determined by the difference in weights before and after sampling. For the analysis of metals, acid extraction was carried out (Rohra et al., 2018). In acid extraction method, metals will be extracted from filter paper, which was used in air sampler for the collection of particulate matter. Filter paper was digested in a 5-10 ml analytical grade HNO₃ and HCl (1:3) in an 50ml Erlenmeyer flask and keeping them on a hot plate at 40-60°C for 90 minutes till clear solution obtained. Now this clear solution diluted up to 20 ml with distilled water and stored in refrigerator (4°C) until analysis. The metal analysis was done by Inductive Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS). For analyzing DTT, a slightly modified procedure of Cho et al., 2005 was used. The time-dependent DTT consumption was measured in 15 min time intervals (from 0 to 90 min). The water extracts with a known PM mass were incubated at 37°C with DTT (100 µM) in 0.1 M potassium phosphate buffer at pH 7.4 (1 mL total volume). After the incubation, 100 µL of 10% trichloroacetic acid was added to stop the reaction. An aliquot of 0.5 mL of the reaction mixture was taken and then mixed with 1 mL of 0.4 M Tris-HCl (pH 8.9) containing 20 mM ethylene diamine tetra-acetic acid (EDTA). Finally, this reaction mixture was shaken for 30 s after the addition of 25 µL of 10 mM, 5,5'-dithiobis-2-nitrobenzoic acid (DTNB). The concentration of the formed 2-nitro-5-thiobenzoic acid (TNB) product was measured spectro-photometrically at 412 nm. Since such a reaction is sensitive to light (Eyer et al., 2003), the whole experiment was done in the dark.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 depicts the mass concentrations of PM_{1.0} and PM_{2.5} during winter season collected in outdoor air in Agra city at three different locations urban, roadside and rural. The overall average mean concentration of PM_{1.0} at urban, roadside and rural were 27.78 µg/m³, 15.278 µg/m³ and 97.22 µg/m³ respectively. The overall average mean concentration of PM_{2.5} at urban, roadside and rural were 69.42 µg/m³, 51.38 µg/m³ and 288.89 µg/m³ respectively. This results indicates that the average mass concentration of PM_{1.0} and PM_{2.5} in rural site was significantly higher than urban and roadside area. Figure 2 represents metal concentration of PM_{1.0} and PM_{2.5}. According to study results, mean concentrations of heavy metals for PM_{1.0} at urban, rural and roadside were 2.43 µg/m³, 3.79 µg/m³ and 1.58 µg/m³ respectively. Mean concentrations of heavy metals for PM_{2.5} at urban, rural and roadside were 2.18 µg/m³, 2.14 µg/m³ and 4.48 µg/m³ respectively. Above results illustrate that total mean concentration of heavy metals for PM_{1.0} was higher at roadside and for PM_{2.5} was higher at rural site. Figure 3 shows the average activity values of DTT water soluble, volume normalized (DTTv), and water-soluble, mass-normalized (DTTm) of PM_{1.0} and PM_{2.5} during winter season at urban, roadside and rural sites in Agra, City of Taj. For PM_{1.0} the average activity values of OP- DTTv and OP-DTTm at urban, roadside and rural were 285.58 pmol min⁻¹m⁻³, 298.31 pmol min⁻¹m⁻³, 168.29 pmol min⁻¹m⁻³ and 10.28 pmol min⁻¹µg⁻¹, 20.68 pmol min⁻¹µg⁻¹, 1.73 pmol min⁻¹µg⁻¹ respectively. For PM_{2.5} the average activity values of OP-DTTv and OP-DTTm at urban, roadside and rural were 346.23 pmol min⁻¹m⁻³, 269.04 pmol min⁻¹m⁻³, 171.40 pmol min⁻¹m⁻³ and 5.26 pmol min⁻¹µg⁻¹, 5.29 pmol min⁻¹µg⁻¹, 0.59 pmol min⁻¹µg⁻¹ respectively. This results reveals that OP-DTTv and OP-DTTm for PM_{1.0} was found higher at roadside site. For PM_{2.5} OP-DTTv was found higher at urban site whereas OP-DTTm was higher at roadside site.

CONCLUSION

The aim of the study was to explore Particulate Matter (PM) concentration, its chemical characteristics and oxidative potential of PM_{1.0} and PM_{2.5} at different locations as urban, roadside and rural site in Agra city. PM_{2.5} and PM_{1.0} concentrations were found higher at rural site. Heavy metal concentration for PM_{1.0} followed the order roadside > urban > rural and for PM_{2.5} order was rural > urban > roadside respectively. The mean concentration values of OP-DTTv and OP-DTTm for PM_{1.0} was maximum at roadside while mean concentration values of OP-DTTv and OP-DTTm for PM_{2.5} was maximum at urban and roadside respectively.

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CHARACTERISTICS OF SIZE-SEGREGATED PARTICLE NUMBER CONCENTRATIONS IN AN URBAN LOCATION IN INDIA

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Keywords: ULTRAFINE PARTICLES, SIZE-SEGREGATED PARTICLES, NEW PARTICLE FORMATION, GROWTH, URBAN ENVIRONMENT

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols exhibit considerable variability in size, spanning a broad range with a difference of four orders of magnitude between the smallest and largest particles. The spatiotemporal heterogeneity in natural and anthropogenic emission sources results in significant variability in aerosol properties, making it extremely hard to precisely quantify aerosol's climatic effect (Costabile et al., 2009; Kerminen et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2015). New particle formation (NPF, via gas-to-particle conversion) is the largest source of aerosol numbers to the terrestrial atmosphere, and therefore ultrafine particles (Kulmala et al., 2012, Sebastian et al., 2022). Further, the growth of primary particles can significantly alter the total aerosol mass and composition (Gunthe et al., 2021; Mishra et al., 2023) which has implications for Earth's radiation budget and hydrological cycle via aerosol's direct and indirect effect, respectively. In the Indian context, NPF has largely been unexplored in the absence of state-of-the-art instrumentation to characterize atmospheric NPF (Kanawade et al., 2022). The main objective of this study is to quantitatively assess the role of NPF in the size-segregated particle number concentration in an urban location, Hyderabad.

METHODS

In this study, we have used long-term (2019-2022) data of particle number size distribution measured by the nano Condensation Nucleus Counter (nCNC) in the size range of 1 to 3 nm and the Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS) in the size range from 10 nm to 514 nm. Measurements were conducted in the University of Hyderabad campus site (17.46°N, 78.32°E; ~542m above mean sea level). The observation days were broadly categorized into three event types, namely NPF, non-event and undefined based on visual inspection of the contour plot of particle number size distributions, following the procedure outlined by Dal Maso et al. (2005). We additionally utilized in-situ measurements of particulate matter with a diameter smaller than 2.5 μm ($\text{PM}_{2.5}$) to identify polluted days following the NAAQS criteria (days with $\text{PM}_{2.5} > 60 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). The size-segregated particle number concentrations in the cluster mode (sub-3nm), nucleation mode (10-25 nm), Aitken mode (25-100 nm), and accumulation mode (100-514 nm) were calculated for each identified event type.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The size-segregated particle number concentrations showed a distinct seasonal pattern, with the highest particle number concentrations during the pre-monsoon months (March - May) and the lowest during the winter months (December - February) (Figure 1). The highest particle number concentrations in the pre-monsoon season coincide with the highest frequency of NPF event occurrence. Amongst them, the cluster-mode particles constituted the largest fraction of particle number concentrations and the accumulation-mode particles constituted the lowest. The cluster mode particle number concentrations were found to be the highest during NPF event days than other event types. The positive association between cluster mode particles and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ indicates that NPF is not inhibited at high pre-existing particle concentrations unlike in the USA and Europe (Figure 2). This further suggests that the balance between the precursor vapor concentrations and the pre-existing particle concentrations decides when NPF will trigger in the polluted boundary layer under given atmospheric conditions. However, the negative association between nucleation mode particles and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ suggests that not all cluster mode particles grow to nucleation mode size. Further, the seasonal variation in size-segregated particle number concentrations is presented.

Figure 1. Monthly percentage of occurrence of NPF, non-event polluted and undefined events days based on total valid observations days at Hyderabad during 1 April 2019 to 7 December 2022.

Figure 2. Correlation between $PM_{2.5}$ concentration and particle number concentration in each mode during winter season (December-February).

CONCLUSIONS

The following are the major conclusions drawn from this study

- The formation of cluster mode particles is not inhibited in an urban polluted environment, while only a small fraction grows to the nucleation mode size range, indicating either small clusters are lost to large pre-existing particles (winter) or unavailability of precursor vapors for the growth of small cluster to nucleation mode and larger size (pre-monsoon).
- Our results underline the critical importance of NPF studies in the Indian context, which has implications for human health (ultrafine particles) and climate (newly formed particles can reach cloud condensation nuclei active sizes).

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AEROSOL CHARACTERIZATION OVER INDIA USING SKYNET RADIOMETER NETWORK OF IMD

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Keywords: AEROSOLS, OPTICAL PROPERTIES, MICRO-PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS, CLOUDS, SINGLE SCATTERING ALBEDO

INTRODUCTION

There are several ground-based networks (SKYNET, AERONET, CARSNET, MPLNET, EARLINET, ARFINET etc.) for aerosol studies across the globe. In the Asian region, AERONET, SKYNET, CAESNET and ARFINET are the maximum of the users among the ground-based networks. The India Meteorological Department (IMD), functioning under the Ministry of Earth Sciences (MOES), GoI, has established a network composed of Prede Sun-Sky Radiometers in June 2011 for aerosol characterization over different environments to assess their impact on weather, health, and climate. In the present communication, the results of the network observations carried out over Delhi (urban) and Visakhapatnam (coastal) during 2019, 2020 and 2021, are discussed with an aim to (i) examine the aerosol characteristics over contrasting environments and (ii) investigate the aerosol loading of pre-, during and post-COVID 19 phases due to various human interventions / anthropogenic activities.

METHODS

The sun-sky radiometer is a narrow-band filter photometer that measures direct solar and diffuse sky radiation at selected wavelengths and at several scattering angles. Figure 1 depicts the network of Prede sun-sky radiometers at different geographical locations associated with different environments in India. The subset shows the instrument and associated sub-systems. The data archival, retrieval and analysis procedures have been explained elsewhere (Nakajima *et al.*, 2020; Kudo *et al.*, 2021). Intercomparison experiments to calibrate and validate the products of SKYNET observations with those of GNSS/GPS and

AERONET sun-sky radiometers have been reported in the literature (Devara *et al.*, 2013; Campanelli *et al.*, 2018).

Figure 1. Prede Sun-Sky Radiometer Network in India

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The results from two typical experimental sites of the Network stations, namely, Delhi (DLH) and Visakhapatnam (VSP) associated with urban and coastal environments, respectively, during the period from 2019 to 2021, better suitable for studying the impact of COVID19 and its impact on air quality and human health and the associated mitigation methods.

It is clear from Fig. 2 that the AODs exhibit higher values at VSP as compared to those at DLH, which could be due to dominance of coarse-mode maritime aerosol particles. The AE values show larger (dominance of fine-mode particles) over an urban station, DLH as compared to those over the coastal station, VSP, where they are smaller (dominance of bigger particles). The SSA are greater (more absorbing particles) over DLH as

Figure 2. Monthly mean variations with error bars in Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) (a), Angstrom Exponent (AE) (b), Single Scattering Albedo (SSA) (c), and Asymmetry Parameter (ASY) (d) over DLH and VSP during 2019-2021.

compared to VSP (more scattering particles). The average AP values are dominant over DLH (dry and near to non-spherical) as compared to VSP (wet and near spherical). It may be noted here that the data need more treatment for cloud screening to remove the multiple scattering effects. The results from the data archived over the remaining sites, considered in the present study, will also be discussed in the paper.

CONCLUSIONS

The results show the efficacy of the India-SKYNET not only for satellite data validation as ground-truth but also to devise mitigation methods to achieve the climate sustainability.

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INTRA- AND INTER-CITY VARIABILITY OF OUTDOOR PM_{2.5} AND CARBONACEOUS FRACTIONS OUTSIDE URBAN RESIDENCE IN INDIA

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Keywords: PM_{2.5}, Organic carbon, Elemental carbon, APEAL Study.

INTRODUCTION

Particulate matter (PM) having an aerodynamic diameter equal to or less than 2.5µm enters deep inside the lungs, causing adverse health problems such as asthma, bronchitis, cardiovascular disease as well as, visibility deterioration, and climate impacts (Pope *et al.*, 2009; Kumar and Krishna 2017; de Prado Bert *et al.*, 2018; Raparathi and Phuleria, 2021). Carbonaceous aerosols are a significant fraction (~10-70%) of PM_{2.5}, which include organic carbon (OC) and elemental carbon (EC), are important aerosol constituents due to their adverse impacts on human health and radiative forcing (Hayes *et al.*, 2019). In rapidly growing economies such as India, exposure to PM_{2.5} is a primary concern due to their significant heterogeneity. Thus, it became essential to understand the characteristics of PM_{2.5} and its constituents at a regional and local level. This study is part of the APEAL (Longitudinal Effects of Air Pollution Exposure on Adolescents Lungs), a prospective cohort study in multiple cities of India. In this pilot study, our primary aim is to understand the inter and intracity variation of outdoor PM_{2.5} and its chemical characteristics in four geographically divergent cities in India.

METHODS

This pilot study measured 24-hour exposures of PM_{2.5} in 7-9 homes across four Indian cities, Delhi, Mumbai, Bangalore, and Mysore, using portable low-volume air samplers for seven days during May 2022. All loaded quartz filters underwent thermal/optical carbon analysis to measure OC and EC using the IMPROVE-A protocol (Interagency Monitoring of PROtected Visual Environments) and a multi-wavelength OC-EC analyzer (DRI Model 2015) (Raparathi and Phuleria, 2021). The study sites were selected based on their proximity to major roads and further categorized into traffic-exposed and urban background sites. During the sampling, demographic and household activity-related information was also collected from the residents through a structured questionnaire.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

PM_{2.5} Concentrations

The weekly PM_{2.5} mean ± SD levels for Mumbai, Bangalore, Mysore and Delhi were 57.2 ± 12.8 µg/m³, 53.0 ± 9.0 µg/m³, 32.3 ± 9.3 µg/m³, and 90.4 ± 12.0 µg/m³ (Figure 1). The different intensities of emission sources, such as vehicular traffic and meteorological differences among the cities, likely drive these levels. Mean residential outdoor PM_{2.5} in all cities is significantly higher than the fixed-site regulatory monitoring station levels, implying the underestimation of PM exposure while utilizing the central fixed-site data (Figure 1). Result indicated that there were multiple days in Mumbai and Bangalore when the daily PM_{2.5} levels exceeded the standard (60 µg/m³), while Mysore only had one violation. On the other hand, Delhi exceeded the standard for all days. Comparatively higher heterogeneity is observed in the PM_{2.5} among the homes in Mysore, with an average coefficient of divergence (COD) of 0.29 compared to the other three cities (COD = < 0.14 for all three). For Mumbai and Bangalore, there were a few days when daily PM_{2.5} levels exceeded the daily PM_{2.5} standard (60 µg/m³), whereas Mysore had only one such violation while daily PM_{2.5} exceeded the standard for all days in Delhi. Comparatively higher heterogeneity is observed in the PM_{2.5} among the homes in Mysore (average COD = 0.29) and compared to the other three cities (COD = < 0.14 for all three of them). No significant differences were found between the seven-day average and daily PM_{2.5} levels for most sites across all cities (p-value >0.05).

Figure 1. Residential outdoor daily PM_{2.5} concentrations in different cities along with the concurrent fixed site regulatory monitoring station measurements.

Elemental and Organic Carbon

The highest OC and EC were in Delhi, which is ($15.4 \pm 4.7 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $5.0 \pm 2.8 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively) which were similar to Bangalore (13.4 ± 9.3 and $4.8 \pm 1.9 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), while Mysore exhibits the lowest levels (30% of Delhi levels). OC and EC contribute 16-18% and 4-6% of the PM_{2.5} mass, respectively. The OC/EC ratios vary similarly (3.0-3.9) for the four cities, implying the contribution of fossil fuels (through vehicular emissions) in all cities. The OC/EC ratios at some homes were very high, likely due to biomass burning (coconut shells and wood burning), which was also reported during our sampling.

CONCLUSIONS

Our data suggests that outdoor residential exposures to PM_{2.5} likely exceed the levels obtained from regulatory fixed site locations and vehicular sources impact the exposures in all cities regardless of the magnitude of PM levels. Our data also shows that daily outdoor PM_{2.5} reasonably represents weekly air pollution exposures in all these cities. Additional analyses are currently being conducted to understand the effect of meteorology and the relationship between different carbonaceous fractions.

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ANALYSIS OF NEW PARTICLE FORMATION EVENTS AND FAVORABLE CONDITIONS AT A HIGH-ALTITUDE LOCATION

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Keywords: AEROSOL SIZE DISTRIBUTION, NPF, GROWTH RATE, FAVORABLE CONDITIONS, WESTERN HIMALAYAN REGION.

INTRODUCTION

The process through which tiny particles, especially nanometer size, are produced and grow from gaseous precursors in the atmosphere is known as new particle formation (NPF). NPF is the largest source of aerosol number concentration in the atmosphere (Maso et al., 2005; Kulmala et al., 2013; Zhang et al., 2012; Sebastian et al., 2021). The freshly new formed particles participate after grow nucleation mode to Aitken mode in cloud formation through condensational growth and coagulation scavenging (Kamra et al., 2015; Das et al., 2023). In this study, NPF events identified in the aerosol size distribution measured with a NanoScan SMPS in the nanoparticles ranging from 11.5 nm to 154 nm at a high-altitude location Swami Ram Teertha Campus (30.34 N, 78.40 E, 1706 m AMSL), Hemvati Nandan Bahuguna Garhwal University Tehri Garhwal from 1 October 2020 to 30 August 2021.

METHODS

We have classified NPF events into different types based upon visual inspection of the contour plot of the aerosol size distributions (Maso et al., 2005). The identification of NPF has been determined by the presence of distinctly new mode of particles with diameters smaller than 25 nm and with a steady growth in diameter of this new mode for at least 6 h such that aerosol size distributions display a “banana” shaped aerosol growth. The particle growth rate (GR) has been calculated by fitting a first-order polynomial line through growing particle mode diameter between 10 and 25 nm as a function of time and calculated its slope, following Maso et al., (2005) methodology, modified and updated by Westervelt et al. (2013). The particle formation rate of 11.5 nm particle ($J_{11.5}$) has been found using the simplified approximation of the general dynamics equation, describing evolution of the aerosol size distribution.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

In this study, we have observed 53 NPF events out of 143 observation days. The shift of mode diameter from 14 nm to 25 nm during NPF by the particle number size distribution illustrates the particle growth remains between ~1.25 to ~5 nm/hour. Most of these events occurred in the pre-monsoon season during the hottest months (March-April-May) of the year. Aerosol Size Distribution spectrum for the events days shows two maxima as compared to the Aerosol Size Distribution spectrum of all days. Analysis of the meteorological parameters, the wind speed is maximum and came from Southeast direction (which is valley area) during the NPF event.

CONCLUSIONS

We have observed 53 NPF events out of 143 observation days. The wind pattern indicates the probability of newly formed particles and further growth under a large source of condensing vapor (transported from nearby lower-altitude regions) and low pre-existing particle concentrations (background mountain site) is high compared to the previous studies.

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AN INSIGHT INTO SEASONAL VARIATION OF PARTICULATE LEVELS IN A HOSTEL ROOM:
A PILOT STUDY

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Keywords: INDOOR AIR QUALITY, PARTICULATE MATTER, SEASONAL CHANGES, I/O

INTRODUCTION

Particulate Matter (PM) is one of the crucial parameters of indoor air quality (IAQ) affecting occupant's health and well-being. There are various sources of PM in indoor micro-environments (MEs), such as occupant activities (Abdel-Salam, 2022; Ni et al., 2020) and infiltration of outdoor air indoors (Bi et al., 2021). While levels and impacts of PM outdoors are well-known, its effects in MEs are receiving recent attention. This study aims to characterize indoor PM inside the hostel rooms and examine variation due to seasonal changes.

METHODOLOGY

This research falls into two categories of the scope of this conference— aerosol characterization and air quality. We collected real-time data for PM along with the CO₂, temperature, and relative humidity (RH) through Optical Particle Sizer (OPS-3330) and Testo 440 inside a hostel room of a university campus. The PM concentrations in ten different bin sizes ranging from 0.3–10 µm were noted. We conducted the sampling in two phases —during winter and monsoon seasons inside the room and collected outdoor data from the UPPCB station.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 reports indoor PM mass concentration observed inside a hostel room during two different seasons, winters and monsoons. The I/O ratio, which indicates the relation between indoor and outdoor PM levels, is reported <1. Observed PM levels were significantly higher (around 62.37%) in the winter season compared to monsoon ($t(5561)=1.96$, $p<0.000$). Measured PM_{2.5} levels were significantly correlated with lower bin sizes ranging from 0.3–2, whereas particle concentration of size 2–10 µm was correlated with PM₁₀ levels during both seasons. All correlations were statistically significant ($p<0.05$). The results of this study support the theory of subsiding conditions that trap the particles in the atmospheric boundary layer during winters over Indo-Gangetic plains (Lau et al., 2009).

Season	PM _{2.5} (µg/m ³)			PM ₁₀ (µg/m ³)		
	Mean (Std. Dev)	Max–Min	I/O	Mean (Std. Dev)	Max–Min	I/O
Winter	24.03 ± 5.67	36.24–9.89	0.96	40.98 ± 15.83	307.33–13.92	0.89
Monsoon	11.96 ± 3.53	31.17–3.00	0.60	21.14 ± 9.62	127.42–4.47	0.55

Table 1. PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ mass concentration and I/O during winter and monsoon seasons.

No significant correlation was found between indoor PM levels, CO₂, and RH. Figure 1 shows the fine particles (< 1µm) have a statistically significant larger fraction in total PM during winter while particles >1µm dominate in monsoon season ($p<0.000$). A comparison of indoor and outdoor PM concentrations can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Fraction of different size particles in total PM during monsoon and winter

Figure 2. Indoor and outdoor PM values during monsoon and winter season

CONCLUSIONS

The data from the present study provides the following inferences

- Indoor PM levels are highly impacted by outdoor levels as I/O are less than one. Indoor PM levels are significantly lower than outdoors (I/O<1), which can be attributed to indoor infiltration of outdoor PM levels.
- Lower levels indoors during monsoon compared to winter indicate the impact of wet scavenging of particles or their leaching away from the atmosphere, leading to lower concentrations. However, high particle levels during winter can be due to a lower atmospheric boundary layer resulting in higher outdoor levels.
- A high correlation among PM values for lower size bins (0.3–2 μm) and upper size bins (2–10 μm) during both seasons indicates the common source contributing to indoor PM levels.
- The contribution of fine particles in total PM (<1μm) is dominant during winters. This is a cause of health concern since these particles can be more hazardous than the coarser PM. This is an indication for planners to adopt/ design mitigation strategies accordingly.

Through this study, we found that seasonal changes in the atmosphere affect outdoor and indoor air quality. Factors influencing the transport of particles from outdoors to indoors inside hostel rooms, in this case, need to be further investigated to improve IAQ.

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DECADAL TREND OF BLACK CARBON AEROSOLS AT A SEMI-URBAN LOCATION IN THE CENTRAL IGP

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Keywords: Black Carbon, IGP, Aethalometer, Trend, Aerosols.

INTRODUCTION

Black carbon (BC), also known as soot, is a component of fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) and is primarily produced through incomplete combustion of fossil fuels, biomass, and other organic matter. It has negative impact on both human health and the climate (Bond et al., 2013). BC concentrations can vary over time and space due to a variety of factors, including emissions sources, meteorological conditions, and local environmental factors. Several studies have investigated BC variation over the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP), with a focus on understanding its sources, distribution, and impacts on air quality and climate (Tiwari et al., 2016; Vaishya et al., 2017). The present study highlights the BC variation and its trend using long-term ground-based observations over the Gorakhpur region, located in the central IGP.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

Black Carbon (BC) concentrations were measured using an Aethalometer AE33 (Drinovec et al., 2015) model (Magee Scientific, USA). The Aethalometer AE33 is a widely used instrument for real-time measurement of BC concentrations based on the principle of filter-based optical absorption. It measures the differential attenuation of light through a clean and a particle laden filter. This measurement of absorption of light is simultaneously done at seven wavelengths. BC mass concentration is then calculated from the absorption coefficient by multiplying it with a wavelength specific mass absorption cross-section (Weingartner et al., 2003).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The present study focuses on the temporal variations of Black Carbon (BC) concentrations at Central IGP region in Gorakhpur station over a span of 10 years, from 2013 to 2022. Boxplots representing the annual distribution of BC concentrations reveal a significant decreasing trend in BC levels, with a rate of $0.67 \pm 0.21 \mu\text{g m}^{-3} \text{yr}^{-1}$ (Figure 1). This decline suggests a positive improvement in air quality and a potential reduction in BC emissions in the region.

Over the Indian region, Manoj et al. (2019) observed decreasing trend in BC of $0.242 \pm 0.053 \mu\text{g m}^{-3} \text{yr}^{-1}$ during 2007 – 2016. In another study performed over the Varanasi of central IGP indicate the increase in BC trend of $0.9 \mu\text{g m}^{-3} \text{yr}^{-1}$ for period of 2009 – 2013 (Srivastava et al., 2019). In our study, BC data for the period of 2013 – 2022 has been used as no other trend analysis studied over the IGP region during this period.

Fire radiative power (FRP) data from MODIS and absorption aerosol index (AAI) data from OMI was analysed to find out if the reasons of decrease in BC concentrations over the years. It is seen, in Figure 2, that FRP and AAI, both, show an increasing trend of 1.089 W yr^{-1} and 0.024 yr^{-1} , respectively. This indicates that there might be a potential decrease in BC emissions from fossil fuel sources and increase in BC from biomass-burning sources resulting in a net decrease in BC concentrations over the years over the central IGP. Several factors could contribute to the observed decreasing trends in BC concentrations over the study region. One potential reason is the implementation of stricter regulations on industrial emissions and vehicular pollution. Increased public awareness and regulatory interventions aimed at reducing emissions might have led to improvements in air quality, resulting in lower BC levels. Additionally, advancements in technology and the adoption of cleaner energy sources could have played a crucial role in reducing BC emissions. The shift towards renewable energy sources and the use of cleaner fuels could contribute to the observed decreasing trend in BC concentrations.

CONCLUSIONS

This study presents a comprehensive analysis of the decadal trends in BC concentrations at Gorakhpur, in the central IGP. The findings indicate a consistent decrease in BC levels, both annually and across all seasons. The decline can be attributed to a combination of factors, including regulatory measures, and technological advancements. There is also a potential increase in BC emissions from biomass-burning sources. These results underscore the importance of continued efforts to reduce BC emissions and improve air quality in the region.

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STABLE ISOTOPIC COMPOSITION ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ - $\delta^{15}\text{N}$) OF TOTAL SUSPENDED PARTICULATES (TSP) AND ROAD DUST IN DELHI.

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Keywords: ISOTOPES; TOTAL CARBON; GRID CELLS; TSP; ROAD DUST

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution has been a serious environmental problem in India, affecting air quality, climate revolution, and human health. Total suspended particulates, known as TSP, typically consist of a heterogeneous blend of airborne solids and low-vapor-pressure liquid particles, encompassing a wide range of aerodynamic particle sizes, typically ranging from 0.01 to over 100 μm (USEPA, 1999). Chemical compositions in aerosol as a tracer such as elements, organic carbon, elemental carbon, stable carbon and nitrogen isotopes, ion species, etc (Aggarwal et al., 2013; Bikkina et al., 2016). The stable carbon and nitrogen isotopic ratios (referred to as $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{TC}}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{TN}}$) of total carbon (TC) and nitrogen (TN) present in atmospheric aerosols have been valuable in gaining insights into the origins and mechanisms that influence the chemical composition. The relative contributions of emissions from biogenic emissions, BB, and FFC have been determined using the TC ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) values of aerosols (Lim et al., 2022; Widory, 2007). Stable nitrogen isotopes ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$) serve as a tool for pinpointing major contributors to and processes involving atmospheric nitrogen. This approach aids in examining the impacts of nitrogen releases from agricultural fields, particularly those stemming from non-point sources, while also shedding light on the nitrogen chemistry within specific geographic areas and the influence of human-generated nitrogen emissions (Wang et al., 2017). Road dust is one of the major sources of atmospheric particles. The chemical composition of dust particles deposited on roads are among the indicators most used to study the health of urban ecosystems (Christoforidis and Stamatis 2009; Li et al. 2013, 2019) so the study of the stable C and N isotope compositions of several road dust samples and TSP samples to identify the main sources of local contamination.

METHODS

Samples were collected in 47 sites in 47 grid cells (5 \times 5 km²) (Peak traffic hour: 9 am to 11 am) in February 2019 in a campaign mode during winter and 157 road dust samples were collected during the morning (9 am to 11 am) in February 2021 from 65 grid cells in triplicate manners in Delhi. In general, large pollution episodes are observed during winter in Delhi. In Jangirh et al., 2022, road dust is considered as one of the main sources of total suspended particulate (TSP), sampling was done in February 2021 to identify further sources. For determining the isotopic values of stable carbon (¹³C) and nitrogen (¹⁵N), an Isotope Ratio Mass Spectrometer (IRMS) (Instrument Model: Isoprime 100, Elementar, Isoprime, UK) along with an elemental analyzer (Model: Pyrocube, Elementar, UK) was used for the analysis. For TSP samples, a circular punch of 1 cm² was taken from every sample to measure TC and TN and their isotopic values. All aliquots are tightly packed in the pre-cleaned tin boats and form the round pellet. The sample pellet was automatically introduced in the elemental analyzer (EA), where the sample pellet gets combusted in a combustion oven at 1150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. For road dust, about 3 mg of road dust was packed into a tin capsule and introduced into the EA auto sampler. Isotope compositions are expressed as $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values, which represent the relative difference expressed per mil (‰).

Figure 1. Sampling sites for TSP and Road dust

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The average of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ was observed -21.68 ± 0.9 ‰ with a range of -23.42 ‰ to -18.78 ‰. The highest $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ value (-18.78 ‰) likely occurred due to the influence of Asian dust, aligning with $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values typically associated with soil organic matter, which fall within the range of -20 ‰ to -15 ‰. The observed values point to a variation of sources which include biomass burning, coal combustion, and biogenic sources of C4 plants. Similarly, the observed values of $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ range from 2.07 to 31.63 ‰ with an average value of 23.81 ± 4.9 ‰ indicating ranges of source-endmembers i.e., soil dust, vehicular fossil-related sources, volatilized fertilizers, urban waste incineration, livestock waste, burning of natural gas and C3, C4 plant biomass. In the context of wintertime pollution in Delhi, heavy pollution episodes are primarily linked to soil-related factors when total suspended particulates (TSP) concentrations exceed $400 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, and the total carbon-to-nitrogen (TC/TN) ratios are below 30. Within our current investigation, it is noteworthy that TC/TN values below 30 were observed at 43 out of 47 sites, underscoring the significance of soil-derived organic compounds such as humic acid as substantial contributors to water-soluble organic nitrogen (WSO_N). Moreover, the sources of nitrogen-containing aerosols within TSP are attributed to soil dust, biomass fuel combustion, and fossil fuel combustion.

The stable C and N isotope compositions of road dust samples collected in Delhi showed that $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ displayed large variations from -24.61 to -12.17 ‰ with an average of -15.92 ± 2.13 ‰. These values are close (-23.6 ‰ to -22 ‰), which reflect the contribution of C3 and C4 plants, cement and construction work values (-15.3 ‰), coal combustion (-25.1 to -23.6 ‰). Whereas for $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ varied from -14.98 to 53.91 ‰ with an average of 16.36 ± 10.39 ‰, respectively. Variations in sources in Delhi pointed towards diesel combustion (1.7 ‰ to -21 ‰), and coal combustion ($+6$ to 13 ‰). Organic fertilizers, such as plant compost or liquid and solid animal waste, generally exhibit higher initial $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values ($+6$ to $+30$ ‰) than inorganic fertilizers (from -6 ‰ to $+6$ ‰; Xue et al., 2009).

CONCLUSIONS

The observed values $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ pointed to a variation of sources which include biomass burning, coal combustion, and biogenic sources of C4 plants whereas values of $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ showed variation in sources of soil dust, vehicular fossil-related sources, volatilized fertilizers, showing a ^{15}N depletion with the decrease of the TN content, indicating nitrogen isotope fractionations induced by secondary processes. Results showed that the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of road dust identified the presence of contribution of C3 and C4 plants, cement and construction work, and coal combustion similarly $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ of road dust showed organic fertilizers, coal combustion, and diesel combustion.

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ANALYSIS OF SURFACE MORPHOLOGY AND ELEMENTAL COMPOSITION OF PARTICULATE MATTER IN CENTRAL HIMALAYA REGION

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Keywords: AEROSOL, PARTICULATE MATTER, FESEM-EDX, CENTRAL HIMALAYA, SURFACE MORPHOLOGY.

INTRODUCTION

Particulate matter PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ are a major environmental issue globally (Squizzato et al., 2012). It comprises of a complex mixture of dust, pollen, ash, soot, metals amongst numerous solid and liquid chemicals present in the atmosphere (Hanrahan et al., 2012). PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ triggers health effects upon inhalation and can be transported further by atmospheric circulation, due to its long residence time of days to several weeks in the atmospheres. Field emission Scanning electron microscopy coupled with energy dispersive X-ray (FESEM-EDX) is a non-destructive analytical method for high resolution surface imaging and quantitative identification of elements present in the sample (Singh et al., 2014). This technique is capable of providing detailed information on chemical composition and particle morphology as well as improved understanding of the properties and sources of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ (Galvez et al., 2013). The elemental composition of fine particulates is more useful with a view to establish their origin and their potential effects on human health. Till now, the studies on elemental composition of fine particulate matter using FESEM-EDX analysis are limited in the hilly region of Uttarakhand. In this study, PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ samples are analysed for FESEM-EDX and sampling was done at a high-altitude location Swami Ram Teertha Campus (30.34 N, 78.40 E, 1706 m AMSL), Hemvati Nandan Bahuguna Garhwal University Tehri Garhwal.

METHODS

PMs samplings was done by using APM-550 (for PM_{2.5}) and APM-460 (for PM₁₀) samplers (M/s Envirotech Pvt. Ltd., India) with a flow rate of one cubic meter per hour. The quartz filter papers were used for PM sampling. Before and after sampling, the filter papers were kept in a desiccator for 24 Hours to remove the moisture content. The desiccated filter papers were weighted using an electronic microbalance with 0.01 mg resolution (Gautam et al., 2018). The particle concentrations were determined gravimetrically by the difference in their weights before and after the sampling. The surface morphologies and elemental composition of airborne particles of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ samples were examined by field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) coupled with energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX). 0.5 cm of the dry filter samples were cut and coated with a thin film of Gold (Au) to make the samples electrically conductive for SEM-EDX analysis. We have collected the data from November 2020 to May 2021 over the SRT campus.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The morphological characteristics of particles detected in PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ by FESEM analysis are depicted in the figure 1. The EDX spectra revealed the relative abundance of elements – Si, C, Na, O, K and Al. Elemental levels of Si and C were significantly higher than other elements. Silicon (Si) is one of the largest constituents of soil-derived mineral particles. Therefore its occurrence may be due to transportation of atmospheric airborne soil particles or from fly ash produced during combustion. Also, elevated level of carbon (C) was associated with high carbonaceous materials which might be expected due to combination of diverse anthropogenic activities and forest fires over the observation site.

CONCLUSIONS

Particulate matter PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} morphology and elemental composition in the central Himalaya region is identified. Si and C dominated and the most abundant elements present in all samples while soot, aluminosilicate and irregular shape mineral particles were the most common inhalable particles.

Figure 1: SEM Image of PM2.5, chemical composition and their spectrum.

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VARIATION OF ELEMENTAL SOURCE CHARACTERIZATION AND COMPOSITION IN DELHI NATIONAL CAPITAL REGION FROM PRE-BURNING TO POST-BURNING PERIOD

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Introduction

Delhi NCR region suffers from the intense pressure of urbanization, industrialization, and the nearby agricultural burning events in north-western India (Punjab, Haryana). As a result, ambient air quality is deteriorating with time and can have negative health effects on humans, including respiratory problems, and cancer-causing effects from metals like Mn, Cu, Pb, and Cr. As metals are specific markers for a variety of emission sources and to capture episodic high pollution events, real-time chemical characterization and further source apportionment of metals are needed of the hour. To achieve this, we have used the real-time metal concentration measuring instrument XACT-625i at two urban sites in New Delhi (Indian Institute of Technology Delhi (IITD) and Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology Delhi (IITM)), during winter 2019. Further for analyzing the role of very high pollution agricultural residue burning, we divided our sampling period based on our companion study by Lalchandani et al.2022 into pre-burning (1st week to 3rd week of October 2019), burning (4th week of October to mid-November 2019), and post-burning period (mid-November 2019 to early January 2020). The Source Apportionment by Positive Matrix Factorization (PMF) using the ME-2 engine algorithm was conducted at two sites to understand their variations in different periods. Various emission sources, including motor vehicles, power plants, construction activities, and biomass burning emit fine particles and related (trace) metal components. This source apportionment study offers valuable insights into the impact of agricultural residue burning during different seasonal periods within the Delhi NCR region.

Methodology

The input data matrix of the elements measured with half-hourly time resolution was prepared by first filtering the elements based on the percentage of data points below their Minimum Detection Limit (MDL) (provided by manufacturer Cooper Environmental Services). Twenty-two elements (Al, Si, S, Cl, K, Ca, Ti, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Ni, Cu, Zn, As, Se, Br, Rb, Sr, Sb, Ba and Pb) were found to have 80% of their data points above MDL and were used in the PMF input. PMF using the ME-2 algorithm was applied to the elemental dataset in both IITD and IITMD sites during the three periods. The unconstrained PMF was run from 3 to 11 factors in both sites. The 8-factor solution is selected as the optimum solution in both the sites after 20 seeds run analysis and the selection of factors and the uncertainty using the bootstrapping method. The complete detail of the methodology is provided in Shukla et al.,2022. The resolved 8 factors solution includes fireworks, SFC-I, SFC-II, Cl-rich, S-rich, Cu-rich, Coal combustion, and road dust.

Results and Discussions

In the IITD and IITMD sites, the Cl-rich source exhibited significant fluctuations, transitioning from lower levels during pre-burning (6% and 14%) to substantially higher percentages during burning (29% and 35%). These shifts suggest the influence of nearby biomass-burning activities and meteorological factors. In IITD, the Cl-rich source's contribution continued to rise during the post-burning period (42% and 33%) due to prevailing conditions of a low Planetary Boundary Layer Height (PBLH) and elevated Relative Humidity (RH) during the extreme winter period.

Conversely in IITMD, the contribution of S-rich sources remained relatively consistent at around 30% during pre- and post-burning periods but dropped to 16% during the burning phase. Additionally, the Road dust factor's contribution notably decreased from pre-burning (21%) to burning (7%) and post-burning (6%). Whereas the SFC1 factor in both IITD and IITMD sites rises from pre-burning to during the burning period, then declines during the post-burning period in both sites as shown the Figures 1 & 2.

Fig 1. Elemental contribution during the Pre-burning, Post-burning, and Burning period in the IITD site

Fig 2. Elemental contribution during the Pre-burning, Post-burning, and Burning period in IITMD site

Conclusion

The Delhi-NCR study during the winter revealed seasonal variations in pollution source contributions at two sites, IITD and IITMD. The Cl-rich source exhibited substantial fluctuations, peaking during the burning period (29% to 35%), indicating the significant influence of biomass burning from nearby states and meteorological conditions. In IITD, the Cl-rich source further increased during the post-burning period due to low Planetary Boundary Layer Height (PBLH) and high Relative Humidity (RH) during extreme winter conditions. The contribution of S-rich sources remained stable during pre-burning and post-burning periods but decreased to 16% during the burning period, suggesting being influenced by seasonal factors, are less affected by burning activities. The Road dust factor's contribution consistently decreased from pre-burning to post-burning periods at both sites, this indicates that road dust emissions play a less prominent role during the winter season in this region. These findings underscore the need for targeted interventions to control biomass burning and consider meteorological conditions in air quality management strategies for the Delhi NCR region, with potential implications for policymakers and stakeholders.

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AEROSOL VOLATILITY OVER HIGH-ALTITUDE SITE IN WESTERN GHATS, INDIA: EFFECT OF SEMI-VOLATILE ORGANICS COATING.

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Keywords: Aerosol volatility, PMF, SOA, semi-volatile organics.

INTRODUCTION

Volatility is one of the most important physical properties of organic and inorganic aerosol (OA & IA), as it determines the partitioning of its components between the vapor and particulate phases. OA and sulfate are the most abundant species over the observation site (Mukherjee et al., 2018, 2020). Due to the complex composition, the volatility of organic aerosol is one of the major sources of uncertainty in measuring and modeling ambient aerosols. The main goal of the present study is to i) To determine the volatility of the different chemical constituents of sub-micron aerosol by comparing the ambient run with the denuded run (fixed temperature) and ii) estimate changes in different organic aerosol contributions (POA vs SOA) under ambient and denuded conditions.

METHODS

The schematic of the experiment conducted at HACPL, Mahabaleshwar during 1st February, 2021 to 28th February, 2021 to determine the volatility of the sub-micron aerosol is given below. The Thermal denuder system was coupled with HR-TOF Aerosol Mass Spectrometer for sub-micron aerosol chemical composition and scanning mobility particle sizer (SMPS) for aerosol size distribution. The thermal denuder system was kept at 150° C and switching time between ambient air flow and denuded air was kept at a time interval of 10 minutes.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The diel variation of non-refractory (NR-PM1) species i.e organics, sulfate, nitrate and ammonium as measured by AMS under ambient temperature and thermally denuded (at 150°C) temperature are shown in Figure 1 (a-d). As can be seen from the figure 1a, the organics were dominant throughout the day with higher mass concentration during afternoon to evening hours for ambient run. In contrast very less variability in concentration was observed with a slightly higher mass concentration during evening hours. The average concentration of organics for ambient and denuded run was estimated to be $2.57 \pm 1.21 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and $1.17 \pm 0.44 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ respectively. It is important to note that the organics peak during morning (~11:00 am) and evening hours (~07:00 pm) was completely absent for during denuded run indicating the higher abundances of high volatile organic aerosols during the time period. On the other hand, sulfate exhibited afternoon and night-time higher concentration for both ambient and thermal denuded conditions. As noted from figure 2b, the difference in sulfate mass concentration for denuded and ambient run was significantly less than that of the organics indicating its less volatile nature. Further, nitrate exhibited daytime low and night time high mass concentrations which resembled its diel variation to be majorly governed by temperature dependent partitioning (Mukherjee et al., 2020). A significantly low mass concentration of nitrate during denuded run indicated its high volatile nature and may possibly in ammonium nitrate (highly volatile) form. Ammonium exhibited similar diel profile as sulfate for both denuded and ambient run; it exhibited slight increase (from 0.53 to 0.59, $p < 0.005$) in the correlation with sulfate from ambient to denuded run indicating more abundances of ammonium sulfate in the denuded phase. Surprisingly, the correlation between ammonium and nitrate reduced significantly from ambient run to denuded run which further affirmed the abundance of nitrate as ammonium nitrate form. Additionally, the ammonium concentration was estimated for both ambient and denuded run and compared with the measured ammonium concentration. The slope was calculated as 0.91 (measured vs predicted) for ambient run which indicated the aerosol to be slightly basic in nature. Whereas, for denuded run the slope was 1.67 indicating the high acidity (ammonium escaped due to high volatility) of the remaining aerosol. In terms of total mass, the NR-PM1 mass was observed to be 48% volatile and the rate of volatility can be estimated as 0.39% per °C. As observed in the diel comparison of ambient and denuded run, each species exhibited different volatility. The average volatility was estimated as 54%, 26%, 80%, 68%, and 64% for organics, sulfate, nitrate, chloride and ammonium. The volatility rate was highest for nitrate (0.64% per °C) and lowest for the sulfate (0.21% per °C).

Positive Matrix Factorization (PMF) resulted 4 factors (figure 2 a-d) hydrocarbon like organic aerosol (HOA), biomass burning organic aerosol (BBOA), Semi-volatile oxygenated organic aerosol (SV-OOA), Low volatile-

oxygenated organic aerosol (OOA). The HOA can be identified with characteristics peak of m/z 41, m/z 43, m/z 55, and m/z 57 which are typically contributed by the hydrocarbons emitted by fossil fuel combustion. BBOA is comprised of m/z 29, m/z 60 and m/z 73 and Bae et al., (2012)

reported that Levoglucosan which is a characteristic tracer for biomass burning, peaks at m/z 60 ($C_2H_4O_2^+$) and m/z 73 ($C_3H_5O_3^+$). SV-OOA and LV-OOA both were comprised of m/z 44 but differ in the fraction of abundance of m/z 44 (CO_2^+) and m/z 43 ($C_3H_7^+/C_2H_3O^+$). SV-OOA was comprised of higher fraction of 43 which indicated the factor to be semi volatile type. In contrast, LV-OOA is comprised of higher fraction of m/z 44 with a meagre contribution from m/z 43. The average percentage contributions of these four factors during denuded and ambient run were evaluated and further compared (2 e-f). SV-OOA drastically decreased from 44% to 18%, followed by HOA (20% to 15%), BBOA (10% to 7%). LV-OOA showed significant increase (31% to 56%). The drastic decrease of SVOOA as compared to other source factor indicated possible coating of SV-OOA in the course of regional transport (continental air mass). The similar characteristics can be visible in high resolution fitted AMS data where the oxygenated hydrocarbon related ions showed higher to equal volatility in comparison to hydrocarbon ion peaks (figure 2f). This observation further supports the possible coating of semi-volatile organics (oxygenated hydrocarbons) on existing primary or secondary organic aerosols.

CONCLUSIONS

Aerosol volatility of sub-micron aerosols were extensively studied utilizing AMS data over HACPL, Mahabaleshwar during February, 2021 (winter). The following conclusion were obtained,

- Nitrate showed highest volatility among the sub-micron aerosols followed by Ammonium, Organics, chloride and sulfate.
- Highest volatility was observed in the accumulation mode as compared to aitenk and nucleation mode.
- PMF analysis revealed higher SOA abundances in denuded air as compared to POA
- Higher volatility rate of SV-OOA compared to POA indicated the possible coating effect.

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ROLE OF METROLOGICAL CONDITIONS AND SOURCES INFLUENCING ATMOSPHERIC NH_x OVER A SEMI-URBAN SITE IN NORTH-WESTERN INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN

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Keywords: Reactive nitrogen; Ammonia; Source; Nitrogen isotopic composition; India

INTRODUCTION

Recent satellite-based observation has identified a significantly high concentration of NH₃ over the Indian subcontinent, in which the Indo-Gangetic plain (IGP) has been identified as a major global hotspot (Kuttippurath et al., 2020). This necessitates a dire need to have a better understanding of the sources and atmospheric processes affecting the abundances of reactive nitrogen species (Nr), especially NH_x, over the entire Indian subcontinent, with major focus on the IGP. The stable isotopic signatures of NH_x ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$ of gaseous NH₃ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ of particulate NH₄⁺) have been used effectively for tracing sources of NH₃ gas and understanding the formation processes of NH₄⁺ particulates. NH₃ can be emitted from multiple sources, which usually have a distinct $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ -NH₃ values (Felix et al., 2013). Due to the presence of multiple emission sources of NH₃ with distinct $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ -NH₃ values, coupling isotopic signatures of NH_x with a Bayesian mixing model is used as a powerful tool for source apportionment of NH₃ in different environments (Wu et al., 2021). Furthermore, it is important to track the gas to particulate conversion and understand the different atmospheric conditions influencing the same. The present study aims to investigate insights on the sources and atmospheric processes affecting Nr using species specific isotopic signature of nitrogenous aerosols over a semi-urban agricultural site located in northwest IGP region with a major focus on studying the NH_x system on a diurnal scale.

METHODS

PM_{2.5} sampling was carried out using a high volume (1.13 m³/min) sampler in Patiala. Major ions (water-soluble cations (NH₄⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺) and anions (Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻) were analysed using ion chromatography (Dionex-5000). Isotopic analysis of $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ -TN and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ -NH₄⁺ was carried out using Isotope Ratio Mass Spectrometer (IRMS, Delta V Plus, ThermoFisher Scientific, Germany) attached to an Elemental Analyser (EA, FLASH 2000). Source apportionment was performed using Bayesian Mixing Model (MixSIAR) for tracking NH₃ sources.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Day and night-time average concentration of TN and NH₄⁺-N showed no significant diurnal difference. In terms of isotopic signatures, average $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ -TN was 10.5±1.7‰ and 8.4±1.6‰ whereas $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ -NH₄⁺ was 12.1±1.1‰ and 10.9±1.1‰ in day and night-time samples, respectively, and the diurnal differences were significant (student's t-test, p<0.05). Diurnal variation in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ -NH₄⁺ (or $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ -TN) can be either due to differences in emission sources or different atmospheric chemistry during day-time or night-time. Mixing model (MixSIAR) based on $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ -NH₃, suggests that non-agricultural emissions (NH₃ slip: 47±24%) dominates over agricultural emissions (24±11%), combustion sources (19±14%), and biomass burning (10±8%) for atmospheric NH₃. A negative correlation between $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ -NH₄⁺ and ambient relative humidity (RH) (Figure 1), as well as daytime NO₃⁻-N concentration, were also observed. This is attributed to the possibility of NH₄NO₃ volatilization during day-time owing to lower RH and higher temperature, resulting in isotopic enrichment of the remaining NH₄⁺ in aerosol phase. Moreover, a significant negative correlation between $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ -NO₃⁻ and temperature during day-time supports the possibilities of potential dissociation and loss of NO₃⁻ from NH₄NO₃ resulting in isotopic enrichment of the residual NO₃⁻.

Figure 1. Relationship between $\delta^{15}\text{N-NH}_4^+$ and RH during the study period.

CONCLUSIONS

This study reports the stable isotopic signature of TN, $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$, and $\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$ in day/night pair $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ samples collected over a semi-urban site (Patiala) in the IGP during winter. NH_3 emission was highest from slip ($47 \pm 24\%$) followed by agriculture ($24 \pm 11\%$), combustion sources ($19 \pm 14\%$), and biomass burning ($10 \pm 8\%$) with no significant diurnal variability during the study period. Further, a significant diurnal trend in $\delta^{15}\text{N-NH}_4^+$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N-TN}$ was observed which was found to be due to volatilization and dissociation of NH_4NO_3 during day-time owing to lower RH and higher temperature, thus shifting the isotopic signature of $\delta^{15}\text{N-NH}_4^+$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N-TN}$ towards a more positive side. The same was not favoured during night-time owing to cooler temperature and high RH conditions. This study highlights the importance of non-agricultural emission as a major source of NH_3 over a region dominated by agricultural activities (IGP), and the importance of local meteorology in shaping the isotopic signature of nitrogenous species.

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**GEOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISATION AND QUANTIFICATION OF ASSOCIATED
NUTRIENTS OF MINERAL DUST OVER ARID/SEMI-ARID REGIONS OF WESTERN INDIA- A
MAJOR SOURCE OF DUST TO THE NORTHERN ARABIAN SEA**

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Keywords: Aeolian Dust, trace elements, Micro-nutrient, Arabian Sea, The Thar Desert.

INTRODUCTION

Mineral dust is an essential component of aerosols emitted into the atmosphere by strong surface winds, predominantly from arid and semi-arid regions. The emitted dust can be transported and deposited thousands of kilometres from the source region (Kumar et al., 2020). Dust deposited in marine and terrestrial ecosystems can provide several nutrients and major metals essential for the primary productivity of nutrient-limited ecosystems and affect the biogeochemical cycles (Jickells et al., 2005). However, quantifying the major and trace elements from the Indian Arid region to the Arabian Sea is sparse. Here, we present soluble as well as the total major and trace elements data of the aerosols collected during the summer season (May to July) from Ahmedabad (Urban) and Barmer, Rajasthan (Rural), along with the Sr and Nd isotopic ratios measured during four major dust outbreaks observed during the sampling period, documenting source characteristics and relative contribution from different sources. In addition, dry deposition fluxes of the trace elements for the entire sampling period will be presented.

METHODS

A total of 38 and 42 samples PM₁₀ samples were collected over Ahmedabad and Barmer, Rajasthan, India, from May to July (AMD: May and June, BAR: June and July), respectively. The samples are collected using the tissue quartz filters using high volume samplers (HVS) with a flow rate of 1.13m⁻³ min⁻¹. The dry deposition filters were weighed gravimetrically to determine the aerosol concentrations in the two sampling locations. Part of the aerosol samples were used to extract the soluble fraction of the major and trace elements which HR-ICP-MS measured. The same samples were acid digested, and the total major and trace elements concentrations were measured in ICP-OES. The soluble and total concentrations of the elements were used to determine the solubility of the different elements in two sampling locations. Two dust storms were observed in each sampling location at different times of sampling. To identify the provenance of the dust storms, the samples were processed to measure the Sr-Nd isotopes by MC-ICP-MS.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Strong temporal variability of aerosol concentrations is observed at both the sites, and the concentrations are impacted by the dust storms passing over the sampling sites. High peaks are due to the dust storms during the sampling period. The aerosol concentration in AMD ranges from 44 to 289 µg m⁻³, whereas the concentration in the BAR ranges from 40 to 535 µg m⁻³.

Average concentrations in both AMD and BAR during June are twofold higher for BAR than AMD. This is mainly due to the arrival of the SW monsoon winds during June over the Ahmedabad region, and the dust sources are still active in the Barmer region—major and trace elements concentrations.

Figure 1: Average concentrations of total major and trace elements at Ahmedabad and Barmer

Calcium (Avg: AMD = $11 \pm 7 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, BAR = $13 \pm 7 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) concentrations is the highest among all major elements, followed by Al (Avg: AMD = $7 \pm 4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, BAR = $11 \pm 7 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$), Fe (Avg: AMD = $4 \pm 2 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, BAR = $6 \pm 4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) and Mg (AMD = $3 \pm 2 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, BAR = $4 \pm 2 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). Among the trace metals, Zn, Cu, Cd and Pb are comparatively higher in AMD than BAR samples, showing more anthropogenic contribution in AMD than in the remote location BAR.

Fe solubility is less than 1% in most of the samples, except a few dust storm samples show high solubility. The lower Fe solubility is comparable with those reported in previous studies over the Arabian Sea during different seasons. (Srinivas et al., 2012 and Panda et al., 2022). The average Solubility of Mg is $34 \pm 19\%$ and $22 \pm 7\%$ for AMD and BAR, respectively, whereas for Mn, it averages $36 \pm 14\%$ for AMD and BAR with $11 \pm 19\%$. The solubility of Cu is $13 \pm 5\%$ for AMD samples and averages $14 \pm 8\%$ for BAR samples. Zn, which correlates poorly with Al, can be mainly from anthropogenic emissions and has the solubility of $17 \pm 21\%$ and $5 \pm 9\%$ for AMD and BAR.

Two dust storms were observed in both sampling locations during the sampling period. The dust storm sources were identified using Sr-Nd isotopic values and air mass back trajectories. The dust sources to Barmer are identified as SW Asian dust sources, such as the Helmand Basin and other deserts in Pakistan and Afghanistan. In contrast, one dust storm to Ahmedabad is backtracked to the Arabian Peninsula and the other one to the SW Asian sources. The Fe solubility of the dust originating from the SW Asian sources is comparatively high to the dust from other sources. This indicates the importance of dust sources in nutrient supply to the oceans.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the atmospheric flux of the major and trace elements is reported, showing the influence of dust storms originating from the SW Asian dust sources. The fractional solubility of major and trace elements shows variability based on the dust sources over western India, which gives an overview of the atmospheric nutrient transport to the northern Arabian Sea.

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SOURCE IDENTIFICATION OF PM_{2.5} IN AN INDIAN URBAN-DESERT REGION

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Keywords: Source apportionment, PM_{2.5}, desert-urban

INTRODUCTION

Fine particulate matter, PM_{2.5} (aerodynamic diameter of $\leq 2.5\mu\text{m}$) are complex mixture of chemical species primarily emitted from natural and anthropogenic sources and formed as secondary pollutants through chemical reactions in the atmosphere. PM_{2.5} has been of concern because of their adverse effects on human health (Deng et al., 2019), climate change and visibility reductions. Hence, the understanding of atmospheric chemistry and in-depth knowledge of the contributing sources of PM_{2.5} and its components is imperative for comprehending how aerosols influence climate and for devising effective strategies to curb PM_{2.5} levels. In view of the presence of salt lakes and saline soil in Rajasthan, in association with the anthropogenic emissions and natural desert dust, this study finds its importance in delivering an understanding of sources governing the PM_{2.5} composition and identification of local and regional source locations that would serve as database for validation of climate model and emissions inventories.

METHODS

The USEPA-PMF5.0 (Paatero et al., 2014) was used to apportion the fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) measured (every alternate day, 24-hour integrated sampling) over the receptor site at a desert-urban region (Bikaner, India) from January 2019 – December 2019. Concentrations of chemical species comprising PM_{2.5} mass with their corresponding errors were used in the model to identify factors as sources and a combination of factor contributions. Onsite wind-speed and wind-direction data, and NOAA HYSPLIT air-parcel back trajectories data were used for identifying local and regional sources locations, respectively. Variation of factor contributions on different temporal scales, and factors contributing to high PM_{2.5} mass concentration has also been investigated.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Factors identified through PMF analysis in decreasing order of their mean percentage contribution to PM_{2.5} mass are secondary sulphate (25.2%), resuspended dust (23.6%), residential cook-stove (13.4%), smelter and non-tail-pipe emissions (11.3%), vehicular emissions (10.8%), lake and sea salt (8.5%), secondary nitrate (4.8%), and brick kilns (2.2%) (Figure 1). The mean mass resolved by the model in this study was observed to be closely related to measured PM_{2.5} ($R^2=0.91$, slope = 0.97) mass concentration.

Winter and post-monsoon PM concentrations in the region were majorly regulated by secondary sulphate and residential cook-stove emissions, contributing to 22% and 22-27%, respectively. Dust storms prevalent in the region during pre-monsoon and monsoon have resulted in higher resuspended dust contribution (30-43%) from crustal sources during these seasons. Salt lakes in the region have influenced the fine PM mass with its effect aggravated during the monsoon by the sea-salts from the Arabian Sea. The fine PM mass has been impacted by salt lakes in the area, which is exacerbated during the monsoon by sea-salts from the Arabian Sea. Smelters, non-tailpipe emissions, and vehicular emissions were substantial contributors to moderately polluted to poor conditions (PM_{2.5} loadings $>60\ \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). Furthermore, highest PM_{2.5} loading ($>90\ \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) marking the very poor conditions in the region was contributed by residential cook-stove emissions and secondary sulphate. While vehicular emissions were found to be primarily local, numerous smelters from northern states had potential influence on PM mass. The prominent seasonality in the source contributions observed in this study is particularly suggestive of substantial influence of meteorology on PM loading in the region.

Figure 1. Source contribution to PM_{2.5} and their seasonal variation

CONCLUSIONS

In sum, the present study has shed light on the complex interplay of various factors influencing air quality. Seasonal variations have revealed distinct patterns, with secondary sulphate and residential cook-stove emissions dominating during winter and post-monsoon periods, while dust storms and salt lakes play a more prominent role during pre-monsoon and monsoon seasons. These findings emphasize the need for tailored strategies to address specific seasonal challenges. Furthermore, the identification of contributors to poor air quality conditions, such as smelters, non-tailpipe emissions, and residential cook-stove emissions, provides valuable insights for policymakers and environmental agencies to prioritize mitigation efforts. Finally, the observed seasonality in source contributions underscores the crucial role of meteorological factors in shaping PM_{2.5} loading in the region, highlighting the importance of a holistic approach that considers both emission control and meteorological conditions in air quality management. This analysis serves as a critical resource for formulating effective air quality improvement strategies, ultimately contributing to the well-being and health of the residents and improved air quality in the studied region.

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CHEMICAL COMPOSITION AND SOURCE APPORTIONMENT OF PM_{2.5} IN CENTRAL HIMALAYAN REGION OF INDIA

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Keywords: AEROSOL, SOURCE APPORTIONMENT, HIMALAYAN REGION

INTRODUCTION

Ambient aerosols consist of organics, mineral dust, metals as well as sea salts and inorganic pollutants. Relative abundance of these components is highly variable both temporally and spatially (Gawhane et al., 2017). Several researchers have reported chemical properties of aerosols and source apportionment of aerosols over the Indian region; however, very limited studies have been reported over the Himalayan region (Kuniyal et al., 2014, Gautam et al., 2018). The assessment of ambient air quality of the Himalayan region of India is one of the major issues as it has been affected due to rapid urbanization and mass tourism activities. In this paper, we present chemical composition and source apportionment of particulate matter <2.5 μm (PM_{2.5}) and meteorological parameters collected at Srinagar of Uttarakhand, a central Himalayan region of India.

METHODS

PM_{2.5} (n=39) were collected at Srinagar (560m amsl) of Uttarakhand of the central Himalayan region of India during Jan-Dec 2017 in a year-long period. PM_{2.5} samples were collected (12 h basis) simultaneously on prebaked QM-A filters by Fine Particle Sampler. Analysis of OC, EC, WSIC of PM_{2.5} were carried out using OC/EC carbon analyzer; Ion Chromatograph, respectively. The details of chemical analysis of PM are discussed in Bisht et al. (2015). Principal component analysis (PCA) was performed to identify the possible sources of PM_{2.5} over central Himalayan region of India.

RESULTS

Figure 1. Seasonal variations of water-soluble ionic species in PM_{2.5} during the study period.

Figure 1 shows the Seasonal variations of water-soluble ionic species of PM_{2.5} at Srinagar central Himalayan region. The analysed mass concentrations of PM_{2.5} accounted for 70% over the region, whereas, the unidentified mass PM_{2.5} accounted for 30%, which may be carbonate rich minerals, calcium sulphate and alumino-silicates, etc. PCA identified the three major components of PM_{2.5} corresponding to the different

sources, and identified as secondary aerosol, crustal / mineral / soil dust and biomass burning, based on the loading of the variables in the factor.

CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, source apportionments of PM_{2.5} were done using PCA over the central Himalayan region of India based on the chemical compositions of PM_{2.5} collected during a year-long period. PCA identified the three major sources such as secondary aerosol, crustal/mineral/soil dust and biomass burning of PM_{2.5} over the region.

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**POLYCYCLIC AROMATIC COMPOUNDS (PAHS) FROM DOMINANT SOURCES AND THEIR
ENTRAINMENT IN AMBIENT AIR OVER INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN**

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Keywords: Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons; Agricultural waste burning; Diesel emissions; Coal combustion; Wood burning.

INTRODUCTION

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) are organic compounds generated by incomplete combustion of biomass, coal, and fossil fuels, which are carcinogenic, semi-volatile, and have lower aqueous solubility (Keyte et al., 2013). The source identification, environmental fate and transport of PAHs are crucial due to its carcinogenic and/or mutagenic characteristics (Rajeev et al., 2021). The mass concentration and chemical characteristics of PAHs varies with variation in the combustion material, process and other parameters (Lima et al., 2005; Rajeev et al., 2023). Therefore, insights about the origin, fate and distribution of PAHs are critical for implementing control measures of air pollution. In this regard, relative contribution from various combustion sources to ambient levels of PAHs have been assessed in this study.

METHODS

Particulate matter (PM) samples from diesel and bio-diesel fuelled engine exhaust emissions (with and without commercial DOC), agricultural-waste burning, biofuels (wood) and raw coal, carbonized coal, and coal briquettes with different cook stoves were collected on quartz filter (Das et al., 2022; Shukla et al., 2017; Singh et al., 2021). Ambient PM samples were collected from Allahabad and Kanpur (~200 km apart). PM samples were collected onto a pre-baked quartz filter using a high-volume air sampler (Kumar and Gupta, 2015) during the winter of 2015-16 (Rajeev et al., 2021). Detailed information about the collection, experimental setup and sampling sites is provided in Rajeev et al., 2021; Rajeev et al., 2023. PAHs analysis was done on GC-MS (Agilent GC: 7890B; MSD: 5977B) equipped with a capillary column (DB-5MS column) which uses helium as a carrier gas. 16 USEPA-identified PAHs i.e. Naphthalene (NAP), Acenaphthylene (ACY), Acenaphthene (ACE), Fluorene (FLU), Phenanthrene (PHE), Anthracene (ANT), Fluoranthene (FLA), Pyrene (PYR), Benzo (a) anthracene (BaA), Chrysene (CHR), Benzo (b, j) fluoranthene (BbjF), Benzo (k) fluoranthene (BkF), Benzo (e, a) pyrene (BeaP), Indeno (1,2,3-c,d) pyrene (IP), Dibenzo (a,h) anthracene (DahA) and Benzo (g,h,i) perylene (BghiP) were analyzed in this study. The detailed analysis information is provided in Rajeev et al., 2023.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

High molecular weight PAHs fraction was found to be highest in the PM emissions from coal combustion > agricultural waste burning ~ wood burning > cow-dung cake burning > bio-diesel exhaust > bio-diesel exhaust with DOC > diesel exhaust > diesel exhaust with DOC. The dominant PAH compounds contributing to total PAHs loading are BbjF, BeaP, and IP in each source sample except for the case of diesel and bio-diesel exhaust with DOC installed.

Based on carcinogenicity analysis, 5-ringed compounds, containing the most carcinogenic PAHs are present in the highest percentage of emissions from wood burning and agricultural waste burning. The carcinogenic potential of the particulate PAHs from different sources has been assessed and emissions from wood burning are found to be the most carcinogenic.

The diagnostic ratios for different combustion sources have been reported in this study for further utilization in the future source apportionment studies. Based on these results, the percentage contribution from various sources to the ambient PAHs loading has been determined in this study.

Figure 1. Cross-plot of FLA/(FLA+PYR) with (a) IP/ (IP + BghiP) and (c) ANT/ (ANT + PHE); and BeaP/ (BeaP + CHR) with (b) IP/ (IP + BghiP) and (d) ANT/ (ANT + PHE) of combustion sources. The signature ratio for the indicated sources are shown by dotted lines (Ravindra et al., 2008; Yunker et al., 2002).

CONCLUSIONS

The investigation of particulate PAHs from diesel and bio-diesel fuelled engines (with and without DOC) agricultural waste burning, wood, cow-dung cake, and coal combustion has been assessed. Diagnostic PAHs ratios range from each source sample has been reported and dominant sources contributing to the ambient aerosol loading have been reported.

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UNDERSTANDING THE MOLECULAR-LEVEL CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF SOURCES OF FINE (PM_{2.5}) WATER-SOLUBLE ORGANIC AEROSOL IN LUCKNOW

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Keywords: source apportionment, extractive electrospray mass spectrometry, water-soluble organic aerosol

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution is a major environmental hazard in India that claims over 1 million lives each year via exposure to fine airborne particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) (Lelieveld et al., 2015; Pandey et al., 2021). The densely populated Indo-Gangetic plains are severely impacted, and frequently experience very high PM_{2.5} concentrations contributed by diverse anthropogenic emission sources that exhibit large seasonal variations (Tobler et al., 2020). The current air pollution mitigation strategies stress on regulating anthropogenic emissions, however their effectiveness is restricted by a limited understanding of the types and relative impact of different air pollution sources in the region. Using Lucknow as our case study megacity, we applied offline state-of-the-art mass spectrometry and advanced source apportionment techniques to investigate the chemical composition and relative contributions of sources contributing to fine water-soluble organic aerosol in the mid-Indo-Gangetic plains.

METHODS

12-hour PM_{2.5} filter samples were collected between December 2020 and April 2021 using a high-volume sampler in Lucknow. The samples were dissolved in milliQ water and extracts were nebulized in laboratory to study the water-soluble organic aerosol (WSOA) using high-resolution time-of-flight aerosol mass spectrometry (HR-ToF-AMS), extractive electrospray ionization time-of-flight MS (EESI-LTOF MS) and total organic carbon analyzer. The elemental composition, inorganic ions and organic tracers (e.g. acids, sugars) were also measured using ion chromatography mass spectrometry. Subsequently, the source apportionment analysis was performed via positive matrix factorization (PMF) using the SoFi software in IGOR Pro to identify the relative contributions of different sources, and their bulk and molecular-level chemical profiles. PMF is a multivariate factor analysis tool that decomposes time trends in chemical composition into factor contributions and their chemical profiles by performing chemical mass balance between measured concentrations of species and the sum of source contributions for those species as explained by the equation below:

$$X_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^p g_{ik} * f_{kj} + e_{ij}$$

Here, X is the data matrix with i number of samples and j number of chemical species, p is the number of sources, f is the chemical profile of each source with mass contribution g, and e_{ij} is the residual for each sample.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The average wintertime WSOA concentration in Lucknow was 2-3 times higher than summer and reached a maximum of ~340 µg m⁻³ in December 2020. Source apportionment results showed that nighttime concentrations were 60% higher than daytime in winter driven largely by primary biomass burning sources (primary-BBOA) that contributed 40% of nighttime WSOA. These sources correlated strongly (Pearson correlation coefficient, r > 0.9) with specific organic tracers (e.g. levoglucosan, mannosan and galactosan), and their molecular-level chemical profile obtained from EESI-LTOF measurements showed strong contributions from reduced nitrogen-containing compounds (Figure 1) that have been previously shown to originate from unaged biomass burning emissions (Laskin et al., 2009) (Laskin et al. ES&T 2009). Overall, this suggested that local nighttime biomass burning (e.g. for heating purposes) could be an important source of air pollution during winter in Lucknow.

Aged biomass burning (aged-BBOA) contributions (12-14%) were also observed during winter, which together with primary-BBOA constituted over 50% of nighttime WSOA. The aged-BBOA was not observed in summer

indicating seasonal contributions from regional sources (e.g. agricultural burning). Sulfur-containing OA was also important that contributed 18-27% of WSOA during winter but reduced significantly (9-11%) during summer. It showed good correlations with selenium, methanesulfonic acid and 4-methylphthalic acid indicating anthropogenic source contributions (e.g. coal combustion).

Figure 1. Molecular composition of primary biomass-burning organic aerosol source in Lucknow.

The day- versus night time WSOA concentrations were comparable during summer. Biogenic source contributions were dominant, which constituted 50-60% of summertime WSOA. Interestingly, minor contributions (10-15%) from primary-BBOA emissions were also observed indicating continued influence of combustion-related sources across seasons. Alongside winter and summer sources, a spring season-based oxygenated OA (spring-OOA) factor was also observed that was prevalent in January-February 2021. It correlated with glycolate, tartarate, citrate and sulfamic acid, some of which result from aqueous-phase processing of acetic acid in the atmosphere, and indicated both biogenic and anthropogenic source contributions.

CONCLUSIONS

Our results showed that WSOA in Lucknow resulted from a combination of primary and secondary sources. Of these, primary-BBOA resulting from local combustion activities was a major contributor to wintertime WSOA and drove the very high concentration spikes ($> 300 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) in peak winter. It also somewhat influenced summer WSOA. Sulfur-containing OA from anthropogenic sources contributed nearly a quarter of WSOA mass in winter. We found regional biomass burning sources (aged-BBOA) to be relatively minor contributors in Lucknow during winter and absent in summer. During summer, biogenic sources were most important contributors ($>50\%$) to WSOA with minor contributions from other sources.

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SOURCE APPORTIONMENT OF PM_{2.5} PARTICLE BY ELEMENTAL (TRACER) PMF OVER DELHI REGION: A CAPITAL CITY OF INDIA

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Keywords: SOURCE APPORTIONMENT, PMF, PM_{2.5}, DELHI POLLUTION.

INTRODUCTION

Aerosols in the atmosphere have strong impacts on people's health, visibility, climate change, and the environment and crops by adding acids and nutrients (Molina et al., 2015; Ulbrich et al., 2009). Delhi is one of the most polluted regions in the world, with regular extreme air pollution events and haze incidents occurring in recent years, necessitating an understanding of the sources to build effective mitigation methods. The primary aim of this work has been to investigate the origins of elemental fraction of PM_{2.5} particles using the positive matrix factorization (PMF) model in the Delhi region during the summer season. The PMF model has significantly identified and categorized eight factors that contribute to air pollution. These factors are secondary chloride (32%), automotive emissions (20%), dust-related sources (19%), power plant emissions (12%), biomass burning (8%), waste incineration (5%), a factor associated with high levels of lead (3%), and industrial emissions (1%).

METHODS

The measurements of element have been conducted at the Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Delhi campus, located at coordinates 28°32'N and 77°11'E. The Xact measuring equipment are stored in a laboratory located on the highest floor of the building situated on the university campus, where temperature control is maintained. The study session for the summer season is from 1st April 1st to May 11th 2021. PMF is the multivariate factor analysis widely used that decompose data matrix into two matrixes: source profile matrix (F) and source contribution matrix (G). The equation of PMF is as follows.

$$X = GF + E \quad (1)$$

Where X is an input data matrix (m×n) of n species concentration at m time steps. G (m×p) is a fractional contribution matrix that estimates the p source profile at the m-time step. The model gives the optimal solution of equation (1) by minimizing the objective function Q (goodness of fit parameter) which is defined as:

$$Q = \sum_i^m \sum_j^n \left(\frac{e_{ij}}{u_{ij}} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1. Source contribution of elemental fraction of PM_{2.5}.

In this study, a comprehensive Positive Matrix Factorization (PMF) analysis was conducted to discern the primary sources contributing to Particulate Matter (PM). Eight significant factors were resolved, with

secondary chloride, vehicular emissions, dust, power plants, biomass burning, lead-rich sources, waste incineration, and industrial emissions accounting for 32%, 20%, 19%, 12%, 8%, 3%, 5%, and 1% of the total elemental fraction of PM_{2.5} concentration, respectively. Fig (1). Further characterization of these factors revealed distinct element profiles: secondary chloride was dominated by chlorine (Cl), vehicular emissions by silicon (Si), calcium (Ca), potassium (K), aluminium (Al), chlorine (Cl), sulphur (S), iron (Fe), titanium (Ti), and manganese (Mn), dust by silicon (Si) and iron (Fe), biomass burning by chlorine (Cl), potassium, and iron (Fe), waste incineration by chlorine (Cl), zinc (Zn), silicon (Si), and sulphur (S), and industrial emissions by copper (Cu) and iron (Fe). Fig(2). These findings contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of PM sources and their chemical compositions, aiding in the formulation of effective environmental policies.

Figure 2. Source profile resolved by PMF model.

CONCLUSIONS

- The dominant factors were ranked as follows: secondary chloride, vehicular emissions, dust, power plants, biomass burning, lead-rich sources, and industrial emissions.

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INVESTIGATION OF THE CONNECTION BETWEEN THE NUMBER SIZE DISTRIBUTION MODES AND MULTIPLE TRACE GASES (NO_x, SO₂, CO, AND O₃) AND PM_{2.5}.

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Keywords: Particle number concentration, Trace gases, primary emissions.

INTRODUCTION

Delhi's atmosphere is very complicated. Delhi's atmosphere contains aerosol particles sensitive to surface interactions, coagulation, deposition, and transit, making it difficult to pinpoint their sources based on physical size distributions. However, we can learn more about the sources of the particles by linking each particle mode to different trace gases. We may learn more about the primary sources of particles in each mode and the dynamical processes these particles go through under various pollution levels by analyzing how size-segregated particle number concentrations respond to variations in trace-gas and PM_{2.5} concentrations.

METHODS

The aerosol sampling was conducted inside the Indian Institute of Technology, Delhi campus (28.5457° N, 77.1928° E, 230 m above sea level). A scanning mobility particle sizer (SMPS) was used to measure the size distribution of submicron particles with sizes ranging from 10-1000 nm at 4-minute resolution. The hourly measurements of trace gases (SO₂ (ug/m³), NO_x (ug/m³), and CO (ppm)) are from the nearest Pollution Control Committee (DPCC) monitoring station located at RK Puram (about 3–4 km aerial from the measurement site). The correlation of different modes of particles with trace gas concentration was calculated using linear fitting.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

In general, there was no apparent relationship between the SO₂ concentration and the concentration of

nucleation mode particles. The concentrations of Aitken, accumulation mode particles, and SO₂ concentration exhibited positive correlations (0.3 and 0.4, respectively). This shows that local and

transported pollution influenced Aitken and accumulation mode particles. The association of accumulation mode particles with SO₂ shows that local and transported pollution was a factor. NO_x is regarded as the pollution tracer that primarily results from traffic (Beevers et al., 2012). Although traffic emissions can be a source of cluster mode particles on polluted days, we did not observe any association between the nucleation mode concentration and NO_x concentration (Zhou et al., 2020). These elements would lessen the relationship between NO_x concentration and particle numbers in the nucleation phase. Traffic emissions may be a significant source of Aitken mode particles, given the positive correlation between the Aitken mode particle number concentration and the NO_x concentration. According to past research (Zhou et al., 2020), traffic emissions can contribute to accumulation mode particles in urban settings, as evidenced by the positive correlation between the accumulation mode particle number concentration and the NO_x concentration. The CO concentration had a positive correlation with the accumulation mode particle number concentration, but no clear correlation with the particle number concentration of the two other modes.

CONCLUSIONS

The correlation between CO concentration and particle number concentrations in each mode was highly comparable to NO_x, indicating that CO and NO_x may have common sources, such as vehicle emissions. There was a positive link between the CO concentration and the particle number concentration of the accumulation mode. Still, there was no discernible correlation with the particle number concentration of the two other modes. This finding supports our earlier research that local emissions were primarily responsible for Aitken particle number concentrations. At the same time, regional and transported pollution significantly impacted accumulation mode particle number concentrations more than local emissions.

The concentrations of particles in different modes showed diverse reactions to changes in trace gas concentrations. The primary factor that led to the formation of nucleation mode particles was the existence of distinct sources and dynamics affecting each NPF. Traffic emissions significantly contributed to the formation of particles in all transportation modes and were the primary source of cluster and nucleation mode particles. The Aitken mode particles begin in local emissions, the impact of transported and regional pollutants, and their growth from the nucleation mode. Our analysis found that non-point sources (NPF) and transportation emissions substantially impacted the production of ultrafine particles in Delhi. To better understand the possible effects of ultrafine particles on health and air quality, we must conduct additional research on their origins and physical and chemical properties. Furthermore, policymakers should consider the presence of ultrafine particles when developing plans to manage air pollution in methods for determining the origin of sources, such as cluster analysis and receptor modeling. Regulations should be established to control primary emissions from transportation and precursor emissions that create secondary ultrafine particles through nucleation and subsequent particle growth.

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**ASSESSMENT OF VEHICULAR AMMONIA EMISSIONS IN THE MEGACITY OF DELHI:
RESULTS FROM NEAR- ROAD AND ON-ROAD MOBILE MEASUREMENTS**

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Keywords: On-road Ammonia, Vehicular Emissions, Mobile Monitoring.

INTRODUCTION

Ammonia is abundant in the Delhi's atmosphere which readily reacts with atmospheric acidic species such as nitric acid (HNO₃), sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄) and hydrochloric acid (HCL) to form inorganic components of PM_{2.5}, thereby affecting regional air quality. Agriculture including livestock farming is the major ammonia source which is considered to contribute ~60% of global inventory. Recent studies around the world showed that vehicular ammonia could be the dominant source especially in the urban areas where vehicles density is relatively higher (Fenn et al., 2018; Sun et al., 2014). NH₃ could be emitted from Three- Way Catalytic Convertors (TWCs) in gasoline vehicles and use of SCR catalyst in diesel engines where NH₃ in the form of urea is explicitly used (Abualqumboz et al., 2022; Hopke & Querol, 2022; Sun et al., 2014). Hence, in this study, we investigated near-road and on-road ammonia concentration via mobile monitoring approach to determine on-road NH₃/CO₂ emission ratio in the Delhi region. Given, the CO₂ emission inventories are relatively accurate, total vehicular emissions can be estimated. Finally, the obtained results are compared with regional emission inventory estimates and that of other megacities across the world.

METHODS

Clear Air Research Laboratory (CARLab) placed at IIT Delhi is a diesel-based research vehicle platform fitted with comprehensive suite of measurements characterizing range of particulate and gaseous species. For this, three gas analysers are installed in CARLab measuring CO₂ (Licor), CO (Horiba) and NO_x and NH₃ (Ecophysics, Switzerland). First, self-sampling measurements were conducted to ascertain the contribution of our own vehicle to the measurements obtained. Next, the background concentration was quantified and subtracted from the obtained time-series. The first percentile within certain temporal window is used to calculate background values (Pu et al., 2023). Then the on-road enhancements of concentrations were calculated by obtaining point-to-point differences between instant signal and background value. Finally, the on-road emission ratio was calculated to determine emission factor.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Self-sampling sampling results showed that there is minimal increase in the enhancement due to our own vehicle which is insignificant as compared to on-road concentrations. Near-road and on-road mobile sampling was conducted. On-road concentration were significantly higher than fixed-site concentrations obtained from CPCB site. After applying background estimation technique, on-road emission ratio was obtained to calculate vehicular emission estimates for the Delhi region.

Figure 1. Distribution of on-road emission ratio from mobile monitoring in Delhi region.

CONCLUSIONS

On-road emission ratio of NH_3/CO_2 (ppb/ppm) is obtained via mobile monitoring from the Delhi region. Vehicular emission estimates were obtained from this study.

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**AEROSOL MASS DENSITY MEASUREMENTS FOR VARIOUS CHEMICAL SPECIES USING
BETA ATTENUATION TECHNIQUE**

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Keywords: Aerosol, Mass concentration, Beta Attenuation.

INTRODUCTION:

Beta attenuation technique has been used widely for continuous monitoring of atmospheric aerosol mass concentration. Many researchers have used BAM to measure PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ at different locations around the world. Sensors based on beta gauging have capability to characterize aerosol concentrations with high spatial and temporal resolution (Gobeli et al., 2008 and Jaklevic et al., 1981). In general, the accuracy of these monitors relies on the conversion factors which are obtained in laboratory conditions or at the most localized field environment. In absence of availability of the site dependent conversion factors or the option to obtain better approximations, BAMs are used with the same set of conditions as mentioned during the installation. This is then attributed to the variation in the aerosol water content or the volatility of the constituents of the sampled particles (Tomasi et al., 2017). The application of same mass attenuation coefficient for different environmental conditions using BAM for mass concentration measurements appears to be a general logic. This study aims at filling this gap area viz., measuring conversion factor/mass attenuation coefficient for different chemical compounds and variation of mass attenuation coefficient for different environmental conditions.

OBJECTIVE

The aim of this study was the experimental determination of mass attenuation coefficient for different chemical compounds representative of typical Indian atmospheric aerosol conditions using a laboratory level prototype beta attenuation monitor named **Automatic Aerosol Activity Sampler (AAAS)**. The two major objectives of the study can be listed down as:

- Obtaining 'beta attenuation coefficient' for chemical compounds representative of typical Indian atmospheric aerosol environment.
- Estimating the weighted averaged conversion factors for urban, rural and marine Indian atmospheric aerosol conditions.

Automatic Aerosol Activity Sampler (AAAS)

AAAS instrument is similar to beta attenuation monitor (BAM) but works with a different methodology and a different set-up. Loaded filter paper samples were kept between a C-14 beta source and plastic scintillation detector. It consists of beta ray source C-14 (coated powder of barium carbonate) whose maximum beta particle energy is 156 KeV having half-life of 5568 years, plastic scintillator detector ZnS (Ag), aerosol sampling arrangement and counting electronics. The beta ray flux passing through absorbing matter, such as dust deposited on a filter decreases nearly exponentially with the increasing mass.

Variation of beta attenuation for single species

Varying mass samples for aerosol particles of individual NaCl, (NH₄)₂SO₄, KCl, NaNO₃, Oxalic Acid, MgSO₄, Ca(NO₃)₂, KI, Soot, CsI and Atmosphere were generated. These samples were then subjected to AAAS and for each species, beta attenuation was obtained. Beta attenuation is expected to increase with deposited mass on the filter paper. For all the species, saturation of beta attenuation with respect to mass was observed. Fig. 2 (a) show the % beta attenuation variation with mass for aerosol particles deposited on the filter paper.

(a)

(b)

For different chemical species, % beta attenuation saturated after reaching threshold mass will remain constant. To determine this limiting value of mass or the upper limit of the instrument, all plots were fitted empirically using following equation Fig 2 (b)

$Y = Y_0 + A \exp\left(-\frac{X}{t}\right)$ where, Y_0 is the saturation value, limiting mass = Mass corresponding to $0.9 Y_0$. Thus, it could be concluded that the instrument is not suitable for use above this limiting mass. Table 1 shows the estimated limiting masses of various aerosol species considered in this study with their respective beta attenuations.

Table 1: Limiting masses and % beta attenuation of various aerosol species

Species	Saturation Value (Y_0)	Limiting mass (mg)	% Beta Attenuation
			Y
NaCl	86.56	61.112	84.523
NaNO ₃	81.72	64.094	79.174
Soot	88.45	65.339	85.825
MgSO ₄	80.97	72.756	77.533
CsI	93.73	76.248	88.511
Oxalic acid	94.93	81.058	88.907
KCl	82.98	81.252	77.794
KI	95.1	91.759	87.352
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	91.36	99.25	82.374
Atmosphere	108.76	138.72	88.146

CONCLUSIONS

Beta attenuation was studied for NaCl, (NH₄)₂SO₄, KCl, NaNO₃, Oxalic Acid, MgSO₄, Ca(NO₃)₂, KI, Soot, CsI, Atmospheric Samples. The study was categorized in two segments viz., Variation of beta attenuation and determination of mass attenuation coefficient (μ_m) from I/I_0 plots for various species. The beta attenuation varied from 53.2% for atmospheric aerosol and 57% for (NH₄)₂SO₄ to 70.8% for CsI. This highlights the importance of not using single beta attenuation Coefficient (μ_m), as the chemical composition of atmospheric aerosol particles is a function of location, season and source term.

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LONG-TERM AEROSOL OPTICAL DEPTH VARIATION OVER INDO GANGETIC BASIN

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Keywords: AOD, MODIS, AERONET, IGB.

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols, comprising various solid and liquid particles in the atmosphere, significantly affect Earth's climate, water cycle, and human health by scattering and absorbing solar radiation (Ramanathan *et al.*, 2001, Ramanathan and Carmichael, 2008, Lelieveld *et al.*, 2019). They originate from natural sources like dust and sea salt spray and human-made sources like vehicle emissions and industrial activities.

In the last two decades, Earth Observing System (EOS) sensors, including MODIS, MISR, OMI, AVHRR, and VIIRS, have been developed to monitor aerosols at different spatial and temporal resolutions (Bilal *et al.*, 2017; Mhawish *et al.*, 2018). In India, satellite remote sensing and ground-observed aerosol data, particularly from MODIS and VIIRS, have been widely used.

This research focuses on assessing the accuracy of MODIS aerosol products, specifically Terra-MODIS AOD (MOD08_D3), by comparing them with ground-based AERONET AOD measurements. The study covers 13 years, from 2010 to 2022, at three locations (Jaipur, Kanpur, and Gandhi College) in the highly populated and polluted Indo-Gangetic Basin (IGB) region.

METHODS

In this study, we utilized AERONET sites located in Jaipur (26.91° N; 75.78° E), Kanpur (26.45° N, 80.33° E), and Gandhi College (25.87° N; 84.13° E) over the Indo-Gangetic Basin (IGB). The IGB encompasses 21% of India's land area and houses over 40% of the country's population. Ground observation data were collected from these three AERONET locations. We used MODIS terra satellite data, specifically Collection MOD08_D3_v6, to obtain Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) at 550nm resolution at these locations. Additionally, AERONET AOD at 500nm was used, and values at 550nm were estimated using the Angstrom exponent within the wavelength range of 440-675nm. Both AERONET and MODIS offer daily mean AOD observations, with AERONET providing ground-based data and MODIS offering satellite-based data at 1-degree resolution. We conducted an inter-annual temporal comparison between AERONET and MODIS AOD, assessing the correlation coefficient (r), root mean square error (RMSE), and relative mean bias (RMB) to evaluate MODIS AOD performance at these three IGB locations.

Figure 2 Geographical distribution of AERONET sites at three different locations over IGB in India.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 2 (a-c) displays annual MODIS and AERONET AOD variations at three locations (Gandhi College, Jaipur, and Kanpur) in the IGB region from 2010 to 2022.

- MODIS AOD annual means: Gandhi College (0.67 ± 0.31), Jaipur (0.29 ± 0.24), Kanpur (0.69 ± 0.30).
- AERONET AOD annual means: Gandhi College (0.65 ± 0.27), Jaipur (0.42 ± 0.21), Kanpur (0.60 ± 0.25).
- High AOD (>0.5) at Gandhi College and Kanpur indicates mixed aerosol loading, while Jaipur has low aerosol loading.
- Increasing AOD trends: Gandhi College (0.013/year MODIS, 0.010/year AERONET), Jaipur (0.009/year MODIS, 0.018/year AERONET), Kanpur (0.003/year MODIS and AERONET).

Figure 3 (a-c) correlation between MODIS and AERONET AOD at three locations (Gandhi College, Jaipur, and Kanpur) in the IGB region from 2010 to 2022.

- Strong correlation between MODIS and AERONET AOD at Gandhi College (r : 0.92), with slight MODIS underestimation (RMB: -0.028) and low RMSE (0.039).

- Correlation at Jaipur (0.64) and Kanpur (0.92) also shows good agreement. RMB: Jaipur (0.15), Kanpur (-0.083). RMSE: Jaipur (0.15), Kanpur (0.083).

Figure 3. Time series plot of yearly average AOD of MODIS and AERONET (for $\lambda = 550\text{nm}$) at (a) Gandhi College (b) Jaipur (c) Kanpur.

Figure 4. Scatter plot of MODIS AOD at 550 nm against the AERONET AOD 550 nm at three sites (a) Gandhi College (b) Jaipur (c) Kanpur over IGB region. The solid red line is the 1:1 line.

CONCLUSIONS

The MODIS AOD was analyzed using AERONET ground-based data across three IGB region locations from the years 2010 to 2022. The assessment of annual trends and correlations, providing insights into AOD variations. The conclusion of annual trends and correlation between MODIS and AERONET AOD are provided in the bullet points below,

- The highest MODIS mean AOD: is at Kanpur (0.69), lowest: is at Jaipur (0.29).
- The highest AERONET mean AOD: is at Gandhi College (0.65), lowest: is at Jaipur (0.42).
- Highest annual trend (MODIS): Gandhi College (0.013/year), lowest: Kanpur (0.003/year).
- Highest annual trend (AERONET): Jaipur (0.018/year), lowest: Kanpur (0.003/year).
- Highest correlation (MODIS vs. AERONET): Kanpur (0.92), lowest: Jaipur.
- Highest RMSE: Jaipur (0.15), lowest: Gandhi College (0.039).
- Highest RMB: Jaipur (0.15), lowest: Gandhi College (-0.028).

This study sheds light on AOD trends and comparisons in this highly polluted area.

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STUDY OF AEROSOLS OPTICAL DEPTH OVER FOUR MAJOR CITIES OF INDIA

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Keywords: AOD, Air Quality, MODIS, RH, Temperature.

INTRODUCTION

Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) is an important parameter that determines how much direct sunlight is prevented by aerosol particles that can reach at the earth surface. During recent decade, increasing urbanization and industrialization leads to increase in pollution load. With such a massive rate of pollution, AOD quantity has also significantly increased over India. Ramanathan et al., (2001) and Lawrence and Lelieveld, (2010) reported that Indian subcontinent is considerably affected by long-range transportation of aerosols. AOD over four major cities of India i.e. Delhi, Kolkata, Chennai and Jaipur have been analyzed using satellite data of twelve years (2007-2018).

METHODS

The present research attempt to analyses the annual and seasonal variations of AOD over four major cities of India. Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) onboard NASA's Aqua and Terra platform Level-3 AOD data has been utilized to study. The monthly variation of mean AOD for the twelve-year period has been assessed by using radial plot and frequency distribution respectively. AOD tendencies have been calculated to know the prominent change in average AOD. Twelve years average AOD as well percentage increase in AOD has been estimated. The metrological conditions, such as Temperature, Relative humidity as well winds speed and direction are also archived and matched. Wind direction and wind speed for winter, pre-monsoon, monsoon and post monsoon season have been depicted by spatial plot. Further, cumulative effect of mean AOD along with mean temperature and RH are provided to conclude the main points drawn from the study.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Annual mean analysis reveals highest aerosol loading in Indo Gangetic Plains (IGP) and significant increasing trends from past to present year. Significant statistical trends have been found at 95% confidence level. Delhi recorded maximum AOD during monsoon season (0.95-1.05), whereas in Kolkata maximum AOD observed during winter season (0.95-1.05). Chennai shows low to moderate mean AOD for all the seasons. Annual and Seasonal mean AOD tendencies have been calculated to know the prominent changes in average aerosol loading during the past twelve year (2007-2018). Maximum increase in AOD percentage from 2007-2018 is obtained for Kolkata (39%), followed by Delhi (27.34%), Chennai (26.30%) and Jaipur (16.53%). Further, cumulative effects of different meteorological parameters i.e. temperature, wind speed and relative humidity along with AOD have been studied over four major cities. Annual and seasonal AOD tendencies (%) for twelve-year period (2007-2018) computed by combined MODIS Terra and Aqua product are shown in Table 1.

Table1: Annual and Seasonal mean AOD tendencies calculated from the period 2007-2018 over four major cities.

City	AOD tendencies (%)				
	Annual	Seasonal			
		DJF	MAM	JJAS	ON
Delhi	6.86%	12%	0%	4.74%	0%
Kolkata	12.20%	15.9%	15.80%	3.50%	14.36%
Chennai	4.07%	2.02%	1.30%	4.80%	4.50%
Jaipur	3.0%	4.08%	0%	-2.21	4.90%

CONCLUSIONS

The results demonstrated that the overall, 2007-2018 twelve years mean AOD reflects, Delhi was in the peak of aerosol concentration (0.821 ± 0.057), closely followed by Kolkata (0.817 ± 0.08) and then Chennai (0.433 ± 0.028), whereas Jaipur (0.430 ± 0.027) recorded the least aerosol loading

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**DIURNAL VARIATION OF PARTICLE NUMBER CONCENTRATION AND SIZE
DISTRIBUTION OF AEROSOL PARTICLES IN MYSURU CITY, INDIA**

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Keywords: PARTICLE NUMBER CONCENTRATION, NANOSCAN SMPS, SIZE DISTRIBUTION.

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols (ultrafine and fine particles) play a key role in understanding the global climate change and exposure to these particles cause adverse health effects on humans by damaging heart, lungs and even the central nervous system increasing the risk of mortality and morbidity (Slezakova et al., 2013, Gui et al., 2022). The size distribution, mass density, number concentration and surface density are the key parameters of the atmospheric aerosol particles which are significant to study the risk and influence they cause on human health and atmospheric phenomenon. In this study, the particle number concentration and size distribution of the airborne atmospheric aerosol particles in Mysuru City (12.2958° N, 76.6394° E), Karnataka State, India was studied.

METHODS

Particle number concentration and size distribution of the airborne particles in the range 11.5 nm to 365.2 nm were measured in Mysuru City, India during 2020 – 2022 using a NanoScan SMPS(TSI 3910) (Tritscher *et al.*, 2013). Twenty four hours measurements were conducted in two different locations to study the diurnal variation as well as influence of traffic on distribution of aerosols. Measurements at both the sites were done 1 to 2 m above the ground level. Number concentration of different modes of particles i.e. nucleation mode (11.5 – 20.5nm), Aitken mode (20.5 – 100nm) and accumulation mode (100 – 365.2nm) were observed.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The studies were conducted at Location 1, inside the University of Mysore campus, which is slightly free from vehicular pollution with very low traffic and Location 2, a national highway where the vehicular pollution is high. Total concentration of the particles (20.5 – 100 nm) was observed to be higher in the early morning and evening compared to afternoon and night at both the locations which hints the role of traffic in the total concentration. Strong correlation between traffic movement and total concentration was observed only in the morning.

The comparative study of average concentration of different sized particles is shown in the graph (Figure 1). The nature of the graph for size distribution with average particle concentration is showing similar behaviour at both the locations under observation. The particles with size 36.5 nm to 115.5 nm showed higher concentrations. It was observed that particles of size 75 to 150 nm are found to have higher concentration in highway than in case of university campus. But higher sized particles (205.4nm, 273.8nm and 365.2nm) are having slightly higher concentration in campus than in the highway. Possible reason for this is higher sized particles are secondary particles which are formed from the coagulation of the nucleation and Aitken mode particles. And these particles can travel long distance as well.

Total concentration includes the sum of an hourly averaged concentration of particles from 11.5 – 365.2 nm (Figure 2). This gives us an idea about how much particles (in this range) we are exposed to per minute. It has been found that daily average of total concentration shows similar pattern for the diurnal variation in both the locations. Starting from midnight the total concentration shows minimum values in both locations. From 5 – 6 am onwards the value starts increasing with the sunrise, beginning of human activities and vehicle movement with peak value of about 22000 particles/cm³ in campus and 50000 particles/cm³ in the highway and thereafter the concentration has decreased in both the locations. The two possible reasons may be the vehicle movement was observed to be less in the afternoon than in the morning hours (7 – 10 am) and also due to the increase in temperature in the afternoon hours, the particles travel higher in the atmosphere and faster. Since our observation site is near to the ground, we see comparatively lower value in the total

concentration. During late afternoon and evening hours an increase in the total number concentration was observed but not as much as in early morning hours. A strong correlation of total average concentration with anthropogenic activities and vehicle moments was observed mainly in the morning hours. From midnight till sunrise, both the locations showed similar total number concentrations. In fact, from midnight to 4am, college campus is having slightly higher particle concentration than in the highway. This emphasizes the role of traffic and anthropogenic sources in the total concentration.

Figure 1. Size dependent particle number concentration

Figure 2. Diurnal variation of particle number concentration

CONCLUSIONS

The particle number concentration and size distribution of aerosols were studied in Mysuru city. It was observed that the total concentration and size distribution of aerosols are affected by the anthropogenic activities hinting the role of traffic besides this the temperature also plays a key role.

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AEROSOL CLOUD INTERACTIONS

**LONG-TERM VARIABILITY IN AEROSOL, CLOUD AND THEIR INTERACTION OVER NORTHERN
INDIAN OCEAN**

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Keywords: AEROSOL, CLOUD, NORTHERN INDIAN OCEAN, ANTHROPOGENIC EMISSION, CLIMATE CHANGE

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols have crucial impacts on regional and global climate at different temporal scale and potential to modulate the Earth's radiation budget through their direct (via scattering/absorbing of solar radiation) and indirect effects (via serving as cloud condensation nuclei and perturbing of cloud microphysics). The interaction between aerosol and cloud is one of the largest uncertainties to determine global radiation and future climate projections (Allen et al., 2021). These uncertainty in aerosol – cloud interaction (ACI) is largely depended on regional heterogeneity in aerosol and cloud, their vertical distribution, meteorological conditions, and their interaction with complex non-linear atmospheric processes. Northern Indian Ocean (NIO) experience a large heterogeneity in aerosol loading on both spatial temporal scale via continental outflow and long-range transport from adjacent arid/semi-arid regions and largely governed by wind circulation patterns (Kumar and Tiwari, 2023; Tiwari et al., 2022). Thus, long term quantification of changes in aerosol and cloud characteristics and their interactions on both temporal as well as spatial scale will provide a crucial information for the better assessment of future climate change. Thus, in this study, we try to evaluate the long-term spatial-temporal variability in aerosol and cloud parameters, their trend and mutual interactions over the Northern Indian Ocean.

METHODS

In this study, 18 years (2003–2020) MODIS Aqua (MYD08_M3_C6.1) Level_3 daily data for both aerosol and cloud properties have been analyzed. Only the daytime liquid phase valid retrievals of cloud properties and spatio-temporal collocated aerosols are used in the analysis. Generalised Least Squares fitting method is used to calculate long term trend. ACI matrix is calculated by method suggested in Feingold et al., (2001). For ACI calculation, cloud top temperature < 273 K and cloud top pressure < 680 hPa at every collocated grid point are excluded to ensure shallow warm clouds while cloud optical depth < 4 and cloud effective radius (CER) < 4 μ m are also discarded to avoid uncertainties associated with optically thinner clouds.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

A larger spatial variability in aerosol optical depth (AOD) is observed with maximum value (AOD > 0.3) near the coast which decreases gradually towards open ocean suggesting influence of continental outflow. Cluster analysis of air mass back trajectories confirmed a significant contribution of continental sources in aerosol loading over the different regions of NIO through the long-range transportation (not shown here). In contrast to AOD, CER shows an opposite nature in spatial distribution. An increasing trend in AOD (>0.003 yr⁻¹) is found over the entire NIO except northern Arabian Sea where AOD show decreasing trend (-0.001 yr⁻¹) despite having of highest long term mean AOD climatology (i.e. 0.44 \pm 0.03). The overall pattern ACI suggest a significant prevalence of anti-Twomey effect over northern portion of NIO during winter season that later shifted southward in pre-monsoon and summer monsoon (not shown here).

Figure 1. Spatial variability in long term mean (a) AOD, (b) CER, (c) annual AOD trend and (d) ACI (for DJF month) over the Northern Indian Ocean.

CONCLUSIONS

An increasing trend in AOD ($>0.003 \text{ yr}^{-1}$) over the NIO, particularly over coastal region suggests a significant contribution of anthropogenic emission in total aerosol loading. Study suggests that although ACI index highlight anti-Twomey effect yet the interaction between aerosol and cloud may not be casual and depends on other factors like regional aerosol types, meteorological conditions etc. The present study will provide in-depth information about the aerosol-cloud characteristics for a long-term scale over NIO and could be useful in regional aerosol-cloud interaction induced climate forcing estimation.

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OBSERVATION OF CLOUD BASE HEIGHT DURING THE PRE-MONSOON AND MONSOON SEASONS OVER DIBRUGARH

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Keywords: Ceilometer CL31, Cloud base height, cloud occurrence frequency.

INTRODUCTION

Clouds occurring at any altitude have the ability to warm or cool the Earth's atmosphere by absorbing or reflecting back the solar radiation. Clouds either trap the emitted longwave radiation, which warms the environment or reflect back the incoming solar radiation into space and thus cooling the atmosphere (Satheesh and Moorthy, 2005; Lee *et al.*, 2009; Wright *et al.*, 2010). A heavy cloud cover shields the surface from incoming solar radiation thereby cooling the atmosphere, whereas at night, the outgoing radiation is trapped by cloud cover and subsequently warms it. Besides impacting the radiative balance of the Earth, clouds are observed to impact the global greenhouse effect (Liou, 1986) and thus have a weightiness in climate studies. Apart from atmospheric phenomena, understanding and analysing cloud base heights has its importance in aviation safety as well. The cloud dynamics is affected by aerosols through "semi-direct" and "indirect" effects, that in turn impact on climate in general. The semi-direct effect is the warming or cooling of the atmosphere as a result of aerosols absorbing or diffusing solar energy. This may alter the stability and circulation of the atmosphere, affecting the development and characteristics of clouds. The impact of aerosols on cloud characteristics like cloud duration, albedo, and precipitation effectiveness is connected to the indirect effect. The present study is carried out at Dibrugarh (27.47°N, 94.91°E, 111 m amsl), a location that presents possibilities to investigate a wide range of meteorological phenomena and their effects on local and regional climates owing to its varied topography, proximity to the Brahmaputra River and the Himalayan foothills. Moreover, the cloud characteristics and its dynamics over this location has not been explored yet. Thus, the present study will add new insights into the cloud dynamics.

METHODS

To continuously monitor the clouds over Dibrugarh, a Vaisala Ceilometer (CL31) is operational from March, 2023. This instrument gives near vertical short and powerful laser pulses of wavelength ~910 nm up to a height of 7.5 kilometres with a resolution of 10 metres. The backscattered light provides the information on presence of clouds, haze, fog, precipitation and other hydrometeors. The ceilometer functions on the correspondence of the time difference between the transmitted and received laser pulse after backscattering from the hydrometeors.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The Frequency of occurrence of low-level, mid-level and high-level cloud base height during March-August 2023 reveals prevalence of more mid-level clouds in April (~80%) followed by March (60%) (Figure 1). This is associated with more Convective Available Potential Energy values during the pre-monsoon season (figure not shown). During monsoon season, the low level clouds are more dominant with the highest occurrence frequency of ~50% in August followed by ~45% in July. Thus, the monsoon rain mostly occurs from low level clouds. Overall the cloud coverage is more in monsoon season, with ~96% of time the sky

being overcast, than in pre-monsoon with least cloud occurrence in April (~47%). These CBHs are used further to validate Sentinel-5P NRTI satellite observation.

Figure 1: The cloud occurrence frequency of Low-level, Mid-level, and High-level clouds during the months of (a) March, (b) April, (c) May, (d) June, (e) July, (f) August

CONCLUSIONS

There exists a distinction between the monsoon and pre-monsoon clouds over Dibrugarh as observed from Cloud Base Height statistics. Mid-level clouds are more prominent in pre-monsoon, whereas in monsoon low-clouds are prevalent.

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OBSERVED AEROSOL CHARACTERISTICS AND THE ROLE OF METEOROLOGICAL PARAMETERS DURING WINTERTIME FOG/LOW CLOUD EVENT OVER A HIGH-ALTITUDE SITE, WESTERN GHATS, INDIA

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Keywords: Fog/low cloud, aerosol and meteorological parameters, ground-based observation, Western Ghats.

INTRODUCTION

Fog, which can be defined as a cloud at ground level with surface visibility less than 1km. Over Indian sub-continent, fog is observed mainly during the winter season (December–January). This fog can cause economic loss due to major disruption to road, aviation, and marine transport (Gultepe et al., 2007). Many studies have reported the economic loss due to fog (Kulkarni et al.2019; Pithani et al.,2020) Therefore understanding the formation and evolution of fog events is essential. It has been reported that the formation of fog is highly influenced by variations in land-surface characteristics, topography, and pollution, which affect the dynamics and microphysical properties. Hence the prediction of fog has long been a challenge to the operational forecasters. This is mainly due to the complex processes involved in fog formation, development, and dissipation (Gultepe et al. 2007, Pithani et al. 2019), which are not well represented. For a better representation of fog-related processes in numerical weather prediction (NWP) models, we need accurate observation from various locations/ environments.

METHODS

For understanding the processes associated with wintertime fog event various ground-based instruments has been used. Ground-based radiometer (MWR) of model MP-3000A (manufactured by Radiometrics Corporation, USA), a 35-channel temperature, water vapor, and liquid water profiler was used to confirm the presence of fog and to understand the thermodynamics associated with fog event. Apart from obtaining the vertical profiles, the radiometer also provides surface parameters, i.e., temperature and relative humidity, integrated products such as vapor and liquid, and cloud base height. Environmental Dust Monitor (EDM 180) from GRIMM Aerosol Technik, which has been designed for the continuous measurement of airborne dust and its particle size distribution (<http://www.dustmonitor.com/>). The TSI- Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS) which measures 10–300 nm particle concentration with a minimum scan time of 5 min was used to get the size resolved aerosol number concentration. The measured values are distinguished according to the fractions PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, and PM_{1.0} in $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. An Automatic Weather Station (AWS) is used to obtain the wind direction (WD) and wind speed (WS).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Initially, fog event was identified using visualizing INSAT 3D and MODIS satellite true colour images in addition to the details India Meteorological Department (IMD) daily weather report (IDWR). Based on the images and IDWR, a fog event was identified on 15 December 2016. In this study, various processes related to the fog event observed during 14-15 December 2016 have been presented. Surface parameters such as temperature (T) and dew point temperature (TD) analysed showed very less difference (T-TD) during 12:00 am to 08:30 am on 15th Dec. 2016. At the same time, the RH also showed above 99%. Temporal variability of liquid profile obtained from MWR showed ~ 0.06 to 0.10 gm^{-3} till 500 m above ground level (AGL) and integrated liquid showed a maximum of 0.52 mm during the same time. Analysed cloud base height (CBH) also showed below 500m AGL during the same time. Variations in all these parameters confirm the presence of nocturnal fog over the study region.

Further analysis of aerosol number size distribution and PM_{2.5} showed lower number and mass concentration during the event compared to pre- and post-event. This suggests the scavenging of ambient aerosols either by fog water droplets scavenged the aerosols via nucleation or coagulation and hence reduction in interstitial aerosol concentration. To understand the impact of meteorological parameters variability associated with wind speed has been checked. It is noted that prior to the event winds were strong whereas

there existed calm winds during the event. This suggests the atmosphere remained saturated due to less mixing and under strong winds there is a mixing of dry air leading to the prevention of fog formation.

Fig. Temporal variation of T, TD, RH, CBH and Integrated liquid along with vertical profile of liquid.

CONCLUSIONS

- The present study showed the robustness of co-located ground-based observations for the detailed understanding of fog-related processes over a particular region.
- Temporal variability of surface meteorological parameters along with liquid confirmed the presence of fog.
- The fog was observed from night to early morning hours of 15 December 2016 suggesting the radiation type of fog.
- Reduced aerosol number and mass concentration indicated the scavenging of ambient aerosols by fog.
- Calm winds during the period were conducive to the persistence of fog for a long hour.

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UNDERSTANDING THE IMPACT OF ANTHROPOGENIC ACTIVITIES ON CCN ACTIVATION OVER A HIGH-ALTITUDE SITE IN WESTERN GHATS, INDIA

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Keywords: Aerosol-CCN, anthropogenic activity, ground-based observations, high-altitude

INTRODUCTION

The capability of an aerosol particle to act as a cloud condensation nucleus (CCN) for the generation of cloud droplets depends first and foremost on the local supersaturation (SS) conditions, followed by its size and chemical composition. When considering a specific composition and supersaturation level, the activation of a particle as CCN is solely determined by its dry size. The spectrum of CCN, which portrays the availability of CCN at different SS, is influenced by various factors, namely the number concentration, standard deviation, median diameter, and internal mixing state of the particle distribution. Understanding the physico-chemical properties of atmospheric aerosols provides insight into the hygroscopic behaviour of aerosols and CCN-activity which in turn affect the atmospheric radiation budget, cloud formation processes, and human health.

METHODS

To study the aerosol-CCN variability and its activation characteristics over a high-altitude site, Mahabaleshwar (17.92°N, 73.66°E, 1348 m AMSL), various ground-based observations have been used. The TSI- Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS) which measures 10–300 nm particle concentration with a minimum scan time of 5 min was used to get the size-resolved aerosol number concentration. Cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) were measured with a CCN counter (CCN-200), which is a continuous flow thermal gradient instrument of the Roberts and Nenes (2005) design manufactured by Droplet Measurement Technologies (DMT). This can be operated in different supersaturations (SS) varying from 0.07 to 2% and at present SS of 0.5%.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Initially, temporal variation of CCN concentration for four different SS has been analyzed from May to October for three year period (2020-2022) to understand its behaviour during southwest (SW) monsoon (June to September or JJAS) including transition periods (May and October). A bimodal distribution was noted in the diurnal variation of CCN concentration with prominent peaks in the morning and afternoon hours and the CCN concentration showed an increase with respect to SS, irrespective of the period of observation. It is noted that the morning (afternoon) peak is much stronger for JJAS (May) (Figure.1.). No significant diurnal variation was noted for October month but overall the concentration remained higher compared to other months. A detailed analysis of CCN during the southwest (SW) monsoon showed high concentrations during June and September compared to peak monsoon (July and August) over the study region. Further, the total aerosol number concentration and number size distribution has been analyzed which also exhibited a bimodal peak similar to CCN concentration. Analyzed aerosol number size distribution showed the dominance of Aitken mode particles (~30-150 nm particle diameter) over the study region. These are agreeable with the reported results from the same region (Leena et al., 2016; Mukherjee et al., 2018). Further, the CCN to total aerosol ratio (or activation fraction, AF) has been analyzed which varied from 0.1 to 1.1 with clear diurnal variability. AF showed higher in the very early morning hours and later slightly decreased during SW monsoon which is probably due to the significance of size distribution of aerosol particles or the chemical nature of emitted aerosols, i.e., mixed nature (hydrophilic and hydrophobic) (Singla et al., 2019). For a detailed understanding of the impact of anthropogenic activities two contrast periods have been considered i.e., the year 2020 (COVID-19 lockdown or restricted period) and 2022 (COVID-19 unlock or no restriction). Explicit analysis of these two periods showed a relatively higher concentration of aerosol and CCN during the year 2022 compared to 2020 especially during SW monsoon. The difference in the

aerosol-CCN concentration between the years 2020 and 2022 suggested that anthropogenic activities are significantly contributing to CCN activation (figure.1). As the study region is one of the best tourist spots of Western Ghats (WG), there is a possibility of vehicular emission is contributing to the aerosol loading and CCN activation during the year 2022 which is absent for 2020.

Figure.1. Diurnal variation of CCN concentration for 0.5% SS for May, JJAS, Oct respectively for the year 2020 to 2022 (top row) and Bar pot showing the mean CCN concentration for 2020 and 2022 along with difference for May, JJAS and Oct. Vertical line - standard deviation

CONCLUSIONS

- Aerosol-CCN variability over a high-altitude site has been studied using ground-based observations.
- A clear temporal variation is noted in aerosol and CCN concentration over the study region with morning (afternoon) peak being much stronger for JJAS (May).
- Variability in AF suggested the significance of size distribution of aerosol particles or the chemical nature of emitted aerosols
- Analysis suggests a significant role of anthropogenic activities in aerosol loading and contributing to the CCN activation, particularly during SW monsoon over the study region.

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INVESTIGATING THE MICROPHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF WARM CLOUDS OVER SOUTH ASIA

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Keywords: T-RE CURVE, AEROSOLS

INTRODUCTION

Clouds play a significant role in the Earth-atmosphere system, influencing regional weather patterns, precipitation, and the radiative budget. However, aerosol-cloud interaction (ACI) is recognized as one of the largest sources of uncertainty in predicting climate change. Higher aerosol concentrations lead to an increase in cloud droplet concentration and a decrease in droplet size. Consequently, this results in a higher visible albedo for clouds with a constant liquid water path (LWP) (Twomey 1974). Higher aerosol concentrations may also enhance the amount of low-level cloudiness and cloud lifetime by reducing drizzle, thereby imposing an additional cooling effect on the global climate system (Albrecht, 1989).

Understanding the evolution of the vertical profiles of cloud microphysical properties is crucial for determining their impact on the hydrological cycle and radiative effects. From cloud base to top, the microphysical classification includes zones of diffusional droplet growth, coalescence droplet growth, rainout, mixed-phase precipitation, and glaciation (Rosenfield and Lensky., 1998). The main objective of this study is to investigate the microphysical zones of various cloud clusters that form over oceanic regions in South Asia. To achieve this, Level 1 and Level 2 data from NASA's NPP-SUOMI mission are utilized.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

We utilize space-borne measurements from the Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite (VIIRS) onboard SUOMI-National Polar-Orbiting Partnership satellite platform, launched on October 28, 2011 to retrieve cloud properties. The satellite-based data for this study are available and accessible from NASA website (<https://ladsweb.modaps.eosdis.nasa.gov>). The methodology used here involves defining a window containing a convective cloud cluster with elements representing all growing stages, typically containing several thousands of pixels. Calculate the median and other percentiles of the Cloud drop effective radius (r_e) for each 1°C interval of cloud-top temperature (T). Then graphical representation of the T versus r_e curves of the 15th, 50th, and 85th percentiles are displayed. Cloud drops nucleate near the base and gradually grow with height. Therefore, the cloudy pixels with the smallest r_e and highest T represent the cloud base. The underlying assumption of this method is that time and space are exchangeable, so the composition of the tops of various clouds reaching different heights in a convective cluster at a given time is similar to the time evolution of a cloud top composition as it grows with time.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

T- r_e profiles (15, 50, and 85 percentiles) for various cloud clusters over oceanic regions of South Asia are studied. Analysis reveals the existence of different microphysical processes in various selected cloud clusters and most of the changes that appear are related to the environment whether it is clean or polluted. For a clean environment (AOD ~ .206), large increase of droplet growth rate with height indicates coalescence (Figure.1). On the other hand, within a polluted environment (AOD ~ .62), the sluggish rise of cloud effective radius with height above the cloud base points to cloud droplet growth primarily driven by diffusional processes, with minimal coalescence (Figure.2).

The existence of the threshold (14 μ m) can be used to explain the suppressing effect of anthropogenic aerosols on precipitation, leading to substantial weather modification in polluted areas. These interactions between aerosols and clouds thus play a major role in the Earth's energy budget which can potentially accelerate the current global climate change.

Figure.1. NPP/VIIRS high resolution(375m)image of the analyzed area(indicated by red box) (71° - 75° , 2° - 6°) on 24 January 2018 is shown. The corresponding T - r_c relationship for the cloud within the enclosed area has been plotted. The red vertical bar at $14\mu\text{m}$ denotes precipitation threshold.

Figure 2. NPP/VIIRS high resolution (375m)image of the analyzed area(indicated by red box) (72° - 76° , 9° - 13°) on 17 January 2018 is shown. The corresponding T - r_c relationship for the cloud within the enclosed area has been plotted. The red vertical bar at $14\mu\text{m}$ denotes precipitation threshold.

CONCLUSIONS

T - r_c graphs were plotted for different cloud clusters to identify the changes in microphysical and precipitation forming processes. Analysis revealed that aerosol loading has a significant role in determining the growth rate of warm clouds.

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**A STUDY OF THE IMPACT OF SIZE SEGREGATED AEROSOLS ON CLOUD PROPERTIES
OVER THE NORTHERN INDIAN OCEAN**

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Keywords: Aerosol optical depth, cloud fraction, aerosol-cloud interactions, Northern Indian Ocean.

INTRODUCTION

Aerosols play a critical role in characterizing Earth's climate directly by scattering or absorption of solar and terrestrial radiations and indirectly by aerosol-cloud interactions (ACI) (Altaratz et al., 2014). Functioning as cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) or ice nucleating particles, they can alter both microphysical (such as cloud droplet number or size) and macrophysical (such as cloud cover) properties of clouds (Seinfeld et al., 2016). These modifications in cloud properties lead to instant changes in cloud albedo, known as the radiative forcing due to aerosol-cloud interactions (RF_{ACI}), which is the most uncertain component in quantifying the climatic effects of anthropogenic burden of aerosols (Masson-Delmotte et al., 2021).

Apart from the chemical composition, one of the most critical factors determining aerosol's efficiency to function as CCN is the size of the particles (Jose et al., 2021). Here, we study the influence of size-segregated aerosol optical depth (AOD) on various cloud properties over the regions of the Northern Indian Ocean (NIO) using satellite observations. The Arabian Sea (AS) and the Bay of Bengal (BoB) in the NIO were chosen in this study as these regions experience a continuous load of aerosols from natural and anthropogenic sources with high seasonal variations. The Northern Equatorial Indian Ocean (NEIO) region is taken as a control in this study because of the minimal aerosol load over this region (pristine conditions). The study area is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 5. Map showing our study area with three bounding boxes representing the region of AS, BoB and

METHODS

To comprehend the variations in cloud properties due to size differentiated AOD over our study area, the aerosol and cloud properties from the latest MODerate resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) atmosphere Level 3, QA weighted Collection 6.1, daily product 'MOD08_D3' for Terra (2000-2021), and 'MYD08_D3' for Aqua (2002-2021) were utilized. The results presented here are derived by systematic averaging of the MODIS Aqua and Terra data.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The annual trend analysis results (Figure 2) indicate a significant rise in the fine mode AOD over both AS ($R^2 \sim 0.63$) and BoB ($R^2 \sim 0.65$). The results of correlation analyses between size differentiated AOD and cloud

Figure 2. Annual trend of AOD for (a) fine mode and (b) coarse mode aerosol over AS (in blue), BoB (in red) and NEIO (in black).

Region	AOD (Fine mode)				AOD (Coarse mode)			
	CF	CER	COT	CTT	CF	CER	COT	CTT
AS	0.37	0.16	0.08	-0.13	0.61	0.10	0.06	-0.24
BoB	0.22	0.03	-0.02	0.11	0.51	0.13	0.00	-0.34
NEIO	0.32	0.00	0.08	-0.24	0.47	0.16	-0.05	-0.46

Table 2. Total correlation (Pearson) between size differentiated AOD and cloud properties over our study region.

Figure 3. Different cloud properties (on y-axis) plotted as a function of AOD over a) AS and b) BoB. Blue indicates AOD by coarse particles and Red indicates AOD by fine particles.

properties including cloud fraction (CF), cloud effective radius (CER), cloud optical thickness (COT) and cloud top temperature (CTT) are shown in Table 1. We observed that the response of smaller particles and coarser particles to changes in cloud properties are different over AS and BoB (Figure 3) (the panel for NEIO in Fig. 3 is excluded due to space constraint).

CONCLUSION

A distinct impact of size segregated aerosols on cloud properties is observed over the AS, BoB and NEIO, demanding a more robust in-depth analysis.

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**AEROSOL SPECIES INDUCED SPATIAL MODULATIONS IN THE INDIAN SUMMER
MONSOON (ISM) RAINFALL**

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Keywords: Aerosol modelling, Aerosol cloud interactions, Aerosol effects on monsoon

INTRODUCTION

The Indian summer monsoon (ISM, June to September) is a crucial climatic phenomenon, contributing more than three-quarters of the annual rainfall over the Indian subcontinent. Therefore, changes in the spatio-temporal variability and anomalies in the ISM rainfall have profound impacts on the water resources, agricultural production, and economic and societal prosperity of India. Observational studies indicate an increasing trend in heavy to extremely heavy rainfall events over the Indian mainland in recent decades, notably in the central and northwestern Indian regions. However, they also report a reduction in the ISM rainfall over most of the northern and eastern Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) regions. A picture of how aerosols impact the Indian monsoon is emerging from previous studies (Vinoj et al., 2014; Samset et al., 2019), but a lack of understanding of spatially varying atmospheric burden of aerosol species types and, thereby, the aerosol species radiative perturbations, as well as the coarse resolution of state-of-the-art aerosol-climate models applied in aerosol-monsoon interaction studies has so far prevented accurate assessment of aerosol-induced spatial modulations in ISM rainfall over the Indian region and establish their potential connectivity with the corresponding modulations inferred from observed rainfall. In the present study, we use a well-predicted distribution of aerosol species type (anthropogenic and dust) over the Indian subcontinent to assess the potential impacts of evolving regional aerosol distributions and thereby their radiative perturbations in spatially modulating (weakening or strengthening) the ISM rainfall over India.

METHODS

A spatial concordance is identified between the spatially varying aerosol species burden (anthropogenic and dust) and the inferred spatial modulations in ISM rainfall from the Indian Meteorological Department (IMD) measurements (IMD-rainfall). Aerosol response simulation (ARS) of aerosol species is designed in a fine resolved (25×25 km²) weather research and forecasting (WRF) regional climate modelling system with well-predicted aerosol species distributions for aerosol scenarios (anthropogenic, dust, all-, and no-aerosols) during the monsoon period. The probability density of aerosols-induced rainfall change over the identified regions with weakening or strengthening rainfall is assessed from twenty numbers of designed ARS for five climatic condition years accounting for the changing meteorological climatic patterns (e.g., La-Niña, El-Niño, or the Indian Ocean dipole) during the ISM.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Anthropogenic aerosol AOD values (0.3 to 0.6) are high over most of India, especially over the Indo-Gangetic plain, eastern coast, and Bay of Bengal. Dust AOD values (as large as 0.3) are mainly present over northwestern India. Aerosol radiative perturbations show contrasting all-sky aerosol surface radiative effects from dust and anthropogenic aerosols. Dust aerosols cause surface radiative warming over most of mainland India, while anthropogenic and all-aerosols cause surface cooling, except along the western coast and oceanic regions where there is radiative warming.

The model shows that anthropogenic aerosols mask ISM rainfall by 30-40% over most of India, with the maximum deficiency of -48mm in eastern India. In contrast, dust aerosols enhance ISM rainfall by >50% over central, northwestern India, and the western coast, with a magnitude of +51mm over northwestern India

(Figure 1). The modelled spatial modulations in ISM rainfall match the modulations inferred from IMD-rainfall. The highest probability density of modelled rainfall deficiency (excessive) values due to anthropogenic (dust) aerosols closely matches the corresponding values inferred from IMD-rainfall. The modelled all aerosols-induced maximum rainfall deficiency (strengthening) also corroborates the corresponding values from IMD-rainfall.

The spatial change in monsoonal wind-field dynamics caused by anthropogenic aerosols is a potential explanation for the weakening rainfall. This mechanism is mainly driven by stronger all-sky anthropogenic aerosol radiative forcing contrasts between the ocean and land regions. The increased rainfall is primarily driven by the strengthening of the all-sky shortwave radiative warming in areas having lower clear-sky shortwave radiative cooling, with an increased cloud fraction, in addition to the dust-induced reduced outgoing long-wave radiation. Our study suggests that the spatially varying aerosol all-sky radiative effects attributed to the burden of aerosol species type primarily govern the aerosol-induced spatial modulations in ISM rainfall. The aerosol-induced spatial changes of ISM rainfall as modelled over the Indian subcontinent can potentially explain the corresponding changes inferred from the IMD-rainfall.

Figure 1: Spatial distribution of (a,b) simulated aerosol radiative forcing due to all aerosols, averaged during ISM period at surface for (a) clear sky and (b) all sky; (c) simulated percentage change (with respect to no aerosols) in the ISM rainfall ($\frac{\text{with aerosols} - \text{no aerosols}}{\text{no aerosols}} \times 100$), due to all aerosols

CONCLUSIONS

Our study indicates that the changes inferred from IMD measurements can potentially be explained by modeled aerosol-induced spatial modulations in ISM rainfall by adequately accounting for the evolving regional aerosol distributions and their radiative effects. The weakening of rainfall over the Indo-Gangetic plain, with a maximum deficiency over eastern India, is primarily driven by changes in regional wind dynamics due to larger contrasts (radiative cooling and warming) of anthropogenic aerosol radiative forcing between the Indian mainland and oceanic region. The increase in rainfall over central, northwestern India, and western coast (including the Kerala region) is strengthened by the radiative warming of dust aerosols.

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AN OBSERVATIONAL APPROACH FOR STUDYING AEROSOL-CLOUD INTERACTION IN
 WATER CLOUDS OVER AN INDIAN REGION

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Keywords: AEROSOL, WATER CLOUDS, LIQUID WATER PATH

INTRODUCTION

Aerosol-cloud interaction (ACI) is one of the primary sources of large uncertainties in the current understanding of the Earth’s climate system. Compared to global, ACI studies over the Indian subcontinent using in-situ or ground-based or a combination of ground-based, in-situ, and satellite-based observations are sparse. In this study, ACI in water clouds is estimated over an Indian tropical location, Gadanki (13.5°N, 79.2°E), using a combination of ground-based, in-situ balloon-borne, and satellite-based observations. Aerosol and cloud proxies used to evaluate ACI are aerosol optical depth (AOD) and cloud optical depth (COD). Ground-based remote sensing (Micro pulse lidar (MPL) and MST Radar), In-situ (Radiosonde), Space-borne remote sensing (CALIPSO, MODIS), and reanalysis (ERA5) datasets (Fig. 1a) are used in this work.

METHODOLOGY

In this study, to understand the effect of aerosols on water clouds, AOD and COD retrieved from MPL are used as aerosol and cloud proxy, respectively, at constant liquid water path (LWP) retrieved from the radiosonde. COD, by integrating cloud extinction coefficient, from 0 to 30m, 30 to 60 m, 60 to 90m, and 90 to 120m from cloud base height are used. The aerosol extinction coefficient is integrated from 300 m below the cloud base height to 1000 m, as shown in Figure 1(b) (green lines), to obtain AOD (Schmidt et al., 2015). Datasets are divided into different LWP bins, each of width 30 g/m². Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (r) is used to denote how dependent cloud optical depth is on aerosol optical depth in each LWP bin. ACI parameter (ACI_i) is also calculated.

Figure 6: (a) Pictorial representation of the datasets used to study ACI over Gadanki. (b) ACI monitoring scheme followed in the present study.

RESULTS& DISCUSSIONS

The ACI analysis shows that the correlation between AOD and COD is highest near the cloud base and it decreases as the height above the cloud base increases for all the LWP values ranging from 30 to 150 g/m² (Fig. 2). This is consistent with the theoretical concept that the aerosol concentration determines the cloud droplet number concentration near the cloud base (Twomey and Warner,1967). ACI at the cloud base shows a decreasing pattern as the cloud base temperature decreases for LWP values of 30 to 60 g/m² whereas different patterns for all other LWPs. High ACI is observed when the wind direction at the cloud base is northeasterly. It is backed by the high occurrence of water clouds and the high contribution of surface aerosols during the winter season over Gadanki. Thus, the estimated ACI supports the theoretical concept of an increase in cloud fraction during polluted conditions. The two case studies using vertical wind observations from MST radar

show that a significant correlation between AOD and COD is observed even up to 90m above the cloud base during updraft at the cloud base altitude, due to the increased flow of aerosol/CCN into the cloud, which is not observed during downdraft conditions.

Figure 7: Correlation coefficient between COD and AOD at different LWP bins. The estimated ACI_r parameter in each case is written on the top of each bar.

CONCLUSIONS

Aerosol-cloud interaction on water clouds is estimated over an Indian tropical region using a combination of ground-based, in-situ, and satellite-based observations. The correlation between AOD and COD is highest near the cloud base and it decreases as the height above the cloud base increases for all the LWP values ranging from 30 to 150 g/m². ACI by constraining the background meteorological conditions is also analyzed. ACI at the cloud base is high when the cloud base temperature is high. High ACI is observed when the wind direction at the cloud base is north-easterly. High ACI is observed even up to 90m above the cloud base by constraining the background dynamical conditions like vertical wind. Thus, the liquid water path and background meteorological and dynamical conditions play a major role in determining the aerosol-cloud interaction process. Since the estimated ACI supports the theoretical concepts of aerosol indirect effect, the approach proposed in this study is a feasible method to estimate the aerosol-cloud interaction on a regional scale.

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IMPROVEMENT IN FOG SIMULATION DUE TO DIFFERENT SOIL MOISTURE INITIALIZATION OVER NORTH INDIA

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Keywords: Aerosol-cloud interactions, Fog modeling, Fog

INTRODUCTION

Fog occurrences over the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP), North India, is arguably the largest (spatially) annual winter weather phenomenon that obstructs the daily chores of millions of people and has severe implications on various economic sectors of the country. Interestingly, these events take genesis, evolve, and dissipate in a highly aerosol-laden planetary boundary layer. Yet fog forecasting using state-of-the-art models remains difficult, primarily due to the deviation of the initial and boundary conditions (Yadav et al., 2022), domain nesting (Kutty et al., 2021; Steeneveld et al., 2015), and mainly disparate sub-grid scale parameterizations, such as PBL, aerosol activations and land surface fluxes (Parde et al., 2022; Pithani et al., 2018; Poku et al., 2019). Since fog is a boundary layer phenomenon, surface moisture and energy fluxes are crucial for its accurate representation. Here, we investigate the implications of change in the initial soil moisture/temperature conditions on the simulated fog layer over north India.

METHODS

We have used the state-of-the-art WRF-Chem (version 3.5.1) to simulate the fog layer over North India. The model is coupled with the community land surface model (CLM) to simulate the various surface fluxes and budgets. We further force the model with ECMWF Reanalysis v5 (ERA5) and Indian Monsoon Data Assimilation and Analysis soil moisture/temperature to understand the sensitivity of the simulated fog layer on the soil moisture/temperature. ERA5 is the 5th generation of the ECMWF reanalysis dataset with a global resolution of 0.25°. On the other hand, IMDAA is a new bias-corrected high-resolution atmospheric reanalysis over the Indian region. The data is available at 12km resolution. The model was initialized on 23rd January 2018 and ran till 26th January 2018. The simulation will tease out the late January 2018 widespread fog event that formed over the IGP.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1. The first layer cloud fraction for 24 January 2018 06UTC in the model initialized with a) ERA5 and b) SM/ST. c) Indicate the true color MODIS onboard Terra observation of fog over IGP.

A widespread fog event formed on 24 January after the passage of a western disturbance on 23 January 2018. On 24th the fog layer was only over the western part of the IGP, as shown in figure 1c. After a 24-hour model spin-up to stabilize the simulated meteorology and chemistry, the model, which was initialized with ERA5 SM/ST started to simulate fog as shown by the surface level cloud fraction in Figure 1a (which is similar to the observed fog layer over the IGP by MODIS figure 1c). On the other hand, the model initialized with IMDAA's SM/ST could not simulate the fog event for the whole simulation period. We found that over the

western IGP, there was around ~100% lower soil moisture content in the IMDAA (~0.05-0.06 m³/m³) compared to the ERA5 soil moisture content (~0.1 m³/m³). This had a significant impact on the fog simulations over North India. Previously, Parde et al. (2022) also found out that improving the soil moisture and temperature values could significantly improve the simulated fog event over Delhi NCR.

CONCLUSIONS

The fog layer was simulated using chemistry-coupled high-resolution WRF-CHem over North India. We investigated the simulated fog's sensitivity on the input soil moisture and temperature and found a general dry bias did not favor fog formation over the western IGP throughout the simulation period. However, further analysis needs to ascertain the implications of this observed dry bias on fog.

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CONTRASTING AEROSOL-CLOUD INTERACTION FOR NON-PRECIPITATING WARM CLOUDS OVER THE EASTERN AND WESTERN INDO-GANGETIC PLAINS

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Keywords: AEROSOL-CLOUD INTERACTION, MODIS, CLOUD EFFECTIVE RADIUS, AEROSOL OPTICAL DEPTH.

INTRODUCTION

Assessing the impact of aerosols on cloud microphysics (known as aerosol-cloud interaction, ACI) under distinct geographical and meteorological conditions is indispensable for providing insight into the anthropogenic influence on the hydrological cycle over South Asia. Estimating ACI over the Indo-Gangetic plains, which is one of the most populated and polluted regions of the world, is highly challenging due to inherent limitations in measurement techniques and the complex interplay between aerosol and meteorology on clouds over this region. The presence of high aerosol loading and non-precipitating low-level stratocumulus clouds during winter provides an opportunity to study ACI over IGP.

METHODS

This study analysed spatially and temporally collocated data from Moderate Resolution Spectroradiometer (MODIS) Aqua Level-3 for clouds and aerosols data during winter (2003-2021) over eastern and western IGP. Here we estimated ACI only for non-precipitating warm clouds, based on the following screening criteria (i) $4 \mu\text{m} < \text{cloud effective radius (CER)} < 28 \mu\text{m}$, (ii) $4 < \text{cloud optical thickness (COT)} < 40$, (iii) cloud top pressure (CTP) $> 700\text{hPa}$. Also, to minimize the satellite retrieval uncertainty of aerosols caused by fog, haze, and clouds we applied the following screening criteria (i) $0.05 < \text{AOD} < 1.5$, (ii) $\text{AOD}(470\text{nm}) > \text{AOD}(550\text{nm}) >$

$\text{AOD}(660\text{nm})$. To estimate ACI $\left(-\frac{\partial(\ln\text{CER})}{\partial(\ln\text{AOD})}\right)_{\text{LWP}}$ for non-precipitating warm clouds, linear regression is

applied to aerosol optical depth (AOD) and CER at a fixed liquid water path (LWP).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

This study presents a contrasting variation of ACI with LWP over the eastern and western IGP. Specifically, a reversal from the anti-Twomey (ACI < 0) to the Twomey effect (ACI > 0) was observed at an LWP bin of 75-100 gm^{-2} over western IGP, whereas the anti-Twomey effect was prevailing over eastern IGP for all LWP bins as shown in Figure 1. Also, a contrast in the ACI variation with LWP over eastern IGP is found out between our work and previous study (Khatri et al., 2022). The detailed findings will be presented in the meeting.

Figure 1. Variation of ACI with LWP over (a) Eastern IGP, and (b) Western IGP, numbers shown in bar plots are the number of data points to estimate ACI for corresponding LWP bin.

CONCLUSIONS

A reversal from the anti-Twomey to the Twomey effect was observed at the LWP bin of 75-100 gm^{-2} over western IGP, whereas the anti-Twomey effect was observed over eastern IGP for all LWP bins.

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CMIP5 MODELS INCLUDING AEROSOL INDIRECT EFFECT PERFORMS BETTER IN
 SIMULATING THE TRENDS IN EXTREME RAINFALL OVER INDIA

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Keywords: Aerosol-Cloud interactions, CMIP, monsoonal rainfall trends

INTRODUCTION

Clouds form an essential part in the Earth’s climate system. Water vapor condenses on activated aerosols, known as cloud condensation nuclei, to form cloud droplets (Warner and Twomey, 1967). An ensemble of cloud droplets constitutes a cloud. Since the industrial revolution, the surface processes have been constantly releasing greenhouse gases and aerosols into the atmosphere. Clouds and aerosols independently regulate the Earth's energy budget, making them influential climate forcers (Charlson et al., 1992; Ramanathan et al 1989). Over India, a multitude of clouds form that differ each season. Aerosols affect the cloud by modulating its microphysics (known as aerosol indirect effect; Albrecht, 1989; Twomey, 1974) and thermodynamics (known as aerosol induced invigoration effect; Fan et al., 2018; Koren et al., 2005; Rosenfeld et al., 2008; Sarangi et al., 2017) thereby increasing the cloud reflectivity (albedo). Observations over India suggest that aerosol-induced invigoration of deep convective towers produces thicker anvil clouds that effectively reduce the shortwave forcing at the surface, leading to surface cooling (Sarangi et al., 2017).

METHODS

Here, we investigated the aerosol-induced changes to the cloud’s morphology from CMIP5 models during the monsoon season (June through September) for the historical period (1975-2005). For this, firstly, we segregate the models that incorporate the aerosol direct effects (hereafter REM_{ADE}) and the model that incorporates all aerosol effects (aerosol direct and indirect effects; hereafter REM_{ALL}). From these group models, we then isolate each cloud layer’s top height and base height and plot composites of cloud occurrence frequency per year on bivariate axes of cloud top height *versus* cloud thickness.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1. The JJA cloud occurrence frequency (number per year) with co-located top height and thickness for a) REM_{ALL}, b) REM_{ADE}, and c) percentage change in the occurrence frequency with respect to the REM_{ALL} group.

As shown in figure 1a, the majority of clouds (mainly low, and middle clouds) in REM_{ALL} are primarily thicker than clouds simulated in the REM_{ADE}. The inclusion of aerosol indirect effect in the models leads to an increase in overall cloudiness by enhancing the lifetime/prevalence of low and midlevel clouds. Using high-resolution simulations, Sarangi et al. (2018) have also reported similar aerosol-induced cloud structure changes and estimated a reduction in surface temperature by 1–2°C during the Indian monsoon. Such aerosol-mediated cloud radiative effect on surface temperature can weaken the monsoon circulation (Bollasina et al.,

2011; Guo et al., 2015; Zelinka et al., 2014). Hence, an increase in cloudiness and associated surface cooling can explain the simulated general drying of the Indian landmass in the REMALL models.

CONCLUSIONS

We find direct evidence from CMIP5 models that the inclusion of aerosol indirect effect can increase cloudiness in the models and thereby leads to better simulation of extreme rainfall trends during Indian monsoon (Rai et al., 2023).

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ROLE OF AEROSOL AND CLOUD MICROPHYSICAL PROPERTIES IN FORECASTING CLOUD TOP TEMPERATURE USING RANDOM FOREST

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Keywords: Black carbon, organic carbon, cloud top temperature, cloud top pressure, PM2.5

INTRODUCTION

Clouds are very important parameter for shaping and regulating the weather and climate. They affect how the solar and terrestrial radiation interact in earth- atmosphere system, making the cloud characteristics crucial for climate studies (Hollmann et al., 2013). The cloud top temperature is very important to analyse the microphysical properties of cloud and weather phenomena. Analysis of satellite data has shown a significant correlation between global cloud cover and aerosols (Ignotv et al., 2005; Kaufman et al., 2005). Some studies has represented the decrease in cloud cover with high aerosol optical depth (Koren et al., 2008). In this study, the 23 years satellite data (2000-2023) analysed for predicting the cloud top temperature considering 12 independent variables i.e. cloud top pressure, evaporation loss of cloud water, air temperature, cloud fraction, liquid water cloud water path, ice cloud water path, PM2.5, black carbon, organic carbon, sulphate, cloud albedo and AOD over the Sikkim Himalaya region. Random forest method builds numerous randomized decision trees and sums their prediction by averaging, has shown great performance where the variables are much larger alongside the observation numbers. In this method, the decision trees are resulted from bootstrapping technique of the dataset, to improve the performance.

METHODS

The satellite data are collected from the Goddard Earth Sciences Data and Information Services Centre (GES DISC), NASA's data archive portal (<https://giovanni.gsfc.nasa.gov>). The data used as independent variable are black carbon column mass density, organic carbon mass density, sulphate column mass density, cloud albedo, AOD, PM2.5, evaporation loss cloud water, cloud fraction, air temperature from MERRA-2 with 0.5*0625° resolution and cloud top temperature, liquid water cloud water path, ice cloud water path, from MODIS-Terra and cloud top temperature (dependent variable) from MODIS-aqua with 1° resolution. The data is tuned to select the optimum number of independent variable to run the RF model based on minimum root mean squared error (RMSE) value with 500 number of iteration. The dataset split into 70% for training and 30% testing of the model.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The optimum number of variable (*mtry*) obtained based on the basis of least RMSE was 8 and the model is tuned with this value. The RF model performed well for the given dataset to predict the cloud top temperature with R² value is 0.93. The important factor identified for the given dataset and study area are the most important factors identified for the prediction are cloud top pressure, liquid water cloud water path, evaporation loss of cloud water, air temperature and PM2.5 followed by the ice cloud water path, AOD, cloud albedo, cloud fraction, organic carbon, sulphate and black carbon.

Figure 1: Optimized number of predictors for best model fit based on least RMSE

Figure 2: Variable importance in percentage (%) for the prediction of Cloud Top Temperature

CONCLUSIONS

The RF model has a good proficiency to predict the cloud top temperature in the combination of cloud and aerosol properties.

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SEASONAL AND DIURNAL VARIATION IN CLOUD CONDENSATION NUCLEI OVER A RURAL LOCATION

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Keywords: Aerosol-Cloud Interaction, Cloud Condensation Nuclei, CCN Counter

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols affect the climate through interaction with solar as well as terrestrial radiation. This interaction takes place in both direct as well as indirect ways (Li *et al.*, 2022). The direct interaction of aerosols with radiation is understood reasonably well. However, the indirect interaction of aerosols with radiation through modification of cloud properties termed Aerosol-Cloud Interactions (ACI) is yet unclear. Besides, the radiative forcing due to ACI is estimated to be -0.84 ± 0.6 W/m². The large spread in radiative forcing due to ACI is partly due to a lack of knowledge on Cloud Condensation Nuclei (CCN). The CCN is the aerosol upon which the saturated water vapour condenses to form a cloud droplet. From the existing literature, CCN studies have been reported from various locations in India including urban, coastal, and hill stations. However, there is no study reported from a rural location where different aerosol composition and background is expected. Therefore the present study aims to present the variations in CCN concentrations over a rural location, Gadanki in South India.

METHODS

Measurement of CCN is being carried out from NARL, Gadanki (13.5°N, 79.2°E) using a CCN counter. This instrument creates supersaturation in the column based on the principle of ‘faster diffusion of water vapor than heat’ (Roberts and Nenes, 2005). Subsequently, grown droplets are measured using an optical particle counter (OPC). NARL CCN Counter was operated at super saturations (SS) of 0.2-1.0 % with an interval of 0.2%. In this study, CCN data from October 2019 to August 2023 has been analyzed. The raw data from the CCN counter needs to be checked for various factors. Due to instability in the thermal gradient within the cylindrical column, initial 6 minutes of data at 0.2% SS and 2 minutes of data at other SS were removed. The time discarded data is further checked for OPC voltage, flow ratio and data points not following the set criteria are ignored. We have made sure within the hour at least 50% of data points are available at each SS even after applying all the data reduction methods discussed here.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

From the monthly, seasonal variation (Fig.1) of the total CCN concentration (N_{CCN}), the highest values are noticed in pre-monsoon followed by winter, post monsoon, and monsoon with the mean values of 2879.7 #/cc, 2517 #/cc, 2150.8 #/cc, and 1142.6 #/cc respectively. Diurnal variations of N_{CCN} showed a morning peak around 08 hours and an evening peak around 20 hours. The diurnal variation in the seasonal mean size distribution of CCN concentration (at 0.4% SS) showed maximum CCN concentration in the range 100-1000 #/cc contributed by 2-5 μ m, moderate CCN concentrations in the range 10-100 #/cc is contributed by 1-2 μ m and low CCN concentrations in the range 10⁻¹-10 #/cc is observed in 0.5-1 μ m range. The CCN and SS relationship is explained by Twomey’s empirical relationship (k-parameter). The higher the value of k, the lower the solubility (hygroscopicity), and size of aerosol. Seasonal statistics of the k-parameter show the highest in monsoon (~0.65), least in winter (~0.4), and comparable in post monsoon and pre-monsoon (~0.5). By comparing the mean values of the N_{CCN} over our location with that of remaining locations in India, we have noticed that CCN concentrations over Gadanki are more than that of high altitude stations and below the values from coastal, polluted sites in India

Figure 1. Box plot shows the (i) Monthly and (ii) Seasonal variation in CCN Concentration over Gadanki.

CONCLUSIONS

CCN variations are reported for the first time in a rural location Gadanki in India. The long-term observations show high CCN in the pre-monsoon followed by winter, post monsoon and monsoon. Diurnal variation in CCN is noticed with first peak in the morning around 08 h and the second in the evening at around 20 h. The diurnal peaks are contributed by the grown particles in the size range from 0.5-2 μm . The CCN-SS relationships analysed in terms of k-parameter suggest the small sized particles and/or less water soluble particles growing to CCN during monsoon. Comparison with other locations indicates Gadanki lies between polluted/coastal and high altitude sites with respect to the CCN concentration.

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INFLUENCING FACTORS ON CLOUD CONDENSATION NUCLEI (CCN) VARIATIONS OVER A RURAL LOCATION

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Keywords: Aerosol-Cloud Interaction, Cloud Condensation Nuclei, Pre-cursor gases, Aerosol

INTRODUCTION

As far as the climate effects of aerosols are concerned, the Aerosol-Cloud Interaction (ACI) is an important process to be understood. Since quite long time, efforts are underway in this direction using both observations and simulations. If so, information on Cloud Condensation Nuclei (CCN) becomes important as it is fundamental to the formation, macro and micro-physical process of clouds. Although CCN is a sub-set of aerosols, the capability of the aerosols to act as CCN depends not only the aerosol sources, sinks but also on many factors, processes for example aerosol size/composition, nucleation etc. In the present study, we shed light on finding out the factors that influence the variations of CCN over a rural location, Gadanki (13.5°N, 79.2°E) in South India. To understand this, we utilized the simultaneous observations of supporting data from various collocated instruments available from NARL, Gadanki.

METHODS

Simultaneous observations of aerosol scattering coefficient, absorption coefficient, number concentration from a Nephelometer, Aethalometer and an Aero-dynamic Particle Sizer (APS), pre-cursor, trace gas information on CO, NO₂, NH₃, SO₂ etc., from trace gas analysers, meteorological information from AWS, radiometers, fire activity information from MODIS fire counts is combined with the CCN measurements from a CCN counter over Gadanki for a period of observations from October 2019 to August 2023. All the data sets were averaged for the corresponding hours. As all the physical parameters are in different units, and to ease the interpretations, we have normalised all the datasets (Wang *et al.*, 2022). To quantify the influencing parameters on CCN, correlation analysis is carried out and fit parameters are obtained.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

By comparing the monthly variations of CCN with the monthly variations of aerosol, meteorological, and precursor gases, we noticed that variations in N_{CCN} are similar to the gases and aerosols in Post-Monsoon and Monsoon. Variations of N_{CCN} from December to March are similar to the variations of CO, BC, and NO₂ and opposite to the variations of total scattering coefficient, total number concentration (N_a), and single scattering albedo suggesting the influence of fine mode aerosol in these months. On the other hand, in the month of April, there is a sudden increase in SSA and N_a which indicates the contribution of scattering aerosols. For explaining the diurnal variations of N_{CCN} , collocated parameters (aerosol, gases) have been normalised and plotted in one scale (Fig.1). From the normalized diurnal variations of CCN and influencing factors, it is understood that the morning peak and evening peak are due to anthropogenic aerosols and gases (with the effect of fumigation in the morning). However, except in the monsoon, noon time increase is noticed due to an increase in concentrations of SO₂ which undergo photochemical reactions driven by high temperatures.

Figure 1. Diurnal variations in normalized values of CCN (solid black line) and supporting dataset (dashed lines) for post monsoon (i-iii), winter (iv-vi), pre-monsoon (vii-ix) and monsoon (x-xii).

CONCLUSIONS

To understand the influence of CCN variations observed over a rural location, Gadanki in India, simultaneous observations of supporting data set on aerosol, gases, and meteorological parameters is analysed for the period of observations of CCN. The results suggests, contribution from fine mode, absorbing aerosol during December to March and coarse mode aerosol during the April. CCN variations from morning and evening hours are influenced by aerosols, gases and noon time variation by SO_2 . The study demonstrates the importance of anthropogenic activities and phot-chemistry on CCN activity of aerosols.

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**AEROSOL-WARM CLOUD INTERACTION OVER EASTERN INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN
 DURING WINTER SEASON**

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Keywords: Aerosol-Cloud Interactions, Twomey effect, Indo-Gangetic Plain, Winter

INTRODUCTION

The aerosol concentrations due to anthropogenic emissions has increased significantly in the modern times. However, their effect on the cloud microphysics is still not understood with certainty. The location of eastern Indo-Gangetic plain (EIGP) between high altitude regions of Himalayan foothills and Central Indian plateau (Figure 1) makes it very likely for accumulation of high concentrations of aerosols during winter season due to shallow atmospheric boundary layers. This increased aerosol concentrations in the region are also confirmed by satellite observational data from MODIS. A significant occurrence of warm clouds is also found over the region during winter. This makes the region suitable for studying the aerosol-warm cloud interactions over land.

Figure 8 Eastern Indo-Gangetic Plain Study Region (outlined in black)

METHODS

The present study uses the MODIS Aqua Level 3 Daily Data over the region for the period between 2006-2021 for obtaining aerosol and cloud related properties. ERA5 reanalysis data from ECMWF is utilized for obtaining temperature and relative humidity data at different pressure levels. The aerosol extinction profiles derived from CALIOP instrument onboard CALIPSO are used to obtain the vertical distribution of aerosols over the study region. The contribution to column extinction by different aerosol types is derived from MERRA-2 reanalysis data set. Aerosol optical depth (AOD) under dry condition is estimated from the satellite (MODIS-Aqua) reported ambient AOD₅₅₀ by making reasonable corrections for the hygroscopic growth using aerosol compositions from MERRA-2, aerosol vertical distribution from CALIOP, and relative humidity from ERA-5. AOD under ambient and dry conditions, and aerosol index (AI) are used as cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) proxy for investigating their effect on warm-cloud properties like cloud effective radius (CER) and cloud fraction (CF). The lower tropospheric stability (LTS) is estimated as the difference between the potential temperatures at 700 hPa and 1000 hPa, derived from ERA5 temperature data. The RH at 700 hPa is considered as free tropospheric humidity (FTH). The estimation of aerosol-cloud interaction for quasi constant liquid water path (LWP) is done using the following formula

$$ACI = \frac{-\partial \ln(\text{Cloud Property})}{\partial \ln(\text{CCN Proxy})} \Big|_{LWP}$$

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Hygroscopic growth and aerosol size mode dominance are the two critical factors affecting the use of ambient AOD as a proxy for CCN. The use of AOD estimates under dry condition as a CCN proxy helps to alleviate the hygroscopic growth issues. Similarly, the use of aerosol index for CCN estimates addresses the issues due to varying aerosol sizes. The magnitude of estimated ACI values is found to decrease in the order of AOD_{amb}, AOD_{dry}, and AI consistently at all LWP bins (Figure 2). There is also a general decreasing trend observed in the magnitude of ACI with increasing LWP for all aerosol loading cases. The evaluation of p-values from student-t test confirms the existence of a statistically significant (p < 0.05) positive correlation between CER and aerosol loading for all three cases at lower LWP values. These observations contrast with the expected Twomey effect which dictates a negative correlation between CER and aerosol loading.

Figure 9 Comparison of ACI estimates for three aerosol loading cases under different LWP bins

It is found that at least 58% of data points in each LWP bin correspond to LTS < 15 K and FTH < 40%. It is also observed that the relative occurrence of high LTS cases (LTS > 15 K) decreases with increasing LWP. In contrast, the cases corresponding to LTS bin 10-15 K show a predominant occurrence at all LWP bins. The FTH occurrence towards lower LWP bins largely correspond to a drier cloud top (FTH < 40%) while the occurrence of moister cloud top (FTH > 40%) was found to increase towards higher LWP bins. It is likely that under lower FTH conditions, the dry air entrainment towards the cloud top leads to evaporation-entrainment effect causing the evaporation of smaller droplets. The prevailing weak LTS conditions and drier air conditions towards the cloud top are suggested to be the likely cause for the observed anti-Twomey effect.

CONCLUSIONS

The present study found the persistent occurrence of a statistically significant positive correlation between aerosol loading and cloud effective radius over the study region towards lower LWP regimes (< 100 g m⁻²), irrespective of the aerosol loading type used to better represent CCN. The cloud top air conditions are found to be predominantly dry (RH < 40%) during winter over EIGP with a prevailing weak LTS conditions (LTS < 15 K). The study indicates a possible evaporation-entrainment effect towards the cloud top as the cause for observed anti-Twomey effect over the study region.

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SULPHATE AEROSOL AND CLOUD PROPERTIES: A DRIVER OF RAINFALL CHANGE IN INDIA

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Keywords: SULPHATE AEROSOL, CLOUD PROPERTIES, RAINFALL, AEROSOL-CLOUD INTERACTION.

INTRODUCTION

Sulphate aerosols, a major air pollutant is produced when sulphur dioxide (SO₂) gas combines with atmospheric water vapour. Its sources include power plants, factories, and vehicles. They have a variety of impacts on the climate of the Earth, including scattering incoming solar radiation and raising the planet's albedo. By modifying the characteristics of the clouds, they also indirectly affect rainfall (Xie et al., 2022).

The term "aerosol-cloud interaction" refers to the indirect impact of sulphate aerosols on rainfall (ACI). The ACI happens when sulphate particles penetrate clouds, increasing the amount of cloud droplets while decreasing their size. Because sulphate particles serve as the cloud condensation nuclei (CCN), sulphate aerosols are known to enhance the quantity of cloud droplets. Cloud droplets increase as CCN increases. In addition to boosting the quantity of cloud droplets, they can also make the droplets smaller, which can prevent raindrops from growing. This is because sulphate particles have the ability to absorb water vapour, which may cause bigger cloud droplets to fragment into smaller ones. Smaller cloud droplets are less likely to create rain or snow because they have a lower precipitation efficiency. This has the net effect of making the clouds reflect more sunlight than they would otherwise if the sulphate aerosols weren't present. The amount of precipitation that falls from the clouds may decrease as a result of this (Wang et al., 2021).

METHODS

There are numerous ways to study how sulphate aerosol, cloud characteristics, and rainfall interact. Nevertheless, there are some difficulties in determining the concentration of sulphate aerosols in the atmosphere as well as in predicting and quantifying how sulphate particles may affect clouds in various climatic situations. However, satellite data might offer helpful insights into this procedure. In addition to the features of clouds, such as cloud optical depth, cloud droplet number concentration, cloud liquid water path, and rainfall, satellites can also monitor the amount of sulphate aerosol in the atmosphere. Thus, satellite data was used in our study to better understand the ACI process. This study examined the impact of sulphate aerosol on rainfall in three different parts of India i.e., Bhubaneswar (an urban coastal city), Kolkata (a metro city) and Jamshedpur (an industrial city). To explore the same, data on cloud liquid water path, sulphate surface mass concentrations, and rainfall were collected using MODIS, MERRA2, and NASA's POWER data, respectively. The purpose of this study was to determine the sulphate concentration in three different regions having different sources of air pollution and industrial activity. It also aimed at studying the interaction of sulphate concentration with the local rainfall.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The analysis found that the highest sulphate content was in Jamshedpur, followed by Kolkata and Bhubaneswar. This points to industrial pollution as a significant source. The study also revealed a negative association between sulphate concentration, cloud liquid water path and rainfall concentration for all three

cities. This can support the hypothesis that an increase in atmospheric sulphate content can result in a considerable decline in rainfall quantity and intensity.

CONCLUSIONS

The discovery has significant ramifications for our comprehension of how sulphate aerosols affect climate change. The findings imply that industrial emissions are a large contributor to sulphate aerosol in India, can significantly affect rainfall patterns, and may even be enhanced in regions with high industrial emissions. The results of this study have important implications for the management of rainfall in India as water resources of the cities can be significantly impacted by this. Future research should concentrate on conceptualising the relationship between sulphate aerosol, cloud characteristics, and rainfall in various Indian locations. Additional studies employing cloud chamber experiments, numerical models, and other techniques will be necessary to address this. Future research should concentrate on the impacts of sulphate aerosol on various cloud types, levels of aerosol pollution, and how this process affects the global climate.

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**REGIONAL STUDY OF AEROSOL-CLOUD PROPERTIES DURING RAINFALL REGIMES:
WESTERN INDIA AND THE ARABIAN SEA**

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Keywords: aerosol-cloud interaction, regional variability, rainfall regimes, Indian subcontinent.

INTRODUCTION

Uncertainty in precipitation patterns over Asia is more of a concern, especially for a country like India due to its geographical location. Moreover, India is a monsoon-dominated country which receives 80% of its rainfall from the southwest monsoon. Present study focuses over Western India where severe rain/drought conditions occurred during past few years and also over the Arabian Sea from where summer monsoonal trough originates. To understand regional variability, study of aerosol-cloud-rainfall interactions play an important role as aerosol is source of cloud and cloud is the only source of rain. Increase in aerosol concentration may increase the cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) concentration, which leads to more but smaller cloud droplets for constant cloud liquid water (Twomey, 1977). Thus, changes in aerosol concentration show significant impact on cloud properties and hence cloud formation processes. This in turn may lead to alter rainfall patterns (Shah and Srivastava, 2019). In addition to it, rainfall heterogeneity in terms of occurrence of deficit, normal, and excess monsoon conditions is subject to a high degree of variation over Western India (Pal and Al-Tabbaa, 2010). So, the study focuses to understand the role of aerosol-cloud interactions during different rainfall regimes at regional scale. Such study can help to know cloud formation processes and hence can improve uncertainties in rainfall patterns for better weather prediction.

METHODS

Present study focuses to see variations of aerosol-cloud properties over two heterogeneous regions – one land (Western India, hereafter referred to as WI: 20.5-28.5°N, 66.5-73.5°E) and one ocean (Arabian Sea, hereafter referred to as AS: 09-19.1°N, 57.6-72.9°E). Level 3 monthly averaged gridded (1°x1°) satellite products such as Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) and Cloud Effective Radius (CER in μm) were taken for liquid clouds from MODIS on-board Terra (MOD08_D3 v6.1). Uncertainties of AOD are $\pm (0.05+0.15 \text{ AOD})$ over land and $\pm (0.03+0.05 \text{ AOD})$ over ocean were taken into consideration for further analysis (Levy et al., 2007). CER retrievals taken for this study have uncertainties less than $0.1\mu\text{m}$ (Nakajima & King, 1990). Monthly data of Precipitation Rate (PR in mm/day) from the Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission (TRMM) at a spatial resolution of $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ were taken. Further Indian Meteorological Department (IMD) web portal provides daily ground based rainfall measurements ($0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$), which were utilized to differentiate study years (2000-2018) into normal, deficit and excess rainfall scenarios.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Variations in AOD, CER and PR for different rainfall conditions are more prominent over WI than those observed over AS (Fig. 1). The inter quartile range of AOD observed for different rainfall conditions is 0.15-0.85, 0.12-1.00, and 0.21-1.10 for excess, normal, and deficit, respectively. Over AS, the trend observed for excess, normal, and deficit rainfall is opposite to that observed over WI. Also, the variations in the distribution of CER show almost no difference for various rainfall conditions, which may be due to the lesser variations observed in AOD ranges across excess, normal, and deficit conditions. The range of values for CER over AS went as high as $\sim 22 \mu\text{m}$. CER values higher in the AS region than in the WI region. AOD difference between WI and AS are ~ 0.07 , 0.11 , and 0.20 for excess, normal and deficit scenarios respectively, which is same as observed for CER during deficit rainfall conditions. This again may be due to presence of various types of CCN such as elemental carbon, water-soluble inorganic species (in PM10 and PM2.5), organic carbon and mineral dust over WI, whereas also over AS, presence of hygroscopic nuclei dominates. The PR values exhibit larger differences during different rainfall conditions, unlike AOD and CER over AS. The PR is also observed to be higher in the AS region compared to the WI region. This may be due to comparatively larger values of CER in the region. The distributions over AS are more skewed compared to those on land. The upper whiskers in both study regions may suggest that the smaller part of the region has higher values of PR. Overall, the effect of variations in rainfall over land is also reflected in the PR values, but aerosol-cloud properties depict fewer variations across different rainfall conditions. This may be due to land-sea interactions and the significant role that AS plays in driving the southwest monsoon.

Figure 1. Variations in (a, b) AOD (c, d) CER (μm) and (e, f) PR (mm/day) over AS and WI during normal, excess and deficit rainfall scenarios (June-September) respectively.

CONCLUSIONS

Difference in aerosol-cloud properties were seen over land and oceanic regions, which is a sign of regional variability. High variability is seen over WI as compared to AS, due to more atmospheric processes over land region. Thus, the role of excess and deficit rainfall scenarios were captured in aerosol-cloud interactions. Also, dependency of PR on CER was found during normal, excess and deficit rainfall regimes. Hence, regional scale studies play a prominent role to understand excess as well as deficit rainfall scenarios.

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CLOUD-FORMING POTENTIAL OF ANTHROPOGENIC SULFATE AEROSOLS: INSIGHTS FROM SO₂ EMISSIONS OF A COAL-FIRED POWER PLANT IN INDIA DURING THE COVID LOCKDOWN

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Keywords: New Particle formation and growth, Sulfate aerosols, CCN activity, Lockdown

INTRODUCTION:

Understanding the impact of aerosols on climate, particularly their role in cloud formation and precipitation, is vital. The influence of atmospheric aerosols on cloud formation and precipitation largely depends on their microphysical and chemical characteristics. Anthropogenic emissions influence these processes, especially during cleaner conditions, as seen during India's COVID-19 lockdown. To gain insights into the impact of anthropogenic emissions on cloud formation during the relatively cleaner conditions of the COVID lockdown in Chennai, India, we conducted comprehensive assessments of ambient aerosols, focusing on their cloud-forming potential and chemical properties. While the lockdown reduced overall pollution, certain sectors like coal-fired power plants continued to operate, offering a unique opportunity to isolate their effects on aerosol-cloud interactions. These investigations unveiled a remarkable event characterized by new particle formation and rapid growth within the sulfur dioxide (SO₂) plume emitted by a large coal-fired power plant located approximately 200 kilometres south of our measurement site at IIT Madras campus. Analysis of aerosol properties and cloud formation during this event revealed that the sulfate-rich particles significantly increased cloud condensation nuclei concentration. This research establishes a baseline for comparing aerosol-cloud interactions under cleaner conditions against the typical heavy pollution scenarios, shedding light on their contribution to climate change and the importance of mitigating aerosol pollution in coastal areas.

METHODS:

Ambient aerosol properties measurements were conducted at IIT Madras in a temperature-controlled lab with a specialized inlet installed 14-meters above sea level. The chemical composition (nitrates, sulphates, chlorides and organics) of sub-micrometre non-refractory particles also known as NR-PM₁ was measured using a quadruple ACSM (Aerosol Chemical Speciation Monitor). The ACSM measurements sampled the air every 15 minutes. A Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer (SMPS) of TSI make was employed to measure the number size distribution of the aerosol particles and this in turn helped calculate the mass fraction of total PM_{0.5}. A CCN counter with a thermal gradient in the downstream direction, in conjunction with a differential mobility analyser (DMA) and a condensation particle counter (CPC), made size-resolved CCN measurements sampling particles over a range of 20 -350 nm. The black carbon content of the air was measured using an Aethalometer which sampled the air every minute. Additionally, the dispersion modelling of aerosol particles from Neyveli Powerplant was carried out using the HYSPLIT dispersion model.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

The new particle formation (NPF) event reported here began shortly after sunrise within the continental air mass, with rapid growth in particle numbers and size. Chemical composition analysis showed a predominance of organic aerosols, but an unusual increase in sulfate after a change in the wind-direction to South/South-westerly, indicated its significant role in particle growth during this cleaner period, in contrast to typical organic-dominated nanoparticle growth seen under more polluted conditions.

Figure 10 Various aerosol characteristic properties and meteorological conditions observed and derived for 1 May 2020 on the day of the rapid particle growth event. **a** 48-h backward-trajectories obtained for each hour between 06:30–18:30 LT and automatic weather station data (inset), indicating predominant southerly winds. **b** Time series of wind direction color coded by the wind speed. The transition period is marked with a white circle. **c** Time series showing the variations in chemical components in PM_{10} measured on the event day. On the same plot, the orange line indicates the variation in the sulfate:organic ratio measured by ACSM. **d** Sub-micrometer particle number size distribution measured by SMPS showing rapid particle growth during the event (local time plotted against diameter and scaled by normalized particle number concentration). The yellow line indicates the geometric median diameter of the mode fitted to the number size distribution, and the black line shows the black carbon concentration, which remained $<4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ throughout the event. (Singh et al., 2023)

Unlike the typical new particle formation (NPF) events, often initiated by organic precursors, this event was driven by elevated sulfate levels resulting from the condensation of H_2SO_4 originating from the Neyveli power plant's SO_2 plume. In a business-as-usual scenario, such NPF and growth processes are typically inhibited due to the significant pre-existing aerosol surface area resulting from local sources of H_2SO_4 condensation and particle coagulation. Notably, the sulfate-rich particles we observed exhibited unusually high CCN activity and number concentration across a range of supersaturations, characterized by kappa (κ) values surpassing those in the business-as-usual scenario, signifying a heightened potential for cloud formation.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, our observations during the lockdown period revealed a unique event of new particle formation and rapid growth in a tropical coastal region with reduced anthropogenic emissions. This growth was closely linked to elevated sulfate levels, likely originating from the condensation of H_2SO_4 resulting from SO_2 emissions by a coal-fired power plant located 200 km south of our site. This event's aerosols exhibited strong cloud-forming potential, with high cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) activity, primarily driven by increased sulfate fractions. The data collected on aerosol composition, growth rates, CCN concentrations, and hygroscopicity offer valuable insights into the influence of aerosol properties on cloud and precipitation processes in a cleaner environment. Notably, our study provides the first direct observational evidence of coal-fired power plant SO_2 emissions significantly enhancing aerosol CCN activity. We emphasize the importance of considering increased aerosol mass burdens resulting from new particle formation when devising policies to mitigate $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ pollution, particularly in India's pollution-prone coastal regions.

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AEROSOLS AND AIR QUALITY

VOLATILE ORGANIC COMPOUNDS IMPACT ON OZONE AND SECONDARY ORGANIC AEROSOLS FORMATION IN THE RURAL ATMOSPHERE: ASSESSING ESTIMATION AND SEASONAL VARIABILITY

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Keywords: VOCs, Rural atmosphere, OFP, SOAP.

INTRODUCTION

Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) serve as precursors for tropospheric ozone (O_3) and Secondary Organic Aerosol (SOA) formation. The formation of O_3 and SOA serve as direct indicators of the oxidative capacity specific to a given chemical environment, varying between urban and rural atmospheres. The current study investigates the oxidizing capacity of the relatively less explored tropical rural atmosphere (Gadanki). This is accomplished by measuring the concentrations of various VOCs and combining them with OH loss rates to estimate the potentials for O_3 and SOA formation (OFP and SOAP, respectively). Continuous diel VOC measurement data encompassing four distinct seasons and comprising over 4000 samples have been utilized to estimate OFP and SOAP and their variations across different seasons. Additionally, efforts have been made to comprehend the contribution of different sources to O_3 and SOA formation.

METHODS

The concentrations of VOCs have been measured using Gas- Chromatography technique coupled with Flame Ionization Detector (GC-FID) (Broadway and Tipler, 2012; Sindhu et al., 2023). The parameters Ozone Formation Potential (OFP), Propylene Equivalent Concentration (PEC), Secondary Organic Aerosol Formation Potential (SOAP) and OH Loss Rate (L_{OH}) have been estimated using the individual VOC concentrations to investigate the atmospheric oxidizing capacity. Positive Matrix Factorization (PMF) model has been utilized for the source apportionment of measured VOCs (Sindhu et al., 2023).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The oxidizing capacity of the rural tropical site Gadanki has been investigated by estimating the parameters OFP, PEC, SOAP and L_{OH} of measured VOCs from December 2021 to November 2022. A comprehensive analysis of these parameters for each VOC and VOC seasonal variations has been carried out

Figure 1. Percentage contribution of VOC groups, seasons and sources to total OFP

Among the 31 measured VOCs, 1,3,6 trimethylbenzene (20.1%) exhibits the highest OFP, followed by ethylene (15.8 %). Among all 4 seasons, the post-monsoon season records a high OFP (385.7 ppb). Increased concentrations of certain VOCs with higher MIR values during the monsoon and post-monsoon periods, attributed to greater vegetation cover, result in higher OFP. Aromatic VOCs are the primary contributors to O_3 formation, followed by alkenes and alkanes (Figure 1). The source apportionment using

PMF model has resulted in 4 different sources namely biogenic, biomass burning, fossil fuel, and natural gas (Sindhu et al., 2023). Using the contribution of each factor, the OFP and SOAP formed from different sources are estimated. The results show that the biomass burning factor is the dominant contributor for OFP followed by the biogenic factor (Figure 1).

n-dodecane (33.8%) has the highest SOAP, followed by styrene (17.48 %). The summer season experiences a high SOAP (5604.34 ppb). Elevated concentrations of specific VOCs with higher SOAP_i values and higher L_{OH} of VOCs in summer contribute to the heightened SOAP. Alkanes are dominant in contributing to SOA formation, followed by aromatic VOCs. Among the sources, the biomass burning factor is the dominant contributor to (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Percentage contribution of VOC groups, seasons and sources to total SOAP

The higher MIR and SOAP_i values of aromatic VOCs contribute to their elevated role in O₃ and SOA formation. The major VOCs and the sources contributing to O₃ and SOA formation exhibit significant differences based on the concentration, number of C-atoms, L_{OH}, MIR and SOAP_i values. Among the sources, biomass burning VOCs predominantly contribute to both O₃ and SOA formation, showcasing a distinctive feature of the rural atmosphere.

CONCLUSIONS

The oxidizing capacity of the rural atmosphere differs from the urban atmosphere, characterized by distinct VOCs, VOC groups (alkanes, alkenes and aromatic VOCs) and emission sources contributing to OFP and SOAP. Biomass-burning and biogenic factors together contribute 63% to OFP and biomass burning factor alone contribute 55% to SOAP, distinguishing the rural atmosphere from its urban counterpart, where traffic emissions predominantly influence OFP and SOAP.

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EXPLORING 17-YEAR SATELLITE INSIGHTS AND ANALYZING PROBABLE ANTHROPOGENIC AND NATURAL CAUSES TO UNCOVER NITROGEN DIOXIDE TRENDS IN INDIA'S NORTH EASTERN REGION.

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Key words: Nitrogen Dioxide, Natural and anthropogenic sources

1. Introduction

Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) significantly influences the Earth's atmospheric radiative balance, altering oxidation capacity and chemistry, and impacting the lifetime of greenhouse gases. It primarily emanates from industrial processes, vehicle combustion, biomass fuel and crop residue burning, and soil emissions (Cheng et al., 2012). Natural sources include lightning and soil emissions. NO₂ contributes to degraded air quality, adversely affecting human health. Thunderstorm lightning has been considered a major source of nitrogen oxides (NO_x, i.e. NO (nitric oxide) and NO₂ (nitrogen dioxide)) since von Liebig (1827) proposed it as a natural mechanism for the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen (Hutchinson, 1954). The global Lightning-induced nitrogen oxides LNO_x source is one of the largest natural sources of NO_x in the atmosphere (Galloway et al., 2004) and certainly the largest source of NO_x in the upper troposphere, in particular in the tropics (WMO, 1999). Here, we aim to quantify the increasing/decreasing trends of troposphere column NO₂ and examine seasonal variations. Besides the lightning count is also considered to connect with the NO₂ for its contribution. The assessing NO₂'s spatiotemporal distribution and identifying emission sources are crucial to formulating effective reduction strategies.

Figure 1: TCN over the eight states

Figure 2: Lightning flashes over the eight states

2. Data and Methodology

Tropospheric NO₂ concentrations were obtained from the Ozone Monitoring Instrument (OMI) on the Aura satellite. OMI measures the Earth's backscattered radiation within the spectral range of 264–504 nm (Streets et al., 2013). To derive tropospheric column concentrations of NO₂, the attenuation measurements provide slant column densities, converted to vertical column densities using appropriate air mass factors.

4. Result and discussion

4.1 Intra-annual variation over NERI

Fig. 1 illustrates the temporal and spatial mean seasonal TCN over the eight states of NERI spanning 17 years, from 2005 to 2022. The annual mean TCN exhibits the highest concentrations in Assam (1.57×10^{15} mol cm⁻²), Meghalaya (1.60×10^{15} mol cm⁻²), and Tripura (1.62×10^{15} mol cm⁻²), while Sikkim records the lowest (5.28×10^{14} mol cm⁻²). TCN levels are generally elevated during the pre-monsoon and winter across all states, followed by the post-monsoon and monsoon seasons. In the pre-monsoon period, Manipur shows the highest TCN (2.58×10^{15} mol cm⁻²), followed by Mizoram and other states, while Arunachal Pradesh and Sikkim exhibit the lowest TCN (8.74×10^{14} mol cm⁻² and 5.27×10^{14} mol cm⁻²), respectively. This observed pattern of high TCN during the pre-monsoon months is attributed to significant biomass burning in these states.

4.2 Long-term TCN over NERI

The annual variations of TCN from 2005 to 2022 were observed by the satellite for four seasons across the eight northeastern states of India. Across all seasons, Assam consistently displayed the highest TCN value (1.57×10^{15} mol cm^{-2}), along with Meghalaya, Tripura, and Nagaland. On the other hand, Sikkim and Arunachal Pradesh recorded the lowest TCN values (5.28×10^{14} mol cm^{-2}). Notably, all states experienced an increase in TCN over the seventeen-year period (2005 to 2022). This long-term increase in TCN is influenced by anthropogenic factors, such as rising vehicle numbers, industries, and population density.

4.3 Natural and anthropogenic sources of TCN

Natural Source: This is because higher humidity levels lead to stronger hydrometeor concentrations and updraft velocities, both of which contribute to intense lightning. Lightning stands as one of the largest natural sources of atmospheric nitrogen oxides (Galloway et al., 2004). Fig. 2 illustrates the average seasonal variation of lightning flashes across different states in the North Eastern Region (NER). The pre-monsoon and monsoon seasons exhibit the highest lightning activity. During the pre-monsoon season, Meghalaya and Tripura record the highest number of lightning flashes, while Arunachal Pradesh experiences the lowest. In the monsoon season, Meghalaya, Tripura, and Mizoram witness the highest lightning frequency.

Anthropogenic source: Anthropogenic NO_2 primarily originates from combustion engines that burn fossil fuels, such as oil, natural gas, and coal, to produce energy. The formation of NO_x during combustion processes involves three gas-phase reaction mechanisms (García R et al., 2014). In the NERI region, the principal sources of NO_2 are attributed to an increasing number of vehicles and factories, biomass burning in household appliances, and the burning of crop residues (Fig. 3).

Forest fire: India's North Eastern Region (NER) boasts some of the largest tropical and sub-tropical forest reserves, including wet evergreen, semi-evergreen, moist deciduous, coniferous forests, mixed forests, and shrubs (Roy and Joshi, 2002), covering nearly 64.66% of its geographic area. The spatially averaged fire count density (in FC km^{-2}) over a fifteen-year period shows the highest value in Mizoram (0.398), followed by Nagaland (0.257), Tripura (0.251), Manipur (0.190), Meghalaya (0.138), Assam (0.065), Arunachal (0.027), and Sikkim (0.008). Fire counts vary from 64,092 to 1,07,506 in March, 4,972 to 6,204 in January, and 12,268 to 28,393 in February. Forest fires are significant sources of NO_2 .

5. Conclusion

The NERI is experiencing increasing NO_2 production due to population growth, urbanization, industrialization, agricultural demands, energy consumption, forest fires, and lightning. Assessing the spatiotemporal distribution of NO_2 and identifying emission sources is crucial for formulating effective reduction strategies. This approach addresses both air quality concerns and broader environmental health challenges within the NERI.

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Figure 3: Trends of anthropogenic sources

SEASONAL VARIABILITY OF ATMOSPHERIC NO_2 CONCENTRATION OVER AHMEDABAD CITY USING SATELLITE DATA

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Keywords: Air quality, Greenhouse gas, NO_2 , Remote Sensing.

INTRODUCTION

Air quality depends on the greenhouse gases, aerosols particulates suspended in the air and some harmful constituents released from the grounds like combustion of fossil fuels etc. Studying these factors helps us understanding the current air quality of the place as well as the future probable trend that the air quality will take. The gases responsible for the trapping of the heat in the atmosphere and causing greenhouse effect and therefore global warming are known as greenhouse gases. One of such gases is Nitrogen dioxide (NO_2). Study of NO_2 is important because it is not only itself responsible for global warming but also with its constituent gas Nitric oxide NO, it is crucial in the production of ozone, which is also a greenhouse gas. Ozone is produced from the destruction of NO_2 into $NO \wedge O$. This oxygen then combines with O_2 molecule to form O_3 [Pancholi et al., 2017]. Therefore, it is necessary to know the concentration of NO_2 gas. There are many natural and anthropogenic sources of NO_x (term for representing both NO_2 and NO) such as fossil fuel consumption. Most of the sources of NO_x , are always near to the detection point of it since NO_x has very short chemical lifetime [Ghude et al., 2008]. Rapid increment in the urbanization, industrialization are important sources of pollution. [Akimoto, 2003]. The present study aims to quantify seasonal variability of NO_2 gas from the satellite and ground-based observations.

DATA AND METHOD

Ahmedabad (study area) is considered to be one of the mega cities in India. This causes the city to be more prone to air pollution. Satellite based measurement was validated at CPCB station installed at Maninagar (22.995° N, 72.604° E), Ahmedabad, India. The satellite-based data of NO_2 from Sentinel 5P was used in this study. Sentinel 5P satellite is a near polar, sun synchronous orbit satellite. The data of Sentinel was collected and processed on Google Earth Engine and was extracted at city area and point location, in this case, Maninagar. Monthly variations in concentration of NO_2 were plotted for 2019 to 2022. Using GIS software, the concentration of NO_2 was mapped throughout India.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Fig 1 shows the spatial distribution of NO_2 over India. We can see the pockets of regions showing very high concentration representing the polluted regions. The high concentrations are associated with highly populated metropolitan urban regions and major thermal power stations in India. NO_2 concentration taken from the satellite has been averaged to the monthly values. Fig 2 (a) and (b) shows seasonal variability of concentration of NO_x in different years and comparison of ground and satellite observations respectively. From this we can observe that there is a seasonal behavior in the concentration. We notice that every year, the concentration is highest in winter and lowest is monsoon season. The reason for this seasonal variation could be due to change in the planetary boundary layer (PBL). PBL is the lowest part of the atmosphere and depends on the changes in the planetary surface. The thickness of PBL depends on the intensity of the surface heating. More heated surface results in more PBL thickness. Therefore, in winter since the PBL is low, the gases are more densely packed and so the concentration is highest at that time. Another reason may be due to the variation in the burning of biomass which results in the emission of NO_x gas. Fig 2b shows seasonal variation in different years and comparison of ground and satellite observations. It can be seen that the satellite based seasonal pattern is in resemblances with the ground based measured data.

Figure 1. Variation of concentration of NO_2 all over the India for year 2020

Figure 2. (a) Monthly variation of concentration of NO_2 ($\mu mol/m^2$) for 2019-2022 using Sentinel 5P. (b) Monthly comparison (year 2022) for Sentinel 5P ($\mu mol/m^2$) and ground data ($\mu g/m^3$)

CONCLUSIONS

Study shows potential applications of satellite technology in addressing the air pollution monitoring for large region. Seasonal variation in NO_2 concentration observed from satellite is in agreement with ground data.

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VARIABILITY OF BLACK CARBON CONCENTRATION AND ITS ASSESMENT OVER AN URBAN CITY AHMEDABAD

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Keywords: Aerosols and Air Quality, Black Carbon, In - Situ measurements, Urban Area Emissions.

INTRODUCTION

Black carbon (BC), often called soot, is a dominant form of light absorbing aerosols in the Atmosphere. It is emitted by incomplete combustion processes, due to both man-made (e.g., diesel engines) and natural sources (e.g., wildfire) with a lifetime of 7-10 days in the lower troposphere with notable spatial and temporal variability in its sources and emissions. These types of aerosols absorb the incoming shortwave solar radiation and outgoing longwave terrestrial radiation, and is therefore considered an important contributor to the direct radiative forcing through warming in the Atmosphere (Ramachandran, 2007).

METHODS

The present study focusses to investigate the variations in Black Carbon aerosols over a semi-arid urban city of Gujarat, Ahmedabad (23.0329° N, 72.5517° E) for a time span of two years from January 2021-December 2022. Long intensive in situ- measurements of BC was taken using the Aethalometer instrument to understand its seasonal and diurnal contrast along with the calculation of Delta C (UV370nm- UV880nm) indicative of enhanced absorption in near-UV and low-visible wavelengths attributed to the presence of biomass burning and light absorbing particulate matter over the period of time (Panchal, 2020).

Table - 1 Descriptive Statistics: Concentration of Black Carbon aerosols (μgm^{-3}) over the time span.

Year	2021	2022
Mean	5.93	5.54
Standard Deviation	3.54	3.08
Maximum	11.72	10.76
Minimum	1.81	2.23

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Continuous and real-time measurements of Black Carbon aerosols have been carried using the Aethalometer (AE-33) instruments over Ahmedabad. The overview of statistics features of the dataset is shown in the Table-1. The average seasonal dependence of Black Carbon as per the figure – 1 indicates that the concentration of BC is highest in Winter ($\sim 10.54\mu\text{gm}^{-3}$) and Post-Monsoon ($\sim 10.34\mu\text{gm}^{-3}$) in comparison with Summer ($\sim 7.13\mu\text{gm}^{-3}$) and Monsoon ($\sim 5.27\mu\text{gm}^{-3}$) which is due to observed due to varying meteorological conditions (wind direction, wind speed, relative humidity, air temperature, air pressure, rainfall, and boundary layer height dynamics) as well as increase consumption of biomass and fossil fuels for heating and cooking purposes in Winter and process of washout by precipitation during rainfall. Along with these the average diurnal variations of the hourly average BC depicts a bimodal peak one in the morning observed at around 07:00 - 9:00 am and other at night from 19:00 – 21:00 pm. The gradual increase of BC during morning hours maybe due to the process of fumigation in which after sunrise as the Mixed Layer (ML) grows, the elevated pollutants are mixed down to the surface due to turbulence (Shaeb, 2019). During the afternoon hours BC is found to be lesser as compared to morning and evening hours. The more prominent night-time peak is the result due to the combined effect of the shallower boundary layer as well as increased traffic density during night (Ramachandran, 2007). The Delta – C observations also shows a diurnal pattern similar to BC with range between 4 to 1 μgm^{-3} , with peak at night and dip in afternoon. Delta – C also shows seasonal behaviour as show in Figure 1

Figure 1 – Seasonal Variation of Black Carbon and Delta C over Ahmedabad city for year 2021 and 2022

Figure – 2 Average Diurnal variation of Black Carbon and Delta-C over the time span (2021 – 2022).

CONCLUSIONS

On analysing the concentration of Black Carbon (BC) for two year’s (January 2021- December 2022) the seasonal – diurnal pattern and optical characterisation were observed. The BC concentrations are higher during winters and post – monsoon period. The diurnal variation in Delta-C was mostly consistent with the $\text{BC}_{880\text{nm}}$ profile, having a bimodal peak. The study discusses the sources too which can be helpful in understanding the impact of BC on air quality. However further analysis is required to characterize its behaviour.

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DETERMINATION OF SEASONAL RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PM_{2.5} WITH METEOROLOGICAL PARAMETERS FOR AN URBAN CITY: AHMEDABAD

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Keywords: PM_{2.5}, Meteorological Parameters (MP), Seasonal Behaviour, Aerosols and air quality.

INTRODUCTION

PM_{2.5} is a particulate matter having the size of 2.5 micrometres or even smaller is considered to be harmful as it can easily penetrate the respiratory system. As its concentration is affected by meteorological condition of the region, it is essential to find the relationship between them. (Krishna, 2018) used temperature, wind speed, relative humidity and planetary boundary layer to find their relationship with PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ for Pune and Delhi. (Khobragade, 2022) states that PM_{2.5} concentration are more during winter due decrease in temperature and lower wind speeds. The wind direction is also one of the variables affecting PM_{2.5} concentration (Li, 2017).

METHODS

The present study aims to find the dependence of PM_{2.5} with meteorological parameters (MP) for Ahmedabad which is an urban city in Gujarat. It is a semi-arid region located at 23.0225° N and 72.5714° E. The hourly data for the analysis of the two-year time span (June 2021 till June 2023) was acquired from the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) website. The seasonal interdependence of PM_{2.5} with several MP like Relative Humidity (RH), Ambient Temperature (AT), Wind Speed (WS) and Wind Direction (WD) is discussed in the present module. The seasonal climatology in this study is classified as Winter (December - February), Summer (March - May), Monsoon (June - September) and Post- Monsoon (October and November) as designated by India Meteorological Department (IMD).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1. Monthly variation of PM_{2.5} and MP for the year 2021 – 2023

Figure 2. Seasonal relationship of PM_{2.5} with MP for (a) Winter (b) Summer (c) Monsoon (d) Post-Monsoon

From Figure 1, the average concentration for Ahmedabad lies between 0-80 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ where lowest concentrations are recorded during monsoon whereas for winter, they are significantly higher. The Diwali festival celebration might be a reason that PM_{2.5} is higher during post-monsoon. The data also shows seasonal pattern. As seen from Figure 2, the PM_{2.5} correlation with MP varies according to the season. The WS is found to be negatively correlated in all seasons which shows that the wind causes the transportation of particulates causing dispersion and less concentration. During winter, monsoon and post-monsoon a negative correlation of RH is observed with PM_{2.5} whereas in summer, it is less correlated. During monsoon as RH is high, it can suppress the particulate matter which results in low concentration (Khobragade, 2022). As high temperature causes the vertical dispersion of particles, a negative correlation is seen in summer with AT. WD also plays a significant role in PM_{2.5} concentration. It was found that in winter, the prominent WD is easterly and north-easterly and in summer south-easterly to south-westerly. Southerly and north-easterly WD prevails in post-monsoon and south-westerly in monsoon illustrating the transport of PM_{2.5} from that direction.

CONCLUSIONS

There is transport of particulates due to wind hence WS depicts negative relation. The present study concludes that the concentration of PM_{2.5} is influenced by MP depending upon the seasons such that AT has negative correlation during summer resulting from high temperatures in comparison to other seasons. Also the correlation of RH varies according to season.

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SEASONAL VARIATION IN AEROSOL VOLUME SIZE DISTRIBUTIONS IN FOUR DIVERSE LOCATIONS IN INDIA

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KEYWORDS: AEROSOLS, AIR QUALITY, AEROSOL VOLUME SIZE DISTRIBUTION, AERONET

INTRODUCTION

Aerosols, solid or liquid particles, are ubiquitous in the atmosphere. Atmospheric aerosols cover a wide size range, with four orders of magnitude difference between the smallest and the largest aerosol particle. Aerosol size distribution is strongly modulated by the interplay among different atmospheric processes, source, sink, and interactions among aerosol types that collectively shape the behaviour of aerosols in the atmosphere. The understanding of evolution of aerosols in the atmosphere across various geographical locations offers valuable insight regarding the origin, transport, nature, and evolution of aerosols. Aerosol climatic effects are strong functions of both aerosol size and composition. Here, the main objective is to examine seasonality in aerosol volume size distribution (VSD) in four diverse locations in India, namely, Kanpur, Gandhi College, Pune, and Jaipur.

METHODS

In this study, we utilised Aerosol Robotic Network (AERONET) level 2 inverted long-term aerosol VSD for 22 logarithmically equidistant discrete size bin in the range of 0.05 μm to 15 μm [Dubovik et.al., 2006]. These data were derived using the Almucentar sky radiometer for four permanent monitoring sites in India: Kanpur (2001-2022), Gandhi College (2006-2021), Pune (2004-2019), and Jaipur (2009-2022). Additionally, we have also incorporated Single Scattering Albedo (SSA) at 440nm wavelength and Angstrom exponent (α) values for 440-870nm wavelengths from AERONET for these locations, in our analysis.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The contour plot of aerosol VSD showed distinct variability and seasonality across all four locations in India. All four locations clearly exhibited bimodal log-normal characteristics in aerosol VSD, with the dominance of coarse mode in all four locations. Aerosol VSD illustrated the lowest accumulation mode in Jaipur while the lowest coarser mode in Pune. Gandhi College, which is in the eastern Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP), showed the highest accumulation mode among all sites, indicating the presence of aged aerosols. Furthermore, we identified different aerosol types in all locations by examining the associations between SSA, α , and volume concentration. We observed higher SSA and higher α in Kanpur, Jaipur, and Pune, suggesting the presence of aerosols that efficiently scatter light and a predominance of coarser particles. This indicates that these regions may be susceptible to natural events like dust storms and biomass burning. In Jaipur, the combination of high-volume concentration with high SSA and low α , as well as high SSA and high α , suggested a diverse aerosol composition likely originating from a mix of anthropogenic and natural sources. This scenario implies variable air quality and complex interactions with light, underscoring the importance of detailed local environmental studies. Understanding these mixed aerosol sources is crucial for assessing both air quality and regional climate impacts, highlighting the necessity for continuous monitoring and in-depth analysis.

Figure 1. Aerosol Volume size distribution over Kanpur, Gandhi College, Pune, and Jaipur

CONCLUSIONS

The following major conclusions are drawn from this study

- The long-term semi-continuous AERONET data offers utility to examine evolution of aerosols in the atmosphere.
- Aerosol volume size distributions showed distinct seasonal and diurnal variability in all locations with strong heterogeneity indicating interplay between different sources and atmospheric processes.

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EXAMINING CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF PM_{2.5} AT RESIDENTIAL OUTDOORS DURING FESTIVE FIREWORK EVENTS ACROSS MUMBAI, INDIA

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Keywords: Chemical composition; Diwali; Fireworks; Mumbai; PM_{2.5}

INTRODUCTION

An increase in particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) pollution in urban areas during non-rainy periods is a serious health hazard. In addition to high emissions from vehicular and industrial sources, elevated concentrations of PM_{2.5} are often observed during firework events, especially during Diwali, the festival of lights. While several studies have examined the impact of such festive fireworks on PM mass concentrations based on fixed ambient monitoring locations, the chemical composition and PM exposures in residential neighbourhoods are poorly examined. Therefore, the aim of the study is to comprehend the spatial and temporal variations in PM_{2.5} and its chemical composition for the samples collected in the residential neighbourhoods of Mumbai during the pre- Diwali, Diwali, and post-Diwali periods.

METHOD

Residential outdoor PM_{2.5} samples were collected from 10 different residential sites across Mumbai using low-volume air samplers during the day (6 a.m.-6 p.m.) and night (6 p.m.-6 a.m.) during Diwali, two days prior to and after the Diwali in October 2022. Post-gravimetry, the collected PM samples were analysed for trace elements, heavy metals, and inorganic ions using Inductively Coupled Plasma- Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS) and Ion Chromatography (IC).

Figure 1: Spatial and temporal variation in total metals and inorganic ions during pre-Diwali, Diwali, and post-Diwali periods in the different sites of Mumbai, India

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

PM_{2.5} was significantly elevated during the Diwali night for all the sites ($520 \pm 270 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), with a maximum concentration of $1168 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. PM_{2.5} levels were 107 ± 81 and $199 \pm 178 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ during the pre- and post-Diwali periods, respectively. Several toxic metals, viz. Cu, Pb, Zn, Cd, and Mn were significantly elevated (by 157%, 120%, 95%, 66% and 28%, respectively) during Diwali night. Similarly, the dominant inorganic ions like Na⁺, K⁺, NH₄⁺, Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, and SO₄²⁻ were also increased by 59%, 81%, 50%, 162%, 94%, and 51% respectively, during the Diwali night. The levels of these chemical constituents during post-Diwali were also higher than pre-Diwali night, albeit less elevated than Diwali, suggesting the impact of residual fireworks activity after the Diwali festival (Figure 1).

CONCLUSIONS

Our findings implicate that high exposure to toxic PM constituents during and post-Diwali nights in residential areas due to festive fireworks may lead to short-term adverse health effects, especially in vulnerable populations. Additional analysis, including health impact risk assessments, associations among different chemical species, and the effect of meteorological parameters, is currently underway.

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UNDERSTANDING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN AOD AND NIGHT TIME LIGHTS OVER AHMEDABAD CITY

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Keywords: Aerosols and air quality, Night Time Lights, Aerosol Optical Depth, Light Pollution.

INTRODUCTION

Aerosols are tiny particles having size range from 1nm to 100 μm which are present in the atmosphere having either natural or anthropogenic origin. Aerosols play a key role in air pollution, radiation balance, cloud formation, etc. Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) is a key parameter in studying the aerosol radiative and scattering effects. Major sources of anthropogenic aerosols include industrial and urban emissions. Urbanization is the decrease in proportion of people living in rural areas. It also refers to the growth in infrastructure due to increase in population hence demanding an expansion of city area. This expansion of urban area is known as urban sprawl. This also leads to an increase in the use of artificial illumination sources. Increase in AOD can increase the scattering from the artificial light sources giving rise to light pollution [Ayudyanti, et. al., 2021]. Hence the study of Nighttime lights (NTL) data [Noam Levin, et. al., 2020] in relation with variation in AOD can be useful in understanding urban sprawl of a city and light pollution.

DATA AND METHODS

Location: This study has been performed for the location of Ahmedabad city, India located between (22.90°N, 72.45°E) and (23.10°N, 72.70°E). This location was selected due to it being a mega city and having a dense population.

1. NOAA-VIIRS data: For NTL data, monthly averaged radiance composite images (GeoTiff) using nighttime data from the Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite (VIIRS) Day/Night Band (DNB) from Google Earth Engine for the decade 2013-2022 (Product name: NOAA_VIIRS_DNB_MONTHLY_V1_VCMCFG) are utilised. The average radiance is in units of $\text{nW}/\text{cm}^2/\text{sr}$. Image resolution is 15 arcsecond (~500m at the Equator). This data was averaged over the study area specified above. Monthly variations for each year as well as yearly variations (averaged over months) were plotted.
2. MODIS Terra AOD: For AOD data, time series area averaged MODIS Terra AOD at 550nm for the decade 2013-2022 is utilised. Yearly variations (averaged over months) were plotted.
3. Correlation between yearly NTL and AOD was found.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The monthly variations of NTL (Fig 1) for each year show that there is no such drastic change in NTL for a single year, but a continuous increment is observed every year. The sudden drops are observed for the monsoon months June to September indicating no data or less data due to cloud cover. However in Fig 2 which shows yearly variation of NTL exhibits an increase in average radiance every year. This increase indicates the impact of urbanization and the urban sprawl of the city. For the same decade (2013-2022) yearly variation in AOD (at 550nm) can be seen in Fig 3 which also shows an increase in AOD over the city for the given time period. Fig 4 depicts the correlation between AOD and NTL. The Pearson correlation comes out to be $R=0.6119$ (indicating a positive association) and the Spearman correlation comes out to be 0.70909. Hence there appears to be a strong correlation [Akoglu, 2018] between NTL and AOD.

Figure 1: Monthly variation of average radiance of nighttime lights for each year from 2013-2022

Figure 2: Yearly variation of average radiance averaged over months of nighttime lights over Ahmedabad

Figure 3: Yearly variation of MODIS Terra AOD(550nm) averaged over months for

Figure 4: Correlation between nighttime lights and AOD ($R^2=0.3745$, $R=0.6119$)

CONCLUSIONS

The results show a clear increase in NTL with AOD indicating increase in urbanization and urban sprawl of Ahmedabad city over the decade 2013-2022. NTL can also be used to understand light pollution. However further investigation and research is required to understand the relation between NTL data and aerosol data available from satellite.

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ESTIMATION OF TRUE HOUSEHOLD PM_{2.5} EXPOSURE IN INDIA AND IT'S VARIATION OVER THE LAST DECADE

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Keywords: PM_{2.5}, HAP, True exposure, NFHS

INTRODUCTION

Multiple toxic products from incomplete combustion of solid cookfuel in households is amongst the leading environmental risk factors contributing to Global Burden of Disease. India being from a Low-middle income country (LMIC) has a very high prevalence of solid fuel use. Several recent studies have attributed the largest share of household air pollution (HAP) towards ambient PM_{2.5} (particulate matter of aerodynamic diameter of less than 2.5 μm) concentration in India. Hence household concentration and personal exposure assessment are crucial to evaluate India's current situation and for policy framing in upcoming years.

METHODS

In this study we have estimated 24 hour-average PM_{2.5} concentration and true exposure in rural households at the district, state, and national level using the model developed by Balakrishnan et al. 2013 using the most recent nationally representative datasets of NFHS-4 (2015-16) and NFHS-5 (2019-21). Household and living room concentration are estimated using regression models (described in the above-mentioned paper) using household parameters like type of cooking fuel use, kitchen location, ventilation type, cooking duration, and geographic location. Once kitchen and living room concentration is estimated, time weighted mean exposure for a person is calculated using the formula given below. This is the true exposure for a person who stays in the kitchen during cooking and the rest of the day in the living area.

$$Exposure = \frac{Cooking\ hour \times kitchen\ conc. + (24 - Cooking\ hour) \times living\ room\ conc.}{24}$$

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

We estimated kitchen concentration, living room concentration, and true exposure value of rural households using the above methodology.

	PM _{2.5} ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) in 2015-16	PM _{2.5} ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) in 2019-21
Kitchen conc.	338	291
Living room conc.	102	94
True exposure	146	128

Table 1. Comparison of nationally averaged PM_{2.5} value between NFHS-4 and NFHS-5.

In all the cases PM_{2.5} level reduced in recent years with compare to 2015-16. We found out, that the type of fuel used has the maximum correlation with the PM concentration value, so we checked how the use of LPG (which is a cleaner fuel) as primary cooking fuel has changed over these two periods. During NFHS-4, fraction of households using LPG was 38% whereas during NFHS-5 it increased to 51%. But neither the change of LPG user fraction nor the PM levels are uniform across districts, which makes it interesting to study this at a sub-national level.

Fig 1. Relative change in true exposure value in 2019-21 with respect to 2015-16

CONCLUSIONS

There is a clear reduction of $PM_{2.5}$ concentration level from 2015-16 to 2019-21. This is associated with the reduction of solid fuel users across the country. But no causal relation has been established in this present work. Also, there is a clear disparity of true exposure value between a person who cooks and a person who doesn't cook (spend the entire day in the living room). Nevertheless, these two values have also reduced between the said two periods.

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CITY-BASED EMISSION INVENTORY MAPPING OF ATMOSPHERIC POLLUTANTS FOR AN INDUSTRIAL REGION (HALDIA): IMPLICATION FOR EFFECTIVE CONTROL AND MITIGATION

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Keywords: Emissions; Emission inventory; Air quality modeling

INTRODUCTION

A reliable and comprehensive emission inventory is one of the key steps to address the problem of air pollution. Emission inventories quantify the sources as well as the amount of pollutants emitted into the atmosphere and help identify the major contributors to air quality degradation, evaluate the effectiveness of emission control measures, and support air quality modelling and management (EPA, 2022). Haldia City is a major industrial hub in the Indian state of West Bengal and hosts several large-scale industries, such as petrochemicals, fertilizers, steel, power plants, and ports, as well as small-scale industries, such as brick kilns, rice mills, and workshops. The city also experiences high traffic congestion and domestic fuel burning, which contribute to air pollution. Due to the exceedance of National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQs) from year 2016-20, the city was listed as a Non-Attainment City (NAC) under the National Clean Air Programme (NCAP) (CPCB, 2021). Developing a high-resolution emission inventory covering diverse sectors and pollutants for the Haldia region would aid in the identification of local emission hotspots and provide valuable information for policymakers, researchers, and stakeholders to effectively evaluate the current air pollution scenario and trends in the Haldia region to design effective mitigation strategies.

METHODOLOGY

A multi-pollutant emission inventory is prepared following a bottom-up methodology for the base year 2021. The sources of emissions are categorized into three types: point, line, and area. Point sources included 71 brick kilns, 24 industries, six crematories, two thermal power plants and one landfill. Emissions from the transportation sector are classified as line sources. The residential sector, refuse burning and marine sector are considered as area sources of emission.

Emissions

The emissions (E_p) were calculated using the equation below:

$$E_p = \sum_{s=1}^n \sum_{t=1}^m \sum_{f=1}^p (A \times EF_p \times (1 - \mu))$$

A is the emission-related activity; EF_p is the emission factor of the pollutant p corresponding to sector s , technology t , and fuel f . μ is the efficiency of the air pollution control device. Emission factors are obtained from various literature relevant to the Indian context. The unit for emission factor is taken as g kg^{-1} (gram of pollutant emitted per kilogram of fuel burnt). Activity data has been collected by consulting annual reports of various industries, central and state pollution control boards, the Right to Information Act, port trust, etc. A questionnaire is also prepared for Haldia municipality to gather additional activity data.

Spatial distribution of emissions

The emissions calculated based on the above equation are spatially distributed using ArcMap v10.8 with a grid resolution of $1 \times 1 \text{ km}$ and the grids with high emission flux are identified as hotspots of emission.

Reconciliation of emissions

The emissions prepared for the Haldia region (bottom-up approach) are reconciled with the recently estimated constrained emissions (top-down approach) (Ghosh and Verma, 2023) over West Bengal for black carbon (BC) and sulfur dioxide (SO_2) aerosol species.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

An emission inventory is prepared covering an area of 321 km^2 . Figure 1(a) shows the contribution of various sectors to the emissions. It is estimated that industries and thermal power plants are the primary contributors to SO_2 emissions (with shares of 38% and 36%, respectively) due to the usage of coal with high sulfur content. For nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and carbon monoxide (CO) emissions vehicle exhaust due to freight movement via heavy and light-duty vehicles is the dominant source (71% and 43% respectively) as most of these vehicles are diesel-operated. The residential sector shares a significant contribution in CO emissions (40%) as the rural areas in the region rely heavily on fuelwood, rice straw, etc. for cooking purposes which results in incomplete combustion of fuel resulting in high CO emissions. Figure 1(b) shows the emission hotspots over the Haldia region. The city center (wards 13 and 21) is an emission hotspot for BC, organic carbon (OC), non-methane volatile organic compounds (NMVOC), and OC pollutants due to

the presence of two major industries and two traffic intersections located in proximity. Durgachak (wards 8 and 9) is an emission hotspot for NO_x emissions as it has two major traffic intersections of the region as well as three industries. Haldia Energy Limited, a coal-based thermal power plant located in the Haldia region is a hotspot for SO₂ and particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) emissions. It can be observed from the analysis that the hotspots are dynamic concerning the type of pollutant, hence, a single mitigation strategy targeting one site or one pollutant will not be feasible to control the emissions over the entire Haldia region and there is a need for ward-wide and pollutant wide source control measures.

Figure 1. (a) Sectoral contribution to the emission of various pollutants (b) Emission hotspots over the Haldia region (dashed circle represents hotspot and various color represents aerosol species)

CONCLUSIONS

A fine-resolution emission inventory is prepared for the Haldia region and the potential hotspots in the region are identified. This emission inventory can be utilized as an input parameter to perform chemistry transport model simulations. The emission inventory can provide valuable information for policymakers, researchers, and stakeholders to understand the current status and trends of air pollution in Haldia city and to design effective mitigation strategies.

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**INDIA'S AEROSOL POLLUTION: STATE-WISE LONG-TERM (2005-2019)
CHARACTERISTICS, FUTURE PROJECTION (2023) AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS**
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Keywords: Source apportionment, Future projection, Policy recommendation, ARIMA

INTRODUCTION

Over-urbanization and industrialization are increasing day by day to meet the increasing demands of the growing population resulting in uncontrolled emissions in India. Pandey et al. (2019) revealed that in 2019, air pollution in India was responsible for a staggering 1.67 million premature deaths (95% uncertainty interval 1.42–1.92), constituting 17.8% (15.8–19.5) of the nation's total mortality. Apart from ambient air pollution, deaths from the use of residential solid fuel for cooking and other household activities caused early death and ill health among lower-income Indians (Chafe and Chowdhury, 2021). Since the 20th century, Government of India has adopted many policies and mitigation strategies to combat air pollution. However, air pollution in India is still a major concern. Therefore, we carried out an in-depth and long-term study of aerosol pollution for each of the states in India to better understand the current and future scenarios. In addition, a novel approach was adopted for the recommendation of possible and immediate actions to be taken by the Government and policymakers for air pollution mitigation.

METHODS

Percentiles of long-term mean values of AOD were used to indicate the vulnerability of the states in India in terms of aerosol pollution. Based on these percentiles, we define four different zones: green or safe zone (AOD value of less than 25th percentile; < 0.3), blue or less vulnerable zone (AOD value between 25th and 50th percentile; 0.3–0.4), orange or vulnerable zone (AOD value between 50th and 75th percentile; 0.4–0.5) and red or highly vulnerable zone (AOD value greater than 75th percentile; > 0.5). To understand the change in the source of aerosol pollution, source apportionment using principle component analysis (PCA, a receptor model) was carried out in three phases (phase 1:2005–2009, phase 2: 2010–2014, and phase 3: 2015–2019). Thereafter, future prediction has been carried out with a uni-variant statistical model, Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA). The IGP along with Odisha falls under red zone, western and central Indian states with few south-eastern states fall under orange zone as can be seen in Fig 1a.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Major air sources of pollution in vulnerable and highly vulnerable states in India.

Over Punjab and Haryana, the major aerosol pollution sources in Phase 1 were vehicular emissions (VE), which got dominated by crop residue burning (CRB) in the later phases. Vehicular emissions (VE) in Uttar Pradesh and solid fuel burning (SFB) in Bihar dominated in all the phases. For West Bengal, in phase 1, VE remained the top source which changed to SFB in recent times. Jharkhand, Odisha, Chhattisgarh, Madhya Pradesh, and Gujarat have coal-based thermal power plants (TPP) as the major sources of air pollution in all three phases. In southern states (Telangana, Karnataka, Kerala, and Andhra Pradesh) VE, and in north-eastern India (Assam, Meghalaya, and Tripura) open biomass burning was the major source of aerosol pollution in all three phases.

State-wise future prediction (2023) of AOD using ARIMA

IGP states show a 2–20% increase in AOD at the end of 2023, with the highest increase in Punjab. However, they would remain as a red zone in the near future too. Maharashtra, Chhattisgarh and Madhya Pradesh show a 7–17% increase in AOD and will shift from the orange to the red zone (Figure 1 (b)). A very high increase of 22–24 % has been predicted for Karnataka and Kerala and shift from less vulnerable to vulnerable zones (Figure 1(c)).

Proposed recommendations for reducing the vulnerability of some states

Simple linear regressions were carried out between the AOD and the generation capacity of the power plants from “Carbon Brief”, for the period of 2005–2019 for six states dominated by TTPE for proposed recommendation. We proposed that if we reduce 13, 5, 10, 7, 10, and 8 GW of the existing thermal power plants in the states of Odisha, Jharkhand, Madhya Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Maharashtra, and Gujarat respectively we can bring down the AOD and move to the blue (relatively safe) zone.

Figure 1 (a) Zones w.r.t to AOD mean (2005-2019) and state-wise major sources (b) percentage change of AOD in 2023 w.r.t to 2019 and (c) paradigm shift in vulnerability in 2019 and 2023

CONCLUSIONS

Coal-fired thermal power plants were the major sources of air pollution in most of the western, central, and eastern states of India. In IGP, solid fuel burning crop residue burning, and vehicular emission were the major sources of aerosol pollution. In most of the south Indian states, vehicular emission was the dominant source. 5-13 GW thermal power plant emission can reduce aerosol pollution to a safer limit in those states that are dominated by TPPE.

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LONG-TERM TREND OF AIRBORNE PARTICULATE MATTER (PM₁₀ AND PM_{2.5}) AT TROMBAY, MUMBAI INDIA

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Keywords: PARTICULATE MATTER, PM₁₀, AIR QUALITY, LONG TERM TREND.

INTRODUCTION

Aerosol monitoring is crucial for assessing air quality, protecting human health, understanding climate dynamics, and managing environmental impacts. It enables informed decision-making, policy formulation, and effective measures to address the challenges posed by aerosol particles in the atmosphere. Based on the aerodynamic diameter of particles, PMs are classified into PM_{2.5} (PM with an aerodynamic diameter < 2.5 mm), PM₁₀ (PM with an aerodynamic diameter < 10 mm), and TSP (total suspended particles) (Kim et al., 2010). PM exists as a complex mixture of extremely small particles and liquid droplets including acids (such as nitrates and sulfates), metals, organic chemicals, etc. The extent of its pollution in the atmosphere can thus be affected by a number of variables including the number, size, shape, surface area, chemical composition, solubility, and origin (Ahmad et al., 2015). Long-term monitoring allows the identification of trends and patterns in aerosol concentrations, sizes, and compositions. This helps researchers understand how aerosol emissions change over time due to various factors such as industrial activities, urbanization, and climate variations. As aerosols play a significant role in climate dynamics by influencing the Earth's radiative balance (Barnpadimos et al., 2012). Long-term data on aerosol properties contribute to climate models, aiding in the accurate prediction of climate changes and variability. Over time, changes in aerosol levels can impact air quality and human health. Overall, long-term aerosol monitoring is essential for understanding the complex dynamics between aerosols, the atmosphere, human health, and the environment. It supports informed decision-making, helps address emerging environmental and health challenges, and contributes to the development of effective policies and strategies for a sustainable future.

METHODS

Mumbai, undergoing rapid and advanced industrialization and urbanization, is anticipated to have an adverse impact on the environment, including the quality of ambient air. Over a decade from January 2010 to December 2019, atmospheric aerosol samples were systematically collected. The collection frequency amounted to at least twice a week for a duration of 24 hours, resulting in an annual tally of approximately 104 measurements, aligning with CPCB guidelines. The sampling took place at an elevation of 20 meters above ground level within a sheltered structure, aimed at mitigating extreme weather effects while ensuring unobstructed airflow to prevent wake influences. Glass microfiber filters (EPM 2000) were chosen due to their commendable air particulate retention efficiency, coupled with low pressure drop, high resistance to clogging, and minimal moisture-induced alkalinity. PM₁₀ samples were collected using respirable dust sampler (Envirotech APM 460 NL), while PM_{2.5} samples were collected using WINS based sampler (Envirotech, APM 550).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

All the data of particulate matter concentration i.e. PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} were treated statistically summarized in annual and monthly averages to know their trend over the study period. The mean concentrations of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} for the entire study period were found to be 86 ± 30.5 and $52 \pm 18.2 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, respectively. Fig. 1 A) and B) shows the trend in PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} observed at monitoring station between 2010 and 2019, respectively. Statistically significant decreasing trend ($p < 0.001$, $r^2 = 0.68$) is estimated for the annual average PM₁₀ concentration during study period. The maximum annual average concentration of PM₁₀ is estimated in 2011 which is exhibited 54.6% higher than the lowest one for 2019 ($68.65 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). For all over the monitoring period, annual averages of PM₁₀ were found to be exceeding the national ambient air quality standards (NAAQS) values stipulated by central pollution control board (CPCB) of India which is $60 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$.

Fig 1. Trends of PM₁₀ (A) and PM_{2.5} (B); and their ratios (C) during sample period at study area. The PM_{2.5} to PM₁₀ ratios were computed for all samples collected, exhibiting values spanning from 0.39 to 0.80, with a mean of 0.61 ± 0.06 . **Fig. 1 C)** illustrates a whisker plot showcasing the time series of PM_{2.5} to PM₁₀ ratios for the study site. The mean ratios remained relatively consistent throughout the sampling duration, except for 2015, when a slightly elevated ratio was observed compared to other years. This divergence could potentially stem from sporadic events like dust storms and fires in the nearby dumping yard vicinity in the year 2015.

CONCLUSIONS

Annual averages of PM₁₀ concentration were found to be above the national ambient air quality standards (NAAQS) and WHO air quality guideline values. Annual average concentrations of PM_{2.5} indicates decreasing trend specifically after 2014 AD at the study site. PM_{2.5} to PM₁₀ ratios indicating there are both fine and coarse particulate matter sources around study area.

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EFFECT OF EXSICCATION ON THE PARTICULATE AND CHEMICAL EMISSIONS FROM VEHICULAR EXHAUST

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Keywords: VCCI, PAHS, TOTAL CARBON, DENUDER, PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION

Introduction

Vehicular emission is one of the major anthropogenic sources of aerosol pollution. Due to rapidly growing urbanization, the vehicular population all over the world is on the surge (González et al., 2018), resulting in elevated levels of traffic related pollutants like carbon monoxide, nitrogen oxides, hydrocarbons, and particulates (Fecht et al., 2016). Apart from these pollutants, the automobile tail pipe emissions also majorly consist soot (black carbon), some organic compounds (Agarwal and Mustafi, 2021), and moisture. The presence of moisture plays an important role in the physical as well as chemical characteristics of aerosols emitted from the vehicular exhaust. The effect of presence or exsiccation of moisture on the emitted particulates and organic compounds is an important aspect of vehicular pollution management that needs to be effectively studied. In this work, the vehicular emission's particulate size distribution was studied and the effect of removal of moisture (exsiccation) on this size distribution as well as on the emission of carbon and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in the vehicular exhaust was determined. The size distribution was carried out using variable configuration cascade impactor (VCCI). Additionally, a moisture denuder made of activated silica gel was designed and used to study the effect of moisture removal.

Materials and Methods

Different models of diesel and petrol vehicles were chosen for the study (4 each). Using a Variable configuration cascade impactor (VCCI), the vehicles' exhaust was collected over 15-minute intervals on glass fiber filter papers. The filter papers were dried, weighed, and desiccated prior to each sampling. In a subsequent experiment, a Moisture denuder made of activated silica gel was introduced between the tailpipe and VCCI to capture moisture. The setup involved a funnel-shaped sampler near the vehicle's exhaust pipe, directing the exhaust through the moisture denuder. This was followed by a VCCI for size fraction measurement and an Anderson pump to maintain airflow (Tiwari et al., 2013). Glass fiber filter papers (EPM 2000, Whatman) served as both particle collection surfaces and backup filter in the cascade impactor. The impactor was maintained at an airflow rate of 10 lpm, with each vehicle type approximately accounting for 0.15 cubic meters of air. The vehicles were maintained in ignited condition with alternate sessions of idling and accelerating every 2 minutes. Analysis of organic (OC) and total carbon (TC) was conducted using a TC-TN analyser while the analysis of PAHs was carried out by high pressure liquid chromatography (HPLC).

Results and Discussion

The PM loading observed in diesel vehicle emission were bimodal while the petrol vehicle exhausts showed a trimodal distribution over the studied particle size range as shown in fig 1. The maximum PM load was observed in size 11.2-15.1 μm fraction in diesel vehicles (150 mg/m^3) while it was maximum in $>21.3 \mu\text{m}$ size fraction in petrol vehicles (180 mg/m^3). The effect of exsiccation with moisture denuder was also clearly visible as the PM loading reduced by about 48% in diesel vehicles whereas it reduced by about 40% in petrol vehicles. The maximum PM load with use of moisture denuder was observed in size 0.75-1.13 μm fraction in diesel vehicles (65 mg/m^3) while it was maximum in same size fraction for petrol vehicles as that of without denuder i.e. $>21.3 \mu\text{m}$ size fraction (98 mg/m^3).

Fig 1. Size distribution of total particulate matter loading in diesel and petrol vehicle exhaust

Table 1 shows the effect of exsiccation on organic and total carbon emission from the vehicular exhaust. It was observed that there is nearly no difference in OC concentration with and without denuder. However, TC concentration reduced significantly with denuder in both diesel (40%) as well as petrol (18%) vehicle exhausts.

Table 1: Effect of moisture removal on Carbon concentration in the exhaust emissions

Size Fraction	DIESEL Vehicles						Petrol Vehicles					
	Organic Carbon			Total Carbon			Organic Carbon			Total Carbon		
	Without Denuder	With Denuder	Difference	Without Denuder	With Denuder	Difference	Without Denuder	With Denuder	Difference	Without Denuder	With Denuder	Difference
<0.1	20.9	17.6	3.4	27.8	23.1	4.7	23.3	21.2	2.1	32.8	26.7	6.0
0.1-0.3	5.1	5.8	-0.8	13.3	6.7	6.6	5.1	6.1	-1.0	9.3	8.9	0.4
0.3-0.5	1.0	2.0	-1.0	9.1	5.1	4.0	3.8	4.7	-0.9	9.6	6.2	3.4
0.5-0.75	3.9	1.6	2.4	11.4	5.9	5.5	3.5	5.8	-2.3	9.4	7.7	1.8
0.75-1.13	4.7	4.5	0.2	12.0	7.5	4.4	6.2	5.3	0.9	7.7	9.1	-1.5
1.13-2.23	5.7	4.5	1.2	12.7	6.9	5.8	6.2	8.0	-1.8	14.0	10.8	3.2
2.23-5.47	5.3	4.5	0.8	9.6	5.2	4.4	3.6	4.0	-0.4	13.6	7.5	6.0
5.47-7.38	4.3	4.8	-0.4	10.4	5.8	4.6	8.8	6.8	1.9	9.7	8.5	1.2
7.38-11.2	3.6	4.6	-1.0	10.2	5.8	4.4	5.9	5.7	0.2	9.1	8.0	1.2
11.2-15.1	3.5	2.6	0.8	9.7	6.0	3.7	6.4	4.4	2.0	8.6	7.5	1.1
15.1-21.3	2.6	4.2	-1.6	9.1	5.4	3.7	7.0	5.9	1.1	10.6	8.6	2.0
>21.3	6.5	5.1	1.4	11.3	5.9	5.4	6.2	7.1	-1.0	11.2	8.7	2.5
Total	67.0	61.7	5.3	146.6	89.2	57.4	85.8	85.0	0.8	145.7	118.4	27.3

About 17 PAHs congeners were analysed by HPLC in the backup filters. The total PAHs concentrations were as high as 27 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in diesel exhaust while in Petrol it were about 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. With moisture denuder the reduction in total PAHs was about 50% in diesel exhaust and about 18% in petrol exhausts.

Conclusion

It was observed overall that exsiccation result in reduction of particulate emission by about 40-50% while the Carbon and PAHs emissions also reduced by about 18- 50%. It can be concluded that exsiccation of exhaust gases with silica gel can reduce the overall vehicular emissions significantly.

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TRACING THE DELICATE BALANCE: QUANTIFYING PM_{2.5} WASHOUT PATTERNS IN DELHI'S ATMOSPHERE

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Keywords: PARTICULATE MATTER, PRECIPITATION, RECOVERY, WASHOUT.

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution, particularly the presence of fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) with a diameter of 2.5 micrometres or less, poses a serious threat to public health and the general well-being of urban areas. Delhi, India stands out among the cities dealing with high PM_{2.5} levels as a dramatic example of the difficulties in managing air quality. The complex interaction of air pollutants with meteorological elements, particularly rainfall, is crucial in determining the dynamics of PM_{2.5} concentrations (Jung et al., 2022). The process of "washout," in which precipitation efficiently scavenges suspended particles from the air and temporarily reduces pollution, is a crucial method by which harmful pollutants are removed from the environment.

It is essential to comprehend the complex relationship between rainfall and PM_{2.5} concentrations when developing management measures for air quality. This study embarks on a meticulous exploration of this connection by quantifying the phenomenon of PM_{2.5} washout across Delhi.

This study intends to completely analyse the links between PM_{2.5} concentration soon before rainfall and the resultant percentage of washout, as well as the correlations between rainfall intensity, duration, and the washout percentage. The study also aims to determine the recovery time needed for PM_{2.5} levels to reach pre-rain levels.

METHODS

The study used two major datasets to calculate the amount of PM_{2.5} washout across Delhi. The Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) provided values of PM_{2.5} that were averaged across periods from 15 to 30 minutes for the first dataset. The second dataset contained data from the Global Precipitation Measurement (GPM), collected at 30-minute intervals. Data between the 5th and 95th percentiles were taken into consideration to concentrate on representative PM_{2.5} levels. Instances of no precipitation were replaced with NaN values as part of the preprocessing of rainfall data. The range of rainfall data was also limited to the fifth to the ninetieth percentiles. Finding the episodes of rainfall and determining the times that corresponded was the first step. After that, for each rain event, the PM_{2.5} concentration immediately before rain (30 minutes prior) and after rain (30 minutes thereafter) was retrieved. The "washout amount" (Δ), or the difference between these two PM_{2.5} values, was computed. The percentage of washout was calculated as [% washout = (Δ / PM_{2.5} just before rain) * 100%]. The range of PM_{2.5} readings immediately before a downpour were divided into five uniform bins to examine potential links. Then, a thorough analysis was carried out to see whether there was any connection between these bins and the associated washout %. In a similar manner, the range of rainfall values was divided into five uniform bins, enabling an analysis of possible connections with the washout %. With the aid of this methodical methodology, a thorough investigation of the complex interactions between PM_{2.5} concentrations and rainfall characteristics was made possible, providing new information on the dynamics of PM_{2.5} washout throughout the Delhi region.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

This concise figure outlines the monthly trends in rainfall intensity (mm/hr) and PM_{2.5} concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) over the depicted timeframe. The x-axis denotes the months, while the left y-axis corresponds to rainfall and the right y-axis corresponds to PM_{2.5} concentration.

The blue line graph tracks the fluctuations in rainfall, demonstrating peaks during periods of heavier rain and troughs during drier spells. On the right side, the orange line graph illustrates the changes in PM_{2.5} levels, with spikes indicating elevated concentrations and dips representing lower levels.

Figure 1. Variation of rainfall and PM_{2.5} over months.

The figure below succinctly presents the relationship between washout effectiveness and three key influencing factors: initial PM (Particulate Matter) concentration before rainfall, rainfall duration, and rainfall intensity. The representation showcases various impacts of the washout process.

Figure 2. Influence of initial PM before rainfall, rainfall duration, and intensity on washout efficiency.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the study emphasizes the importance of these factors in understanding particle removal during rainfall events, crucial for effective air quality management and environmental planning. This insight aids in advancing our understanding of the complex dynamics between precipitation and airborne particulate matter.

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ASSESSMENT OF AIR QUALITY BENEFITS IN TERMS OF PARTICULATE MATTER DUE TO PROPOSED TRANSPORT-SECTOR CONTROL INTERVENTIONS IN PUNE CITY

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Keywords: Vehicular pollution, PM, Control strategies.

INTRODUCTION

The transportation sector in Pune city has observed an exponential growth in last few decades and the number of vehicles on road has been rising at an alarming rate. With ever increasing demand for transportation, the transportation sector in Pune city has been one of the main causes of air pollution and climate change. Road transport (TRAN) and the road dust re-suspension (RDST) are the two largest contributors to city-level PM_{2.5} (TRAN: 39% and RDST: 23%) and PM₁₀ (TRAN: 20% and RDST: 41%) emissions. Pune administration has recently introduced a variety of emission control measures to reduce vehicular emissions, but the quantification of air quality benefits is very limited. We conducted a systematic review of vehicular emission control efforts and benefits in terms of air quality improvements for future years (2025 and 2030) in Pune city.

METHODS

We developed three hypothetical emission scenarios namely: No-further control (NFC), low-ambition (LAS) and high-ambition (HAS) to include eight major policies and technology considerations such as implementation of Bharat Stage (BS) – VI standards, roll-out of Ethanol blended Gasoline (E20), increased penetration of Electric Vehicle (EV), Non-Motorised Transport (NMT), use of Mass Rapid Transit System (MRTS), improved public transport (PTI), increased shared mobility (SHMO) and implementation of High Capacity Mass Transit Corridor (HCMTR). The changes in PM emissions for three defined scenarios and subsequent impact on ambient air quality were calculated following a scientific approach. The adopted methodology mainly involved quantification of the emissions and subsequent AERMOD dispersion modelling analysis to understand the air quality benefits achievable under three emission control scenarios in Pune city.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The tail-pipe particulate matter (PM) emissions reduction in Pune city under three hypothetical scenarios is illustrated in Figure 1. In 2030, there will be advancements on the technology and alternative fuels front. E20 fuelled vehicles will be running on roads, along with a substantial increase in BS-VI and electric vehicles (EV). The combined effect of different control options could result in a significant decrease in tail-pipe PM emissions i.e. 21.2% and 30.2% in low (LAS) and high (HAS) ambition scenarios, respectively. The tail-pipe emissions and road dust re-suspension are inter-linked and are dependent upon the vehicle kilometres travelled (VKT). We also estimated the potential PM emission reductions due to VKT reduction under three control scenarios for future years 2025 and 2030. Figure 2 (a) and (b) show the combined effect of control measures on vehicular (VEE) and re-suspended road dust (RDST) on PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ emissions (TPY) in Pune city, respectively. In 2025 the PM_{2.5} emissions are projected to reduce by 14 and 21 per cent in LAS and HAS, respectively whereas in 2030, the PM_{2.5} emissions are expected to decrease by 27 and 39% in LAS and HAS, respectively compared to respective NFCs. Similarly, the PM₁₀ emissions are also expected to decline significantly in 2025 (17% in LAS and 25%HAS) and 2030 (29% in LAS and 43% in HAS).

We used AERMOD dispersion model to quantify the air quality benefits at selected monitoring locations in Pune city. The AERMOD predicted annual average concentrations of PM_{2.5} at three selected locations ranged from 29.1 to 50.1 µg/m³ during 2030. In 2030, combined reduction of transport and road dust emissions showed significant reduction in PM_{2.5} (26.9 to 30.7%) and PM₁₀ (28.2 to 38.1%) concentrations at selected locations in Pune city.

Figure 1. Projected control intervention wise exhaust particulate matter (PM) emissions (vertical bars) for LAS and HAS in 2030. The lines with markers show control intervention wise percent change (secondary y-axis)

Figure 2. Changes in PM_{2.5} (a) and PM₁₀ (b) emissions from vehicular exhaust and re-suspended road dust with NFC, LAS and HAS in 2025 and 2030. The numbers on top of bars indicate potential percent reduction compared to respective NFC scenarios.

CONCLUSIONS

Our work highlights an important fact that, even the most aggressive vehicular control measures may not be able to meet the annual average air quality standard for PM₁₀ i.e. 60 µg/m³, at selected locations and a multi-sector and multi-scale approach is needed, which prioritises the reduction in local emissions within Pune city.

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IMPACT OF BIOMASS BURNING ON AEROSOL PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OVER A SEMI-ARID STATION, ANANTAPUR

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Keywords: Black Carbon, Biomass Burning, Anthropogenic Sources, Semi-Arid Region

ABSTRACT

The study analyzes the results of a case study on the impact of an extensive grassland fire on the physical of aerosols in the month of February, 2023 by using In-situ observations (Aethalometer) at a semi-arid station, Anantapur in southern peninsular India. In a typical diurnal pattern, there is a gradual build up in the black carbon (BC) mass concentrations from the morning and a sharp peak occurs between 07:00 and 09:00 local time (LT), almost an hour after the local sunrise. The diurnal variation of BC aerosol shows sharp morning and evening peaks associated to the local anthropogenic activities and boundary layer dynamics. It is observed that BC mass concentration starts increasing and the increase are quite substantial from 14:00 to 16:30 hours during the burning days. This is in sharp contrast to the normal diurnal pattern seen on the previous days. It is noticed that during afternoon hours (14:00 to 16:30) of the burning days ($\sim 10.11 \pm 4.75 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) is almost 5 times higher than that of the normal days ($\sim 1.86 \pm 0.16 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). The averaged BC mass concentration at 880 nm increased during biomass burning days is about to be $3.99 \pm 0.61 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ compared to normal days ($2.45 \pm 0.23 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). Moreover, the percentage change BC during burning days was approximately 63% higher than that of on any other days of that period.

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IMPACT OF COVID LOCKDOWN ON AEROSOL PROPERTIES: INSIGHTS INTO VERTICAL DISTRIBUTION, SUBTYPE, AND SECONDARY PARTICLE FORMATION

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Keywords: AEROSOL AND AIR QUALITY, COVID-19, CALIPSO, SECONDARY PARTICLE.

INTRODUCTION

This study investigates the effects of COVID-19 lockdown on aerosol characteristics in the north Indian atmosphere, focusing on three distinct phases (PI, PII, and PIII) in 2020, in comparison with the years 2017-2019. The study employs a combination of remote sensing observations, reanalysis datasets, and ground-based measurements to examine the optical properties of aerosols and their natural and anthropogenic subtypes.

METHODS

The investigation involves the selection of two distinct geographical areas for comparative analysis: Delhi/NCR (DN) situated in the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP), and Nainital (NT) located in the Central Himalayas (CH). The research employs strict lockdown measures as a framework, which resulted in a significant reduction in daily average PM_{2.5} concentrations ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) in the northern Indian region. The study evaluates various aerosol components such as BC, OC, dust, and SO₄ levels to understand their behaviour during different lockdown phases. Vertical analysis is conducted to assess changes in aerosol characteristics using particulate Extinction Coefficient (EC), Depolarization Ratio (PDR), Colour Ratio (PCR) across different altitudes, with a specific focus on the CH.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

During Phase II of the lockdown, the study identifies noteworthy patterns: absorbing aerosols such as BC, OC, and dust display substantial reductions, while SO₄ levels increase, signifying the prevalence of scattering mode aerosols. The vertical analysis further unveils remarkable reductions in aerosol content (EC) across various altitudes in both DN and NT areas. This decline is more pronounced in the foothills of the CH. The study also reveals altitude-dependent shifts in the particle size distribution, with fine particles being prevalent at higher altitudes in the NT region and larger particles demonstrating increased asphericity near the surface in DN, due to mixing and hygroscopic growth. The investigation uncovers intriguing insights into aerosol behaviour during different lockdown phases. Notably, the shifts in aerosol subtype occurrences during PII are highlighted, with dust/polluted dust frequencies varying across altitudes due to boundary layer processes.

Figure 1. Impact of different primary and secondary air quality indicators with $PM_{2.5}$ in northern India before, during and after the COVID lockdown. Relative change in averaged concentration of NO_2 , $PM_{2.5}$, O_3 , and $PM_{2.5}/CO$ during PII concerning PI (a, d) and PIII concerning PI (e, f). The time series of normalized ratios representing $PM_{2.5}$, NO_2 , and O_3 are presented in the lower panel (i). The normalized ratios of all components are calculated using the time series scaled with the mean of the pre-lockdown phase (PI), and daily variation is eliminated with the lowess smoothing technique. Note: The solid line denotes variation of different parameters in NT, while the dashed line represents DN, while grey shading in PIII represents an episodic event.

CONCLUSIONS

The study indicates that despite the relative reduction in primary aerosols like NO_2 , there isn't a substantial decrease in PM concentrations. Specifically, Phase III of the lockdown unveils significant enhancements in ozone (O_3) levels, particularly in the Indo-Gangetic Plain and Central Himalayan foothill regions, attributed to secondary particle formation (Mahato et al. 2020) and Stratosphere and Troposphere Exchange (STE) events. This emphasizes the intricate interplay between aerosol dynamics and chemistry and underscores the importance of comprehensive chemical models to effectively resolve aerosol components.

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**LONG TERM AIR POLLUTANT TRENDS OVER AN URBAN LOCATION (PUNE) IN INDIA:
EFFECTS OF METEOROLOGY AND EMISSIONS**

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Keywords: Air Quality, Meteorological normalisation, Air pollutants, long-term trends.

INTRODUCTION

Growing economy and rapid industrialisation and with the expansion of urban centres, air pollution is a growing concern in most areas of the world. The amount of air pollutants in the atmosphere at a particular location and time is based on the emissions, meteorology and various physicochemical conditions (Walker et al., 2022). To estimate the trends of the air pollutants statistical based models, prove essentially in complementing the chemical transport models (Grange and Carslaw 2019). Many previous studies have established that removal of impact of meteorology on the air pollutant trends largely helps in analysing the causes of the reduction or increase of the pollutant. Long term atmospheric trends have been assessed by various statistical models like random forest models, boosted regression trees, generalised additive models etc. In this study, the data of various air pollutants (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, O₃, NO₂ and CO) have been analyzed for a period of 9 years. The random forest (RF) method was used to separate out the impact of meteorology on the long-term trend. This is further beneficial in the mitigation strategies.

METHODS

This work includes the air pollutant datasets obtained from the System of Air Quality and Weather Forecasting & Research (SAFAR) Air Quality Monitoring Stations over an urban location Pune. The meteorological parameters data from the Automated weather stations. Hourly dataset of PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂ and O₃ was considered along with the meteorological parameters like wind speed (ws), wind direction (wd) air temperature (T), Relative humidity (RH) (SAFAR AQMS and AWS dataset), total precipitation, boundary layer height, surface pressure, solar radiation (ERA5 reanalysis data). Data for the years 2014 to 2022 was analysed to identify the perturbations from the varying meteorological conditions. A machine learning methodology based on a random forest (RF) methodology has been used to calculate the deweathered hourly concentrations. The RF method was based on the rmweather (Grange et al., 2018) R package and the ranger (Wright and Ziegler) R package.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The 9 year (2014-2022) average concentrations of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ over Pune indicated that it exceeded the annual average limit defined by the National Ambient Air Quality Standards. The trend analysis of the air pollutants before and after the process of deweathering has been analysed. The method used to identify the trend of the air pollutants is the TheilSen trend estimator. It is observed that prior to the normalisation, the trends obtained are not significant, whereas after deweathering the data the trends obtained are significant at p<0.01,0.05,0.001. The PM_{2.5} concentrations indicate an increasing trend at 0.41 µg/m³/year whereas the PM₁₀ concentration indicated a significant decrease of 2.33 µg/m³/year. Similarly, NO₂ also indicated an increase however O₃ concentration indicated a decreasing trend. By using the random forest method of deweathering the air pollutant data, the meteorological effect on the dataset is removed. Thus, the trend obtained after performing this is only a result of the emissions of the air pollutant.

Figure 1. The plot shows meteorologically normalised monthly mean concentration (blue curve) of $PM_{2.5}$. The solid red line shows the trend estimate and the dashed red lines show the 95% confidence intervals for the trend based on resampling methods. The overall trend is shown at the top-left as 0.41 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) per year and the 95% confidence intervals in the slope from 0.04 to 1.06 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3/\text{year}$. The ‘*’ show that the trend is significant to the 0.01 level.

CONCLUSIONS

The meteorological normalisation technique using RF was helpful in obtaining less uncertain trend estimates of the air pollutants as compared to the standard method. The $PM_{2.5}$ concentration indicated an increase in the concentration after the removal of the meteorological parameters, which indicates that the emissions play the most significant role in the increase. Thus, the method of deweathering the air pollutant data, helps in identifying whether it is the emission sources that play a role in modulating the pollutant concentration over a long-term period. This thereby helps in devising mitigation strategies for particular location.

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**AEROSOL & CLOUD INDUCED CHANGES IN SURFACE IRRADIANCE OVER DIFFERENT
TERRAINS IN PENINSULAR INDIA**

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Keywords: AOD, Solar irradiance, MFRSR, Western Ghats

INTRODUCTION

Over the Indian sub-continent, long-term surface observations revealed that aerosols and clouds play an important role in reducing the incoming solar radiation at the surface called solar dimming (Padmakumari et al., 2010). Western Ghat (WG) mountains in the peninsular India run parallel to west coast of India in the north-south direction and play an important role in distribution of monsoon rainfall on the windward (WW) and leeward (LW) sides of WG. In the present study, the high temporal variability of solar irradiance in the high altitude windward terrain is studied in conjunction with similar measurements collected at a low altitude terrain on the leeward side, thus representing two contrasting terrains falling under less pollution and heavy rainfall, and more pollution and less rainfall zones, respectively.

METHODS

Data used is shortwave Global Horizontal Irradiance (GHI) obtained from a ground-based Multi Filter Rotating Shadowband Radiometer (MFRSR). It is operated at a high altitude station Mahabaleshwar (17.92° N, 73.66° E, ~ 1348m above MSL) located on the WW side of the WG (WWG) during the period May 2018 to June 2023. Aerosol Optical Depths (AOD) for total, fine & coarse modes is retrieved from MFRSR data. For the same period, GHI data from a pyranometer operated at another station Pune (18.52° N; 73.85° E, 560 m above MSL) located in the LW side of the WG (LWG) is also used to study its characteristic features in comparison with that of Mahabaleshwar.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Figure 1 (a, b) shows the diurnal (day average) variability of GHI for clear as well as cloudy days at the stations WWG and LWG. It is noticed that, on a diurnal scale, the fluctuations in clear sky day GHI is higher than cloudy sky day GHI, except on a few occasions. Also, clear day GHI displayed small variability within the month/season as compared to cloudy days. At WWG, the day average GHI maxima reached up to 710 W/m² during pre-monsoon, while at LWG the maximum reached up to 600 W/m², and the average clear days difference between these two stations is ~ 88 W/m². The higher values of clear sky GHI over WWG as compared to LLW reveal that the atmosphere at WWG is cleaner and more transparent as compared to LLG. Pune being an urban area with dense population has high AOD as compared to WWG and also showed increasing trend (Bhaskar et al., 2017). Thus, the reduction in GHI at LLG is a clear indication of solar dimming effect. While cloudy sky GHI still showed large variability at both the stations with minimum values during overcast and large fluctuations during partial clouds. The monthly mean variability shown in Figure 1(c) also reveals higher irradiance values during dry months and lower values during monsoon at WWG as compared to Pune.

The diurnal variability of total AOD (only clear days) at WWG (Figure 1d) shows a maximum value going upto 0.4. While, fine and coarse mode AODs varied up to 0.3 and less than 0.2, respectively. Thus, fine mode AOD is dominant throughout the dry period as compared to coarse mode AOD. At Pune the AOD varies from 0.4 to 0.8.

Figure 1: Diurnal variability of GHI at (a) WWG, (b) LWG and (c) Monthly mean variability of GHI at WWG (red line) and LWG (blue line). (d) Diurnal variability of surface retrieved AOD (500nm) for total, fine and coarse modes.

CONCLUSION

Both aerosols and clouds play a significant role in the variability of GHI leading to solar dimming at the surface, while clouds dominate short term fluctuations even exceeding the clear sky values. In highly polluted regions, there is a possibility that boundary layer aerosols could offset the maximum irradiance. In the dry months, the number of clear sky days decreased, and cloudy sky days increased at both the locations due to unusual synoptic weather conditions. The clear sky days GHI average at WWG is ~ 88 W/m² higher than LWG, indicating a clean and transparent atmosphere at high altitudes and suitable for harvesting renewable solar energy as compared to regions or places which are more polluted, susceptible to frequent dust storms, forest fires or biomass burning. Hence, WWG may be used as a reference station for such comparisons.

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AEROSOLS OVER INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN AND THEIR IMPACT ON THE HIMALAYAN GLACIERS: A LONG-TERM STUDY

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Keywords: Aerosols, Glacier, Indo-Gangetic Plain, Himalayas.

INTRODUCTION

The Himalayan region has the third-largest ice mass on earth outside the polar region at the forefront of climate change. Since the early 1990s, human activities have played a significant role in global glacier loss, potentially accounting for up to 70% of the observed decline (Marzeion *et al.*, 2014). Himalayan glaciers are of immense significance as a crucial water resource for the transboundary rivers in Asia, freshwater originating from these glaciers supports the livelihoods of 1.4 billion people (Immerzeel *et al.*, 2010). The accelerated melting of Himalayan glaciers and the sustainable management of water resources are the most important concerns for society, in recent times. The accelerated melting is connected to two factors: the presence of light-absorbing particles (LAPs), such as black carbon (BC) and dust in the atmosphere which cause a darkening effect, and the regional warming resulting from greenhouse gas emissions (Ramanathan and Carmichael, 2008). The deposition of absorbing aerosols in the snow surface amplifies the absorption of solar radiation, resulting in the darkening of the snow surface, this darkening reduces the snow albedo, leading to an accelerating rate of snowmelt (Flanner *et al.*, 2007). Himalayan glaciers are surrounded by many large cities and tourist stations and also the highly polluted Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP), which is the major emission source of many types of aerosols (black carbon, dust, organic carbon) and transportation of aerosols in the Himalayan region is a serious threat for the Himalayan glaciers. The purpose of this work is to investigate the trend of aerosol rise over the Himalayan glacial region and the impact of the highly urbanized and polluted regions like the Indo-Gangetic Plain on the change of climate over the Himalayas.

METHODS

Aerosol optical depth (AOD), obtained from the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS), a remote sensing satellite onboard the Terra and Aqua satellites launched in 1999 and 2002 respectively, was derived using combined dark target and deep blue algorithms from Aqua's daily level 3, $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ AOD the recent collection of 6.1; C6.1 (MYD08) data spanning 2000 (February) to 2022. Differential AODs were extracted from monthly data of the Modern-Era Retrospective Analysis for Research and Applications (MERRA-2) over the 1990-2022 timeframe. MERRA-2 utilizes version 5.12.4 of the GEOS atmospheric data assimilation system, employing a grid resolution of $0.5^\circ \times 0.625^\circ$ and comprising 72 hybrid vertical layers spanning from the surface up to 0.01 hPa. The analysis of long-term trends over the Himalayan and IGP was conducted using the well-established Mann-Kendall test. The slope of the trend was determined using the Senslope estimator.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

AOD was much higher in the recent decade (2010-2019) compared to the previous decade (2000-2009) in both IGP as well as in the Himalayan region (Figure 1). In the latest decade (2010-2019) the eastern part of the IGP showed a higher AOD value (0.6-1.0) compared to the AOD (0.4-0.7) value in the previous decade (2000-2009) as depicted in Figure 1. A similar type increase in AOD was also observed over the eastern part of the Himalayas in the last decade. It is noteworthy that this part of the Himalayas has a comparatively higher AOD than the western and central Himalayas. In the entire study period, in the winter time, AOD was higher (0.6-1.0) in the central and eastern parts of IGP. However, in western IGP, AOD is much higher (0.6-1.0) in the post-monsoon season as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1 Mean AOD over the Himalayan region and Indo-Gangetic plain for a period (a) 2000-2009 and (b) 2010-2019.

Figure 2 Mean AOD over the Himalayan and IGP region between the years 2000-2019 in different seasons. a. pre-monsoon b. post-monsoon c. winter.

CONCLUSIONS

Mean AOD is comparatively much higher in the last decade than the previous decade in the IGP region as well as in the Himalayan region. AOD is highest in both the eastern part of IGP and the eastern Himalayan region. Our analysis shows that with respect to AOD, the eastern part of the Himalayas is more vulnerable, especially in the premonsoon season however, in the IGP region central and eastern part is more vulnerable specifically in the winter season.

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ROLE OF POLYCYCLIC AROMATIC HYDROCARBONS (PAHs) AND THEIR DERIVATIVES IN PM_{2.5} OXIDATIVE POTENTIAL (OP) DURING FIRE CRACKERS BURNING

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Keywords: OXIDATIVE POTENTIAL(OP), PAHs, N-PAHs, O-PAHs, PM_{2.5}

INTRODUCTION

Increasing aerosol concentration and complex aerosol chemistry have become a matter of concern for both the environment and humans. In addition, emissions during fire cracker burning events like Diwali directly affect the atmosphere and increase health-related issues. Various epidemiological studies show the mechanism of health-related issues (like cardiopulmonary morbidity and mortality) due to exposure to particulate matter (PM) and associated species (Simkhovich et al., 2008; Yu et al., 2022). Oxidative Potential (OP, ability to produce Reactive Oxygen Species, ROS) is the widely accepted mechanism that explains health-related issues in humans due to PM-related species. Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) are ubiquitous organic pollutants that possess carcinogenic and mutagenic properties for humans. These get adsorbed or absorbed on suspended PM, enter the human body via inhalation, and act as a catalyst to produce ROS in-situ. The toxicity of PAHs increases with the increase in molecular mass and derivatization. Their nitrated (N-PAHs) and oxygenated (O-PAHs) derivatives are much more toxic in comparison to their parent PAHs and show higher OP (Libalova et al., 2018). There are various studies reported in the literature explaining the relation of PAHs and aerosol OP, but there is no study present that explains the role of N- and O-PAHs on aerosol OP during a fire cracker burning event. This study was planned to determine the aerosol OP due to the emission of PAHs and their derivatives during a fire cracker burning event in Ahmedabad, India.

METHODS

PM_{2.5} samples (24 hrs) were collected using a high-volume air sampler from an urban site at Physical Research Laboratory, Ahmedabad during November 2020. Organic species in PM_{2.5} samples were extracted in the mixture of dichloromethane and n-hexane in 4:1 ratio. Further, 16 priority PAHs, 13 Nitro-PAHs and 10 Oxy-PAHs were analysed using Gas Chromatography-Mass spectrometry (GC-MS) in a Selected Ion Monitoring (SIM) mode. The OP of PM_{2.5} samples were measured using a DTT assay (Patel and Rastogi, 2018), whereas OC and EC concentrations were determined using an OC-EC analyser via NIOSH-5040 protocol.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Atmospheric PM_{2.5} concentrations were $101 \pm 49.3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ during the sampling period, whereas OC, WSOC and EC concentrations were 19.6 ± 6.46 , 12.4 ± 3.83 and $2.78 \pm 1.77 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, respectively. During the entire sampling period, the highest PM_{2.5} ($237 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) and EC ($6.88 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) concentration was observed on Diwali (November 14, Figure 1A). The average concentration of 16 priority PAHs (Σ PAHs), 13N-PAHs (Σ N-PAHs) and 10 O-PAHs (Σ O-PAHs) were 19.7 ± 18.3 , 1.97 ± 1.36 and $7.44 \pm 4.54 \text{ ng m}^{-3}$, respectively. The highest concentrations of Σ PAHs, Σ N-PAHs and Σ O-PAHs were also observed on Diwali (Figure 1B). This observation indicates that the fireworks, oil lamps and other anthropogenic activities on Diwali not only contribute to PM_{2.5} and EC but also emit a large amount of PAHs and their derivatives in the atmosphere. OP of PM_{2.5} was determined and expressed in two different units: volume normalized OP (OP m⁻³ or OP_v), and mass normalized OP (or OP μg^{-1} or OP_m). The variation in the OP_v and OP_m values are shown in Figure 1A. The slopes (*m*) of OP_v vs PM species plots indicate towards the strength of OP of individual species. During the sampling period the maximum OP_v is associated with the EC ($m=1.83$, $r^2=0.71$), followed by the WSOC ($m=0.51$, $r^2=0.62$) and OC ($m=0.33$, $r^2=0.84$). This inferred that the ROS active species during the sampling duration in Ahmedabad are mainly emitted along with the EC fraction. The increase in the concentrations of PAHs, N-PAHs and O-PAHs on Diwali results in the increase in the OP_v ($19 \text{ nmol DTT min}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-3}$). However, the highest OP_v ($28 \text{ nmol DTT min}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-3}$) and OP_m ($352 \text{ pmol DTT min}^{-1} \mu\text{g}^{-1}$) values was observed one day after Diwali (November 16). These elevated OP_v and OP_m values on November 16 are likely due to the high contribution of Benzo(a)Fluorenone (B(a)F, 40%) to Σ O-PAHs. This inferred that increase in the

concentration of O-PAHs results in the increase in OP. The low value of OP_v and OP_m during November 23 and 26 may be due to other species which are showing antagonistic effects and diluting OP.

Figure 1. Daily variation of (A) PM_{2.5}, OM, EC, OP_v and OP_m, and shaded region represents the Diwali day (B) Σ PAHs, Σ N-PAHs and Σ O-PAHs

CONCLUSIONS

In Ahmedabad, fireworks and anthropogenic activities emit large amount PM_{2.5}, EC, PAHs, N-PAHs and O-PAHs in the atmosphere. ROS active species are emitted mainly along with the EC fractions followed by WSOC and OC fractions. B(a)F contributed 40 % to ΣO-PAHs on November 16 which results in high OP_v and OP_m values. Increase in the PAHs, N-PAHs and O-PAHs concentration on Diwali results in the increase in OP_v.

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YEAR-LONG STUDY OF THE CONTRIBUTION OF FOSSIL FUEL AND BIOMASS BURNING TO BLACK CARBON OVER AN URBAN CITY

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Keywords: Aethalometer Model, Black Carbon, Fossil Fuel, Biomass Burning.

INTRODUCTION

Black Carbon (BC) aerosol, is a specific category of carbonaceous aerosols that is distinguished by its ability to absorb light. The formation of this phenomenon occurs through the incomplete combustion of fossil fuels (BC_{ff}) as well as biomass burning (BC_{bb}) sources (Bond *et al.*, 2004). It is responsible for the absorption of shortwave solar radiation and longwave terrestrial radiation. This study examines the measurements of real-time BC mass concentrations for a period of one year (December 2020 to November 2021) in Varanasi. This dataset encompasses the real-time measurements of BC mass concentrations and evaluates the hourly contributions of BC_{ff} and BC_{bb} to the overall BC mass.

METHODS

Utilizing a seven-channel Aethalometer AE-33 operating at a flow rate of 2 LPM, we conducted continuous, real-time measurements of BC aerosol mass concentration. Observations were captured at one-minute intervals. To quantify the contributions of BC_{bb} and BC_{ff} to the overall BC at 880 nm, we directly derived information from the aerosol absorption coefficients, which were calculated using the aerosol light absorption cross-section from the Aethalometer, as well as from the Angstrom exponents (Sandradewi *et al.*, 2008). Figure 1 shows the meteorological parameters, including temperature (Temp), relative humidity (RH), wind speed (WS), and Atmospheric Boundary Layer (ABL) height data for the study period over the measuring site.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 2(b) illustrates the proportional contribution of BC_{ff} and BC_{bb} to the overall BC. Throughout the year, BC_{ff} exhibits its highest levels, primarily during noon hours (80%), owing to the prevalence of fossil fuel combustion processes. Conversely, BC_{bb} demonstrates its greatest contribution during morning hours (between 7:00 and 8:00 IST) and night hours (between 20:00 to 22:00 IST), accounting for 43% and 48% respectively.

In Figure 3(a), the hourly variations of BC are significantly positively correlated ($R = 0.91$) with RH due to hygroscopic growth, where BC particles absorb moisture from the air. Conversely, there exists a robust negative correlation ($R = -0.90$) between the hourly variations of BC and temperature due to increased dispersion and dilution of pollutants, including BC aerosols, facilitated by higher temperatures in Figure 3(b). Likewise, the hourly variations of BC exhibit a strong negative correlation ($R = -0.90$) with WS in Figure 3(c). Lastly, the hourly variations of BC are characterized by a pronounced negative correlation ($R = -0.94$) with ABL height due to the larger vertical dispersion allowed by an elevated ABL height, resulting in a more widespread distribution of pollutants over a larger volume of air and thus reduced concentrations at specific levels in Figure 3(d).

Figure 1. Diurnal variation of Temperature, Relative Humidity, Atmospheric Boundary Layer, and Wind Speed over the study site during 2020-21.

Figure 2. Diurnal variation of BC, BC_{ff}, and BC_{bb}, (a) and % contribution of BC_{ff} and BC_{bb} to BC, (b).

Figure 3. Correlation of diurnal BC mass concentrations with meteorological parameters such as (a) relative humidity, (b) temperature, (c) wind speed, and (d) atmospheric boundary layer.

CONCLUSIONS

The key findings of this study can be summarized as follows:

1. Diurnal variations in BC mass concentrations, BC_{ff} , and BC_{bb} exhibit distinctive patterns characterized by two prominent peaks observed throughout the study duration. These peaks emerge during the early morning and late-night hours, followed by a subsequent decrease in the afternoon.
2. These diurnal variations are influenced by dynamics within the boundary layer and shifts in surface meteorological parameters. Wind speed changes throughout the day, particularly higher in the afternoon, contribute to lower BC concentrations during that period. In the evening, a shallower boundary layer confines aerosols near the surface, leading to heightened concentrations that peak at night.
3. BC originating from fossil fuels (BC_{ff}) constitutes 80% (annually) of the total BC concentration and a larger fraction of BC from biomass burning (BC_{bb}) is prominent during the morning (43%) and night hours (48%).

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COMPREHENSIVE EVALUATION OF BIASES IN SO₂ REANALYSIS DATA AGAINST SATELLITE OBSERVATIONS OVER INDIAN REGION DURING COVID-19 LOCKDOWN

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Keywords: Sulphur dioxide, Aerosols, Lockdown, Air quality.

INTRODUCTION

Sulphur Dioxide (SO₂) has both direct (scattering of solar radiation) and indirect effects on the climate (acting as cloud condensation nuclei (CCN)) (Boucher et al., 2013). Large changes in SO₂ also influence the radiative forcing of aerosols (Seinfeld and Pandis, 2006). Excess amounts of SO₂ in a particular region can significantly reduce air quality. Reanalysis datasets provide a good estimation of SO₂ over the Indian region. The performance of each dataset is affected by the study area and period, as well as the spatial and temporal resolutions of the data. Moreover, it is necessary to analyse the behaviour of these datasets during sudden sensitive extreme conditions, which haven't been encountered in previous decades. COVID-19 is one such natural laboratory to check the reliability of SO₂ reanalysis datasets over a particular region in comparison with direct observations as strict lockdown was implemented during that period to control the spread of the disease. Therefore, in the present study, biases of reanalysis datasets of SO₂ number density are analysed with the help of space-borne observations over the Indian region during the lockdown period.

METHODS

In this study Columnar SO₂ data is taken from Modern-Era Retrospective analysis for Research and Applications Version 2 (MERRA - 2), and Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS), along with TROPOMI OFFL/L3_for analysis. The comparison between the datasets has been done for SO₂ hotspot regions in India. A total of four regions have been identified as hotspots based on the satellite spatial variation in the SO₂ number density over the country (Figure 1a). The regions include the Western (R1) and Eastern (R2) Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP), the Eastern part of central India (R3), and the western part of India encompassing Gujarat (R4).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1b shows the estimation of columnar SO₂ over the Indian region during the months of March, April, May (MAM) (lockdown days) from the year 2019 to 2022. It is noted that SO₂ concentration is higher in R2 in 2022 (>0.4 DU) than in 2019 (0.2-0.3 DU). In case of MERRA-2 the changes in SO₂ concentrations over the study region are contradicting during the lockdown years and its estimation seems monotonous for the past 4 years. While, in the case of CAMS observations, it captured the changes in SO₂ over the years and it has also captured the variation of SO₂ concentration over highly concentrated regions of R3 and R4 as well.

The anomaly with observed and reanalysis data sets is shown in Figure 1c. It is observed that in R1, MERRA-2 overestimates SO₂ by > 25% during 2020 & 2022. In R2 (Eastern IGP), MERRA-2 SO₂ is overestimated in all the years and the overestimation crossed more than 40% during the lockdown year. In R3, MERRA-2 deviates by ±25% from the observation. In R4, MERRA-2 underestimated the observation by 25% except for the lockdown year.

In the case of CAMS, the R1 is within the range of ±25% from observation (Figure 1d.). R2 overestimates by 35%. In R3, it underestimates during the period of study and its deviation from observed data is ~35%. In R4, the underestimation was about 42% during the years 2019 and 2021 but surprisingly CAMS observation shows <6% deviation for R 4 and R5 during the lockdown year.

Figure 1. (a) Selected regions of study using TROPOMI observations. (b) Maps showing yearly variation of SO₂ during MAM (2019-2022). (c) Maps showing anomaly of SO₂ reanalysis datasets with respect to TROPOMI observation. (d) Percentage of deviation estimated over the regions of interest.

CONCLUSIONS

We have analysed columnar SO₂ measurements from satellite and reanalysis data products. It’s found that CAMS data is more close to observation in R1 and R2, while MERRA-2 in R3 and R4 other than the lockdown year. During the lockdown period, biases observed with respect to MERRA-2 are high as compared to CAMS over India. This study suggests that profound care should be taken while choosing reanalysis datasets for sensitive studies over the Indian region. Since SO₂ has temporal and spatial variability, optimum care should be taken in choosing the reanalysis datasets for any small-scale regional studies.

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ANALYTICAL PARAMETERS AND ROS GENERATION CAPABILITY SUPPORTING HEALTH RISK ASSESSMENT OF SIZE-SEGREGATED PARTICULATE MATTER BOUND METALS

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Keywords: SIZE-SEGREGATED PM, METALS, HEALTH RISK, DITHIOTHREITOL ASSAY

INTRODUCTION

PM bound Fe, Cu and Zn is capable of penetrating deep inside the human lungs, thereby initiating reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation by Fenton's or Fenton-like reaction which ultimately leads to cell death due to build-up of oxidative stress (Jan et al., 2018). Dithiothreitol (DTT) assay is widely used to determine oxidative stress generated by ROS (Bates et al., 2019). Thus, in this research work, we investigated PM bound metals viz. Fe, Cu and Zn and their correlation with DTT activity.

METHODS

SITE DESCRIPTION AND SAMPLING

Based on ongoing industrial growth and population density, Kharadi, Pune was selected for sampling. Sampling was performed from December, 2022 to February, 2023 by eight stage cascade impactor (Tisch Environmental Inc.).

METAL ANALYSIS, HEALTH RISK ASSESSMENT AND DTT ASSAY

Collected PM samples were extracted in aqua regia and analysed by atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AAS, Shimadzu, AA-7000) for metal concentration. Air quality index (AQI), and average daily dose (ADD) for individual metal was calculated by using equations provided by USEPA.

$$AQI = \frac{\text{Mass concentration for 24 hrs}}{24 \text{ hrs NAAQS standards}} \times 100$$

$$ADD = \frac{\text{Concentration} (\mu\text{g m}^{-3}) \times \text{Inhalation Rate} (15.3 \text{ m}^3 \text{ d}^{-1}) \times \text{Exposure Duration} (20 \text{ yrs})}{\text{Body Weight} (60 \text{ Kg}) \times \text{Average Exposure Time}}$$

Time interval based DTT activity was calculated by treating 1000 μl of each PM extract with DTT (1 mM), DTNB (10 mM) and Tris-HCl EDTA base.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

PM MASS CONCENTRATION

Fig. 1, depicts the size segregated PM concentration in Kharadi. Average PM_{10} and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ mass concentration for Kharadi was found to be $428.2 \pm 35 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and $146.4 \pm 29 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, respectively.

Fig. 1: Average stage-wise PM mass concentration

METAL CONCENTRATION, HEALTH RISK ANALYSIS AND DTT ACTIVITY

Fig. 2, depicts the average concentration of metals at Kharadi site. Highest concentration of Fe was recorded followed by Zn and Cu. Calculated values for average daily dose (ADD) of metals for an average 60 Kg person, are reported in Table 1.

Fig. 2: Average stage-wise concentration of metals bound with PM

Table 1: AQI and ADD ($\mu\text{gKg}^{-1}\text{day}^{-1}$) for Kharadi

PM	AQI	ADD		
		Fe	Cu	Zn
PM ₁₀	109.01	3.4596	0.1758	0.3504
PM _{2.5}	82.69	1.6105	0.1125	0.2104

Fig. 3: Correlation of DTT activity with PM bound metal concentration

Pearson's Correlation was applied to the dataset obtained for metal concentration and DTT activity by using R-Studio (fig. 3). Fe (p value= 0.03372) and Cu (p value= 0.8512) were having positive correlation with DTT activity, while Zn was having the lowest correlation.

CONCLUSIONS

Study of size-segregate particulate matter and its correlation with DTT activity is successfully performed for Kharadi, Pune, from December, 2022 to February, 2023. Observed PM mass concentrations exceeds, NAAQS standards set for PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}. Highest average elemental concentration of Fe (13.57 μgm^{-3} bound with PM₁₀) is recorded, followed by Zn and Cu. Health risk assessment of these quantified metals showed that the air quality falls under the poor category. Observed DTT activity is positively correlated with concentration levels of Fe and Cu with p values of 0.03372 and 0.8512, respectively.

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DYNAMIC POLLUTION DETECTION AND CALIBRATION OF LOW-COST SENSORS FOR LOW AND HIGH CONCENTRATION REGIONS USING MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES

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Keywords: Air Quality Monitoring, Low-Cost Sensor, Local Air Quality Variation, Calibration Factor.

INTRODUCTION

Timely and accurate air quality monitoring is of paramount importance for assessing environmental health risks and enabling effective pollution management strategies. Traditional monitoring approaches like the Environmental Beta Attenuation Monitor (E-BAM) and High-Volume Sampler provide accurate measurements, but their deployment is limited due to high costs often results in spatial data gaps (Le et al., 2020). In contrast, low-cost sensors offer an economical solution for wider coverage, but their data quality necessitates validation. This study presents a comprehensive approach that combines the strengths of high-temporal-resolution low-cost sensors (PurpleAir- Plantower PMS 5003) and machine learning-based calibration using co-located E-BAM data in ambient condition.

METHODS

The low-cost sensor (LCS) was installed alongside the E-BAM at two distinct locations: one at Anand Vihar, Delhi, a highly polluted area, and the other near Powai CAQMS located at IIT Bombay, Mumbai, which is characterized as a low-pollution zone. The data was collected from February 2023 to August 2023 for both sites. The data were analysed using time series plot to understand the sudden change in pollution captured by LCS vs E-BAM. The Z-score method was used to remove the outlier prior to performing the machine learning modelling. The calibration study was performed using multiple machine learning algorithm for both sites using PM_{2.5} concentration obtained from E-BAM (reference) and LCS, also included the relative humidity (RH) and temperature (T) obtained from LCS. The previous studies found that RH & T are the crucial parameters for the LCS calibration (Lee et al., 2020; Liang, 2021; Aix et al., 2023). The algorithms used are Multiple Linear Regression (MLR), Random Forest (RF), K-Nearest Algorithm (KNN), Gradient boosting regression (GBR), and Support vector regression (SVR).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The result of time series plot showed that LCS very well captured the small period episodic event because of the high temporal resolution data (2-minutes). The PM_{2.5} concentration obtained from E-BAM did not capture the such events because of the low temporal resolution (1-hr average) data as shown in the Figure. The descriptive analysis of air quality data from both monitoring sites, indicates noteworthy differences shown in the Table 1. The mean concentration obtained by E-BAM & LCS for Delhi site (117.60±90.18 & 66.50±58.86 respectively) are significantly high as compared to Mumbai site (34.03±32.86 & 39.36±44.27 respectively). The result suggests that LCS are able to capture the trend nicely. However significant difference in the mean concentration observed at Delhi site compared to Mumbai site, which emphasize the requirement of different calibration factor for both the sites.

The various machine learning models were applied for developing calibration factors for both the sites as shown in Figure for Mumbai site. The result showed that the Random Forest (RF) algorithm (R²-0.86 & RMSE-10.93) and Gradient Boosting Regression (GBR) algorithm (R²-0.85 & RMSE-10.92) perform better compared to all four considered model for Mumbai site. The Delhi site result showed that the Gradient Boosting Regression (GBR) algorithm (R²-0.64 & RMSE-25.00) performed better. The GBR algorithm was found to more descriptive because of the lesser difference in the training and testing score, which avoids the overfitting of the model.

Table 3. Descriptive analysis of the reference instrument (BAM) & LCS (PurpleAir) for both site

Statistics	Powai, Mumbai		Anand Vihar, Delhi	
	PM _{2.5} _E-BAM	PM _{2.5} _LCS	PM _{2.5} _E-BAM	PM _{2.5} _LCS
Mean	34.03	39.36	117.60	66.50
Standard Deviation	32.86	44.27	90.18	58.86
Minimum	4.27	1.00	1.00	1.60
Maximum	214.84	473.74	780.50	489.43
Count	4433	4433	4077	4077

Figure 11. Time series plot of LCS (2-min & 1-hr) & BAM (1-hr).

Figure 12. Calibration result of LCS using multi machine learning model.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the integration of low-cost sensors (LCS) and reference instruments like the Environmental Beta Attenuation Monitor (E-BAM) showcased their complementary roles in air quality monitoring. LCS exhibited a unique capacity to capture the episodic pollution events due to their high temporal resolution. Moreover, machine learning-based calibration models were applied to correct the LCS data with reference measurements, enhancing their accuracy. The study's findings underline the potential of LCS in supplementing traditional monitoring networks, while the calibration process highlights the necessity of accurate calibration models. These insights contribute to advancing the field of air quality assessment, enabling more informed decision-making and proactive pollution management strategies.

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COMPARATIVE STUDY OF AMBIENT AIR POLLUTANTS IN MAJOR CITIES OF
UTTARAKHAND INDIA

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ABSTRACT: The air pollution increases due to industrialization and urbanization. The problem of air pollution is not of India, but it is a global problem. It can influence local and regional weather, climate/climate change and public health. In the present paper, the variations in the concentrations of air pollutants (particulate matter: PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and gaseous pollutants: SO₂ and NO₂) at Haridwar, Rishikesh, Haldwani, Rudrapur and Dehradun site name (Clock Tower and Raipur Road) station in Uttarakhand, India. These data are analysed from 2014 to 2021. Mean concentrations are observed to be higher during the pre-monsoon season as compared to the winter and monsoon. Correlation analysis shows the profound impacts of meteorology and local dynamics on the observed variations in observed trace species. It is observed that the PM₁₀ concentration is about two times higher than the prescribed national standard while SO₂ and NO₂ levels were within the predetermined limits, fixed by the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) New Delhi, India, for residential, commercial, and industrial areas. A detailed statistical analysis (Correlation coefficient, average, standard deviation, kurtosis, and skewness) also has been carried out based on monthly average values of the observed air pollutants and meteorological parameters.

Keywords: Statistical analysis, Particulate Matter, and Gaseous Pollutants.

IMPACT OF AEROSOLS ON WHEAT PRODUCTIVITY IN PUNJAB REGION OF INDIA

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Keywords: Aerosols and air quality, agricultural productivity, radiation use efficiency, PAR.

INTRODUCTION

India's economy is reliant upon the primary sector with more than half of its population (52%) employed in agriculture and allied activities. Cereals constitute the biggest portion of Indian agricultural production and wheat is among the most cultivated crops in the country. Punjab is one of the hotspots for wheat production in the country, known as the wheat basket of India (Bodh et al., 2019). Unfortunately, being situated in the Indo-Gangetic plain which is an air pollution hotspot, Punjab also suffers from high levels of air pollution every year, especially during the pre-monsoon and winter seasons (Ramanathan et al., 2007; Jangid et al., 2021). Winter is the time for wheat cultivation in the region (Rabi crop). Therefore, the effect of aerosol pollution on the productivity of wheat warrants serious investigation.

Aerosols scatter the incoming solar radiation increasing the diffused fraction of photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) (Kaskaoutis et al., 2006). An increase in the diffused PAR has been associated with enhancement of the Radiation use efficiency (RUE) of plants (Chapin et al., 2002; Greenwald et al., 2006). This is significant for the productivity of C₃ plants such as wheat which get light saturated under high direct PAR. Higher diffused PAR leads to better availability of radiation to the shaded leaves of the canopy and thus results in higher photosynthesis rates (Kobayashi et al., 2005). Niyogi et al. (2004) showed in their study that high aerosol optical depth (AOD) leads to increase in the daytime carbon sink for crop plants in cloudless conditions.

METHODS

The present analysis has been carried out for the period of 2000-01 to 2017-18 using yearly data for the Rabi season (December, January and February). We have used the district-wise annual yield (tonnes/hectare) data for all the districts of the Indian state of Punjab provided by the National informatics centre, ministry of communication, Government of India. Surface PAR flux values (direct/diffused) for the study region have been extracted from the Terra/Aqua Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) and Clouds and the Earth's Radiant Energy System (CERES) measurements combined in the SYN1deg product. AOD measurements by the Terra MODIS sensor are retrieved as level-2 products for the assessments of aerosol loading over the study region for the study period. We then use suitable computational tools to process the retrieved data by binning variables like AOD and surface diffused PAR for their correlational analysis with wheat yield.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Variation of annual yield with the mean seasonal AOD shows a statistically significant increasing trend for low to moderate values of AOD (Fig. 1a). However, we find saturation in yield for higher values of AOD. Here we argue that the increased fraction of diffused PAR due to aerosol scattering (Fig. 1b) results in the enhancement of the overall wheat productivity (Fig. 1c) over the region. Model results have shown that while low to medium levels of aerosol scattering help increase crop productivity in both C₃ and C₄ plants, a further increase in the aerosol loading ultimately results in a decrease in yield (Mera et al., 2006; Greenwald et al., 2006), which is also corroborated by our findings.

There may be other climatic, technological and crop management factors which can affect the crop yield and these are to be discussed and analysed in our study and further research.

Figure 13. Correlational and statistical analyses of pairs of variables used in the study to assess the effect of aerosols on wheat productivity in Punjab.

CONCLUSIONS

We find that there is statistically significant positive correlation between the AOD and yield of wheat over the study region. We propose that this can be due to the enhancement of RUE of the wheat plants as a result of higher levels of surface diffused PAR which increases as a result of aerosol scattering in the atmosphere. However, we observe a saturation in yield values at higher AOD values. Thus, we propose that the positive effect of aerosols on primary productivity should be considered in assessments of the effect of pollution on plants. Also, the incorporation of plant-aerosol processes in crop simulation models is necessary for better accuracy in crop modelling.

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**COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT IONISATION BASED TECHNOLOGIES FOR PARTICLE
MATTER CAPTURE IN AN INDOOR ENVIRONMENT**

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Keywords: Ionisation, technology, PM capture, scale up, indoor environment.

INTRODUCTION

Indoor air quality is a major concern in the modern environment since people especially in urban areas spend 80-90% of their time indoors. Among different indoor pollutants, particulate matter (PM) are major concern for health due to its smaller size and easy attachment to different species. However, conventional PM capture technologies like filtration have lot of drawbacks like increased pressure drop resulting in increased energy consumption, sustainability issues regarding disposal of filters, bioaerosol generation and additional expenses associated with frequent cleaning of filters. Additionally, emerging PM capture technologies like non-thermal plasma and botanical filtration are still on laboratory scale due to lack of understanding of their mechanism of PM capture. In this regard, ionization, a technology widely preferred technology for industrial PM collection has several advantages such as high efficiency removal, minimal pressure drop, and flexibility of keeping as standalone/induct, reduced pressure drop resulting in minimal energy consumption, requirement of cleaning of plates by used itself thereby reducing the maintenance charges and its capability to capture multiple pollutants. Therefore objective of current study is the intercomparison of different ionisation based technologies in terms of their effectiveness in PM capture. This study will assist in selecting best-performing ionisation technology for PM capture in an indoor environment.

METHODS

The current study has selected five best-performing ionisation devices available in commercial market and as well as from various previous literature. Each of them followed different mechanism of ion generation, operated at varied voltages and generated different number of ions (Characteristics of each ionisers are illustrated in Table 1). Every experiment was performed by passing PM laden air at flow rate of 15 LPM through a square crosssectional chamber with inner dimension 4.3 x 4.3 x 15 cm respectively. Overall, the experimental setup used in current study consisted of three parts namely PM collection, capture part as well and measurement part consisting of various PM measurement devices as shown in Figure 1. PM collection part included either atomisation of standard aerosols or drawing real indoor PM by employing pump.

For understanding effectiveness of ioniser in capturing PM under various scenarios, tests have been performed with standard aerosol specified by ASHREA as well as with PM drawn from real indoor scenarios. PM capture performance of each ioniser was evaluated with several standard salts like magnesium chloride, aluminium sulphate and potassium chloride having different PM number size distributions as well as with real indoor PM sources like candle burning, mosquito coil, incense sticks, infiltrated PM and ambient PM. By comparing PM number concentration at off and on condition of ioniser PM capture efficiency was evaluated

Figure 1. Schematic of experimental setup used in current study

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Different ionisation-based technologies were compared in terms of their efficiency of PM capture for standard aerosols and are illustrated in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Comparison of total PM capture efficiency of ionisers with standard aerosols

Sl No	Ionizer	Characteristics of tested ionisers	No of generated ions (#/cc)	Total efficiency (%) from 10 nm to 1µm
1	Ioniser-A	Input : DC 12V Output voltage : DC -4 kV to -6kV	15×10^6	59.60
2	Ioniser-B	Input: 100-240 V AC Output: 5 to -12 kV DC	8×10^7	87.89
3	Ioniser-C	Input : DC 12V Output voltage : -4 kV to -6kV DC		90.33
4	Electrostatic precipitator	Output: 9 kV DC	1.59×10^6	98.50
5	Static bar	Output: 7 kV DC 37 stainless steel in all four directions	1000 V-100V in 0.5 seconds	99.87

From Table 1, one can understand that static bar is the best-performing ioniser with efficiency of 99.87% for wide PM sizes ranging from 10 nm to 1µm. Additionally, it also captured PM in real indoor scenarios like major indoor sources, infiltrated PM and outdoor PM effectively thereby suggesting its possible application in capturing PM of different physical as well as chemical characteristics in different concentrations coming from numerous sources effectively. The results of ESP in current study are in agreement with efficiency of ESP performed in similar setting (Kulkarni et al., 2002).

CONCLUSION

Comparing different available ionisers, static bar was found to capture wide range of PM of different characteristics effectively. Although PM capture is primary requirement of an air cleaner, secondary consequences like by generation of toxic by-product emissions, multipollutant removal and cost of air cleaner affect long term usage. This aspects have been evaluated in preliminary scale and understanding of same is required in scaling up of designed static bar into a commercial air purification product.

TROPICAL CYCLONE INDUCED AIRQUALITY ANALYSIS USING GOOGLE EARTH ENGINE

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Keywords: aerosol, air quality, cyclone.

INTRODUCTION

Tropical Cyclones (TCs) are formidable atmospheric phenomena that wield both detrimental and beneficial impacts. They wield influence over atmospheric variables and the dispersion of air pollutants, yielding diverse effects (Badarinath, 2009). Geographically bounded by the Arabian Sea in the west and the Bay of Bengal in the east, TCs significantly shape the atmospheric conditions and air pollution patterns across India and parts of Southeast Asia. This study delves into the examination of the impact of the recent tropical cyclone *Biparjoy*, occurring from the 6th to the 19th of June 2023 (IMD Report 2023), over the Arabian Sea, on the air quality of the Indian subcontinent.

METHODS

For the current analysis, the Modern-Era Retrospective Analysis for Research and Application, version 2 (MERRA-2), serves as the primary data source. The study utilizes the concentration of particulate matter PM_{2.5}, derived from the MERRA-2 dataset (hourly time-averaged M2T1NXAER data). To comprehend the behavior of aerosol optical depth, the MODIS/Aqua Aerosol 5-Min L2 Swath 3km (MYD04_3K) dataset is utilized. Cyclone trajectory and eye information are provided by the Indian Meteorological Department (IMD). Furthermore, u and v winds at 850 hPa are sourced from the fifth-generation ECMWF reanalysis (ERA5).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1. MERRA-2 calculated PM 2.5 on 16 June 2023 and 19 June 2023 (before and after landfall).

Tropical cyclone Biparjoy formed over the southeast Arabian Sea around 6 June 2023 and eventually intensified into an Extremely Severe Cyclonic Storm and a Category 3-equivalent tropical cyclone. As it intensified and advanced from south to north (cyclone track shown in Figure 1), the particulate matter is seen moving from the Somali Peninsula to the Arabian Sea. As this cyclone made landfall on 15th June, 2023 as a Very Severe Cyclonic System with maximum sustained wind speed (MSW) of 115-125 kmph (65 knots) gusting to 140 kmph (75 knots), it is seen efficiently displacing the particulate matter carried with it and melt away over eastern and peninsular India decreasing the air quality over southern states.

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IMPACT OF FIREWORKS ON AEROSOL AND AIR QUALITY OVER MEGA CITY - AHMEDABAD

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Keywords: Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD), Black Carbon (BC), Urban Environment, Air Pollution.

INTRODUCTION

Aerosols in the troposphere can affect the Earth's climate in several important ways on local, regional and global scales. Atmospheric pollutants such as sulphur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), carbon monoxide (CO), particulate matters (PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}) and several other metals like aluminum, manganese, and cadmium, etc, are released in significant quantity associated with serious health hazards due to fireworks. (Pratap, 2021). Diwali is an important Indian festival celebrated in the month of October or November every year with huge firework displays across the country for a period of about 5–6 days. Bursting and burning of firecrackers during festive celebrations inject a lot of aerosols into the atmosphere locally and temporarily. Hence, a seven day's long intensive in situ measurements of Black Carbon and Aerosol Optical Depth were collected to capture pre to post-Diwali and New Year festival celebrations marked with massive fireworks for the city of Ahmedabad, India (Chhabra, 2020).

METHODS

The study was carried out at a semi-arid urban location of Ahmedabad city. The experiment was set up at St. Xavier's College in Navrangpura area because of its strategic location in the heart of urban Ahmedabad (23.03° N latitude and 72.55° E longitude). The in situ measurements were collected for seven days starting from 22th October (pre-Diwali) to 28th October, 2022. Diwali festival was celebrated on 24th October, 2022. In situ AOD measurements were collected on an hourly basis during 0800 – 1500 hr using well calibrated Microtops II Sunphotometer instrument and BC measurements were collected for 16 hours daily (0800 hr morning to 1200 hr midnight) using state-of-the art Magee Scientific Aethalometer- AE33 instruments. Measurements of PM were collected from the nearby station of CPCB installed at Space Applications Centre (SAC), ISRO. This study depicts the variation of Aerosol Optical Depth and Black Carbon (BC) for a period of seven days of Diwali festival over the largest metropolitan city of Gujarat, Ahmedabad.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The daily variations in AOD, PM_{2.5} and BC concentrations during the study period are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig 2. The data analysis indicates that during seven days of the study period, AOD at 500 nm was observed with a gradual increase till next two days after Diwali (24th October) with maximum AOD (0.636) on 27th October and followed with a gradual decrease. The high AOD value indicates increased atmospheric turbidity. In Ahmedabad, Diwali festival is followed with New Year day, and traditionally a large amount of firecrackers are burnt throughout the Diwali night and next day morning to mark the beginning of the New Year. These firecrackers burning results in high aerosol loading indicated by high AOD observed on the day after following Diwali (25th-27th October 2022). On observing the PM 2.5 values, a similar trend to that of AOD is seen. A gradual increase in PM 2.5 values are observed during the period of Diwali celebrations (22th-27th October) with maximum value reaching up to 127.12 µg/m³ on 27th October, which is followed by a decrease. This shows a increase in concentrations of Particulate Matter in the atmosphere.

The intensive in-situ measurements of Black Carbon (BC) were also evaluated which showed elevated values of Black carbon on Diwali days (23th-24th October) with a maximum value of 11.26 µg/m³ on 23rd October, followed by a decrease and then a gradual increase till 28th October. The high values of black carbon show the elevated input of carbonaceous aerosols in the atmosphere which are harmful for the health. The values of Angstrom Exponent (α) were derived from AODs. The analysis of angstrom exponent showed values of $\alpha > 1$, for all the seven days of the study. The values of Angstrom Exponent greater than 1 indicate the presence of accumulation mode aerosols in the atmosphere, which is also evident from the result obtained from analysis of PM 2.5 and BC (Black Carbon).

Fig. 1. Variation of AOD and PM 2.5 over Diwali Period (22th – 28th October)

Fig. 2. Variation of BC over Diwali Period (22th – 28th October)

CONCLUSIONS

The study during the Diwali celebration in the year 2022 showed increase in AOD values and PM 2.5 concentrations. The Black Carbon (BC) concentrations also depicted significantly high values on the day of Diwali (24th October). The Angstrom exponent calculated from the AOD values were found to be greater than 1 indicating presence of accumulation mode aerosols in the atmosphere which is evident from the analysis of PM2.5 and BC data, which showed elevated values. These anomalies can be a result of large amount of firecrackers that are burnt throughout the Diwali night and next day morning to mark the beginning of the New Year which increases the input of carbonaceous and particulate matter in the environment.

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DIURNAL PATTERNS IN AMBIENT PM_{2.5} EXPOSURE OVER THE GANGA RIVER BASIN

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ABSTRACT

With significant effects on human health and environmental quality, air pollution, in particular fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), is a significant environmental concern. The Ganga River Basin, a region of enormous socioeconomic and ecological significance in South Asia, is the subject of this study's investigation of diurnal trends in ambient PM_{2.5} exposure. With its enormous population and variety of anthropogenic activities, the Ganga River Basin endures different levels of air pollution. It is essential to comprehend the temporal fluctuations in PM_{2.5} concentrations in order to create effective mitigation plans and safeguard both ecosystem health and human health.

The study makes use of thorough air quality data gathered from several monitoring stations placed at strategic locations throughout the Ganga River Basin. The dataset's wide temporal coverage enables a thorough investigation of diurnal patterns. Time series analysis, clustering, and geographic modeling are just a few of the statistical and computer methods used to handle and analyze the data.

According to preliminary research, PM_{2.5} concentrations vary throughout the Ganga River Basin during the day in diverse ways. Urbanized areas have recognizable patterns with higher PM_{2.5} levels at times of heavy traffic and industrial activity. Rural areas, on the other hand, exhibit varied diurnal patterns that are impacted by regional factors like agricultural activities. Additionally, the study pinpoints transitory regions where changes in diurnal rhythms result from intricate interplay between urban and rural effects.

To comprehend their involvement in influencing diurnal PM_{2.5} changes, climatic elements like temperature, wind speed, and atmospheric stability are also looked at. Through correlation and regression studies, the impact of these variables is determined, advancing our understanding of the underlying causes of diurnal rhythms.

For decision-makers in the fields of public health and urban planning, the findings have important consequences. Targeted interventions can be created to reduce exposure during peak pollution hours by analyzing the temporal fluctuations in PM_{2.5} concentrations. The study also offers recommendations for improving the efficiency of present pollution control methods so that they better correspond with diurnal variations.

The Ganga River Basin's ambient PM_{2.5} exposure diurnal patterns are clarified by this study, in conclusion. The results highlight how complex the dynamics of air pollution in this area are, driven by a combination of anthropogenic and environmental causes. The study's findings add to the continuing discussion on air quality management and highlight the necessity for context-specific measures to deal with problems caused by pollution. This study provides a critical basis for sustainable development strategies that prioritize both environmental health and human well-being as the Ganga River Basin continues to experience urbanization and industrialization.

**EVALUATION OF VEHICULAR EMISSION INFLUENCE ON PM_{2.5} DURING THE
LOCKDOWNS AND UNLOCK PHASES OF COVID-19 IN LUCKNOW, INDIA**

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Keywords: AIR QUALITY, EMISSION LOAD, VEHICULAR POLLUTION, COVID-19, PM_{2.5}

INTRODUCTION

The lack of cohesive infrastructures, road networks, and increased population demands in most urban areas in India caused the spread of a heterogeneous source mix which influences air pollution levels to exceed the national standards persistently (Kansal et al, 2023 and Prasad, 2023). Further, the enforcement of stringent regulations for air pollution abatement in non-attainment areas has also been observed to end with little success (Lu et al., 2020). The past studies critically emphasized that the industrial and vehicular emissions are the major contributing sources to the deterioration of air quality by paying little attention to local fugitive sources (Dai et al., 2023). The recent source apportionment studies for different cities in India under the scope of NCAP (National Clean Air Programme) of MoEF&CC are recommended to be carried out by considering urban land use changes along with improved ground-air monitoring network (Guttikunda et al., 2023 and Yadav et al., 2023). In this connection, the present study purposed to understand the likely difference in the influence of vehicular emissions and local fugitive sources on ambient PM_{2.5} using significant 9-site air-monitored data during the sequential lockdowns of COVID-19 in Lucknow, India. An intervention approach of the vehicular emission inventory during episodic phases of lockdown (March-April, 2020), partial lockdown (April 2021) and unlock (March-April 2022) of COVID-19 correlates to PM_{2.5} measurements from different land use areas in Lucknow city such that the extent influence of traffic to all other fugitives are distinguished. The study outcomes reassure the importance of regulatory attention on fugitive sources along with traffic emissions for effective urban air quality management.

METHODOLOGY

Ambient air monitoring and analysis of samples were carried out for PM_{2.5} using ARA N-FRM samplers simultaneously at 9 locations covering different land use patterns such as residential (Aliganj, Vikas Nagar, Indira Nagar, and Gomti Nagar), commercial (Charbagh, Alambagh, Aminabad, and Chowk) and industrial areas (Amousi) in Lucknow during lockdown (2020), partial lockdown (2021) and unlock (2022) phases of COVID-19 that occurred in the sequential years. The total 8 sampling days covered a month period in each year. Besides, a concurrent traffic survey was also conducted for the near major roads of all the sampling sites through video recording for counting the different types of vehicles passed for the whole day. The vehicle counting was done at 15-minute intervals every 2 hours during the morning, afternoon, and evening on all the sampling days. The total number of vehicles per day plying on the road was calculated based on the observed vehicle fleet survey count method (Dutta and Wanida, 2021; CPCB, 2023). The emission load by the different categories of vehicles in the atmosphere was determined using emission factors that were reported in recent studies (CPCB, 2023). Geo-referenced correlation analysis was done between the vehicular emission and corresponding site-specific PM_{2.5} of COVID-19 lockdown phases in the city to assess the impact of vehicular movements and other activities of fugitive sources.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A grid-based (~ 2km x 2km) mean emission load of vehicles plying near roads of PM_{2.5} monitoring sites was compared for consecutive COVID-19 lockdown, partial lockdown and unlock phases in Lucknow (**Figure-1**). During the lockdown phase, the mean emission load of vehicles was found undeviating between the sites. However, vehicular movement influence in terms of increased PM emission load was observed at all 9 sampling sites from the lockdown to the unlock phase of COVID-19. The line source emissions were observed significantly higher in commercial than residential sites in the city due to the density and number of vehicle movements on the roads for commercial sites certainly increased. Besides, the mean emissions of different types of vehicles from three lockdown phases along with the site-specific concentration of PM_{2.5} at 9 sampling are detailed in **Figure-2**. The emissions of cars and trucks were higher during the unlock phase and the same type of vehicle emissions were notified low during the lockdown phase. While, the range of PM_{2.5} during the COVID-19 lockdown, partial lockdown, and unlock phases was observed 41.9 µg/m³ to 82.3µg/m³, 68.2 µg/m³ to 129.6µg/m³, 71.3 µg/m³ to 135.7µg/m³ in the residential, commercial and

industrial areas respectively. The mean $PM_{2.5}$ trends in the residential sites and commercial sites for all three phases of COVID-19 are indicative of the cumulative influence from both traffic as well as other local sources. Despite the impact of COVID-19 lockdowns on vehicle movements, the study also identified a prompt increase in mean $PM_{2.5}$ during the partial lockdown and unlock phase of COVID-19 for both residential and commercial sites, where the overlaying was in commercial sites. The near unaffected mean $PM_{2.5}$ levels even during the transition of partial to unlock phases bring abrupt attention to fugitive sources other than vehicles in the city. The present study revealed that some regions have a significant influence of fugitive sources to $PM_{2.5}$ concentration other than vehicular exhaust. Various local activities along with the city traffic, such as trash burning, construction and demolition activities, street food stalls, and hotels and restaurants were resumed during partial lockdown to unlock phases of COVID-19, and the emissions of fugitive sources likely influenced the $PM_{2.5}$ significantly.

CONCLUSION

The study evaluated the relative influence of traffic to fugitive emissions on ambient $PM_{2.5}$ using episodic events of the sequential COVID-19 lockdowns in Lucknow. The partial and unlock phases of COVID-19 with resumed urban activities bring the regular non-attainment situation in the city. The gradual increase in $PM_{2.5}$ levels during the transitions from COVID-19 lockdown to unlock phase is indicative of the cumulative influence from both traffic as well as fugitive sources. Further, the mean $PM_{2.5}$ as well as traffic emissions were overlapped with their values particularly in the commercial sites for the partial lockdown and unlock phases of COVID-19, which reveals that the impact of fugitive sources other than vehicle emissions on $PM_{2.5}$ is significant. The current study motivates the future research with special focus to regulate the traffic and fugitive source emissions for better urban air quality.

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STUDY OF AEROSOLS OPTICAL DEPTH OVER FOUR MAJOR CITIES OF INDIA

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Keywords: AOD, Air Quality, MODIS, RH, Temperature.

INTRODUCTION

Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) is an important parameter that determines how much direct sunlight is prevented by aerosol particles that can reach at the earth surface. During recent decade, increasing urbanization and industrialization leads to increase in pollution load. With such a massive rate of pollution, AOD quantity has also significantly increased over India. Ramanathan et al., (2001) and Lawrence and Lelieveld, (2010) reported that Indian subcontinent is considerably affected by long-range transportation of aerosols. AOD over four major cities of India i.e. Delhi, Kolkata, Chennai and Jaipur have been analyzed using satellite data of twelve years (2007-2018).

METHODS

The present research attempt to analyses the annual and seasonal variations of AOD over four major cities of India. Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) onboard NASA's Aqua and Terra platform Level-3 AOD data has been utilized to study. The monthly variation of mean AOD for the twelve-year period has been assessed by using radial plot and frequency distribution respectively. AOD tendencies have been calculated to know the prominent change in average AOD. Twelve years average AOD as well percentage increase in AOD has been estimated. The metrological conditions, such as Temperature, Relative humidity as well winds speed and direction are also archived and matched. Wind direction and wind speed for winter, pre-monsoon, monsoon and post monsoon season have been depicted by spatial plot. Further, cumulative effect of mean AOD along with mean temperature and RH are provided to conclude the main points drawn from the study.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Annual mean analysis reveals highest aerosol loading in Indo Gangetic Plains (IGP) and significant increasing trends from past to present year. Significant statistical trends have been found at 95% confidence level. Delhi recorded maximum AOD during monsoon season (0.95-1.05), whereas in Kolkata maximum AOD observed during winter season (0.95-1.05). Chennai shows low to moderate mean AOD for all the seasons. Annual and Seasonal mean AOD tendencies have been calculated to know the prominent changes in average aerosol loading during the past twelve year (2007-2018). Maximum increase in AOD percentage from 2007-2018 is obtained for Kolkata (39%), followed by Delhi (27.34%), Chennai (26.30%) and Jaipur (16.53%). Further, cumulative effects of different meteorological parameters i.e. temperature, wind speed and relative humidity along with AOD have been studied over four major cities. Annual and seasonal AOD tendencies (%) for twelve-year period (2007-2018) computed by combined MODIS Terra and Aqua product are shown in Table 1.

Table1: Annual and Seasonal mean AOD tendencies calculated from the period 2007-2018 over four major cities.

City	AOD tendencies (%)				
	Annual	Seasonal			
		DJF	MAM	JJAS	ON
Delhi	6.86%	12%	0%	4.74%	0%
Kolkata	12.20%	15.9%	15.80%	3.50%	14.36%
Chennai	4.07%	2.02%	1.30%	4.80%	4.50%
Jaipur	3.0%	4.08%	0%	-2.21	4.90%

CONCLUSIONS

The results demonstrated that the overall, 2007-2018 twelve years mean AOD reflects, Delhi was in the peak of aerosol concentration (0.821 ± 0.057), closely followed by Kolkata (0.817 ± 0.08) and then Chennai (0.433 ± 0.028), whereas Jaipur (0.430 ± 0.027) recorded the least aerosol loading

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A COUPLED MODELLING SYSTEM FOR AIR QUALITY AND EXPOSURE ASSESSMENT

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Keywords: AIR QUALITY, PM2.5, HIGH RESOLUTION MODELLING, EXPOSURE

INTRODUCTION

There is growing evidence of adverse health impact linked with the exposure to particulate pollution. Exposure to the fine particulate matter (PM2.5) is one of the leading risk factors worldwide as well as for India having both short-term and long-term health effects. This is a major concern in urban areas such as Delhi where people are exposed to high levels of air pollution (Singh et al., 2021). The urban PM2.5 is spatially heterogeneous in nature and contributed by the local pollution sources emitted within the city limits and the regional sources emitted within the airshed region. The concentration of PM2.5 is governed by the local and regional emission sources and meteorology involving complex non-linear chemistry, transport, radiation, micro-physical processes. Regional models can be run at fine resolutions (~1-2km) for air quality and impact analysis; however, they cannot capture the spatial heterogeneity caused by the traffic emissions. The recent advancement is to couple the local dispersion models with regional models to provide high resolution pollution concentration. This approach can capture pollution gradients observed at finer resolution (~10-100m). The high-resolution simulations are essential accurate exposure and health impact studies as using a few point observations can lead to the exposure biases. The objective of this study is to develop and apply a coupled modelling system to analyse air quality concentrations and estimate the exposure to PM2.5 over Delhi.

METHODS

A multiscale coupled modelling system has been developed by coupling a regional model with a line source dispersion mode to simulate PM2.5 concentration at high resolution (100m x 100m) over Delhi. The regional model is a 3D Eulerian model that includes dynamical and chemical processes including long range transport processes. The line source dispersion model (Singh et al., 2014) is based on a Gaussian finite line source approach and includes dry deposition. The dispersion parameters are modelled as a function of the Obukhov length, friction velocity and mixing height. The coupled system uses regional emissions from EDGAR and inhouse developed high resolution traffic emissions (Biswal et al., 2023). The model uses a high-resolution population dataset to estimate the population exposure. Simulations have been carried out for 2018 over Delhi. Figure 1 shows the

Figure 1. Model domain of the coupled modelling system.

modelling domain of the megacity Delhi with an area of 1483 km² and located at 28°34'N and 77°12'E in the Indo Gangetic Plains (IGP) of India. The performance evaluation of the modelling system to predict the

spatial variability of the PM_{2.5} concentration has been done by comparing it with CPCB/DPCC surface PM_{2.5} observations across Delhi.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The performance evaluation shows that the model captures the spatial heterogeneity of PM_{2.5} concentration across the city caused by road traffic emissions along the road network across Delhi. The traffic emissions and increment of the particulate matter over the road network is examined related to different locations across Delhi. The spatial distribution of the simulated PM_{2.5} shows high concentration near the busy roads and congested locations and traffic junctions. The concentration decreased with distance from the roads eventually levelling to the urban background level. The PM_{2.5} levels gradually increase from the outskirts to the center of Delhi which is proportional to the enhanced anthropogenic emissions. The normalised exposure shows distinct distribution. The exposure analysis shows that 100% of the Delhi's population was exposed to PM_{2.5} levels above NAAQS and over 75% of the total population was exposed to levels above 80 µg/m³.

CONCLUSIONS

A multiscale coupled modelling system has been developed for Delhi for air quality and exposure assessment over Delhi. The spatial distribution of simulated PM_{2.5} concentration shows spatial heterogeneity of PM_{2.5} concentration across the city. The concentration gradually increases from the outskirts to the center of Delhi and shows spikes near the roads. While entire residential population of Delhi is exposed to PM_{2.5} levels above NAAQS, the people living and working near the road are exposed to high levels. This study provides a high resolution PM_{2.5} concentration for Delhi which can be used for exposure and health impact assessment.

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STUDY OF PARTICULATE MATTER AROUND KUDANKULAM NUCLEAR SITE AND ITS CORRELATION WITH METEOROLOGICAL PARAMETERS

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Keywords: SUSPENDED PARTICULATE MATTER, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, METEOROLOGICAL

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols affect regional and global climate directly by absorbing and scattering the incoming and outgoing solar radiation. Aerosols also have adverse impact on human health (Ajay Vikram et al, 2001). Particulate matter are characterized by their size fractions and PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} consists of PM of aerodynamic diameter equal to and less than 10 and 2.5 microns, while Suspended Particulate Matter (SPM) consists of heterogeneously sized particles. Particles larger than 10 μ size tend to settle slowly by gravitational settling. This paper attempts to explore the correlations between atmospheric weather category and particulate matter, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} recorded at Kudankulam site. SPM, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} were simultaneously monitored at three locations during 2019-22 around the Kudankulam nuclear site and its residential area by using Respirable Dust Sampler (Envirotech). The SPM, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentrations observed at the three locations during the study period are in the range 73-80, 42- 48 and 20-23 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ respectively. Maximum particulate concentrations are observed in the winter followed by summer. Higher PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀ ratio during winter ($R^2= 0.92$) and lower during monsoons ($R^2= 0.4-0.5$) are observed. This study will be helpful in understanding the seasonal variations of particulates, source apportionment and mitigation strategies.

METHODS

This study has been carried out in and around Kudankulam site which is located along southeast coast of Gulf of Mannar, 25 km north east of Kanyakumari. Three sampling stations are selected in the vicinity of Kudankulam nuclear site, two in nuclear site and one in residential area. Airborne particulate samples were collected for 24 hours using a Respirable Dust Sampler (Envirotech) with a cone separator collected using a glass fibre filter paper of area 382 sq.cm (22.2 cm x 17.2 cm) for PM₁₀ and teflon filter paper of 30 mm diameter for PM_{2.5}. The samples are collected at four locations twice in a month at ground level for four year period from 2019-2022.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The mean variation of SPM, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} during the period 2019-2022 are given in **Table 1**. It is observed that at all the locations, the particulate concentrations are within the prescribed limit of air quality levels as per pollution control board guidelines. During the study period, maximum SPM was 113 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in the construction area and 119.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in the working plant in the month of May and August respectively. Highest PM₁₀ recorded was 61.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and lowest, 21.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in the month of January and July, respectively. Maximum PM_{2.5} observed was 26.9 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in the month of January and minimum of 12.2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ was observed in the month of October. At Kudankulam site, the predominant wind directions are NE, W, WNW and NNE. The variation of particulate matter with different size fractions like PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentrations are influenced by both the seasonal anthropogenic activities and by meteorological factors. The observed data reveals a general trend of maximum during winter (Jan-Feb) followed by summer (March-May). In the winter season, PM concentrations are elevated due to the stable weather conditions resulting from inversion. This leads to suspension of PM_{2.5} fine particulates with poor circulation of wind. Minimum trend is observed during monsoon period. North east monsoon brings heavy rain in this region. During rain, particulates are washed out from the atmosphere. During South West monsoon, the wind velocities are generally higher and particulates get circulated, transported and diluted in the atmosphere. This leads to minimum PM concentrations in the atmosphere. During summer, when solar insolation is high and strong winds are absent, convective eddies play an important role in atmospheric motions and favour formation of pollutants / particulates through photochemical reaction due to high atmospheric air temperature (Arthur Stern, 1976). During monsoon, SPM concentrations show decreasing trends. In SW monsoon, Kudankulam site experiences high wind speeds. It is observed that wind speed is the dominant meteorological parameter that determines the degree of dispersion of gaseous and particulate pollutants. Large dilution, dispersion and transport during high winds aid reduction of pollutants concentrations in the

atmosphere due to the mixing of large volume of fresh air with the air contaminants. **Table 2** gives the month wise particulate concentrations along with observed meteorological variables recorded at study site.

Table 1: Statistical variation of Particulates

Location	SPM µg/m ³		PM ₁₀ µg/m ³		PM _{2.5} µg/m ³	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Residential Area (Colony)	73.3	11.6	41.7	12.1	19.9	3.9
FISH Building - Construction Area (KK 3-6)	80.7	13.4	47.7	11.5	23.1	4.3
MMLab - Working plant (KK 1-2)	79.1	16.1	46.2	12.9	22.4	4.3

Table 2: Meteorological conditions and Average of SPM, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} at Kudankulam Site

Months-> Particulates	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
SPM (µg/m ³)	80.0	81.6	83.6	85.3	86.5	81.7	77	76.9	79.7	77.5	69.0	78.9
PM ₁₀ (µg/m ³)	54.1	50	51.7	52.3	51.3	48.6	42.4	42.6	43.6	42.4	38.6	42.7
PM _{2.5} (µg/m ³)	51.3	49.4	49.9	48	46.2	47.2	43.5	45.7	45.8	43.5	38.6	44.3
Air Temperature (°C)	27.6	28.7	29.7	30.6	30.7	30.6	29.7	29.3	28.9	28.4	27	26.5
RH (%)	80.2	76.1	76.2	78	75.8	72.6	74.2	77.1	79.9	82.7	89.3	85.3
Avg wind speed (m/s)	3.2	3.4	3.0	2.9	4.6	5.1	4.8	4.8	4.6	3.5	2.4	3.0

Conclusions

During monsoon, the pollutant concentrations decrease considerably due to high south westerly winds aiding dilution and rain washout. In the winter (Jan-Feb), the recorded pollutant concentrations show a slight increase due to low winds, poor circulation and stable weather resulting from inversion. It can be concluded from the study that the particulate concentrations observed at all the locations around Kudankulam Nuclear site are very low.

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MEASUREMENT AND HEALTH RISK EVALUATION OF COOKING-GENERATED PARTICLES IN THE COMMUNITY KITCHENS OF DAKSHINA KANNADA, INDIA

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Keywords: indoor air pollution (IAP), community kitchen, PM, health risk assessment

INTRODUCTION

Exposure to indoor air pollution (IAP) is of concern since it is a potential health hazard. Culinary activity is one of the main sources of IAP in household. Large number of studies have focused on IAP and the associated health hazard, due to cooking practices around the world but studies on this aspect in community kitchens, which serve food for large number of population, were not examined. Particularly in highly populated developing countries such as India. In this study, the concentrations of PM₁, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀ were measured in the indoor air of a variety of community kitchens. PM ratios were determined, and they are in the order PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀ > PM₁/PM_{2.5} > PM₁/PM₁₀. The study shows that workers in community kitchens are exposed to enhanced air pollution, and the corresponding health risks are evaluated.

METHODS

Urban and suburban locations within the 40 km radial zone of Mangalore city, South West Coast of India were chosen for this study. The PM measurement was carried out at a variety of kitchen set ups, such as: students hostel, schools, college cafeteria, and restaurants. Real-time 24 h PM monitoring was conducted at 15 community kitchens using the portable PM monitoring system APT MAXIMA (Applied Particle Technology Inc, 1900 S. Norfolk Street Ste. 350, San Mateo, CA 94403). It is a real-time PM monitoring and recording instrument, along with ambient temperature, pressure, and humidity data.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Each kitchen workplaces was monitored continuously for a duration of 15 to 20 days to record PM concentration during cooking and non-cooking periods to capture all events in the sampling period. A comparison of the 12 h average data of PM₁, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀ concentrations in different kitchens are presented in Fig.1. The PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} values were similar, whereas PM₁ is lower by a factor of 2 when compared to the other two species. The PM concentration values are higher (range=50-1017 µg m⁻³) when compared to those reported for dwellings (range= 48-185 µg m⁻³) by other investigators (Prashant et al., 2022). This is due to the high emission rate during cooking and longer cooking periods. The diurnal trends observed in all the community kitchens are similar. The PM size fraction ratios were in the order PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀ > PM₁/PM_{2.5} > PM₁/PM₁₀, which confirms that resuspension of particles generated in the cooking process is a major contributor to the total PM₁₀ concentration. In general, PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀ ratio <0.5 represents conditions where the observed PM levels are dominated by PM₁₀, while PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀ ratios >0.5 characterize cases with a dominant PM_{2.5} fraction. The fine to coarse particles ratio provides information about the particle origin and their formation process. Higher values of this ratio suggest the contribution from anthropogenic sources, and a smaller ratio indicates considerable involvement of coarse particle, which might be related to natural sources (Sugimoto et al., 2016). Excess Lifetime Cancer Risk (ELCR), Hazard Quotient (HQ), Excess Risks (ER), and Attributable Fraction (AF) due to PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ were evaluated from the PM concentration values. The obtained ELCR values (1.7x10⁻⁵ to 1.3x10⁻⁴) were higher when compared to the recommended limit for humans in the range of 1x10⁻⁵ to 1x10⁻⁶ by WHO (2013) and less than 1x10⁻⁶ by U.S.EPA, (2007). The non-carcinogenic risk HQ>1 for all the community kitchens exceeded the threshold value. The above results underlines the need for detailed study in community kitchens since a section of workers (professionals) are exposed to high PM concentrations continuously.

Figure 1. Comparison of PM₁, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀ concentrations in different kitchens. Daily 12 h data, corresponding to the cooking and non-cooking activity in kitchen was averaged for a month and presented

CONCLUSIONS

The results presented in this paper represent a preliminary study on the assessment of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ in community kitchens and their associated impact on the health of the worker. The study shows that the potential impact of fine particulate matter related air pollution on the workers at the community kitchen is higher. A detailed study on this aspect is now progressing.

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**PARTICULATE MATTER AND BLACK CARBON WASHOUT OVER NORTH INDIAN CITIES:
IMPLICATIONS FOR URBAN AIR QUALITY**

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Keywords: PARTICULATE MATTER, BLACK CARBON, PRECIPITATION, WASHOUT.

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution is a persistent and growing concern in urban environments worldwide, with its impacts on public health, climate, and ecosystems increasingly evident (WHO, 2019). Among the numerous pollutants that contribute to deteriorating air quality, black carbon (BC) and fine particulate matter with a diameter of 2.5 micrometers or less (PM_{2.5}) stand out as particularly harmful constituents. As an integral component of particulate matter, BC possesses the unique ability to absorb sunlight and thereby exacerbate atmospheric warming, making it a critical factor in both air quality and climate change considerations (Bond et al., 2013). This fine particulate matter predominantly originates from diverse sources, including but not limited to fuel combustion, construction-related dust, and vehicular exhaust emissions (Chatterjee et al., 2023). While much research has been conducted on the sources, composition, and health implications of PM_{2.5} and BC, a critical aspect that demands attention is the washout effect. The washout effect refers to the removal of these pollutants from the atmosphere through precipitation, such as rainfall (Zhao et al., 2020). This natural cleansing mechanism helps to temporarily reduce the concentration of pollutants in the air, leading to improved air quality (Guo et al., 2016). In light of this research gap and the urgency of addressing air pollution concerns, this study highlighted relationship between rainfall and the washout effect of PM_{2.5} and BC. By examining the washout dynamics by rain events, we aim to unravel the temporal aspects of particle removal and assess the immediate and long-term impacts on air quality. Furthermore, this study aligns with global efforts to better understand and mitigate the impacts of urban air pollution on both public health and the environment.

METHODS

To assess the washout of PM_{2.5} and BC in the Delhi and Agra cities, we consider PM_{2.5}, BC, and rainfall for the year 2018-2019 during Monsoon (June-Sep). This study has been used two primary datasets to conduct the analysis. The first dataset of PM_{2.5} was provided by the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) and BC concentration data from AE-33 aethalometer, ISRO-GBP, ARFI Network Agra, India. These measurements were averaged over short time intervals of 15 to 30 minutes. The second dataset was sourced from the Global Precipitation Measurement (GPM) database, offering precipitation data at 30-minute intervals. The analysis focused on representative PM_{2.5} levels and BC data within the 5th to 95th percentiles were selected, filtering out extreme values. Instances of no precipitation in the rainfall data were replaced with NaN (Not a Number) values to accurately represent non-precipitating conditions. The range of rainfall data was constrained to values within the fifth to the ninetieth percentiles to exclude extreme precipitation events. For each identified rain event, we have extracted PM_{2.5} and BC concentration measurements taken immediately before the onset of rainfall (approximately 30 minutes prior) and after rainfall (approximately 30 minutes following). The difference between these two PM_{2.5} and or BC values were calculated, yielding the "washout amount" (Δ). Then we have quantified the effectiveness of PM_{2.5} and BC removal during rainfall by using following formula:

$$\text{washout amount } (\Delta) = (PM_{2.5} \vee BC \text{ just before rain} - PM_{2.5} \vee BC \text{ just after rain});$$
$$\text{percentage washout amount } (\% \Delta) = \left(\frac{\Delta}{PM_{2.5} \vee BC \text{ just before rain}} \right) * 100\%.$$

Quantile mapping was employed to divide the PM_{2.5} and or BC into five bins (below 1st quantile, within 1st and 2nd quantile, within 2nd and 3rd quantile and more than 3rd quantile). A comprehensive analysis was conducted to explore any potential associations between these PM_{2.5} and BC concentration bins and the corresponding washout. Similarly, the range of rainfall intensity values was segmented into five percentile bins. This allowed for an examination of potential relationships between different levels of rainfall intensity and the resulting washout percentages.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Washout of particulate matter concentration can be affected by many factors such as initial concentration just before rainfall, rainfall intensity and duration on which rainfall happens. The figure below succinctly presents the relationship between washout effectiveness and three key influencing factors: initial PM

(Particulate Matter) concentration, rainfall duration, and rainfall intensity. The representation showcases various impacts of the washout process. It was found that, for effective washout, threshold PM concentration (median) should be close to 60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and for BC (median) 3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Further, % washout in particulate matter is prominently increasing with the increase in rainfall duration, but an inconsistent washout pattern found for BC washout. Additionally, as the rainfall intensity increases, the % washout for particulate matter also increases. But irregular washout signal obtained for BC. This may be because of different scavenging mechanisms for various aerosol species.

Figure 2. Percentage Washout due to the influence of initial $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ before rainfall, rainfall duration, and intensity (a-c) and washout for black carbon (d-f).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study emphasizes the importance of various factors in understanding particle removal during rainfall events, which is crucial for effective air quality management and environmental planning. This insight aids in advancing our understanding of the complex dynamics between precipitation and airborne particulate matter. More focus study can be carried out for species specific scavenging modeling.

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ASSESSMENT OF CO-INCIDENCE BETWEEN AIR POLLUTION AND TEMPERATURE EXTREMES IN THE INDIAN SUBCONTINENT

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Keywords: Air pollution, Temperature Extremes, Co-Incidence, WRF-Chem.

INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, escalating greenhouse gas emissions have led to a significant increase in extreme heat events worldwide. Recent studies highlight the role of black carbon in exacerbating extreme heat events in India (Mondal et al., 2020). These events, along with declining air quality, pose substantial public health challenges. Co-exposure to extreme heat and poor air quality elevates cardiovascular and respiratory mortality risks by 29.9% and 38.0%, surpassing the individual effects of extreme temperatures and PM_{2.5} exposure (Rahman et al., 2022). Understanding the combined health impact of air pollution and extreme heat is crucial. This study investigates the intersection of PM_{2.5} and temperature extremes to identify vulnerable regions and offer insights for targeted strategies in mitigation and adaptation.

METHODS

In this study, a comprehensive WRF-Chem simulation was conducted in 2019 covering the South Asia Cordex Domain (12°S-40°N and 39°-121°E) using WRF-Chem model version 3.9.1 with a 27 km horizontal resolution, 48 vertical layers, and a 1-hour time step. Meteorological data came from the ECMWF reanalysis dataset (ERA-Interim). The model incorporated gas phase chemistry from RADM2, the Secondary Organic Aerosol Model (SORGAM), and aerosol microphysics from the Modal Aerosol Dynamics Model for Europe (MADE). Simulations included a one-month spin-up period in December 2018. Emissions data sourced from SMOG-India COALESCE for Indian anthropogenic sources were combined with global emissions from CEDS, GFED, and trash burning inventory, covering black carbon, organic carbon, sulphur dioxide, oxides of nitrogen, ammonia, mineral matter, and non-methane volatile organic compounds with a spatial resolution of 5km x 5km. Daily varying anthropogenic emissions were input at the surface layer, except for forest fires and energy production sectors, which were distributed vertically. In PM_{2.5} analysis, annual mean PM_{2.5} data are assessed via percentile ranges (50th, 70th, 90th, and 100th) against the National annual ambient air quality standard (NAAQS) of 40 µg/m³. Grid cells exceeding the NAAQS (which coincides with the 50th percentile) are classified as 50-70th (moderate), 70-90th (severe), and 90-100th (extreme) percentiles. For temperature, a fixed threshold of 35°C was used. Metrics like mean Tmax, Txx (the maximum value of the Tmax) in the hot season of MAMJ, and days with Tmax ≥ 35°C were calculated at the grid level, with color coding (light brown for severe, dark brown for extreme) for regions exceeding the threshold. The analysis aimed to identify spatial coincidence of high PM_{2.5} and extreme temperatures.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Elevated PM_{2.5} exposure prevails across various regions of India, with a focus on the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP), where annual average PM_{2.5} concentrations range from 52–140 µg/m³, well above air quality standards. The results are consistent with recent studies (e.g. Chatterjee et al., 2023), in which high PM_{2.5} concentrations occur in the IGP from Punjab in the west to West Bengal in the east. Simultaneously, northwestern and central India experience consistently elevated summer temperatures exceeding 35°C, attributed to meteorological conditions like North-Atlantic blocking and anomalous cooling in the Pacific. Research by Rohini et al. (2016) notes an increase in heatwave frequency, duration, and intensity in northwestern India, mirroring the north-central region defined by Ratnam et al. (2016). These extreme temperatures intersect with high PM_{2.5}

concentrations in the IGP region, possibly intensifying health and environmental concerns. Furthermore, central and northwest India endure more than 20 days, and in some areas over 25 days, when T_{max} exceeds the specified base reference temperature of 35°C .

Fig.1. Spatial distribution of (a) annual $PM_{2.5}$ concentration over India, with contours identifying regions under the 50th, 70th, 90th, and 100th percentile ranges of $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations. (b) summer months (MAMJ) T_{max} mean over India (c) summer months (MAMJ) T_{xx} over India (d) number of days during the summer months (MAMJ) over India during which T_{max} was 35°C or more

Significant spatial coincidence is observed in the IGP region, where extreme $PM_{2.5}$ pollution coincides with severe T_{max} and T_{xx} , at the 90–100th percentiles of both variables. Also, overlaps exist between extreme $PM_{2.5}$ pollution and high temperature extremes, especially T_{xx} across the region. Additional spatial coincidence of high air pollution occurs with numbers of days with T_{max} exceeding 35°C , from 15–25 days at individual grid scale. $PM_{2.5}$ constituents like black carbon can exacerbate temperature extremes by modifying the atmosphere's radiative properties. Exposure to extreme heat events can worsen air pollution impacts on worsening cardiovascular and respiratory diseases as well as broader early life, neural and systemic disease impacts (Xu et al., 2019). Beyond human impacts, broader ecosystem impacts on agriculture merit evaluation.

CONCLUSIONS

The convergence of temperature extremes and air pollution extremes entails substantial risks spanning multiple sectors. It is apparent that the central and northwest regions of India are most susceptible to the confluence of these extreme events

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ANNUAL AND SEASONAL VARIATION OF AEROSOL OPTICAL PROPERTIES OVER DELHI
 FOR FIVE YEARS

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Keywords: AEROSOL OPTICAL DEPTH, ANGSTROM EXPONENT, MODIS.

INTRODUCTION

Aerosols are solid or liquid particles dispersed in the atmosphere. They can be of natural or anthropogenic sources. It can influence the local, regional and global climate by direct (absorbing sunlight) or indirect effect (affecting formation of clouds). Aerosols affect the quality of air and human health and are of great concern now-a-days. Delhi is considered one of the most polluted cities, so the analysis of aerosol optical properties over such area is necessary to assess the air quality. The seasonal changes of aerosol optical properties will give insight into the trend of their variation. This poster focuses on the study of aerosol optical depth and angstrom exponent over Delhi to determine their variations and size of aerosols present.

METHODS

The data on aerosol optical properties was retrieved by MODIS (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer) which is a key instrument aboard the Terra (originally known as EOS AM-1) and Aqua (originally known as EOS PM-1) satellites. MODIS Time series-Area averaged, Deep Blue for Land only Aerosol Products were considered. The product used from MODIS is level 3 product at resolution of 1° x 1°. Two aerosol products taken into account were Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD, τ) at 550 nm and Angstrom Exponent (AE, α) for the period of five years from January 2018 to December 2022. Study area chosen is Delhi, which is a megacity and surrounded by Indo-gangetic plains in the North and East, the arid region Thar desert in the West and mountain range Aravalli in the South.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The major findings are

- General trend of Aerosol Optical Depth is seen decreasing from the year 2018 to 2022. Highest AOD was seen in the year 2019 with maximum AOD of 3.50 and average AOD value of 0.82 ± 0.6 .
- Post-monsoon season has a very high and summer season has the lowest AOD values during the study period.
- For maximum of time in five years the Angstrom exponent (α) value was greater than 1, with highest mean value 1.61 ± 0.9 . Only summer season showed the values lower than 1.

Table 1. Seasonal variation of Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD, τ) over Delhi

Season	Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD)				
	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Winter	0.63 ± 0.54	0.66 ± 0.36	0.80 ± 0.75	0.61 ± 0.39	0.60 ± 0.30
Summer	0.62 ± 0.26	0.52 ± 0.22	0.48 ± 0.24	0.60 ± 0.25	0.70 ± 0.33
Monsoon	0.93 ± 0.45	0.96 ± 0.76	0.83 ± 0.33	0.90 ± 0.31	0.72 ± 0.29
Post-monsoon	0.78 ± 0.42	1.11 ± 0.73	0.88 ± 0.51	0.86 ± 0.60	0.96 ± 0.54

Figure 1. Seasonal variation of (i) Angstrom Exponent (α) and (ii) Aerosol Optical Depth (τ) of five years from 2018-2022 over Delhi.

CONCLUSIONS

Dominance of fine mode particles for maximum duration of the study period. Only Summer season shows the dominance of coarse mode particles. Winter and monsoon season showed the prevalence of fine mode particles. The year 2019 has the highest aerosol loading with coarse mode particles. Coarse mode aerosols have significant effects on radiative forcing, both in shortwave and longwave spectrum. This study is useful for further monitoring of sources and sinks of aerosols, to assess Air Quality and to calculate Earth Radiation Budget.

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ESTIMATION OF PM_{2.5} CONCENTRATION IN THE KASHMIR HIMALAYAN REGION, INDIA

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Keywords: Particulate Matter, Climate Change, Air Pollution, Kashmir Valley.

INTRODUCTION

PM_{2.5} has been of concern worldwide because of adverse health effects (Chowdhury and Dey, 2016; David et al., 2019) local air-quality issues and climate change (IPCC, 2001). Himalayas having largest extent of glacier resources outside the poles are showing enhanced glacier melting due to climate change which has been attributed mostly to aerosols especially by the deposition of black carbon (Maurer et al., 2019; Bhat et al., 2017). The Himalaya's high-altitude mountainous regions are vulnerable to climate change, where ambient PM and their composition play an important role (Lelieveld et al., 2001; Venkataraman et al., 2002). Considering the above climatic and health impacts the present study was taken to estimate the fine aerosol concentration in Kashmir Himalayas.

METHODS

In the present study, 24-h PM_{2.5} samples were collected every other day on Teflon filters using five channel MetOne® (USA) Speciation Air Sampling System (SASS) over Kashmir as a representative Himalayan region site for NCAP-COALESCENCE project from January 2019 –December 2020. Gravimetric analysis of PM_{2.5} mass was performed on Teflo® filters and mass was determined as the difference in weights between equilibrated filters prior to sampling and post-sampling using microbalance (MSU6.6S-000-DF, Sartorius, Germany) at a temperature of 22±1 °C and relative humidity (RH) of 35 ± 2%.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The results from the two year study showed that PM_{2.5} mass concentration ranged from 6µgm⁻³ to 415µgm⁻³ with annual average of 49µg m⁻³ dominated by winter and autumn peaks. Annual mean concentration of PM_{2.5} in 2019 was 46µgm⁻³ and in 2020 it was 62µgm⁻³ which are 1.15 and 1.6 times higher than the Indian NAAQS annual average limit (40µgm⁻³) respectively. Approximately 23% of the total sample concentrations were higher than the Indian NAAQS 24-hr average limit (60µgm⁻³) and 38% were above annual average of 40µgm⁻³. During the entire study the maximum seasonal average concentration was observed in winter (99µgm⁻³) followed by autumn (73µgm⁻³), summer (26µgm⁻³) and minimum concentration was recorded in spring (20µgm⁻³). During autumn and winter the average PM_{2.5} concentrations were 1.2 and 1.7 times higher than Indian 24-hour NAAQ standards respectively (Table 1). There is significant seasonal difference in PM_{2.5} concentration during the study period. The higher concentration during autumn and winter are due to biomass burning for space heating and stagnant atmospheric conditions. The impact of COVID-19 lockdown has been discussed.

Table 1. Seasonal comparison of PM_{2.5} concentration (µgm⁻³) during the year 2019 and 2020

2019				2020			
Season	Min	Max	Avg	Season	Min	Max	Avg
Spring	5.6	41.2	16.0	Spring	7.6	98.0	24.7
Summer	15.3	42.4	25.7	Summer	10.0	48.4	25.6
Autumn	17.5	177.3	57.5	Autumn	10.3	415.2	88.5
Winter	9.2	255.4	91.5	Winter	26.9	408.6	105.8

Figure 1. Time series plot of PM_{2.5} concentration (μgm^{-3}) during the year 2019 (a) and 2020 (b)

CONCLUSION

Two-year long study of PM_{2.5} showed the mass concentration of ~23% of the total samples (338 samples) was higher than the Indian NAAQS annual average. Strong seasonality was observed for PM_{2.5} concentration, with highest concentrations in winters and autumn, and lowest in spring. From this study it can be concluded that biomass burning, secondary organic aerosol formations and specific meteorological conditions determine the characteristics of aerosols in this Himalayan region.

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ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF LAND USE AND LAND COVER CHANGES ON ATMOSPHERIC POLLUTANT OVER UTTARAKHAND

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Keywords: LAND USE LAND COVER, REMOTE SENSING, AIR QUALITY, NO₂, O₃

INTRODUCTION

The complex relationship between Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) dynamics and atmospheric pollutants is of increasing concern amidst rapid urbanization and global demographic shifts. This regional analysis delves into this intricate interplay, offering crucial insights for informed policy decisions and sustainable development. LULC changes, stemming from urban expansion, agriculture, deforestation, and industrialization, exert profound environmental impacts. These transformations affect terrestrial ecosystems and atmospheric conditions, leading to shifts in meteorological patterns, air quality, and greenhouse gas emissions, with global climate and public health repercussions. (Yang et al., 2021)

Our study adopts a regional perspective, investigating the dynamic connection between LULC change and atmospheric pollutants, considering urbanization rates, industrial trends, and resource management practices. Employing comprehensive datasets and advanced spatial analysis, we aim to identify key drivers and patterns in LULC change and pollutant concentrations. Additionally, we assess their effects on regional climate, air quality, and overall environmental sustainability. (Bilal et al., 2017)

METHODS

In this study, Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) maps were classified utilizing the Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier, providing a comprehensive spatial representation of land transformations. Additionally, atmospheric pollutant data PM_{2.5}, Nitrogen Dioxide (NO₂), and Tropospheric Ozone (O₃) concentration, were obtained and subjected to processing. These datasets form the basis for our regional analysis, enabling the exploration of correlations and impacts between LULC changes and various atmospheric pollutants in the study area.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS -

Our analysis revealed intriguing inside into the relationship between LULC and atmospheric pollutant in Uttarakhand region. SVM classifier effectively classified the LULC map into Dense Vegetation, built up, Water body, Barren land, agriculture land. Key land use changes identified include decrease in Dense vegetation and increase in built up was recorded over time, indicating dynamic nature of land transformation in the region.

The atmospheric pollutant data shows varying concentration across the studying area, highest level of PM_{2.5}, NO₂ and O₃ were observed in Agricultural area. Our analysis revealed notable correlations between specific LULC types and pollutant level. Figure 1 illustrates a decrease in the mean concentration of NO₂ from 2019 to 2020(29.374 to 26.945 μmol/m²) attributed to the COVID-19 pandemic, followed by a significant increase in 2022(33.298 μmol/m²). If we examine the ozone concentration, we find that it hasn't significantly changed over years (0.123 to 0.127 mol/m²). Both forest and open forest areas are displaying a consistent pattern: a decline in concentration from 2019 to 2020, followed by a substantial upsurge from 2020 to 2022.

Table.1 Annual statistics of NO₂(μmol/m²) and o₃(mol/m²) over different land use land cover in Uttarakhand.

Atmospheric Pollutant	Agriculture	Bare Land	Built-up	Flooded Vegetation	Forest	Open Forest	Snow/ice	Water Body
NO ₂ 2019	34.074	9.615	29.374	29.148	18.755	15.348	8.120	24.604
NO ₂ 2020	32.613	9.262	26.945	26.630	18.630	14.892	9.197	23.303
NO ₂ 2022	40.776	11.252	33.298	33.917	23.420	18.258	9.822	28.715
O ₃ 2019	0.124	0.120	0.123	0.123	0.122	0.122	0.120	0.123

O ₃ 2020	0.126	0.122	0.126	0.126	0.125	0.124	0.122	0.126
O ₃ 2022	0.127	0.122	0.127	0.127	0.126	0.125	0.122	0.126

CONCLUSIONS

Our research underscores the intricate relationship between LULC changes and atmospheric pollutants, initially there was decrease in NO₂ concentration due to lockdown in which all industries and different anthropogenic activities are decreased while after it there is sharp increase may be due to the forest fire, increase in built up and vehicular emissions over time. This emphasizing the need for a holistic approach to environmental management and sustainable development. By understanding these connections, we can work towards a more sustainable and healthier future for our region and beyond.

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DEVELOPMENT OF A NOBEL DEVICE TO ENHANCE AEROSOL REMOVAL EFFICIENCY OF ANY NON-CONDUCTING AIR FILTER

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Keywords: AEROSOL REMOVAL, AIR PURIFICATION, AIR QUALITY, AIR FILTRATION.

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution has become a major threat to human health as well as global climate. Estimated one out of 6 premature deaths are caused by pollution. In the 2015, 6.67 million premature deaths were caused by air pollution worldwide, which is almost 3.8 times higher than deaths caused by other types of pollutions (Fuller et al., 2022). Air pollution can cause various health problems including asthma, acute respiratory infection, cardiovascular & cardiopulmonary diseases, and lung cancer etc. Each increase of PM_{2.5} by 10 µg/m³ can be associated with increment of 24% cardiovascular diseases, 6% cardiopulmonary diseases and 8% lung cancer mortality. (Chen & Kan, 2008).

Present commercial air purifiers mainly consist of a high-efficiency particulate air (HEPA) filter to capture dust and submicron particles. HEPA filter is generally made up of glass fibers or polyester fibers, which are non-biodegradable. Whereas other biodegradable filters (like cotton fiber filter) are not as efficient as HEPA filters. The present work relates to a technology which can enhance the filtration efficiency of any filter it is used with. In this way, we can use not only cheap but biodegradable filters with almost comparable efficiency to HEPA filters. Also, this invention can enhance efficiency of already available air filters to achieve extremely purified air.

METHODS

The present invention essentially includes a conductive net that is sandwiched between filters, a negative air ionizer, a voltage multiplier, and an insulating covering. The material chosen for the conductive net was a metal net/mesh. All the open ends of metal net/mesh were sealed by plastic sealant. The metal net/mesh was sandwiched between two layers of cotton filters. Three types of filters were homemade using medical grade cotton wool. Before making the filters, the cotton wool was washed and dried. After drying, layers of cotton wool were taken out and compressed using a cloth iron. Filters were given the name F1, F2 & F3 with decreasing filter thickness. The conductive net/mesh was connected to the positive end of a voltage multiplier. The other (negative) end of the voltage multiplier is grounded for a continuous positive voltage supply. Figure 1(A) shows the arrangement for testing the effectiveness of present invention which includes a negative air ionizer upstream, the filter assembly constructed as described above, an aerosol spectrometer (GRIMM model 1.108), a flow meter and a suction pump. This assembly was manufactured in Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur. The testing was done for 7 days in 28 number of sets for each condition. Also, the variation of PM reading within each set was very small and hence can be ignored. Test was done under ambient atmospheric conditions.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The idea behind the filter assembly was to hold the static electric charge for long time with least losses so that it can transfer the electric static charge to the cotton (non-conductive) filter. The holding and transferring of electric static charge were confirmed using an electrostatic polarity detector. The intention behind the invention is to enhance the aerosol capturing efficiency of the low cost, biodegradable cotton filter. Figure 1(B) shows the increase in aerosol removal efficiency of filter F1 by using the above-described filter assembly. An increment in aerosol removal efficiency can be seen for all size range of aerosol from 0.3 to 20 µm. The change in increase in efficiency for different particle size range might be caused by difference in the ability to hold charge by particle of each size, along with the difference in inertia of different sized particles to deviate from original path to be collected on filter fibre due to electrostatic attraction. The device is supposed to be worked with the voltage multiplier 'on', hence longevity of charge on filter was not tested. But in future while optimising the technology, the charge retention will surely be tested.

Figure 1: (A) Test setup for aerosol removal efficiency. (B) Test results of filter F1 @ 20 LPM flow rate.

CONCLUSION

In the present work, a successful development of a new technology to enhance the aerosol removal efficiency of a low cost, biodegradable and less efficient filter was achieved. The filter F1 with the presented assembly at 20 LPM has achieved more than 90% efficiency for particle size up to 0.8 µm with a simple cotton filter having a pressure drop of only 0.5mm H₂O (at 20 LPM air flow rate). This head loss is 4 times lesser than HEPA filter. This technique can be used to manufacture indoor or outdoor air filters using cheap filter material which are also biodegradable. Which will be helpful in removing aerosols from air to provide a cleaner and healthier environment.

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AGRICULTURE, REACTIVE NITROGEN AND AIR POLLUTION LINKAGES IN INDIA

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PROBLEM STATEMENT

Agricultural production, especially for food, is essential for the sustenance of human society, yet current practices have resulted in wide-ranging environmental damages. Much of these damages result from a class of pollutants called reactive nitrogen (Nr), that are emitted in various forms (eg: NH₃, N₂O, NO_x), from a diverse range of sources (agriculture, industry, transport) and impacts all environmental media from local to global scales (Sutton *et. al.*, 2008). Food systems have significantly contributed to air pollution (globally: 2% of NH₃ emissions, 58% primary PM_{2.5} emissions and 13% NO_x emissions) (Balasubramanian *et al.*, 2021) and climate change (one-third global GHG emissions) (Balasubramanian & Babbar, 2022; Crippa *et al.*, 2021). As a result, the sustainable management of Nr to meet growing global food demand has been identified as a Grand Engineering Challenge (Sutton *et. al.*, 2011). It is crucial to systematically budget the multi-media release of Nr emissions, and subsequent flows and impacts, especially for India which faces the extraordinary dual challenge of ensuring the food and environmental security of roughly 1.6 billion people by 2050 (UN, 2013).

APPROACH

System Boundary and assumptions

Here, we build an Environmentally Extended Input-Output Accounting for Nr with focus on the agriculture sector in India for years 2000-2020. This approach enables the estimation of total magnitude and source contributions of total nitrogen (N) inputs, as well as the fate of N that leaves this system and eventually re-enters into another system or pool. Of interest are contributions from internal drivers including biological N fixation and external drivers including fertilizer production and application, livestock manure management, atmospheric N deposition, fuel use for agricultural production and irrigation (Figure 1). Data is obtained at the national scale from a combination of literature surveys, reports from national agricultural organizations, and national and international data repositories (World Bank, IndiagriStat *etc.*) Outflows from the sector are determined by combining the identified national and sector specific activity levels with emission factors to estimate emissions of NH₃ and NO_x.

KEY FINDINGS

N input to Indian croplands has increased from 32 Tg-N to 52 Tg-N between 2000-2020. Fertilizer consumption (58%) ranks first among the total element followed by biological N fixation (16%), deposition (10%), and livestock manure (6.5%) of the total Nr used in the cropland sector for year 2020. Over time, irrigation water has experienced the most substantial increase in N content, showing a significant rise of 200%. Following closely, fertilizer application and deposition saw percentage changes of 86% and 25%, respectively. These findings indicate that the irrigation water is responsible for the highest change in N content. Our results of Nr loss from cropland align with this observation, as we noticed that a significant portion of applied N is lost through runoff (40%), which then gets reintroduced into croplands, contributing to the notable increase in irrigation-N. The N input increase in croplands between 2000 and 2020 has led to fluctuating overall Nitrogen Use Efficiency (NUE) ranging from 46% to 57%. Between 2000 and 2020, the overall Nr loss into the environment increased from 9.31 Tg-N to 14.51 Tg-N. In the year 2000, of the total Nr losses (*i.e.*, 9.31 Tg) into the environment, 42% went into the atmosphere and 58% into the hydrosphere. This has since altered to a release of 39% into the atmosphere and 61% enter the hydrosphere of total 14.51Tg-N in year 2020. In the big picture, for the year 2020, the greatest amount of N is lost to the environment as nitrites and nitrates in runoff (40%), followed by ammonia emissions to the atmosphere (32%) and N leaching (20%). Our study demonstrates the need to quantify Nr losses into the atmosphere, as it has direct impacts on human health and climate. In particular NH₃ emissions from the agricultural sector needs to be further studied, with our estimates suggesting the main polluters are fertilizers (56 % of NH₃-N), manure application (28%) and atmospheric deposition (12%). A detailed spatio-temporally varying emissions inventory for NH₃ will be essential for

predicting secondary PM_{2.5} formation as well as to study ecosystem damages occurring from dry and wet deposition of reactive nitrogen species.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To reduce agricultural emissions' pollutant impacts on health and the environment, we must cut fertilizer usage without compromising food and fuel security. To determine the optimal fertilizer application per unit area it is crucial to investigate crop-specific type fertilizer application rate, and application techniques to identify the main sources of higher emissions. Studying the relationship between emissions and deposition is vital for optimizing nitrogen inputs in agriculture. Understanding this correlation helps manage environmental impact and promote sustainable agricultural practices.

Figure 1 shows the Environmentally Extended Input-Output Accounting (EEIOA) from Indian cropland pool. Subsector includes all the inputs into the cropland. Outputs includes N flows from agriculture sector into different media i.e., atmosphere, hydrosphere and terrestrial (values are in Tg-N).

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RAJASTHAN COVID-19 AIR QUALITY STUDY: SATELLITE AND GROUND DATA ANALYSIS

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Keywords: Covid-19, Satellite Data, Ozone, Health, Air pollutant

ABSTRACT

Especially in developing countries where lots of Air pollutant exist but the Ground based ozone is a harmful pollutant for urban populations. This significantly increases the risk of heart, lung diseases and affects agricultural products. In India, a nationwide Shutdown was imposed from (24.03.2020 to 31.5.2020) to prevent the spread of COVID-19. The lockdown changed air pollution on different continents. Here, we present changes in two of the most important air quality-related nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and Ground based ozone (O₃), from satellite (NASA) and (CPCB) observations during the Lockdown (April–May 2020) and release periods (June–September 2020) in Western part of India to study baseline emissions when anthropogenic sources declined significantly. NO₂ levels significantly decreased during the lockdown due to the lockdown of public transportation and industrial activities. The most substantial declines were observed in the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) region and Western India's industrial and transport zones. Additionally, a similar rise in Ground based ozone concentrations has been observed during that period. A significant drop has been found in NO₂ in Jodhpur, Jaipur, and Udaipur. As Shutdown restrictions were eased during the opening period, NO₂ concentrations gradually increased and ground based ozone decreased in most of the city in western part of India. Consequently, this investigation underscores the need for prioritizing pollution mitigation strategies. It underscores the significance of enforcing stringent regulations to oversee the origin of man-made pollutants, with special emphasis on controlling emissions from both the transportation and industrial sectors.

STUDY OF EFFECTIVENESS OF AIR CHANGES IN A TYPICAL LABORATORY
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Keywords: Air change per hour (ACH), Effective dilution, Computational fluid dynamics (CFD).

INTRODUCTION

Airborne radioactive materials are often encountered in the workplace environment during normal operational state in any radiological facility. Their concentration is generally controlled by the engineered safety features such as forced ventilation system or sometimes dilution. Based upon this, air change per hour (ACH) is decided in these workplaces during both normal and off-normal conditions to prevent any occupational exposure to the radioactive aerosols. Aerodynamic behaviour of aerosols does not follow the behaviour of air streamlines exactly, and thus the question on the appropriateness of selection of ACH based on the rule-of-thumb approach of dilution arises for a relatively complicated geometry. In the present work, we used a computational fluid dynamics model coupled to aerosol dynamics software (ANSWER) to estimate the effective dilution rate for different potential release locations in a typical radiological facility. Our method involved detailed simulation of dispersing aerosol particles in a typically chosen radiological laboratory of such a facility to analyse.

METHODS

A finite volume-based software ANSWER (Patankar 1980; Runchal 1987; Versteeg and Malalasekara 2007) that solves the full 3-D Navier-Stokes equations, for both incompressible and compressible fluids is used to simulate the geometry for some accidental release of $10^{12}/sec$ for 100 sec with lognormally distributed aerosol population having CMD=300.0 nm and GSD=2.1 nm as shown in figure 1. ANSWER solves an integro-differential equation (master equation) that covers the aerosol microphysical dynamic processes with different sub modules, each of which have been validated with respect to their analytical and/or experimental solutions by Rajagopal et al. (2018).

Figure 1: Layout of a typical laboratory.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 2 gives the information about the evolution of aerosol concentration in the laboratory for 6 ACH. It is observed that even after the 6000 sec of the release, the average concentration inside the room remains of the order of 10^7 particles/m³ for release location R2. Similar study is carried out for different source locations as well. For release location RDC3, after 4000 sec from the release the concentrations die out sufficiently and reaches $\sim 10^4$ particles/m³. Thus, the time required for reduction in aerosol concentration is much smaller than that for the release location R2.

Therefore, the source location plays an important role in the accumulation and removal process of aerosol particles inside the laboratory because of the nonuniformity in flow and association of different aerosol microphysical processes. This observation may be utilised deciding the ACH value for a laboratory in such a way that the recommended working level concentration may be restored within optimum time.

Figure 2. Variation of number concentration with time with inclusion of aerosol dynamics in ANSWER when release location is R2(left) and RDC3(right).

CONCLUSIONS

Our results imply that inclusion of aerosol microphysical processes in the flow dynamics may be crucial to determine the effective dilution rate of aerosol concentration in a geometry (with partitions and non-uniformity w.r.t. inlet/outlet locations) and therefore minimizing the occupational exposure.

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EMISSIONS FROM TRADITIONAL VERSUS GREEN FIREWORKS OVER AHMEDABAD: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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Keywords: Organic aerosols, Green crackers, Air quality, Pollution reduction

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, global concern has grown over the impact of air quality on health and the environment due to increased pollutants from activities like transportation, industries, and construction. Initially, research focused on the long-term effects of these emissions. However, recent attention has shifted to short-term events like annual firecracker burning during festivals. Firecrackers emit not only primary fine particles but also gases like SO₂, NO_x, VOCs (precursors of secondary particles), and metals, causing visibility issues and health risks by penetrating deep into the respiratory system. Fireworks are the integral part of celebrations like New Year's Eve, the Lantern Festival in China, and Diwali in India, etc.

The green cracker policy of the Indian Supreme Court, introduced in the year 2018, has sparked a comparison between traditional and 'green' firecrackers. These 'green' firecrackers are engineered to minimize the release of particles, sulphur dioxide, heavy metals, and noise, thereby reducing their adverse environmental and health effects. The present study undertakes an analysis of non-refractory particulate matter (NR-PM_{2.5}) emissions during periods of both traditional and green firecracker usage over Ahmedabad. By comprehending this analysis, we evaluate the efficacy and impact of green crackers, thus progressing towards more conscientious and environmentally friendly celebrations.

METHODS

We conducted a study from October 23rd to October 25th, 2022, with a focus on October 24th (Diwali). The research was carried out at Physical Research Laboratory (PRL), Ahmedabad (23.0°N, 72.6°E, and 49 m above sea level). PRL's location, around a kilometre away from residential areas and surrounded by educational institutions, enables diverse air sampling.

We employed HR-ToF-AMS to gather real-time size-segregated chemical info on NR-PM_{2.5}, in V mode (DeCarlo et al., 2006). An adapted PM_{2.5} cyclone and diffusion dryer ensured proper particle capture and dry air. After collecting data, we analyzed it using special software – SeQUential Igor data RetRiEval (SQUIRREL) and Peak Integration by Key Analysis (PIKA) written in IGOR (Wavemetrics, Inc., Lake Oswego; Canagaratna et al., 2007). These programs helped us figure out the mass concentrations of different component in the air, like organic aerosols (OA), sulphate (SO₄²⁻), nitrate (NO₃⁻), ammonium (NH₄⁺), and chloride (Cl⁻).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

During the study conducted over Ahmedabad, a considerable degree of variability was noticed in the mass concentration of NR-PM_{2.5}, ranging from 7.6 to 178.2 µg/m³, as well as in its individual components such as OA, SO₄²⁻, NO₃⁻, NH₄⁺, and Cl⁻, which exhibited ranges of 4.6–147.6 µg/m³, 1.1–28.7 µg/m³, 0.1–4.9 µg/m³, 0.3–16.8 µg/m³, and 0.0–12.1 µg/m³, respectively, over the study duration.

In 2017 at PRL, it was observed that there was a sudden increase of 3.5 times higher NR-PM₁ mass concentration due to extensive firecracker combustion (Rastogi et al., 2019; Singh et al., 2019). However, this study from the year 2022 exhibited an increase of ~1.8 times mass concentration of NR-PM_{2.5} during Diwali periods, as illustrated in Table 1, which is very less compare to year 2017. Furthermore, we have compared the mass fraction of organic aerosols (OA), which was the dominant species during both years. In the year 2017, the mass fraction of OA was observed to be 65±14.1% during non-Diwali period, whereas 85±4% during Diwali period (Rastogi et al., 2019). However, in year 2022 it was 66±8% during non-Diwali period and 66±5% during Diwali period which shows that mass concentration has increased but fraction of OA remain similar. These observations can be attributed to the implementation of the green cracker policy mandated by the Supreme Court of India in 2018.

Pre-2018, conventional crackers spiked pollution, elevating NR-PM₁. Post-policy, eco-friendly crackers with reduced metal, sulphur, nitrogen, and oxygen-rich compounds showed drastic reduction in NR-PM_{2.5} loads. Our study showed the positive effects of these changes.

Table 1. Comparison of mass concentration and mass fraction of both year's study period.

Component	NR-PM ₁ (2017)				NR-PM _{2.5} (2022)			
	Non Diwali	Diwali	Non Diwali	Diwali	Non Diwali	Diwali	Non Diwali	Diwali
	µg/m ³		Mass fraction (%)		µg/m ³		Mass fraction (%)	
PM	17.4 ± 8.8	88.5 ± 42.1	-	-	27.1 ± 20.2	47.9 ± 25.5	-	-
OA	11.7 ± 7.4	68.4 ± 32.6	65 ± 14	85 ± 4	18.6 ± 16.1	32.1 ± 19.1	66 ± 8	66 ± 5
SO ₄ ²⁻	3.6 ± 0.7	11.6 ± 6	23 ± 9	13 ± 2	5.3 ± 2.5	9.9 ± 5.7	23 ± 7	22 ± 7
NO ₃ ⁻	0.5 ± 0.5	2.3 ± 1	4 ± 2	4 ± 1	0.9 ± 1.0	1.9 ± 1.0	3 ± 1	4 ± 1
NH ₄ ⁺	1.3 ± 0.3	1.6 ± 0.4	9 ± 3	2 ± 2	1.9 ± 1.2	2.8 ± 2.3	8 ± 2	6 ± 2
Cl ⁻	0.2 ± 0.2	4.6 ± 3.1	1 ± 1	4 ± 2	0.4 ± 0.8	1.2 ± 1.8	1 ± 1	2 ± 2

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the study explored the mass concentration of NR-PM_{2.5} during Diwali and provides valuable insights into the impact of firecracker emissions on air quality. Looking back to 2017, Diwali celebrations were associated with a substantial increase in particle mass due to extensive firecracker use. However, our study's findings in 2022 showed a different picture, showing less emission of NR-PM_{2.5} on the day of Diwali compare to pre-policy years.

This reduction in particle emission highlight the positive impact of eco-friendly firecrackers adhering to the green cracker policy. These crackers contain fewer pollutants like metals, sulphur, and nitrogen, while incorporating oxygen-rich compounds. In essence, using cleaner firecrackers has improved Diwali air quality. This demonstrates that regulations and innovative approaches can reduce pollution, making cities healthier and cleaner. However, further research on spatial scale is needed to substantiate the impact of green crackers.

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**SOURCES DRIVING MULTI-SCALE EMISSIONS OVER INDIA: AN APPLICATION OF THE
SPECIATED MULTIPOLLUTANT GENERATOR (SMOG)-INDIA**

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Keywords: Emissions, SMOG, air pollution, fuel-technology linked emission factors, BC.

INTRODUCTION

Emission inventories are essential tools for understanding the causes and consequences of air pollution and climate change and developing mitigation policies and agreements central to public health and ecosystem protection. Global emission inventories have strengths including addressing a comprehensive list of emission sectors, completeness of pollutant lists, transparent and consistent emission estimation methodologies, and common spatial resolution of data. However, they typically cannot capture region-specific activities and practices, especially those occurring in the informal economy at sub-country scales. Further, the spatial and temporal distributions of emission releases critically influence resulting air pollution and its impacts, as well as the design of effective mitigation strategies. SMOG-India, a new integrated emissions inventory management system (EIMS) for India comprises a database management system, an emission calculator module embedded with robust sectoral methodologies, and a query-based web interface for visualization. This work will illustrate an application of SMOG-India on analyzing source-sector contribution to multi-scale emissions to understand implications for air quality policy.

METHODS

Sectoral activity data are derived from a comprehensive collection of input datasets, including field surveys, measurements, and secondary sources like industrial production, vehicle registration, crop production, and population data. These inputs are used to estimate monthly emissions from five significant sectors: power plants, industry, transport, residential, and agriculture, all for the year 2019. Emissions are then distributed at a high spatial resolution of 5x5 km using sector-specific spatial proxies. These proxies include data related to road networks, urban and rural population counts, plant coordinates, croplands, and urban built-up areas. This high spatial resolution allows for the evaluation of emission impacts and source contributions at city, state, and national levels simultaneously.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Here we evaluate how multi-scale emission mitigation can be used for effective air pollution control by comparing dominant sources impacting emissions at two scales, those of cities and state levels. The National Clean Air Programme (NCAP, Ganguly et al., 2020) targets 122 cities in exceedance of India's national ambient air quality standards (NAAQS). It seeks to implement city-wide mitigation plans to reach an ambitious 20-30 % reduction in the time frame of 2024. We evaluate primary PM_{2.5} and black carbon (BC) emission sources to understand what mitigation strategy might be suitable at these two scales.

Illustrating this approach with an example, sources impacting BC emissions at geographically distinct regions, at state and megacities (Figure 1). A notable finding is that typically, sources impacting emission differ from each other at city and state scales. While formal economy sectors like thermal power, industry, and transport emissions together are dominant at the city scale, being focussed upon in the NCAP, those from informal sectors like residential biomass combustion, agriculture residue burning, and brick manufacture dominate at the state scale. For example, agriculture residue burning and residential sectors dominate at state levels of ~70% in Telangana and Punjab, while diesel vehicles and industries (formal and informal) dominate at the city-level levels of ~80% in Hyderabad and Amritsar.

Targeting a particular sector (or sectors) for effective mitigation of any pollutant, in this case BC, requires a multi-scale emission analysis. This is because the dominant contributors to BC vary at different spatial scales. Consequently, the best approach to control BC emissions is keenly tied to the residential sector and brick

production and would be very negligibly impacted by emissions from diesel vehicles, which occurs as a dominant signature at the city level for Lucknow.

The high resolution of SMOG India allows for an evaluation of emission intensity in grids that lie within city boundaries, and those in adjoining rural areas. Typically, cities are understood to be high-emission zones. This is true for some megacities, like Mumbai and Hyderabad (Figure 1b). However, for others like Lucknow, Jaipur, and Amritsar, there is minimal contrast in emission intensity between the city and their adjoining rural areas.

Figure 1(a) Source contribution to BC emissions at state and city levels. (b) BC emissions at megacities and adjoining areas

CONCLUSIONS

Emissions from formal economy sources (industry, thermal power, and transport) control city-level emissions while those from the informal economy (residential, agriculture residue burning, and brick manufacture) control state-level emissions. Urban conglomerates and rural areas can both contribute to high emissions, and the general assumption of low emissions in rural areas may not be valid. Importantly, limiting mitigation to city-level actions would not be sufficient to tackle air pollution in India.

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COMPARATIVE STUDY OF SUB-MICRON PARTICLE REMOVAL USING AIR FILTERS AND ELECTROSTATIC PRECIPITATOR

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Keywords: Air purification, Sub-micron particles, Air filters, Electrostatic precipitators

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution has emerged as a critical global concern, significantly affecting human health and environment. With increasing urbanization, industrialization and population growth, the release of hazardous particles and gases into the atmosphere has increased. Particularly, in developing countries like India, numerous cities are ranked among the most polluted globally. To address this pressing issue, innovative air pollution control technologies are essential for both indoor and outdoor environments. In this study, a systematic investigation is conducted for characterizing removal efficiencies of filtration and ionization-based technologies. Various locally available air filter medias were evaluated for overall and size-dependent efficiency and pressure drop. Their performance results are compared with ionization technology such as electrostatic precipitator (ESP).

METHODS

The experimental setup is followed ISO-16890 standard test aerosols to evaluate the removal efficiency of air filters and ESP. A Collison nebulizer (CH Technologies Inc, USA) having a 6-jet nozzle was used to generate microdroplets from KCl salt solution. These microdroplets were carried by nitrogen gas (99.997%) at a flow rate of 8.6 LPM. Further, microdroplets were passed through a diffusion dryer to reduce moisture content below 40% relative humidity (Sebastian et al., 2021), so as to produce theoretically one dry aerosolized particle. Subsequently, the aerosol stream was diluted (50%) with highly pure nitrogen gas in a cylindrical chamber. These diluted particles were challenged to evaluate filter media performance in a specially designed custom-built Air Filter Holder (AFH) to ensure uniform particle collection. With a maintained flow rate (17.17 LPM) and face velocity (0.5 m/s), the isokinetic sample was drawn to aerosol measuring research-grade instrument for characterization of particle concentration. The filter media were tested with a SMPS instrument, specifically a long-differential mobility analyzer (long-DMA, Model 3938L50, TSI Inc., MN, USA) at 0.59 LPM, was used to classify the mobility diameter of particles in the range of 13 nm to 420 nm. Similarly, for evaluation of indigenously designed lab-scale ESP (Designed configuration: single-pass axial flow; cross-section: square; full width: 43 mm; length: 150 mm; central discharge electrode radius: 0.1 mm), the AFH was replaced with ESP and the remaining setup was kept similar as it was done for the air filter testing. The ESP with an axial aerosol velocity of 0.15 m/s was used for the evaluation.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The efficiencies of different air filters (i.e., HEPA, fine and pre-filter) were studied to check the removal of salt particles generated from the 0.2M KCl solution and results are shown in Figure 1. The study was performed at a flow rate of 17.17 LPM and face velocity of 0.5 m/s using 6-jet Collison nebulizer. The generated particles were challenged on various filter media for detecting particle removal efficiency. The removal efficiency of different filters was found to be 99.997%, 60-90% and <30% for HEPA, fine and Pre-filters, respectively (shown in Figure 1). Similarly, the initial pressure drops were 2346, 168 and 45 Pa for HEPA, fine and Pre-filters, respectively. Different efficiencies and corresponding pressure drop might be mainly due to characteristics of the individual filter. HEPA filters often are densely packed, fine filters with fibres are medium packed, whereas pre-filters are loosely packed. Effective fiber diameter in the range of 1-10 μm , 10-30 μm and 30-60 μm for HEPA, fine and Pre-filters, respectively. Also, HEPA filters are less porous compared to fine filters and pre-filters are highly porous. Further, literature suggested that particle collection efficiency of the ESP is as high as 95% for minimum flow rate of 10 m^3/min at an ionization voltage of 8 kV with collection plates at 7 kV (Kim et al., 2013). The performance of an Electrostatic Precipitator (ESP) was evaluated by varying applied voltage (8, 9, and 10 kV) to assess its efficiency. It was found that, the highest efficiency of 74% was achieved at 10 kV, specifically within the particle size range of 13 to 400 nm. This outcome can be attributed to the ESP's filtration efficiency, which relies on factors such as migration velocity, residence time, and the voltage applied across the discharge electrode and collection plate.

Figure 14. Particle removal efficiency for tested filters and ESP using KCl salt (Experimental conditions: Salt concentration = 0.2 M, Face velocity = 0.5 m/s, for ESP discharge electrode at 8, 9 and 10 kV).

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a comparison between air filtration and ionization technologies was performed to identify suitable technology for mitigating indoor air pollution. Based on five different flat air filter media testing, it is concluded that fine filters should be used in air filtration systems. The HEPA filter showed a removal efficiency of 99.997% for particles ranging from 13 nm to 400 nm but the pressure drop was very high. Whereas, for a similar size range the ESP was capable to remove with an efficiency of 74% when the discharge electrode potential is 10 kV. Therefore, the removal efficiency of HEPA filters are much higher in comparison to ESP. This study provides evidence that the air filters are better than ESP for removing submicron particles and should be used for closed indoor environment.

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**DIURNAL VARIATION IN INDOOR AIR QUALITY DUE TO PERSONAL COMFORT SYSTEMS-
A CASE STUDY**

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Keywords: Indoor air quality, climate impact, carbon footprint, energy efficiency.

INTRODUCTION

With the increasing amount of time people spend indoors, the significance of indoor air quality has surged, aligning with the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG 3) which emphasizes well-being and good health. Ensuring optimal indoor air quality is pivotal in this regard. Personal comfort systems (PCS), a popular choice in recent times, have become integral to our indoor environments. However, a critical gap exists in studies that comprehensively assess their impact on user health and the environment. This study aims to address this gap by investigating the influence of personal comfort systems- fan heaters, on indoor air quality. Employing cost-effective sensors, we meticulously monitored various indoor air quality parameters in unoccupied rooms, with and without the device in operation. The findings underscore the adverse effects of these heaters on indoor air quality, shedding light on potential health implications for users. Beyond health concerns, these devices significantly contribute to environmental challenges. Their high energy consumption levels result in a substantial carbon footprint, further exacerbating climate-related issues. Notably, several studies have underscored that the improper design and operation of PCS can lead to increased energy consumption, negating their intended energy-saving benefits (Rawal et al., 2020). Consequently, this study delves into the carbon footprint of these devices, elucidating their detrimental impact on our climate. Moreover, personal space heaters, including electric fan heaters, inherently exhibit inefficiency, demanding high wattages to achieve the desired effect, even when placed in close proximity to the user (Zhang et al., 2015). This inefficiency underscores the urgency of assessing and addressing their environmental repercussions, while also highlighting the need for more sustainable alternatives in the pursuit of healthier indoor environments and a greener planet.

METHODS

The study was conducted in the hostels of IIT Kanpur during the winter season. A low-cost sensor was employed to monitor the indoor air quality. The sensor was calibrated with standard procedures before the measurements were carried out. The low-cost sensor was used to measure parameters such as TVOC (Total Volatile Organic Carbon), PM (Particulate Matter), CO₂, temperature, and humidity. The study was conducted in four vacant rooms. The monitoring was done in two sets, the first, without the application of the device, and, the second, when the device was in operation. The data from the sensor was retrieved and analysis was carried out. The diurnal variation of various air quality parameters was analyzed in four vacant rooms having the same monitoring period. To provide a comprehensive overview, the data of different air quality parameters was averaged for these four rooms, creating average plots to illustrate the trends. Notably, the presence of the fan heater resulted in a substantial reduction in PM_{2.5} levels. Conversely, TVOC levels exhibited a consistent increase with the usage of the heater. Moreover, the application of the fan heater introduced observable differences in CO₂ levels within the rooms. Additionally, humidity levels experienced a notable decrease, while temperature levels showed a significant rise in response to the heater application.

Figure 15:Diurnal variation of indoor air quality parameters with the application of fan heater.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Notably, the presence of the fan heater resulted in a substantial reduction in PM_{2.5} levels. Conversely, TVOC levels exhibited a consistent increase with the usage of the heater. Moreover, the application of the fan heater introduced observable differences in CO₂ levels within the rooms. Additionally, humidity levels experienced a notable decrease, while temperature levels showed a significant rise in response to the heater application. The phenomenon can be ascribed to the diminishment of particle size resulting from the shift in the dew point. Consequently, this caused a reduction in the size of PM_{2.5} particles, making them undetectable within the sensor's range. The elevation in CO₂ levels can be attributed to the implementation of stringent ventilation practices, typically employed during the winter season. Meanwhile, the rise in TVOC levels can be linked to emissions from various indoor objects, accentuated as temperatures increase with the device's operation. The carbon footprint of the device was calculated to be 1.640 kg of CO₂ equivalent per unit of electricity consumption.

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PM_{2.5} PREDICTION USING MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES BY FILLING SATELLITE AOD GAP FOR INDIA

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Keywords: NCAP, SATELLITE DATA, AOD, GBD, PM_{2.5}.

INTRODUCTION

The National Clean Air Program (NCAP), launched in 2019, targets a 40% reduction in PM_{2.5} levels across 132 non-attainment cities by 2026. While the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) has increased ground monitoring, rural areas remain underserved. To address this, the study integrates satellite data with ground monitoring, using machine learning to fill gaps in daily aerosol optical depth (AOD) data. Despite challenges from cloud cover, the research focuses on India, aiming to estimate daily ambient PM_{2.5} levels from 2017 to 2022. In summary, this research employs machine learning to enhance satellite data, offering valuable perspectives for policymakers and public health officials dealing with the impact of PM_{2.5} exposure in India.

METHODS

We used Machine learning model for filling satellite gaps in aod product and PM_{2.5} prediction by using range of predictor variables like metrological data from era-5, CAAQM data from CPCB and other socio-economic data like DEM, NDVI, Population count were used. To address gaps in AOD observations and estimate daily PM_{2.5} concentrations at a fine geographical resolution (1 km x 1 km), the study employs machine learning techniques. The XGBoost algorithm, chosen for its efficacy in handling numerous predictor factors and filling data gaps, is utilized. Additionally, a random forest model, recognized for its proficiency in managing high-dimensional datasets, is incorporated. To refine the models, GridSearchCV is applied for parameter tuning, and a five-fold cross-validation strategy is implemented post data segmentation into training and validation sets. This stringent validation process ensures the accuracy and applicability of the models in predicting PM_{2.5} concentrations.

Figure 1. Scatter plot of Measured versus Predicted PM_{2.5} values at (left) daily, monthly (middle) and (right) annual scale. The line in red shows the regression line between measured and predicted PM_{2.5}.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

The study evaluated the reliability of gap-filled Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) and PM_{2.5} data, acknowledging challenges in comparing satellite AOD with ground-based measurements due to cloud cover and limited ground-based data in India. By randomly selecting 500,000 valid data points, a robust correlation coefficient (R) of 0.96 was achieved, validating the accuracy of the gap filled AOD data for PM_{2.5} derivation. Evaluation against Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) ground monitoring showed promising results at daily, monthly, and annual scale is 0.86, 0.91 and 0.92 respectively (Figure 1). Biases in annual AOD and PM_{2.5} statistics were revealed, linked to satellite sampling gaps, showcasing regional variations during the National Clean Air Program (NCAP) era (2017-2022).

Figure 2. Spatial pattern of with and without gap for AOD (upper panel) and PM_{2.5} (bottom panel) and its differences during the NCAP era (2017 to 2022).

CONCLUSIONS

The key conclusions of the present study are as follows:

1. Integrating ground-based monitoring methods alongside satellite data can help fill the gaps created by sampling limitations, providing a more comprehensive and reliable understanding of air pollution levels.
2. Accurate measurements of PM_{2.5} exposure are crucial for informed policymaking, as they directly impact health and economic outcomes associated with air pollution.

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REGIONAL AIRSHED APPROACH FOR AN EFFICIENT AIR QUALITY MANAGEMENT IN INDIA

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Keywords: AIRSHEDS, PARTICULATE MATTER, PRIMARY PM_{2.5}, SECONDARY PM_{2.5}, NCAP.
INTRODUCTION

Ambient fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) exposure is a major cause of mortality and morbidity (Balakrishnan et al 2019), thereby adversely impacting the economic development (Cohen et al 2017). Unlike the developed countries, the ground-based monitoring network is inadequate for air quality monitoring and exposure modelling (Van Donkelaar et al 2015; 2016). While the satellite-PM_{2.5} data plays a pivotal role in exposure modelling and health burden estimation in the GBD study (Balakrishnan et al 2019), unfortunately, such data are yet to be accepted (legally) for air quality management by the regulatory agencies across the world. In India, the ground monitoring network maintained by the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) has been expanding rapidly under the National Clean Air Program (NCAP); however, the network is still inadequate to assess regional air quality. Therefore, our study provides the first comprehensive analysis of airsheds in India and highlights the relative contributions of various sectors to primary and secondary PM_{2.5} for the NCAP baseline year.

METHODS

The satellite-PM_{2.5} database was created by converting AOD retrieved by Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectro-radiometer (MODIS) using a dynamic scaling factor from the Modern Era Retrospective and Reanalysis Version 2 (MERRA-2) data. We use the *k*-means clustering method over two decades (2000-2019) of the satellite-PM_{2.5} database to identify the major air sheds in India. The analysis is carried out on a seasonal scale viz., pre-monsoon (Mar-May), monsoon (June-September), post-monsoon (October- November), and winter (December-February). The optimal value of *k* in *k*-means clustering is obtained from the Silhouette score (Rousseeuw 1987) of seasonal PM_{2.5} averaged over the entire duration. We use Python's scikit-learn package to estimate both the Silhouette score and the *k*-clusters. For clustering the data, we check the highest Silhouette score from an initial four clusters to up to a maximum of 12 clusters. The Silhouette Score *S* is defined as

$$S = \frac{b - a}{\max(a, b)}$$

where *a* is the mean intra-cluster distance and *b* is the distance of the nearest sample point that is not part of the cluster from the cluster centroid.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Across the seasons, India has 8-9 major air sheds of varying geographic coverage. In each air shed, the relative share of primary PM_{2.5} to total PM_{2.5} is shown by the background color in Figure 1. In the pre-monsoon season, the relative share of primary PM_{2.5} increased to 40-50% in the IGP and western arid air sheds, and the northern periphery of the large Peninsular India air shed. These regions are affected by dust transported from the western arid regions (Dey, 2020). The Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) behaves either as a gigantic single air shed (e.g., during the pre-monsoon season or as two large air sheds - west and east during monsoon north and south during post-monsoon and north-west and the remaining during winter, North-eastern India is divided into two or three (smaller) air sheds. The western arid region remains an isolated air shed during winter to monsoon, while it becomes part of the northern IGP air shed during post-monsoon. Peninsular India is divided into two air sheds, which vary seasonally. In all air sheds, secondary PM_{2.5} dominates over primary PM_{2.5} in the winter seasons (Dec-Feb).

Figure 1. Relative (in %) contributions of primary pollutants to total $PM_{2.5}$ (shown by the background color) in regional air sheds in India in the (a) winter, (b) pre-monsoon, (c) monsoon, and (d) post-monsoon seasons. Non-attainment cities are marked on the map.

CONCLUSIONS

India has embarked on the NCAP to fight its battle against air pollution. Some earlier research suggests that the air shed approach will improve the air quality at regional and local level. Present work provides the insight of the major regional air sheds in NCAP baseline year. The non-attainment cities lying within an air shed should work together and modify their clean air action plans looking beyond the city jurisdiction.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The ground-based monitoring network is maintained by the CPCB, and the data are freely disseminated. MAIAC AOD data are available from the NASA data portal. Meteorology data are obtained from ERA-5. Digital elevation data are obtained from SRTM. The work on developing satellite- $PM_{2.5}$ product for India is funded by the Central Pollution Control Board.

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A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE PERFORMANCE OF COMMERCIAL AIR CLEANERS

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Keywords: AIR PURIFIER, PARTICLE CAPTURE, AEROSOL, HEPA.

INTRODUCTION

The global COVID-19 pandemic emphasized the seriousness of airborne biological threats, driving the development of air purification technologies like filter-based and ionizer-based systems. Effective indoor air pollution control is crucial, safeguarding human health and reducing the socioeconomic burdens it imposes. Various industries have commercially introduced air purification solutions within this context, each touting exceptional efficacy in mitigating indoor air pollution. Nevertheless, these technologies pivot on distinct principles, prompting the demand for a comprehensive comparative assessment of their performance. This provides an opportunity to meticulously evaluate and refine indoor air pollution control strategies. Additionally, our study aims to shed light on the impact of air purifiers on indoor air quality and their role in mitigating indoor pollution, with a particular focus on their ability to remove particulate matter (PM). We present detailed results on the performance of four commercially available air purifiers, evaluated within a controlled environment at the Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay (IITB). To ensure privacy, the manufacturers' identities are withheld. Notably, such comprehensive studies have been notably lacking in the past, underscoring the significance of our research in advancing understanding and informing future air quality improvement endeavors. (Sawant *et al.* 2000)

METHODS

For a fair and rigorous comparison, all experiments were conducted within a sealed glass chamber (25 m³) (see Figure 1-b) using various air purifiers, with individual baseline measurements taken for background air quality at 308 K and atmospheric pressure. Two distinct real-time air monitoring instruments were employed: Optical Particle size (Model: OPS-3330) and Condensation Particle sizes (Model: CPC-3007), both operating on the principle of light scattering (Made: TSI Incorporated). Prior to commencing the experiments, strict measures were taken to ensure the chamber doors were tightly closed, preventing any external contamination. The real-time monitoring instruments were activated and remained active throughout the experiments. The experimental protocol involved an initial 10-minute period with the air purifier switched off, during which indoor particulate matter (PM) concentration was measured to establish a baseline. Subsequently, the air purifier was activated for the following 20 minutes, after which it was turned off for an additional 30 minutes to allow for relaxation. Continuous monitoring of PM concentration was conducted throughout this time. Each purifier underwent this set of experiments independently, ensuring a robust and comprehensive evaluation.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The assessment of air purifier performance was based on the reduction in particle concentration (Particles/cm³), as measured by the CPC-3007 instrument, which covers a range from 0.01 to >1.0 μm. Additionally, the particle size distribution during the operation of the air purifiers was analysed using OPS-3330, which spans a range from 0.3 to 10 μm. The comprehensive results obtained from the CPC-3007 analysis are visually presented in Figure 1, clearly indicating that air purifiers A, B, C, and D achieved particle concentration reductions of 56.1%, 80.4%, 84.6%, and 15.8%, respectively. Further insights into particle removal efficiency concerning different particle sizes are summarized in Table 2. As evident from Table 2, greater efficiency in particle removal is observed for larger-diameter particles. Conversely, smaller particles pose a greater challenge for effective separation. In summary, the performance ranking of the tested

Table 1. Performance of commercial air purifiers in 25 m³ chamber (As per CPC-3007, 0.01 to >1.0 μm).

Purifier	η_0 (%)	τ (min)	λ_1 (h ⁻¹)	CADR (m ³ /h)		Air Purification Technology Employed
				Estimated	Claimed	
A	56.1	8.6	7.0	174	225	HEPA+ Ionization+ UV
B	80.4	5.3	11.0	284	250	HEPA+ Adsorption
C	84.6	5.9	10.2	255	380	HEPA+ Adsorption
D	15.8	40.1	1.5	37	260	HEPA+ Adsorption

air purifiers follows the order: B > C > A > D. This suggests that HEPA filtration is highly effective for particles larger than 0.3 μm, but achieving efficient capture for particles smaller than 0.3 μm may

necessitate additional improvements. Moreover, these purifiers were proven to have 100% removal efficiency for PM

10. These results are in line with those of past work of Offermann *et al.* (1985)

Figure 1. (a) Temporal decay of particle concentration for different air purifiers (-- indicates the on/off time) (b) Experimental Chamber.

Table 2. Particle removal efficiency (%) for different particle size distributions (according to OPS-333).

Particle Diameter (µm)	0.3	0.9	2.5	5.2	8.0	10.0
A	55.0	51.0	79.2	100.0	100.0	100.0
B	87.1	92.3	97.9	91.7	66.7	100.0
C	85.6	91.1	90.9	100.0	100.0	100.0
D	3.4	7.6	7.1	0.0	50.0	100.0

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, our evaluation of air purifier performance revealed notable differences among tested models, with air purifier B demonstrating the highest efficacy in reducing particle concentration, particularly for larger particles (see Table 2) and high CADR (see Table 1). HEPA filtration was highly effective for particles above 0.3 µm. Particle size emerged as a crucial factor, influencing each purifier's efficiency. The ranking of air purifiers in terms of performance was B > C > A > D, providing consumers with valuable guidance for selecting the most suitable air purifier for their indoor air quality needs. Further research is necessary to enhance the capture efficiency of smaller particles, contributing to improved indoor air quality and health outcomes.

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GASES AND AEROSOLS EMISSIONS FROM FIRED CLAY CLAMP KILNS IN INDIA

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Keywords: Carbonaceous aerosols, Emission factor, emissions, clamp kilns

INTRODUCTION

Brick kilns are often found near the population centres and emit significant amount of gaseous and carbonaceous species, therefore, it is essential to understand its effect on air quality and climate. Fired clay bricks are typically fired in small-scale traditional kilns that burn coal or biomass without pollution controls (Weyant et al., 2014). A recent study by Tibrewal et al. (2023) reports significant presence of clamp kilns, oldest and most traditional form of fired clay brick making, in Peninsular India. Also, very few studies have reported emission factors (EF) from clamp kilns emission making emission estimates uncertain. This study estimates EFs using on-field experiments data and the total emissions from clamp kilns by combining EFs and activity estimates from Tibrewal et al. (2023).

METHODS

The modified form of NCAP-COALESCE sampler (Venkataraman et al., 2020) was used to measure the gaseous and particulate properties. A total of 17 measurements were conducted on clamp kilns of different size and combustion stage. Real time gaseous and optical properties were measured and PM mass was collected on the PTFE, Nylon and Quartz filter papers. Using these filter substrate ions, metals and mass concentrations were obtained. Further mass balance method was used to derive the EF as g of pollutants per kg of fuel burnt. These EFs were then multiplied with fuel consumption in clamp kilns taken from Tibrewal et al. (2023) and emissions at district level have been obtained.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The average emission factor of PM_{2.5}, OC and EC are found to be 2.3 ± 1.1 g/kg, 0.5 ± 0.6 g/kg and 0.05 ± 0.07 g/kg, respectively. We also looked at the optical properties from the real-time instrument data and found average AAE_{370/660} (AAE_{660/880}) values to be 2.6 (1.2). Relatively higher AAEs in the clamp kilns indicate a strong contribution by brown carbon aerosol, likely emitted by biomass combustion, which is used as a supplementary fuel in the kilns.

Total PM_{2.5} emissions from clamp kiln is estimated to be 53.8 Gg y⁻¹ (~25% of total national emission from the FCBK industry). Similarly, BC and OC emission is found to be 7.7 and 2.6 Gg y⁻¹, respectively. Comparing the total emission using EF from this study to that of old emission factors from the literature, we find an overestimation of approx. 4% for CO₂ and CO. However, due to reduced EF of PM_{2.5}, BC and OC, the emission was underestimated by 29%, 89% and 16%, respectively. We observed that top 5 states (Andhra Pradesh, Maharashtra, Madhya Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, and Karnataka) contribute to 84% of these national emissions from clamp kilns. This can be attributed of the dominance of clamp kilns in these states as described in Tibrewal et al. (2023)

Table 1: Emissions (Gg y⁻¹) of different pollutants from clamp kilns in India

State	PM _{2.5}	BC	OC	CO ₂	CO	SO ₂
Andhra Pradesh	13.5	0.67	1.974	12181	425	67
Maharashtra	11.57	0.574	1.691	10437	364.3	57.4
Madhya Pradesh	7.61	0.378	1.112	6865	239.6	37.8
Tamil Nadu	5.83	0.288	0.852	5261	183.6	29
Karnataka	5.7	0.281	0.834	5148	179.7	28.3
Others	8.59	0.429	1.237	7747	270.8	42.5
Total	52.8	2.62	7.7	47639	1663	262

Figure 1: District level emission of PM_{2.5} from clamp kilns in India

CONCLUSIONS

Emission factors from present study can be considered more representative of clamp kilns in South Asia as it covers measurements from all size range and combustion phases of clamp kiln production cycle. Further, the study concludes that the emission from clamp kilns is significant. Although the share of particulate emission from clamp kiln constitutes 20% of total national FCBK emission, the emission in Peninsular areas such as Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu and Andhra Pradesh with high percentages of clamps are higher.

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**DIURNAL VARIATION OF PARTICLE NUMBER CONCENTRATION AND SIZE
DISTRIBUTION OF AEROSOL PARTICLES IN MYSURU CITY, INDIA**

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Keywords: PARTICLE NUMBER CONCENTRATION, NANOSCAN SMPS, SIZE DISTRIBUTION.

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols (ultrafine and fine particles) play a key role in understanding the global climate change and exposure to these particles cause adverse health effects on humans by damaging heart, lungs and even the central nervous system increasing the risk of mortality and morbidity (Slezakova et al., 2013, Gui et al., 2022). The size distribution, mass density, number concentration and surface density are the key parameters of the atmospheric aerosol particles which are significant to study the risk and influence they cause on human health and atmospheric phenomenon. In this study, the particle number concentration and size distribution of the airborne atmospheric aerosol particles in Mysuru City (12.2958° N, 76.6394° E), Karnataka State, India was studied.

METHODS

Particle number concentration and size distribution of the airborne particles in the range 11.5 nm to 365.2 nm were measured in Mysuru City, India during 2020 – 2022 using a NanoScan SMPS(TSI 3910) (Tritscher *et al.*, 2013). Twenty four hours measurements were conducted in two different locations to study the diurnal variation as well as influence of traffic on distribution of aerosols. Measurements at both the sites were done 1 to 2 m above the ground level. Number concentration of different modes of particles i.e. nucleation mode (11.5 – 20.5nm), Aitken mode (20.5 – 100nm) and accumulation mode (100 – 365.2nm) were observed.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The studies were conducted at Location 1, inside the University of Mysore campus, which is slightly free from vehicular pollution with very low traffic and Location 2, a national highway where the vehicular pollution is high. Total concentration of the particles (20.5 – 100 nm) was observed to be higher in the early morning and evening compared to afternoon and night at both the locations which hints the role of traffic in the total concentration. Strong correlation between traffic movement and total concentration was observed only in the morning.

The comparative study of average concentration of different sized particles is shown in the graph (Figure 1). The nature of the graph for size distribution with average particle concentration is showing similar behaviour at both the locations under observation. The particles with size 36.5 nm to 115.5 nm showed higher concentrations. It was observed that particles of size 75 to 150 nm are found to have higher concentration in highway than in case of university campus. But higher sized particles (205.4nm, 273.8nm and 365.2nm) are having slightly higher concentration in campus than in the highway. Possible reason for this is higher sized particles are secondary particles which are formed from the coagulation of the nucleation and Aitken mode particles. And these particles can travel long distance as well.

Total concentration includes the sum of an hourly averaged concentration of particles from 11.5 – 365.2 nm (Figure 2). This gives us an idea about how much particles (in this range) we are exposed to per minute. It has been found that daily average of total concentration shows similar pattern for the diurnal variation in both the locations. Starting from midnight the total concentration shows minimum values in both locations. From 5 – 6 am onwards the value starts increasing with the sunrise, beginning of human activities and vehicle movement with peak value of about 22000 particles/cm³ in campus and 50000 particles/cm³ in the highway and thereafter the concentration has decreased in both the locations. The two possible reasons may be the vehicle movement was observed to be less in the afternoon than in the morning hours (7 – 10 am) and also due to the increase in temperature in the afternoon hours, the particles travel higher in the atmosphere and faster. Since our observation site is near to the ground, we see comparatively lower value in the total

concentration. During late afternoon and evening hours an increase in the total number concentration was observed but not as much as in early morning hours. A strong correlation of total average concentration with anthropogenic activities and vehicle moments was observed mainly in the morning hours. From midnight till sunrise, both the locations showed similar total number concentrations. In fact, from midnight to 4am, college campus is having slightly higher particle concentration than in the highway. This emphasizes the role of traffic and anthropogenic sources in the total concentration.

Figure 1. Size dependent particle number concentration

Figure 2. Diurnal variation of particle number concentration

CONCLUSIONS

The particle number concentration and size distribution of aerosols were studied in Mysuru city. It was observed that the total concentration and size distribution of aerosols are affected by the anthropogenic activities hinting the role of traffic besides this the temperature also plays a key role.

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ASSESSING PROGRESS TOWARDS CLEANER AIR IN DELHI NCR

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Keywords: PM_{2.5}, NCAP, NAAQS, Delhi

INTRODUCTION

In response to India's alarming levels of fine particulate air pollution and the well-documented health repercussions (Balakrishnan et al., 2019), the National Clean Air Program (NCAP), 2019 was launched by the Indian government in 2019. Originally aiming for a 20-30% reduction in nationwide Particulate Matter (PM) concentration levels by 2024, NCAP recently escalated its targets to a more ambitious 40 % reduction by 2026. This study underscores the importance of a comprehensive assessment of air quality improvement in Delhi NCR, specifically focusing on PM_{2.5} ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), driven by the severe health impacts of air pollution. The program's stringent time-bound targets stress the need for monitoring and assessing progress toward NCAP's objectives, necessitating ongoing evaluation to gauge goal attainment. Additionally, this study aligns its timeline (2017-2022) with NCAP's objectives, offering a comprehensive assessment of the strides made. Our study leverages ground-based in-situ measurements for assessing the progress of improvement in PM_{2.5} concentrations in the Delhi NCR region.

METHODS

Data is acquired from the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB)'s Continuous Ambient Air Quality Monitoring (CAAQM) network for ground-based measurements analysis. The extent to which PM_{2.5} levels surpass the national ambient air quality standards (NAAQS) is determined by calculating the monthly percentage of days exceeding NAAQS thresholds for various years within the study timeframe. The methodology excludes stations with over 50% missing data in the observations collected from monitoring sites.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Annual PM_{2.5} concentrations in Delhi were 109.28 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in 2017 and reduced to 104.36 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ by 2021. In 2022, PM_{2.5} levels decreased even further to 98.52 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, suggesting a steady yearly decline in PM_{2.5} levels compared to values recorded in 2017. This comprehensive analysis examined the improvement in PM_{2.5} levels observed in the Delhi NCR region. Figure 1 indicates the monthly percentage of days exceeding the NAAQS thresholds throughout the study period. The highest percentage of PM_{2.5} was 96.8 % in October month in 2019 and the lowest was 16.1% in July 2020. A higher percentage of PM_{2.5} was observed during the winter (Oct-Jan) and relatively less during the summer (Mar-May) and monsoon (Jun-Sept) in Delhi.

Figure 1. Monthly percentage of days exceeding the NAAQS for different years (2017-2022) of Delhi

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the annual PM_{2.5} values in 2021 and 2022 were 4.49% and 9.85% lower than in 2017. Notably, the reduction was observed primarily during the summer, with no significant changes seen during the winter. Mitigation measures should be strengthened further to accelerate initiatives focused on the winter months. Hence, this study plays a pivotal role in tracking progress and informing policy decisions, advancing India's journey toward achieving cleaner and healthier air, a goal of national and global significance.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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AIR QUALITY AND CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACTS OF SUGARCANE DERIVED BIOENERGY PRODUCTION

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Keywords: SUGARCANE, COMPARATIVE LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT, AIR POLLUTION, GREENHOUSE GAS

INTRODUCTION

For energy securities, bioenergy production has been extensively promoted in countries like India (Bhatt et al., 2020). India is the 3rd largest country after China and the USA in terms of bioenergy production (Chauhan and Singh, 2023). Bioenergy production is an energy and resource-intensive process and it has health and environmental impacts due to particulate matter (PM_{2.5} & PM₁₀) and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Shyamsunder et al., 2019). The PM and GHG emissions largely depend upon the type of input (energy and resources), direct and indirect land use during the feedstock production and energy conversion process (Hill et al., 2009). Thus, a systematic life-cycle analysis (LCA) of bioenergy production is necessary to evaluate the air pollution and climate change impact. We have selected sugarcane for this LCA study since India is the world's 2nd largest producer (Hiloidhari et al., 2021) and it has shown promising value for renewable energy generation. Hence, the purpose of the study is to quantify the air pollution and climate change impact with the energy production potential using the LCA tool.

METHODS

Figure 1. Life cycle flowchart for sugarcane system depicting system boundary, different lifecycle stages, inputs, and outputs considered for inventory setup and impact assessment for scenario 1: Sugarcane and sugar production without bioenergy cogeneration, with a focus on the fate of field residues (burning of sugarcane crop residue/trash in the field).

Figure 2 - Life cycle flow chart for scenario 2: sugarcane and sugar production with bioenergy cogeneration focused on the fate of process residues (electricity generation from bagasse and ethanol production from molasses).

The type and fate of residues produced at the agricultural (field residues: crop residues/ trash) and industrial (process residues: bagasse and molasses) stages are considered while developing the two scenarios. The system of interest, the contributing sectors, and the material flows are all defined using the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology according to EMS 14040 and 14044. The life cycle operations that occur before sugarcane cultivation, sugar, bagasse generated electricity, and ethanol production are classified as upstream (input generation) processes, whereas all subsequent processes are considered downstream (input use) processes (see Figures 1&2). A comparative LCA of sugarcane and bioenergy production are compared, with an emphasis on air quality (as measured by particulate matter and other pollutants) and GHG emissions. Air pollutants are being analyzed with a focus on sugarcane residue burning and upstream activities, whereas GHG emissions are being assessed across the entire life cycle. The study is based on 1 tonne of sugarcane as the function unit where the energy and resources are treated as input while emissions to air and products are accounted as output to compile the life cycle inventories as shown in Figures 1 & 2.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 summarises the impacts (air pollution and GHG) resulting from the production and processing of 1 tonne of sugarcane. CO₂, CH₄, N₂O, arsenic, VOCs (volatile organic compounds), and PM are among the air pollutants released by the production of sugarcane and bioenergy (Table 1). The cultivation of 1 tonne of sugarcane results in 8 kg of residue which emits 0.06 kg of PM during open burning. Bagasse and molasses are used for bioenergy production, and it involves a combustion process. The burning of bagasse to produce energy releases PM (1.6 Kg) (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀) along with VOC and CO₂.

Climate change impact: The total life cycle GHG emissions associated with cultivation, transportation, industrial, cogeneration, and ethanol production is estimated to be 1597 kg CO₂eq with 97% from the cultivation stage. The GWP for upstream processes has been estimated to be 20.45 kg CO₂eq. The highest share of GWP from upstream and downstream processes are contributed by the pre-cultivation (19.36 kg CO₂eq) and cultivation (1529.48 kg CO₂eq stages respectively). The use of sugarcane-derived bioenergy facilitates the reduction of GHG emissions by 20% for the E20 (80% gasoline with 20% ethanol) fuel and 70% with the bagasse-electricity replacing the coal-electricity. Hence, a complete LCA study of sugarcane cultivation helps to evaluate the emissions impact which will help implement mitigation pathways to reduce air emissions impact.

Table 1. Air pollutant emissions and GWP of different process units from the sugarcane system

Air pollutants	Air pollutant emissions from different process unit					GWP of different process unit	
	Pre cultivation	Pre-industrial	Pre-cogeneration	Pre-ethanol	Upstream	Stages	GWP (kg CO ₂ eq per tonne sugarcane)
Carbon dioxide	18.09	0.927	0.0746	2.00E-02	1.91E+01	Pre-cultivation	19.36
Methane	0.01	3.55E-04	2.35E-05	4.02E-06	1.04E-02	Pre-industrial	0.98
Dinitrogen oxide	0.002	6.62E-05	4.79E-05	6.67E-06	2.12E-03	Pre-cogeneration	0.09
Arsenic	1.86E-06	1.10E-07	1.10E-08	2.33E-09	1.98E-06	Pre-ethanol	1.47
Benzene	0.00013	9.67E-06	9.10E-07	1.49E-07	1.41E-04	Cultivation	1,529.48
Cadmium	2.54E-06	3.97E-08	4.57E-09	1.07E-09	2.59E-06	Transportation	13.82
Ethylene oxide	2.08E-07	7.51E-08	4.12E-10	6.17E-11	2.84E-07	Industrial	21.98
Formaldehyde	0.0001	3.65E-06	2.82E-07	1.32E-07	1.04E-04	Cogeneration	8.785524
Nickel	0.00006	1.29E-06	1.21E-07	5.14E-08	6.15E-05	Ethanol production	1.137584
PAH	0.00001	4.53E-07	7.05E-08	9.43E-09	1.05E-05		
PM	0.0095	4.51E-04	3.17E-05	5.71E-06	9.99E-03		

CONCLUSIONS

The LCA study helps to quantify the air pollution and climate change impact of sugarcane-based bioenergy. From the study, it can be concluded that among the downstream processes, pre-cultivation causes the highest environmental impact which involves the production of urea and electricity for sugarcane cultivation. Hence, the life cycle analysis acts as a vital tool to identify and evaluate the hotspots across the production chain. The concluding trade-off will aid in the evaluation of the net environmental impact and support decision-making. Scaling such outcomes to the state or national levels can help establish the co-benefits for energy security and environmental health benefits.

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HISTORY, RATIONALE AND DESIGN BASIS OF OUTDOOR AIR CLEANING SYSTEM IN DELHI

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Introduction

In order to combat worsening air pollution episodes in megacities, equipping the society with a suitable clean air delivery technology will be a helpful step, among a portfolio of measures. The conception of a design of outdoor air cleaners began to be discussed in scientific circles since 2015 (Cao et al. 2015). It was quite clear from engineering and mathematical considerations that high-throughput clean air delivered into ambient domain, could travel significant distances to supply purified air to public. This amounts to creation of a clean air zone by technological means. In view of the acute air pollution events faced in the city of Delhi and other places during winter, there were ongoing efforts by central agencies to explore the outdoor air cleaning technologies. Upon careful examination of the engineering basis of various proposals, it was clear that the system proposed by the group of aerosol scientists from the University of Minnesota, had the suitable Clean Air Delivery Rate (CADR), following as it were, from established filtration principles. Hence it was considered suitable for a pilot study for assessing its performance in ambient domain of Delhi. The design concept was provided by the Clean Air Care CCL set up by the University of Minnesota faculty, and the systems were installed by Tata Projects Limited with technical support from IIT Bombay. The two units, one at Anand Vihar and another at Connaught place are funded by the Central Pollution Control Board and the Delhi Pollution Control Committee, respectively. IIT Bombay conducted the detailed performance evaluation studies of the system itself as well as that at various distances from it. The objective was clear: Evaluate the range of impact and the air cleaning efficiency for PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ at different distances from the installed facility, in the ambient domain.

Methods:

Features of the MSACS

The MSACS operates on the principle of sucking polluted air from top of a chimney, clean the air by passing through an assembly of filters and release the cleaned air at the breathing level of general public. It has four main components: (i) A 20m tall and 8m wide square tower lets in the polluted draft air, (ii) a two layered, specially arranged Novel Geometry Filtration System (NGFS), covering an area of ~1600 m² removes the PM_{2.5} (iii) 40 axial fans provide power for the suction to maintain an air flow rate of 3.6 10⁶ m³/h (=1000 m³/s) and (iv) rectangular release outlets at the ground level eject the clean air into the ambient atmosphere at the breathing height of the public. Additionally, Data Acquisition System is installed to continuously record the operating parameters of the system. The NGFS is specially designed to provide low pressure drop (initially about 30 Pa) and high efficiency (>85%) of removal of PM_{2.5}. The facility covers a footprint of 45mx45m. The air jet is ejected on all 4 sides through rectangular opening of size 23mx4.2m at an area averaged ejection velocity of 2.6 m/s. The design based Clean Air Delivery Rate is ~960 m³/s.

Performance evaluation:

Both the systems were commissioned in September 2021. Several post commissioning tests including frame strengthening to minimize filter dislodging, leak detection and rectification were carried out. Flow rates, pressure drops and intrinsic and buffer zone PM filtration efficiencies were regularly monitored to estimate CADR. The performance of the system in the ambient domain was evaluated by field measurement campaigns using PM monitors and meteorological instruments. CFD based modelling estimates have also been carried out to assess the impact in ambient domain, influence of topographic features and meteorological parameters. The studies were completed at the end of September 2023. Wealth of data collected during the study on the effect of meteorological parameters, effect of seasons and fluctuating pollutant levels etc. were subjected to elaborate statistical analysis to obtain estimates of impact of the Tower on the air quality improvement at various distances.

Fig.1. Installed Medium Scale Air Cleaning System at Connaught Place

CONCLUSIONS

The project had a strategic achievement of setting up a first of its kind in the world through a multi-institutional collaboration within a short time frame of 10 months. The internalization of the knowledge and practical experience by the project partners is another major achievement of this project in the crucial area of air pollution control technology. Innovative concepts based on aerosol science were used in designing this first of its kind system as well as novel methodologies were adopted in evaluating the performance in ambient domain. These have added considerable value to our efforts at ensuring capacity building in the context of air pollution control. Most importantly, there were several technical achievements in terms of establishing the intrinsic system performance of the system as well as data driven assessment of the zone of influence in ambient domain which will go a long way in providing alternative approaches to combat the menace of urban air pollution.

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CFD MODELLING OF PERFORMANCE OF MEDIUM-SCALE OUTDOOR AIR CLEANING SYSTEMS INSTALLED IN DELHI

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Keywords: Air cleaning tower, CFD modelling, zone of influence

INTRODUCTION

Technological solutions for creating clean air zones in human confluence regions should be considered important supplementary options among the portfolio of measures to combat severe air pollution episodes. Outdoor air cleaning is a novel concept and it is essential to explore the suitability of such technological solution in Indian context. For understanding the suitability of such system in Indian ecosystem, Medium Scale Air Cleaning Systems (MSACS) have been installed at Connaught place in Delhi. It was commissioned on October 2021 and performance measurement was started afterwards to understand the capability of the system. System was evaluated for flow rates, pressure drop and intrinsic efficiency of the system and as well as it was evaluated for the performance in ambient domain at various distance.

The CFD modelling has been done to understand the dispersion of clean air in the domain and important of various key parameters that influence the performance of the tower in providing clean air is investigated.

METHODS:

1. Description of CFD model:

Computational Fluid Dynamic (CFD) approach was followed to model the spatial distribution of released air in the areas surrounding the MSACS. A customized CFD software built for this particular problem was used to simulate the flow field around the tower. The three-dimensional incompressible Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) equations are chosen to solve the mean velocity field. Two transport equations for the turbulent kinetic energy and turbulent kinetic energy dissipation rate are also solved for the closure of the governing equations. The velocity of the air emerging from the fans is employed for propagating the clean air in the ambient domain. The PM concentration profile in the effected air is evaluated using the filtration efficiency and ambient PM concentrations typical of wintertime conditions are assumed for solving the scalar advection-diffusion equation. Various wind velocities and topographic scenarios are considered for the analysis. The performance parameter is defined by the percentage change in concentration at a given location brought about by the operation of the ACS during operating scenarios

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The MSACS is located in an area adjacent to the traffic training park (28.62827°, 77.21051°), Baba Kharak Singh Rd, near Gurudwara Bangla Sahib, Hanuman Road Area, Connaught Place, New Delhi, Delhi, India 110001. To the northeast (NE), 50 m is the junction of the Bangla sahib lane to the Baba Kharak Singh road. To the East-northeast (ENE), within 150 m is the ONGC Shivaji Maharaj Stadium station. To the Southwest (SW), at 118 m is the Bangla Sahib Gurudwara. (250 m SW of the MSACS). Some example CFD simulation results are presented in the figures.

Layout of the Connaught Place site with nearest buildings/structures/obstacles

CFD simulation results clearly indicates (as shown in Figure) that wind direction significantly influences the clean air zone. Based on the direction, zone of influence varies in all directions. Most effect is observed in the downwind direction. Other simulation results at various wind speed indicate it performs better in lower windspeed which is generally observed for winter seasons. Detailed results will be present for various scenarios and will be compared with the monitoring results.

CONCLUSIONS

The CFD simulation results under various scenarios indicate meteorological parameters such as wind speed and wind direction influence the dispersion of clean air that eventually affect the clean zones. Various simulation has been done and indicates that clean air zone is impacted by the clean air delivery rate as well as the influence by the near by structures that prevent the clean air to disperse.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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**SEASONAL VARIATION OF AEROSOLS AND METEOROLOGICAL PARAMETERS OVER A
RURAL BACKGROUND SITE IN THE INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN**

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ABSTRACT

Air pollution is a global issue that poses many health risks. The Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) region is one of the most densely populated regions in the World, but ground-based observations of air pollutants and met parameters are highly limited in this region. The IGP region of India faces some of the most severe air pollution problems on Earth that threaten human health, food security, ecosystems, environmental sustainability, and the climate. In the context of reducing air pollutants, their source and adverse effects on the environment and health should be identified. Meteorological parameters and geographical locations are among the most important factors that impact the severity of air pollutants. The aerosol concentration is a measure of pollutants in the atmosphere and their correlation with meteorological parameters at a rural site in IGP, the pollution and met data are examined for the summer season of year 2023. The daily and monthly data of aerosols were obtained from GIOVANNI NASA and met data was obtained from the Automatic weather station a research station of the Purvanchal University Jaunpur, Uttar Pradesh India. Pollutants such as Aerosols (AOD), ozone (O₃), and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), are considered in this study in combination with the meteorological parameters of temperature, relative humidity, wind speed, wind direction atmospheric pressure, rainfall, and solar radiation. Pollutant concentration and meteorological parameter variations were inspected in the form of diurnal and seasonal annual variations. The findings in this study indicate that air pollutant concentration shows an increasing trend and consequently, the air quality has worsened in summer compared to monsoon in Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) in association with the meteorological parameters.

Keywords: AIR POLLUTANT, METEOROLOGICAL PARAMETERS, AIR QUALITY, CLIMATE CHANGE, WEATHER PREDICTION

INDOOR AIR PM_{2.5}, PAHs, AND MICROBIAL CONTAMINANTS – HAZARDOUS HEALTH EFFECTS ON WOMEN

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Keywords: SEASONAL VARIATION, LLCR, PASSIVE METHOD, HEALTH ASSESSMENT.

INTRODUCTION

Indoor air pollution (IAP) has emerged as a significant concern in contemporary times. Given that a significant proportion of the population spends around 90% of their time inside, it has been empirically shown that IAP is associated with a considerable increase in the prevalence of severe morbidity. Women have a heightened vulnerability to the impact of IAP owing to their physiological characteristics and prolonged engagement in domestic activities. (Taushiba et al.,2023). Therefore, in order to evaluate the degree of pollutant concentration and the corresponding risk among women in India, the current research was undertaken.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present study was conducted in the city of Nawab i.e., Lucknow. The study period was divided into two seasons i.e., summer (April, May, and June 2022) and winter (November, December, and January 2022-2023). PM_{2.5} and associated PAHs samples were collected through GF/A 47 mm filter paper with the help of APM 550, Envirotech sampler at a flow rate of 17.5 LPM (liters per minute) for 24 hours (Dwivedi et al.,2022), and carcinogenic risk of PAHs was calculated from LLCR (Lifetime lung cancer risk) equation, while microbial contaminants (bacteria and fungi) were measured from the Petri plate gravitational settling method (passive method) by using different agar media, NA (Nutrient agar) for bacteria while PDA (Potato dextrose agar) for fungi in kitchen, washroom and living room.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the winter season, the concentrations of TPAHs were higher at H5 (298.5 ng/m³) due to various activities happening in households like heating coal, and fuel used in cooking, smoking, and open garbage systems and the LLCR values for BaP were found to be higher at H6 house in the winter season. Bacterial concentrations at dwellings H3 were found to be 4980.21 CFU/m³ higher than the World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines during the summer season. Similarly, the concentration of fungi 524.23 CFU/m³ at households H5 is also beyond the WHO limits and the greatest average concentration during 24 hours was recorded as 209.1 µg/m³ during the winter season shown in Table 1.

S.no	Households	Concentrations of PM _{2.5} (µg/m ³)		TPAHs (ng/ m ³)		Total microbial contaminants load (CFU/m ³)			
						Bacteria (NA)		Fungi (PDA)	
		Summer (PM _{2.5})	Winter (PM _{2.5})	Summer (TPAH)	Winter (TPAH)	Summer (June)	Winter (January)	Summer (June)	Winter (January)
1.	H1	86.6	104.1	25.12	47.1	3014.33	851.87	327.64	91.74
2.	H2	55.2	108.9	34.3	52.5	2752.22	878.08	524.23	104.84
3.	H3	94.6	128.1	69.7	98.7	4980.21	1284.37	458.70	52.42
4.	H4	119.6	202.3	157.88	204.1	2752.22	445.59	511.12	65.52
5.	H5	142.1	190.6	150.97	298.5	2306.62	878.08	524.23	52.42
6.	H6	167.0	209.1	140.26	185.4	2359.	917.40	183.48	12.92

Table 1. Seasonal concentrations of pollutants (PM_{2.5}, TPAHs, and microbial contaminants (bacteria and fungi)

CONCLUSION

The findings revealed that the levels of PM_{2.5} exceeded the recommended thresholds by a factor of 3-4. The highest average concentrations were high during the winter season, kitchen had the greatest dosage rates of both bacteria and fungus, suggesting that women may be more vulnerable. According to LLCR BaP appears to have the highest potential of causing lung cancer in women. This study emphasizes the need for forecasting and creating efficient management plans to reduce the pollutants covered above.

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EFFECT OF COVID-19 RESTRICTIVE MEASURES ON AEROSOLS IN THE INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN REGION

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Keywords: AOD, BC, COVID-19, IGP, SATELLITE REMOTE SENSING

INTRODUCTION

Severe acute Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) has been considered one of the major health disasters of the 20th century (WHO, 2020), which has led to unprecedented challenges to socio-economic reform worldwide. The COVID-19-induced lockdown provided a unique opportunity to investigate the changes in aerosol loading over heavily aerosol-laden regions like the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP). During the initial phases of the lockdown period, nearly all human-related sources of pollution in India were notably diminished (Srivastava, 2020; Pratap et al., 2021). This resulted in a temporary enhancement of air quality, attributed to the decrease in emissions of anthropogenic aerosols and other pollutants originating from industries, transportation, and various human activities. The present study emphasizes the variability in columnar aerosol properties at 10 different cities of the IGP during pre-lockdown (Pre-LD: 1st–24th March), lockdown (LD: 25th March – 31st May) and post-lockdown (Post-LD: 1st–30th June) period of 2020, and further compared with respect to the same period of 2015 – 2019. In addition, the actual change in aerosol levels during the total lockdown period is estimated by eliminating the impact of seasonal variations.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

To assess the impact of lockdown measures on aerosols in the IGP, we have categorized the IGP into three regions: Western IGP represented by Amritsar, Patiala, Delhi and Agra; Central IGP represented by Kanpur, Gorakhpur, Varanasi and Patna; and Eastern IGP represented by Asansol and Kolkata. For the present study, Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) level3 combined DB-DT retrieved daily AOD from Terra and Aqua satellite, and Modern MERRA-2 reanalysis hourly averaged BC mass concentration data are used. The LD period is considered LD(A) and LD(B) depending on the implementation of four phases of the lockdown. LD(A) represents the initial two phases of the lockdown from 25th March to 14th April 2020, while LD(B) represents the latter two phases of the lockdown from 15th April to 31st May 2020. The percentage change (PC) was calculated to quantify changes that occurred during the lockdown phases (i.e. Pre-LD, LD(A), LD(B) and Post-LD) in 2020 with respect to the same phases of 2015–2019, using the following relation:

$$PC = \left[\frac{(Phase)_{2015-2019} - (Phase)_{2020}}{(Phase)_{2015-2019}} \right] \times 100.$$
 In order to remove the seasonal biases and

ascertain the absolute change in AOD and BC levels due to the COVID–19–induced lockdowns, the seasonal influences during the period of 2015 – 2019 were taken as a reference. To eliminate the seasonal influences, we have calculated the percentage change during the lockdown period of 2015 – 2019 with respect to Pre-LD period of 2015 – 2019. Further, the estimated percentage change and the Pre-LD of 2020 is used to normalize the lockdown period of 2020 to ascertain the changes that occurred during this period were only due to the COVID-19 induced lockdown. Based on this an estimation of the absolute percentage change (APC) during the lockdown period was done.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

As the lockdown progressed, all IGP cities witnessed a gradual decline in AOD and BC, which suggests the significant impact of lockdown measures on aerosol loading. During the first two phases of the lockdown i.e., LD(A), the central IGP witnessed a maximum decrease in AOD and BC of 30% and 14.5% followed by the eastern (25.4% and 10.4%) and western IGP (25.3% and 7.5%) (Table 1). During the third and fourth phases of lockdown i.e., LD(B), a further decline in AOD was observed over all the cities, indicating reduced anthropogenic activities. During LD(B), the maximum drop in BC was observed over the central IGP (14.5%) followed by the eastern IGP (10.4%) and the western IGP (7.5%). During this period, the maximum decline in BC concentration occurred at Gorakhpur, Varanasi and Kolkata. During Post-LD period restrictions on public and private transport, industries, and other anthropogenic activities were lifted. It was reflected in the BC measurements where an increase of 6 – 9% throughout the IGP was observed.

Table 1: Percentage change (PC) in AOD and BC concentration over different regions/cities of the IGP during Pre-LD, LD phases and Post-LD period of 2020 with respect to the same period of 2015 – 2019.

Region/Cities	Percentage Change in AOD (%)	Percentage Change in BC (%)
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of the IGP	Pre-LD	LD(A)	LD(B)	Post-LD	Pre-LD	LD(A)	LD(B)	Post-LD
West IGP	11.6	-25.3	-28.4	-3.0	4.02	-7.5	-4.2	6.0
Amritsar	-2.1	-33.7	-37.1	-0.8	1.27	-3.4	-20.2	-5.0
Patiala	13.5	-23.9	-27.3	-2.3	1.65	-10.2	4.1	12.6
Delhi	15.5	-21.0	-22.8	-1.6	6.70	-9.5	-3.6	10.1
Agra	19.4	-22.5	-26.3	-7.1	6.46	-6.6	3.2	6.0
Central IGP	20.4	-30.0	-23.7	-6.1	8.76	-14.5	-7.2	8.2
Kanpur	31.7	-26.6	-24.2	-0.7	12.15	-12.0	-1.6	2.3
Gorakhpur	5.8	-33.7	-25.7	-3.8	5.89	-17.9	-11.6	11.0
Varanasi	30.8	-25.0	-19.2	-10.6	8.44	-15.3	-8.2	10.2
Patna	13.2	-33.8	-25.6	-9.4	5.7	-12.7	-7.4	9.3
East IGP	3.6	-25.4	-21.8	3.4	6.79	-10.4	0.4	8.7
Asansol	8.1	-27.8	-18.9	5.5	6.47	-5.7	3.0	18.0
Kolkata	-1.0	-22.9	-24.6	1.3	7.11	-15.0	-2.2	-0.7

Figure 1. Percentage change (PC) and absolute percentage change (APC) in (a) AOD and (b) BC during total lockdown (LD) period with respect to the same time frame of 2015 – 2019.

During the total lockdown period, both PC and APC show a maximum reduction in AOD in central IGP (26.5% and 38.5%), followed by western IGP (24.9% and 34.6%), and eastern IGP (23.2% and 25.9%). According to APC, the cities of western and central IGP show a large absolute decrease in AOD of 30 – 40% during the lockdown period with the maximum decrease observed in the central IGP cities of Kanpur (43.2%), Varanasi (40%) and Patna (37.5%). The estimated APC indicates a major reduction in BC was observed in the central IGP (18.2%), where Gorakhpur and Varanasi showed a maximum decrease of 19.6% and 18.8%, respectively.

CONCLUSIONS

This study presents a comprehensive analysis of COVID-19 lockdown impact on aerosol properties over the IGP and highlights unprecedented reductions in AOD (~ 40 %) and BC (~ 20 %), due to the imposition of lockdown and subsequent cessation of aerosol sources, by removing seasonal influences. Following the lockdown, most of the cities of the IGP experiences substantial build-up of aerosols as a result of the lifting of restrictions on public and private transports, industries and other anthropogenic activities.

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DEVELOPMENT OF PRIORITIZED CLEAN AIR ASSESSMENT TOOL (PCAT) FOR IDENTIFICATION OF CRITICAL LOCATIONS TO IMPROVE AIR QUALITY

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Keywords: AIR QUALITY INDEX; MITIGATION; AIR POLLUTION; INDIA

INTRODUCTION

The undifferentiated mass concentration of Particulate Matter (PM) often drives the air quality assessment based on National Air Quality Index (NAQI) over the Indian region. The country has a particularly high level of PM pollution, but the impact caused by the undifferentiated PM mass is yet to be comprehended. The PM over the Indian region is composed of chemical components varying in physicochemical properties which are dependent on meteorological conditions, and regionally and seasonally changing emission sources. Though the potential of PM components in causing health risks is still to be adequately understood, it is suggested that the PM components may not be equally important in causing adverse health effects [Daellenbach et al., 2020]. When considering PM mass as the driving factor to describe air quality, there is a possibility that locations having similar PM mass concentrations are placed in the same category of an air quality descriptor, irrespective of the significant concentration of other criteria pollutants anticipated having potential health impacts. Hence, it is essential to include the cumulative impact of all pollutants while estimating the air quality of a region.

METHODS

In the present study, 6 criteria air pollutants monitored across 14 cities spread throughout the geographical expanse of India are considered to evaluate the air quality. The 24-h mean (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, SO₂, NO₂) and 8-h (CO & O₃) concentration of the criteria pollutants at locations under study are obtained from the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB), India website for the winter (Nov 2015-Jan 2016) and summer months (Mar 2016-May 2016). The Indian NAQI is estimated which represents the air quality of a location based on the National Ambient Air Quality Standards followed by CPCB. To identify locations that need immediate control measures among the ones with poor air quality, a Prioritized Clean Air Assessment Tool (PCAT) is developed based on the fuzzy integrated Mitigation Priority Index (MPI). The fuzzy tool is used to deal with uncertainty where the normal probability theory fails due to large computational expensiveness. The present study describes the application of Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) for determining the relative weights of air quality parameters (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, SO₂, NO₂, CO and O₃) and the development of a potential fuzzy membership function by deriving weights through a matrix-based technique rather than assigning them arbitrarily. As part of implementing the AHP method, a pair-wise judgement matrix comprising the relative importance scores based on Saaty's scale are compiled by taking unbiased inputs from a 5-member expert panel. In the present study, O₃ is assigned with the highest weight due to its adverse health impact at lower concentrations, which is also reflected in its 8-h monitoring based on the exposure of the community to the pollutant and its short-term health effects. After calculating the membership category for each of the pollutants, the membership category matrix is built, where each row denotes the severity of the health risk due to various pollutants. To identify various consequences of each of the alternatives on the air quality, an Ordered Weighted Product (OWP) approach is implemented for fuzzy aggregation. Scores are assigned to corresponding membership values to obtain crisp output, which represents the MPI for a specific day.

Figure 1. Flowchart explaining the details of steps involved in development of PCAT.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The daily mean concentration of criteria pollutants averaged over each of the winter and summer months are utilized to estimate the NAQI and compared it with the 24-h national ambient air quality standards (NAAQS)

and WHO guideline values (24-h). Considerably high (3–4 times the NAAQS) daily mean PM_{2.5} concentrations averaged over the winter and summer months are observed during the study period. The daily mean concentration of the PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} averaged over the winter is higher than summer by 7–47% and 20–71%, respectively. The analysis of chemical species demonstrated that SO₂, NO₂ and CO are higher in the winter than summer by 16–50%, 25–70% and 16–85%, respectively. Based on the NAQI estimate, Varanasi is identified as the most polluted city followed by Delhi and Jaipur during winter while Varanasi is followed by Patna and Jodhpur during summer seasons. Among the locations considered, most of the cities are under unhealthy NAQI (value above 100), and the NAQI mostly ranged from moderately polluted to very poor (NAQI between 150–400). The PCAT-obtained MPI identifies the city that requires the most urgent mitigation, incorporating all criteria pollutants’ cumulative effect and considering their anticipated health impacts. Using PCAT, Delhi and Varanasi are identified as critical locations considering NAAQS during the winter and only Varanasi during the summer. However, when more stringent WHO guideline values are adopted, six locations, namely Pune, Patna, Delhi, Jaipur, Jodhpur, and Varanasi are identified as critical during the winter along with Solapur during the summer. The recognition of locations such as Pune and Solapur for mitigation reflects the importance of the cumulative impact of all pollutants which are otherwise neglected.

Figure 2. Variation of NAQI and MPI during winter and summer months. The label inside the graph provides NAQI and MPI categories corresponding to its range.

CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, the daily mean concentration of six criteria pollutants for two consecutive seasons, winter and summer, were utilized to assess the air quality of 14 locations representing the geographical expanse of the Indian region. The daily PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentration at all sites were in violation of the 2009 NAAQS and WHO air quality guideline for PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}; both greatly influencing the NAQI of Indian cities. As obtained from PCAT, Delhi and Varanasi need immediate pollution control measures, taking NAAQS considerations among the cities considered in the present study. Taking into account WHO guidelines, the PCAT led to obtaining seven cities needing prioritized air quality control measures. The assessment from this tool, when integrated with NAQI, provides an effective approach to control air quality from the perspective of potential health benefits.

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LONG TERM STUDY OF ATMOSPHERIC AEROSOL PROPERTIES & THEIR RADIATIVE IMPACT OVER INDO GANGETIC BASIN

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Keywords: Aerosol Optical Depth, Angstrom Exponent, Single Scattering Albedo, AERONET, Indo-Gangetic Basin

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols play a crucial role in the Earth's atmosphere and imposes the various effect on earth's radiation budget, climate, weather, air quality, human health (Jethva et al., 2018), and hydrological cycle (Rosenfeld et al., 2008). The Indo-Gangetic basin (IGB) is one of the most populated and polluted area, with heavy aerosol loading throughout the year. Urban-industrial areas are a primary source of anthropogenic aerosols, but polluted dust can originate from wide range (Masoumi et al., 2013). Several studies have been conducted to better understand the characteristics of aerosols and their radiative effects (Kedia et al., 2018) but still, the Earth's radiation budget remains highly unclear (Kaskaoutis et al., 2016) because the morphology and chemical composition of dust particles are complex. Aerosol optical depth (AOD) having well-known impact on aerosol radiative forcing (ARF), but size distribution of aerosols, single-scattering albedo (SSA), and morphology is also impacted (He et al., 2015). In the present study, the temporal variations of AOD, SSA, ARF, and their size distribution are studied by using AERONET data over three different locations of IGB. The study of aerosol inversion factors (SSA, size distribution parameters, and ARF) are crucial and contribute significantly to climate modelling projections.

METHODS

Three different locations of IGP are considered in this study, namely Jaipur, Kanpur, Karachi. The Jaipur (urban and desert dust influenced region) and Kanpur (urban and highly industrial area) is the metropolitan city of Indian subcontinent. The Karachi is the metropolitan city of Pakistan subcontinental having busiest deep-water ports. AOD, AE, SSA, ARF are taken from the ground-truth AERONET observations for the period 2012-2022. In the condition of no clouds, the uncertainty in the AOD calculation is less than 0.01 for longer wavelengths ($k > 0.44 \mu m$) and less than 0.02 for shorter wavelengths; nevertheless, the uncertainty in the columnar water vapour calculation is considerable and can reach 10% (Dubovik et al., 2000).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Fig. 1 (a-c) show the yearly variation of AOD and AE over three different locations namely Jaipur, Kanpur, and Karachi, respectively for the study period 2012 to 2022. Over the IGB region Jaipur and Kanpur have high AOD > 0.5 and AE > 0.5 suggested that the existence of mixed aerosol loading. However, the higher values of AE > 0.5 also suggested that an abundance of fine mode particles over this region. While relatively low AOD values are reported over Karachi, which indicates that low aerosol loading existence between 2012 & 2022. The higher value of SSA is observed an extremely high (0.98) during the catastrophic dust storm that passed over Karachi on July 5, 2014 (Iftikhar et al., 2018). The range of SSA values are found (0.89-0.976) over Jaipur, which indicating that aerosol particles are more likely to have scattering nature (Payra et al., 2013). In our investigation, SSA values are neither extremely high nor extremely low; rather, intermediate SSA values have been reported across all regions, indicating that particles are both moderately absorbing and scattering.

The yearly variation of ARF at the top of atmosphere (TOA), bottom of atmosphere (BOA), and in the atmosphere (ATM) over Jaipur, Kanpur and Karachi is shown in Fig. 3 (a-c), respectively. The negative values of ARF are found for the TOA and BOA, which indicating a cooling effect over all three locations. Positive values of ARF are found in the atmosphere, which indicating that the warming atmosphere. Fig. 4 (a-c) shows the correlation between AOD and ARF at three different sites. It is found that the ARF is directly

proportion to the AOD with the value of $R^2=57.47\%$ over Kanpur, $R^2= 39.34\%$ over Karachi and $R^2= 0.05\%$ over Jaipur which suggests that the aerosols can modify the Earth's radiation budget significantly.

Figure 18. Correlation between AOD & ARF at Jaipur(a), Kanpur(b), and Karachi(c) respectively for the year 2012-2022.

CONCLUSIONS

The present study mainly focused on the long-term variation of aerosol parameters like AOD, AE, SSA, and ARF over 3 locations in IGP using ground-based AERONET observations for the years 2012 to 2022. The higher values of AOD and AE are found with increasing trend over Jaipur and Kanpur, which suggested that a mixed aerosol loading and an abundance of fine mode particles. However, a comparatively low AOD values is found over the Karachi site with increasing trend, which indicates that a low level of aerosol loading. SSA indicates the scattering and/or absorbing nature of particles, the positive trend of SSA shows abundant of scattering particles over Jaipur and Kanpur. At Karachi, the SSA showed decreasing trend, which indicates the possibility of aerosol particles with absorbing in nature. On the other hand, at Jaipur, the mixing of aerosol particles (scattering and absorbing in nature) is existing because the increasing trend of SSA is found for 440 nm and the decreasing trend is found for other wavelengths. The correlation between AOD and ARF was found which suggests that radiative forcing is affected by aerosol particles into the atmosphere that modify Earth's radiation budget significantly. In addition, a positive trend of radiative forcing over Jaipur and Karachi suggests a significant role in the atmospheric phenomenon (like monsoon circulation and hydrological cycle).

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AEROSOLS AT WORKPLACE: HAZARD, EVALUATION & CONTROL MEASURES TO MINIMIZE EXPOSURE

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Keywords: Control measures, Exposure Limit, Local Exhaust Ventilation (LEV), Capture velocities

INTRODUCTION:

Aerosols are ubiquitous in industrial sectors and are small particles suspended in the air & travel significant distances from the sources generated through various processes and machineries and exists in the form like vapour, dust, mist, fumes, smoke etc. Possibility of generation of aerosols from various operations/processes like construction, generation of high purity materials, designing of different components, chemical and radiological processes, cleaning of heavy components/materials, synthesis of compounds and their characterizations, waste management, healthcare and many research projects etc.

This paper discusses the various operation in a mechanical workshop where multi-dimensional works such as fabrication of components, engraving and designing of micro components, cleaning etc being carried out using various machineries like lathe machines, abrasive water jet, boring, milling & grinding machines, cutting & shearing machines, heat treatment facilities, welding of different components and joints etc. Due to varied operations possibilities of generation of aerosols cannot be neglected in these areas.

Further, effectiveness of Local Exhaust Ventilation and its statutory requirements is also discussed along with a case study focussing on the possibility of generation of lead aerosols in a process involving lead alloy in closed loop system.

HAZARDS:

Inhalation of aerosols containing irritant particles/dust can lead to respiratory discomfort, coughing, and inflammation of the airways and very fine particles (PM_{2.5}) and ultrafine particles (PM_{0.1}) can penetrate deep into the respiratory system and get deposited in lungs or even enter the bloodstream. Aerosols containing hazardous chemicals like heavy metals, or toxic gases can cause systemic poisoning and adverse health effects like cancer etc. Aerosols contributes to air pollution and climate change dynamics. Aerosols released during industrial processes can obstruct visibility and may lead to accidents.

OPERATION GENERATING AEROSOL IN MECHANICAL WORKSHOP

Mechanical workshops encompass a wide range of activities, and the types of aerosols generated can vary based on the specific processes and materials used.

Table 1. Various operations generating aerosols in a Mechanical Workshop

Processes generating Aerosols	Sources
Metalworking Operations	Cutting, grinding, milling, drilling metal surfaces generate metal particles and metal oxide dust
Welding and Soldering	Welding and soldering processes release fumes and gases that contain fine particulate matter.
Machining and Tooling	Milling, turning, and machining for precision work generates fine metal shavings and dust aerosols
Surface Finishing	Sanding, polishing, and spray painting, coatings & solvents used can create aerosols.
Coolant and Lubricant Mist	Coolants, lubricants, and cutting fluids in machining operations generates oil vapours during contact with hot surfaces.
Abrasive Blasting	Sandblasting or water jet or abrasive blasting can produce aerosols by propelling abrasive materials against surfaces, causing particles to become airborne.
Material Handling	Transportation and shifting of materials within the workshop
Cleaning and Maintenance	Sweeping, vacuuming, and use of different cleaning agents

LOCAL EXHAUST VENTILATION SYSTEMS (LEV)

Local exhaust ventilation (LEV) is one of most effective engineering control measure which mitigates the air borne aerosols contaminants by containing or capturing them locally, at the emission point. Its effectiveness of LEV depends on proper hood design, adequate airflow and velocity to maintain effective transport.

Recommended flow rates standards:

Indian Standard (IS): 3103-1975 (Reaffirmed 2004): —Code of practice for industrial ventilation recommends different range of capture velocities are recommended.

Chemical and radiological laboratories mostly use fume hoods as LEVs and its effectiveness is ensured by maintaining an adequate linear face Velocity across its sash front. As per Indian Standards: IS 4209 (2013): — Chemical Laboratories-Code of Safety, IS 4906 (2003): — Code of safety for radiochemical laboratory; AERB Safety Guide No. AERB/RFRS/SG-2 (2015); —Radioisotope Handling Facilities.

CASE STUDY: Airborne concentration of lead obtained in a process involving circulation of lead alloy in a closed loop.

MATERIALS AND METHOD: Air and Swipe sampling were conducted near the system operating with lead alloy circulating in loop at a high temperature at different experimental conditions. Sampling was done using Staplex Pump. The samples were leached out from filter paper and analysed in ICPMS and EDXRF.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS:

As per ACGIH, 2019, Threshold Limit Values (TLV) of lead in the environment is given is 0.05 mg/m³ (Time Weighted Average (TWA)). The measured data shows comparatively less concentration of lead in air samples in comparison to the settled particles in nearby proximity of the loop. The measured value of lead in air doesn't exceed the Threshold Limit Value (TLV-TWA).

Table-2: Lead Concentration in working environment of Lead Operation

Sr. No.	Condition	Concentration in air
1	Air Samples	
	Heating (Pre-experiment) condition of LBE in loop	1.73 x 10 ⁻⁴ mg/m ³
	Circulation condition of LBE in loop	6.3 x 10 ⁻⁵ mg/m ³
2	Swipe Samples	
	On Floor	3.43 x 10 ⁻² mg/m ²
	Near Valve	1.13 x 10 ⁻² mg/m ²
	On Wall	2.34 x 10 ⁻² mg/m ²

Conclusion:

It's important to note that while minimum flow rates and capture velocities are a crucial consideration, the overall design and effectiveness of the LEV system depend on multiple factors and it should meet the necessary standards for worker safety and health. By addressing these safety control measures in a workshop, employers can create a safer work environment, reduce the risk of occupational aerosol exposure, and protect the health and well-being of their workers. The measured value of lead in air doesn't exceed the Threshold Limit Value (TLV-TWA) due to availability of adequate ventilation.

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INVESTIGATION OF HEALTH RISKS ASSOCIATED WITH PM_{2.5} EXPOSURE IN BENGALURU CITY, INDIA

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Keywords: SEASONAL ANALYSIS, WEEKDAY AND WEEKEND, HAZARD INDEX, HEALTH IMPACTS, AIRQ+

INTRODUCTION

Ambient air pollution primarily contributing from fine Particulate Matter (PM_{2.5}) is one of the top environmental risks in India attributing to more than a million deaths annually. The present study evaluates the characteristics of PM_{2.5} at various locations of Bengaluru metropolitan city and assesses the health risk due to PM_{2.5} exposure.

METHODS

Real time PM_{2.5} levels are extracted from reference grade instruments during the period Jan-Dec 2022 from the nine monitoring locations (one at the CSTEP office and eight CPCB Continuous Ambient Air Quality Monitoring Stations) spread across the city (categorized as kerbside, residential and industrial). Seasonal exposures for winter (Dec–Feb), summer (March–May), monsoon (June–Sep), and post-monsoon (Oct–Nov) along with the weekday and weekend impacts are assessed and compared. The magnitude of health risks was accounted by estimating the chronic daily inhalation, hazard quotient, cancer risk and Hazard Index based on risk assessment guidance provided by USEPA. In addition, the probability of occurrence of lifetime cancer risks was evaluated due to continual exposure to PM_{2.5}. Furthermore, the health impacts was estimated using the AirQ+ model developed by WHO.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Bapuji Nagar present along the kerbside had the highest daily mean PM_{2.5} concentration (46.53 µg/m³) while Hombe Gowda with the lowest (25.54 µg/m³) located in a residential area, while all the monitoring stations overshoot the specified exposure limit of 15 µg/m³ (24 h average WHO standards) (Figure 1). Statistically all the three locations are significantly different ($p < 0.05$) based on one way ANOVA test. Similarly, from seasonal analysis (Figure 2.a) it is apparent that, statistically PM_{2.5} levels varied across the seasons. Weekday and weekend concentrations (Figure 2.b) are compared through paired *t*-test and found to be statistically different ($p < 0.05$). Bapuji Nagar exhibited high non-carcinogenic risk while lowest from Hombe Gowda. Finally, risk assessment indicated that more than 3 years of continuous exposure to PM_{2.5}, would increase the likelihood of developing a lifetime average cancer risk. Additionally, health impact assessment revealed high incidence per 100,000 population for restricted activity days, workdays lost, hospital admissions from respiratory diseases and hospital admissions from cardiovascular diseases of 339, 332, 49 and 23, respectively.

CONCLUSIONS

The PM_{2.5} levels are compared across the various locations in the city followed by seasonal, weekday and weekend trend analysis for the year 2022. The health risks from PM_{2.5} exposure was estimated. The results shows that there is a pressing need to focus on controlling the polluting sources across various monitoring sites.

Figure 1. Comparison of PM_{2.5} across various sites. The 25th and 75th percentiles are represented by the box, 1%–99% is represented by whiskers, and the mean is represented by the solid square

Figure 2. (a) Seasonal Analysis and (b) Weekday and weekend trends

Location	CDI	HQ	CR
CSTEP	1.19341E-06	1.99	4.144E-05
Bapuji Nagar	1.86386E-06	3.10	6.472E-05
Hebbal	1.1563E-06	1.92	4.015E-05
Silk Board	1.35997E-06	2.26	4.722E-05
Hombe Gowda	1.02277E-06	1.70	3.551E-05
Jaynagar	1.27209E-06	2.12	4.417E-05
BTM Layout	1.51127E-06	2.52	5.247E-05
BWSSB	1.18255E-06	1.97	4.106E-05
Peenya	1.5669E-06	2.61	5.441E-05
Average	1.34768E-06	2.24	4.679E-05

Table 1. Exposure risk to PM_{2.5} at varied locations of Bengaluru city.

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**A STUDY OF THE ATMOSPHERIC CHEMISTRY OF VOCs AND TRACE GASES: THEIR ROLE
IN THE FORMATION OF SECONDARY ORGANIC AEROSOLS**

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Keywords: Volatile Organic Compounds, Trace Gases, SOA.

INTRODUCTION

Clean air is an essential requirement for the healthy existence of human beings. In the last two decades increase in emissions from industries, agriculture and vehicles have resulted in the enhancement of volatile organic compounds (VOCs), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), carbon monoxide (CO) and other harmful air pollutants (Kumari et al., 2021). VOCs, NO_x and CO are the major precursors of tropospheric ozone (O₃) and play an important role in tropospheric ozone chemistry, Secondary Organic Aerosols (SOAs) and air borne toxic chemical formation in the Planetary Boundary Layer (PBL) (Mandal et al., 2023). VOCs are precursors for most of the atmospheric processes and also results the formation of SOA, both of which greatly harm human health and significantly affect the Earth's climate. In the present study, the diurnal variation of VOCs and trace gases, ozone forming potential and SOA of VOCs is shown from January, 2019 to December, 2019 in the ambient air of Dayalbagh Agra.

SAMPLING SITE AND METHODOLOGY

Measurements of VOCs and Trace gases (NO_x, CO and O₃) were carried out at a sub-urban site, Dayalbagh, Agra (27°10'N, 78°05'E) during Jan-Dec 2019. Climatically, Agra is warm and dry during the summer and cool in the winter. (Kumari et al., 2021).

O₃, NO_x AND CO MEASUREMENT

The levels of surface O₃, NO_x and CO were measured through continuously operating O₃ (Thermo Fischer Model 49i), NO_x (Thermo Fischer Model 42i) and CO (Teledyne T300) analyzers, respectively. The detailed description of the measurements has been discussed elsewhere (Baghel et al., 2023).

VOLATILE ORGANIC COMPOUNDS MEASUREMENT

Online sampling of VOCs has been carried out on Tenax-TA Tube (60-80 mesh) using the Air-Server unit attached to the Gas Chromatograph- Mass Spectrometer. The VOCs were analysed using thermal desorption on a Thermal Desorption Unit (TDU) with UNITY-Xr and Air Server-XR (Markes International Limited) coupled with a Gas chromatograph (GC) (Agilent) equipped with a Mass selective detector MSD (Agilent 5977B GC-MSD/FID (Agilent Technologies, USA).

The SOAP method has been widely used to estimate the contributions of different VOC species to SOA formation, which can be calculated by the following equation (Zhang et al., 2017)

$$\text{SOAP}_i = \frac{\text{Increment in SOA mass concentration with species } i}{\text{Increment in SOA with toluene}} \times (100)$$

where SOAP_i is the SOA formation potential parameter for species i (unitless). The potential of SOA formation for species i (PSOAP_i) can be calculated by the following equation (Zhang et al., 2017):

$$\text{PSOAP}_i = \frac{\text{VOC}_i \times \text{SOAP}_i}{100} \times \text{FAC toluene}$$

where FAC is fractional aerosol coefficients.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The mean concentrations of measured VOCs at the study site are shown in Figure below. The sum of VOCs ranged from 60.7 to 200.9 µg/m³ with an average concentration of 126.9 ± 34.0 µg/m³. Among all VOCs, Toluene showed the maximum concentration range from 20.6-57.0 µg/m³ with average concentration (42.2 ± 12.3 µg/m³) followed by, butane (21 ± 3.2), Propane (20.1 ± 2.5) and iso-pentane (19.2 ± 4) (Figure 1 (A)). Out of the measured VOC species, the most dominant compounds found at study site were aromatic hydrocarbons (BTEX-benzene, toluene, xylenes, ethylbenzene), aromatic accounted between 40 and 55% in all VOCs. Alkanes contributed most (63.7%) to VOC mixing ratio while aromatics contributed most to the SOAP with contributions of 49.5%. The main VOCs sources were vehicle emissions (39.0%), combustion sources (22.5%), gasoline evaporation (14.2%), solvent usage (11.6%) and 12.6% were other sources. Vehicular sources had the highest proportions to the VOC reactivity and SOAP, with average contributions of 36.0% and 51.6%, respectively.

Figure 1: (A) Average concentration of VOCs and (B) temporal variation of trace gases (NO_x, O₃ & CO). The average concentration of NO_x, O₃ and CO were 5.1±3.1ppb, 41.1±20.3ppb and 513±253ppb respectively (figure 1 (B)). O₃ shows higher concentration during the afternoon time. The nighttime low levels of ozone were due to loss through NO, NO_x, CO and VOCs showed bimodal pattern, morning, and evening peak. These peaks correspond to peak traffic emissions hours and boundary layer processes. During morning hours, although traffic emission is high, but dilution of air takes place due to rising PBL height whereas during nighttime, traffic emissions are almost similar, but PBL height is low which results in accumulation of pollutants near surface.

CONCLUSIONS

The photochemical generation of surface ozone takes place through nonlinear reactions in presence of NO_x and VOCs. The average concentration of NO_x, O₃ and CO were recorded (5.14± 3.2), (41.1±20.1) and (513±205.1) ppb, respectively. The sum of VOCs ranged from 60.7 to 200.9 µg/m³ with an average concentration of 126.9 ± 34.0 µg/m³. VOCs, NO_x, and CO shows bimodal peak during morning and late evening, O₃ showed maximum value in afternoon. Vehicular sources had the highest proportions to the VOC reactivity and SOAP, with average contributions of 36.0% and 51.6%, respectively.

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AMBIENT AIR QUALITY MONITORING OVER RURAL AREAS USING INDIGENOUS TECHNOLOGY (AMRIT)

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Keywords: Rural air quality, PM_{2.5}, low-cost sensors, real-time monitoring, air quality management

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution can have adverse effects on human health across the globe (State of Global Air, 2020). Notably, over the Indian subcontinent, the global burden of disease estimates air pollution is one of the leading risk factors for premature death and contributes significantly to the burden of diseases in India (Balakrishnan et al., 2019). The national population-weighted annual average fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) level in India was always five to twenty-five times higher than the World Health Organization air quality guidelines of 5 µg/m³ (WHO, 2021); and more than ninety-nine percent of the population was exposed to unhealthy air across the years (Apte and Pant, 2019). These high PM_{2.5} concentrations were not only responsible for the lower air quality but also had implications on human health, and climate and affected the functioning of the ecosystems (Yadav et al., 2022). In recent years, significant efforts have been made to understand scientific complexities related to the air quality in India. One such important initiative taken by the Indian Ministry of Environment Forests and Climate Change (MoEFCC) was the National Clean Air Programme (NCAP) in 2019, which aims to reduce air pollution levels and increase the number of continuous air quality monitoring stations over the different cities across India (Ganguly et al., 2020; Guttikunda et al., 2023).

It is important to note that air pollution is ubiquitous; and does not have an urban-rural disparity. In rural regions of India, annual PM_{2.5} concentrations exceed 100 µg/m³ and the non-urban emissions are two to four-fold higher than the emissions from the other regions (Karambelas et al., 2018 and Ravishankara et al., 2020). Additionally, a large percentage of India's population resides in rural India. Despite this, at present, the in-depth scientific assessment of the air pollution scenario in rural regions of India is not only warranted but also requires immediate attention. However, the presence of air quality monitoring stations in rural areas is very scarce, which leads to a limited understanding of rural air quality. Notably, the origin and fate of the contaminants and their associated health effects need to be investigated in-depth. Thus, the lack of comprehensive knowledge on rural air quality would affect effective policy interventions and mitigate the harmful effects of air pollution on the rural population. With this rationale, The “Ambient Air Quality Monitoring over Rural Areas using Indigenous Technology (AMRIT)” project, was conceived, developed, and implemented on the ground by the Center of Excellence – “Advanced Technologies for Monitoring Air-quality iNdicators (CoE -Atman), Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur (IIT Kanpur).

AMRIT PROJECT

The AMRIT projects aim to monitor air quality in rural areas across the Indian states for better air quality management and policy interventions. The state-of-the-art Sensor Ambient Air Quality Monitor (SAAQM) network will be effectively used for air quality monitoring and real-time source attribution. Importantly, in line with the “Atma-Nirbhar” initiative by the Government of India, the AMRIT project aims to develop the next generation of air quality sensors for air quality monitoring. The sensors were acquired from two Indian startups namely Airveda and Respirer Living Sciences which were responsible for the design, development, and fabrication of the PM sensors. In the first phase, about 1400 SAAQM will be deployed at the block level over the Indian states of Bihar and Uttar Pradesh (UP) as shown in Figure 1. The location of the SAAQM stations is designed in a way that will cover most of the rural regions, organized (unorganized) industry locations, and the urban regions of Bihar and UP. Overall, the key objectives of the projects are as follows:

1. Deployment of SAAQM for rural air quality monitoring.
2. Optimization of SAAQM for different environments and evaluation of the difference between rural and urban air quality in India
3. The proposed extensive SAAQM data will also be used to create micro air-sheds within the different states so that the air quality at the district level can be effectively managed by understanding the contribution from the various sources within the micro air-shed (i.e., industries, vehicles, etc.) & also sources within the larger air-shed.

4. Comparing data with emission inventories, source attribution analysis, & pollution models over different states.
5. Develop novel tools for data mining, network calibration, data visualizations, and interpretation.
6. Help demarcate rural regions to understand how much rural air pollution can be attributed to local sources vs. nearby urban clusters of any state.
7. Enable awareness and education programs on air pollution and health in rural areas of Indian States.
8. Establishing the rural air quality data for science studies & policy development for rural air quality management.

Figure 1. Overview of the AMRIT Project

SUMMARY

The AMRIT project envisioned a significant contribution to the understanding of rural air quality monitoring by putting a step forward to building a large SAAQM using the indigenously built portable monitors. The co-located devices with EBAM reference grade monitors at IIT Kanpur which also show a good agreement with CAAQMS on the field will be qualitatively used for the scientific understanding of air pollutant scenarios and most importantly, aid in the identification of different micro and macro air-sheds which will be helpful for the effective management of pollutants at different spatial scales. As estimated by Guo, et al., 2018 that Bihar (0.12 million) recorded higher premature mortality compared to other states and to achieve a 50 % reduction in PM_{2.5} mass concentration related premature mortality, the PM_{2.5} mass concentration needs to be reduced by 65 %, respectively for Bihar. With the high density of monitoring networks with fine spatial-temporal resolution, PM_{2.5} mass concentration data could give better insights into the health and economic impact and policy framework of air pollution at the block level. Overall, the AMRIT project is an integrated effort, which not only aims for ambient air rural quality monitoring and management but also underpins India's national clean air program and commitments to climate change mitigation at the global level.

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PARTICULATE MATTER AND METAL CONCENTRATION IN (PM_{2.5} AND PM₁₀) AND THEIR MICROBIAL NATURE OF AEROSOL IN AMBIENT AIR, DURING WINTER IN AGRA, REGION

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Keywords: Particulate Matter, Air Pollution, Heavy Metals, Microbiota (Fungi & bacteria), Human Health

INTRODUCTION

Particulate Matter (PM) in the atmosphere influences the Earth’s radiation balance and climate atmospheric chemistry, visibility, and the health of living beings including humans (Haywood & Ramaswamy, 1998). On a global scale, direct radiative effects from PM like PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ are of directly anthropogenic origin and are dominated by sulfate and carbonaceous PM (Schult et al., 1997). These particles are very hazardous to human health. When inhaled, breathing particles reach up to the alveoli of the lungs and cause very serious disorders, especially PM_{2.5}, which is more hazardous because it reaches the lungs more deeply than PM₁₀. These PM particles are not only dust but also carry different microorganisms on them, called bioaerosols. For the study of these bioaerosols, we had done sampling in semi-urban industrial areas (Trans Yamuna, Agra) 27.208080,78.051363 and semi-urban roadside areas (Khandari, Agra) 27°12'37.7"N 77°59'24.3"E.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the present investigation, particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), microbial concentration, and metal concentration in the ambient environment of the city of Taj, i.e., Agra (India) were assessed. The average mass concentration of PM₁₀ at Khandari and Trans Yamuna was found to be 232.81 µg/m³ and 231.85 µg/m³ respectively and the concentration of PM_{2.5} was found to be 147.24 µg/m³ and 121.91 µg/m³ respectively during the study period.

Fig. 1: PM mass concentration level

The total metal concentration of heavy metal in this study for PM 2.5 at trans-Yamuna was found 245.01 µg/m³ and follows the order Mg> Ca> K>Fe>Al>Sr>Li>Pb>B>Cr>Ba>Zn>Mn>Cu>Ni>Cd>Co. The total metal concentration of heavy metal for PM 2.5 at Khandari was found 250.37 µg/m³ and follows the order Mg> Ca> K>Fe>Al>Sr>Pb>B>Cr>Li>Zn>Ba>Cu>Mn>Cd>Ni>Co. In particular, for PM 2.5, the concentration of Mg and Ca was found highest, and Co was the lowest on both sides of Trans Yamuna and Khandari. The total metal concentration for PM₁₀ at Khandari and Trans Yamuna was found 252.93 µg/m³ and 250.70 µg/m³ respectively. At the Khandari site, heavy metal concentration for PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} was found higher than at the trans-Yamuna site.

The composition of bacteria and fungi using a culture technique was also examined, which indicates that bacterial concentration was higher as compared to fungi. A total of 7 fungal types including 3 species were recorded. **Figure 3.** shows the monthly data of fungal colonies recorded and identified. The maximum fungal colonies were recorded during the month of November and lowest in the month of December. The high concentration of fungal counts in the month of November may be moderated rainfall, medium temperature and high humidity which are suitable of microbial growth. Picture 1 show fungi isolated from air. Total 7 species viz., Aspergillus Niger, Aspergillus flavus, and A fumigates were isolated. The maximum bacterial colonies were recorded during the month of November and December and lowest in the month of January. Picture 2 show bacterial isolated from air. Total 3 species viz., Gram Positive and Gram Negative were isolated.

Picture1: Fungi: Aspergillus Flavus (23/11/2022, PM₁₀) **Fungi: Aspergillus Niger** (28/11/2022, PM_{2.5}& 3/12/2020, PM₁₀)

Picture2: Bacteria: Gram Negative (23/11/2021, PM₁₀) **Bacteria: Gram Positive** (10/12/2022, PM₁₀)

Fig. 3. Microbial Activity

The levels of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ are much higher than the recommended value set by NAAQS in India. Bacteria and fungi count numbers and nomenclatures were also reported in the study. Instead of the traditional culture method, BOD incubation techniques were adopted in this study. Culture techniques had been used for microbial growth and biological characterization using different media, pH, temperature, and incubation periods. This study may help in developing control measures to mitigate air pollution.

CONCLUSIONS

Ambient aerosol samples were collected at Trans Yamuna (Industrial Area) and Khandari Crossing of Agra region from November to January. Chemical and Biological characterizations of aerosols were carried out. The concentration of airspora was highest in October and lowest in January. Atmospheric conditions viz., temperature, relative humidity, rainfall etc. plays very important role. In the PM mass concentration of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ was found higher at trans-Yamuna in January month and the mass concentration of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ was found higher in December month. The Khandari site, heavy metal concentration for PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} was found higher than at the trans-Yamuna site.

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LONG-TERM AEROSOL OPTICAL DEPTH VARIATION OVER INDO-GANGETIC BASIN

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INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols encompass an assortment of solid and liquid particles with varying sizes, shapes, and compositions suspended within the atmosphere, and they significantly impact Earth's climate, the water cycle, human health, and many more by scattering and absorbing incident solar radiation (Ramanathan *et al.*, 2001, Ramanathan & Carmichael, 2008, Lelieveld *et al.*, 2019, Papadimas *et al.*, 2012). Over the past twenty years, numerous sensors belonging to the Earth Observing System (EOS), including the Moderate-resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS), Multiangle Imaging Spectroradiometer (MISR), Ozone Monitoring Instrument (OMI), Advanced Very-High-Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR) and Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite (VIIRS) have been developed to capture aerosol characteristics across varying spatial and temporal resolutions (Bilal *et al.*, 2017; Mhawish *et al.*, 2018). Recently, a range of investigations have been conducted across India utilizing satellite remote sensing and ground-observed aerosol data. Instruments such as MODIS and VIIRS aboard satellites have been widely employed to oversee AOD on both global and regional levels (Yao *et al.*, 2018; Sawyer *et al.*, 2020; Su *et al.*, 2022). MODIS sensor is regarded as a potent tool for monitoring aerosol over a broad scale and with a high degree of spatial accuracy (Zhang *et al.*, 2016; Wei *et al.*, 2020). The validation of aerosol products from the MODIS satellite is conducted by comparing with ground-observed AOD data obtained from 3 distinct stations located across the IGB region is highly recommended because it is a highly populated and polluted region worldwide. This research aims to assess the effectiveness of MODIS aerosol products, specifically Terra-MODIS AOD (MOD08_D3) with ground-based AERONET AOD measurements, and explore the temporal variation of AOD for a span of 13 years, from 2010 to 2022 at three different locations (Jaipur (JP), Kanpur (KNP), and Gandhi College (GC)) across the IGB region.

STUDY AREA, DATASETS AND METHODOLOGY

This is accomplished by utilizing AERONET sites, specifically those situated in JP (26.91° N; 75.78° E), KNP (26.45° N, 80.33° E), and GC (25.87° N; 84.13° E) as shown in Figure 1. In the current study, we have used the Collection MOD08_D3_v6 Combined Dark Target and Deep Blue AOD at 550nm for land and ocean. The latest version (V3) and level 1.5 direct sun algorithm AOD was obtained from three AERONET location over the IGB region in India for this study. AERONET and MODIS offer ground-based and satellite-based daily mean AOD observations with the spatial resolution of 1°, respectively. The inter-annual temporal match of both types of observations is necessary to compare the AERONET & MODIS AODs.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure 2 (a-c) shows the yearly variation of MODIS AOD and AERONET AOD at three different locations GC, JP, and KNP over the IGB region, respectively, and their trends for the study period of 2010 to 2022. Annual mean values of MODIS AOD are found to be (0.67 ± 0.31) , (0.29 ± 0.24) , and (0.69 ± 0.30) over GC, JP, and KNP respectively. Similarly, for AERONET AOD is found to be (0.65 ± 0.27) , (0.42 ± 0.21) , and

(0.60 ± 0.25) , respectively over three regions. The GC and KNP have high AOD > 0.5 suggesting that the mixed aerosol loading while it found relatively low AOD values at JP, which indicates the low aerosol loading. The higher increasing trend is observed for GC with MODIS AOD, while the lowest trend is for KNP. Similarly, the higher trend of AERONET AOD is obtained at JP, while the lowest trend is for KNP.

Fig.19. Geographical distribution of AERONET sites at three different locations over IGB in India.

From Figure 3(a-c), the correlation analysis for GC shows good agreement ($r: 0.92$) between MODIS and AERONET AODs. The relative mean bias (RMB) at GC is -0.028 , which suggests that the MODIS AOD is underestimated

compared to the AERONET AOD. The root mean square error (RMSE) at GC is found to be very low

(0.039). Similarly, for JP and KNP, the correlation coefficient is found to be 0.64 & 0.92 respectively, which also shows good agreement between ground-based and MODIS-observed AOD.

Fig.20. Time series plot-yearly avg. AOD (MODIS&AERONET) ($\lambda=550\text{nm}$) at (a)GC (b)JP (c)KNP

Fig.21. Scatter plot of MODIS vs AERONET AOD (550nm) a)GC b)JP c)KNP over IGB region. Solid red line is 1:1 line

CONCLUSIONS

The MODIS AOD was analyzed using ground-based AOD from AERONET over 3 locations in the IGB region for 13 years from 2010-2022. The highest correlation coefficient between MODIS and AERONET AODs is found at KNP (0.92) and the highest RMSE is found at JP (0.15). The highest RMB is found at JP (0.15) and the lowest is found at GC (-0.028).

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**PM_{2.5} CONCENTRATION FORECASTING IN URBAN AREAS USING MACHINE LEARNING
MODELS**

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Keywords: PM_{2.5}, Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) model, Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)

INTRODUCTION

Forecasting air pollution is essential due to its impact on human health, particularly in urban areas. Air pollution forecasting gives early warnings, improves the quality of life, and facilitates environmental sensing research, allowing authorities to take necessary action (Lee et al., 2020). Machine Learning (ML) models are more accurate, adaptable, and self-correcting and have been used for air pollution forecasting in recent years. The XGBoost model predicted PM_{2.5} (Particulate matter with an aerodynamic diameter of less than 2.5 μm) concentration in Tehran better than the Random Forest Algorithm and Deep learning models (Joharestani et al., 2019). Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) outperformed Multi Linear Regression (MLR) and Support Vector Regression (SVR) in different studies conducted in Kolkata and Delhi (Bera et al., 2021; Masood et al., 2020). The first Indian research to employ the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) model to forecast PM_{2.5} concentrations in 15 major Indian cities was conducted by Aggarwal et al., 2021. Previous studies have primarily focused on individual cities, neglecting the need to address spatial-temporal changes in forecasting. Despite India being severely impacted by air pollution, research on air pollution forecasting remains scarce, underscoring the significance of this study. This study aims to forecast PM_{2.5} concentration five days in advance using the Machine learning models. Air pollution forecasting is crucial in informing the public about future air quality, enabling government authorities to provide sufficient warning and undertake necessary preparations.

METHODS

The study area is two polluted cities in India: Delhi and Kanpur. Since Delhi and Kanpur share comparable geographical and climatic characteristics, Delhi adopts the Kanpur model for predictions and forecasts. The study compared the accuracy of XGBoost (Figure 1(a)), MLP, and LSTM models, and the best model is adopted for future studies. The meteorological and air quality data obtained from the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) from 2016 to 2023 is used in the study. Missing data correction and outlier removal are the pre-processing techniques. The pre-processed dataset is split into training and testing data. Air quality forecasting is conducted in Kanpur by modifying the existing model. Forecasting air quality is difficult due to the absence of air quality data for the testing dates. Root mean square error (RMSE) and daily percentage error are metrics for model validation, and tuning of hyperparameters improves model efficiency. Percentage error is determined for forecasting study to analyze the model's forecasting ability.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

By time-series split, 80% of the data trained the Kanpur prediction model, while 20% of the data tested the model. The RMSE reported for the XGBoost model is 36.88 μg/m³, less than the LSTM (39.32 μg/m³) and MLP (40.85 μg/m³). XGBoost model has better prediction performance and is applied for further research. The forecasting efficiency or RMSE of the Kanpur yearly XGBoost model is 30.28 μg/m³. This model forecasts PM_{2.5} concentration with a percentage error of less than 20% for the initial four days. The Kanpur XGBoost model is trained with Kanpur data and tested with Delhi data for the prediction analysis in Delhi, and the computed RMSE for the model is 39.18 μg/m³. The forecasting efficiency of the XGBoost model for Delhi is 26.61 μg/m³ with a percentage error of less than 12% for the first three days.

Figure 1. (a) Framework of XGBoost model for air quality prediction. (b) Monthly forecast results of Kanpur for the period of 2016 to 2023.

Monthly forecasts are conducted for Kanpur City to determine the effect of meteorology on prediction performance. February, March, April, May, June, July, August, September, October, and December months were forecasted with RMSE lower than the yearly forecast model for fifteen days, as shown in Figure 1. The RMSE for January and November is very high and underestimates the forecast. Among the forecasted monthly models of Kanpur, December month effectively forecasted PM_{2.5} concentration with an RMSE of 4.86 µg/m³ and a daily percentage error of less than 5% for the initial four days. Analyzing the daily percentage error for March, June, and July shows an initial divergence and is not a suitable model for the forecast of PM_{2.5} concentration. Monthly forecasts are superior to yearly forecasts by analyzing the RMSE and daily percentage error. Monthly forecast models can capture the meteorological and air quality trends throughout the study period.

CONCLUSIONS

This study predicted PM_{2.5} concentration using XGBoost, MLP, and LSTM for Kanpur, and the best model predicted Delhi. XGBoost has the lowest RMSE of 36.88 µg/m³ while predicting Kanpur. The Kanpur XGBoost model predicted PM_{2.5} concentration in Delhi with an RMSE of 39.18 µg/m³; thus, the Kanpur model is predictable for Delhi. The yearly forecast of Kanpur city forecasts the first four days with an RMSE of 5.4 µg/m³ and a daily percentage error of less than 20%. Over the first three days, the daily percentage error for Delhi's yearly forecast is less than 12%. The December month forecast of Kanpur city performs best with an RMSE of 4.86 µg/m³ and a daily percentage error of less than 5% for the first four days. This is the first study in India to employ the XGBoost algorithm to predict and forecast at Kanpur. This work lowered daily percentage error for prediction and forecasting models. The model underestimates the results for January and November, which must be addressed in future works.

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ATMOSPHERIC LEVELS, SOURCES, AND HEALTH RISK ASSESSMENT OF PAHS ASSOCIATED WITH PM₁ AND TSP IN AN URBAN SITE IN THE HISTORIC CITY OF TAJ
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Keywords: POLYCYCLIC AROMATIC HYDROCARBON, URBAN, TSP, PM₁, HEALTH RISK

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution in densely populated areas has worsened over the last several decades due to industrialization and poor urban planning, especially in developing nations contributing to 7 million premature deaths yearly (HEI, 2020). In 2022, India ranked eighth globally for poor air quality, with an average PM_{2.5} level of 53.3 µg/m³ exceeding the WHO's guideline by over ten times (IQAir, 2022). Among various categories of particulate organic constituents, the ambient concentration levels of trace chemical compounds of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) are a matter of concern for human health due to their highly persistent nature and adverse health impacts. In this study, we determined the concentration and health risk associated with the PAHs bound to PM in two different fractions i.e., total suspended particulate (TSP) and PM₁ at an urban site in Agra.

METHODS

Measurements of PAHs were carried out at an Urban site Sikandra in the City of Taj, Agra. 24-hour samples of total suspended particulate matter were collected on quartz fiber filters (QFFs) using a High-volume Air sampler Envirotech-1000X and PM₁ was collected on 47 mm quartz microfibre filters using low volume Air sampler APM 550 Envirotech. Before sampling, QFFs and QMFs were baked at 750 °C and 500°C for 6 h, in a muffle furnace to eliminate any background contamination and packed in aluminum foil packages until used. After sampling the filters were kept at low temperature (<4°C). The PM samples were collected for two seasons i.e., winter (Dec-Feb) and summer (Apr-Jun) for the year 2022-2023. A total of 40 samples (20 samples of TSP and 20 samples of PM₁ fraction) were collected during the study period.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The mean TSP concentration recorded during the study period was 309.3±24.5 µg/m³ with an average total of 16 PAHs concentration equal to 391.4±153.0 ng m⁻³. Notably, higher concentrations of PAHs were observed during the winter (683.2±256.4 ng m⁻³) compared to the summer period (99.5±49.6 ng m⁻³) and this difference was statistically significant at a 95% confidence level. These findings align with previous studies by Albuquerque et al. (2016), and Jakovljević et al. (2018).

Upon calculating the concentration of combustion-derived PAHs (Fla, Pyr, BaA, Chy, BbF, BkF, BaP, IP, and BghiP) it was found that more than 70% of COMPAHs were bound to PM₁ while about 50% were present in TSP which suggested coal combustion and vehicle emissions as the primary sources of PAHs in the study area. This was further identified through diagnostic ratio (DR) analysis. Ratios of individual PAHs with PAHs having the same molecular weight emitted from different sources are usually source-specific and can be used as fingerprints to identify the sources and to reduce the uncertainties. In the present study, the DRs like IP/ (IP + BghiP), BaP/BghiP, Flu/ (Flu + Pyr), and Anth/ (Anth + Phen) were calculated (Table 1). The DR suggests that most of the PAHs bound to TSP and PM₁ probably had identical sources in winter (pyrogenic) and were found consistent with studies carried out at Kanpur & Kolkata, respectively (Rajeev et al. 2021; Saha et al. 2017). However, petrogenic sources were the main contributor in summer.

Table 1. Diagnostic Ratio Value for Winter and Summer Season in TSP and PM₁

		IP/IP+BghiP	BaP/BghiP	Flu/ (Flu + Pyr)	Anth/ Anth+Phen	ΣCOMPAHs/ ΣPAHs
TSP	Winter	0.57±0.02	0.93±0.08	0.38±0.04	0.16±0.06	0.49
	Coal Combustion	Coal Combustion	Fossil Fuel Emission (0.4-0.5)	Pyrogenic		
PM₁	Summer	0.80±0.09	0.47±0.02	0.09±0.01	0.02±0.01	0.59
	Coal Combustion	Traffic Emission	(Gasoline Emission <0.4)	Petrogenic		
TSP	Winter	0.28±0.01	1.40±0.12	0.38±0.02	0.24±0.03	0.75
	Pyrogenic	Coal Combustion	Fossil Fuel Emission	Pyrogenic		
PM₁	Summer	0.50±0.01	0.86±0.04	0.64±0.05	0.08±0.01	0.72
	Petrochemical	Traffic Emission	Coal+Biomass (>0.5)	Petrogenic		

Health risk indices (ILCR) were computed, taking into account the toxicity of each compound and considering

different age groups within the population. A risk level of 10^{-6} , signifying a minimal cancer risk over a human lifetime, was used as a benchmark, while values falling between 10^{-6} and 10^{-4} indicated a potential cancer risk. Risks exceeding 10^{-4} represented significant cancer risks. The contribution of carcinogenic PAHs, including BaA, Chy, BbF, BkF, BaP, IP, and DbA, to total PAH concentration revealed that over 70% of these compounds were present in the PM_{10} fraction, whereas only 47% were present in TSP. BaP (most toxic PAHs) concentration (4.9 ng m^{-3} in PM_{10}) exceeded the air quality standard for $PM_{2.5}$ (1 ng m^{-3}) suggesting a potential health risk. Thus, health risks associated with 16 PAHs were calculated using the equation given by Rodriguez et.al., 2020.

The incremental lifetime cancer risk (ILCR) levels for PM-bound PAHs via ingestion, inhalation, and dermal contact were determined for: children (5–19 years), and adults (20–70 years) in both winter and summer periods as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Incremental Lifetime Cancer Risk (ILCR) via ingestion, inhalation, and dermal exposure pathways

		Ingestion		Inhalation		Dermal	
		Children	Adult	Children	Adult	Children	Adult
PM₁₀	Winter	1.27E-04	1.24E-04	2.42E-06	6.05E-06	5.16E-04	8.91E-04
	Summer	3.98E-05	3.87E-05	7.56E-07	1.89E-06	1.61E-04	2.78E-04
TSP	Winter	1.89E-04	1.83E-04	3.58E-06	8.96E-06	7.65E-04	1.32E-04
	Summer	5.32E-05	5.17E-05	1.01E-06	2.53E-06	2.16E-04	3.72E-04

CONCLUSIONS

Measurements conducted at an urban location in Agra revealed seasonal variations in PAH concentrations. PAH levels were higher in the winter ($683.2 \pm 256.4 \text{ ng m}^{-3}$) than summer (91.8 ± 49.6) for TSP and higher in winter ($203.1 \pm 20.1 \text{ ng m}^{-3}$) than summer ($78.1 \pm 20.1 \text{ ng m}^{-3}$) for PM_{10} . Both seasons exhibited a prevalence of 4-ring and 5-ring PAH compounds. During both measurement periods, heavy PAHs, typically linked to vehicle emissions, outweighed light PAHs. Diagnostic ratios pointed to pyrogenic sources, including coal, wood, biomass burning, and traffic emissions, as the primary contributors to PAHs in TSP and PM_{10} , particularly during winter while petrogenic sources contributed majorly during summer. To assess cancer risk, the TCP was calculated using toxic equivalency factors. The average TCP was 4.4 ng m^{-3} in the summer, 14.4 ng m^{-3} in the winter for PM_{10} and 5.9 ng m^{-3} in the summer, 21.0 ng m^{-3} in the winter for TSP. The ILCR was evaluated for two age groups: children (5–19 years) and adults (20–70 years). Both summer and winter posed a cancer risk to moderate levels for adults and children majorly through dermal exposure followed by ingestion. Notably, the ILCR value for adults and children via inhalation remained below the permissible maximum limit for cancer risk (10^{-6}). However, the substantial increase in PAH levels during the winter (ten times higher than in summer), along with associated health risks, underscores the importance of continuous monitoring of PAH levels in finer particle fractions (PM_{10}). These findings provide crucial insights for future strategies aimed at controlling PAH sources and enhancing the quality of life for urban populations.

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AEROSOL TRANSPORT AND DEPOSITION

**DECADAL REVERSAL OF DUST AEROSOLS: IMPLICATION OVER THE SUMMER
MONSOON PRECIPITATION CHEMISTRY OVER THE WESTERN GHATS**

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Keywords: Dust Aerosol, decadal reversal, Rainwater, Western Ghats, Indian summer Monsoon

INTRODUCTION

Indian summer monsoon rainfall over the Western Ghats (WG) region covers a vast area of 160,000 km² to the west coast of the Peninsular India is crucial in-terms of the ground water recharge, livelihood and flora and fauna. Over the few years many studies show that the extreme rainfall due to climate change impacts has changed the amount and intensity and arrival of the monsoonal rainfall, however, its chemically changing nature has not been much explored up till recently (Bhaskar et al., 2022). This study explores the impact of long-term changes in atmospheric aerosols and its role in chemically changing trends of rainwater pH and its composition. The long-term trends of rainwater composition shows that the summer monsoon rainfall acidity (decreased pH) has increased and stabilised (at Pune and Kodaikanal stations located) over the WG region with respect to the previous decade (1984 to 2000), despite rise in the anthropogenic (SO₂ and NO₃) aerosols in the recent periods. This stabilization in rainwater pH and acidity (stable alkalinity) indicates an increase in cationic aerosols such as from Ca²⁺ from dust. The transport of mineral dust (Ca²⁺), from the middle-eastern region from across the Arabian Sea at mid tropospheric level (L Yang, et al., 2019) and also an increase in construction activity in the recent period (after 2000) are found to be the viable factors for this stabilization of the rainfall acidity in recent decades.

METHODS

Long-term (1984-2015) rainwater composition of water-soluble ionic species and rainwater pH from WMO-GAW stations (Pune and Kodaikanal) were investigated to understand the changes in long-term aerosol and rainwater chemistry. Both aerosol pH as well as the rainwater pH trends and its compositions were explored to insight the impacts of long-term changes role of transported mineral dust. Principal component analysis of MERRA-2 and MODIS total AOD (at 550nm) over the Arabian Sea were investigated to understand the long-term changes in dust transport its effect on rainwater chemistry during Indian Summer monsoon rainfall (ISMR).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Long-term chemistry of rainwater composition over Pune (Figure 1) shows a decrease in rainwater Ca²⁺ (dust tracer) between 1984 to 2000, however, a reversal (increase) is witnessed after 2000. While a linearly increasing trend in Kodaikanal Ca²⁺ is noticed for both of these periods. A decadal decreasing trend in rainwater Ca²⁺ is seen between the 1984 to 2000, whereas an increasing trend visible after year 2000 in conjunction with MERRA-2 AOD show similar phase transition for EOF1(60%) and other EOFs for the Arabian Sea region. This suggest that the mid-tropospheric mineral dust transport trends closely match with the rainwater Ca²⁺ and thus remains as its major source. MODIS-Terra AOD in agreement with the reanalysis MERRA-2 product also shows similar increasing AOD trends over the Arabian Sea along with Ca²⁺. Despite an increasing trend in both the stations, a long-term linearly decreasing trend in rainwater pH for the both stations indicates a concomitant effect of the increase in CO₂ and higher contribution of anthropogenic acidic species in the region.

Figure 1. Rainwater Ca^{2+} annual trend for Pune station. PCA analysis of MERRA-2 total AOD (at 550nm).

CONCLUSIONS

The long-term (1984-2015) trends of rainwater composition and AOD suggest increasing mid-tropospheric wind transport of mineral dust from across the Arabian Sea during ISMR from middle eastern region. This increased mid-level dust transport indicates greater influx of dust Ca^{2+} and higher neutralization effects in rainwater pH. However, a linearly decreasing trends of rainwater pH with slow rate of descent after 2000 indicates higher neutralization potential due to increase in Alkaline Ca^{2+} .

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SEASONAL VARIATION OF MINERAL DUST AND AEROSOL IRON OVER THE ARABIAN SEA
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Keywords: ATMOSPHERIC DUST, NUTRIENT, IRON, ATMOSPHERIC PROCESSING

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric dust is a potential source of macro and micro nutrients (trace elements) to the surface ocean, specifically open ocean and oligotrophic water. Subsequent to their deposition, they enter into surface biogeochemical cycle and significantly alter different biogeochemical processes, including primary productivity. Supply of atmospheric dust and nutrients always associated with prevailing wind pattern. The Arabian Sea experiences major reversal of wind pattern; south-west wind (during monsoon) and north-east wind (during winter), which can affect dust supply and nutrient flux to the Arabian sea (Kumar et al., 2020). It is thus important to quantify atmospheric dust and associated trace elements (particularly Fe) over the marine region. In this context, we collected aerosol samples over the Arabian sea during monsoon (SSD-40 and SSD-55) and winter (SSD-68) following same cruise track covering a large area of the Arabian Sea.

METHODS

Aerosol samples were collected on-board RV-Sindhu Sadhana in the year 2017 (SSD-40) and 2018 (SSD-55) during August and December-January 2019 (SSD-68) representing monsoon and winter season respectively. A total of 43 aerosol samples (TSP-Total suspended particle) were collected during monsoon and 23 aerosol samples (PM₁₀) were collected during winter. All the samples were collected on PALLFLEX Tissuquartz filter (8" × 10") filters with the help of high-volume sampler (monsoon-ENVIROTECH Model APM-430) (winter-TISCH Environmental) at an average flow rate of 1.1 m³ min⁻¹. Post collection all the samples were stored at -20°C until its further analysis at our laboratory.

A piece of aerosol sample leached with Milli-Q (18.2 MΩ .cm) and leachate used for analysis of soluble trace elements (using Q-ICP-MS) and major ion (using Ion-Chromatograph). Another 1/8th part of aerosol sample under went acid digestion, where an acid mixture of HF + HNO₃ (2:5) used to make a clear solution and stored in 2% HNO₃ solution until its further analysis for total trace element analysis (using ICP-OES). Detail analytical procedures are described in Panda et al. (2022).

RESULT & DISCUSSION

The Arabian Sea receives higher dust flux during monsoon ($13.8 \pm 10.6 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$) compare to winter ($11.2 \pm 5.3 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$), (Fig-1a). Similar to dust, higher Fe flux observed during monsoon ($0.8 \pm 0.6 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$) as compared to winter ($0.6 \pm 0.2 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$) Fig-1a. Fe/Al ratio shows

similar variation (0.7 ± 0.3) for both the season which suggest dust is a major contributor of total Fe over the Arabian sea irrespective of season. We estimated fractional solubility and it was found higher during the winter ($5.9 \pm 3.2 \%$) season in contrast to the monsoon ($0.8 \pm 0.9 \%$) (Fig-1b). Lower total Fe but higher fractional solubility suggests role of biomass emission as well as atmospheric processing controls the fractional solubility during winter.

Fig-1 (a) Seasonwise dry deposition flux of dust and total iron. (b) Seasonal variation of fractional solubility.

In addition, these results were corroborated with high enrichment factor (1.7 ± 0.5) and good correlation of soluble Fe with nss-K^+ ($p = 0.48$; $p < 0.05$) during winter months. This also indicates the role of continental outflow from the Indian sub-continent to the marine atmospheric boundary layer of the Arabian Sea which is missing during the monsoon months.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Atmospheric dust is one of the potential sources of micro nutrient (Fe) over the Arabian sea.
2. Arabian sea receives higher dust during monsoon season in contrast to winter months.
3. Fe over the Arabian sea is majorly associated with dust; however partial influence of anthropogenic emissions is observed during winter.
4. Atmospheric processing of dust during winter enhances Fe% over the Arabian sea.

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ANALYSIS OF EFFECTIVE PLANT SPECIES TO ABATE RESUSPENDED DUST OF
AN ARTERIAL ROAD IN LUCKNOW, INDIA

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Keywords: ROAD DUST, PLANT SPECIES, APTI, DCP, AIR POLLUTION

INTRODUCTION

Rapid urbanization changes the land use patterns and scatters the source mix of air pollution within the city. Increased public demand escalate the movement of vehicles in urban road networks which worsens the air quality. Recent urban planning included vegetation belts between and sidewalks of the roads to mitigate air and noise pollution. The vegetation also acts as a defense line for the traffic and serves as bio-remediators to protect public health. Plants differ greatly in terms of their biochemical makeup, which aids in their ability to adopt unfavourable environmental changes such as ascorbic acid levels (AA), Total chlorophyll content (TCC), leaf extract pH (P), and relative water content (RWC) (Flowers et al., 2007). Investigations emphasized the characterization of plant species as three main groups based on their air pollution tolerance index (APTI) i.e., sensitive (APTI: 1-11), moderated (APTI: 12-16), and tolerant (APTI: 17 or higher) to recommend plants for near roads (Karmakar et al., 2021; Leghari et al., 2011). However, understanding the potential plant species in capturing road-resuspended dust and sinking associated metals of dust at near-road ways is very few (Bharti et al., 2018; Jia et al., 2020). Therefore, the objective of current study is to determine the effective plant species that reduce concentration of aerosolized dust particles for an arterial road in Lucknow. The study findings encourage the use of suitable plant species for near road air pollution mitigation in metropolitans.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in post-monsoon season in 2022 for an arterial road site (VIP Road) in Lucknow, India where dust entrainment is predominating due to regular traffic movement. Site-specific near-road sampling and gravimetric analysis were carried out for ambient PM₁₀ based on the BIS method (IS 5182 part 23, 2006). Leave samples from ten different plant species that were already exist and well grown between the arterial road line of ~2km were collected using conventional techniques reported in the literature (Singh et al., 2021). The tolerance level of different plant species in terms of APTI was determined based on the equation: $APTI = [A (T+P) + R]/10$, Where A=Ascorbic acid (mg/g), T=Total chlorophyll content(mg/g), P=pH of leaf extract and R=Relative water content of the leaf (%). The resuspended road dust capturing potential by the ten plant species at the road site was determined by measuring the surface areas of sampled leaves using graph paper, and weight of the dust loaded on each leaf was determined gravimetrically (Bharti et al., 2018). Subsequently, 15 metals and 5 ions analysis for dust captured on leave was performed through ICP-MS and IC analytical procedures respectively which were illustrated in earlier study (Khan et al., 2016).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mean 24-hour ambient PM₁₀ was observed 264.7µg/m³ at near road site (VIP Road) in Lucknow. **Table-1** illustrates scientific name of ten different plant species in the study site and their biochemical characteristics such as total chlorophyll content (TCC), ascorbic acid (AA), pH (P), relative water content (RWC), and APTI. The common name of the respective ten plants is Kaner, Devil's Tree/ Milkwood Pine, Neem, Peepal, Mango, Guava, Sycamore, Castor, Amaltas and Custard Apple. The variation of these biochemical characteristics between ten different plant species was observed significantly, where TCC, AA, pH, and RWC were ranged by 2.6–16.7mg/g, 8.32–18.5mg/g, 5.8–6.9, and 68-88% respectively. Based on APTI value, plant category was identified as sensitive, moderate and tolerate. Among the ten plant species, *Ficus religiosa* and *Annona reticulata* were identified as highly tolerant and susceptible plant

Table-1: Biochemical Properties and APTI of Plant Species planted at VIP Road in Lucknow city

Plant ID	Plants Species Name	TCC (mg/g)	P	RWC (%)	AA (mg/g)	APTI	Plant Category
P1	Nerium oleander	2.62	6.62	0.80	15.8	11.61	Moderate
P2	Alstonia scholaris	5.23	6.85	0.68	12.68	10.39	Sensitive
P3	Azadirachta indica	6.65	6.35	0.75	18.45	18.07	Tolerance
P4	Ficus religiosa	14.78	6.93	0.79	15.67	26.75	Tolerance
P5	Mangifera indica	9.85	6.05	0.88	8.32	11.61	Moderate
P6	Psidium guajava	6.37	6.78	0.76	11.78	11.75	Moderate
P7	Platanus occidentalis	7.20	6.32	0.82	12.76	14.08	Moderate
P8	Ricinus communis	16.76	5.94	0.86	12.54	24.55	Tolerance
P9	Cassia fistula	3.98	6.45	0.82	13.62	11.65	Moderate
P10	Annona reticulata	3.65	5.80	0.87	8.74	7.18	Sensitive

species respectively against adverse air quality at study site. Besides, analysis for the road-resuspended dust-capturing potential (DCP) by the ten different plants is illustrated in **Figure-1**. The maximum DCP of $1.09 \pm 0.08 \text{ mg/cm}^2$, $1.05 \pm 0.07 \text{ mg/cm}^2$, and $0.85 \pm 0.05 \text{ mg/cm}^2$ were identified by the plants P7, P5, and P4 respectively while the lowest was found in plant P1 (0.35 mg/cm^2). Further, Pb, Cr, Zn, and Cu and SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- , and NH_4^+ speciated markers of road dust were also captured significantly by same plant species.

Dust Capturing Potential (DCP) of plant species

Metals /Ions	Metals and Ions Composition in DCP of Plant Species (g/kg)									
	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10
Na	28.91	27.76	28.72	28.65	28.21	27.83	27.74	28.73	27.81	28.01
K	66.67	65.76	66.02	65.92	67.95	65.76	63.86	65.19	64.91	63.98
Ca	52.82	53.2	52.86	51.63	52.81	51.92	53.66	53.82	54.02	53.06
Mg	55.48	53.76	54.61	53.84	55.42	53.11	54.09	54.93	53.78	52.08
P	0.83	0.78	0.82	0.74	0.79	0.73	0.83	0.87	0.81	0.76
Fe	35.58	32.87	33.68	34.64	35.92	36.37	35.75	35.68	37.95	37.25
Si	88.91	87.82	88.04	86.69	87.35	79.32	83.67	87.32	89.03	88.45
Al	41.12	42.84	41.34	43.82	42.62	41.97	43.87	40.05	40.97	40.91
V	0.097	0.092	0.095	0.094	0.089	0.085	0.076	0.088	0.087	0.093
Cu	0.245	0.238	0.247	0.251	0.247	0.239	0.287	0.257	0.261	0.265
Cr	0.132	0.129	0.127	0.121	0.128	0.129	0.132	0.135	0.126	0.131
Pb	0.372	0.375	0.374	0.365	0.371	0.383	0.381	0.372	0.349	0.371
Zn	0.51	0.48	0.47	0.5	0.53	0.48	0.047	0.045	0.043	0.62
Ba	0.57	0.53	0.54	0.47	0.48	0.63	0.61	0.53	0.61	0.54
Co	0.0004	0.0003	0.0004	0.0005	0.0004	0.0005	0.0004	0.0003	0.0005	0.0004
Ni	0.157	0.161	0.153	0.158	0.0149	0.0142	0.0153	0.143	0.138	0.154
Mn	0.63	0.64	0.61	0.62	0.58	0.63	0.52	0.57	0.58	0.59
NH4+	0.745	0.762	0.753	0.757	0.743	0.752	0.759	0.698	0.712	0.735
NO3-	0.0008	0.0007	0.0007	0.0006	0.0008	0.0007	0.0006	0.0005	0.0006	0.0005
SO42-	3.04	2.99	2.96	2.89	2.67	2.88	2.67	2.92	2.61	2.87

Figure -1: Identification of effective plant species planted at VIP Road in Lucknow city for (A) road dust capturing potential and (B) composition of associated metals and ions in the captured road dust

CONCLUSION

The mean PM_{10} of $264.7 \mu\text{g/m}^3$ at the study site was an indication of the significant influence of traffic-entrained road dust in ambient air. Among the ten plant species in the study roadway, air pollution tolerance was identified as high by *F. religiosa*, *R. communis*, and *A. indica* plant species. The DCP and intake of associated metal of dust particles were found significant by *Platanus occidentalis*, *Mangifera indica*, and *Ficus religiosa* plant species. Therefore, these three plant species shall be selected for the high dust-entrained roadways to control dust pollution. The approach and the outcomes of the study encourage future investigations for effective plant species identification with respect to land use patterns in urban areas to mitigate air pollution in metropolis.

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INVESTIGATING THE CONVECTIVE TRANSPORT POSSIBILITIES OF LOWER ATMOSPHERIC POLLUTANTS TO THE UTLS REGION USING RAINWATER AND AEROSOL CHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION

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Keywords: ATAL, Rainwater, UTLS, Aerosols, PILS-IC

INTRODUCTION

Attempts to understand the chemical composition of the Asian Tropopause Aerosol Layer (ATAL) have concluded that, it predominantly consists of nitrate aerosols (Vernier et al., 2018). Previous aircraft measurements have suggested that NH_3 pollution from Asia could serve as the precursor for nitrate aerosols in ATAL through gas-to-particle formation after undergoing convective uplift to the Upper Troposphere and Lower Stratosphere (UTLS) regions (Appel et al., 2022). In this study, it is aimed to investigate the potential pathways of convective transport of lower atmospheric pollutants by analysing the chemical composition of rainwater and aerosols in a highly convective region, Kolkata (Head Bay of Bengal). The Particle Into Liquid Sampler (PILS) system (PILS-IC) established at Kolkata Camp Observatory of the National Atmospheric Research Laboratory (KCON) has been used for the chemical characterisation of aerosol and rain water samples during monsoon and post monsoon seasons.

MEASUREMENTS AND METHODS

Both aerosols and rainwater have been collected at the KCON, which is established in the Regional Remote Sensing Centre (RRSC-East), ISRO, Kolkata (22.58°N, 88.45°E). PILS system (Metrohm, Model ADI2081) has been used to sample the aerosols and rainwater sample have been collected with a homemade rainwater collector. Each sample was subjected to simultaneous anion, cation, and trace metal analysis using the Metrohm 940 Professional Vario dual-channel Ion chromatograph. Several parameters such as marine and non-marine fractions, fractional acidity, neutralisation factors have been estimated using the ion analysis data. PCA analysis have been used to source apportion the ions analysis. AIRS ammonia data at different altitudes along with INSAT 3D Outgoing Longwave Radiation (OLR) data have been used to substantiate the observations and convective transport possibilities.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The analysis revealed a significant dominance of NH_4^+ and NO_3^- ions in both rainwater and aerosol samples during the monsoon and post-monsoon seasons, with the dominance increasing during the post-monsoon season. Air mass trajectories indicated a clear influence of the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) region during the post-monsoon season, which is well-known for its dense agricultural activities and industries. High concentrations of these pollutants, even at higher altitudes, have been observed in Atmospheric Infrared Sounder (AIRS) measurements. Moreover, using OLR and vertical wind as proxies for tropical deep convection and updrafts/downdrafts, respectively, we found evidence supporting the possibility of convective transport of these lower-level pollutants to the UTLS regions during the monsoon season. Figure 1 summarises the findings of this study.

Figure 1. Graphical summary of the findings of the study.

CONCLUSIONS

This study provides evidence for the potential convective transport of lower atmospheric pollutants, including NH_3 and other precursor gases, to higher levels. These pollutants could partially serve as the source of nitrate aerosols in the ATAL through gas-to-particle formation processes.

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AEROSOL TRANSPORT MECHANISMS OVER THE CENTRAL HIMALAYAN REGION

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Keywords: Boundary Layer Height, Stability, Aerosol Optical Depth, Central Himalaya.

INTRODUCTION

Over mountainous regions, turbulent transport and mixing processes significantly influence the atmospheric structure and make the variation in boundary layer evolution more complicated. These turbulent processes determine the accumulation of pollutants, including aerosol distribution and pollutant dispersion in the boundary layer that affect visibility with the formation of dense fog or haze. Due to the development of orography-induced local circulations, diurnal mountain flows, and their interaction at various spatiotemporal scales, the boundary layer-aerosol interaction and pollutants transport processes are more complicated over complex mountainous terrain than in homogeneous plain regions. Here, the role of the boundary layer on the aerosols is investigated using total aerosol optical depth (AOD) measurements at 550 nm using the Aerosol Observing System (AOS) during the Ganges Valley Aerosol Experiment (GVAX) campaign over Manora Peak Nainital.

METHODS

The inter-relation of the AOD with the boundary layer height (BLH) and mean atmospheric stability (N^2 and wind shear) is investigated during the winter and spring seasons. Further, the assessment of pollutant transport mechanisms is carried out during both seasons using a vertical cross-section analysis across the site, along with the development of the atmospheric boundary layer and wind flow pattern using the ERA5 dataset averaged for the season.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The variation of AOD with BLH and stability conditions across the site has suggested the dominance of coarse mode particles and high aerosol loading with a deeper boundary layer in spring in contrast to winter. Since the observation site is located over a mountain peak that is far from any direct emission of pollutants, therefore, pollutant transport over the site could also be possible through the terrain-forced flows and diurnal mountain wind systems. The widespread long-range transported dust from arid regions of Thar Desert, Middle-East and North Africa by synoptic flow in support with slope-winds are responsible for adverse air quality over the region during this period (Solanki et al., 2013; Kumar et al., 2018; J. Singh et al., 2022). After analyzing such contrasting seasonal differences in aerosol loading, the schematic picture of the daytime pollutant transport pathways from a highly polluted industrial plain region to complex mountains is shown in Figure 1. In winter (Figure 1a), pollutants are trapped within a relatively shallow CBL than in spring due to relatively weak surface heating. During winter, wind speed and turbulences are observed to be calm and weak; therefore, large pollutant concentrations can be trapped within inversion layers over the plain region. Therefore, in this season, only weak mountain-induced circulations can transport the pollutants over mountains from the adjacent pollution sources. During spring (Figure 1b), in the plain region, strong surface heating breaks the inversion layers, and strong westerly flows produce shear-induced turbulent eddies that mix the pollutants with clean air and diffuse the polluted air toward the mountains. At the interface of the mountain and plain, the boundary layer outflow due to the slope wind is stronger as the differential heating is more pronounced as compared to the winter. Therefore, in spring, both horizontal advection of deep boundary layer mixed pollutants over IGP and strong mountain-induced circulation are responsible for pollutants transport over the site.

Figure 1. The pollutants transport pathways within the boundary layer during winter and spring.

CONCLUSIONS

Over the central Himalayan site, pollutant transport in spring is dominated by the advection of deeply mixed polluted air from the Indo-Gangetic Plain, strengthened by strong mountain-induced circulations, while in winter, only weak mountain-induced circulations contribute.

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AEROSOL OPTICAL DEPTH TRENDS OVER THE LAST TWO DECADES IN THE ARCTIC

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Keywords: Aerosol Optical Depth, High Arctic, Trends, AEROSOL ROBOTIC NETWORK

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols are tiny solid particles or liquid droplets suspended in the atmosphere. They are often observed as dust, smoke, and haze and have size ranges from a few nanometres to tens of micrometres (Seinfeld & Pandis, 1998). Atmospheric aerosols are essential for weather and climate as they work as cloud condensation nuclei. Anthropogenic emissions of aerosols alter the Earth's radiative balance, leading to changes in climatic and atmospheric processes. Earth's climate is affected by aerosols' "direct" and "indirect" effects. The direct effect is where aerosols absorb or scatter radiation back into space. In the indirect effect, aerosol particles modify the microphysical and radiative properties of clouds like albedo, lifetime, phase, and probability of precipitation (Zhao & Garrett, 2015). Furthermore, the deposition of certain types of aerosols, like dust and black/brown carbon, on the surface of snow and ice can trigger albedo feedback and facilitate ice melting (Beres et al., 2020).

The Arctic region is experiencing a warming trend approximately four times faster than the global average (Rantanen et al., 2022), a phenomenon referred to as Arctic Amplification. Over the last few decades, many factors have been proposed for the Arctic Amplification phenomenon, and aerosols are one of them (Rantanen et al., 2022). Aerosol observations using satellite remote sensing over the Arctic region are challenging due to the high surface reflectivity of snow/ice-covered surfaces (Srivastava, 2022). By consistently monitoring the optical characteristics of aerosols in the Arctic, we can improve our understanding of their impact on the Arctic. However, due to the challenging conditions, aerosol measurements are limited.

The study of long-term spatio-temporal trends of aerosol optical depth (AOD) provides a meaningful insight into the impact of aerosols on climate. Several studies have used ground-based instruments, satellite retrievals and models to investigate AOD trends. Some studies have shown decreasing trends of AOD over the oceanic region and increasing trends over developing countries (Mehta et al., 2016). Here, we focus on analysing trends of AOD and the aerosol Fine Mode Fraction (FMF) within the high Arctic region (>65°N). We use the AEROSOL ROBOTIC NETWORK (AERONET) measured AOD and provide a comprehensive understanding of the spatio-temporal variations in AOD and FMF in the high Arctic.

METHODS

The AERONET level 2 measurements used in this study were made using the CIMEL sunphotometers (CE-318). We have utilised AOD and FMF at 500 nm in the present study. These data are filtered for clouds and have passed thorough quality assurance procedures, complemented by pre-field and post-field calibration. All trends have been calculated using the bootstrap re-sampling method. The significance of the trend is determined by using the t_B value, where $t_B = |B/\sigma_B|$ and values greater than 2 indicate 95% significance, where B is the coefficient of the trend.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Most of the analysed sites show a non-significant annual declining trend in AOD, apart from Andenes, which has a significant decrease of $-3.03 \pm 0.92\%$ per year. However, Ny-Ålesund has a marked increasing trend of $6.47 \pm 2.94\%$ per year. Contrasting trends emerge in the Fine Mode Fraction (FMF), where some sites exhibit an increasing trend, while other sites show a decreasing trend. It is noteworthy that fine Mode AOD predominantly prevails within the Arctic region. In the Spring season (March, April, May), a notable decrease in AOD is observed across nearly all sites. This decrease is due to decreasing emissions of pollution in European countries. However, the trend in FMF during this period is inconclusive. During Summer (June, July, August) and Autumn (September, October, November), no definitive patterns are observed in either AOD or FMF.

Fig 1: Trends of AOD and FMF over the Arctic during the spring (March-April-May) season. Solid spheres depict significant trends, while circles represent insignificant trends.

CONCLUSIONS

Our analysis reveals a significant decreasing trend in AOD during Spring (March-April-May) in the Arctic, while no clear trends are observed in the FMF across all seasons. Notably, no substantial trends are observed for AOD and FMF in other seasons or annually.

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CHANGE IN THE AEROSOL DISTRIBUTION DURING AN EXTREMELY SEVERE CYCLONE

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Keywords: CYCLONE, AEROSOL, DUST, SEA SALT, AEROSOL OPTICAL DEPTH

INTRODUCTION

A substantial issue with broad socioeconomic ramifications, cyclone-induced disasters represent a serious risk to the nations bordering the Indian Ocean. Indian region observes a significant number of depression/deep depression/ cyclonic and severe cyclonic activities over the surrounding oceanic area (Wahiduzzaman et al., 2022). Aerosol, once emitted, air currents carry them both horizontally and vertically. Studies have indicated the role of aerosol in the occurrence of the cyclones (Cotton et al., 2012). We know that the aerosols act as cloud condensation nuclei and various aerosol concentrations (primarily sea salt aerosols) intensify and transported to higher levels in the atmosphere owing to horizontal and vertical movement associated with cyclone. Thus, aerosols indirectly contributed in the modulation of strength of cyclones (Rosenfeld et al., 2007; Carrió and Cotton, 2011). However the role of cyclones in the redistribution and generation of aerosol is less explored. In the present work, we studied the redistribution and generation of aerosols owing to a severe cyclone in the Bay of Bengal region during May 23, named Mocha.

METHODS

In the present work, we have observed changes in aerosol spatial and vertical distribution over the Bay of Bengal during the development of severe cyclone Mocha and its landfall. To assess the aerosol properties, we studied the MERRA-2 reanalysis daily data of dust, sea salt, black carbon (BC), and Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) has been used (Source: <https://goldsmr4.gesdisc.eosdis.nasa.gov/data/MERRA2/M2T1NXAER.5.12.4>). The time duration selected for this study is from 4 May 23 to 20 May 23. The Mocha cyclone started to form on 9 May 23 and dissipated by 15 May 23. We selected five days before and after the cyclone time duration to monitor the background conditions before and after the cyclone development. We selected the Bay of Bengal region for the study, ranging from 6 °N-22 °N; 84 °E-94 °E.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

We performed this study to monitor the changes in the aerosol concentration during cyclone development. We studied the spatial and vertical distribution of sea salt aerosols, dust aerosols, black carbon (BC) aerosols, and aerosol optical depth (AOD). Sea salt aerosol concentration started to increase with cyclone development over this region. Before the cyclonic activities, the sea salt concentration was about $\sim 100 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ while with cyclone development it reached about $2400 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ near the core and surrounding region. Wind over ocean generates of the sea salt aerosols and bubble bursting is the prominent contributor to this due to wind stress (Monahan and Muirheartaigh, 1980; Stokes et al., 2013). During the cyclonic activities, there is significant increase in the wind stress at the oceanic surface, and thus large amount of sea salt aerosols are generated during this process. Dust concentration before the cyclone ranged below $5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the region, reaching more than $60 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ as the cyclone reached near the land and its land fall. Significant high dust aerosol concentration was observed after the landfall of the cyclone. The increase in the dust aerosols is owing to soil erosion caused due to high wind associated with the cyclone and also because of destruction activities happens during its land fall. Change in spatial distribution is observed in the BC concentration, though its concentration does not change a lot. AOD variation showed significant changes during this event (Figure 1). Figure 1 gives change in the AOD values before and during the development of the cyclone over this region. The AOD is an indicator of aerosol loading in the atmosphere and thus change in all aerosol components can be reflected in the AOD variation. AOD variation indicated that, during the cyclone's development, sea salt contributed primarily to it, and with landfall of it, dust aerosol also contributed significantly.

Figure 1. AOD variation over the Bay of Bengal during the development and dissipation of Cyclone (9-16 May 23).

CONCLUSIONS

In the present work we have investigated the change in the different aerosol components along with AOD during a cyclonic activity. During the cyclonic activity sea salt aerosols and dust aerosols showed a significant increase in its concentration. Several time increase has been noticed in these aerosols during the formation and dissipation of cyclone. Sea salt aerosols concentration increase could be seen also the line of movement while the dust aerosol concentration increases near the West Bengal region in India, and over Bangladesh and Myanmar region. Both these aerosols are wind generated and during the cyclone wind stress significantly increases at land surface and oceanic surface. BC aerosol concentration did not show a drastic change in its concentration. As AOD values are indicative of aerosol loading in the atmosphere thus AOD values showed notable changes during the formation of cyclone.

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DIURNAL VARIATION OF BLACK CARBON OVER MACHOI GLACIER IN KASHMIR

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Keywords: Aerosol transport and deposition, Indian Himalayas.

INTRODUCTION

The process of climate change is intricate and is influenced by multiple atmospheric factors and processes. One of the crucial factors contributing to climate change is atmospheric aerosols, which alter the Earth's radiation budget, cloud formation, and precipitation patterns, among other things (IPCC, 2007). Aerosol contains various light-absorbing particles (LAPs hereafter). LAPs speed the snow melting process by disturbing the snow albedo and its radiative forcing (RF) due to increased solar radiation absorption from surface darkening (Qian et al., 2015). The snow's high reflectivity helps bounce back solar radiation to space. Aerosols such as black carbon and dust particles can absorb solar radiation and reduce the snow's albedo, increasing solar radiation absorbed by the snow. This increase results in more melting, changes in the timing and amount of snowmelt runoff, and can even affect the ecosystem and hydrological processes. Furthermore, the deposition of aerosols on snow can alter the snow's physical and chemical characteristics, leading to changes in the snowpack and affecting the water resources in these regions. Therefore, understanding the interaction between aerosols and snow is crucial because it has significant implications for regional and global climate and the environment.

Himalayan glaciers are impacted by dust storms that come from arid and desert regions to the west, specifically the Middle East, before the monsoon season. Every year before the start of the summer monsoon, mineral dust originating from the deserts of southwest Asia is carried over the foothills of the Himalayas (Gautam et al., 2013). The Himalayan region experiences high dust and BC loadings mainly from local and regional emission sources, but aerosols are also transported from the IGP to the Himalayan foothills (Raatikainen et al., 2014; Sarangi et al., 2016). Due to its remote locations the quantification of aerosol properties is hard to infer. The present paper focuses on the diurnal variation of aerosol properties over Machoi glacier.

DATA AND METHODS

To gather comprehensive insights, various aerosol properties including Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD), Black Carbon (BC), and Particulate Matter (PM) are meticulously measured for 4 days (27th – 30th June 2022) across the Machoi glacier (located at coordinates 34.270 N, 75.530 E 4200m asl). These measurements are conducted utilizing specialized tools, which include a Sun-photometer for AOD assessment, a portable MicroAeth for precise BC measurements, and an Optical Particle Counter (OPC) for PM evaluation and aerosol size distribution. While the mass measurement obtained from OPC may not be highly precise, our main objective was to assess the relative increase from morning to afternoon and the transition from PM_{2.5} to PM₁₀. The measurements for AOD are acquired at hourly intervals spanning from 800 hrs to 1600 hrs, whereas the BC and OPC assessments are executed continuously, employing a sampling interval of 5 minutes from 800 hrs to 1600 hrs.

Figure 1: The chart depicts the diurnal variation of PM, BC and AOD levels recorded over the Machoi Glacier. The forenoon period spans from 800 to 1100 hours, while the afternoon period spans from 1200 to 1600 hours.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The graphical representation in Figure 1 illustrates the diurnal fluctuations in PM, BC, and AOD. Observing the figure uncovers a notable rise in the magnitude of each parameter as the day progresses from the forenoon to the afternoon. Both PM and BC concentrations exhibit an approximate 200% increase, while AOD experiences a rise of about 45% during this transition. This pronounced increase in PM concentration compared to AOD might be because there's not much total change in aerosol content, but only vertical redistribution. While AOD is primarily related to aerosol particles in the atmosphere, the composition of these particles can change throughout the day. Different types of aerosols, such as dust, sea salt, or organic matter, may have different effects on AOD. Therefore, even if the AOD increases by 50%, the composition of aerosols within it may change in a way that contributes to the larger increase in PM concentrations. The IGP is known for its high pollution levels due to a combination of urban activities, biomass burning, and meteorological factors. Pollutants generated in this region might be transported by wind to the study area and gets mixed within the ascending boundary layer, consequently leading to the significant afternoon rise in PM, BC, and AOD values.

CONCLUSIONS

A substantial increase in the PM and BC concentrations can be seen during afternoon compared to forenoon. This notable PM increase, compared to AOD, may result from vertical redistribution of aerosols rather than a substantial change in their total content. Wind transported pollutants may be the major source to the significant afternoon increase in PM, BC, and AOD. We lack enough information about aerosols, how they move, settle, and their characteristics in glacier ice in the Indian Himalayas. More on-site measurements are needed to better grasp aerosol makeup and its impact on snow and ice in this area.

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EFFICIENCY OF WET DEPOSITION IN PM 2.5 REMOVAL OVER INDO GANGETIC PLAIN DURING WINTER

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Keywords: wet-deposition, IGP, winter, aerosols.

INTRODUCTION

There is a noticeable seasonal variation in PM_{2.5} pollution over Indo Gangetic Plane(IGP), and the winter months have much higher PM_{2.5} pollution loading than other times of the year (Bran and Srivastava, 2017; Kota et al., 2018; Ojha et al., 2020; Upadhyay et al., 2020). The main contributors to the region's severe pollution vary from desert dust brought by winds, industrial emissions, vehicular exhaust and power plants. Agricultural residue burning in the northern Indian states of Punjab and Haryana is believed to have contributed to local pollution. Factors such as low wind speed and high humidity contribute to very high levels of air pollution in northern India, especially during the winter months. Wintertime high aerosol loading over the Indo-Gangetic region is a significant environmental concern with adverse effects on human health and the climate system. Wet scavenging is an essential natural mechanism that helps to mitigate the concentration of PM_{2.5} in the atmosphere, contributing to cleaner air and improved air quality for human health and ecosystem well-being. This study uses observational data to analyse the relation between particulate matter concentration and rain over the Indo-Gangetic plain during the winter season from 2016 to 2020.

METHODS

For the winter seasons from 2002 to 2021, Aerosol Optical Depth(AOD) from Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer(MODIS) and monthly precipitation from Global Precipitation Measurement(GPM) for the Indo–Gangetic Plain were analysed to look for any trends. A correlation analysis between these two data sets was also conducted. The rain (from Indian Metrological Department) in various stations over IGP, was also examined together with the frequency distribution of the daily PM_{2.5} concentration (from Central Pollution Control Board) during different winter seasons. The Estimates were made of the PM_{2.5} concentration drop during each rain event for various stations over IGP (Panchkula, Kanpur, Muzaffarpur, Punjab Agricultural University, Amritsar, Varanasi, Noida, Faridabad, IHBAS Delhi, R K Puram and Gaya). At these stations, they are analysed along with the daily concentration of different aerosol species.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

For the years 2002-2021, an increasing trend in winter-time AOD was observed for IGP. Simultaneously, for the same period and season, a very slight decreasing trend in precipitation over the region was observed. The IGP region has a negative correlation between precipitation and AOD for the winter season, whereas other regions, such as the central Arabian Sea and parts of the Indian Peninsula, have a positive correlation for the same season. For IGP, 11 of 19 winter seasons (58%) showed a negative correlation between precipitation and AOD, with nine years (82%) showing a more negative correlation greater than 0.5. Over 19 consecutive years, the correlation coefficient seems to vary from 0.9 on the negative side to 0.8 on the positive side. It's also worth noting that four of the years had a positive correlation of more than 0.5 between AOD and precipitation. A reduction in PM_{2.5} concentration of up to 70% and rainfall of up to 6 mm is associated with approximately 50% of total winter rain events. Most stations studied showed a seasonal decrease in PM_{2.5} concentration, with the frequency of rain events being more critical than the amount of rain. This

dependency, too, took on different forms for different stations. The relationship between the decrease in PM_{2.5} after each rain event and the concentration of different aerosol species varies from station to station.

Figure 1. Plot of the correlation coefficient between monthly precipitation(GPM) and monthly AOD(MODIS) for the winter months(Dec, Jan & Feb) for the years 2002-2021.

CONCLUSIONS

For the winter season, there is an inverse relationship between aerosol loading and precipitation in the IGP region. For various polluted stations in IGP, the winter rain events result in lower PM_{2.5} concentrations. Depending on the type, frequency, and amount of rain, as well as the local emission, the wet deposition of PM_{2.5} varies from station to station. During the winter, wet deposition is effective at removing PM_{2.5} from the IGP.

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**INFLUENCE OF METEOROLOGICAL PARAMETERS ON THE DIURNAL VARIATION OF
PM_{2.5} CONCENTRATION OVER DELHI**

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Keywords: Air Quality, Particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), Meteorological Parameters, Aerosols, Diurnal variation.

INTRODUCTION

Particulate matter pollution is one of the most prevalent environmental problems in India. Particulate matter is a mixture of suspended particles in the air, of which PM_{2.5} (PM_{2.5} with an aerodynamic diameter less than 2.5) is of particular significance due to its severe health effects. A variety of factors influence PM_{2.5} concentrations, including meteorological parameters, anthropogenic sources, chemical processes etc. PM_{2.5} pollution is expected to further deteriorate in the coming decades, due to rapid ongoing urbanization as well as industrial growth. This particulate pollution over any specific region also has important implications to the other regions through effective transport mechanism governed by the Asian summer monsoon to the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere, where pollutants can be re-distributed on a wider scale and thus affect the global climate and air quality (*Chen et al. 2020*). Assessment of diurnal variations of urban PM_{2.5} concentrations and their relationships with the various meteorological parameters is the key to understanding the drivers of air pollution and devising effective mitigation strategies in Indian megacities.

METHODS

The present study is an attempt to investigate the impact of meteorological parameters in dispersion of pollutant air parcel and its variation with time over Delhi, India. For this, CAAQMS operated in Delhi have been selected on the basis of data availability and the location of the area. The hourly and daily average data of PM_{2.5} and meteorological parameters have been collected for year 2019 and processed further accordingly.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The outcome of the study depicts that the meteorology has significant influence on the PM_{2.5} concentration. It was observed that diurnal pattern between two stations shows a time lag between the occurrence of peak hours, which might be due to movement of air parcel due to direction of flow of wind. The wind influences the dispersion or movement of air parcels in the atmosphere. It was also reflecting 2 maxima in diurnal variation of PM_{2.5} concentration at any given location i.e., one in the forenoon and the other in the night time. The day time maximum is caused by vehicular emission, road side dust and wind-blown dust and the night time maximum is the result of stable boundary layer and less mixing depth

Figure 1: Movement of PM2.5 Pollution mass over Delhi in different time interval (a) 00:00 Hour (b) 05:00 hour (c) 12:00 hour (d) 20:00 hour

Figure 2: Diurnal Variation of PM2.5 pollution in different locations of Delhi (a) Day Time Maxima, (b) Night Time Maxima

CONCLUSIONS

The study concludes that meteorology has significant influence on the PM2.5 concentration. The diurnal variability in the distribution of the pollution is attributed mainly to the meteorology.

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CRUISING THROUGH COMMUTES: CHARACTERIZATION AND DEPOSITION MODELING OF SIZE-SEGREGATED PM EXPOSURE

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Keywords: Aerosol Characterization, PM deposition, Health effects

INTRODUCTION

Urban commuters across various Asian locales grapple with elevated levels of PM_{2.5} pollution stemming from traffic bottlenecks during peak hours. A plethora of research studies has substantiated the susceptibility of individuals who traverse to workplaces or other destinations to deleterious vehicular emissions, culminating in an escalation of air pollution, particularly in densely congested urban corridors. This quandary assumes remarkable prominence in Asian domains, wherein residents routinely allocate a substantial fraction, approximately 8%, of their daily act of commuting. As unveiled in recent investigations by (Lee et al. 2022), denizens within this Asian expanse, on average, expend between 39 to 91 minutes daily for their commuting endeavours. A multitude of epidemiological inquiries persistently underscores robust associations between human exposure to traffic related PM and the onset of adverse cardiovascular and respiratory health maladies (Lee et al. 2022). Nevertheless, a comprehensive grasp of PM exposure, its chemical composition, the mechanisms governing its transport, and its deposition on urban commuters still eludes us. This study marks the first attempt to investigate size-segregated PM (PM_{2.5}, PM₁, PM_{0.5}, and PM_{0.25}), elemental and organic composition, and age-specific lobar deposition in the context of diverse transportation modes, such as motorcycle, car windows open (WO), car windows closed (WC), and bus travel.

METHODS

During the specified timeframe spanning from July 21st to August 28th in the year 2022, we conducted a comprehensive monitoring (Saravanampatti to Gandhipuram) in Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India, focusing on size-segregated PM (PM_{2.5}, PM₁, PM_{0.5}, and PM_{0.25}). This endeavour encompassed the observation of morning (09:00 to 10:30 a.m.) and evening (05:00 and 06:30 p.m.) during peak commuting hours, involving the utilization of various modes of transportation, namely motorcycle (Hero pleasure), car WO (Swift RS), car WC (Swift RS), and bus (TNSTC). To monitor the size-segregated PM, we employed the SKC cascade personal sampler, which operates on the principles of inertial impaction, with a constant flow rate set at 9L/min. In order to elucidate the elemental composition, Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectroscopy for each mode of transportation and employed Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy for the analysis of organic elements in the PM_{2.5} filters. Furthermore, for the simulation of age-specific lobar deposition, the multiple path particle dosimetry model (Asgharian et al. 2001) (<https://www.ara.com/mppd/>), encompassing various age groups including infants (3 months), toddlers (28 months), children (8 years), adolescents (14 years), and adults (21 years) to understand the deposition of PM.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings unequivocally demonstrate a marked increase in PM concentration during the evening commute hours compared to the morning, depicting a discernible diurnal trend. The percentage distribution of each size-segregated PM fraction indicates a hierarchical pattern of PM_{0.25} > PM_{2.5} > PM₁ > PM_{0.5} > PM_{0.25} for both morning and evening rush hours, as illustrated in Fig 1. Motorcycle commuters experienced the highest PM exposure at 36%, followed by car commuters with WO (28%), those with car WC (19%), and bus passengers (17%). This pattern of exposure underscores the influence of atmospheric conditions during evening commuting hours, which tend to impede air circulation, thereby fostering PM accumulation. Consequently, this phenomenon leads to heightened concentration levels as opposed to the daytime period characterized by greater dispersion. It is important to note that atmospheric PM undergoes various microphysical processes, including coagulation, condensation, and nucleation, which collectively contribute to its heterogeneity within the PM_{2.5} fraction. Elemental composition analysis of PM_{2.5} samples revealed the presence of B > Ca > Fe > Pb > Al > Hg > TI > Mg > Cu > K > Na > Mn > Cr were commonly present in various modes of commuting. Interestingly, vehicles themselves are a significant contributor to the accumulation of road dust through their wear-and-tear on parts like brake pads and tires which contain Ca, Na, Mg, and K. The organic elemental composition from FTIR predominant groups namely carbonyl, carboxylic, OH, SO₄²⁻, CO₃²⁻, C-H, C=C, C=O, and C-O were observed for all the modes of commuting. The

presence of these organic compounds when exposed causes serious health effects such as respiratory infections and cardiovascular diseases. The findings indicate that the infant group exhibited the highest deposition of size-segregated PM, followed by the children and toddler groups, in that order. Fig 2 illustrates the deposition fraction visualization of PM_{2.5} among motorcycle commuters. Regarding the deposition of PM_{2.5}, they predominantly settle in the head region (55–95%) and the tracheobronchial region (3–44%). However, the deposition of PM₁ is most pronounced in the pulmonary region (36–63%) and the tracheobronchial region (28.2–52.7%), with the exception being the adult age group, where PM₁, PM_{0.5}, and PM_{0.25} exhibit the highest deposition percentages in the pulmonary regions. In terms of lobar deposition, the lower lobes receive the highest deposition (61.4%), followed by the upper lobes (29.2%) and middle lobes (9.4%). PM 0.25 dominates the deposition across all five lobes in infants, children, and adults.

CONCLUSION

During evening rush hours, motorcycle commuters experienced the highest exposure levels at $182.36 \pm 23.65 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. Size-segregated PM concentrations followed this order: $\text{PM}_{0.25} > \text{PM}_{2.5} > \text{PM}_1 > \text{PM}_{0.5} < \text{PM}_{0.25}$, with exposure patterns ranking as motorcycle > Car WO > Car WC > Bus across all commuting modes. Elemental composition analysis consistently identified B (26%), Ca (18%), Fe (11%), Pb (11%), Al (9%), Hg (8%), TI (7%), Mg (3%), and various other elements such as K, Na, Mn, Cr, and Cu, collectively constituting an additional 7%. Organic compounds, including carbonyl, carboxylic, OH, SO₄²⁻, CO₃²⁻, C-H, C=C, C=O, and C-O groups, were detected in all commuting modes, posing potential health risks, particularly respiratory and cardiovascular effects upon exposure. Regarding regional deposition, the pulmonary region received the highest deposition in all commuting modes. Deposition patterns followed this sequence: Children > Toddler > Infant > Adult > Adolescent for all age groups across commuting modes. Lobar deposition analysis revealed that the left lower lobes accounted for 59.3% of the deposition, while the right lower lobes contributed 40.7%.

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ATMOSPHERIC AEROSOL DEPOSITION STUDIES AROUND KUDANKULAM NUCLEAR SITE

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INTRODUCTION

Aerosols are liquid or solid particles suspended in the atmosphere, typically with diameters on the order of nanometers to microns. These particles impact air quality and the radiative balance of the planet. Aerosol particles from both natural and human sources are present in the atmosphere. The movement of aerosols in the atmosphere is caused by transport, dispersion, and deposition. Transport is movement caused by a time-averaged wind flow. Dispersion results from local turbulence, that is, motions that last less than the time used to average the transport. Deposition processes, including precipitation, scavenging and sedimentation cause downward movement of pollutants in the atmosphere which ultimately remove the pollutants to the ground surface. Dry deposition is a key process for the removal of aerosols from the atmosphere and plays an important role in controlling the lifetime of atmospheric aerosols. Indeed, the lifetime of an aerosol in the atmosphere is determined by wet and dry deposition, with wet deposition losses being typically estimated to account for the majority of submicron particles removal from the atmosphere. Furthermore, wet deposition is eventually more important locally or regionally, close to aerosols emission sources, whereas dry deposition would be more important in areas far from emission sources. The objective of this study is to investigate the deposition flux of aerosol particles by using natural cosmogenic ⁷Be as a tracer. ⁷Be attaches predominantly to aerosols in the submicron size range (Papastefanou and Ioannidou, 1995), therefore it is susceptible to the same transport and depositional processes governing these aerosols, making it a useful atmospheric tracer (Brost et al., 1991). These aerosols can reach the ground under clear sky conditions through particle sedimentation (dry deposition), but are removed more efficiently from the atmosphere by precipitation scavenging (wet deposition).

METHODS

Aerosol samples were collected on a glass fiber filter paper using high volume air sampler, and deposition samples were collected on grease coated polyethylene sheets on monthly basis. For wet deposition, rain water samples were collected during rainy season. All the samples were processed and analyzed for ⁷Be by HPGe detector.

The dry deposition rate (di)_{dry} (Bq m⁻²s⁻¹) and dry deposition velocity (V)_{dry} (m s⁻¹) were estimated by using the equations 1 & 2.

$$(V)_{dry} = \frac{(C)_{drydep}}{C_a} \quad \text{-----1} \quad \text{-----2}$$

Where (C)_{drydep} is the total dry deposited activity (Bq) for a period of D days, A is the area of exposure (m²). C_a is the ⁷Be concentration in air (Bq m⁻³). Wet deposition rate (di)_{wet} and the velocity (V)_{wet} was estimated by using the equations 3 & 4

$$(V)_{wet} = \frac{(C)_w}{RF} \quad \text{-----3} \quad \text{-----4}$$

Where (C)_w is the cumulative rain water activity collected for a period of D days (Bq m⁻³). RF is the cumulative rainfall (m) for a period of D days.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Deposition velocities of aerosols by dry and wet processes are summarized in **Table 1**. **Figure 1** explains the overall statistical values of dry and wet deposition velocity. For ⁷Be-bearing particles, the dry deposition velocity varied from 1.0E-03 to 3.4E-02 m s⁻¹ (Papastefanou et al, 1995). Grönholm et al reported that the dry deposition velocity over the Scots pine forest, Hyytiälä, Finland by Eddy covariance method (EC) varies from 6.0 E-04 to 5.3E-03 m s⁻¹. Allen et al reported that the mean dry deposition velocity estimated by Gradient method in Sports fields at the University of Essex, Colchester, England is 1.00 E-03 m s⁻¹. Estimated dry deposition velocity is found to be 1.49E-04 to 4.00E-03 m s⁻¹ and the mean value is 1.20E-03 m s⁻¹. Estimated wet deposition velocity is found to be varying from 1.96E-03 m s⁻¹ to 6.70E-02 m s⁻¹ and the mean value is 1.85E-02 m s⁻¹. Wet deposition velocity is found to be greater than dry deposition velocity by about an order of magnitude. Still dry deposition plays an important role at Kudankulam site because this

site is located in the rain shadow region of the Western Ghats. It gets scanty rainfall. Reported aerosol deposition velocities are comparable with the theoretical model values as well as reported literature values.

Table 1: Aerosols Deposition velocity around Kudankulam from 2011 to 2018

year	Dry deposition rate (12 samples/year)				No of samples	Wet deposition rate (samples no indicated)			
	m s ⁻¹					m s ⁻¹			
	Range		mean	Stdev		Range		mean	Stdev
2011	5.20E-04	7.56E-04	6.38E-04	1.67E-04	6	1.22E-02	2.72E-02	1.87E-02	7.67E-03
2012	5.84E-04	1.11E-03	7.95E-04	2.28E-04	1	--	6.63E-02	6.63E-02	---
2013	3.54E-04	2.00E-03	8.77E-04	6.79E-04	10	1.96E-03	2.50E-02	1.10E-02	8.23E-03
2014	1.01E-03	4.00E-03	1.96E-03	1.21E-03	12	2.74E-03	5.43E-02	1.88E-02	1.54E-02
2015	1.49E-04	2.53E-03	1.09E-03	1.03E-03	13	5.01E-03	1.60E-02	1.24E-02	5.02E-03
2017	3.98E-04	2.52E-03	1.34E-03	8.44E-04	6	6.18E-03	4.22E-02	2.26E-02	1.70E-02
2018	3.92E-04	2.07E-03	1.27E-03	8.43E-04	8	2.35E-03	6.70E-02	2.14E-02	2.40E-02

Figure 1. Box plots for Dry and wet deposition rate

CONCLUSION

Using cosmogenic ⁷Be as tracer, aerosol deposition rates have been evaluated for the nuclear site around Kudankulam. The magnitude of dry deposition vis-a-vis the wet deposition has been studied and site specific values of deposition rates have been obtained. These deposition rates are good simulation for radioactive aerosols for application in radio ecological models in case of any radiation emergency scenario to assist the authorities for quick and fast decision making in the implementation of the counter measures. Though wet deposition rate is an order or more higher than the dry deposition rate, the importance of dry deposition rate in Kudankulam site which receives scanty rain fall is brought out.

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EVALUATION OF SODIUM AEROSOL TRANSPORT EFFICIENCY IN CIRCULAR TUBE

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Keywords: SODIUM AEROSOL, AEROSOL TRANSPORT EFFICIENCY, AEROSOL SAMPLING.

INTRODUCTION

The accurate evaluation of aerosol transport within sampling tubes is pivotal for diverse fields ranging from particulate monitoring, industrial quality control and design of the instrument. Sampling tubes constitute a fundamental component of aerosol collection systems, where their ability to effectively transport aerosol directly impacts the reliability of collected data and the precision of subsequent analyses. However, the transport efficiency test for the sampling tube and instrument is rarely carried out by the researcher. The aerosol loss in sampling tube is still a significant problem affecting the credibility of measured data and leads to the underestimation of concentration and sampling bias. The aerosol deposition inside sampling tube depends upon various factors viz. carrier gas flow rate, aerosol size ranges, particle density, different tube design, length, and diameter of the sampling tube etc. Many mechanisms like gravitational settling, diffusion and turbulent-induced impaction govern the aerosol transport efficacy through sampling tubes. Thermophoresis also contributes to deposition, but it comes in play only if a temperature gradient is there. There are many semi-empirical relations that have been developed in the second half of last century to predict the aerosol deposition fraction and are widely used. The calculated results were compared with many experimental observations (Wang *et al.*, 2022). However, for the sodium aerosol transport efficiency from sampling tube hardly any study available in literature. Hence, a simple method for sodium aerosol loss in the sampling tube need to be analysed before performing the experiment and same should be validated with observations. Towards this objective, the present work has been initiated. In this paper, the sodium aerosol transport efficiency in circular tubes focusing on variations with particle diameter, tube length, and flow rates been estimated. The subsequent sections, explains the detailed methodology, semi – empirical relations, results, and discussion.

METHODS

In a horizontal tube, aerosol can settle on the walls by virtue of many deposition mechanisms. The aerosol transport through sampling tube for different flow conditions have different empirical relationship for determining transport efficiency (η). In case of laminar flow in circular tubes, η is given as (Fuchs, 1964):

$$\eta = 1 - \frac{2}{\pi} \zeta \quad (1)$$

Where, $\zeta = \frac{3}{4} Z = \frac{3}{4} \frac{L}{D_t} \frac{V}{U}$, Z is gravitational deposition parameter, L is length of tube, D_t is inner diameter of the tube, V is particle terminal settling velocity, U is flowing velocity inside tube.

$$V = \frac{\rho d_p^2 g}{18 \mu} \quad (2)$$

Where, ρ is density of particles, d_p is diameter of particle, g is acceleration due to gravity, μ is dynamic viscosity of air. Transport efficiency due to diffusion is calculated as (Gormley and Kennedy, 1949):

$$\eta = 1 - 2.56 \varepsilon^{\frac{2}{3}} + 1.2 \varepsilon + 0.177 \varepsilon^{\frac{4}{3}} \quad \text{for } \varepsilon < 0.02 \quad (3)$$

$$\eta = 0.819 \exp(-3.675 \varepsilon) + 0.097 \exp(-22.3 \varepsilon) + 0.032 \exp(-57 \varepsilon) \quad \text{for } \varepsilon > 0.02 \quad (4)$$

Where, $\xi = \frac{\pi DL}{Q}$, D is particle diffusion coefficient. Since in the present study, the flow is laminar region, deposition due to impaction can be neglected which comes in case of turbulent flow. Combined transport efficiency due to gravitational settling and diffusion can be obtained by multiplying the individual transport efficiencies.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The sodium aerosol behaviour in a large containment required either intrinsic sampling or sample drawn for a long distance. Sodium aerosol behaviour studied in MINA facility has different lengths of sampling tube ranges from 1.0 - 4.0 m (Kumar *et al.*, 2023) and other properties are given in Table 1. The estimated η with aerosol diameter for different tube lengths at fixed flow rate (10 LPM) and different flow rates at fixed length of tube (4.0 m) is shown in Figure 1. The η is found to be decreasing significantly for aerosol diameter $\geq 5 \mu\text{m}$. However, there is not much change for $\leq 1 \mu\text{m}$ irrespective of sampling length and flow rates. Upon increasing flow rate transport efficiency increases and upon increasing length it decreases.

Parameters	Value along with unit
Tube diameter (D_t)	10 mm
Length of tube (L)	1.0, 2.0, 3.0 & 4.0 m
Flow rate (Q)	5, 8, 10, & 13 LPM
Density of aerosol particle (ρ)	2130 kg/m ³
Carrier gas density (air density)	1.3 kg/m ³
Kinematic viscosity of air at 25 °C	1.562 x 10 ⁻⁵ m ² /s

Table 1. Parameters used for estimation of aerosol transport efficiency from sampling tube.

Figure 1. Variation of aerosol transport efficiency with aerosol diameter.

CONCLUSIONS

The present study provides valuable insights into the factors affecting η in sampling tubes. Understanding how particle size distribution, tube length, diameter, and flow rate influence efficiency is crucial for designing and optimizing aerosol sampling systems. These findings contribute to the development of more accurate and reliable aerosol sampling methodologies for future aerosol experiments.

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RESUSPENSION DYNAMICS OF THERMOPHORETICALLY DEPOSITED PARTICLES VIA SHOCKWAVE INTERACTION

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Keywords: SHOCKWAVE, THERMOPHORETIC DEPOSITION, RESUSPENSION

INTRODUCTION

In the event of a meltdown at a nuclear power station, the core can liquefy, which is called corium. It is possible for the vessel to be damaged or perhaps completely destroyed if this corium comes into contact with liquid water and causes steam explosions. This phenomenon is called a "vapor explosion" (Cronenberg and Benz 1980). The mishap can also cause hydrogen to build up, which could result in explosions inside the containment building (Abou-Rjeily et al. 2011). The shockwave created by these explosions has the capacity to fragment and resuspend the deposited particles and can propel them to great distances (Brandt et al., 1987; Strecker and Roth, 1994). The purpose of this investigation is to learn more about the dynamics between shockwaves and the metal oxide particles that have been deposited by thermophoresis.

METHODS

A plasma torch aerosol generator (PTAG) with 25 kW power was used to create zinc metal oxide particles. Zinc metal powder was fed into the plasma flame, where it vaporized, reacted with oxygen, and condensed into zinc metal oxide aerosol particles. These particles were passed through thin stainless steel sheets placed about 1 m away from the PTAG, undergoing thermophoretic deposition for an hour. The average temperature gradient remained at 530 K due to pipe wall and gas temperatures of 640 K and 1184 K. The research used an open-end shock tube with a high-pressure driver section and a low-pressure driven section, separated by a diaphragm membrane. The test section, located 3 m downstream of the diaphragm, featured the deposited metal oxide plate for non-intrusive studies. High-speed cameras at 14000 fps and a 200 W LED light source were used to capture the dynamics of resuspension.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Compared to loosely deposited layers, thermophoretic deposition results in higher packing density, effectively forming a cohesive entity. This dense particle layer generates stronger baroclinic vorticity when exposed to a shockwave due to pressure and density variations. When a Richtmyer-Meshkov instability (RMI) is triggered, a disturbance occurs in the layer at the loose particle's location. Some particles resuspend in the flow, overcoming gravity as they move behind the shockwave, causing particle erosion and the formation of microscopic cavities. Internal pressure inside the cavity decreases, leading to layer segregation and resuspension as a lump due to pressure differentials. This is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Formation of cavities in particles deposited via thermophoresis

The relative effect of shock strength (Mach number) on particle resuspension is seen in Figure 2. Stronger shock waves induce particles to resuscitate at a much faster rate because the flow behind the shock wave is moving more quickly, further disintegrating the agitated particles at the interface. As the shockwave's intensity rises, it has been found that the resuscitation process quickens. The graph between the normalised vertical displacement with respect to time for various Mach values is shown in Figure 3. Since there is no shock wave disruption at first, there is no displacement. When the baroclinic vorticity reaches a certain level, the particle lumps split and begin to move vertically before atomizing. This phenomenon manifests earlier for greater Mach values than for lower Mach numbers. The vertical displacement has nothing to do with the lump's atomization.

Figure 2. Resuspension at varying Mach numbers

Figure 3. Vertical displacement of particle lump

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this experiment have provided valuable insights into the complex dynamics of particle resuspension, particularly in the context of thermophoretic deposition and shock wave amplitudes. It is evident from our findings that the process of particle resuspension is distinctly different from particles that have merely been loosely deposited. One key observation is the sensitivity of particle resuspension to the amplitude of the shock wave. Shock waves play a crucial role in dislodging particles from their thermophoretically deposited state. Higher shock wave amplitudes result in a more effective resuspension process. This sensitivity emphasizes the dynamic nature of the resuspension phenomenon, which responds to external forces. The distinct behaviour of particles that have been thermophoretically deposited can be attributed to the stronger bonding that forms between them during this process. This enhanced bonding leads to a higher packing density, resulting in the formation of particle clusters. When subjected to the shock wave, these clusters are dislodged as a unit, initially creating a lump of particles in suspension. However, what makes this study particularly intriguing is the subsequent atomization of these particle lumps during the resuspension process. Atomization refers to the further breaking down of the particle cluster into smaller individual particles. These smaller particles are liberated from the lump, allowing them to be carried even further and over greater distances by the fluid flow. The atomization process is of significant importance as it enhances the transportability of the particles. Smaller particles exhibit improved aerodynamic properties and are less prone to gravitational settling. Consequently, they can be transported over longer distances in the surrounding environment, potentially impacting air quality, health, and other environmental factors.

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PARTICLE DEPOSITION IN G3-G6 RESPIRATORY AIRWAY BIFURCATIONS

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Keywords: aerosol transport, respiratory deposition, CFD simulation, respiratory bifurcation.

INTRODUCTION

The human respiratory system can functionally be classified into two broad zones: (a) conducting zones (nose to terminal bronchioles) which transport the air into and out of the respiratory system and (b) respiratory zones (respiratory bronchioles and alveolar ducts) where gas exchange takes place. These zones are partitioned into 23 generations of dichotomous branches extending from trachea (G0) to the alveolar ducts (G23). A predictive knowledge of particle transport through these bifurcating airways is important either to optimize therapeutic effects of pharmaceutical aerosols or to minimize harmful effects of toxic/radioactive aerosol exposure. To explore deposition pattern of inhaled aerosols in the respiratory tract, computational fluid particle dynamics (CFPD) simulations are now widely used. In this study, we have adopted a Eulerian, sectional, internally mixed aerosol model using Aerosolved (v 2.0) [1] open-source code to study deposition pattern in G3–G6 airway. The dimensions and orientations of G3-G6 region are chosen following the symmetric Weibel Type A (1963) model [2].

METHODS

The computational geometry (Fig. 1) of G3 – G6 airway has been prepared using the parameters given in Table 1. A refined mesh (Fig. 2) has been generated in the computational domain with total number of elements of 3191812 and total number of nodes of 590922. Computation has been carried out for Reynolds number 1000 which leads to an inlet velocity of 2.61 m/s for the given inlet dimension.

Generations	Length L (mm)	Diameter D (mm)	Bent radius R (mm)	Carinal ridge radius r (mm)
G3	7.6	5.6	9.0	0.45
G4	12.7	4.5	7.0	0.35
G5	10.7	3.5	5.6	0.28
G6	9.0	2.8	-	-

Table 1. Generation parameters for G3 – G6 (symmetric Weibel Type A (1963) model) [3].

Figure 1. Computational model of G3–G6 prepared for simulation using data from [3].

The air flowing in the respiratory airways has been considered to be homogeneous, Newtonian, and incompressible in nature. Uniform velocity profile is applied at the inlet cross section, pressure-outlet boundary condition is implemented at the outlets, non-slip boundary condition is employed at walls. The compressible PISO (Pressure-Implicit with Splitting of Operators) algorithm has been adopted to solve the transient Navier-Stokes equations. A time step of 1E-5 s is used to ensure that the Courant number is less than 1 and total flow time is set as 0.1 s. A poly-disperse aerosol size distribution with CMD of 1 μm and

σ_g of 2.5 is considered. Sectional model is used for resolving the particle size distribution, with a total of 15

sections representing particle diameters spanning from ~ 36 nm – 27 μ m (equivalent to particle mass of $2.53E-20$ kg to $9.87E-12$ kg).

Figure 2. Refined mesh of computational geometry.

Figure 3. Velocity profile at Z=0 plane.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Fig. 3 shows the axial airflow profile along frontal plane where the incoming airflow first splits at the first bifurcation and boundary layers are formed at the walls as well as carinal ridge region. Higher axial air flow rates are observed at generations G4.1, G5.2 and G6.3 for left side and similar pattern can be observed for right side as well. Fig. 4 shows a closer view of counter rotating secondary flows inside G5.2 branch which appear downstream of the carinal ridge during inhalation. These secondary flows have noticeable influences on particle deposition and higher deposition is observed where the axial airflow is higher. This deposition effect is much pronounced for higher size particles as compared to lower size. Fig. 5 shows normalized particle deposition flux on for sizes 0.15 μ m and 26.6 μ m. Higher size particles are mostly deposited by inertial impaction whereas smaller particles are mainly deposited due to Brownian diffusion. The simulation results have found to be consistent with results given by Ou et al, 2020 [3] who adopted a Euler – Lagrangian approach for the simulation using commercial CFD code FLUENT.

Figure 4. Simulated secondary flow streamlines and contour of constant axial velocity at a cross sectional plane on G5.2.

Figure 5. Aerosol deposition fluxes for sizes 0.15 μ m and 26.6 μ m viewed from front. The color indicates the deposited number flux ($\#/s$) normalized to surface averaged inlet flux ($\#/s$).

CONCLUSIONS

In the present work, flow profile and aerosol deposition pattern have been studied inside a three-dimensional in-plane triple-bifurcation airway model (G3–G6) using a Eulerian- Eulerian aerosol transport model. It is shown that air flow profile strongly influence the particle deposition. Higher sized particles deposit more where air flow rates are higher. Lower size particles (< 1 μ m) deposit nearly uniformly across the geometry.

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RISK ASSESSMENT STUDY OF DEPOSITED PARTICLES IN HUMAN BREATHING PASSAGE THROUGH A DOSIMETRY MODEL APPROACH

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Keywords: PARTICULATE MATTER, MPPD, PM DEPOSITION, SIZE SEGREGATED PARTICLES

INTRODUCTION

The size of particulate matter (PM) plays a crucial role in determining their potential harm (Cipoli et al., 2022). When inhaled, these particles can penetrate deep into the respiratory system and exacerbate diseases such as asthma, bronchitis, COPD, respiratory infections, etc. (M et al., 2022). Inside the human respiratory tract (HRT), PM gets deposited in either head, tracheobronchial or pulmonary region of the lungs. In the present study, multiple path particle dosimetry model is used to assess the deposition of different fractions of PM in human airways.

METHODS

The sampling was carried out in two sites of Pune. Site-1 is a semi-industrial area in eastern part and site-2 is a traffic area in the central region. A portable real time monitoring device, Grimm Aerosol spectrometer 11-D was used to conduct sampling from December 2022 – February 2023. The Multiple-Path Particle Dosimetry (MPPD) model version 3.04 was used to analyse the data. The model calculates the deposition and clearance of aerosols considering the factors such as particle size, breathing patterns, lung geometry, and physiological parameters to estimate where particles are likely to deposit within the respiratory tract. Of the eight available models to simulate lung deposition, Yeh-Schum Symmetric model was considered for the present study. Deposition fraction was calculated using mass median aerodynamic diameter (MMAD). The model values were accepted as input parameters except for aerosol concentration.

The health risk assessment was done by calculating the average daily dose (ADD) in $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1} \text{day}^{-1}$ and hazard quotient (HQ), according to the following equations,

$$ADD = \frac{\text{Concentration} (\mu\text{g m}^{-3}) \times \text{Inhalation Rate} (15.3 \text{ m}^3 \text{ day}^{-1}) \times \text{Exposure Duration} (15 \text{ years})}{\text{Body Weight} (60 \text{ kg}) \times \text{Average Time} (15 \times 365 \text{ days})}$$

$$HQ = \frac{ADD \times \text{Body Weight} (60 \text{ kg})}{RFC (\text{inhalation reference concentration } \mu\text{g m}^{-3}) \times \text{Inhalation Rate} (15.3 \text{ m}^3 \text{ day}^{-1})}$$

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

PM CONCENTRATION

The average size segregated PM mass concentration in site-1 and site-2 were found to be $182.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and $83.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ for PM_{10} , $81.9 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and $54.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and $57 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and $46.4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ for PM_1 . The average particulate mass concentration at site-1 was found to be 4 (for PM_{10}) and 6 times (for $\text{PM}_{2.5}$) higher than WHO standards (PM_{10} - $45 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ - $15 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) and approximately 2 times higher than the NAAQ standards (PM_{10} - $100 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ - $60 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). Similarly, at site-2, the average mass concentration of PM was 2 (PM_{10}) and 4 ($\text{PM}_{2.5}$) times higher than WHO standards but was found to be under control according to the Indian NAAQ standards. In site-1 and site-2 the size segregated number count was found to be PM_1 (1143, 515) > $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ (443, 127) > PM_{10} (20, 5). It can be inferred that the PM number count is more in site-1 as compared to site-2. At both sites the number of fine and ultrafine particles surpassed the number of coarse particles.

DEPOSITED MASS RATES AND HEALTH RISK ASSESSMENT

Deposited mass rate (DMR) is the rate at which PM mass gets deposited in the different regions of the lungs viz. head, tracheobronchial and pulmonary. Table 1 shows the total and regional DMR at both sites. Higher PM concentration in site-1 correlates with the higher values of DMR there.

Table 1: Total and regional deposited mass rate (in $\mu\text{g min}^{-1}$) in both sites

PM	Site-1				Site-2			
	Total	H	TB	P	Total	H	TB	P
PM_1	0.124	0.058	0.022	0.043	0.1	0.046	0.018	0.035
$\text{PM}_{2.5}$	0.176	0.082	0.031	0.062	0.117	0.055	0.021	0.041
PM_{10}	0.397	0.185	0.071	0.14	0.181	0.084	0.032	0.063

The regional DMR per unit area for both sites are shown in fig. Results indicate that PM₁₀ has significant contribution as compared to PM₁ and PM_{2.5}. More deposition is seen in head region followed by tracheo bronchial and pulmonary region.

Fig. 1: Regional deposition mass rate per unit area at both sites.

Fig. 2: Clearance in the a) alveolar b) TB regions post exposure in both sites

The rate of removal of particles from HRT is the clearance. Fig. 2 depicts the rate of post exposure alveolar and TB clearance of PM mass. The tracheobronchial clearance of PM is greater as compared to alveolar clearance in both sites. Greater mass of PM is cleared in TB region initially owing to high concentration. Mucociliary activity influences clearance in the TB region. In the alveolar region clearance takes place via phagocytosis or by blood or lymphatic transport.

At site-1 the ADD values were 46.45 (PM₁₀), 20.88 (PM_{2.5}) and 14.55 (PM₁) while at site-2 it was 25.04 (PM₁₀), 13.81 (PM_{2.5}) and 11.84 (PM₁) in µg kg⁻¹ day⁻¹. The HQ values at site-1 were 3.64 (PM₁₀), 16.38 (PM_{2.5}) and at site-2 were 1.96 (PM₁₀), 10.83 (PM_{2.5}). Higher values of HQ for PM_{2.5} signifies higher risk from inhalation of fine particles. The HQ for PM₁ could not be calculated due to unavailability of RFC.

CONCLUSIONS

The concentration in both sites was above WHO prescribed limits but was under control at site-2 for NAAQ standards. The size segregated mass concentration followed the trend PM₁₀ > PM_{2.5} > PM₁ while number count was found as PM₁ > PM_{2.5} > PM₁₀. The results revealed that DMR was highest for PM₁₀ followed by finer counterparts and was maximum in H > P > TB. The DMR per unit area was H > TB > P. The PM mass clearance was slower in alveolar region than in tracheobronchial region. All the HQ values are >1, which infers significant health risk to the population at both sites.

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PARTICLE DEPOSITION IN A STRAIGHT HORIZONTAL TUBE

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Keywords: aerosol deposition, horizontal tube, CFD simulation, gravitational settling.

INTRODUCTION

The behaviour of fluid flow in a pipe is mainly governed by the effects of gravity and viscosity relative to the inertial forces of the flow. Particle deposition inside a pipe geometry is primarily controlled by three phenomena, namely, inertial impaction, gravitational settling, and diffusion. Particle deposition in a straight or bent pipe geometry may seem to have a simple configuration, but it possess a wide range of applications from a larger scale (for e.g., oil transport) to smaller ones (blood circulation in blood vessels or respiratory airflow). Several analytical formulae are available to predict particle deposition fraction [$=1 - (\text{droplet flux at outlet/droplet flux at inlet})$] in a tube geometry; however, they are based on either fully developed flow condition or other specific flow profiles. It becomes more challenging when the pipe geometry is very small and has bifurcations and inclination with respect to gravity which is very common in a respiratory airway system. While impaction is of primary concern in the large airways, gravitational settling (or sedimentation) is most important in the smaller airways and the alveolar region, where flow velocities are low and airway dimensions are small. Since, sedimentation has its maximum removal effect in horizontally oriented airways, in this study we have considered a small tube geometry where the simulated deposition fraction has been compared with available analytical formulae.

METHODS

We have considered a tracheal dimension (tube diameter $D = 0.018$ m, length $L = 0.125$ m, and mean inlet velocity $U_o = 1.166$ m/s). This cylinder is placed horizontally, and air is flowing inside it with velocity U_o from left to right face. The flow Reynolds number is 1380 which ensures a laminar flow inside it. Uniform velocity profile is applied at the inlet cross section whereas pressure-outlet boundary condition is implemented at the outlets. Non-slip boundary condition is employed along the airway walls. The compressible PISO (Pressure-Implicit with Splitting of Operators) algorithm has been adopted to solve the transient Navier-Stokes equations. The total time of simulation is chosen such that a steady state flow has been attained inside the tube. In this study, we have adopted a Eulerian, sectional, internally mixed aerosol model using Aerosolved (v 2.0) [1] open-source code to study aerosol deposition. Two sets of simulation have been carried out: with gravity and without gravity to investigate the particle deposition due to settling. In this case, a poly disperse aerosol (water droplet) is considered. Sectional model is used for resolving the droplet distribution, with a total of 20 sections representing droplet diameters (d_p) spanning from $\sim 8.7 - 48.87$ μm .

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The analytical expressions of deposition fraction for different types of fluid flow in a circular horizontal pipe are given in Table 1. The expressions are given in terms of $\kappa = \frac{3}{4} \frac{v_{\text{settling}}}{U_o} \frac{L}{D}$, where $v_{\text{settling}} = \frac{\rho_p g d_p^2 C_c}{18 \mu}$ [$\rho_p =$ particle density, $C_c =$ slip correction factor, $\mu =$ fluid viscosity, $g =$ gravitational acceleration]. The analytical expressions indicate that particle deposition fraction depends on the nature of flow in the pipe. These expressions have considered 3 different types of idealised flow pattern which may not be valid in real situations. For example, for the present pipe configuration, the fluid velocity profile is shown in Fig. 1. The profile is not parabolic which indicates that the flow is not an ideal Poiseuille flow.

Table 1. Analytical expressions of deposition fraction (P_s) for fluid flow in a circular horizontal pipe.

Type of Flow	Analytical expressions of deposition fraction (P_s)
Poiseuille fluid flow (Wang, 1975; Heyder and Gebhart (1977)) [2,3]	$P_s = \frac{2}{\pi} \left[2\kappa \sqrt{1-\kappa^{2/3}} - \kappa^{1/3} \sqrt{1-\kappa^{2/3}} + \arcsin(\kappa^{1/3}) \right]$
Plug flow (Heyder,1975)	$P_s = 1 - \frac{2}{\pi} \left[\arccos\left(\frac{4}{3}\kappa\right) - \frac{4}{3}\kappa \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{4}{3}\kappa\right)^2} \right]$
Well-mixed Plug flow (Morton, 1935; Fuchs 1964; Finlay, 2001) [4]	$P_s = 1 - \exp\left[\frac{-16}{3\pi}\kappa\right]$

Figure 1. Radial velocity profile at different locations along the length of the tube.

Figure 2. Variation of the fraction of aerosol depositing in a horizontal tube with respect to parameter κ .

It can be seen from Fig. 2 that particle deposition fraction depends on flow profile under consideration. The deviations in deposition fractions estimated using well-mixed plug flow model and the CFPD simulation lie between 2 - 4%. However, if we use Poiseuille flow model, then the deviations lie between 2 – 5.5%. In plug flow, the velocity of the fluid is assumed to be constant across any cross-section of the pipe perpendicular to the axis of the pipe which does not hold in this case. Apart from this, the fluid profile is not exactly a Poiseuille flow. This is due the fact that the condition for the fully developed Poiseuille flow is $\frac{x}{D} > 0.06 \mathfrak{R}$,

where Re is the Reynolds number. In this case, $\mathfrak{R} = 1380$, $D = 0.018$ m which results in an entrance length of $x = 1.5$ m. However, the length of the tube in this case is 0.125 m which is less than this entrance length and hence, fully developed flow has not been generated in this case.

CONCLUSIONS

In order to verify the effect of gravitation in deposition, the problem of particle deposition in a straight horizontal tube under the sole influence of gravity is simulated. We have compared the simulated deposition fraction of aerosols with the analytical models. It is seen that the deposition fraction depends on the fluid profile and the assumptions made in the analytical expressions may not hold good in all situations. The local deposition profile across the cross sections cannot be captured well enough by these analytical models since most of them assumed uniform concentration profile at a particular distance along the length of the pipe, while in reality, a deposition pattern exists.

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AEROSOL MODELLING

COMPARATIVE ESTIMATION OF BLACK AND ORGANIC CARBON IN THE PENINSULAR REGION UTILIZING SAFAR AND EDGAR EMISSION INVENTORIES

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Keywords: SAFAR, WRF-Chem, Black Carbon, Organic Carbon

INTRODUCTION

We address the elaborate interactions of carbonaceous fine particulate matter (C-PM) in the Peninsular region of India, where Black Carbon (BC) and Organic Carbon (OC) particles arise from incomplete combustion in diverse sectors such as transportation, power plants, and residential areas (Kumar et al., 2023). The health and climate impacts of C-PM are substantial, contributing to cardiovascular diseases, and lung cancer, and influencing warming and cooling effects. C-PM can remain in the atmosphere for up to a week (Bond et al., 2004; Beig et al., 2021). This investigation aims to evaluate C-PM simulations utilizing the WRF-Chem model for the entire year of 2018. Employing both the EDGAR-HTAP and high-resolution SAFAR 2018 emission inventories, we scrutinize the intricate interplay of C-PM and meteorological parameters. By assessing simulation performance against the MERRA reanalysis, we explore how BC and OC emissions influence near-surface mass concentrations, thereby advancing our comprehension of C-PM dynamics in this region.

METHODOLOGY AND DATA

This study aimed to simulate concentrations of BC₀ and OC in the Peninsular region of India region using the WRF-Chem V3.9.1.1 model. Simulations employed two emission inventories: EDGAR HTAP and a high-resolution SAFAR 2018 inventory. The study used two nested domains, covering Southeast Asia and the Indian region, with varying horizontal resolutions. The model included micro physics options, gas-phase chemical mechanisms (MOZART-4), aerosol models (GOCART) with aqueous-phase chemistry, and NCEP FNL data for meteorological conditions. EDGAR-HTAP, a widely-used gridded dataset, provided emissions estimates for pollutants, while SAFAR 2018 employed a high-resolution GIS-based approach. Observation data from MERRA reanalysis, offering spatiotemporal variation, were used for comparison.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

From MERRA, model simulation with two emission inventories, regional fluctuation of wind speed, PBL height, surface temperature, BC, and OC across the Peninsular region of India during winter, pre-monsoon, monsoon, and post-monsoon for the year 2018 is shown in Fig.1. Wind speed aligns directionally with MERRA, slight magnitude difference due to constraints. Monsoon exhibits higher wind speeds, winter lower due to stability. PBL height underestimates except for monsoon; pre-monsoon sees higher height favoring mixing. Monsoon witnesses lower PBL due to moisture, and cloud cover; winter shows higher PBL due to temperature variations, and local geography. Surface temperature correlates with MERRA, which is slightly underestimated (Sathyanadh et al., 2017). Pre-monsoon and monsoon seasons display higher temperatures due to intense solar radiation. Eastern Peninsular, Andhra Pradesh, experiences elevated temperatures; Bangalore has lower temperatures due to elevation and local winds.

Fig.1 (d1-d12) and (e1-e12) depict spatial BC and OC concentration distribution across winter, pre-monsoon, monsoon, and post-monsoon in the Peninsular region, contrasting MERRA and model (SAFAR and EDGAR). BC_{SF} and OC_{SF} (SAFAR) simulations demonstrate strong alignment with MERRA compared to BC_{ED} and OC_{ED} (EDGAR). Simulated C-PM concentrations with SAFAR show slight overestimation due to increased emissions from vehicles, residential sectors, and energy usage. EDGAR-simulated C-PM concentrations are underestimated. BC and OC concentrations are slightly higher in winter than post-monsoon and pre-monsoon, with lower concentrations in the monsoon. Winter C-PM concentrations in the Peninsular region are approximately four times higher than in monsoon. Monsoon season's lower C-PM concentrations result from atmospheric conditions such as cloud cover, wind speed, PBL height, moisture effect, washout effect, and lower emissions. While monsoons lead to improved air

quality, local emissions, industrial activities, and anthropogenic pollution sources still influence air quality. Bangalore, Chennai, and Kochi exhibit higher C-PM concentrations due to urbanization, industrialization, population density, and energy demand. BC and OC simulations with SAFAR better capture Peninsular stubble burning than EDGAR (Kumar et al., 2023).

Fig.1. Seasonal variation of C-PM and met-parameters from MERRA and model (SAFAR and EDGAR)

CONCLUSIONS

This study presents a comprehensive assessment of carbonaceous fine particulate matter (C-PM) concentrations across the Peninsular region of India, employing advanced modelling techniques and two distinct emission inventories: SAFAR and EDGAR, compared with MERRA for 2018. The analysis reveals that the model simulations align well with MERRA for key meteorological parameters such as wind speed, Planetary Boundary Layer (PBL) height, and surface temperature, providing valuable insights into their seasonal variations. PBL height simulations capture enhanced mixing during pre-monsoon and lower heights in monsoon, indicative of atmospheric moisture and stability. Simulated C-PM concentrations with SAFAR exhibit slight overestimation, primarily attributed to increased emissions from vehicular and residential sources, and intensified energy consumption, as captured by the high-resolution SAFAR emission inventory. Conversely, EDGAR-simulated concentrations are underestimated. Seasonal variations in C-PM concentrations reveal elevated levels during winter, attributed to various emissions and atmospheric conditions, while monsoons result in improved air quality due to factors like cloud cover, wind speed, and washout effects. Hence this study reveals that SAFAR's emission inventory better captures the dynamics of BC and OC concentrations, exhibiting the influence of local emissions, weather patterns, and regional characteristics, particularly during stubble burning. The findings hold significant implications for understanding air quality, climate impacts, and public health in the Peninsular region.

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**STUDY OF AEROSOL-BOUNDARY LAYER INTERACTIONS DURING THE WINTER
SEASON OVER THE INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN**

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Keywords: REGCM, AEROSOL OPTICAL DEPTH, AEROSOL RADIATIVE FORCING.

INTRODUCTION

The Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) is one of the most inhabited and severely polluted regions in the world. This region experiences a significant and varied aerosol load attributed to multiple emission sources, industrial activities, population growth, distinct topography, and regional meteorological factors (Nair et al., 2007; Bharali et al., 2019). IGP experiences severe fog conditions (high aerosol load & poor air quality) during winter season and the accumulation of aerosols in the boundary layer throughout the winter has a substantial impact on the health of about one billion people there. Further, these pollution episodes affect the day-to-day life, visibility and regional climate. There are several studies investigated the influence of various emission sources, such as agricultural residue burning and vehicular emission, on the prevalence of high aerosol load over IGP (Jethva et al., 2019; Kumar et al., 2020). On the other hand, several studies highlighted the role of meteorological conditions (low wind speed, shallow boundary layer, and high relative humidity) on favouring these high aerosol conditions over the IGP (Nair et al., 2020; Bharali et al., 2019). Aerosol forcing has a significant impact on the evolution of the boundary layer, which strengthens the accumulation of pollutants close to the surface (Bharali et al. 2019). The study by Nair et al. (2007) highlighted the strong relationship between the temporal evolution of aerosols and boundary layer height over the IGP. Thus, variations in the boundary layer impact aerosol loading, and conversely, aerosol forcing plays a role in boundary layer evolution, as evidenced by multiple studies (Bharali et al., 2019; Ding et al., 2016; Li et al., 2017; Tie et al., 2017).

Numerous studies have extensively documented the prevalence of aerosol loading across the Indian subcontinent and acknowledged the role of boundary layer processes in modulating diurnal aerosol fluctuations, but a notable research gap persists in examining the impact of aerosols on boundary layer properties over IGP. Hence, the focus of this study is to understand the effect of aerosols on boundary layer height, meteorology, thermodynamics, and air quality and to investigate potential feedback mechanisms underlying the interplay between aerosol and boundary layer processes during the winter season over IGP.

METHODS

The model adopted for the present study is the regional climate model (RegCM) version 4.6. A comprehensive discussion on RegCM4 and its various parameterization schemes can be found in literature (Giorgi et al., 1993; Giorgi et al., 2012). The model was configured over South Asia with a horizontal resolution of 30 km and comprising 18 sigma vertical levels for the period 2013-2018. Through a detailed sensitivity analysis, the most optimal parameterization schemes for the simulation is selected. Out of all the sensitivity experiments conducted, the combination of Tiedtke over land and Emmanuel over the ocean as cumulus convection schemes, along with the community land model (CLM4.5) as a land surface scheme and the University of Washington (UW) as the PBL scheme, emerges as the most appropriate configuration for the IGP during the winter season. This study investigates the implications of aerosol-boundary layer interactions through two RegCM simulations: one without aerosol feedback (AERONFB) and the other with aerosol feedback (AEROWFB).

The aerosol optical depth (AOD) simulated by RegCM for the winter season is compared with the AOD from MODIS, which is shown in Figure 1. The model is capable of reproducing broad features of the spatial pattern of AOD over IGP quite well. The AOD over northern parts of India was found to be higher than that in peninsular India. This is a characteristic feature of aerosol loading over the Indian region during the winter season. This may be due to the proximity of the region to sources of natural aerosols from the deserts and also due to higher growth rate of population, urbanisation and industrialisation.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The substantial aerosol loading over IGP results in significant solar dimming at the surface. The change in net solar radiation caused by aerosols is quantified as aerosol radiative forcing (ARF). The spatial distribution of the DJF composite of (2013-2018) ARF at the top of the atmosphere (TOA), surface (SUR), and atmosphere (ATM) is shown in Figure 2. The winter months ARF_{TOA} values are primarily negative (cooling) throughout the Indian subcontinent and the nearby ocean area, while being positive over the Himalayan highlands covered in snow. This shift in radiative forcing occurs due to the abrupt alteration in surface albedo. A significant cooling is seen over Northern India, with ARF_{TOA} values between ~ -10 and -20 Wm^{-2} . In Figure 2(b), ARF at the surface (ARF_{SUR}) is depicted for the Indian region, revealing a solar radiation reduction exceeding 15 Wm^{-2} across most of the area. Notably, substantial surface cooling ($< -25 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$) occurred over IGP during the winter season. The amount of radiation trapped in the atmosphere due to aerosol absorption (ARF_{ATM}) is estimated as the difference between the ARF_{TOA} and ARF_{SUR} as shown in Figure 2(c). The ARF_{TOA} are mostly greater than $+8 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ over most of the Indian region with values as high as $+20 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ over IGP during the winter season.

Aerosol-radiation interaction cools the lower or entire planetary boundary layer (PBL) and warms the upper PBL or atmosphere above it, which leads to stable stratification of the atmosphere. The decreased solar radiation at the ground reduces the sensible and latent heat fluxes, affects the growth and evolution of the convective boundary layer and induces important feedbacks. The lower PBL height and poor ventilation result in increased concentration of pollutants which favor the formation of wintertime fog/haze over IGP. The large amount of energy trapped by aerosols in the atmosphere leads to the diabatic heating and changes in the meteorological and thermodynamical variables. The dynamical feedbacks and regional climate implications of large scale surface dimming and atmospheric heating due to aerosols over the Indian region, especially over the IGP during the winter season will be investigated.

CONCLUSIONS

The important findings of the study are:

1. The aerosol induced cooling at TOA is mostly negative over Indian landmass and surrounding oceanic regions, whereas positive values are seen over the snow-covered regions of Himalayas. The sharp change in the surface albedo leads to this kind of change in radiative forcing.
2. The high surface cooling ($< -25 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$) was observed over IGP during the winter season. Due to low aerosol loading, surface forcing over the Himalayas are relatively smaller.
3. The ARF_{TOA} are mostly greater than $+8 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ over most of the Indian region with values as high as $+20 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ over IGP during the winter season.

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**MODELLING THE PRE-MONSOON AOD OVER INDIA: DUST AND ANTHROPOGENIC
RADIATIVE EFFECTS**

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Keywords: AEROSOL OPTICAL DEPTH, INDIA, AEROSOL RADIATIVE FORCING, AERONET

INTRODUCTION

Recent investigation of aerosols from global aerosol multi-models show that forward model simulations were unable to reproduce the ground-based station-observed aerosol optical depth (AOD) and their spatial distribution over the Indian subcontinent (Kumar et al., 2018). Estimation of aerosol-induced radiative effects and its impact on climate requires accurate analysis of aerosols optical properties. Assessment of aerosol optical properties is a complex process as they exhibit large variability in space and time due to their low atmospheric lifetime, wide variety in their size and chemical composition. In addition, transport of aerosols and seasonal variations cause a change in the optical characteristics of aerosol species due to the variation of the mass extinction coefficient with particle size. Ground-based and satellite observations can provide the aerosol properties with limitations of low spatial coverage and less frequency, respectively. Satellite-derived values are often assessed relative to ground-based observations. Therefore, chemical-transport models when evaluated against ground and satellite observations, can provide higher spatial and temporal scale information on pollutant emissions, air quality, aerosol radiative forcing, visibility, and global climate change.

METHODS

High-resolution aerosol transport simulations are carried out with a state-of-the-art Eulerian chemistry-transport model, CHIMERE (version 2017). The CHIMERE model in the present study is forced externally by Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF-V3.7) model as a meteorological driver in offline mode. Simulations are carried out over the Indian domain (6° N to 38° N and 68° E to 99.25° E) at a horizontal resolution of $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$. These simulations are performed at a temporal resolution of 1 h for the year of 2015 (January–December: 8760 hours), with a spin-up time of 31 days (December, 2014; 744 hours). The optical properties are estimated with OPTical properties SIMulation (OPTSIM) using the 3-dimensional aerosol mass concentration simulated in CHIMERE. In OPTSIM, the aerosol size distribution is interpolated to a finer resolution to ensure the best integration as possible where the aerosol concentration number is optically active. Aerosol optical properties are estimated based on mie theory, considering internal homogeneous mixing. The optical properties are estimated at six wavelengths (440, 500, 532, 550, 870, and 1064 nm) at the same horizontal and temporal resolution as of CHIMERE. Simulations of aerosol radiative transfer calculations are conducted in WRF-Solar as per the meteorological initial and boundary conditions provided to the WRF.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The spatial distribution of pre-monsoon mean AOD at 550 nm is compared with satellite (MISR) observations for the year 2015 (Figure 1). The spatial pattern of AOD showing high values in the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP, 0.45-0.55) is consistent with the features of observed AOD from satellite retrievals (0.4-0.55) with a slight over-estimation (30%) in the upper-IGP region. The IGP has a higher AOD than most parts of India attributed to high population density and greater emission sources (Verma et al., 2022). Large seasonal mean AOD values are also estimated over the Indian state of Telangana (0.5-0.6) which is over-estimated (25%-35%) as compared to MISR retrievals. The simulated AOD is also found to be in good agreement (NMB: 17% for 16 locations) with AOD from ground-based observations (AERONET and individual measurements) at stations over India.

The dust and anthropogenic contributions as estimated through the constrained simulations suggest highest contribution of dust AOD in the North-western region (0.3-0.4) followed by upper IGP (0.2-0.26). Simulated anthropogenic AOD is greater than dust AOD over the IGP region. The highest anthropogenic AOD is obtained over central and eastern IGP followed by the east coast of India.

Further, the pre-monsoon shortwave radiative perturbation due to total, dust and anthropogenic aerosols over the Indian region is evaluated at surface (SUR), atmosphere (ATM) and top of atmosphere (TOA). The positive value of the radiative effect signifies warming due to aerosols and vice versa for the negative value of the radiative effect. The radiative effect at TOA due to total aerosols is negative over the north-western region and positive for other parts of India. The net radiative effect of total aerosols at the SUR is cooling (-70 to -80 W m^{-2}) in contrast to warming ($+65$ to $+80 \text{ W m}^{-2}$) in the atmosphere. The magnitude of radiative perturbations caused by anthropogenic aerosols is higher compared to dust at SUR and ATM. Anthropogenic aerosols have a net warming effect at TOA ($+20$ to $+50 \text{ W m}^{-2}$) in contrast to a net cooling effect (-20 to -40 W m^{-2}) by dust aerosols. The most substantial values of radiative perturbations due to anthropogenic aerosols are observed over the IGP region while the effect of dust aerosols is prominent over the north-western region of India.

Figure 1. Spatial distribution of pre-monsoon mean AOD at 550 nm from constrained simulations (a), Multi-angle Imaging Spectro-Radiometer (MISR, b) and corresponding percentage bias (c)

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the tropospheric column AOD simulated by a high-resolution OPTSIM-CHIMERE was evaluated with satellite data (MISR) and ground-based measurements over India for the pre-monsoon months of 2015. The model captured the general features of spatial variation of AOD at 550 nm with higher values over IGP than most of India as also seen in the satellite observations. The simulated AOD is in good agreement with the satellite observations with slight over-estimation over upper-IGP and southern states of Telangana and Andhra Pradesh. A good association (NME: 22%) is also achieved between simulated AOD and ground-based measurements. Assessment of anthropogenic and dust AOD showed high influence of anthropogenic aerosols over the IGP region while that of dust over north-western region. Analysis of radiative perturbations due to aerosols showed atmospheric warming ($+65$ to $+80 \text{ W m}^{-2}$) and surface cooling (-70 to -80 W m^{-2}) over the Indian subcontinent.

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BENEFITS OF EMISSION ABATEMENT USING A NOVEL TECHNOLOGY FROM DIESEL GENERATOR SETS IN INDIA FOR CLEANER AIR

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Keywords: DG-set; emissions; PM_{2.5}; WRF-chem; health benefits

INTRODUCTION

Diesel generator sets are used as a standby source in domestic sector, hospitals, industrial and commercial sectors, the use of which is surging with increasing electricity demand in a country like India. DG set contributes to the emission of fine particulate matters (PM_{2.5}), carbon monoxide (CO), oxides of sulfur and nitrogen, and volatile organic carbon (VOC), causing poor ambient air condition. The National Clean Air Programme (NCAP) identified the DG set as one of major pollution sources in the non-attainment cities. The location of DG sets installed in restaurants, schools, institutes, hospitals are generally the densely populated areas of the city; which substantially increases its adverse impacts on human health (Guttikunda and Calori, 2013). Considering all the ill effects, the NCAP has promoted using retrofitted diesel generators having a minimum specified particulate matter capturing efficiency of atleast 70% or shifting the diesel generators from diesel based fuel to gas based generator. Here, we have examined the retrofit technology called Chakr Sheild (<https://chakr.in/particulate-matter-emission-control-device/>) which was proven to capture 80% of particulate matter emission from the exhaust of diesel engines without causing any damage to the generator. Hence the broad objectives of this study are: i) to estimate the reduction in particulate matter concentration after applying the retrofit technology ii) to quantify the health benefit corresponding to the improved air quality.

METHODS

Aerosol transport simulations are carried out in model WRF-chem (version 4), configured with online coupling between the state-of-art regional meteorological model WRF (Weather Research and Forecasting) and a regional chemistry-transport model. Emissions of BC, OC, NO_x, NH₃, SO₂ and other particulate matter (OPM) from “Speciated Multipollutant Generator” over India (SMoG) India emission inventory are implemented in the simulations, conducted for the year 2015 at a resolution of 50 km. Two simulations are conducted: (1) baseline for business as usual (BAU) scenario, and (2) CASE 1: considering 80% abatement in DG-set emissions after applying retrofit technology. A percentage change in the concentration of PM_{2.5} in CASE 1 is calculated with respect to that from baseline scenario. The information obtained from simulations are then applied to the high resolution (1 km x 1 km) gridded PM_{2.5} concentration data estimated by Dey et al., 2020, to estimate the final PM_{2.5} concentration. This is done to overcome the underestimation in simulated PM_{2.5} concentration in the chemical transport model and also the accuracy of the PM_{2.5} concentration for each scenario shall increase.

Physical Processes	Parameterization schemes
Cloud microphysics	Lin scheme
Short wave radiation	Goddard Shortwave scheme
Long wave radiation	Rapid Radiative Transfer Model (RRTM)
Surface physics	Unified NOAH Land Surface Model
Boundary layer	Mellor-Yamada- Janjić TKE scheme
Cumulus	Grell-Devenyi ensemble scheme
Chemical Processes	Schemes
Gas-phase chemistry	CBMZ chemical mechanism
aerosol chemistry	MOSAIC using 4 sectional aerosol bins including some aqueous reactions
Photolysis	Madronich photolysis scheme

Table 1: List of physics and chemistry schemes in WRF-CHEM used in the study

To calculate the health burden and DALYs, the methodology is as follows: For all the states and all-genders, age-distributed baseline mortality rates has been obtained for six non-communicable diseases (NCDs: Ischemic Heart Disease, stroke, and type-2 Diabetes Mellitus (adults, >25 years), Chronic Obstructive pulmonary Disease (all ages), Lower Respiratory Infection and Preterm-Birth (child, upto 5

years)) from the GBD-India portal. From the census projected report (2011-2036), the age-distributed population sizes (upto 5, 25-49, 50-69, 70+, and all ages) for the year 2015 has been interpolated. The population-weighted mean exposures are obtained from WRF-Chem simulations for the districts and states for the above mentioned two scenarios. The population attributable fraction (PAF) for the NCDs has been estimated using the MR-BRT (meta-regression, Bayesian, Regularized, trimmed) exposure-risk functions. With this function, the attributable risks (Relative Risk, RR) for the NCD outcomes for different exposure levels can be estimated which can be done by incorporating the globally published meta-analyses on ambient and household air pollution, and second-hand smoking. In this study, the premature mortality has been estimated using the following GBD assessment framework (Murray et al., 2015, 2020).

$$PAF = (1 - \frac{1}{RRR}) \quad (1)$$

$$Mortality = PAF \times Baseline-mortality\ rate \times Age-distributed\ population \quad (2)$$

Here, ‘RR’ is the relative risks at various exposure levels, ‘PAF’ is the population attributable fraction, and ‘mortality’ is the attributable health burden.

The health benefit in terms of reduced mortality attributable to DG-set exposure has been estimated by taking the difference of health burden estimates (i) from Baseline and Case 1 exposure.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

From the figure, it can be seen that applying the retrofit technology in the DGsets, there can be a reduction of around 5-20% in the concentration of PM_{2.5} with respect to that of in the baseline scenario, with 34% reduction in NCT of Delhi. Figure B & C provides the percentage reduction in rural and urban areas due to the retrofit technology. Most of the states have been benefitted by reduction of population exposure between 10-20 %. 5-10% reduction in urban population exposure is observed over Uttar Pradesh, Bihar which are among the polluted states of the country. The premature mortality and DALYs for the baseline scenario was 1.17 million (UI: 0.9-1.44) and 33.57 million (27.52-39.6), respectively which has been observed to reduce significantly for CASE 1 scenario. It has been found that 95278 (80986-109570) excess deaths and 1.56 million (1.31-1.81) DALYs could be prevented due to 80% reduction in DG-Set emissions in the country.

Figure 1: Spatial distribution of percentage reduction in A) PM_{2.5} concentration in CASE 1 with respect to Baseline scenario B) exposure of PM_{2.5} for CASE 1 in respect to baseline or BAU scenario for the urban areas (B) exposure of PM_{2.5} for CASE 1 in respect to baseline or BAU scenario for rural areas

CONCLUSIONS

A reduction 2-15% in the fine particulate matter concentration is observed due to retrofitted DG-set, in comparison to that of the baseline scenario leading to ~10% reduction in premature mortality and ~ 4.6% reduction in DALYs. The retrofit technology can be one of the effective measure towards creating better air quality and reducing health burden. Its proper implementation is the need of the hour in taking a step towards sustainable future.

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**SPATIAL AND TEMPORAL DISTRIBUTION OF ORGANIC CARBON AEROSOL OVER
INDIAN SUBCONTINENT: MODEL VALIDATION AND EVALUATION**

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Keywords: ORGANIC CARBON, WRF-CHIMERE, SEASONAL VARIABILITY

INTRODUCTION

Organic carbon (OC) aerosols are complex carbon-containing particles in the atmosphere that significantly affect air quality, atmospheric chemistry, and climate forcing. These small, bright-coloured carbon aerosols emitted directly or formed in situ from less volatile hydrocarbon byproducts (Seinfeld, 2016) play a role in scattering light, leading to negative climate impact. OC aerosols not only have direct effects but also interact with clouds, initiating the first indirect effect. Recent studies revealed that a fraction of the organic matter called 'brown carbon' is capable of absorbing solar radiation but not to the same extent as black carbon (BC). Growing anthropogenic activities like fossil fuel emissions, biomass burning, land use changes, and industrial development have contributed to a sharp rise in the amount of OC in the atmosphere. Therefore, understanding the proper chemistry of organic carbon (OC) is crucial for accurately assessing its role in climate forcing. While ground-based measurements offer valuable data, they struggle to accurately represent the complex spatial distribution of OC aerosols across diverse regions. Comprehensive modeling is crucial for studying their varied impacts on climate, including radiative forcing, cloud properties, air quality, and health. However, precise modeling of aerosol properties remains challenging due to factors like particle size, chemical composition, and mixing complexity. The Indian region lacks a precise assessment of OC-induced radiative effects on a seasonal basis, demanding a thorough evaluation of OC aerosol distribution and seasonality using enhanced emission data.

METHODS

In the present study, hourly OC transport simulations are carried out with a state-of-the-art Eulerian chemical transport model (CTM), CHIMERE (version 2014b). The CHIMERE model uses Weather Research Forecasting (WRF-V3.7) externally imposed pre-estimated meteorology. Simulations include the Indian domain (6°N to 38°N and 68°E to 99.25° E) using a horizontal grid resolution of 0.25°×0.25°. Using observation-constrained emissions, two sets of hourly OC transport simulations are run for 2015 (January–December: 8760 hours) with a spin-up duration of 31 days (December 2014: 744 hours)(Ghosh & Verma, 2023). Regional chemical transport model CHIMERE uses MELCHIOR2 for gaseous chemistry. Fields of chemical concentration are calculated with a time-step of a few minutes (using an adaptive time-step sensitive to the mean wind speed). The horizontal transport is solved with the VanLeer scheme, and vertical using an upwind scheme with mass conservation. Initial and boundary conditions are determined by monthly climatologies of the global chemical transport model Laboratoire de Meteorologie Dynamique General Circulation Model coupled with Interaction with Chemistry and Aerosols(LMDz-INCA). The domain grid has 20 vertical levels in σ -pressure coordinates, spanning from the surface (997 hPa) to 200 hPa. The WRF regional meteorological model offers hourly fields with a 0.25°×0.25° horizontal grid resolution. Modern numerical weather forecast model WRF techniques are presented in Ghosh et al., 2021. The 2015 WRF simulation utilizes 1° x 1° spatial resolution from GFS National Centre for Environmental Prediction operational global analysis data for initial and boundary meteorological conditions.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

In the current study, seasons are divided into six to understand the seasonal fluctuations in OC aerosols across India: (i) November to December, winter (Win); (ii) January to February, winter monsoon (Wmon); (iii) March, transition to summer (Tsumm); (iv) April to May, summer (Summ); (v) June to September, southwest monsoon season (SWmon); and (vi) October, transition to winter (Twin).

Figure 1 (a) Spatial distribution of simulated seasonal mean of OC averaged during winter (b) comparison of modelled and measured seasonal mean of organic carbon across stations over India (colours represent stations and shapes depict locations)

High OC concentration was observed during Win, Wmon and transition months. In winter, low temperatures, gentle winds, and calm conditions trap pollutants, limiting dispersion causing an increase in OC concentration. The OC concentration is typically higher, especially over the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) region ($>45\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$), followed by that over central India ($10\text{--}35\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). In IGP, agricultural and biomass burning contributed significantly to high OC concentrations. Southern India's lower OC concentration compared to other regions is due to its southern peninsula location and proximity to marine surroundings. The onset of the southwest monsoon introduces cleaner air masses from distant oceans, contributing to this pattern. During the summer months, higher wind speeds, improved mixing, and reduced calm wind conditions disperse pollutants, resulting in lower OC concentrations, further aided by decreased agricultural burning. The arrival of widespread rainfall during SWmon effectively washes out atmospheric pollutants, resulting in the lowest OC concentrations observed throughout the year. However, even during the SWmon, the IGP retains relatively higher OC concentrations due to its geographical features and continued emissions.

Ground-based monthly organic carbon (OC) concentration data from various stations representing distinct geographical locations: megacity (Delhi and Kolkata), urban (Hyderabad, Kanpur, Varanasi, Pune), and semi-urban (Kharagpur) were utilized to validate the model-simulated OC concentrations (Figure 1(b)). The model effectively replicated the seasonal variations in OC concentration for Delhi across all seasons with a bias of less than 35%. With the exception of Tsumm, bias was less than 35% in Varanasi and Kolkata. The model performed well at Kharagpur during the Win and SWmon seasons, maintaining a modest 3% bias. Similarly, the model demonstrated effective performance at Kanpur station, exhibiting biases below 25% for most seasons. Across all stations and different seasons, a consistent trend was observed wherein the model consistently underestimated concentrations during the SWmon period. A similar pattern was observed for the Summ season, except for Delhi, where concentrations were not underestimated.

CONCLUSIONS

The study revealed that organic carbon aerosol exhibits both seasonal and spatial distribution patterns across the Indian subcontinent. Elevated OC concentrations were identified during the Win, Wmon, and transition months. The Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) emerges as a hotspot for elevated OC levels due to agricultural and biomass burning. The model validation using ground-based data from diverse locations highlights its capability to reproduce observed variations accurately, notably in Delhi for all seasons and in Varanasi and Kolkata except Tsumm with a bias of less than 35%.

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**ESTIMATION OF AEROSOL SPECIES IMPACT OVER THE HIMALAYAN HINDU KUSH
REGION - VALIDATION AND IMPLICATIONS ON SNOW-MELT RUNOFF FROM
GLACIERS: PRESENTING THE HYPSONETRIC GLACIER ENERGY MASS BALANCE
MODEL**

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Keywords: Aerosol modelling, Aerosols over Himalaya, Aerosol impact on Himalayan Glaciers

INTRODUCTION

Snow-melt water from glaciers located over the Himalayan Hindu Kush (HKH) region is the source of major rivers of India. In recent years, these glaciers have been retreating at an alarming pace, making populous regions of northern India vulnerable to water shortages. Along with warming, which is above the global average over the HKH region (Qiu, 2008), the region is also facing a significant amount of particulate pollution. These aerosols when deposited over the pristine snow surface of HKH glaciers, alter the albedo of upper mixing layer of snow, leading to higher absorption of solar radiation and accelerated melting of snow (Santra et al., 2019). However, remote regions and unfavorable weather conditions hinder measurement studies. Moreover, estimation of the cumulative and relative impact of all aerosol species over the region is still overdue. Thus, in this study, a hybrid model combining an adequate estimation of aerosol species over the region; a snow, ice, aerosol radiation model; and a novel hypsometric glacier energy mass balance model (HGEMBM) developed in our laboratory are used to carry out a quantitative and comparative analysis of the cumulative and relative impact of aerosol species including black carbon (BC), organic carbon (OC), Sulphate and other water-soluble (Sul-OWS) and Dust aerosols.

METHODS

Atmospheric concentration of aerosol species (OC, Sul-OWS, Dust) was estimated from the free-running aerosol simulations (*freesimu*) with a general circulation model and also from constrained simulation (*constrsimu*) approaches. Estimated aerosol optical parameters like aerosol optical depth (AOD₅₅₀) and single scattering albedo (SSA₅₅₀), and species-wise aerosol atmospheric concentrations were validated using available observational data over the region. A snow, ice, aerosol radiative spectral albedo simulation (SNICAR) has been used to estimate the snow albedo reduction as a percentage of pure snow (% SAR) corresponding to aerosol species-wise concentrations in snow. Simulation and sensitivity analysis of aerosol species induced SAR to increase in annual glacier runoff (AGR) is carried out over the identified glaciers using the developed novel hypsometric glacier energy mass balance model (HGEMBM). The model integrates glacier hypsometry data, albedo calculations based on surface conditions, and meteorological inputs like temperature, humidity, radiation, wind speed, and precipitation. The model uses both energy balance and mass balance models as required for estimating the snow-melt runoff, combining the energy balance model, which includes along with other energy transfers, heat conduction into the glacier, and the mass balance model, which incorporates accumulation and melting of ice and snow along with refreezing of water in the snow layer in a vertical dimension. The model involves solving complex integral and partial differential equations to calculate the variation of temperature, density, and surface albedo of snow and ice layers with respect to time and depth. Development of this HGEMBM enables the computation of surface temperature, melt-water generation, and the corresponding snow-melt runoff from the Himalayan glaciers, offering an understanding of aerosol-albedo interactions and their impact on the HKH glacier system.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Among the *freesimu*, GCM-indemiss (with India emission) exhibits better conformity with measured AOD₅₅₀ and SSA₅₅₀ over stations with an acceptable normalized mean bias (NMB). For atmospheric concentration of aerosol species, GCM-indemiss simulated values compare considerably well with the measurements of OC and Sul-OWS aerosols over the high altitude (HA) stations. However, over the low altitude (LA) stations simulations using *constrsimu* approaches, mostly profile approach (PA) performs relatively better. A hot-spot location of higher OC, Sul-OWS, and Dust concentration is identified near Manora peak. Seasonal analysis of aerosol species concentrations over the region reveals winter-time values to be lower than pre-monsoon ones. Although OC, Sul-OWS, and Dust concentration in snow are found to be 2 to 5 times higher than BC, SAR due to these species are estimated to be much lower than due to BC. Cumulative SAR due to all aerosols is estimated to be as high as 7% to 8%, over Gangotri and

Chorabari glaciers. HGEMBM could simulate the available observed snow-melt runoff from a glacier with adequate accuracy along with the vertical profile of snow and ice temperature based on the provided slope and hypsometry. Simulation of annual runoff increase (ARI) due to aerosol-induced reduction in snow albedo using the HGEMBM indicates HKH glaciers to be 2 to 3 times more sensitive to SAR than Tibetan glaciers. Five out of nine glaciers are estimated to have ARI of more than 300 mm w.e. y^{-1} due to total aerosol-induced SAR (Pindari, Sankalpa, Gangotri, and Chorabari being the most affected ones). Pindari glacier, being more sensitive to SAR, was found to have the highest annual runoff increase (ARI), despite having a lower SAR. BC aerosols, despite having less than 15% contribution to total aerosol loading over the region, contribute more than 50% to the total ARI over all the glaciers (Figure: 1).

Figure 1. Percentage contribution of BC, OC, Sul-OWS, and Dust aerosols towards the total ARI due to aerosols along with observed average yearly recession ($m y^{-1}$)

CONCLUSIONS

Spatial distribution of AOD, SSA, and aerosol species (i.e. OC, Sul-OWS, and Dust) atmospheric surface concentrations are adequately estimated over the Himalayan Hindu Kush region. HGEMBM could adequately simulate the snow-melt runoff, as well as the vertical profile of glacier parameters like snow and ice temperatures. The sensitivity of Himalayan glaciers to SAR due to the deposition of aerosols is estimated. Pindari glacier, being more sensitive to SAR, has the highest ARI, despite a lower SAR. Five out of nine glaciers have ARI higher than $300 mm w.e. y^{-1}$. BC aerosols contribute less than 15% to the total aerosol loading but contribute more than 50% to the total aerosol-induced ARI, followed by dust, Sul-OWS, and OC respectively. This signifies the importance of a required reduction in BC aerosols over the region to effectively mitigate the impact of aerosols.

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WRF-CHEM SIMULATION OF BLACK CARBON CONCENTRATION OVER INDIAN REGION

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Keywords: Black carbon, WRF-CHEM, Indo-Gangetic Plain

INTRODUCTION

Black carbon (BC) emissions have significant implications for air quality, human health, and climate. BC particles, produced from burning fossil fuels and biomass, not only worsen air pollution but also contribute to global warming by absorbing sunlight (Bond et al., 2013). It's important to understand BC's distribution, sources, and effects in order to manage air quality and addressing climate change. But in India, where BC emissions are a major concern due to various sources like vehicles, industries, and biomass burning, uncertainties exist due to limited studies and incomplete emission data make it challenging to accurately estimate BC levels across the region.

The Weather Research and Forecasting model with Chemistry (WRF-CHEM) is a tool that combines weather and chemistry, simulate BC concentrations across India at high spatial resolutions can help bridge the gap left by sparse observational data and incomplete emission inventories. In this work, we used WRF-CHEM to get insight into the temporal and spatial variability of BC concentrations by incorporating various emission sources, local atmospheric conditions, and intricate transport pathways.

METHODS

Employing the WRF-CHEM, we simulated BC concentrations across India at a high 0.25x0.25-degree resolution over a year. We executed three simulations: (1) Constrained (Verma et al., 2017), (2) EDGAR-HTAPV3 (https://edgar.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dataset_htap_v3), and (3) Smog-India (Sadavarte and Venkataraman, 2014), integrating observationally constrained, global bottom-up, and local bottom-up BC emissions, respectively.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Constrained simulation yielded low normalized mean bias (NMB) (<20%) and root mean square error (RMSE), indicating efficient BC pollution capture over the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP). This signifies improved accuracy via observationally constrained emissions over the IGP compared to bottom-up emissions. However, model performance was limited in regions with dry conditions, significant local BC emissions high altitude regions. This limitation suggests unaccounted BC sources beyond the IGP in the constrained emission inventory.

Simulated BC concentration sensitivity primarily resided in emission strength changes over the IGP region, shedding insight into the complex interactions between emission inventories, regional sources, and atmospheric transport that influence the distribution of BC.

The diurnal variation of modelled BC replicated key trends with early morning maxima and afternoon minima in major cities with dominant local emissions, like Delhi, Kolkata, etc., but failed to capture subtle diurnal fluctuations.

CONCLUSIONS

Our findings underscore BC emission characterization, source sensitivity, and diurnal patterns. Furthermore, the study highlights the necessity of refining emission inventories and addressing atmospheric transport dynamics. These insights offer a valuable framework for enhancing WRF-CHEM's accuracy in simulating BC concentrations across India, encompassing temporal variations and source complexities.

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**MODELLING OF HAZE EVENT OVER DELHI REGION: IDENTIFICATION,
CHARACTERIZATION AND MODEL EVALUATION**

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Keywords: Haze Identification, Air Quality, Meteorology, WRF-CHIMERE, Model Evaluation.

INTRODUCTION

Haze episodes, characterized by high fine particle concentration and low visibility, are often observed over the Northern Indo-Gangetic Plain, including Delhi-NCR, during post-monsoon and winter seasons. These episodes pose a huge negative burden on human health, the environment and economic aspects. [Lalchandani et al., 2022]. The combined influence of local emissions, meteorology, regional transport, and topography results in the complex formation mechanism of haze [Fu and Chen., 2017], making it difficult to predict based on only observational studies. Therefore, it necessitates modelling the episodic haze in a chemistry-transport model, which can provide information on the inter-relationship between meteorology, chemistry, transport and local emissions, aiding in developing required control measures. The present study uses the CHIMERE chemistry-transport model to replicate the identified haze event over the Delhi-NCR region. The questions addressed through our study include: 1.) How does Air Quality and Meteorology vary during the identified haze and non-haze period? and 2.) What is the performance of the model in representing the meteorology, air quality and PM_{2.5} chemical components, mainly Organic Aerosols (OA), Black Carbon (BC), Sulphate (SO₄²⁻), Nitrate (NO₃⁻) and Ammonium (NH₄⁺)?

METHODS

Temporal trends analysis is performed at RK Puram air quality monitoring station within the Delhi-NCR Region for ten days (i.e., from 8th Nov to 18th Nov 2019). For this, the whole study period is categorized into three sub-periods: 1. pre-haze (8th - 11th Nov 2019); 2. haze (12th - 15th Nov 2019); and 3. post-haze (16th - 18th Nov 2019) based on PM_{2.5}, RH and visibility conditions. The required measured daily mean mass concentration data of Particulate Matter (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀), trace gases (carbon monoxide (CO), ozone (O₃), sulphur dioxide (SO₂), and nitrogen-dioxide (NO₂)) and meteorological parameters (Temperature (T), Relative humidity (RH) and wind speed (WS)) are obtained from Central Pollution Control Board [<https://airquality.cpcb.gov.in/>]. Observed daily air visibility data is obtained from the National Centers for Environmental Information USA [<https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/>]. CHIMERE is an Eulerian chemistry-transport model (CTM) [Menut et al., 2013], which requires meteorology and primary pollutant emissions as external input to calculate and provide atmospheric pollutant concentrations based on well evaluated and state-of-the-art parameterisations and Modular framework that includes aerosol processes of formation, dispersion, and deposition (dry and wet), gas phase chemical mechanisms and aerosol chemistry schemes. Details about the chemical mechanisms used for aerosols and gaseous species available in CHIMERE are described in Menut et al., 2013. In the present study, CHIMERE (version: 2014b) externally forced by Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF-V3.7) model as a meteorological driver is applied. Model simulations are performed by keeping a spin-up time of 15 days. The initial and boundary meteorological conditions for WRF simulations are obtained from the Global Forecast System (GFS) National Center for Environmental Prediction - FINAL operational global analysis data. Simulations of air quality in CHIMERE are carried out over the Indian subcontinent at a temporal resolution of 1h, horizontal grid resolution of 25 km × 25 km and 20 vertical levels in sigma-pressure coordinates ranging from the surface (997 hPa) to 300 hPa. The anthropogenic emissions implemented in the modelling setup are from the observation-constrained emissions recently estimated using integrated modelling approaches by Verma et al., 2017 and Ghosh et al., 2023 and global bottom-up emission inventory of Emission Database for Global Atmospheric Research-V4 [http://edgar.jrc.ec.europa.eu/htap_V2/index.php]. More details regarding the WRF-CHIMERE modelling setup over the Indian Region are available in Verma et al., 2017.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Based on the compiled measurement analysis over the Delhi-NCR region, when conditions like daily PM_{2.5} greater than 60µg/m³, visibility less than 1km and RH within 60% to 70% existed continuously for more than

two consecutive days is identified as a Haze Event. $PM_{2.5}$ gradually accumulated, and its mean concentration was around $357.2 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ during the haze, approximately thrice in the pre-haze condition. Further, the ratio of $PM_{2.5}$ to PM_{10} is around 0.68, indicating that 68% of the particles are fine fraction during haze. Similarly, all other pollutants, including RH, had a good synchronicity with $PM_{2.5}$ and had an increasing trend compared to the pre-haze period. Concentrations of NO_2 , $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} were much higher than National Ambient Air Quality Standards, indicating severe air pollution during haze episodes, which is unsuitable for the residents of Delhi. Besides visibility, WS and T decreased with the increase in $PM_{2.5}$, indicating calm and stable conditions during the haze period compared to pre-haze. Model predictions also showed similar conditions during the haze period. The statistical metric Pearson's coefficient of correlation (R), which indicates the strength of the correlation between modelled and observed variables, is calculated to evaluate the model's performance. Table 1 shows the modelled daily mean mass concentration and (R) of the entire study period (8th-18th Nov 2019). From Table 1, it can be observed that the R-value is in the range of 0.75 to 0.99 for all the analyzed species except for RH and T. This shows that the WRF-CHIMERE model can capture the trends of the pre-haze, haze and post-haze period. Further, we compared the modelled chemical components data with the observation data of Lalchandani et al., 2022, through which we validated only during haze and post-haze period. Although the model underestimated the mass concentrations, it captured the rate of increase of the chemical components nearly similar to that of the observed data. From this, through modelling, we found that the rate of increase of SO_4^{2-} - NO_3^- - NH_4^+ was higher than OA during the haze event compared to pre-haze, inferring the significant role of inorganic aerosols during hazy conditions.

Table 4. Model Performance Statistics during the entire study period

	$PM_{2.5}$	OA	NO_3^-	SO_4^{2-}	NH_4^+	BC	NO_2	CO (mg/m^3)	SO_2	RH (%)	WS (m/s)	T ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
Model ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	92.0	41.2	8.3	3.9	4.0	13.9	83.4	0.13	80.0	29.7	1.7	25.6
R	0.86	0.75	0.94	0.96	0.97	0.73	0.99	0.77	0.86	0.52	0.94	0.66

CONCLUSIONS

WRF-CHIMERE model is able to reproduce the temporal variation trends of $PM_{2.5}$ and its components, with R value above 0.70. Based on modelled chemical component data it was found the rate of increase of SO_4^{2-} - NO_3^- - NH_4^+ together was higher than OA during the haze event compared to pre-haze, inferring significant role of inorganic aerosols.

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IDENTIFYING AEROSOL SOURCES FROM LOW-COST PARTICLE SENSORS IN MUMBAI

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Keywords: Low-cost sensors, source identification, particulate matter, non-negative matrix factorization

INTRODUCTION

Low-cost sensors (LCS) have the potential to provide accurate and reliable measurements of air quality in real-time. This improves our ability to monitor, identify sources of pollution and develop mitigation strategies for effective air quality management. However, recent research on LCS has largely focused on monitoring, exposure assessment and calibration aspects. In this study, we investigate the applicability of LCS data collected at ambient sites for characterizing and apportioning aerosol sources.

METHODS

The data was collected with Alphasense optical particle counter (OPC) N2 during a field sampling conducted for 15 days, 12 h a day from May 16 – May 30, 2022, at five different sites inside the Indian Institute of Technology Bombay (IITB) campus. The sites selected for the sampling were the construction site (S1), aromas (S2), hostel hub (S3), central library (S4), and main gate (S5). Non-negative matrix factorization (NMF) (Lee and Seung, 2001) is applied to the data collected using OPC to characterize and identify the aerosol sources. Given a non-negative matrix V ($m \times n$), NMF finds two non-negative matrices W ($m \times k$) and H ($k \times n$) with the constraint that all three matrices have no negative elements. Here, W is the feature matrix representative of the characteristics of the factor while H is the coefficient matrix representative of the contributions/intensity of the factor.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

NMF was applied to decompose the OPC data into two, three, four and five factors solutions for each site. A careful evaluation of correlation coefficients amongst various factors, coupled with a knowledge of the sources present at the sites, led to the consideration of two factors solution for the sites S2, S3 and S4 and three factors solution for the sites S1 and S5. Factor 1 of the sites exhibits strong similarity with each other and is present during the entire sampling period for each site with high loadings of PM_{10} , representative of the dust source, including wind-blown soil dust, construction dust and resuspended road dust (Parthasarathy et al., 2016; Police et al., 2018). This factor is the most dominating source across all the sites as dust is the major source of atmospheric aerosols and the principal contributor of coarse particles in Mumbai during summer, as reported in the literature. Factor 2 of the sites exhibit strong similarity with each other and is dominated by the particles of bin 0, bin 1, $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} , representative of traffic and mixed sources such as vehicles, industries, marine etc. This factor is a mixture of other aerosol sources in Mumbai, as reported in the literature. The NMF resolved the third factor for only two sites 1 and 5. The factor profiles at both sites show strong similarity (0.8). Factor 3 is dominated by bin 0, bin 1, bin 2, bin 3 and bin 4 (PNC $\geq 1.7 \mu m$) and has high PM_1 and $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations than PM_{10} , indicative of heavy-duty diesel vehicles (HDDV), which have high loadings of fine particles ($\geq 1.8 \mu m$ aerodynamic diameter; $PM_{1.8}$) (Robert et al., 2007). This is the advantage of using high-resolution data, as episodic activities can also be captured which could have merged with other sources when using daily data. The approach identifies the transient traffic and other sources, pointing towards real-time source apportionment capability.

Figure 1. Contribution of aerosol sources at different sites of IIT Bombay

CONCLUSIONS

The results obtained in this study show that the triangulation of the sources characterized by a network of LCS can help identify the region's major sources. The availability of high-resolution data is advantageous as the episodic activities can also be captured which might be suppressed otherwise. Another aspect of this approach is the application of particle count, which represents the physical characteristics of the source contrary to the chemical characteristics as in the traditional source apportionment techniques. This study provides evidence that despite their inherent limitations, the network of LCS can be useful in attaining interpretable information about pollution sources and recommends extensive use of LCS for source characterization in the future.

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**QUANTIFYING THE IMPACT OF CROP RESIDUE BURNING ON AMBIENT PM_{2.5} MASS
CONCENTRATION OVER THE INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN USING THE WRF-CHEM MODEL**
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The Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) is valuable in terms of soil fertility and population, but it also has the poorest air quality in India. During October-November, intensive in situ crop residue burning (CRB) is overserved in the northern region of India, resulting in severe air pollution over IGP. In this study, first attempted to understand the dominant area, period of burning, and hotspot districts in Punjab and Haryana from 2012 to 2019. We then used weather research and forecasting coupled with a chemistry model (WRF-Chem) to simulate meteorology and air pollution with modified anthropogenic emission and hybrid chemistry. Finally, we quantified the role of total CRB and hotspot districts in daily air quality over IGP using several sensitivity tests run with WRF-Chem. The Western Pakistan, Punjab, Haryana, Uttar Pradesh (UP), and Madhya Pradesh are the dominant regions, and burning activity occurred primarily between 10 October and 20 November, with hotspot districts accounting for 80 and 50% of total state fire count in Haryana and Punjab, respectively, from 2012 to 2019. Temperature was simulated excellently over all sites with NMB less than 0.02 and $r > 0.75$, but wind speed was slightly overestimated, except in Punjab, Rajasthan, and West Bengal (WB), and PM_{2.5} was excellently capture almost all heterogeneity and replicate ground reality with NMB less than 0.2 and $r > 0.65$ over most validation sites, except few sites in Delhi, Punjab, Haryana and WB. The National Capital Region has the highest PM_{2.5} loading, followed by Punjab, Haryana, UP, Bihar, and WB. The CRB contributed PM_{2.5} loading from total CRB and hotspot districts are 5-27 and 5-16%, respectively. The hotspot districts contributed up to 70% of total CRB loaded PM_{2.5} in Western, Central, and Eastern cities, and about 50% in Northern cities (Amritsar, Patiala, Delhi, and Faridabad). The top ten districts in terms of human health benefit from the elimination of total CRB are seven from Uttar Pradesh, two from Punjab, and one from Delhi. This study suggests that scientists, researchers, and policymakers focus first on hotspot districts to address this issue. Furthermore, in order to create and implement policies, a thorough understanding of the sociodemographic and economic status of hotspot districts is required.

Keywords; WRF-Chem, Crop residue burning, hotspot districts, and health benefits.

AEROSOL OPTICAL DEPTH VS PM_{2.5}: ADAPTATION OF HYBRID OPTIMIZATION ALGORITHMS FOR TEMPORAL PREDICTION.

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Keywords: Hybrid algorithms, ANN, BAT, Optimization, Machine Learning, PM_{2.5}.

INTRODUCTION

Particulate matter, an atmospheric aerosol, can impact Earth's climate system by either directly or indirectly altering incoming solar energy and outgoing longwave radiation (Huang et al., 2014). The absorption and scattering of short- and long-wave radiation by aerosols is often referred to as a direct effect of aerosols on radiation, as are aerosol-induced changes in cloud macro- and microphysical properties that contribute to cloud condensation. The indirect consequences are cores or ice cores (Liu et al., 2012; Zhao and Garrett, 2015). Harmful radiation from aerosols is relatively strong in East Asia due to increasing pollutant emissions. (Liu et al., 2012). Aerosol can also influence precipitation amounts and patterns by affecting the microphysical properties of the cloud. A worldwide chemical transport model (CTM) was used to determine the universal PM_{2.5} concentration spread from the AOD derived from Satellite (Van Donkelaar et al., 2010). The 2012-13 atmospheric Aerosol Research China network campaign determined the correlation between AOD and PM_{2.5} (Xin et al., 2016). There are substantial differences in the relationship between PM_{2.5} and AOD for various locations (Guo et al., 2009; Ma et al., 2014). In the sequence of numerous studies meteorological studies along with the types of aerosols may influence the association between AOD and PM (Ma et al., 2014).

Existing studies have relied on MODIS for data consideration and understanding the association existing between AOD and PM_{2.5}. This is the first study where Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite (VIIRS) satellite data is used for PM_{2.5} prediction and to determine the relationship that exists between AOD and PM_{2.5}. The results were incorporated to check the reliability of Machine learning algorithms such as Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Support Vector Machine (SVM) along with hybrid algorithm ANN-BAT for the location Chennai precisely to Manali. The aim of the study was to predict daily PM_{2.5} levels using AOD data where there are few ground monitoring stations. The study conducted covered the period 2016 to 2020 for the Manali, Chennai location with a total of 1509 daily records. The study was inspired by a hybrid algorithm, so the study helped to diverge the results of machine learning algorithm, namely artificial neural network, and a hybrid algorithm, namely artificial neural network – BAT algorithm.

METHODS

The entire study was conducted on 1509 data sets. Data collected for AOD was from VIIRS, NASA and PM_{2.5} was collected from CPCB. Due to the enormous data length, we found that better results were achieved in 98% and 99% of training and in 2% and 1% of testing. The 98% of the data is 1478 data for training and 31 data for testing, which is 2%. Likewise, it turned out that 99% of the data, which contained 1493 data and 16 data for testing, was 1%. The study included two machine learning algorithms, namely Artificial Neural Network (ANN) and Support Vector Machine (SVM), including polykernel function, normalized polykernel function, Puk and RBF function and a hybrid algorithm ANN-BAT.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The results of ANN-BAT are given in the figures 1 and 2 which describes the training and testing phases. The performance of the models was verified using performance indicator namely Relative Mean Square Error (RMSE). The correlation coefficient (R²) of PM_{2.5} and AOD is 0.58. Statistical analysis shows that the mean and standard deviation of AOD and PM_{2.5} are 55.53 ±42.11 and 2.89 ±1.45, respectively, along with their skewness of 3.477 and 0.289, respectively, followed by a kurtosis of AOD and PM_{2.5} at 328.97 and 17.06, respectively. The results showed that 98% and 99% of training and 2% and 1% of ANN tests had better results with RMSE of 21.09 µg/m³, 22.05 µg/m³ during training and 17.95 µg/m³ and 12.54 µg/m³ provided for testing. For SVM, out of four functions, the normalized polykernel function was found to be better with an RMSE of 21.79 µg/m³ in training and 19.7 µg/m³

Figure 1 and 2 shows the AOD and PM_{2.5} for 98% and 99% of training and 2% and 1% of testing for ANN-BAT for 20 iterations respectively.

in testing for 98% of training and 2% of tests. Simultaneous SVM normalized polykernel with 99% training and 1% testing RMSE of 21.86 µg/m³ is achieved during training and 13.19 µg/m³ during testing. Similarly, the results from ANN-BAT shows that 98% and 99% of training and 2% and 1% of testing with better RMSE of 14.09 µg/m³, 11.36 µg/m³ and during testing it obtained an RMSE of 10.15 µg/m³ and 7.43 µg/m³.

The results show that ANN performs better than SVM even though several features of SVM were tried. The RMSE values of ANN are found to be lower than that of SVM for both training and test sets at 98%, 99% and 2%, 1%. The R2 value of SVM for 99% training and 1% testing was found to be higher than that of ANN and ANN-BAT. This means that in the 15 days of prediction, the SVM model performs better than the ANN according to (Muruganandam et al., 2023) with an R2 of 0.8 for training and 0.9 for testing. The ANN BAT has better RMSE and R2 value compared to ANN in both 98%, 99% of training and 2.1% of testing. This helps us understand that hybrid algorithms give better results. The ANN-BAT produced better results for four hidden layers along with 10 bats after 20 iterations for both 98%, 99% of training and 2%, 1% of testing. Table 1 shows the RMSE results of SVM during training and testing.

Training and testing percentages	Functions of SVM	Training RMSE (µg/m ³)	Testing RMSE (µg/m ³)
Training – 98%, Testing- 2%	Normalised Polykernel	21.79	19.78
	Polykernel	21.81	19.88
	PUK	22.27	21.07
	RBF	21.80	19.84
Training- 99% Testing- 1%	Normalised Polykernel	21.86	13.19
	Polykernel	21.88	13.51
	PUK	22.38	13.62
	RBF	21.86	13.475

Table 1 contains the RMSE values of training and testing for SVM for four different functions at two different percentages.

CONCLUSIONS

- The prediction efficiency shows that from hybrid algorithm and machine learning algorithm, the hybrid algorithm performed better.
- The best fit was obtained for 20 iterations of ANN-BAT for 98% ,99% of training and 2%, 1% of testing.
- Overall, the BAT along with ANN performed better than other models in pattern recognition.

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PM_{2.5} SURFACE CONCENTRATION DERIVATION FROM MODIS AOD: A CASE STUDY OVER KOLKATA (INDIA)

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Keywords: Particulate Matter, AOD, Regression Model, Air Quality.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past decade, air pollution has become a matter of paramount concern, particularly in major urban centres worldwide. It poses a significant threat not only to public well-being and human health but also to the global climate system. Its detrimental effects range from disrupting the hydrological cycle to elevating global temperatures, resulting in a wide array of negative consequences (Satheesh and Ramanathan 2000). Extensive research is currently underway to explore various methods for deriving Particulate Matter (PM_{2.5}) levels in regions lacking adequate monitoring infrastructure, with one such approach being the utilization of Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) from satellite remote sensing technology. This technology has gained considerable traction in recent years for monitoring PM_{2.5} levels from space (Jia and Liu, 2006). This study is centred on deriving PM_{2.5} concentrations at the city-scale in Kolkata. The primary objective of this research is to quantify short-term changes in PM_{2.5} concentrations over Kolkata, which stands as one of the largest urban agglomerations in the North Eastern region of India.

METHODS

The present research attempt to assess the levels of PM_{2.5} over Kolkata for a three-year period spanning from 2019 to 2021. The data is obtained from the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) AOD product. The PM_{2.5} concentration data were collected from seven Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) ground stations situated across Kolkata. Additionally, this study made use of the 1-kilometer MODIS AOD product and meteorological data from Modern-Era Retrospective analysis for Research and Applications, Version 2 (MERRA-2). To derive PM_{2.5} levels, four regression models were developed based on a statistical analysis of the data.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The effectiveness of the developed models in simulating PM_{2.5} concentrations over Kolkata (at the city-level) were assessed by comparing the derived PM_{2.5} values with ground observations from seven monitoring stations. Model 1, which employed Simple Linear Regression, demonstrated a moderate yet statistically significant correlation between the measured and derived PM_{2.5} values ($R = 0.748$, $RMSE = 37.37 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, and $MAE = -14.26$). Combining meteorological factors in Model 2 equations led to an improvement in PM_{2.5} results compared to Model 1. The PM_{2.5} simulations from the Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) model in Model 2 displayed a positive correlation with the on-ground measurements ($R = 0.814$, $RMSE = 22.54 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, and $MAE = 12.30$). Unfortunately, neither Model 3 nor Model 4 yielded satisfactory results, and as a result, they were not used for further analysis or estimation.

Figure 1 illustrates the daily PM_{2.5} concentration profile throughout the observation period, comparing observed data to values generated by Model 2. The model effectively replicates the overall pattern of PM_{2.5} concentrations, including both peaks and dips. Nevertheless, there is a consistent tendency for the model to underestimate concentration values, highlighting the potential for enhancing the model equation designed for estimating city-scale PM_{2.5} levels.

Figure 1. Comparison Graph of PM_{2.5} estimates from Model 2 and Ground-based Observed PM_{2.5} concentrations.

CONCLUSIONS

The results demonstrated that the developed models thus can be used to study the particulate matter concentration over areas where ground-based observation sites are sparse on the city level.

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A RETRIEVAL TECHNIQUE TO PREDICT THE 3-DIMENSIONAL STRUCTURE FROM A MICROSCOPIC IMAGE OF QUASI-FRACTAL AGGREGATES

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Keywords: FRACTAL AGGREGATES, RETRIEVAL METHOD, JAYA.

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution, detrimental to health indoors and outdoors, necessitates informed policies based on extensive research. Recent research emphasises the importance of particulate matter (PM), which is found in aggregated form via particle coagulation. Understanding the properties of these aggregates is critical for understanding their behaviour and growth patterns. These aggregates, in particular, can be explained using quasi-fractal geometry, with a fractal scaling law by establishing a link between the number of monomers (N) and length scale, including the radius of gyration (R_g) and monomer radius (a) as,

$$N = k_f \left(\frac{R_g}{a} \right)^{D_f} \quad (1)$$

where 'k_f' is the fractal prefactor and 'D_f' is the fractal dimension, with values typically ranging from 0.6 to 4.0 and 1 to 3, respectively. The scaling law is employed in computational aggregate generation, allowing for the investigation of their physicochemical characteristics. Due to micro to nano size scale, electron microscopy is often used for imaging aggregate samples, these images are then used for 3D aggregate generation. Previous 3D structure retrieval approaches had limitations, such as only extracting monomer numbers or fractal dimensions or relying on an existing database of fractal parameters in addition to 2D morphological properties (Thajudeen et al., 2015). In order to improve this, a real-time retrieval method predicting 3D structures from microscopic images is proposed. It fuses optimization with tunable forward modelling, now including JAYA, extending on previous work using particle swarm optimization and FracVAL (Singh & Thajudeen, 2023).

METHODS

The proposed model uses JAYA and FracVAL simultaneously to predict the 3D structure from projections of computationally synthesised aggregates. These projections are used to derive six distinct morphological properties: projected area, perimeter, maximum end-to-end projected length, maximum width perpendicular to the maximum length, 2D radius of gyration, and 2D fractal dimension. These 2D properties are further employed for comparative analysis against properties obtained from the projections of generated aggregates using fractal parameters acquired from the population based on the optimization method. JAYA is used in this context to develop a population with fractal parameters (N, k_f, D_f) as coordinate values. Meanwhile, FracVAL is used to generate aggregates based on the fractal parameters of the population. A fitness value 'f' is computed by comparing the input properties to the obtained projection properties. This fitness value is based on the six mentioned 2D properties and provides a measure of the extent to which the created aggregates fit the intended properties, defined as,

$$f = \left[\frac{A_{proj,T} - A_{proj}}{A_{proj,T}} \right]^2 + \left[\frac{L_{max,T} - L_{max}}{L_{max,T}} \right]^2 + \left[\frac{P_T - P}{P_T} \right]^2 + \left[\frac{R_{g2D,T} - R_{g2D}}{R_{g2D,T}} \right]^2 + \left[\frac{W_{max,T} - W_{max}}{W_{max,T}} \right]^2 + \left[\frac{D_{f2D,T} - D_{f2D}}{D_{f2D,T}} \right]^2 \quad (2)$$

where all the properties with 'T' subscript are true or input values. This fitness value provides the population's best and worst fractal parameter values and thus helps in converging the population to the optimal solution. The final retrieved structure will be the 3D aggregate linked with the most similar projection with the lowest fitness value.

The resultant 3D structure was subsequently compared with the initially synthesized 3D aggregate, which was utilized to generate the input image (projection). This comparison was based on five 3D properties: mobility radius, 3D radius of gyration, hydrodynamic radius, orientationally averaged projected area, and anisotropy.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The suggested approach was tested with aggregates containing monomers ranging from 25 to 500 in both point-contact and monodispersed settings, as the study focuses on aerosols, the observed sizes of

aggregates in nature often fall within the specified range such as soot. The larger size of aggregates can be the result of restructuring; also, larger aggregates are prone to break into smaller ones. Moreover, the scaling law is preferably used to generate aggregates with monomers exceeding 25. The ‘ k_f ’ values varied between 0.7 and 1.6, while the fractal dimension ‘ D_f ’ was evaluated between 1.3 and 2.4. Notably, the approach has successfully retrieved structures with an error margin of 10–12%. Table 1 presents the results of the predictions, including relevant fitness values. Figure 1 illustrates two prediction cases where the blue image is the input projection, while the yellow image is the projection that best matches the intended criteria. The retrieved structure for the provided input image is the 3D equivalent of this same projection in yellow.

Table 1. Comparison between the fractal parameters of synthesized aggregate used for the input image and retrieved 3D aggregate

Case No.	Input			Output			Fitness value
	N	D_f	k_f	N	D_f	k_f	
1	50	1.3	1.4	54	1.51	1.61	0.000786
2	50	1.8	1.3	48	1.81	1.53	0.000466
3	50	2	1.1	45	1.98	1.16	0.000546
4	100	1.3	1.4	98	1.23	1.59	0.000674
5	100	1.6	1.6	100	1.63	1.5	0.000594

Figure 1. Comparison of predicted aggregates with Optimal Projections (yellow) and input image (Blue) with Fractal parameters of test cases 2 and 4 (N , D_f , k_f)

CONCLUSIONS

The proposed method highlights its ability to predict the 3D structure of quasi-fractal aggregates from an input image, with an acceptable error rate of up to 12%. The technique predicts structures with a wide range of fractal parameters: N values up to 500, k_f values ranging from 0.7 to 1.6, and D_f values ranging from 1.3 to 2.4. However, with larger D_f values, some limits exist due to monomer overlap, future research will be concentrated on addressing this issue. This methodology is a flexible framework that has been tested using two different optimisation strategies. Users have the option of modifying the procedure to produce even more accurate results. Furthermore, by introducing new configurable forward models, the prediction capabilities of this system could be investigated further.

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**CARBONACEOUS AEROSOLS AND PM_{2.5} ABUNDANCES OVER INDIA AND
CONTRIBUTIONS OF AGRICULTURAL
RESIDUE BURNING**

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Keywords: Aerosols And Air Quality, Aerosol Modelling, Carbonaceous Aerosols, Agricultural Residue Burning

INTRODUCTION

Carbonaceous aerosols impact the climate due to the absorption of radiation by black carbon (BC) and relatively unexplored brown carbon (BrC). Exposure to PM_{2.5} levels above the WHO limit (10 µg/m³) and NAAQs (40 µg/m³) affects human health (Ravishankara et al., 2020, Chatterjee et al., 2023). Emissions from intense burning of agricultural residues have drawn attention due to their impact on ambient aerosol levels (Kulkarni et al. 2020). Kapoor et al., (2023) estimated the detailed agricultural residue availability and the amount of burning for India. The objectives of the study are to (1) find the abundance of carbonaceous aerosol, (2) characterize the temporal period and spatial areas impacted by agricultural emissions, and (3) determine the contribution of agricultural emissions to modeled carbonaceous aerosols and PM_{2.5}.

METHODS

We have used WRF-Chem v 3.9.1 (Grell et al., 2005) with WRFDA (for meteorological data assimilation) to simulate meteorology and chemistry for the year 2019 (at hourly scale) over South Asia CORDEX domain (12°S to 40°N and 39° to 121°E) at 27 Km horizontal resolution with 48 vertical levels upto 50 hPa. Initial 1 month of model run (Dec 2018) was considered as spin up time for model. ERA-interim, and MOZART4 data were used as meteorological and chemical boundary conditions. For physical and chemical parameterisation we followed WRF-Chem modelling set-up used in our previous work (Sharma et al., 2023). Carbonaceous aerosol and PM_{2.5} were evaluated using observation data from COALESCE (CarbOnaceous AerosoL Emissions, Source apportionment and ClimatE impacts) project (Venkataraman et al., 2020) supplemented with measurement studies reported in literature. We made a sensitivity simulation, turning off emissions from agricultural residue burning, to evaluate the contribution of this source to PM_{2.5} and carbonaceous aerosol abundance.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

A clear north-south gradient was observed in model-simulated carbonaceous aerosol (1.7–2 and 2–3 times for BC and OC) and PM_{2.5}. Model underestimated BC (annual observed concentration = 5.6 ± 4.8 µg/m³, annual modelled concentration = 3.1 ± 2.8 µg/m³, NMB = -0.4) throughout the year against measurements taken at 11 locations over India under COALESCE project (Rabha et al., 2023, Maheshwarkar et al., 2022). BC levels were high near industrial areas. There was prominent seasonality in BC and OC concentrations (3–4 times minima to maxima) due to meteorology and emission both. Agricultural emissions were significant in north India, not only during the post-monsoon but also during the winter (DJF), and pre-monsoon (MAM) seasons. Season-wise and region-wise mean modeled PM_{2.5} concentrations (and contributions) from agricultural residue burning range : 33 µg/m³ (30%) during Oct–Nov in Northern IGP, 3–4 µg/m³ (7–10%) during DJF/MAM in Central and Peninsular India, and 1–2 µg/m³ (5–10%) during DJF/MAM in North-east India.

Figure 1. Contribution (percentage and absolute concentration) of agricultural emissions to simulated PM_{2.5} over India. Regions selected for analysis are shown as red boxes.

CONCLUSIONS

High levels of PM_{2.5} and carbonaceous aerosols were simulated and observed during the winter and post-monsoon seasons. The model underestimated black carbon, but predicted PM_{2.5} and OC well. Agricultural residue burning emissions significantly impacted air quality over central and peninsular India during MAM, and DJF seasons. High pollution levels in north-west India during the ON season were well captured. Agricultural emissions contributed significantly during high pollution episodes over selected cities in north and south India.

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SURFACE OZONE SIMULATION USING AUTOMATED MACHINE LEARNING

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Keywords: ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE, AIR QUALITY, AIR POLLUTION.

INTRODUCTION

Ozone, a critical component of our atmosphere, plays a dual role in environmental dynamics. While the stratospheric ozone layer protects the Earth from harmful ultraviolet radiation, ground-level ozone is a major air pollutant that can harm human health and the environment (Zhan et al., 2018). The swift progression in machine learning (ML) techniques, paired with enhanced computational capabilities, has unlocked vast potential for their application in diverse areas, including air quality (Stadtler et al., 2022). However, utilizing ML demands exact computational expertise for optimal outcomes. To simplify this challenge, our study employs an Automated Machine Learning approach to simulate the variation in surface ozone (O₃), a secondary pollutant, over tropical urban environment of Ahmedabad, India.

METHODS

Automated machine learning (AutoML) has emerged to streamline the application of ML to real-world challenges. AutoML automates the processes of algorithm selection, hyper-parameter tuning, iterative refinements, and model evaluation, which simplifies its deployment by eliminating the need for manual hyper-parameter adjustments (Hutter et al., 2018). In this study we have deployed an AutoML from the open-source platform, H2O.ai, incorporated with time series data of primary ozone precursors (NO₂, NO, CO, and C₅H₈) sourced from the CAMS (Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service) reanalysis, along with various meteorological parameters from ERA5 (the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecast's fifth-generation reanalysis) as inputs. Initially, we partitioned the entire time series of data (with the target variable being ozone, along with input variables) into two segments: the training-validation data (70%, spanning 2003–2016) and the testing data (30%, covering 2017–2021). From the training-validation dataset, 70% was randomly chosen to train the model, while the remainder (termed as the validation set) was employed to assess the model's performance. Subsequently, the 30% data from 2017-2021, labelled as the testing data, was utilized to verify that the model wasn't overfitting, ensuring its generalizability and reliability on new, unseen data.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The AutoML algorithm was trained on the training-validation dataset with a cap of 100 models. We provided a few basic inputs to the model: max_models=100, indicating the upper limit of models, and seed=5 to ensure the reproducibility of results. Throughout the AutoML procedure, six distinct machine learning models were evaluated: Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM), Generalized Linear Model (GLM), Distributed Random Forest (DRF), XGBoost, Deep Learning model, and Extremely Randomized Trees (XRT). The cumulative combinations of these models with varying hyperparameters resulted in the total count of 100 models. Among this lineup, the Deep Learning model stood out by achieving the best accuracy, R²=0.85, RMSE=1.9 ppbv, and MAE=1.1. Subsequently, the model underwent sensitivity analyses. The findings from the sensitivity simulations indicated that the model's performance remained commendable (R² = 0.77, RMSE = 2.74, MAE = 2.2) when solely relying on precursor data. In contrast, the model's efficacy decreased when only meteorological data was incorporated into the training.

Figure I: Time series representation of surface ozone in the study area

Figure II: (a) Deep learning model performance from the AutoML, (b) Model performance with Ozone precursors in input, (c) Model performance with meteorological parameters in input

CONCLUSIONS

ONS

Leveraging the long-term chemical datasets from CAMS reanalysis combined with meteorological factors, automated machine learning has been employed to simulate surface ozone in an urban environment. Automated machine learning identifies the optimal algorithm with fine-tuned hyperparameters for modeling urban ozone. The deep learning algorithm accurately simulated daily surface ozone, with a mere 7% (2 ppbv) error, capturing the majority of the variability (accounting for 85% of the total variability).

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EVALUATION OF PM₁₀ AND PM_{2.5} MODEL DATA THROUGH CAMS BIAS CORRECTION
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Keywords: AIR QUALITY, JHARKHAND, CAMS, BIAS-CORRECTION.

INTRODUCTION

In urban and industrialized regions worldwide, air quality is a significant concern due to factors like industrialization, urbanization, and vehicular emissions (Dockery et al., 1993; Kan et al., 2012). Dhanbad, a major city in Jharkhand, India, is known for its historically poor air quality attributed to industrial and mining activities (Gurjar et al., 2008; Jena et al., 2019), with severe implications for residents' health and well-being (Sharma et al., 2020).

METHODS

In our methodological approach, we undertook a twofold data collection process to comprehensively assess pre-monsoon air quality in Dhanbad. Firstly, we gathered observational data, specifically measuring PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentrations during the pre-monsoon season (March-May) 2022, utilizing an air sampler (PARTISOL 2000i) strategically located at the Central Institute of Mining and Fuel Research (CIMFR) campus in Barwa Road, Dhanbad. Secondly, we accessed CAMS data for the same period, which offered a broader spectrum of atmospheric variables. Recognizing an initial correlation, $R^2=0.59$, $RMSE=28.83 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, $MAE=24.25 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for PM₁₀ and $R^2=0.69$, $RMSE=19.02 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, $MAE=15.31 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for PM_{2.5}. Between these datasets, we meticulously applied bias correction techniques to enhance the precision and reliability of the CAMS data. We employed a linear regression model as the bias correction method. Subsequently, we seamlessly integrated the bias-corrected CAMS data with the observational dataset to establish a robust foundation for our air quality analysis.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

We observed that initially, there was a significant disparity between pre-monsoon observational data (March-May) and CAMS data for PM₁₀ (Fig: I), however, through careful bias correction, we have substantially improved their correlation, enhanced data accuracy, and bolstered the reliability of our air quality analysis. Nonetheless, PM_{2.5} did not necessitate bias correction, as it exhibited a strong correlation even prior to adjustment. (Post-correction value for PM_{2.5}: $R^2=0.56$, $RMSE=27 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, $MAE=23 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$).

Figure I. PM₁₀, CAMS and CAMS bias-corrected data

Figure II. PM_{2.5} CAMS and CAMS bias-corrected data

Fig: III Regression plot of PM₁₀ observation and corrected data

CONCLUSIONS

The correction has reduced the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) value, which indicates closer alignment between model predictions and actual observations. Bias correction shows good agreement with PM₁₀ data and hence enhanced PM₁₀ model data accuracy for improved air quality assessment. Also, this correction method is not needed in the case of PM_{2.5}.

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A LANDSCAPE ASSESSMENT WITH THE RECOMMENDATION OF BENCHMARKS FOR THE STATISTICAL EVALUATION OF CHEMICAL TRANSPORT MODEL STUDIES IN INDIA

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Keywords: Model performance evaluation, Chemical transport model, Performance benchmark.

INTRODUCTION

The National Clean Air Program (NCAP) of India involves the establishment and strengthening of air quality monitoring networks in target cities. Real-time data collection and analysis are crucial for effective pollution control. Ambient measurements of air pollutant concentration offer only a snapshot of the atmosphere in a specific location and time. They often pose challenges in interpretation without a conceptual understanding of atmospheric dynamics. The Chemical Transport Model (CTM) is a state-of-the-art scientific model used to simulate atmospheric chemistry and physical conditions. The CTM encompasses descriptions of emission patterns, meteorology, chemical transformations, and removal processes (Seinfeld et al., 2006). Despite its necessity, NCAP does not provide any guidelines related to the use and performance evaluation of CTM.

The current study represents the first-ever attempt to provide a statistical assessment of various CTM studies conducted in different regions of India, with the ultimate goal of utilizing the data published in various peer-reviewed journals between 2008 and 2023 to recommend India-specific performance benchmarks for PM_{2.5} and Ozone. Additionally, the study will also recommend a set of performance evaluation metrics that should be consistently used for the performance evaluation of CTM. The recommendations we propose aim to enhance the accuracy and reliability of CTM studies in India and, consequently, support the development of effective air quality management strategies.

METHODS

We compiled a total of 81 peer-reviewed research papers published between 2008 and 2023. This compilation was the result of a systematic literature search using prominent databases such as Google Scholar, Web of Science, and Scopus. Also, we have only considered those papers, which have reported at least one criteria pollutant concentration along with operational performance evaluation of model with respect to measured data. Further we extracted the reported model performance evaluation metrics values from these studies. To identify performance ranges, rank-ordered distributions were used, specifically focusing on the 33rd and 67th percentiles value to divide the overall distribution into three categories: studies falling within the top 33rd percentile successfully achieve goal comparable to the best-performing models, studies falling between the top 33rd and 67th quantiles meet criteria that the majority of modelling studies attain, and studies falling beyond the 67th quantile indicate relatively poor performance for the specific metric. Here we used the concept of benchmark to evaluate the CTM performance, developed by Boylan & Russell, (2006). Specifically, they defined the concept of “goal” refer to the desired level of accuracy that represents the highest achievable outcome for a model simulation in a specific application and “criteria” are the benchmark used to determine the acceptable level of accuracy for standard modelling applications. We derive the goal and criteria benchmark of normalized mean bias (NMB) and coefficient of correlation (R) for the PM_{2.5} and Ozone.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Among the 81-research paper included in this study, a total of 74 data points of normalized mean bias (NMB) and 82 data points for correlation coefficient (R) were extracted for the total PM_{2.5} concentration and used for the calculation of performance benchmark. A rank order distribution (Fig:1) of these datasets was done and picking the 33rd and 67th percentile values to separate the whole data set into three performance ranges. The top 33rd percentile value of NMB and R are 17%, and 0.67 respectively, which represents the goal benchmark, whereas the top 67th percentile value of NMB and R are 39%, and 0.49

respectively, which represents the criteria benchmark values. For the tropospheric ozone concentrations 38 data point for NMB and 42 data point for R were extracted and used for the calculation of performance benchmark. The value of the top 33rd percentile value i.e., goal benchmark for the NMB and R are 14% and 0.89 respectively. And the value of the 67th percentile i.e., criteria benchmark for the NMB and R are 43% and 0.72 respectively. These goal and criteria benchmarks values can be used to gauge the performance any future CTM studies. Based on our calculations, if the NMB (%) value for PM_{2.5} ranges from 17% to 39%, we can infer that the model has achieved the criteria benchmark and performed satisfactorily. If the value is less than 17%, it means the model has performed well, while a value greater than 39% indicates poor model performance. Here, we would like to clarify that these benchmarks are not intended for pass-fail testing of any CTM simulation. Instead, they provide a sense of CTM performance relative to the historical performance of similar CTM uses.

Fig: 1 A rank order distribution of NMB value for PM_{2.5}(left) and ozone(right) along with the goal and criteria benchmark

CONCLUSIONS

While conducting modelling studies for regulatory purposes, it is crucial to provide context by comparing the model's performance with measurement values. The recommended performance benchmarks will help to gauge the future CTM performances. This research contributes to the ongoing improvement and adaptation of CTM in response to evolving scientific knowledge, enhanced emission inventories, and advancements in computational capabilities.

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NUCLEAR CONTAINMENT AEROSOL BEHAVIOUR STUDIES USING SHAPE FACTORS
 OBTAINED FROM STOKESIAN DYNAMICS APPROACH FOR FRACTAL AGGREGATES

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Keywords: aerosol, fractal aggregate, shape factor, Nuclear Safety, NAUA code.

INTRODUCTION

Nuclear safety codes such as NAUA (mod 5) describing the behaviour of aerosols released into reactor containment in the unlikely event of a severe accident, employ empirical shape factors to invoke the effect of non-sphericity of particles on their mobility and collisional dynamics. Under relatively dry accident scenarios the coagulating nuclear aerosol particles are more likely to be fractal aggregates in which case the shape factor would have dominant effect on their settling dynamics, thereby crucially influencing the survival times of airborne radioactivity in the containment. The present work aims to determine dynamic shape factors from a Stokesian Dynamics approach and apply the results to estimate aerosol survival times in a containment using nuclear aerosol codes under different conditions of aerosol fractality.

METHODS

A fractal aggregate is generated using numerical algorithms, which consist of large number of monomers (monomers are spherical in nature). The scaling law for these fractals is given by Eq. 1; $N = k_f (R_g/a)^{d_f}$

$$(1)$$

where, k_f is a pre-factor, R_g is radius of gyration, d_f is aggregate fractal dimension, a is monomer radius, and N is the number of monomers in an aggregate. The volume equivalent radius (R_v) of the aggregate is can be expressed as, $R_v = N^{1/3} a$. In the Stokesian dynamic approach, the mobility radius (R_m) and the hydrodynamic ratio ($\beta = R_m/R_g$) of the fractal aggregate is obtained by summing all types and all orders of individual hydrodynamic interactions experienced by the monomers making up the aggregate. The dynamic shape factor (χ) is defined as ratio of the drag force on non-spherical particle (F_D) to the drag force on a sphere of equivalent volume moving at the same velocity (F_{Dv}). In the continuum regime, we can say, $\chi = R_m/R_v$. Substituting the values of R_v in terms of β , d_f , N , we can express χ as (Eq. 2):

$$\chi = (\beta^{d_f}/k_f)^{1/3} (R_m/a)^{1-d_f/3} \quad (2)$$

From the values of R_m and β obtained from Stokesian Dynamics simulations for various fractals types, χ were estimated for aggregates of different d_f . The χ values were then clubbed into three broad categories upon classifying aggregates as sparse ($d_f = 1.76$), medium $d_f = 2.5$ dense $d_f = 3$ to represent the likelihood of dry, moderately humid and highly humid atmospheric conditions. Upon incorporating the three shape factors, simulations were conducted using the accident analysis codes NAUA to investigate temporal behaviour of aerosols under certain postulated accidental release conditions.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The data from hydrodynamics simulations (Amalaruban et al., 2022) used to estimate the dynamic shape factor corresponding to different values of d_f is tabulated in Table 1.

Fractal dimension (d_f)	Pre-factor (k_f)	Hydrodynamic ratio (β)
1.76 ± 0.003	1.016 ± 0.016	0.80
2.49 ± 0.001	1.002 ± 0.001	1.18
3.0 ± 0.001	1.125 ± 0.000	1.29

Table 1. Pre-factors and hydrodynamic ratio corresponding to different fractal dimensions

Typical variation of the dynamic shape factor corresponding to $d_f = 1.76$ is plotted in Fig. 1a. The size dependent shape factors are introduced in the accident analysis code NAUA. The input parameters used in the NAUA code are summarized in Table 2. The temporal evolution of mass concentration corresponding to the given inputs is plotted in Fig. 1b.

Input parameter	Value	Input parameter	Value
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Count mean geometric radius	0.33 μm	Release duration	60 min
Geometric standard deviation	1.73	Containment volume	$5.45 \times 10^4 \text{ m}^3$
Aerosol Release rate	4.36 g/s	Total surface area	$1.06 \times 10^4 \text{ m}^2$
		Leak rate	0.3% h^{-1}

Table 2. Input parameters used in the accident analysis code NAUA to study effect of shape factor

Fig. 1a. Shape factor as a function of mobility radius

Fig. 1b. Evolution of air-borne mass concentration

From Fig. 1a, it is observed that the χ for non-spherical particles of fractal dimension 1.76 (in case of dry, chain-like aggregates) reaches a maximum value of ~ 40 , which is in line with the observation of Kops et al. (1975). Similarly, χ is estimated to vary between 1 to 5 for $d_f=2.5$. Aggregate with the lower d_f will have larger value of χ as it experiences a higher drag force. The effect of non-spherical nature is highlighted from the results in Fig. 1b. Air-borne mass concentration of the aerosols reduces slowly for $d_f=1.76$ as compared to $d_f=2.5$ and $d_f=3.0$ (spherical compact aggregates). Upon fitting the decay curve to an exponential function, reduction of air-borne mass concentration of aerosols in the containment can be expressed in terms of the decay constant, λ . λ decreases as fractal dimension decreases thereby implying long time survival of sparse fractal aggregates. The study demonstrates that the shape factors of fractal aggregates will have significant influence on their survival times ($1/\lambda$), in the containment.

CONCLUSIONS

The study illustrates the usefulness of Stokesian Dynamics approach for determining the shape factors for aerosol aggregates in general, and in the nuclear context in particular. It points out at the importance of shape factors and fractality of aggregates in governing the survival times of airborne mass (or radioactivity) in the containment. This calls for more extensive studies of critical aerosol release scenarios and their impact on aerosol survival times in the containment to narrow down conservatism from the perspective of assessment of atmospheric release source terms due to a postulated severe nuclear accident.

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THEORETICAL ESTIMATION OF AEROSOL SHAPE FACTORS

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INTRODUCTION

The size distribution and morphology of particles play a crucial role in determination of their aerodynamic and collision properties. For the sake of simplicity, models describing aerosol dynamics generally assume particles to be spherical and fully dense but aerosols are often neither spherical nor fully dense. In order to get precise information about the aerosol particle metrics, a combination of imaging techniques along with simultaneous measurement of aerodynamic and mobility properties is proposed to obtain fractal dimension and dynamic shape factor. The hydrodynamic radius and the radius of gyration can be estimated using imaging techniques such as scanning electron microscopy (SEM) or transmission electron microscopy (TEM) along with algorithms to study morphology of the aggregate. Aerodynamic and electrical mobility properties of the aggregate can be obtained using electrical low pressure impactor (ELPI) and scanning mobility particle sizer (SMPS), respectively. Present work highlights the systematic approach for determination of morphological descriptors and the corresponding dynamic shape factor.

METHODOLOGY

Aerosol aggregate comprises a number of primary molecules or monomers. These monomers, assumed to be spherical in nature, undergo microphysical process to form a non-spherical aggregate, termed as quasi-fractal aggregate. Though quite complex and random, the morphology can be closely represented by the statistical scaling law using various morphological descriptors. Image analysis of the given aggregate using retrieval algorithms (Singh and Thajudeen, 2023) can provide information of number of primary particles in the agglomerate (n_{pp}), radius of gyration (r_g), diameter of primary particles (d_{pp}), fractal dimension (D_f), projected area (A_p), hydrodynamic diameter (d_h). To estimate mobility equivalent diameter (d_m), one needs to relate mobility diameter to C_c and A_p of the aggregate. Electrical mobility of aggregates is given by;

$$Z_p = \frac{v_{TE}}{E} = n_e e B = \frac{n_e e C_c}{3 \pi \mu_g d_m} \quad (1)$$

where, Z_p is electrical mobility of particles, v_{TE} is terminal electrostatic velocity, E is electrical field strength n_e , is number of elementary charge on particles, e is the elementary charge ($1.6 \times 10^{-19} C$), μ_g is gas viscosity, $B = \frac{C_c}{3 \pi \mu_g d_m}$ is mechanical mobility, $C_c = 1 + Kn(1.257 + 0.4 e^{-1.1/Kn})$ is Cunningham slip

correction factor which is a function of Knudsen number ($Kn = \frac{\pi d_h \lambda}{2 A_p}$). Agglomerate size can be expressed in terms of mobility, mass, aerodynamic, hydrodynamic, volume equivalent diameter or the physical diameter depending upon the property/observable of interest. In case of singly charged particles,

$$\frac{3 \pi \mu_g d_m}{1 + Kn_1(1.257 + 0.4 e^{-1.1/Kn_1})} = \frac{3 \pi \mu_g d_h}{1 + Kn_2(1.257 + 0.4 e^{-1.1/Kn_2})} \quad (2)$$

$$Kn_1 = \frac{2 \lambda}{d_m} \quad \& \quad Kn_2 = \frac{\lambda}{(2 A_p / \pi d_h)} \quad (3)$$

In continuum regime, $Kn_1 \ll 1$, $Kn_2 \ll 1$; $d_m = d_h$ (4)

In free molecular regime, $Kn_1 \gg 1$, $Kn_2 \gg 1$; $d_m = 2 \sqrt{\frac{A_p}{\pi}}$ (5)

Since, mean free path of gas molecules ($\lambda = \lambda_r (101.3/P) (T/293.15) (1 + 110/293.15 + 110/T)$) is a function of temperature and pressure, if aerodynamic measurements are made using electrical low pressure impactor (ELPI), the correction in the mean free path needs to be accounted. Here, λ_r is molecular mean free path at normal conditions (293.15 K and 101.3 kPa), P is pressure in kPa, T is temperature in K. The information about projected area and hydrodynamic radius can be obtained using regression relations for a cluster with given fractal dimension and number of primary particles also referred to as monomers. Further, for aerodynamic properties, ELPI sorts particles according to their relaxation time (τ). The relaxation time in terms of mobility and aerodynamic diameter is expressed as;

$$\tau = mB = \rho_0 d_a^2 C_c / 18 \mu_g \quad (6)$$

For a given agglomerate, since we are looking at the similar aerodynamic property of the agglomerate, $m_{fr} B_{fr} = m_s B_s$ (7)

where, $m_s = (\pi/6) \rho_0 d_a^3$ and $m_{fr} = (\pi/6) \rho_{pp} d_{pp}^3 n_{pp}$ are mass of spherical and fractal particles respectively. For unit density sphere; $d_m = d_a$. The relation between aerodynamic diameter and the number of primary particles in agglomerate is given by;

$$\rho_{pp} \frac{\pi}{6} d_{pp}^3 n_{pp} \left(\frac{1 + Kn_3 (1.257 + 0.4 e^{-1.1/Kn_3})}{6 \pi \mu_g r_h} \right) = \rho_0 \frac{\pi}{6} d_a^3 \left(\frac{1 + Kn_4 (1.257 + 0.4 e^{-1.1/Kn_4})}{3 \pi \mu_g d_a} \right)$$

$$Kn_3 = \frac{\lambda_{ELPI}}{(A_p / \pi r_h)} \quad \& \quad Kn_4 = \frac{2 \lambda_{ELPI}}{d_a} \quad (8)$$

λ_{ELPI} is the mean free path of air at a given pressure in an impactor stage (Marjamaki et al., 2000). In continuum regime,

$$d_a = \sqrt{\frac{\rho_{pp}}{\rho_0} d_{pp}^3 n_{pp} \left(\frac{1}{2 r_h} \right)} \quad (10)$$

In free molecular regime, aerodynamic diameter of the agglomerate is given by,

$$d_a^2 \left(1 + \frac{2 \lambda_{ELPI}}{d_a} \right) = \frac{\rho_{pp}}{\rho_0} d_{pp}^3 n_{pp} \left(\frac{1 + \frac{\lambda_{ELPI}}{(A_p / \pi r_h)}}{2 r_h} \right) \quad (11)$$

Once, we have the information of mobility and aerodynamic properties of an aggregate, dynamic shape factor ($\chi = F_D / F_{Dv}$), defined as ratio of the actual drag force on non-spherical particle (F_D) to the drag force on a sphere of equivalent volume moving at the same velocity (F_{Dv}) can be estimated.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Consider soot particles with $d_m = 300 \text{ nm}$, $\rho_{pp} = 2 \text{ g/cm}^3$ (Jenny Rissler et al., 2013), $d_{pp} = 76 \text{ nm}$ (Rajan Dhaubhadel, 2000). Other inputs are taken from regression relations obtained from algorithms for image analysis (Melas et al., 2014) as, $n_{pp} = 8$, $\ln(A_p / A_{pp}) = 1.8$, $\ln(r_g^2 / r_{pp}^2) = 2$, and other inputs are calculated as, $A_{pp} = 4536.5 \text{ nm}^2$, $A_p = 27444.2 \text{ nm}^2$, $r_g = 103.3 \text{ nm}$. Using Eq. 2, 3, 8 and 9, hydrodynamic diameter and the aerodynamic diameter is estimated to be $d_h = 343.6 \text{ nm}$ and $d_a = 183.5 \text{ nm}$ respectively. It is to be noted that pressure dependent mean free path ($\lambda = \frac{65 * 101.3}{68.19} \left(1 + \frac{110}{293.15} + \frac{110}{293.15} \right) = 171.86 \text{ nm}$) is used to estimate aerodynamic diameter of agglomerate. The corresponding dynamic shape factor is (slip correction factor is ~ 1 and hence not shown in calculation) $\chi = \left((d_m^2 / d_a^2) (\rho / \rho_0) \right)^{1/3} = 1.9$. These results can be further verified using experimental observations/results.

CONCLUSIONS

The study presents a detailed methodology to estimate mobility and aerodynamic properties of an agglomerate by image analysis using an algorithm, which can be verified using experimental observations. The values of mobility and aerodynamic properties of an aggregate can then be used to estimate the fractal dimension and the dynamic shape factor, which can be used in aerosol modelling codes.

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AEROSOL OPTICAL DEPTH VARIATION IN THE INDIAN REGION: INVESTIGATING THE ROLE OF ANTHROPOGENIC AEROSOL

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Keywords: Aerosol optical depth, NCAP-COALESCE, Natural and Anthropogenic aerosol

INTRODUCTION

Aerosols are one of the most significant uncertainties in predicting the Earth's climate, owing to their impact on the atmosphere's radiation balance. Aerosol Optical Depth is vertically integrated aerosol extinction coefficient and the main measurable quantity in the atmosphere. Due to rapid urbanization and industrial growth, aerosol loading in the Indian region has increased over time. Although dust aerosol is a major problem experienced in most cities, other anthropogenic emissions also significantly influence the aerosol optical properties in this region. It is important to estimate the contribution of anthropogenic aerosol (carbon and sulfate) into AOD and columnar burden. Carbonaceous aerosols play a crucial role in climate, with their impact dependent on composition, making accurate assessment essential for addressing global warming. Quantification of season wise contribution anthropogenic aerosol will help in improving the season wise source emission rate. It is expected that species wise AOD variation will follow same trend as species wise variation of aerosol column burden and both. But that may not be exactly true due to calculation methodology of AOD in models for various species and assumption of hygroscopicity. In present study, an estimation of contribution of anthropogenic aerosol to the total AOD and aerosol columnar burden for four seasons is carried out from simulation and the results are discussed with season variation of single scattering albedo (SSA). This work is carried out as a part of NCAP-COALESCE project (Venkataraman et al., 2020).

METHODS

The non-hydrostatic icosahedral atmospheric model (NICAM) coupled with Spectral radiation-transport model for aerosol species (SPRINTARS) is used for simulation of various aerosol and optical properties over Indian region. In the present study, a horizontal resolution of ~ 112 km is set up for simulation. In NICAM-SPRINTARS, bulk aerosol scheme is used in which all aerosol species are assumed to be externally mixed except carbonaceous aerosol in which 50 % of BC from anthropogenic source is externally mixed while remaining are internally mixed as BC and OC. Natural aerosols such as sea salt and dust are emitted online using empirical formula at each model integration step (Takemura et al., 2000). The difference of the concentration between before and after the time step is regarded as the emission flux. Aerosol emissions from SMOG-India-v1 for the Indian domain nested in the global Community Emissions Data System (CEDS) dataset is used in this study for the period 2005–2014.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig.1 and Fig.2 show season wise contribution of anthropogenic aerosol (carbonaceous and sulfate) as fraction of total AOD and season wise SSA distribution. As expected, the AOD follows the pattern similar to the columnar burden except few places. Mismatch in percentage contribution by AOD and columnar load is also reflected in Table 1. During the monsoon and pre-monsoon seasons in India, natural aerosols such as dust and biomass burning particles are often more prevalent (Table 1). In contrast, during other seasons, anthropogenic aerosols, such as those from industrial emissions and transportation, tend to be more dominant. This could be due to increased human activities and pollution levels during these times. Contribution of carbonaceous aerosol in anthropogenic aerosol is $\sim 40\%$ in all seasons. During winter season the contribution of carbonaceous aerosol into total AOD is maximum $\sim 38\%$ and minimum in monsoon (12%). Single scattering albedo (SSA) gives the total effective scattering efficiency of aerosols present in the atmosphere. Range of SSA over the Indian landmass is 0.75-0.9. Adjoining ocean regions show higher SSA ($\sim 0.9-0.95$) due to enhanced humid environment and presence of more hygroscopic aerosols (sea salt, transported sulfate) which increases the presence of aerosol water content,

leading to larger scattering from particles. Low SSA values of the IGP region are due to the presence of a high fraction of carbonaceous aerosols with absorption properties. The percentage contribution of anthropogenic aerosol AOD is tallying with SSA distribution.

Table 1: Percentage season wise contribution of anthropogenic aerosols (Indian land mass average)

Season	DJF	MAM	JJA	SON
AOD	84	58	39	78
Columnar Burden	47	18	9	37

It is observed that, while natural aerosols may contribute significantly to the columnar burden, they may not have the same impact on AOD because AOD is influenced by the size, composition, and altitude of aerosol particles. Several factors can contribute to the observed difference between aerosol column burden and AOD: **a) Particle Size and Composition:** Natural aerosols may consist of larger particles or particles with different optical properties than anthropogenic aerosols, which can affect their impact on AOD, **b) Vertical Distribution:** The vertical distribution of aerosols can vary, with natural aerosols sometimes concentrated in lower atmospheric layers, while anthropogenic aerosols may extend higher into the atmosphere, influencing AOD differently, **c) Aerosol Hygroscopicity:** Aerosols can absorb moisture, especially during the monsoon, which can alter their optical properties and affect AOD.

CONCLUSION

AOD during winter and post-monsoon season is dominated by anthropogenic aerosols (SSA distribution also reproduces this). The percentage contribution as observed in aerosol column burden is not fully reflected in AOD. Understanding these discrepancies is crucial for accurate modelling and monitoring of aerosol behaviour in the Indian region with implications in climate, air quality, and health.

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MODELLING NEAR-SOURCE AEROSOL DYNAMICS: IMPACTS ON SIZE DISTRIBUTION AND OPTICAL PROPERTIES

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Keywords: Near-source parameterization, Dispersion-Coagulation, Optical properties, Mie Theory

INTRODUCTION

Aerosol particles, when initially emitted from various sources, undergo a series of physical and chemical transformations in the atmosphere before becoming integrated into the background aerosol population. In the vicinity of emission sources, coagulation is the primary mechanism responsible for changes in the number concentration and size distribution of aerosol particles. Due to the combined action of coagulation and dispersion, aerosol number size distributions undergo changes following emission, typically leading to a shift towards larger sizes and change in modal width. This phenomenon is especially significant in cases involving large-scale emissions, such as forest fires, biomass burning, volcanic eruptions, aircraft emissions, and explosive releases, where high aerosol number concentrations are typically observed at the emission points. For example, particles freshly generated during biomass burning lies in a size range of 10-70 nm (Bayona et al., 2023), which grow to ~ few hundreds of nm during timescales of <24 h due to condensation and coagulation. Since these transformations occur in close proximity to the source of aerosols, cloud- and climate-models generally do not account for sub-grid aerosol coagulation within the plumes. To enhance the representation of near-source aerosol dynamics within long-range transport models, a parameterization scheme is developed in this study. This scheme estimate effective number loading factors along with their associated size distributions. Furthermore, our investigation in this study extends to assessing the resultant alterations in aerosol optical properties stemming from these near-source aerosol dynamics.

METHODS

A general dynamic equation (GDE) is formulated by combining the coagulation equation (for in-plume aerosol coagulation) with steady-state Gaussian plume model for the dispersion. The GDE is solved using the method of moments in the asymptotic limit of the downwind distance with the initial aerosol size distribution assumed to be log normal. The resulting expressions of count median diameter (CMD_{∞}) and geometric standard deviation (GSD_{∞}) for the final size distribution under the asymptotic limit are as follows:

$$CMD_{\infty} = \left[\frac{6}{\pi} \times \frac{CMV_0}{\psi(\infty)} e^{\left(\frac{9}{2}(\ln GSD_0)^2 - \frac{9}{2}(\ln GSD_{\infty})^2 \right)} \right]^{\frac{1}{3}}, \text{ and } GSD_{\infty} = \exp \left[\frac{1}{3} \sqrt{\ln \left(\frac{e^{9(\ln GSD_0)^2} + 2\mu}{(1+1.32\mu)^{0.76}} \right)} \right].$$

and GSD_0 are count median volume and its geometric standard deviation at $x = 0$, $\psi(\infty)$ is the asymptotic

number survival fraction given by, $\frac{1}{(1+1.32\mu)^{0.76}}$, $\mu = \frac{1}{6\sqrt{3}} \frac{K S_0}{U \sigma_0^{\frac{4}{3}}} \frac{1}{(C\epsilon)^{\frac{1}{3}}}$, K is coagulation kernel, S_0 is

number emission rate at the source location, U is the average wind speed, σ_0 is dimension of source, C is a constant, and ϵ is turbulent kinetic energy dissipation rate. These equations are integral components of the proposed parameterization scheme to model near-source aerosol dynamics within long-range aerosol transport models. To assess how parameterization-induced changes in size distribution affect aerosol optical properties, PyMieScatt (Sumlin et al., 2018), an open-source Python code for performing Mie theory calculations is employed in this study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this current study, we utilize the developed parameterization scheme to investigate the changes in size distribution of carbonaceous aerosols originating from biomass burning sources. An initial lognormal size distribution of $CMD_0 = 50$ nm, $GSD_0 = 1.4$ at the source location is considered. The mass emission rate varies widely, ranging from a minimum of 0.1 g/s in residue burning sources to a maximum

of 15 kg/s in large-scale forest fires. The corresponding number emission rates (S_0) at the source are estimated using the Hatch-Choate relationship. By applying the parameterization scheme to an aerosol plume with a source emission rate of 10^{18} #/s, along with the previously discussed input parameters, the resulting final size distribution yields a CMD of 122 nm with a GSD of 1.45 (as shown in Fig. 1(a)). This outcome highlights a substantial alteration in the size distribution (a 2.44-fold increase in the CMD value), underscoring its importance for inclusion in large-scale climate models.

In Fig. 1(b), the variation of optical parameters obtained through Mie calculations using PyMieScatt is presented. These parameters include Extinction Efficiency (Q_{ext}), Scattering Efficiency (Q_{sca}), Absorption Efficiency (Q_{abs}), Asymmetry Factor (g), Radiation Pressure (Q_{pr}), Back-Scattering Efficiency (Q_{back}), and Back-Scattering Ratio (Q_{ratio}). They are computed for carbonaceous aerosols with a core-shell (water) configuration at relative humidity of 50%, covering a range of source number emission rates (S_0). The application of the near-source parameterization results in modification of Mie efficiencies, encompassing extinction, absorption, and scattering. These efficiencies exhibit a substantial increase, ranging from 0.025 to 1.1, spanning orders of magnitude. Notably, this change of aerosol optical properties becomes particularly pronounced for values of S_0 exceeding 10^{17} #/s.

Figure 1: (a) Shift in size distribution due to near-source parameterization (Initial size distribution: $CMD_0 = 50$ nm with $GSD_0 = 1.4$), (b) Variation of Mie efficiencies with source number emission rate.

CONCLUSION

In summary, this study investigates the evolution of aerosol size distribution originating from emission sources, emphasizing the impact of coagulation and dispersion near emission locations. The results demonstrate substantial changes in aerosol size distributions, underscoring their importance for large-scale climate models. The application of this parameterization significantly modifies aerosol optical properties, as indicated by Mie calculations, with substantial increases in efficiencies for extinction, absorption, and scattering. These findings emphasize the need to account for near-source aerosol dynamics in climate modelling.

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SIMULATIONS OF PM_{2.5} WITH WRF-CAMx AND ESTIMATING AIR QUALITY SOCIAL IMPACT USING REGRESSION ANALYSIS OVER INDIA (EASIUR-INDIA)

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Keywords: Air pollution, Particulate matter, Population, PMCAMx, Marginal social cost

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution refers to the contamination of the atmosphere with substances, such as solid particles, gases, or liquid droplets, above a certain threshold level that is harmful to human health, the environment, and other species. To mitigate various adverse impacts of these pollutants, it is essential to establish and enforce strict laws and regulations aimed at controlling and reducing pollutant emissions. To implement these rules, we first need to know the concentrations of various pollutants in the air. People have done a lot of work in this field to find the concentration level so that policymakers can make strict rules against these agencies. In this work, we first simulate the PM_{2.5} concentration using WRF and CAMx model at a resolution of 30 km and we developed a method “Estimating air quality social impact using regression analysis over India (EASIUR-India)” (taken from (Heo et al., 2016a,b)) to estimate the public health cost of emissions for 2019 for four different seasons for different pollutants.

METHODS

The Comprehensive Air Quality Model Extensions (CAMx) version 4.02 was used in this study to predict the PM_{2.5} concentrations over India. All the hours in 2019 were simulated using the model with a horizontal grid resolution of 30 km (130 X 130 grids) and 14 vertical layers reaching 16 km high covering India and parts of the surrounding countries in Asia. Meteorological inputs were generated using WRF version 4.2.0 with initial and boundary conditions from FNL (Final) Operational Global Analysis data on 0.25° × 0.25° grids from National Center for Atmospheric Research for every 6 h. Initial and boundary conditions for chemical fields were taken from the CAM-Chem Global Chemical Transport Model (6-h temporal resolution) (Buchholz et al., 2019). For emission inventory input we have used the anthropogenic emissions of Carbon Monoxide (CO), Nitrogen Oxides (NOx), Non-Methane Volatile Organic Compounds (NMVOC), Methane (CH₄), Ammonia (NH₃), Sulphur Dioxide (SO₂), PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and Carbonaceous speciation (BC, OC) from the Emissions Database for Global Atmospheric Research (EDGARv5.0) (Crippa et al., 2019). This data base has the base year 2015 at spatial resolution of 0.1degree x 0.1degree and temporal monthly resolution.

For tagged simulations we have used Particulate Matter Source Apportionment Technology (PSAT) (Koo et al., 2009; Wagstrom et al., 2008), which is a CAMx module, played an important role in generating our dataset efficiently. The per-tonne social costs were determined using a conventional impact pathway method. A health-impact function, Eq. (1), estimates the changes in mortality ($\Delta y_{x,y}$ in number of premature deaths) at each down-wind location after a CTM calculates the changes in PM 2.5 concentrations on annual average ($\Delta C_{x,y}$ in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) at each grid cell (x,y) of the simulation domain from given emissions:

$$\Delta y_{x,y} = y_{x,y}^0 \cdot \left\{ 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\ln R}{10} \cdot \Delta c_{x,y}\right) \right\} \quad (1)$$

$$S = \frac{\sum_{x,y} \Delta y_{x,y} \cdot \text{VSL}}{E} \quad (2)$$

Where $y_{x,y}^0$ is the base line mortality (x, y), and R is the relative risk reported by epidemiological studies, i.e. the changes in mortality rate over an increase of 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in PM_{2.5} concentrations. As per U.S. EPA studies for the Asian countries the relative risk values is given 1.08 which was used in the current model study. Further for simplifying method we are calculating the marginal social cost per tonne is calculated as follows Where E is the amount of emission concentrations (in metric ton), and VSL is the value of statistical life.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The concentrations of PM_{2.5} and its components in 2019 were predicted over India using WRF and the CAMx. Model performance was validated against available ground-based observations from national

ambient air quality monitoring stations (CAAQMS). The seasonal variability of PM_{2.5} concentrations was observed to be higher during the winter and lower during the monsoon season, and during all the seasons, the highest PM_{2.5} concentrations were observed over the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) (Fig. 1).

After evaluating the model performance with observations, we have further aimed to estimate the public health costs of fine PM and its precursor emissions by using the PSAT in PMCAMx, but it is computationally very expensive due to their complex processes (Fig. 2). So we have developed a method EASIUR-India that estimates the public health cost of emissions accurately with low computational cost. The PSAT-tagged CTM simulations are used in this method to build a large dataset of air quality and public health costs from marginal emissions throughout India. To estimate the exposed population, two methods were developed: one that assumes a generic downwind plume concentration profile derived from CTM outputs and a simpler method that uses the size of the population within certain distances as a variable. Using the former method, we parameterized marginal public health cost [€/t] as a function of exposed population and key atmospheric variables. We derived models for PM_{2.5} inorganic precursors (elemental carbon, sulfur dioxide, nitrogen oxides, and ammonia), and our model results are compared to estimates calculated directly using CTM outputs (Fig.2). Our findings demonstrate that the public health costs of emissions can be parameterized effectively for policy evaluations based on state-of-the-art CTMs.

CONCLUSION

The concentrations of PM_{2.5} and its components in 2019 were predicted over India using CAMx. Model performance was validated against available ground-based observations from monitoring stations (CAAQMS).

- During winter, monsoon and post-monsoon seasons, the model performed well all over the Indian cities.
- In pre-monsoon the model performance is good in south Indian regions where as rest of the part the model shown strong under estimation with observations.
- The seasonal variability of PM_{2.5} concentrations was observed to be higher during the winter and lower during the monsoon season, and during all the seasons, the highest PM_{2.5} concentrations were observed over the IGP.
- After evaluating the model performance with observations, we have further aimed to estimate the pre-mortality and marginal social coasts of fine PM and its precursor emissions by using the PSAT.
- Over the high population regions we observed that the high pre-mortality. The source concentrations deceased towards to downwind region, the exposed population less effected away from the source.

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MODELING OF AEROSOL FORMATION UNDER RAPID THERMAL TRANSIENTS

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Keywords: Cesium Chloride, particle evolution, general dynamic equation, numerical techniques.

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric release of hazardous material in the form of aerosol has significant potential to cause extensive area contamination and affect human health. The following dispersion and depletion depend on the aerodynamic properties and meteorological conditions. Therefore, characterization of the aerosols at the release point is essential to model the resulting atmospheric dispersion and impact assessment. In general, the release mechanisms of the atmospheric releases are often associated with rapid thermal transients such as bursts, fire etc.; consequently, the experimental measurement remains challenging. Reliable numerical models can serve as a suitable alternative to the characterization of the aerosols. The current study presents the development of a numerical model for simulating aerosol particle formation and evolution and discusses its performance against the experimental results of Cesium Chloride (CsCl) vapour evolution into particles (Di Lemma et al., 2016).

METHODS

Consider a saturated vapour experiencing rapid cooling; the vapour monomers undergo homogenous nucleation and generate particles; these particles further evolve due to microphysical processes such as coagulation and condensation. Let n_k be the number concentration of particles with the volume between v_k and $v_k + dv_k$, the general dynamic equation can be written as,

$$\frac{dn_k}{dt} = \left. \frac{\partial n_k}{\partial t} \right|_{\text{nucleation}} + \left. \frac{\partial n_k}{\partial t} \right|_{\text{coagulation}} + \left. \frac{\partial n_k}{\partial t} \right|_{\text{condensation}} \quad (1)$$

The first term of RHS represents the formation rate of particles through the nucleation process. The second and third terms represent the rate of change of particle number concentration due to coagulation and condensation. The current study uses the sectional method to solve the governing equation numerically. The nucleation process is modelled using the nucleation rate given by Girshick and Chiu (Girshick and Chiu, 1990); the coagulation process is solved using a semi-implicit scheme given by Jacobson (Jacobson, 2002), and the coagulation frequency is estimated using Fuch's coagulation kernel. The condensation process is modelled using the centre-moving scheme given by Jacobson (Jacobson, 2002).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Lemma et al. (Di Lemma et al., 2016) generated CsCl aerosol particles using high-temperature transients of laser heating and measured the aerosol particle size distribution. The initial temperature of the vapour is ~1200K, and the vapour cools down at a rate ~2500 K/s. The numerical results show that, during the cooling, the initially saturated vapour became supersaturated and generated nucleated particles of average diameter ~10 nm. As a result, the particle number concentration rapidly increased to ~10¹⁷ particles per m³. These particles further grew in size due to simultaneous coagulation and condensation processes. The comparison of the numerical results with the experimental measurements is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Comparison of the numerical simulation results with the experimental data of CsCl particle formation under rapid cooling of CsCl.

Fig. 1 shows that the numerical modelling results are comparable with the experimental measurements. Both experiments and numerical results show that the size distribution peaked at $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$ aerodynamic diameter. The study also highlights that the size domain of the particles falls in the inhalable range; therefore, they can cause a significant health effect to humans through inhalation. Thus, the study helped understand the insights of the aerosol evolution processes and their potential to cause significant impacts.

CONCLUSIONS

A numerical model is developed to simulate the aerosol particle formation under rapid thermal transient conditions. The model is validated by comparison of the results with experimental data. The study shows that the numerical models performed satisfactorily in reproducing the experimental observation.

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SEASONAL VARIATION OF AEROSOL OPTICAL DEPTH OVER INDIA UNDER FUTURISTIC CLIMATE SCENARIOS: AN IMPLICATION OF CARBONACEOUS AEROSOLS

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Keywords: Aerosol Optical Depth, Carbonaceous Aerosols, Organic Carbon, Black Carbon, GEOS-Chem

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols, including carbonaceous particles, have profound implications for human health, climate, and air quality in India, a nation experiencing rapid urbanization and population growth (Gunthe et al., 2021; Shekar Reddy & Venkataraman, 2000). These aerosols influence parameters like visibility, precipitation patterns, and air quality, with rising concentrations of sulfate, Black Carbon (BC), Organic Carbon (OC), dust, and Sea Salt (SS) particles over the Indian subcontinent (David et al., 2018). Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD), a key measure of particle concentration, has shown an increasing trend, particularly in densely populated regions like the Indo Gangetic Plain (IGP), impacting climate with rising temperatures and altered monsoon patterns (Cowan & Cai, 2011). These aerosols also pose health risks, contributing to respiratory and cardiovascular diseases (Yang et al., 2019). In light of India's commitment to reducing carbon emissions, this study examines the future trends in carbonaceous aerosols under Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs), focusing on RCP4.5 and RCP8.5. It reveals both current trends and future scenarios, emphasizing the urgency of emission reduction strategies to combat air pollution and improve air quality in India.

METHODS

This study employs version 12.2.1 of the GEOS-Chem 3-D global model, driven by 6-hourly assimilated meteorological data from NASA's Modern Era Retrospective Reanalysis2 (MERRA2). The simulation domain was nested over Asia (11°S-55°N, 60°-150°E), with a horizontal resolution of $0.5^\circ \times 0.625^\circ$ and 47 vertical layers down to 0.01 hPa. Aerosol components encompass black carbon (BC), organic carbon (OC), sulfate-nitrate-ammonium, dust, and sea salt, simulated using standard GEOS-Chem methods. Simulations involve emissions from 2010 and future decades (2010-2100) under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios, driven by 2010 MERRA-2 meteorology. Anthropogenic emissions, including carbon monoxide, non-methane VOCs, sulfur dioxide, NO_x, ammonia, BC, and OC, are categorized into ten activities, with monthly scaling factors enhancing accuracy. Observations for model validation include AOD data from AERONET stations, MODIS measurements from Aqua and Terra satellites, and MERIS data from Envisat, converted to model resolution for assessing aerosol concentration simulations.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Under the RCP4.5 scenario, the AOD increases at a rate of 6.91% AOD per decade until the year 2030 and then there is a decrease of -8.76% AOD per decade. For the RCP8.5 scenario, on the other hand an increase of 8.72% AOD per decade through 2050 and a further decrease of -3.52% AOD per decade from 2050 to the end of the century is observed. The maximum AOD is observed over Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) in both scenarios. Under RCP8.5, 2020-2080 is the period with high AOD, mostly contributed by IGP and East India (EI). A gradual increase in AOD over Central India and some parts of South India and West India from 2030 is noticed, but the reduction in this region is also very much evident from 2090 until the end of the century. Similar to RCP8.5, high AOD is observed over IGP and EI until 2050 in RCP4.5, however a much higher reduction by the end of the century is evident in this scenario.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, these findings underscore the feasibility of future reductions in AOD levels. Although projected future changes in AOD due to carbonaceous aerosols under RCP scenarios provide us with important guidance for mitigation efforts, such projections are subject to uncertainty. However, realizing these potential demands stringent measures to be implemented, either to attain the objective out right or to effectively mitigate its impacts.

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COMBINED REAL-TIME SOURCE APPORTIONMENT

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Keywords: POSITIV MATRIX FACTORIZATION, REAL-TIME SOURCE APPORTIONMENT.

INTRODUCTION

Despite well-documented adverse effects on human health, ecosystems, and air quality (Fuzzi et al., 2015), atmospheric aerosols remain a key uncertainty when assessing anthropogenic impacts on climate change. The identification and quantification of aerosol sources is essential for analyzing policy initiatives, developing and validating air quality forecasts, and responding to extreme air quality events in a timely manner. The advantage of source apportionment (SA) is its ability to reduce an extremely large and complex input data set to a small number of sources related to real-world processes. The output is therefore optimal for monitoring initiatives of this nature. During the past decades, positive matrix factorization (PMF) has been extensively used for the SA of aerosols.

METHODS

The Aerosol Chemical Speciation Monitor (ACSM, Aerodyne Research, Inc.) and the Xact 625i Ambient Metals Monitor (Cooper Environmental) have been proven to be robust instruments for long-term monitoring and characterization of the different species of the atmospheric particulate matter levels. While the ACSM measures non-refractive species (ammonium, chloride, nitrate, organics and sulfate), the Xact measures the elemental composition. There are numerous publications on SA analysis for data from each instrument individually. Almost all studies perform the SA on the data after the measurement campaign ended, i.e., not in real-time.

As recently demonstrated, the rolling window PMF analysis (Canonaco et al., 2022) provides more robust and accurate SA results for multi-seasonal datasets since it overcomes the limitation of static factor profiles in traditional PMF analysis. Using this approach and combining it with chemical mass balance (CMB) analysis, SA results can be obtained in real-time (Chen et al., 2022). While CMB is used to update of the SA with every new measurement, the rolling window technique is used to obtain the up-to-date factor profiles that are used for the CMB based on data of the last 7-14 days.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

In this work, we present the first real-time SA for the two instruments combined, using SoFi RT (Datalystica. Ltd.). The data from the two instruments is automatically uploaded into a cloud folder from where SoFi RT accesses and downloads the data. For the ACSM, PMF is only conducted over the organic aerosol (OA), the other species are added to the final pie chart for completeness. While the real-time result is based on a CMB analysis based on the newest profiles from rolling PMF, rolling PMF is performed with constrained primary OA (POA) profiles using the random a-value approach for the ACSM. The analysis for the Xact is done by using variable specific constraints instead of constraint of full profiles. This approach offers versatility to the model, as it is not necessary to know the exact source profile in a given region, which can vary greatly, but only the relevant tracers.

This novel approach has great potential, as high-quality SA in real-time could help policymakers design and validate mitigation strategies. Moreover, it could be the basis for air quality forecasts and for the public to understand air pollution events better.

CONCLUSIONS

We present an approach to combine the data from ACSM and Xact for real-time analysis. The source apportionment is fully automated and offers a better understanding of the aerosol sources as it is considering organic aerosol and elemental data for the source apportionment analysis.

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TRANSPORT OF AEROSOL THROUGH ANNULAR REGION OF PIPE-IN-PIPE SYSTEM

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Keywords: annular region, pipe-in-pipe, aerosol penetration

INTRODUCTION

In nuclear facilities like spent fuel reprocessing and waste management plants, transfer of high active radioactive liquids is done using pipe-in-pipe arrangement which is an in-built design safety feature. In this arrangement, the inner pipe which contains the liquid is the primary containment and another pipe of larger diameter which houses the primary pipe is the secondary containment. The objective of this arrangement is to contain any liquid in case of failure of the primary pipe containing the radioactive liquid. In order to identify any leakage in the primary pipe, the annular region between the two pipes is purged with particle free air, which is subsequently monitored for its activity concentration. Effective use of this technique will depend on aerosol penetration efficiency, which is derived from understanding the aerosol transport in this type of geometry. Literature survey indicated that aerosol transport is well studied in case of circular pipe both theoretically and experimentally but there is not much data in existing literature about transport of aerosols in annular pipe [1-3]. In view of this, the transport behaviour of the aerosol in annular pipe using a laboratory scale experimental set-up was studied and the results are being presented here.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The laboratory scale experimental set-up consists of two concentric stainless steel pipes of diameter 41 mm and 48 mm and length 4000 mm. The annular space is provided with one air inlet, one outlet and equidistant sampling ports (SP) for aerosol sampling and measurements. The schematic is as shown in Fig.1

Fig.1: Schematics of experimental set-up

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Poly-disperse sodium chloride aerosol is generated using a BARC-made nebulizer. The aerosol is dried and homogenized in a well-ventilated chamber. After characterising, aerosols are fed to the annular space using one of the sampling ports, which is located at 200 mm from the air inlet point. Aerosol size distribution measurement was carried out at different distance axially using other ports (SP-1 to SP-6). Fig-2 shows the time series of the particle number concentration in aerosol chamber and Fig: 3-6 shows aerosol penetration efficiency as a function of flow rate and axial distance. It is seen that the efficiency decreases with increase in particle size as well as increasing air flow rate. This indicated that the air purge-rate optimization is needed to get maximum penetration efficiency. This requires detailed numerical

modelling and simulations to understand the effect of flow rate on different aerosol deposition processes and to develop a generalized formulation to estimate penetration efficiency for all practical purposes.

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**DEEP-BCSI: A DEEP LEARNING-BASED FRAMEWORK FOR BIAS CORRECTION AND
SPATIAL IMPUTATION OF PM_{2.5} CONCENTRATIONS IN SOUTH KOREA**

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Keywords: particulate matter, deep-learning, aerosols and air-quality.

INTRODUCTION

Airborne particulate matter (PM) is a significant pollutant composed of a mixture of solid particles and liquid droplets found in the air, including dust, dirt, soot, and smoke. PM is categorized as PM₁₀, characterized by inhalable particles with diameters 10 micrometres or smaller, and PM_{2.5}, characterized by fine inhalable particles with diameters 2.5 micrometres or smaller. Due to the serious health risks posed by PM_{2.5} pollution, such as cardiovascular and respiratory diseases, accurate and reliable forecasting of PM_{2.5} is essential. Chemical Transport Models (CTMs) such as Community Multiscale Air-Quality (CMAQ) have played an important role in forecasting of PM_{2.5} concentrations. However, their use is constrained by numerous factors, such as the inherent complexities associated with the representation of emission inventories, challenges in obtaining precise input data, and the simplifications involved in parameterization methods. Thus, to address the limitations of CTMs and improve the accuracy of air pollutant forecasting, the application of machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) algorithms has shown promise.

METHODS

To generate short-term forecasts of surface PM_{2.5} concentrations in South Korea up to 3 days in advance, the Deep-BCSI framework employs two supervised learning DL algorithms, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Partial Convolutional Neural Networks (PConv), which are used sequentially for bias correction and spatial imputation. The CNN model is designed to perform bias correction of CMAQ-simulated PM_{2.5} concentrations at the station level. Then, leveraging the improved accuracy of the earlier bias-corrected prediction, the PConv model performs spatial imputation to predict PM_{2.5} concentrations across South Korea at the grid level, including vast areas where the monitoring stations are not in proximity. We trained the Deep-BCSI framework using 72-hour (3-day) Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) and CMAQ simulation outputs with a spatial resolution of 27 km, along with the previous day's ground-based in-situ air quality measurements. See J. Park et al., 2022 for more details on the WRF and CMAQ model configurations. The CNN model targeted the in-situ measurements of surface PM_{2.5} concentrations in Korea. In total, 47 input variables were used to train the CNN model to perform station-based bias correction: (1) 10 atmospheric chemistry variables extracted from CMAQ outputs, (2) 31 meteorological variables from WRF outputs, and (3) 6 observational variables from ground-based air quality monitoring stations across Korea (AIRKOREA) (see <https://www.airkorea.or.kr>), which are the previous day's hourly in-situ measurements (quality-assured by the data provider) of air pollutant concentrations. The CNN model and PConv model were trained using 4 years (2016-2019) of the input dataset. The Deep-BCSI framework was evaluated for the year 2021. The model's loss function is a customized function based on the Index of Agreement (IOA) (Sayeed et al., 2021b). Upon completing the bias correction of the CNN model as described above, we used the resultant bias-corrected station-based PM_{2.5} concentrations across Korea as input for the PConv model to perform spatial imputation, producing grid-based forecasts of PM_{2.5} concentrations. We designed the PConv model based on the U-net architecture. The PConv model was trained using CMAQ-simulated grid-based PM_{2.5} concentrations at 27 km spatial resolution, prepared for the years 2016-2019 with a train-test split of 70%-30%. Then, the performance of the model was evaluated using in-situ measurements of PM_{2.5} concentrations obtained for the year 2021.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The framework’s evaluation is based on data from 402 stations, and the average values are calculated using these stations. Categorical performance metrics, such as THR, HHR, FAR, Overestimation, and Underestimation, are calculated based on AirKorea CAI standards for PM2.5 (see Section 2). For Index of Agreement (IOA), Total Hit Rate (THR), and High Hit Rate (HHR), higher values indicate higher accuracy, i.e., “the higher the better.” On the contrary, for FAR, Overestimation, and Underestimation, lower values indicate better performance, i.e., “the lower the better.”

Figure 1. Performance comparison of PM2.5 simulations for the CMAQ model (red) and CNN model (green) using validation metrics such as Index of Agreement (IOA), Total Hit Rate (THR), High Hit Rate (HHR), False Alarm Rate (FAR), Overestimation, and Underestimation averaged for the 402 stations across South Korea.

CONCLUSIONS

The CNN’s bias-corrected output showed higher accuracy compared to CMAQ, as indicated by higher values of IOA, THR, and HHR. We also concluded that the proposed CNN architecture effectively reduced biases in CMAQ’s simulation, as evidenced by smaller values of FAR, Overestimation, and Underestimation. However, there was an overestimation bias on Day 3 of the CNN model’s output, which can be attributed to the CMAQ input data used in the study.

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DYNAMIC FACTOR EVALUATION IN REAL-TIME SOURCE APPORTIONMENT

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Keywords: POSITIV MATRIX FACTORIZATION, REAL-TIME SOURCE APPORTIONMENT.

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols have severe impacts on climate, visibility, and human health (Fuzzi et al., 2015). To reduce the levels of air pollution, it is extremely important to identify and to attribute the sources of atmospheric aerosols. Positive matrix factorization (PMF) is a powerful tool and is typically used to retrieve robust and accurate source apportionment results from short- and long-term datasets. The source finder SoFi (Datalystica Ltd.) is a widely used, user-friendly and state-of-the-art source apportionment software.

In recent years, the limits of traditional PMF have been pushed, e.g., the rolling window PMF approach (Canonaco et al., 2022) has been introduced to overcome the limitation of static factor profiles in long-term datasets. However, so far the PMF analysis had to be performed after a measurement campaign, letting valuable time passing to understand momentary air pollution episodes. Therefore, automated source apportionment in real-time has been developed. For this SoFi RT (Datalystica Ltd.) is used.

METHODS

For the real-time source apportionment (SA), the data from the measurement instrument (currently operational for ACSM (Aerodyne Research, Inc.) and Xact (Cooper Environmental)) is automatically synchronized with SoFi RT. Then SoFi RT performs two types of automated SA. For the SA results of the latest data point, SoFi RT performs a simple chemical mass balance (CMB) using factor profiles from the rolling PMF analysis that is carried out on a small input window (typically the last 7-14 days prior to the current measurement).

By default, the PMF is conducted over a static number of PMF factors. However, the number of factors might change over the year, i.e., some factors might not be present at all during certain times (e.g., biomass burning organic aerosol (BBOA)) while others might split into two different factors (e.g., one oxygenated OA (OOA) in winter vs a more oxidized OOA (MO-OOA) and a less oxidized OOA (LO-OOA) in summer).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Here, we present a new approach using cluster analysis on a set of two key variables of the raw data for each factor when performing PMF to differentiate the number of present PMF factors for the rolling windows. The shape of the data is captured by performing the farthest point clustering algorithm. The cluster centroids are analysed for collinearity and depending on the outcome one or two factors are passed for the current PMF runs. This approach works over a wide range of different factor combinations that are or are not present, it only requires two key variables for each factor.

With this new approach, the scanning over various numbers of factors can be avoided, resulting in fewer PMF runs compared to classical manual PMF analysis. Furthermore, it allows for an automated real-time SA result approach with minimal user interaction.

CONCLUSIONS

We present an approach to dynamically adjust the number of sources in PMF during real-time analysis in order for an automated and objective identification and quantification of distinct aerosol sources.

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**REAL-TIME SOURCE APPORTIONMENT OF FINE ORGANIC AND INORGANIC
ATMOSPHERIC AEROSOLS IN URBAN AREAS; APPLICATION IN CHINA AND INDIA**
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Keywords: source apportionment, real-time, urban aerosols, PMF.

INTRODUCTION

Despite increasing interest in PM mitigation, knowledge of PM sources in urban areas remains limited and mismatches exist between current source apportionment (SA) capabilities and the needs of policy makers. First, source apportionment studies typically focus either on the organic or on the inorganic components of PM, whereas the total aerosol is potentially of public concern. Second, traditional source apportionment methods are based on sample collection for offline analysis, yielding results with low time resolution (e.g., 24-h average) and rendering inaccessible critical information regarding the diurnal cycles or particular short-lasting pollution events. Finally, although online measurements with higher time resolution have been successfully used for source apportionment, months of post-analysis are typically needed to produce a quantitative result. As a result, while SA studies are useful primarily for targeted policy design and long-term policy evaluation, existing methods are insufficient to inform a timely response to acute events. An effective, targeted, and timely response to short term high pollution events necessitates the development of real-time (RT) SA capabilities.

METHODS

In the current study the implementation of a real-time SA approach is demonstrated for the first time implemented in six Chinese cities (Xi'an, Chongqing, Beijing, Langfang, Wuhan, and Shijiazhuang) during 2020-2022. The software has also been tested for the inorganic component of PM in campaigns in Pune and Lucknow.

The instrumentation used during the sampling campaigns included a quadrupole or time-of-flight, (depending on location) aerosol chemical speciation monitor (ACSM, Aerodyne Research Inc., Billerica, Massachusetts, USA), Xact 625 Ambient Metals Monitor (Cooper Environmental, Tigard, OR, USA), and an aethalometer (AE33, Magee). Taken together, these instruments measure quantitatively the non-refractory submicron aerosol including organic aerosols (OA), nitrate, sulphate, ammonium, chloride, metals and trace elements, and black carbon (BC) at a time resolution of 1-hour or less.

A newly developed real-time SA software, and automated data transfer/integration procedure from the measuring instruments to the SA processor were used to perform SA analysis. The solver of the tool is the multilinear engine (ME-2) (Paatero, 1999). The model can run continuously in stations that are equipped with the aforementioned instruments, and after an initial run time of seven days (required to set the base case) provides information about the source of inorganic and organic fraction of PM, a few minutes after the measurements are completed.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The real-time SA software is used to identify the sources of the organic fraction of PM using ACSM data and the elemental fraction of PM using the Xact data. The SA results from the two datasets are then combined with the information regarding the concentration of ions from ACSM and BC from the Aethalometer, to provide a full characterization of the chemical composition and source contribution of PM.

The quality of the results of the real-time SA software were evaluated by comparing them to state of the art SA techniques. Overall, RT-SA provided results with reasonably low uncertainty.

Fig.1. Source apportionment results for Shijiazhuang

CONCLUSIONS

The application of the RT-SA software in the aforementioned areas showcased that it is possible to get reasonable results using such applications if the model is tuned properly. RT tools can be very useful for policy makers and for automated air-pollution monitoring.

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NUCLEAR AND RADIOACTIVE AEROSOLS

RESUSPENSION DYNAMICS OF THERMOPHORETICALLY DEPOSITED PARTICLES VIA SHOCKWAVE INTERACTION

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Keywords: SHOCKWAVE, THERMOPHORETIC DEPOSITION, RESUSPENSION

INTRODUCTION

In the event of a meltdown at a nuclear power station, the core can liquefy, which is called corium. It is possible for the vessel to be damaged or perhaps completely destroyed if this corium comes into contact with liquid water and causes steam explosions. This phenomenon is called a "vapor explosion" (Cronenberg and Benz 1980). The mishap can also cause hydrogen to build up, which could result in explosions inside the containment building (Abou-Rjeily et al. 2011). The shockwave created by these explosions has the capacity to fragment and resuspend the deposited particles and can propel them to great distances (Brandt et al., 1987; Strecker and Roth, 1994). The purpose of this investigation is to learn more about the dynamics between shockwaves and the metal oxide particles that have been deposited by thermophoresis.

METHODS

A plasma torch aerosol generator (PTAG) with 25 kW power was used to create zinc metal oxide particles. Zinc metal powder was fed into the plasma flame, where it vaporized, reacted with oxygen, and condensed into zinc metal oxide aerosol particles. These particles were passed through thin stainless steel sheets placed about 1 m away from the PTAG, undergoing thermophoretic deposition for an hour. The average temperature gradient remained at 530 K due to pipe wall and gas temperatures of 640 K and 1184 K. The research used an open-end shock tube with a high-pressure driver section and a low-pressure driven section, separated by a diaphragm membrane. The test section, located 3 m downstream of the diaphragm, featured the deposited metal oxide plate for non-intrusive studies. High-speed cameras at 14000 fps and a 200 W LED light source were used to capture the dynamics of resuspension.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Compared to loosely deposited layers, thermophoretic deposition results in higher packing density, effectively forming a cohesive entity. This dense particle layer generates stronger baroclinic vorticity when exposed to a shockwave due to pressure and density variations. When a Richtmyer-Meshkov instability (RMI) is triggered, a disturbance occurs in the layer at the loose particle's location. Some particles resuspend in the flow, overcoming gravity as they move behind the shockwave, causing particle erosion and the formation of microscopic cavities. Internal pressure inside the cavity decreases, leading to layer segregation and resuspension as a lump due to pressure differentials. This is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Formation of cavities in particles deposited via thermophoresis

The relative effect of shock strength (Mach number) on particle resuspension is seen in Figure 2. Stronger shock waves induce particles to resuscitate at a much faster rate because the flow behind the shock wave is moving more quickly, further disintegrating the agitated particles at the interface. As the shockwave's intensity rises, it has been found that the resuscitation process quickens. The graph between the normalised vertical displacement with respect to time for various Mach values is shown in Figure 3. Since there is no shock wave disruption at first, there is no displacement. When the baroclinic vorticity reaches a certain level, the particle lumps split and begin to move vertically before atomizing. This phenomenon manifests earlier for greater Mach values than for lower Mach

numbers. The vertical displacement has nothing to do with the lump's atomization.

Figure 2. Resuspension at varying Mach numbers

Figure 3. Vertical displacement of particle lump

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this experiment have provided valuable insights into the complex dynamics of particle resuspension, particularly in the context of thermophoretic deposition and shock wave amplitudes. It is evident from our findings that the process of particle resuspension is distinctly different from particles that have merely been loosely deposited. One key observation is the sensitivity of particle resuspension to the amplitude of the shock wave. Shock waves play a crucial role in dislodging particles from their thermophoretically deposited state. Higher shock wave amplitudes result in a more effective resuspension process. This sensitivity emphasizes the dynamic nature of the resuspension phenomenon, which responds to external forces. The distinct behaviour of particles that have been thermophoretically deposited can be attributed to the stronger bonding that forms between them during this process. This enhanced bonding leads to a higher packing density, resulting in the formation of particle clusters. When subjected to the shock wave, these clusters are dislodged as a unit, initially creating a lump of particles in suspension. However, what makes this study particularly intriguing is the subsequent atomization of these particle lumps during the resuspension process. Atomization refers to the further breaking down of the particle cluster into smaller individual particles. These smaller particles are liberated from the lump, allowing them to be carried even further and over greater distances by the fluid flow. The atomization process is of significant importance as it enhances the transportability of the particles. Smaller particles exhibit improved aerodynamic properties and are less prone to gravitational settling. Consequently, they can be transported over longer distances in the surrounding environment, potentially impacting air quality, health, and other environmental factors.

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VARIATION OF GROSS ALPHA AND GROSS BETA ACTIVITY CONCENTRATION IN AIR PARTICULATE MATTER AT NAPS NARORA SITE DURING 2012-2022

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INTRODUCTION

Radioactivity is naturally present in the air due to cosmogenic radionuclides (¹⁴C, ⁷Be, and ³H), cosmic radiation, and natural radionuclides present in all rocks and soils (²³⁸U and progenies, ²³²Th and progenies, and ⁴⁰K), and its natural background is increased by anthropogenic sources, such as nuclear/radiological accident, nuclear weapon tests, or the production and application of phosphorus fertilizers [1]. Monitoring of gross alpha and gross beta activity concentration is mandatory around NPP sites for detecting activity peaks associated with radioactivity released to the atmosphere from the facility [2].

Measurement of gross alpha and gross beta activity is usually used as a control indicator of the radioactivity levels in air. The long-term monitoring of gross alpha and beta activity concentrations enables us to study trends and periodic variations and in combination with meteorological parameters, to identify the main meteorological parameters (rainfall, wind speed etc.) influencing the spatial and temporal variability of environmental radioactivity [4].

This paper characterizes the gross alpha and beta activity concentrations and identifies the meteorological factors influencing its temporal distribution at NAPS Narora site. We have used weekly measurements of gross beta activities spanning a Ten year period (2012–2022), with the main purpose of finding variation in gross specific activities and their correlations with meteorological parameters.

METHOD

The study was carried out at Narora Atomic Power Station (NAPS) site (28.1968°N and 78.3814°E) situated in Bulandshahr, India. Air particulate matter(PM) were collected on 50 mm (dia.) Whatman GFA filter mounted at 2.5m height on a high-volume air sampler set at a flow rate of 100-120 lpm on weekly basis. Filter paper was pre post weighed to measure the dust load and divided by total volume of air passed through it to estimate the PM concentration. Long lived beta activity was defined as gross beta activity after four days counting when short lived ²²²Rn progeny decayed into ²¹⁰Pb. Filters were counted on GM tube based gross beta and ZnS (Ag) based gross alpha counter.

$$A_{\alpha\beta} \left(\frac{Bq}{m^3} \right) = \frac{Net\ CPM}{60 \times \epsilon \times V}$$

Where ε: fractional counting efficiency, V: volume of air samples

Month	Gross alpha (mBq/m ³)		Gross beta (mBq/m ³)		PM conc. (µg/m ³)	Temperature (°C)	Relative humidity (%)
	Range	GM	Range	GM			
January	0.34-0.61	0.42	0.04-0.20	0.10	83	13.7	63.2
February	0.30-1.09	0.51	0.05-0.30	0.11	101	16.9	61.7
March	0.31-0.95	0.54	0.08-0.43	0.16	110	22.1	59.2
April	0.31-1.17	0.54	0.04-0.37	0.16	137	27.6	55.6
May	0.30-1.42	0.59	0.06-0.33	0.16	143	31.3	56.2
June	0.30-0.83	0.46	0.06-0.29	0.14	126	32.7	60.2
July	0.30-0.64	0.40	0.06-0.17	0.10	63	30.5	69.2
August	0.33-0.45	0.37	0.03-0.11	0.06	58	29.6	74.4
September	0.30-0.55	0.41	0.03-0.17	0.07	66	28.4	68.3
October	0.35-0.58	0.42	0.03-0.20	0.08	82	24.2	60.8
November	0.41-0.63	0.54	0.07-0.22	0.12	137	19.1	60.3
December	0.36-0.74	0.51	0.08-0.21	0.13	138	14.5	61.1

Table.1 Monthly Geometric mean levels of gross beta, gross alpha and air particulate matter concentration during 2012-2022.

Fig.1 Correlation between monthly geometric mean of gross α , β and air particulate matter. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table.1 presents the range and geometric mean concentration (GM) for gross alpha, gross beta and particulate matter in the weekly samples collected at NAPS Narora site for each month over the sampling years 2012 to 2022. The average gross beta activity of all samples is higher than the corresponding average gross alpha activity. The major source of gross beta activity may be ^{210}Pb , which is a long-lived descendant of gaseous ^{222}Rn . This result can be justified in the atmospheric radioactivity is known to be dominated by the naturally occurring short lived particulate decay products of gaseous radon. However, other secondary sources of radioactivity, such as re-suspended soil particles or anthropogenic activities must be taken into account. Regarding anthropogenic radioactivity, there are several sources such as fertilizers, fossil fuel burning, cement and other metal production (6). Contribution due to NAPS specific released radionuclides is negligible because there is no release of long lived particulate radioactivity in gaseous effluent. The highest values of gross alpha and beta observed during summer season (March to May) and lowest values were observed during monsoon season (June-September). During monsoon season particulate matters gets wash-down to the earth surface resulting lower concentration of gross alpha and gross beta attached to the particulate matter. Fig.-1 shows strong positive correlation between gross beta ($r^2 = 7562$) and gross alpha ($r^2 = 71162$) with PM concentration. Fig.2 shows strong negative correlation between PM and Relative humidity and slight positive correlation between PM and atmospheric temperature excluding monsoon period in which PM gets wash down due to rainfall.

CONCLUSIONS

Higher concentration of gross alpha and beta observed during warm season and lower concentration during monsoon period whereas relative humidity of the atmosphere affects the PM concentration due to dry fallout. Using site specific correlation coefficients for gross alpha and beta the concentrations in surface air can be experimentally predicted from the PM concentrations.

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Fig. 2 Correlation between air particulate matters with temperature and relative humidity.

ASSESSMENT OF CORRELATION BETWEEN ATMOSPHERIC BERYLLIUM-7 CONCENTRATIONS AND TOTAL SUSPENDED PARTICULATE MATTER (TSPM)
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INTRODUCTION

Beryllium-7 (⁷Be) is a cosmic-ray-produced radionuclide. Once formed in the troposphere, it rapidly associates with suspended particles. An activity median aerodynamic diameter (AMAD) between 0.7 and 1.2µm was estimated for these ⁷Be aerosols in the atmosphere (Papastefanou and Ioannidou, 1996). Deposition and scavenging by precipitation is the primary mechanisms for the transport of ⁷Be to the Earth's surface. The mean residence lifetimes of the aerosols were estimated to be 1–2 years for the stratosphere through the tropopause (Rehfeld and Heimann, 1995), 20–35 days for the troposphere, and less than 10 days for the lower atmosphere below precipitation cloud levels. The production rate, deposition flux and atmospheric concentration of ⁷Be are primarily dependent upon latitude, altitude, solar activity and meteorological conditions. ⁷Be has been widely used as a chemical tracer in atmospheric and environmental sciences.

The aim of this study is to investigate the relationship between ⁷Be and Total suspended particulate matter (TSPM). The atmospheric concentrations of ⁷Be and TSPM data were monitored simultaneously at NAPS Narora site during 2018-2021. The seasonal variations of the ⁷Be and the TSPM were compared to study the ⁷Be concentrations and their distribution with respect to the TSPM.

METHODS

The study was carried out at Narora Atomic Power Station (NAPS) site (28.1968°N and 78.3814°E) situated in Bulandshahr, India. The prevailing wind direction in the region is northwesterly and southeasterly. Air samples were collected once a week on a 50 mm (diameter) glass-fiber filter mounted at 2.5m height using a high-volume air sampler set to a flow rate of 100-120 LPM to collect total suspended particulates. The weekly samples were weighed to estimate TSPM in the atmosphere (µg/m³). Filters (4–5 weekly samples) were combined as a monthly sample that was counted with P-type HPGe detector with 50% RE connected to a multi-channel analyzer. The activity of ⁷Be was determined by detecting the emission of gamma rays at 477.59 keV. The spectra were analyzed with Inter winner software. The ⁷Be activity in air (mBq/m³) was decay-corrected to the mid-point of sample collection.

The activity concentration of ⁷Be (Bq/g) in the particulate matter (A_{TSPM}) determined using the following equation based on the assumption that almost all ⁷Be is attached to TSPM in the atmosphere.

$$A_{TSPM} \left(\frac{Bq}{g} \right) = \frac{C_{Be-7}}{TSPM} \times 1000$$

where C_{Be-7}: Atmospheric concentration of ⁷Be (mBq/m³) and TSPM (µg/m³).

Fig.1: Monthly variations and ⁷Be and TSPM in air 2018 to 2021

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Seasonal variation of ⁷Be with the TSPM concentration

During the monitoring period, changes in the monthly variation of ⁷Be and TSPM concentration are represented in Fig.1. The variations of ⁷Be in the atmosphere showed a cyclic pattern similar to those of the TSPM concentrations. Lowest concentrations of TSPM and ⁷Be were simultaneously observed during the Monsoon (Jun. –Sep.), and highest concentrations of were found in the summer (Mar-May). Table-1 shows the variation of ⁷Be concentration in air samples on a seasonal basis during the study period 2018-2021. The values ranged 0.79mBq/m³ in July month to 4.49mBq/m³in April during year 2020. The concentration of ⁷Be in air at a NPP site, Kaiga, India is reported in the range of 1.0 – 5.7 mBq/m³ (James et al., 2004) and is comparable with current study. An unusually high ⁷Be concentration occurring in the (Mar.–Apr.) is referred to as the spring peak (Chao et al., 2012). Similar observations are reported for the study carried out at Belgrade (Lazarevi'c et al.,2009), where ⁷Be activity concentrations in surface air samples, ranged from 1.9 to 10.2 mBq/m³, with increase during summer season. During this period, stratospheric air intruding into the troposphere may enhance the ⁷Be concentration in the air (J.H. Chao, 2013).

Correlating ⁷Be with the PM concentration

⁷Be concentrations (C_{Be-7}) were linearly related to the respective TSPM ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) (Fig.2).

$$C_{Be-7} \left(\frac{\text{Bq}}{\text{m}^3} \right) = 0.0185 \times TSPM \left(\frac{\mu\text{g}}{\text{m}^3} \right) + 0.2696$$

Therefore, the average A_{TSPM} is 18.5 (Bq/g). The strong positive correlation ($r^2 = 0.7214$) between the ⁷Be and TSPM concentrations implies that the ⁷Be concentration can be predicted from the TSPM concentration in the atmosphere. However, the predicted C_{Be-7} is either slightly overestimated or underestimated depending on the seasonal variation of TSPM.

CONCLUSIONS

In the current study, the TSPM concentration was used to explain the seasonal variations of the ⁷Be concentration in the air. Seasonal monitoring results revealed that the ⁷Be concentrations in surface air were influenced by both the seasonal monsoons and the accompanying PM concentrations. The northwesterly wind during summer and winter season, not only carried higher TSPM air masses, but was also associated with higher ⁷Be concentrations than those brought by the southeasterly wind during monsoon season. The ⁷Be concentrations in surface air can be experimentally predicted from the TSPM concentrations.

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FILTRATION CHARACTERISTICS OF SINTERED POROUS FILTERS OF B₄C NEUTRON POISON SUB-ASSEMBLES OF FBTR

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Keywords: STATIC HEAD, ABSOLUTE RATING, FEED, FILTRATE, PSL PARTICLES, MASTERSIZER.

INTRODUCTION

The sintered porous filters (SS316L) are used as final trap filters of B₄C neutron poison pin assemblies in FBTR. It is used to vent the helium generated by (n,α) interaction with B₄C and allow sodium coolant flow by retaining the fragments of B₄C cracked pellets without leaching into the primary sodium circuit. Sintered porous filters are generally not used in precisely size-selective separation (Heikkinen and Harley, 1999). Literature on filtration characteristics concerning the relation of maximum particle size penetrated with max pore size is scarce. For the given pore size of the filter, its thickness and the pressure drop (face velocity) affect the maximum particle size that penetrates. This abstract presents the methodology and results of testing the sintered porous filters (3 Nos – F1, F8, and F13) supplied by NFC, Hyderabad. The maximum particle size that penetrates through the filter, called absolute rating (WER5300), is determined in this test. The qualified filters are being used in poison sub-assemblies of FBTR’s 40 MWt core.

METHODS

The diameter and thickness of the filters are 23 and 3 mm, respectively. It is specified to the particles of > 14 μm size. Test conditions defined are use of water at 20°C, with a flow velocity of 1 lit/h-cm² across the plane area at a pressure drop of 18±2 mbar per mm thickness (PFBR/31150/SP/1015). The schematic of the test set-up is shown in Fig. 1. The SS filter is fixed inside a leak-tight holder. A needle valve is used to control the tested liquid flow across the filter. PSL particles (Make: M/S Polysciences Inc. & M/S Thermo Scientific, USA) of 1% solid suspensions are used to test by dispersing them in Type-II Millipore water. A static water column head of 553 mm above the filter head provides a pressure drop of 54 mbar across the filter, enabling a specified water flow velocity of 1 lit/h-cm². Tested particle sizes are 7, 9, 14.9, and 20 μm as polydisperse form by mixing the sizes in 2.4 L of water.

Testing is done by maintaining a 553 to 570 mm feed water column in the upstream. The volume of the water collected downstream with time (filtrate) is recorded during the 40 min test period, and the flow velocity is measured with time. The first filtrate sample of 250 ml is used to analyze for VSD and mass filtration efficiency (MFE). Volume Size Distribution (VSD) of particles suspended in the feed and filtrate liquids is measured using MASTERSIZER (M/S Malvern, UK) (Dupont et al., 1999; Yang et al., 2014). The suspended particles in the feed and filtrate of each 50 ml are trapped inside the Whatman syringe filters (GF/C with pore size 1.2 μm) by injecting the liquid through it. Filters are dried and analysed for total suspended particle mass in feed and filtrate using a microbalance (M/S Sartorius, with MDL of 2 μg). MFE is determined using Eq-1. Particle number concentration in the feed is known based on the volume of PSL liquid added to the known quantity of water. The number concentration of the particles in the filtrate samples is determined using the values of MFE and VSD of filtrate suspensions. Number filtration efficiency (NFE) is determined using Eq-2. The feed and filtrate liquids are analyzed by optical microscope (ZEISS-AXIO OBSERVER A1) to confirm the size of particles that penetrated to downstream.

$$MFE = \frac{(Feedparticlemass - Filtrateparticlemass) * 100}{Feedparticlemass} \quad NFE = \frac{(FeedparticleNoconc - FiltrateparticleNo. Conc) * 100}{FeedparticleNo. Conc}$$

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Prior to the tests with particles, the flow velocity for the selected static head is verified by using particle-free water passing across the filters. The flow velocity is primarily constant with time using particle free liquid. The measured average velocity is 0.89 ± 0.08 , lt/hr-cm^2 among the three filters (Ref No: F13, F8, and F1), which is slightly less than specified value of 1 lt/hr-cm^2 . The feed having polydisperse particle suspension with three different total concentrations 7.7×10^3 (Low), 2.9×10^4 (medium), and 6.1×10^4 (high) $\#/ml$, are prepared by adding the particles of sizes 7, 14.9, and 20 μm in different volumes. The flow velocity reduces with time as shown in Fig. 2 (given for filter F13 with different concentrations). As time increases, the particles gradually block the pores of the filters and cause resistance to the flow. The possible difference in pore structure among the filters and range of pressure head caused slight differences in the flow characteristics. The flow velocity is reduced to $0.25 \pm 0.07 \text{ lt/h-cm}^2$ within 40 minutes, with the tested concentration range. The size of the particles in the feed ranges from 2 to 35 μm with a median of 12 μm for high concentration and 5 to 30 μm with the same median of 12.0 μm for medium concentration. The filters get blocked faster during high particle concentrations, and further penetration reduces with time. So, the filtrate suspensions get diluted with time, resulting in the concentration below the detectable limit (the 2 μm peak represents the background), as shown in Fig. 3(a). With medium concentration, the VSD of particles in filtrate gets shifted to the lower particle size with a median of $6.2 \pm 1.8 \mu\text{m}$ (averaged over the distributions of three filters) due to filtration of large particles, as shown in Fig. 3(b). MFE of $85\% \pm 3\%$ is observed for filter F13 tested with high concentration. An average MFE of $79 \pm 6\%$ is observed for the three filters, F13, F1, and F8, tested with medium concentration. The number size distribution of the particles in the feed and filtrate samples is determined using the respective VSDs and MFE of $79 \pm 6\%$ during the test with medium concentration, as shown in Fig. 3(c). At 79% of MFE, the average NFE of the three filters is around $99.2 \pm 0.7\%$ for the particles $> 14 \mu\text{m}$ and $99.7 \pm 0.3\%$ for the particles $> 20 \mu\text{m}$. The samples of feed and filtrate during the testing of F13 are analyzed by optical microscope to confirm the size of particles penetrated, as shown in Fig. 4. It shows the relative abundance of the three-sized particles in both liquids. While, 7 μm particles are present in the filtrate in good number, 14.9 μm particles presence is statistically insignificant, and 20 μm particles are entirely absent.

Fig. 4. Images of suspended polydisperse particles in feed and filtrate (F13, medium conc.) (Yellow).

CONCLUSIONS

The flow velocity decreases with time to $0.25 \pm 0.03 \text{ lt/h-cm}^2$ in 40 min with particle suspensions. However, the filters are not blocked entirely with tested concentrations, ensuring the coolant flow to neutron poison subassemblies. The estimated NFE is around $99.2 \pm 0.7\%$ and $99.7 \pm 0.3\%$ for particles $> 14 \mu\text{m}$ and $> 20 \mu\text{m}$ respectively, during the tests with polydispersed aerosols of initial concentration of $2.9 \times 10^4 / \text{ml}$. The optical microscopic images of suspended particles confirm that the largest particle size penetrated could be between 9 to 14.9 μm and hence met the intent specification of retaining $> 14 \mu\text{m}$ particles. Correspondingly, the calculated max pore size may be between 22.5 and 37.5 μm if the filters are sintered with spherical particles (ISO 4003:1977).

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DETERMINATION OF GROSS α AND GROSS β ACTIVITIES IN PM₁₀ AND PM_{2.5} SIZE FRACTIONS OF AIR PARTICULATE SAMPLES AROUND KUDANKULAM NUCLEAR SITE
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Keywords: GROSS ALPHA, GROSS BETA, COSMOGENIC, RADON.

INTRODUCTION

Air monitoring is carried out around nuclear power plants continuously round the year to keep a watch on the atmospheric radionuclides. Gross alpha and gross beta activities are important in understanding the trends of atmospheric radioactivity and for their variation in time. Radioactivity arises from natural radioactive decay of progenies, cosmogenic production in atmosphere, past nuclear weapons tests and nuclear accidents. This paper presents the activity concentrations of gross alpha and gross beta in different size fractions of particulate matter collected around Kudankulam nuclear site. Air particulate samples were collected monthly using PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} air samplers during the study period 2019-22 around Kudankulam nuclear site. Radioactivity is determined in both the filter papers using alpha and beta counting system. The geometric mean of gross alpha and gross beta activities in PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} were 0.25, 1.69 & 0.11, 0.33 mBq/m³ respectively. The data obtained in this study provide a baseline for evaluating possible future changes and a benchmark around Kudankulam nuclear facilities.

METHODS

The systematic measurement of gross α , β activities in air enables us to study periodic variations in air activity apart from allowing to detect any peaks due to any extreme events and to understand factors affecting environmental radioactivity levels. The present study has been conducted for four consecutive years (2019 to 2022) to determine gross α , β in particulate matters around Kudankulam nuclear site. Typical air samplers use glassfibre filter papers to collect particulate matter from air and then using an α , β counter to measure α , β activity on the filter. Air particulate samples were collected for 24 hours using a Respirable dust sampler with a glass fiber filter paper of area 381 sq.cm (22 cm x 17 cm) for PM₁₀ and Teflon filter paper of 30 mm diameter for PM_{2.5}. The samples were collected twice every month, using an oil free vacuum pump at a flow rate of 1000 & 16 LPM for PM₁₀ & PM_{2.5} respectively. The air sampler was kept approximately 6 m above the ground at 4 different locations viz, Kudankulam Nuclear Power Plant (KKNPP) 1 & 2, KKNPP 3 & 4, KKNPP 5 & 6 and AnuVijay Township, a control site. After the end of the sampling period, the filter papers were removed and kept for one month for the short-lived radioisotopes and progenies to decay. Then the filter papers were counted for α activity in ZnS (TI) scintillation counter and for β activity in plastic scintillation counters. Efficiency factors for gross α , β were determined by counting the samples with known amounts of activities prepared in the same geometry as the unknown samples. The calibration of the counting systems for measuring gross α , β activities were performed using ²⁴¹Am and ⁴⁰K standard sources respectively. Self-absorption is not considered in the case of air particulate filters because of the impracticality of determining the penetration depth of the deposit into the filter.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 presents gross α , β activities with particulate matters PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} in different sampling locations around Kudankulam Nuclear site. The gross α activity ranged between 0.02-1.61 mBq/m³ and the gross β activity was in the range of 0.10-3.00 mBq/m³. The distribution trend of gross α , β activities in the PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} particulate matter samples for the study period is shown in **Figure 1**. The gross β activities of almost all the samples were always higher than the gross α activity recorded. The major source of gross β activity is ²¹⁰Pb/²¹⁰Po, which is a long-lived descendant of gaseous ²²²Rn. The other secondary sources like re-suspended soil particles and anthropogenic activity due to sources such as fertilizers, fossil fuel burning, cement and other metal production also have contribution to the activities observed (Semkov et al, 2004). The gross activities of both α , β are observed to be higher during the winter season as the particulate concentrations are maximum during winter due to stable weather conditions resulting from inversion. The meteorological conditions and weather influencing the gross α , β

activities in the atmosphere are temperature, pressure, humidity, and wind direction etc. Table 2 gives the overall statistics of gross α , β activity in particulate matter of this study.

Table 1. Gross α , β activities in particulate matter around Kudankulam Nuclear Site (2019-2022)

Location	Particle Size	Radionuclide	Activity Range (mBq/m ³)	GM (mBq/m ³)	GSD
KK 1 & 2 (Working units)	PM ₁₀	Gross Alpha	0.020 – 1.614	0.319	4.141
		Gross Beta	1.086 - 2.994	1.559	1.378
	PM _{2.5}	Gross Alpha	0.020 - 0.625	0.109	4.263
		Gross Beta	0.100 - 1.137	0.314	3.321
KK 3 & 4 (Construction units)	PM ₁₀	Gross Alpha	0.102 - 0.254	0.160	1.306
		Gross Beta	1.347 - 2.877	1.988	1.334
	PM _{2.5}	Gross Alpha	0.020 - 0.243	0.092	2.757
		Gross Beta	0.100 - 2.017	0.683	2.884
KK 5 & 6 (Construction units)	PM ₁₀	Gross Alpha	0.049 - 0.497	0.199	2.029
		Gross Beta	0.771 - 2.201	1.378	1.693
	PM _{2.5}	Gross Alpha	0.020 - 0.389	0.126	2.882
		Gross Beta	0.100 - 0.769	0.214	2.260
Township (Control Site)	PM ₁₀	Gross Alpha	0.098 - 0.544	0.285	1.675
		Gross Beta	1.369 - 2.803	2.112	1.266
	PM _{2.5}	Gross Alpha	0.020 - 0.475	0.132	2.555
		Gross Beta	0.100 - 0.923	0.241	2.339

Table 2. Statistics of Gross α , β activities in particulate matter

Statistic	PM ₁₀		PM _{2.5}	
	Gross Alpha (mBq/m ³)	Gross Beta (mBq/m ³)	Gross Alpha (mBq/m ³)	Gross Beta (mBq/m ³)
Min	0.024	0.771	0.020	0.100
Max	1.614	2.994	0.625	2.017
GM	0.249	1.693	0.113	0.325
GSD	2.374	1.398	3.241	2.821

Figure 1 Gross α , β trends in particulate matter

CONCLUSIONS

Gross α , β activity in airborne particulate matter sizes have been determined for four consecutive years (2019–2022) around Kudankulam nuclear site. Nuclear power plants do not emit any particulates or gases by virtue of their operation. The results of the study indicate that there is no significant difference in gross α , β activities over the years, but there are seasonal variations due to meteorological factors and weather. The observed air activities are very low and are due to natural variation in the environmental background radiation levels and comparable to the literature values published. The observed gross α , β activities are not plant related. The monthly cumulative gamma spectrometric measurements of the air particulate samples do not show any radionuclide of reactor origin.

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VARIATION OF GROSS ALPHA AND GROSS BETA ACTIVITY CONCENTRATION IN AIR PARTICULATE MATTER AT NAPS NARORA SITE DURING 2012-2022

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INTRODUCTION

Radioactivity is naturally present in the air due to cosmogenic radionuclides (¹⁴C, ⁷Be, and ³H), cosmic radiation, and natural radionuclides present in all rocks and soils (²³⁸U and progenies, ²³²Th and progenies, and ⁴⁰K), and its natural background is increased by anthropogenic sources, such as nuclear/radiological accident, nuclear weapon tests, or the production and application of phosphorus fertilizers (Bossew, P 2017). Monitoring of gross alpha and gross beta activity concentration is mandatory around NPP sites for detecting activity peaks associated with radioactivity released to the atmosphere (EPA 2020). Sampling airborne radioactivity is an important tool to fulfil different objectives. Among them, for environmental monitoring, to control atmospheric environmental releases and ensure the environment and public health; for process quality assurance and control in and around nuclear and radioactive facilities; and for emergency preparedness and response, to provide a basis for appropriate actions in case of accident or terrorist attack (Papastefanou, 2008). Measurement of gross alpha and gross beta activity is usually used as a control indicator of the radioactivity levels in air. The long-term monitoring of gross alpha and beta activity concentrations enables us to study trends and periodic variations and in combination with meteorological parameters, to identify the main meteorological parameters (rainfall, wind speed etc.) influencing the spatial and temporal variability of environmental radioactivity (Tositti, L).

This paper characterizes the gross alpha and beta activity concentrations and identifies the meteorological factors influencing its temporal distribution at NAPS Narora site. We have used weekly measurements of gross beta activities spanning last ten year period (2012–2022), with the main purpose of finding variation in gross specific activities and their correlations with air particulate matter (TSPM) concentration.

METHOD

The study was carried out at Narora Atomic Power Station (NAPS) site (28.1968°N and 78.3814°E) situated in Bulandshahr, India. Air particulate matter were collected on 50 mm (dia.) Whatman GFA filter mounted at 2.5m height on a high-volume air sampler set at a flow rate of 100-120 lpm on weekly basis. Long lived beta activity was defined as gross beta activity after four days counting when short lived ²²²Rn progeny decayed into ²¹⁰Pb. Filters were counted on GM tube based gross beta and ZnS (Ag) based gross alpha counter.

$$A_{\alpha \text{ or } \beta} \left(\frac{\text{Bq}}{\text{m}^3} \right) = \frac{\text{Net CPM}}{60 \times \epsilon \times V}$$

Where ϵ : fractional counting efficiency, V: volume of air samples

Fig.1 Correlation between monthly geometric mean of gross α , β and air particulate matter (TSPM).

Table.1 Monthly Geometric mean levels of gross beta, gross alpha and air particulate matter concentration during 2012-2022.

Month	Gross beta (mBq/m³)	Gross alpha (mBq/m³)	TSPM
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	Range	GM	Range	GM	conc. ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)
January	0.34-0.61	0.42	0.04-0.20	0.10	83
February	0.30-1.09	0.51	0.05-0.30	0.11	101
March	0.31-0.95	0.54	0.08-0.43	0.16	110
April	0.31-1.17	0.54	0.04-0.37	0.16	137
May	0.30-1.42	0.59	0.06-0.33	0.16	143
June	0.30-0.83	0.46	0.06-0.29	0.14	126
July	0.30-0.64	0.40	0.06-0.17	0.10	63
August	0.33-0.45	0.37	0.03-0.11	0.06	58
September	0.30-0.55	0.41	0.03-0.17	0.07	66
October	0.35-0.58	0.42	0.03-0.20	0.08	82
November	0.41-0.63	0.54	0.07-0.22	0.12	137
December	0.36-0.74	0.51	0.08-0.21	0.13	138

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table.1 presents the range and geometric mean concentration (GM) for gross alpha, gross beta and particulate matter in the weekly samples collected at NAPS Narora site for each month over the sampling years 2012 to 2022. The average gross beta activity of all samples is higher than the corresponding average gross alpha activity. The major source of gross beta activity may be due to ^{210}Pb , which is a long-lived descendant of gaseous ^{222}Rn . This result can be justified in the atmospheric radioactivity is known to be dominated by the naturally occurring short lived particulate decay products of gaseous radon. However, other secondary sources of radioactivity, such as re-suspended soil particles or anthropogenic activities must be taken into account. Regarding anthropogenic radioactivity, there are several sources such as fertilizers, fossil fuel burning, cement and other metal production (C. DUENAS, 2004). Contribution due to NAPS specific released radionuclides is negligible because there is no release of long lived particulate radioactivity in gaseous effluent during the study period. The highest values of gross alpha and beta observed during summer season (March to May) and lowest values were observed during monsoon season (June-September). During monsoon season particulate matters gets wash-down to the earth surface resulting lower concentration of gross alpha and gross beta attached to the particulate matter. Fig.-1 shows strong positive correlation between gross beta ($r^2 = 7562$) and gross alpha ($r^2 = 71162$) with PM concentration may be due high dust load results into increased level of natural radioactivity in air.

CONCLUSIONS

Higher concentration of gross alpha and beta observed during warm season and lower concentration during monsoon period. Using site specific correlation coefficients, gross alpha and beta activity in surface air can be experimentally predicted from the particulate matter concentrations.

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⁷Be ACTIVITY IN AIR AND MEAN RESIDENCE TIME AT KAIGA SITE
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Keywords: ⁷Be, Air, Residence time, Kaiga

INTRODUCTION

The radionuclides, of both natural and anthropogenic origin, found in the atmosphere serve as aerosol-borne tracers to study atmospheric transport processes. Among these, ⁷Be is a naturally occurring radionuclide of cosmogenic origin with a radiological half-life of 53 days and a substantial production rate. It forms through spallation processes of light atmospheric nuclei, such as nitrogen (Z = 7) and oxygen (Z = 8) (C Papastefanou, 2004). Soon after its formation, ⁷Be rapidly associates with submicron-sized aerosol particles and therefore, acts as aerosol-borne tracers. It enters into the troposphere due to the vertical exchange of material from the stratosphere and reaches the Earth's surface through both dry and wet depositional events. With the advantage of the short half-life and relatively easy determination, ⁷Be has been widely used as a tracer in atmospheric science. It serves as a potential tool to study environmental processes such as atmospheric circulation, aerosol transit, deposition or removal process, and residence time in the troposphere. Aerosol residence time in the atmosphere is the period in which the particle remains in the atmosphere, between the injection and removal. The residence time depends upon various atmospheric factors such as wet deposition, diffusion etc. (Rangarajan and Eapen, 1990). In the present study, the ground-level air concentration of ⁷Be is estimated during the period 2015-19 at Kaiga and the residence time of ⁷Be was determined using its activity concentration in air.

METHODS

Air particulate samples were collected on glass fibre filter paper using a high-volume air sampler at a flow rate of 50 LPM on a weekly basis. The collected samples were placed in a disc geometry and analysed using a coaxial p-type HPGe detector (50% R.E.) to determine ⁷Be activity. The 477 keV gamma peak of ⁷Be was utilized for activity calculation. Decay correction was applied for the sample collection and counting for ⁷Be activity (J.P. James *et al.*, 2004). The residence time, t_r in the troposphere is calculated using the following equation (Shapiro and Judith, 1976).

$$a_r = \frac{P_r}{H} (1 - e^{-\lambda t_r}) \quad \text{----- (1)}$$

Where a_r is observed mean ⁷Be activity in air Bq.m⁻³, P_r is the production rate of ⁷Be (atoms.cm⁻².s⁻¹), H is the height of tropopause (m), λ is the decay constant d⁻¹ and t_r is the residence time in d. The value of P_r is taken as 2.7×10^{-2} (atoms.cm⁻².s⁻¹), H is 16.5 km (R Ramanadham *et al.*, 1972) and λ for ⁷Be is 1.31×10^{-2} d⁻¹.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The monthly average ground-level air concentration for ⁷Be in the Kaiga region from 2015-19 is presented in Table 1. The monthly mean values of ⁷Be value range from 0.98 to 8.97 mBq.m⁻³. The lowest value was recorded in July (monsoon season), while the highest value was observed in March (summer season). Table 1 clearly illustrates the seasonal variation in ⁷Be concentrations. The variation is notably influenced by precipitation, which contributes to increase wet deposition. This pattern is visually depicted in Figure 1. Similar cyclic and seasonal patterns were observed earlier (J.P. James *et al.*, 2004 and Ceballos *et al.*, 2016). During summer, the elevated ⁷Be-specific activities can be attributed to increased exchange between the stratosphere and troposphere through the tropopause, along with atmospheric level displacement caused by the summer season. Seasonal variation is also associated with the vertical movement of aerosols within the troposphere through convection driven by atmospheric instability and temperature fluctuations (Ceballos *et al.*, 2016). As the monsoon arrives, radionuclides in the air are scavenged to the ground by rain, leading to a shift from dry to wet deposition. Given the annual rainfall of approximately 3500 mm in the Kaiga region, ⁷Be activity in air is reduced during June, July, and August compared to the non-monsoon period.

The residence time of ^7Be at the Kaiga site varies from 4.7 to 60.6 days, with an average of 23.1 days, as indicated in Table 1. Shorter Residence times are associated with rain fall events, such as during the monsoon, whereas longer residence times are influenced by gravitational dry deposition and vertical air transport parameters. Table 1 and Figure 1 also demonstrate that a higher number of rainy days and increased precipitation lead to a decrease in the residence time of ^7Be in the air. Mean residence time at Kaiga site is comparable with study by Shario and Forbes-Resha reported as 35.4 days (Shapiro and Judith, 1976) and also Rangarajan and Eapen reported a range of 20-30 days for tropospheric residence time (Rangarajan and Eapen, 1990). The tropospheric residence time for fission product are in accord with present study (Shapiro and Judith, 1976).

Table 1. ^7Be surface air activity, rainfall and residence time at Kaiga

Month	^7Be (mBq.m ⁻³)	RF (mm)	Rainy day	Residence time (d)
Jan	3.36	7.48	1	17.6
Feb	4.71	0.00	0	25.9
Mar	8.97	4.12	1	60.6
Apr	4.47	7.96	1	24.3
May	4.86	58.13	5	26.9
Jun	2.97	908.54	21	15.3
Jul	0.98	1259.08	25	4.7
Aug	1.30	921.98	24	6.3
Sep	2.91	419.42	15	14.9
Oct	5.56	211.54	9	31.7
Nov	4.88	10.68	1	27.0
Dec	4.01	4.64	1	21.5

Figure 1. Seasonal variation of ^7Be in air at Kaiga

CONCLUSIONS

The monthly mean levels of ^7Be activity in ground-level air were determined at Kaiga during 2015-2019. Throughout the study timeframe, distinct seasonal fluctuations were observed in the ^7Be activity. Specifically, elevated values were noted in summer, while reduced values were recorded during the monsoon phase. The mean residence time for ^7Be at the Kaiga site was calculated to be 23.1 days.

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STUDIES ON THE ACTIVITY RATIO OF ^{210}Po AND ^{210}Pb FROM GROSS ALPHA AND GROSS BETA ACTIVITY IN AIR PARTICULATE MATTER AT KAIGA, KARNATAKA

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Keywords: Gross alpha, Gross beta, KGS, PHWR

INTRODUCTION

A study has been carried out on weekly cumulative air filter samples at ESL, Kaiga Township collected for measurement of gross alpha and gross beta activity levels. Gross α and β activity estimation in the air particulate matter is generally carried out for screening purposes. In this paper, the gross alpha/beta activity is used as a proxy for the estimation of ^{210}Po and ^{210}Pb concentration in the particulate matter at Kaiga. These natural radionuclides can be considered as tracers, as well as chronometers of air mass circulation. Po/ Pb ratio is a relevant clue to attribute an increase of atmospheric radioactivity to an extreme natural event [Terray,2020].

METHODS

Weekly cumulative air particulate matter samples were collected in glass fibre filter paper using Hind Hivac make vacuum pump for a sampling duration of 8 hours per day at a suction rate of $3 \text{ m}^3.\text{hr}^{-1}$. The filter paper is subjected to gross alpha and beta activity counting using ZnS scintillation-based alpha probe and plastic scintillator-based low background beta counter respectively. Terray et.al carried out a study on joint gross alpha/beta measurement and ^{210}Pb - ^{210}Po specific determination in France. The correlation equation generated graphically with respect to the observed data of gross alpha activity versus ^{210}Po and Gross beta activity versus ^{210}Pb is given in Equations 1 and 2 below.

$$\frac{\alpha}{^{210}\text{Po}} = 0.85 \text{-----} (1)$$

$$\beta = 1.27 \times ^{210}\text{Pb} + 0.05 \text{-----} (2)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results of activity of gross α (A_α) and gross β (A_β) for the last 10 years carried out at Kaiga for each calendar year are segregated into four quarters and geometric mean value for each quarter is given in the Table 1. This study shows heterogeneity in activity levels in the different quarters of the year. The average ratio of the A_α/A_β estimated in this study is 0.06. Marina Saez et al reported an average ratio of 0.097 for A_α/A_β in Spain [Marina Saeuz, 2018].

The gross α and β activity in air particulate matter for the year 2018 is presented in Table 2. Year 2018 is considered as the representative year as it falls in the mid-year of the study period. The lowest activity is observed during June to September and is attributable to the predominance of the south west monsoon in the Western Ghat region of India. During the year 2018, the gross alpha activity concentration at Kaiga ranged from $20\text{-}75 \mu\text{Bq.m}^{-3}$ with a geometric mean of 40 and gross beta activity concentration ranged from $25\text{-}1470 \mu\text{Bq.m}^{-3}$ with a geometric mean of 540. Anand et. al carried out measurements of ^{210}Po and ^{210}Pb concentration in surface air at Bombay and reported an overall error of 30% in their data. It may be noted that the gross α and β activity estimated at this site is comparable to the values reported by Terray et al. Hence Correlation equation 1 and 2 above is used for the ^{210}Po and ^{210}Pb activity estimation with the assumption that the variation, if any, may fall within the tolerance of the measurement error. The corresponding geometric mean concentration of ^{210}Po and ^{210}Pb concentration estimated using equations 1 & 2 above is 46 and $378 \mu\text{Bq.m}^{-3}$ respectively. The ratio of $^{210}\text{Po}/^{210}\text{Pb}$ is estimated by taking the mean ratio of activity and the result obtained is 0.12. Anand et al reported a value of 0.12 ± 0.08 for a study conducted in Bombay on the ratio of $^{210}\text{Po}/^{210}\text{Pb}$ in aerosols. The ratio of $^{210}\text{Po}/^{210}\text{Pb}$ estimated from the geometric mean of previous 10-year data at Kaiga is 0.11.

Table 1. Quarterly variation of gross α and β activity in air

Year	Q1 (Jan-March)		Q2 (April-June)		Q3 (July-Sept)		Q4 (Oct-Dec)		Annual	
	Geometric mean gross activity concentration (mBq.m ⁻³)									
	α	β	α	β	α	β	α	β	α	β
2013	0.04 0	1.400	0.030	0.660	0.03 0	0.640	0.030	0.680	0.03 0	0.770
2014	0.03 5	0.770	0.030	0.580	0.05 4	0.630	0.040	0.670	0.04 0	0.658
2015	0.03 0	0.880	0.014	0.600	0.01 0	0.200	0.010	0.300	0.01 5	0.403
2016	0.02 0	0.200	0.010	0.260	0.01 0	0.310	0.040	0.970	0.02 0	0.356
2017	0.04 0	0.807	0.014	0.430	0.01 0	0.376	0.029	0.767	0.02 0	0.560
2018	0.06 1	1.020	0.027	0.410	0.01 2	0.028	0.060	0.650	0.03 0	0.536
2019	0.03 8	0.580	0.033	0.511	0.03 3	0.520	0.040	0.604	0.03 5	0.561
2020	0.05 0	0.710	0.030	0.445	0.01 9	0.240	0.060	0.660	0.03 7	0.470
2021	0.07 9	0.600	0.040	0.360	0.02 0	0.660	0.030	0.320	0.04 0	0.460
2022	0.03 4	0.483	0.037	0.287	0.02 8	0.297	0.02	0.620	0.02 9	0.400
G.M	0.04 0	0.671	0.024	0.436	0.01 9	0.303	0.034	0.591	0.02 8	0.504
A _{α} /A _{β}	0.060		0.056		0.063		0.057		0.056	

Table 2. Monthly variation of gross α and β activity in the surface air during the year 2018

Month	Geometric mean activity concentration (mBq.m ⁻³)						
	Gross α		Gross β		²¹⁰ Pb	²¹⁰ Po	Rain Fall (mm)
	GM	GSD	GM	GSD			
January	0.075	1.18	1.47	1.13	0.850	0.088	0
February	0.057	0.064	1.32	1.11	0.835	0.067	0
March	0.047	1.32	0.69	1.45	1.102	0.055	3
April	0.048	1.21	0.59	1.08	0.811	0.056	18
May	0.036	1.58	0.44	1.387	1.053	0.042	60
June	0.021	1.09	0.25	1.23	0.929	0.025	1108
July	0.020	1	0.309	1.367	1.037	0.024	1465
August	0.020	1	0.259	1.34	1.016	0.024	1023
September	0.023	1.159	0.289	1.56	1.189	0.027	155
October	0.054	1.83	0.568	1.626	1.241	0.064	78
November	0.071	2.42	0.74	1.46	1.110	0.084	0
December	0.048	1.5	0.71	1.44	1.094	0.056	0
GM	0.04		0.54		0.378	0.046	

CONCLUSIONS

Ratio of gross alpha/beta activity is measured at Kaiga. The ratio of ²¹⁰Po/²¹⁰Pb activity is estimated in air particulate samples for the period 2013 to 2022. The indirect estimation of the ²¹⁰Po/²¹⁰Pb activity ratio obtained in the particulate matter at Kaiga site is 0.11.

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USE OF GEOGRAPHIC INFORMATION SYSTEM (GIS) FOR VISUALISATION OF PROBABILISTIC MODELS OF ATMOSPHERIC DISPERSION OF RADIOACTIVE PLUMES

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Keywords: Geographic Information System (GIS), Gaussian Dispersion, Plume, Data Science, gdal (geospatial data-abstraction library)

INTRODUCTION

Geographic Information System (GIS) is an extremely fast evolving field which is technological unification of geography, information and data-science. It has touched our life in every aspect through weather prediction, navigation, resource location and real-time information propagation for enhanced and informative decision-making process with confidence. In field of nuclear energy, it is now being extensively used for overlaying and visualisation of the complex and consequential atmospheric dispersion models on to a GIS platform. The visualisation through a GIS changes the entire perspective of decision making taking into account the area, population and land-cover affected. At BARC we have implemented an enterprises level of e-mapping portal for data visualisation for effective use of visualisation of numerical datasets into easily-understandable format.

Gaussian Plume Model (GPM) is one of the oldest and fairly accurate models for mathematical prediction of atmospheric dispersion based on long-term/short-term meteorological parameters like wind-speed, wind-direction, and atmospheric stability (D. B. Turner, 1994). GPM based dispersion of radionuclides consequent to their normal and accidental release from a nuclear power plant (NPP) is one of the oldest and simplest models widely used in emergency scenarios.

The generalised approximation of concentration, χ , in case of atmospheric dispersion from a point source at height H (along with ground-shine) can be given as (James E. Martin, 2013):

$$\chi(x, y, z) \left[\frac{Bq}{m^3} \right] = \frac{Q}{2\pi\sigma_y\sigma_z} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-y^2}{2\sigma_y^2}\right) \left\{ \exp\frac{-(z-H)^2}{2\sigma_z^2} + \exp\frac{-(z+H)^2}{2\sigma_z^2} \right\}$$

where x, y and z are the downwind, crosswind and height of the plume centreline coefficients in 3D, and σ denotes respective standard deviations.

METHODS

Once the dispersion models are run the resultant cartesian coordinates can be used to overlay the model on a GIS platform, by conversion in geodetic-ellipsoidal coordinates (latitude and longitude), which includes all the relevant layers required for efficient mapping and decision making. The layers consist of administrative boundaries, population, LULC (land-use land-cover), waterbodies (ponds, canals, lakes, rivers, seas etc.), rail, road and other useful databases. These layers could be selectively shown or kept hidden. The relationship between Earth-centred-earth-fixed (ECEF) Cartesian coordinates (x,y,z) and the geodetic coordinates (ϕ, λ, h) of a point are given by:

$$x = (N+h) \cos \phi \cos \lambda; y = (N+h) \cos \phi \sin \lambda; z = \left(\frac{b^2}{a^2} (N+h)\right) \sin \phi$$

where a and b are major and minor semi-axis of the reference-ellipsoid and N is the radius of curvature.

We have used QGIS, an open source platform for GIS studies, for visualization of the layers and *gdal* (Geospatial Data-abstraction Library) tools for conversion of the coordinates. The layers were taken from various open-source providers, like Bhuvan (ISRO), Earth-Explorer (USGS), OpenStreetMap (OSM) etc., and edited as per our requirements. The sectors around NPP were drawn using python plugins available in QGIS. The inputs can be stored in the Postgres database with the help of PostGIS module. The database in the backend is connected to a browser-based portal via Geoserver and Apache, which serves the vector/raster tiles to e-mapping portal.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The typical Gaussian algorithms can be run for single (or sometimes multiple sources) for receptor locations at various distances, which gives ground concentration of contaminants within an acceptable error margin. The results are usually in text, CSV, tabular or matrix format along with coordinates in cartesian i.e., distance and angular distribution, along with concentration profile. The digital overlay can be made static (overlay-visualization) and dynamic (time-dependent input and overlay) based on the integration of the program with a GIS module. The visualization of the data on a geographic overlay transforms the overall perspective by providing on-ground details, in form of GIS layers, which is more human-understandable than a huge tabular data with x and y coordinates (Fig.1). Layers make it aptly clear as to areas which could be more susceptible to contamination, and their socio-economic as well environmental impact could be ascertained by superposition of various layers in conjunction.

Fig. 22: Visualization of four different plumes in geographic coordinates, overlaid on a digital elevation model (DEM) with directional sectors in QGIS. The transformation enhances the overall perspective by providing data in layers (NPP Site: Kaiga)

CONCLUSION

The results of the atmospheric dispersion of the radioactivity due to accidental release could be modelled by GPM models. The coordinates which are evaluated in the cartesian coordinates can be converted using *gdal* algorithm of multiple translation and can be fed to the GIS platform. The GIS platform readily accepts data in Mercator (lat-long). Overlapping the data on mapping portal will provide a clear visual map of the area that is affected. The additional layered information like DEM (digital elevation model), topography and demography databases will further help in an informative and factual decision-making process on ground in real world.

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STUDY ON AIR FLOW PATTERN IN A VENTILATED RADIOACTIVE LABORATORY
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Keywords: AEROSOL, SIZE DISTRIBUTION, CONTINUOUS AIR MONITOR, VENTILATION
INTRODUCTION

The measurement of particulate radioactivity in radiological facilities is a primary requirement for ensuring safety of personnel working with radioactive material. Handling of radioactive material in dispersible forms such as powder or solution always poses a risk of its escape into the ambient air in the workplace. The escaped radionuclides attach itself to the aerosol particles present in the air. The workplace ventilation systems are designed to constantly remove air from the area. In the event of a release, the ventilation dilutes the concentration of the released radioactivity. The air flow pattern, which depends on i) the locations of the inlet and outlet of the ventilation system, ii) inlet and outlet air velocity and flow rate and iii) mechanical obstruction within the area, govern the transport of aerosol particles within the laboratory. The measurement of aerosol dynamics in the laboratory air helps in proper placement of Continuous Air Monitors (CAMs) for effective detection of accidental release of radioactivity (Whicker *et. al*, 2003) In the present study, the variation in the concentration of the aerosols in a once through ventilated laboratory was studied for simulated cases of accidental release of aerosols. The knowledge of air flow pattern in the laboratory enables the prediction of potential exposure to released activity in the absence of CAM data.

METHODS

The study was carried out in a laboratory of dimension 19 m x 10 m x 3 m having multiple air inlet and exhaust points. Aerosol Generator (Model 7811; Aerosol size range: 0.05 μm -0.3 μm) and Particle Counter (Model: 11-D; Measurement size range 0.25-35.15 μm in 31 size channels) from GRIMM were used for the generation and counting of aerosol particles. Initially, background aerosol concentration was measured at different locations in the laboratory. The aerosols were generated at a location which was understood to be the most probable region of accidental release of radioactive aerosols. 1% NaCl solution was used for atomisation to generate the aerosols. De-humidified air was passed through the aerosol produced so as to get dry NaCl particles as particles. The aerosol concentration was measured at different angular and radial distances from the source which was generating aerosols for the entire duration of the measurement. A second measurement was carried out in which the aerosols were generated for a specified time interval after which the aerosol concentration was measured with respect to the passing time. The size distribution of aerosol particles was also measured for both the scenarios.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The initial measurement of background aerosol concentration yielded a value of 90 cm^{-3} . The variation of the total particle concentration with varying distances is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Variation of total particle concentration (a) with distance (b) with time

As can be seen from the Figure 1(a), the particle concentration initially decreases as the distance from the source increases and then does not vary appreciably for farther distances. This observation may be

attributed to the use of a single particular counter for the measurements at different distances. In the present case the particle concentrations at different locations were measured at different times while the generation of the aerosols was continuously in progress. This has led to an increase in total particle concentration with time and hence at greater distances from the source the particle concentrations seem to stabilize whereas in actuality it should have shown a decreasing trend. In the other set of measurements, the aerosol generator was in operation for 5 minutes and the measurements of particle concentrations at a distance of 80 cm from the source at different time intervals were carried out. The results are presented in Figure 1(b). The total particle concentration decreases rapidly with time and within 10 minutes it reached the background concentration level. This reduction in concentration suggests an effective 12 Air changes per hour (ACH) which is within the range of required ACH for a Type-A radioactive laboratory (Smith and Smith, 2009). Figure 2 shows the size distribution of lab aerosols and the NaCl aerosols at specified angular and radial distances from the source.

Figure 2: Size distribution of lab and NaCl aerosols at specified distances

The measured NaCl aerosol concentration did not show significant angular dependence implying that the dispersion of the aerosols in the laboratory air was homogeneous. The results of the experiments indicated that in the present case the CAMs could be placed in any convenient radial direction from the source.

CONCLUSION

In the present study, the variation in the concentration of the aerosols in a once through ventilated laboratory was studied for simulated cases of accidental release of aerosols. Aerosol generator and Particle counter (GRIMM) were used for the generation and counting of aerosol particles. The measurement of background aerosol concentration yielded a value of 90 cm^{-3} . The particle concentrations were observed to decrease rapidly with time suggesting an effective air change rate of 12 h^{-1} which is equal to the required air changes of a type A radioactive laboratory.

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**NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION ON THE EFFECT OF ROOF AND POOL TEMPERATURES
ON SODIUM AEROSOL CHARACTERISTICS IN AN SFR COVER GAS**

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Keywords: SODIUM AEROSOL TRANSPORT, COVER GAS, SFR, OPENFOAM.

INTRODUCTION

In sodium-cooled fast reactors, due to the reactive nature of sodium, provision of an inert isolation layer (known as cover gas space) above the primary sodium boundary is necessary. During reactor operation, sodium aerosols are generated continuously via sodium evaporation and transported to the cover gas space. Understanding the evolution and transport of sodium aerosols within the cover gas is of paramount importance for comprehending their dynamics under various reactor operating conditions. Further, it will also aid assessment of radiological consequences during severe accident scenarios. The sodium aerosol size and its mass concentration are known to be governed by sodium pool temperature, roof-top temperature and geometrical characteristics of the cover gas space (e.g., L/D ratio of the cover gas). In the present paper, a detailed CFD study using OpenFOAM is presented to capture the aerosol dynamics in the cover gas space. The geometrical configuration of an in-house scale-down facility called SILVERINA available at IGCAR is used for numerical simulations. The effect of the roof and pool temperature on sodium aerosol size evolution and mass concentration in cover gas is brought out. The insights gained from these simulations are expected to provide valuable inputs to the designers as well as to the regulators for performing radiological safety assessment.

DESCRIPTION OF GEOMETRY, NUMERICAL MODEL, AND BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

During operation and shutdown of a typical pool type sodium cooled fast reactor, the sodium vapour pressure would be sufficiently high to promote sodium evaporation from the primary pool, leading to nucleation and condensation of the sodium vapour near the pool surface. The sodium aerosols would be transported by convection under the influence of the temperature difference between the sodium pool and roof bottom surface temperature. This necessitates to study aerosol behaviour in the cover gas space under different operating conditions. To study the aerosol dynamics in the cover gas space, a mixture based Eulerian model was used and governing equations were solved in the modified Aerosolved (Frederix 2016; Lucci, Frederix, and Kuczaj 2022), which is written in OpenFOAM framework. Details regarding governing equation and boundary conditions are available in (Patel, Kumar, and Arul 2023). During normal reactor operation, the temperature difference between reactor roof-slab bottom plate and primary sodium pool would be around 410 K, whereas during shutdown condition these temperature difference would be around 165 K. These temperature changes greatly change the aerosol dynamics in the cover gas, as it greatly changes the evaporation characteristics of the primary sodium pool.

In the present paper, a detailed CFD study is presented to capture the aerosol dynamics in the cover gas space. The geometrical configuration of an in-house scale-down facility called SILVERINA available at IGCAR is used for numerical simulations. Aerosol behaviour in cover gas under various pool temperatures (523 to 823 K) and roof temperature (358 to 413 K) is discussed. The geometrical parameters of the TP-1 are as follows: the vessel height and inner diameter are 2235 mm and 750 mm respectively. The cover gas height is kept at ~ 820 mm (similar to PFBR cover gas height). For detailed description of the experimental facility reader is referred to Parth et al. (Patel, Kumar, and Arul 2023).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

For the current study, total seven steady-state simulations have been carried out. The simulations have revealed that the average count mean diameter (CMD) exhibits an exponential variation in relation to the

temperature difference between the pool and roof, as shown in Fig. 1. Whereas, the average temperature in the cover gas shows a linear correlation with the pool and roof temperature difference. Under shutdown conditions with a pool temperature of 523 K and a roof temperature of 358 K ($\Delta T = 165$ K), the average CMD measures approximately $0.46 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 1). During operational conditions with a pool temperature of 823 K and a roof temperature of 413 K ($\Delta T = 410$ K), the CMD increases significantly to $7.73 \mu\text{m}$.

Fig. 1 Evolution of the average CMD in the cover gas with respect to temperature difference between roof-slab bottom plate temperature and sodium pool temperature.

Fig. 2 Mass concentration variation with the variation in the temperature difference between roof-slab bottom plate temperature and sodium pool temperature.

Fig. 3 Mass concentration variation along height for operational conditions (pool temperature: 823 K and roof temperature: 413 K)

In Fig. 2, it can be observed that the average mass concentration in the cover gas follows an exponential relationship with the pool and roof temperature difference. Under shutdown conditions, the average mass concentration in the cover gas is approximately 0.1 g/m^3 . However, during operational conditions, the mass concentration in the cover gas substantially rises to about 35 g/m^3 . Fig. 3 shows the mass concentration variation along the height during operational conditions. As shown in figure, the mass concentration varies between $28\text{--}37 \text{ g/m}^3$. The exponential behaviour in both mass concentration and CMD of the aerosol can be attributed to the exponential characteristic of sodium partial pressure with increasing temperature.

CONCLUSIONS

A detailed CFD model written in OpenFOAM framework was utilized to investigate the impact of both roof and sodium pool temperatures on various aerosol parameters, including mass concentration and aerosol size. The geometrical configuration of an in-house scale-down facility called SILVERINA available at IGCAR is used for numerical simulations. The results revealed distinct trends: the average temperature within the cover gas exhibited a linear relationship with the temperature difference between the roof-slab bottom plate and the primary sodium pool temperature. In contrast, both the mass concentration and the CMD of aerosol exhibited exponential variations. This behaviour can be attributed to the exponential characteristics associated with sodium evaporation. During operational conditions, the mass concentrations in the cover gas varies between 28 to 37 g/m^3 .

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NOVEL TECHNIQUE FOR SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF RADON PROGENY AEROSOLS USING LOW PRESSURE IMPACTOR LOADED WITH LR-115 BASED DRPS

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Keywords: RADON PROGENY, DRPS, ACTIVITY MEDIAN DIAMETER, IMPACTOR

INTRODUCTION

Inhalation of radon progeny is considered as one of the major lung carcinogens due its radioactive and particulate nature. Once inhaled, radon progeny aerosols deposit in different regions of the human respiratory tract that is primarily decided by its activity size distribution (ICRP, 2017). Therefore, it is important to measure the activity size distribution of radon progeny in order to understand which region of respiratory tract is more likely to be exposed and get radiation dose. In the present study, we have evolved a simple technique to measure the Activity Median Diameter (AMD) of radon progeny by using the DRPS (Direct radon progeny sensor) loaded low pressure cascade impactor (D-LPIS).

METHODS

DRPS loaded low pressure cascade impactor (D-LPIS) used for measurement of AMD of radon progeny in the present study, consists of 11 stage Low pressure cascade impactor system (LPIS) in which LR-115 Solid state nuclear tract detector (SSNTD) based DRPS were used in each stage as the deposition media for the radon progeny instead of the Filter Papers (FPs) that were used in the standard LPIS. So, in D-LPIS, progeny activity will be directly deposited onto the DRPS and the subsequent alpha tracks will be recorded. In each stage, 4 nos. of DRPSs were placed at different locations of the impaction plate. Only for the backup filter, DRPSs were placed facing the filter-paper. The schematic diagram of a section of D-LPIS system, along with lower and upper cut-off sizes is shown in Fig 1.

Fig 1. Schematic diagram of the DRPS loaded low pressure cascade impactor system (D-LPIS)

An experiment was carried out in the 8 m³ radon calibration facility, in which the pylon make radon source was used as the source of radon. Measurement of the AMD of the radon progeny attached to the aerosols was carried out simultaneously using the standard LPIS and the newly designed D-LPIS. Both the impactors were operated at a flow rate of 10 l min⁻¹. After sampling, the FPs used in each stage of the LPIS were counted using the ZnS (Ag) scintillation based gross alpha counter and the AMD was determined from the cumulative frequency plot of alpha counts versus particle cut-off size of the LPIS. It

is to note that the FPs need to be counted immediately after sampling owing to the short half life (~ 30 mins) of the radon progeny.

The LR-115 used in the DRPS of the D-LPIS, were given a delay time of 5 hours to allow complete decay of Radon progeny. Subsequently, they were chemically etched using the standard etching protocol (2.5 N NaOH at 60° C for 90 minutes without stirring). The tracks were counted using Polltech make spark counter and the AMD of the radon progeny was determined from the frequency distribution of track density in various stages of the D-LPIS.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The cumulative frequency plot of the alpha activity versus particle cut-off size of the standard LPIS is shown in Fig 2 (a). The activity median size of the radon progeny was found to be 0.20 μm with GSD of 2.88. Fig 2 (b) shows the cumulative frequency plot of the track density versus particle cut-off size of the D-LPIS from which AMD was found to be 0.23 μm with GSD of 2.65 which is in good agreement with the standard LPIS and also with the reported values (Mishra et al., 2009). The D-LPIS is more convenient to determine the activity size distribution as the tracks registered by the alpha's in the LR-115 SSNTD are permanent and hence there is no requirement of immediate counting of the LR-115 films, as required for the filter papers loaded in LPIS.

Fig 2. Cumulative percent versus upper cut-off size using (a) LPIS (b) D-LPIS

CONCLUSIONS

Measurement of activity size distribution of the radon progeny aerosols was carried out using DRPS loaded low pressure cascade impactor (D-LPIS) which is the modified version of low pressure cascade impactor. Using this system, AMD of radon progeny was found to be 0.23 μm (GSD=2.65) which is very close to the AMD value of 0.20 μm (GSD=2.88) measured with the standard LPIS and also with the reported value of AMD of radon progeny. This system will be more convenient to measure the AMD of radon progeny as the tracks registered in the SSNTD film are permanent.

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STUDY OF IODINE OXIDE AEROSOLS IN CONTEXT OF SEVERE NUCLEAR REACTOR ACCIDENTS

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Keywords: IODINE OXIDE, NUCLEAR AEROSOLS, NUCLEAR REACTOR ACCIDENTS.

INTRODUCTION

The release of radionuclides from the core under nuclear reactor accident condition produces high radiation fields, causing radiolytic reactions in the air. Product of air radiolysis (mainly ozone) oxidise I_2 into Iodine oxide (IO_x) aerosols. Expression “iodine oxide” also includes iodine-oxygen nitrogen-hydrogen species in different stoichiometries. This reaction becomes more important due to the high fission yield and radio-toxicity of iodine. Only limited studies (Funke *et al.*, 2012 and Dickinson *et al.*, 2014) exist on the formation and behaviour of IO_x . The removal rates for iodine depends on whether it is in an aerosol or in a vapour form, and therefore, the radiolytic I_2 oxidation plays an important role in source term assessments.

METHODS

The experiment was designed to achieve iodine to IO_x conversion using ozone inside 50 L Perspex chamber (Fig 1). This chamber with multiple sampling lines was kept inside the walk-in chamber to ensure safety of the working place. Ozone generator, oxygen concentrator and iodine chamber were kept outside the walk-in chamber and connected to Perspex chamber via sampling lines. The ozone was generated by ozone generator coupled with oxygen concentrator and fed in to the Perspex chamber. The ozone concentration was continuously monitored by ozone monitor and after getting the steady state, injection was stopped and thereafter iodine vapours (generated by heating) were pushed by external pump. The generated IO_x aerosols were collected using gross sampler and impactor.

Fig 1. (a) Experimental Set-up; (b) Inside walk in chamber

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

02 sets of experiments were performed and the results obtained were analysed for ozone decay and aerosol parameters. The first confirmation of the conversion of iodine vapour to IO_x aerosols came from the collection of aerosols on gross sampler. The obtained mass concentrations on gross sampler for set 1 and set 2 were 16 mg/m^3 and 31 mg/m^3 respectively. The corresponding mass size distribution for set 2 obtained by impactor is shown in fig 2. The analysis shows that 70% of the formed particles lies between $1.13 - 2.23 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$.

Fig 2. Mass size distribution of IO_x particles obtained from impactor.

The fig 3 (a-b) show the decay of the ozone after iodine is introduced in the chamber. As can be seen from both the figures, this decline follows the exponential decay (ExeDec1, Eq 1).

$$y = A e^{\frac{-x}{t}} + y_o \tag{1}$$

The decay constant obtained for experiment 1 and 2 were 0.0125 s⁻¹ and 0.00524 s⁻¹ respectively and the corresponding half-life were 55 s and 132 s. The reaction seems to follow the first order exponential decay and for confirmation log A vs time was plotted (Fig 3(inset)). Obtained straight line in log A vs time re-confirms the first order reaction rate.

Fig 3. (a-b) Ozone concentration vs time plot for set 1 and 2; (inset) Log A vs time plot for set 1 and 2.

CONCLUSIONS

Experiments were carried to achieve radiolytic reaction of iodine to iodine oxide (IO_x) in presence of ozone. The formed IO_x aerosols were measured using gross sampler and impactor for their total aerosol mass concentration and mass size distribution respectively. Rate of formation of IO_x was studied using ozone decay time series. The analysis showed that the reaction follows first order and 70% of the formed particles lies between diameter 1.13 - 2.23 µm.

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GRAPHITE AEROSOL GENERATION AT DIFFERENT HEATING CONDITIONS

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Keywords: Graphite Aerosol, Graphite oxidation, HTRs

INTRODUCTION

To meet the growing global energy demand, it is crucial to reduce emissions of contaminating gases and combustion products(Chen *et al.*, 2014). Nuclear power plants, such as PWR, PHWR, BWR, AGR, and Magnox, play a significant role in meeting energy demands and controlling pollutant emissions (Adamantiades and Kessides, 2009). High-temperature reactors (HTRs) offer an alternative for enhancing power production efficiency, as they produce power at a higher temperature than conventional reactors(Fallis, 2013). However, safety issues need to be addressed in nuclear reactors, as highlighted by the Chernobyl and Fukushima accidents. One potential risk to nuclear reactor safety is air-ingress in case of containment shield failure(Beresford, Scott and Coplestone, 2019). If a coolant pump fails, the temperature of the nuclear rods may rise, leading to a loss of coolant accident (LOCA) (Stanculescu, 2010). Exposure to high-temperature graphite oxidation can result in dust generation, which can carry radioactivity and cause inhalation hazards (Moormann, 2008). Understanding the properties of aerosols generated in an accident scenario is crucial.

EXPERIMENT SETUP AND MATERIAL

The study involved burning graphite samples in a split box-type furnace using a recrystallized alumina tube. The air flow rate was maintained by an air compressor and monitored using a rotameter. The air was passed through a HEPA filter, acting as the oxidant and carrier gas, and transported by an aerosol sampled from a borosilicate glass tube. The isokinetic probe was placed in the center of the borosilicate tube, and a counter-flow heat exchanger was connected to cool the aerosol to the maximum working temperature limit of the aerosol spectrometer. The aerosol was then led to a diluter to reduce particle concentration and cool it before measuring aerosol size and concentration by a spectrometer. More details on the facility, experimental set-up and experimental methodology have been provided in Yadav et al.(Yadav, Khan and Shukla, 2019).In the present research, high-density isotropic graphite sample with 97.28% carbon content was oxidized.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The study investigates the aerosol by oxidizing graphite samples at a constant temperature range of 500-900°C and a flowrate of 25 lpm (Fig1a). It was found that the number concentration decreases with time, with the highest emission observed at 700°C. The activation energy of graphite oxidation, which becomes maximum at 700°C and then decreases, is linked to this. The maximum energy barrier to oxidation occurs at 700°C, resulting in maximum incomplete combustion products. The aerosol emission was initially higher at the beginning of sample insertion, but as heating continued at constant temperature, it began to decline. Prolonged heating reduces the sample's surface area and deactivates reaction sites. However, when graphite was heated at different heating of 2,4,6, & 8 °C/min rate and flowrates 10, 15,20 & 25 lpm (Fig.1b), the aerosol generation was negligible below 570°C, with a peaking profile observed in every condition. The peak concentration was mostly between 600 and 800°C. The aerosol concentration increased with increasing heating rate, with a peak concentration decreasing with increasing air flow rate. The maximum particle concentration was observed at the lowest flowrate (10 lpm) and highest heating rate (8 °C/min).

Figure. 1 (a) Graphite heating at constant temperature (b) Graphite heating at different heating rates and flow rates

CONCLUSIONS

The study examined the emission characteristics of particles, CO, and CO₂ gases in high purity graphite at high temperatures and different heating rates and air flow rates. It was found that oxidation of graphite begins at temperatures exceeding 500°C, with the highest concentration of CO gas and aerosols at 700°C. The peak number concentration was highest at 5.3×10^6 #/cm³ at 25 lpm, with aerosols in the 10-50 nm size range. At variable heating rates, the highest concentration was 5.13×10^6 #/cm³ at 10 lpm. CO gas was obtained for incomplete oxidation at temperatures ranging from 600 to 800°C. Particle generation/formation was observed in the 50-100 nm and 210-365 nm ranges at lower heating rates.

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DEVELOPMENT OF A DIFFUSION SAMPLER FOR TESTING OF RADON BARRIER MATERIALS

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Keywords: RADON, DIFFUSION SAMPLER, RADON REDUCTION

INTRODUCTION

Radon progeny after its formation from parent radon attach to the aerosols present in the atmosphere and behave as radioactive aerosols. It is considered as the major contributor of inhalation dose and a primary cause of lung cancer. By adopting certain mitigation strategies to restrict the entry of radon gas into enclosed spaces, the risk due to radon progeny can be minimized. One such mitigation technique consists of covering the radon entry surfaces with radon barrier materials.

In the present study, we have developed a diffusion sampler based on the methodology described in ISO/TS 11665-13:2017(ISO-2017) and carried out some preliminary experiments to study a few radon barrier materials using this diffusion sampler by determining the percentage radon reduction by these materials. This study will find importance in testing and selection of suitable radon barrier material for the walls and flooring especially, where a radon free clean laboratory is involved.

METHODS

DIFFUSION SAMPLER

A diffusion sampler system was designed as per the guidelines of standard ISO/TS 11665-13:2017. It consists of two chambers, the bottom source chamber (SC) and upper receiver chamber (RC), one above the other, with a volume of $8.01 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^3$ each, made of stainless steel AISI316L and a thickness of 2 mm (Fig. 1). The test barrier area is $7.85 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2$ and it is surrounded by a flange with screws to seal the barrier sample, placed between the two chambers. Each chamber has ports to attach it to radon measuring devices. The leak rate of the sampler is 0.005 h^{-1} as required by the norms of the standard.

EXPERIMENTAL SET UP

The experimental set up is shown in the Fig. 2. The two chambers of the diffusion sampler was connected to two continuous Radon monitors (Gaware et al. 2011) through the ports. The radon source (90 nCi powder source) was kept at the bottom of the source chamber. A closed-loop was maintained for the entire system. A barrier material, silicone rubber of diameter 10 cm and thickness 2 mm was placed between the two chambers and made leak tight. The radon concentration in both the chambers was measured simultaneously for 48 h at 30 minutes time interval. The steady state maximum radon concentration of 200 kBq m^{-3} was reached for the barrier. The typical behaviour of Rn-222 concentration (Bq m^{-3}) versus time (in mins) for silicone rubber is shown in Fig. 3. The percentage radon reduction was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Radon reduction}(\%) = \frac{(C_{SC} - C_{RC})}{C_{SC}} * 100 \quad (1)$$

where, C_{SC} and C_{RC} are radon concentration in source and receiver chamber respectively. The same experiment was repeated for two more barrier materials viz. Aluminised Mylar (AM) of thickness 50 μm and 100 μm .

Fig 1. Diffusion Sampler

Fig 2. Experimental set up

Fig.3. Radon concentration (Bq m^{-3}) versus time (mins) measured in two chambers for silicone rubber

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The percent reduction of radon through the three barrier materials was calculated using Eq 1 and the results are tabulated in Table 1. It was observed that maximum of 99.2% reduction was obtained for AM of thickness $100 \mu\text{m}$.

Table 1. Rn-222 reduction percentage for different barriers

S.No.	Material	Rn-222 reduction (%)
1	Silicone rubber (2 mm)	90.4
2	Aluminised mylar ($50 \mu\text{m}$)	84.1
3	Aluminised mylar ($100 \mu\text{m}$)	99.2

CONCLUSION

A diffusion sampler based on ISO/TS 11665-13:2017 was designed to test the capability of obstructing Radon by some radon barrier materials. Among the three barrier materials studied, Aluminised mylar of thickness $100 \mu\text{m}$ provided a barrier of 99.2% . Hence, it is a suitable barrier which can be used for Radon mitigation application.

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ASSESSMENT OF FP AND SODIUM AEROSOL BEHAVIOR IN A CLOSED CHAMBER
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Keywords: SODIUM AEROSOL, FISSION PRODUCT AEROSOL, SODIUM FIRE.

INTRODUCTION

As a part of the safety analysis of SFRs, liquid sodium poses unique challenges due to the potential release of sodium aerosols in the event of system failures. The FP and sodium aerosols during severe accidents are paramount for environmental protection. Understanding FP and sodium aerosol behaviour in containment is a multifield phenomenon. Firstly, the potential release of radioactive FP into the environment presents a significant radiation hazard, necessitating precise knowledge of their transport and deposition mechanisms. Secondly, liquid sodium can react vigorously with atmospheric constituents and generate aerosol, hampering equipment functionality and making mitigation strategy more critical. Physical and chemical processes, such as condensation, chemical reactions, agglomeration, and deposition, govern the behaviour of FP and sodium aerosols. These processes depend on multiple factors, including temperature, pressure, chamber geometry, and the initial state of the FP and sodium aerosols (Kumar *et al.*, 2023). Therefore, a systematic investigation is indispensable to study the FP and sodium aerosol behaviour in a closed chamber. The paper aims to provide an evolution of FP and sodium aerosols within a scale-down chamber by conducting experiments to gain insights into their temporal evolution, transport, and deposition. The findings of this assessment will contribute to the realistic database for the evolution of aerosol dynamics produced during severe accidents and validate the numerical models for understanding FP and sodium aerosol dynamics in the containment.

METHODS

The experiments were carried out at the MINA facility, which consists of a rectangular steel chamber with a volume of 150 m³. The facility has sophisticated equipment for generating sodium and non-volatile FP aerosol, monitoring spatial gas, wall temperature, aerosol metrological instruments, and a high-speed video imaging system. Experiments were conducted with aerosol concentration envisaged under severe accident conditions, i.e., 4 g/m³ (by sodium fire) and ~ 10 mg/m³ (by vaporization and condensation) in containment. A 40-kW thermal plasma torch aerosol generator (PTAG) system and powder feeder were installed at the MINA facility to initiate experimental work. The PTAG best simulates the aerosol characteristics generated during an accident because of the high temperature vaporizing the materials. The non-volatile FP aerosol (SrO) was generated using a PTAG for ~15 min. The sodium aerosol was generated by burning 2.0 kg of sodium at a temperature spreading in a pool area of ~0.25 m². The aerosol sampling was monitored at multiple locations using real-time and offline aerosol metrological devices.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The operational parameters of PTAG have been optimized by conducting a series of experiments and operated at 25 - 30 kW power, 45 - 55% electro-thermal efficiency, and 25 lpm flow rate plasma forming gas for the generation of FP aerosols using SrO₂ powder. The evolution of SrO aerosol concentration and mean size growth is shown in Fig.1(a). The average suspended number concentration reached a maximum of 4.2*10¹¹ #/m³ during the generation period. From the generation, the number concentration is reduced with time and got 5 times less from maximum concentration in ~5 hrs. The aerosol counts median aerodynamic diameter (CMAD) for initial size distribution is 0.18 μm with σ_g – 1.5, and CMAD increases with time and reaches saturation value (0.38 μm). The observed enhancement of aerosol median size is 100% from the initial median size in ~5 hrs.

Figure 1. Evolution of SrO aerosol concentration and size growth (a) and comparison of SrO and sodium aerosol mass concentration (b).

A comparison of SrO and sodium aerosol mass concentration is shown in Fig.1(b). The suspended mass concentration increased and reached a maximum of $\sim 8.12 \text{ mg/m}^3$ during the generation period. Concentration decreased with time and reduced about 45% from the maximum in ~ 5 hrs. The reduction in suspended concentration is faster in the case of sodium aerosol than the non-volatile fission product aerosol. In five hours, $\sim 99\%$ of sodium aerosols were deposited at the surface of the chamber. The SrO aerosol concentration reduction half time is more than 5 hrs. However, for sodium aerosol, it is less than one hour. The suspended concentration decay is faster for sodium aerosol due to larger particles and higher concentration, resulting in rapid size growth by the coagulation process and faster removal by gravitational settling. Further, hygroscopic growth might be enhancing faster deposition of sodium aerosol. In the case of SrO, aerosol size growth is less due to smaller size and lesser mass concentrations. For example, the size growth factor is 2 for SrO aerosol; however, for sodium, it is ~ 25 in 5 hrs (Kumar *et al.*, 2023).

CONCLUSIONS

The present experimental study has given sizable insight into understanding the evolution of FP and sodium aerosols in a scale-down facility. The observation will be used to validate FP and sodium aerosol dynamics codes for aerosol dispersion and deposition inside the containment to increase confidence in the source term predictions. Further studies are underway to study the mixed behaviour of FP and sodium aerosol dispersion and deposition. Theoretical comparison of FP and sodium aerosol evolution is underway.

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HEALTH EFFECTS AND BIOAEROSOLS

ATMOSPHERIC DEPOSITION OF BIOAEROSOL ON TULSI (*OCIMUM SANCTUM*) OVER INDO-GANGETIC BASIN

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Key words: Atmospheric deposition, *Ocimum* leaves, dry deposition flux, microbial component.

Introduction

Road side trees and plants suffer daily due to deposition. Among many of the major mechanisms, by which air pollutants can be delivered to sensitive surfaces, 'Dry deposition' is an important mechanism (Kumar et al., 2006). The natural surface like plant leaves are exposed as leaves have broader surface area. They permit air to deposit its particulate matter on to its open natural surface. It is estimated that the terrestrial leaf surface area that might be colonized by microbes is about 6.4×10^8 km². The microbial communities in the atmosphere varied including numerous of the different genera of bacteria, fungi, yeasts, algae (Mamta et al., 2015). But bacteria are by far the most abundant inhabitants of the phyllosphere and fungi which are considered as temporary inhabitants of leaf surfaces. Seasonally the highest colonization of microbes is seen in the rainy season comparatively to dry and warm season (Ercolani, 1991). However, in country like India where dry conditions prevail for most part of the year, dry deposition is an important process for the transfer of materials from the atmosphere to the earth surfaces. A limited study on dry deposition of abiotic components to surfaces has been reported however, none has reported on dry deposition flux biotic components on natural surfaces. *Ocimum* popularly known as 'Tulsi' in India has unique position in Indian community as they worship it as well as chew its leaves as they are anti-allergic materials. Hence, study on dry deposition of bacteria and fungi on leaves of *Ocimum* plant are of paramount importance.

Methods

The dry deposition samples on *Ocimum* leaves were collected using surface washing method. 10 leaves of *Ocimum* were tagged, cleaned with ultra-pure water, air dried and exposed for ten days on non-dewy, non-foggy and non-rainy days. Aliquots of the dry deposition samples were used for microbial analysis using culture techniques. Bacteria were isolated using Nutrient Agar Medium (NAM) and fungi were isolated using the PDA media. Identification was carried out on the basis of shape, size and color of the colonies under a light microscope and compared with standard description of fungi and bacteria. The dry deposition flux was determined by dividing the colony forming unit of bacteria and fungi deposited on leaves with surface area of leaves (m²) and exposed time (day) The concentration of fungal and bacterial concentrations in air is expressed as number of colonies forming unit per cubic meter in air (cfu m⁻³) while dry deposition flux was represented as cfu cm⁻² d⁻¹. The phylloplane of bio aerosol on *Ocimum* leaf was analyzed by Scanning Electron microscope (JEOL JSM 58001) from National Institute of Oceanography, Goa and information about morphology of bacteria; fungi and other particulate matter which adhere to the surface were obtained.

Results & Discussion

Microbial deposition on leaf surface is a natural phenomenon but it shows the variation between polluted and non-polluted sites. Once the microbial components get released in the atmosphere from the sources they may find particles as substrate or they may individually travel from one place to another and finally reaches to earth surface via dry and wet deposition. The dry deposition is the major pathway of removal of microbial pollutants from the atmosphere to earth surface in the country like India as dry condition prevails for the most part of the year. Table 1 presents dry deposition flux of microbial components on natural surface.

Table 1: Average, standard deviation and range of dry deposition flux (cfu cm⁻² d⁻¹) of microbial components on *Ocimum sanctum* leaves.

Parameter	Polluted Mean ± SD (Min. to max.)	Non-polluted Mean ± SD (Min. to max.)
Total microbial count	843.6 ± 345.9 (12.5 to 1253.1)	241.3 ± 114.2 (7.6 to 383.7)
Bacterial count	772.0 ± 298.4 (438.6 to 1253.1)	216.6 ± 132.9 (89.5 to 383.7)
Fungal counts	71.6 ± 47.6 (12.5 to 125.3)	24.7 ± 11.3 (7.6 to 36.2)

shows the standard minimum maximum

The table mean, deviation, and of dry

deposition flux of the total microbial component (TMC), fungi components and bacterial components on leaf surface (phylloplane) of *Ocimum* (Tulsi). The deposition flux is the highest for bacteria at both sites. It may be due to the fact that the bacterial concentration in the atmosphere is higher than the fungal concentration. Amongst the sites, the deposition flux at site A is higher than site B. It is akin to site characteristics. Site A is close to the road and hence polluted while site B is away from the main road and hence less polluted. About seven genera of fungi were observed and the relative abundance was highest for *Aspergillus*. Gram +ve bacteria are more in comparison to gram -ve bacteria. White and red color bacteria were more abundant compared to other while coccus shaped bacteria are maximum compared to rod shaped. Molecular characterization of dominant bacterial isolates were carried out by NCBI, Gene Bank, USA and two bacteria were found to be common i.e., *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Korcuria* sps. (Accession number of *Korcuria* sps: KU937323).

Conclusion

The dry deposition of microbes on natural surface of *Ocimum* leaf was determined first time. The mean dry deposition flux of total microbial components on leaf surface of *Ocimum* was high. More microbial and particle deposition on *Ocimum* leaf has been observed because of its rough and feathery phylloplane and the number of phylloplane of fungi and bacteria was significantly high in the road side area as compared to the non road side. Some of the microbial species are pathogenic or infectious in nature. It is important to chew the leaves of Tulsi after proper washing.

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MEASUREMENT OF RESPIRABLE SUSPENDED PARTICULATE MATTER, FINE PARTICULATE MATTER AND VOLATILE ORGANIC COMPOUNDS IN HOUSEHOLDS- FARHEEN ZEHR¹, SAMRIDHI DWIVEDI¹, ANAM TAUSHIBA², ALFRED LAWRENCE¹

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Keywords: FINE PARTICULATE MATTER, TVOCs, INDOOR AIR, HEALTH RISK ASSESSMENT

INTRODUCTION

Majority of people spend 90% of their time indoors, where they are exposed to significantly high concentrations of pollutants than outdoors (Zehra et al., 2023). According to data on daily mortality, exposure to total suspended particles (TSP) and fine particles (PM_{2.5} & PM₁) in outdoor and indoor environments may cause 4-8% of premature deaths on a global scale. Since they can enter the trachea, bronchi, bronchioles, and alveoli, which are among the smallest airways of the lower respiratory tract, fine particles (PM_{2.5} particulate matter with 2.5 μm in aerodynamic diameter) are of especially serious concern (Dwivedi et al., 2023). The current paper addresses the quantitative information on indoor particulate matter (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, and PM_{1.0}) and TVOCs in six urban residential homes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present study was carried out in Lucknow city, from November 2022 to February 2023 in six different households within an indoor environment. PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} samples were collected through GF/A 47 mm filter paper with the help of APM 550 Envirotech sampler, at a flow rate of 17.5 liters per minute for 24 hours. whereas Envirotech APM 577 sampler was used for 24 hours to collect PM₁ with PTFE 47mm filter paper, total volatile organic compounds (TVOCs) were analyzed with the help of sensor-based air quality monitor (model-BR SMART). In order to relate the concentration with households characteristics, various household activities like ventilation, kitchen exhaust, cooking medium, greenery inside and outside the house, households cores activities like cleaning, use of insecticide and pesticides, etc were noted while monitoring.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data obtained revealed higher average concentrations of all the pollutants at all the houses (Table 1), the high concentrations were believed to be due to different household activities. Closure of doors and windows during the winter season and use of oil and spices during long cooking episodes may be one of the major reasons of high concentrations. The difference between the concentration of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} were less and this needs to be further analyzed. TVOCs was found to be highest at H4 and H6 houses and this may be due to use of coal for heating the house during winter.

Table 1. Concentration of PM and TVOC in different households

Households	Conc. PM ₁₀ (μg/m ³)	Conc. PM _{2.5} (μg/m ³)	Conc. PM ₁ (μg/m ³)	Con.TVOCs (mg/m ³)
H1	207.265	191.1093	21.884	0.414
H2	240.175	196.3729	10.812	0.479
H3	234.19	220.6283	27.608	0.934
H4	260.04	233.9848	17.368	9.901
H5	250.1	240.6186	14.640	0.214
H6	228.39	216.6438	13.264	3.771

CONCLUSIONS

The results shows that concentrations of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and PM₁ are higher during winter season and this may be due to less cross ventilation and different indoor sources like use of coal, cooking and cleaning episodes. Health risk assessment was also done and found to be alarming.

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ANALYTICAL PARAMETERS AND ROS GENERATION CAPABILITY SUPPORTING HEALTH RISK ASSESSMENT OF SIZE-SEGREGATED PARTICULATE MATTER BOUND METALS

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Keywords: SIZE-SEGREGATED PM, METALS, HEALTH RISK, DITHIOTHREITOL ASSAY

INTRODUCTION

PM bound Fe, Cu and Zn is capable of penetrating deep inside the human lungs, thereby initiating reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation by Fenton's or Fenton-like reaction which ultimately leads to cell death due to build-up of oxidative stress (Jan et al., 2018). Dithiothreitol (DTT) assay is widely used to determine oxidative stress generated by ROS (Bates et al., 2019). Thus, in this research work, we investigated PM bound metals viz. Fe, Cu and Zn and their correlation with DTT activity.

METHODS

SITE DESCRIPTION AND SAMPLING

Based on ongoing industrial growth and population density, Kharadi, Pune was selected for sampling. Sampling was performed from December, 2022 to February, 2023 by eight stage cascade impactor (Tisch Environmental Inc.).

METAL ANALYSIS, HEALTH RISK ASSESSMENT AND DTT ASSAY

Collected PM samples were extracted in aqua regia and analysed by atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AAS, Shimadzu, AA-7000) for metal concentration. Air quality index (AQI), and average daily dose (ADD) for individual metal was calculated by using equations provided by USEPA.

$$AQI = \frac{\text{Mass concentration for 24 hrs}}{24 \text{ hrs NAAQS standards}} \times 100$$

$$ADD = \frac{\text{Concentration } (\mu\text{g m}^{-3}) \times \text{Inhalation Rate } (15.3 \text{ m}^3 \text{ d}^{-1}) \times \text{Exposure Duration } (20 \text{ yrs})}{\text{Body Weight } (60 \text{ Kg}) \times \text{Average Exposure Time}}$$

Time interval based DTT activity was calculated by treating 1000 μl of each PM extract with DTT (1 mM), DTNB (10 mM) and Tris-HCl EDTA base.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

PM MASS CONCENTRATION

Fig. 1, depicts the size segregated PM concentration in Kharadi. Average PM_{10} and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ mass concentration for Kharadi was found to be $428.2 \pm 35 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and $146.4 \pm 29 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, respectively.

Fig. 1: Average stage-wise PM mass concentration

METAL CONCENTRATION, HEALTH RISK ANALYSIS AND DTT ACTIVITY

Fig. 2, depicts the average concentration of metals at Kharadi site. Highest concentration of Fe was recorded followed by Zn and Cu. Calculated values for average daily dose (ADD) of metals for an average 60 Kg person, are reported in Table 1.

Fig. 2: Average stage-wise concentration of metals bound with PM

Table 1: AQI and ADD ($\mu\text{gKg}^{-1}\text{day}^{-1}$) for Kharadi

PM	AQI	ADD		
		Fe	Cu	Zn
PM ₁₀	109.01	3.4596	0.1758	0.3504
PM _{2.5}	82.69	1.6105	0.1125	0.2104

Pearson's Correlation was applied to the dataset obtained for metal concentration and DTT activity by using R-Studio (fig. 3). Fe (p value= 0.03372) and Cu (p value= 0.8512) were having positive correlation with DTT activity, while Zn was having the lowest correlation.

Fig. 3: Correlation of DTT activity with PM bound metal concentration

CONCLUSIONS

Study of size-segregate particulate matter and its correlation with DTT activity is successfully performed for Kharadi, Pune, from December, 2022 to February, 2023. Observed PM mass concentrations exceeds, NAAQS standards set for PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}. Highest average elemental concentration of Fe ($13.57 \mu\text{gm}^{-3}$ bound with PM₁₀) is recorded, followed by Zn and Cu. Health risk assessment of these quantified metals showed that the air quality falls under the poor category. Observed DTT activity is positively correlated with concentration levels of Fe and Cu with p values of 0.03372 and 0.8512, respectively.

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INVESTIGATION OF HEALTH RISKS ASSOCIATED WITH PM_{2.5} EXPOSURE IN BENGALURU CITY, INDIA

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Keywords: SEASONAL ANALYSIS, WEEKDAY AND WEEKEND, HAZARD INDEX, HEALTH IMPACTS, AIRQ+

INTRODUCTION

Ambient air pollution primarily contributing from fine Particulate Matter (PM_{2.5}) is one of the top environmental risks in India attributing to more than a million deaths annually. The present study evaluates the characteristics of PM_{2.5} at various locations of Bengaluru metropolitan city and assesses the health risk due to PM_{2.5} exposure.

METHODS

Real time PM_{2.5} levels are extracted from reference grade instruments (FEM Grade, MetOne instrument) during the period Jan-Dec 2022 from the nine monitoring locations (one at the CSTEP office and eight CPCB Continuous Ambient Air Quality Monitoring Stations) spread across the city (categorized as kerbside, residential and industrial). Seasonal exposures for winter (Dec–Feb), summer (March–May), monsoon (June–Sep), and post-monsoon (Oct–Nov) along with the weekday and weekend impacts are assessed and compared. The magnitude of health risks was accounted by estimating the chronic daily inhalation, hazard quotient, cancer risk and Hazard Index based on risk assessment guidance provided by USEPA. In addition, the probability of occurrence of lifetime cancer risks was evaluated due to continual exposure to PM_{2.5}. Furthermore, the health impacts was estimated using the AirQ+ model developed by WHO.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Bapuji Nagar present along the kerbside had the highest daily mean PM_{2.5} concentration (46.53 µg/m³) while Hombe Gowda with the lowest (25.54 µg/m³) located in a residential area, while all the monitoring stations overshoot the specified exposure limit of 15 µg/m³ (24 h average WHO standards) (Figure 1.a) and raw data is shown in Figure 1.b. Statistically all the three locations are significantly different ($p < 0.05$) based on one way ANOVA test. Similarly, from seasonal analysis (Figure 2.a along with interquartile ranges) it is apparent that, statistically PM_{2.5} levels varied across the seasons. Weekday and weekend concentrations (Figure 2.b) are compared through paired *t*-test and found to be statistically different ($p < 0.05$). Bapuji Nagar exhibited high non-carcinogenic risk while lowest from Hombe Gowda. Finally, risk assessment indicated that more than 3 years of continuous exposure to PM_{2.5}, would increase the likelihood of developing a lifetime average cancer risk. Additionally, health impact assessment revealed high incidence per 100,000 population for restricted activity days, workdays lost, hospital admissions from respiratory diseases and hospital admissions from cardiovascular diseases of 339, 332, 49 and 23, respectively.

CONCLUSIONS

The PM_{2.5} levels are compared across the various locations in the city followed by seasonal, weekday and weekend trend analysis for the year 2022. The health risks from PM_{2.5} exposure was estimated. The results shows that there is a pressing need to focus on controlling the polluting sources across various monitoring sites.

Figure 1. (a) Comparison of $PM_{2.5}$ across various sites. The 25th and 75th percentiles are represented by the box, 1%-99% is represented by whiskers, and the mean is represented by the solid square (b) Raw data of $PM_{2.5}$ across various sites for complete year

Figure 2. (a) Seasonal Analysis and (b) Weekday and weekend trends

Location	CDI	HQ	CR
CSTEP	1.19341E-06	1.99	4.144E-05
Bapuji Nagar	1.86386E-06	3.10	6.472E-05
Hebbal	1.1563E-06	1.92	4.015E-05
Silk Board	1.35997E-06	2.26	4.722E-05
Hombe Gowda	1.02277E-06	1.70	3.551E-05
Jaynagar	1.27209E-06	2.12	4.417E-05
BTM Layout	1.51127E-06	2.52	5.247E-05
BWSSB	1.18255E-06	1.97	4.106E-05
Peenya	1.5669E-06	2.61	5.441E-05
Average	1.34768E-06	2.24	4.679E-05

Table 1. Exposure risk to $PM_{2.5}$ at varied locations of Bengaluru city.

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MEASUREMENT AND HEALTH RISK EVALUATION OF COOKING-GENERATED PARTICLES IN THE COMMUNITY KITCHENS OF DAKSHINA KANNADA, INDIA

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Keywords: indoor air pollution (IAP), community kitchen, PM, health risk assessment

INTRODUCTION

Exposure to indoor air pollution (IAP) is of concern since it is a potential health hazard. Culinary activity is one of the main sources of IAP in household. Large number of studies have focused on IAP and the associated health hazard, due to cooking practices around the world but studies on this aspect in community kitchens, which serve food for large number of population, were not examined. Particularly in highly populated developing countries such as India. In this study, the concentrations of PM₁, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀ were measured in the indoor air of a variety of community kitchens. PM ratios were determined, and they are in the order PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀ > PM₁/PM_{2.5} > PM₁/PM₁₀. The study shows that workers in community kitchens are exposed to enhanced air pollution, and the corresponding health risks are evaluated.

METHODS

Urban and suburban locations within the 40 km radial zone of Mangalore city, South West Coast of India were chosen for this study. The PM measurement was carried out at a variety of kitchen set ups, such as: students hostel, schools, college cafeteria, and restaurants. Real-time 24 h PM monitoring was conducted at 15 community kitchens using the portable PM monitoring system APT MAXIMA (Applied Particle Technology Inc, 1900 S. Norfolk Street Ste. 350, San Mateo, CA 94403). It is a real-time PM monitoring and recording instrument, along with ambient temperature, pressure, and humidity data.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Each kitchen workplaces was monitored continuously for a duration of 15 to 20 days to record PM concentration during cooking and non-cooking periods to capture all events in the sampling period. A comparison of the 12 h average data of PM₁, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀ concentrations in different kitchens are presented in Fig.1. The PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} values were similar, whereas PM₁ is lower by a factor of 2 when compared to the other two species. The PM concentration values are higher (range=50-1017 µg m⁻³) when compared to those reported for dwellings (range= 48-185 µg m⁻³) by other investigators (Prashant et al., 2022). This is due to the high emission rate during cooking and longer cooking periods. The diurnal trends observed in all the community kitchens are similar. The PM size fraction ratios were in the order PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀ > PM₁/PM_{2.5} > PM₁/PM₁₀, which confirms that resuspension of particles generated in the cooking process is a major contributor to the total PM₁₀ concentration. In general, PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀ ratio <0.5 represents conditions where the observed PM levels are dominated by PM₁₀, while PM_{2.5}/PM₁₀ ratios >0.5 characterize cases with a dominant PM_{2.5} fraction. The fine to coarse particles ratio provides information about the particle origin and their formation process. Higher values of this ratio suggest the contribution from anthropogenic sources, and a smaller ratio indicates considerable involvement of coarse particle, which might be related to natural sources (Sugimoto et al., 2016). Excess Lifetime Cancer Risk (ELCR), Hazard Quotient (HQ), Excess Risks (ER), and Attributable Fraction (AF) due to PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ were evaluated from the PM concentration values. The obtained ELCR values (1.7x10⁻⁵ to 1.3x10⁻⁴) were higher when compared to the recommended limit for humans in the range of 1x10⁻⁵ to 1x10⁻⁶ by WHO (2013) and less than 1x10⁻⁶ by U.S.EPA, (2007). The non-carcinogenic risk HQ>1 for all

the community kitchens exceeded the threshold value. The above results underline the need for detailed study in community kitchens since a section of workers (professionals) are exposed to high PM concentrations continuously.

Figure 1. Comparison of PM₁, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀ concentrations in different kitchens. Daily 12 h data, corresponding to the cooking and non-cooking activity in kitchen was averaged for a month and presented

CONCLUSIONS

The results presented in this paper represent a preliminary study on the assessment of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ in community kitchens and their associated impact on the health of the worker. The study shows that the potential impact of fine particulate matter related air pollution on the workers at the community kitchen is higher. A detailed study on this aspect is now progressing.

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ASSESSMENT OF THE TOXICOLOGICAL IMPACT OF SECONDARY ORGANIC AEROSOLS (SOA) FORMED BY PHOTOCHEMICAL AGING OF EMISSIONS IN AIR-LIQUID-INTERFACE EXPOSED LUNG CELL MODELS

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Keywords : Ambient particulate matter, Secondary Organic Aerosol, Health effects, Air-Liquid-Interface (ALI) cell exposure, lung cell models, anthropogenic emissions, biogenic emissions, cytotoxicity, genotoxicity

In the framework of the aeroHEALTH Helmholtz International Lab and the EU consortium ULTRHAS the impact of atmospheric aging of emissions on health effects is elucidated. We investigated differences in toxicological effects of Secondary Organic Aerosols (SOA) generated by photochemically aging of a biogenic (β -pinene) or an anthropogenic (naphthalene) organic precursor with combustion-derived soot particles (SP) as seed in two different lung cell models exposed at the air-liquid interface (ALI, Oeder et al.). Lung epithelial cell monocultures (A549) and a co-culture model (A549 and EA.hy926-endothelial cells) were exposed at the ALI for 4 h to different aerosol concentrations of pure SP (CAST), β -pinene-SOA on SP (SOA _{β PIN}-SP) or naphthalene-SOA (SOA_{NAP}-SP) on SP. The aerosols were comprehensively characterized (physical/chemical properties) and toxicity tests were conducted to determine cytotoxicity, intracellular oxidative stress, genotoxicity, inflammatory effects etc. in the models (Offer et al.). Both investigated SOA-types caused significant toxicological effects. The toxicological assays furthermore indicated greater adverse effects of SOA_{NAP}-SP compared with SOA _{β PIN}-SP in both cell models. At functional level SOA_{NAP}-SP augments the secretion of e.g. malondialdehyde and interleukin-8, inducing an activation of endothelial cells (co-culture), confirmed e.g. by comet assay suggesting secondary genotoxicity. Chemical characterization of PM revealed distinct differences in the composition of the two secondary aerosol types. It is shown that SOA-compounds can increase the toxicity of primary SP, which are ubiquitous in inhabited and wildfire influenced areas. Aromatic precursors, such as naphthalene caused the formation more oxidized, more aromatic SOA of higher oxidation potential with higher toxicity compared to an aliphatic precursor, such as β -pinene. The influence of atmospheric chemistry on the chemical PM composition play a crucial role for the adverse health-outcomes of emissions. Further comparable experiments have been conducted with CAST soot aerosols (ultrafine particles) with different chemical composition (high/low content of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons) and with real emissions (e.g., fresh and photochemical aged car emissions). An interesting result was obtained with emissions from an EURO6 car, exhibiting all available abatement technologies (particle filter, 3-way catalyst etc.). A very low toxicity of the freshly emitted aerosol was detected. The EURO 6 car exhaust, however, became considerably more toxic after ageing. Thus photochemical processes may have a serious impact on the toxicity and air pollution related health-effects in countries with high solar radiation, as e.g. India.

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HEALTH RISK ASSESSMENT OF INHALABLE BIOAEROSOLS IN DIFFERENT MICROENVIRONMENTS

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Keywords: INDOOR-OUTDOOR, BIOAEROSOLS, SIZE DYNAMICS, HEALTH RISKS

INTRODUCTION

Bioaerosols are ubiquitous in the natural and human environment, including bacteria, fungi, and other microorganisms, with aerodynamic diameters between 0.01 and 100 μm . According to reports, 5–10% of the total suspended particles (TSPs) and around 24% of the total airborne particles were devoted to bioaerosols (Myers et al., 2020; Lal et al., 2017). The concentration of indoor bioaerosols is primarily due to the outdoor ambient air, indoor air conditioning systems, and many human activities, such as talking, sneezing, coughing, and walking. Thus, indoor and outdoor environments are interlinked to each other (Myers et al., 2020). Pyrri et al. 2020 reported that bioaerosols' indoor-to-outdoor ratio (I/O) is essential in estimating their origins. People spend most of their time (90% or above) in indoor settings, viz. houses, schools, and workplaces, and exposure to these high loading of bioaerosols may cause infectious and chronic diseases to the inhabitants (Noda et al., 2022; Dai et al., 2022). The present investigation aimed to study indoor and outdoor airborne bioaerosol levels, size dynamics, and health risks in different residential microenvironments in Pune.

METHODS

Size-segregated aerosol sampling was carried out for bacterial and fungal aerosols in different microenvironments i.e., indoor and outdoor, using a six-stage viable cascade impactor sampler (ACI, Tisch Environmental) in the aerodynamic size ranges, $\geq 7.1 \mu\text{m}$, 7.0-4.7 μm , 4.7-3.3 μm , 3.3-2.1 μm , 2.1-1.1 μm , and 1.1-0.65 μm at two residential site i.e., S-1: Sanghvi and S-2: Pashan, Pune. This study was conducted from January to February 2023, representing the winter season. The sampling was carried out at a breathing height of 1.5 m for 20 minutes at a flow rate of 28.3 L/min. This time is considerably standard to acquire the required number of colony-forming units. Bioaerosols were collected over Petri plates (90 mm) containing sterile media of nutrient Agar for bacteria and sabouraud dextrose agar for fungal fractions. Collected samples were incubated at 37°C for 24 h and 48 h for bacterial and fungal samples, respectively. After the desired duration of agar incubation, diverse macroscopically visual growth of microorganisms on a solid culture medium is counted as a number of colonies, which is referred to as a Colony Forming Unit (CFU). Finally, bioaerosol concentration was calculated in terms of $\text{CFU}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ was estimated using eq.1

$$\text{Bioaerosol concentration} \left(\frac{\text{CFU}}{\text{m}^3} \right) = \frac{\text{Number of colonies (CFU)}}{\text{Flow rate (28.3 LPM)} \times \text{Time}} \quad (1)$$

Health risk assessment, according to the US-EPA, 2009 for estimating the non-carcinogenic health risk of bioaerosols from inhalation pathway for all age groups (i.e., infants, children, adults, and elderly) was also employed in the present study. Detail of parameters and formulae is published elsewhere (Chalvatzaki et al., 2023; Cipoli et al., 2023).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

TOTAL BIOAEROSOLS CONCENTRATIONS: Fig.1. depicts the indoor and outdoor concentrations of bacterial and fungal aerosols in both study locations. Quantification of bioaerosols showed interesting results, and it was found that the average bioaerosol concentration was lower at the site, S-1, than at S-2. The indoor-to-outdoor (I/O) ratios of bacterial aerosols at S-1 and S-2 were 1.25 and 1.09, respectively. Overall, indoor bacterial aerosol concentrations were higher than outdoors, whereas in fungal concentrations, contrary results has been observed (outdoor>indoor). Unlike fungi, human activities can strongly influence indoor bacterial bioaerosol concentrations. In comparison with the WHO guidelines, the reported concentration of bacterial aerosols was found to be 2-3 times elevated, while fungal aerosols met the standards of the WHO, which recommended that a maximum of 500 colony-forming units of bacterial and fungal bioaerosols is acceptable in a residential setting (WHO, 1988; Chalvatzaki et al., 2023).

SIZE-DISTRIBUTION OF BIOAEROSOLS IN INDOOR AND OUTDOOR SETTINGS:Fig. 2a–d depicts the fraction of culturable bacterial and fungal bioaerosols collected on each stage of the six-stage Andersen cascade impactor. Bacterial and fungal aerosols showed different size distributions. Indoor and outdoor bacterial aerosols at size bin $>7 \mu\text{m}$ were 15–17% of the total in both study locations. Most indoor bacterial bioaerosols were concentrated at size $0.65 \mu\text{m}$ (34–41%), while outdoor bacterial aerosols were concentrated at sizes $3.1 \mu\text{m}$ (15–24%) and $0.65 \mu\text{m}$ (7–28%) of the total, respectively. Overall, bacterial aerosol concentrations were dominant at $0.65 \mu\text{m}$. **HEALTH RISK ASSESSMENT OF BIOAEROSOLS :**The non-carcinogenic health risk is represented by the hazard quotient HQ. The hazard quotients of bioaerosols for all age groups i.e., infants, children, adults, and elderly, are shown in Fig. 3. All the HQ values of bacterial aerosols exceeded the recommended limits ($\text{HQ}>1$) for all age groups in both settings. While HQ values of fungal aerosols met the recommended limits for all age groups in both settings. The higher HQ levels were found for the children age group, followed by infants, adults, and the elderly. The higher HQ levels for the children age group indicate that this age group is at risk due to exposure to bioaerosols.

CONCLUSION

The present study’s findings revealed that bacterial aerosols concentration was 2–3 times more elevated, while fungal aerosols met the standards of the WHO guidelines (500 CFU.m^{-3}). Bacterial aerosol concentrations were predominant at stage 6 ($0.65 \mu\text{m}$), while the fungal aerosols were least at stage 6 ($0.65 \mu\text{m}$). Moreover, higher HQ levels were found for the children age group, followed by infants, adults, and the elderly. The higher HQ levels for the children age group indicate that this age group is at risk due to exposure to bioaerosols.

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PM₁ BOUND HEAVY METALS AND HEALTH RISK ASSESSMENT IN URBAN ENVIRONMENT IN AGRA CITY

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INTRODUCTION

Particulate matter (PM) in the atmosphere is a complex mixture of solid and liquid particles suspended in the air consisting of a diverse range of chemical compounds that adversely affects the human health. PM comprises chemical species like heavy metals, ions, Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) and organic compounds [1]. As a result of several anthropogenic activities, substantial amounts of chemical species are continuously expelled into the atmosphere in the form of PM. Cu, Zn, Ba, Pb, Mn, Mo, and Ni are commonly utilised as vehicle source indicators [2]. Heavy metal exposure in atmospheric PM has been related to a variety of health issues, including respiratory and cardiovascular disease, cancer, and neurological disorders [3]. Due to the presence of elements such as Cd, Cr, Cu, Mn, Pb, V, and Zn, high concentrations of PM_{2.5} in ambient air can induce lung disease, heart disease, and premature death in humans [4,5,6,7]. The health risks depend on specific heavy metal, the concentration in the PM, and the duration and frequency of exposure. Children, the elderly, and individuals with pre-existing health conditions are particularly vulnerable to the effects of heavy metals in atmospheric PM. Heavy metal concentrations in ambient air can be considerably altered by atmospheric conditions. Thus, the relationship between heavy metals and meteorological parameters is investigated in order to account for the change associated with meteorological parameters.

METHODS

1) Site Description: The sampling for the study was conducted in Agra at Sikandra an urban site. Agra lies near the Thar Desert, which occupies two-thirds of its western boundary. In Agra Summers are hot and dry, with temperature ranging from 25 to 47 °C and relative humidity levels ranging from 14 to 50% respectively, while winters are typically cold and humid with humidity levels between 56 and 90%. The prevailing winds blow mostly from the west or northwest during winter. Sikandra, an urban site with a population of approximately 102,493 is also surrounded by various industries, including leather, chemicals, packaging, tire, Exide battery, and shoe factories. Sikandra has been chosen as one of the sampling sites for the study. 2) Sample collection and the measurement: The sampling of PM₁ was conducted for a period of one year i.e., December, 2021 to November, 2022. A high volume Sampler (Envirotech APM 577) was utilised to capture PM₁ samples. It was set to a continuous flow rate of 10 L/min for 24 hours, and glass fibre filter paper with a 47mm diameter was employed to collect samples. The filters were weighed before and after sampling to determine mass concentrations using a Mettler Microbalance. Sample was collected weekly and simultaneously at both the sites. Before and after the sample collection the filter paper was wrapped in aluminium foil, kept in zip lock bags, and stored in a freezer at -4°C until the extraction and analysis. Meteorological parameters like wind speed, wind direction for Sikandra (urban site) were recorded from CPCB (<https://app.cpcbcr.com/ccr/#/caaqm-dashboard-all/caaqm-landing/datadays>) [8]. The mass concentration of PM in the ambient air was determined gravimetrically by the difference in the mass of the filter before and after the sampling the filter papers. 3) Extraction of metals: A quarter of the sample loaded filter paper was used for microwave-assisted acid digestion (Microwave Go Plus, Anton Paar) in 6 ml HNO₃ (69%). After digestion, the extract was transferred to pre-cleaned PTFE bottles and made up to 25 ml with deionised water. Concentration of metals was quantitatively determined by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES, Agilent). Extracted sample transferred to polyethylene bottles for later analysis. Fig 1 depicts the location of the site.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1) Levels of PM₁ bound heavy metal concentration: The levels of PM₁ concentrations at the sampling locations, Sikandra exhibited the following trend: Winter > post-Monsoon > summer (Fig 2.). All the seasonal concentrations failed to achieve the air quality standard limits set for PM_{2.5} (60 µg/m³ set by the NAAQs). meteorological conditions and vice versa. The concentration of K was found in adequate amount which clearly indicates the dominance of biomass burning. Heavy metals like Ni, Pb, and Co were spotted in samples collected at Sikandra which are known carcinogenic metals. Heavy metal concentration was found

to be higher in winter than in summer. In terms of carcinogenic heavy metals, the pattern observed $Pb > Ni > Ni$. Similar studies in other countries, such as China [9], India [10], and Italy [12], found that the mean concentration of metals was higher in winter than in summer. 2) Health risk assessment of heavy metals in PM₁. The health risk assessment method for the estimation of the non-cancer and cancer risks from exposure to heavy metals (Cu, Cd, Cr, Fe, Mn, Ni, Pb, and Zn) in PM₁ was based on the USEPA human health evaluation method [14]. Exposure to heavy metals in humans can occur by ingestion, inhalation, or superficial routes [15,16]. The average daily dose of human exposure was calculated for each metal and inhalation exposure route as follows: $ADD_{inh} = C * InhR * EF * ED / BW * AT$. where ADD_{inh} is the average daily dose of each metal in PM₁ through the inhalation, C is the amount of heavy metal in PM₁ in ambient air ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$); ED is the exposure duration (days), BW is the body weight of the exposed group (kg); AT is the averaging time (days); EF is the exposure frequency (days/year). An EF of 350 days per year was used to calculate the lifetime exposure of human.

Fig 1. Location of Sikandra an Urban Sampling Site

Fig 2. Seasonal Variation of PM₁ at an urban site

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the analysis of PM₁ during study period and the samples collected from urban area of Agra city, India, PM₁ concentrations were extremely high in winter season in urban site. The site failed to meet the air quality limits ($60 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in standard) set by NAAQS ($60 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for PM_{2.5} standard limits) in Winter and Post-Monsoon and summer. Heavy metals at urban site in PM₁ during the study period were of serious concern as Cr, Ni, and Pb in the urban area areas failed to meet the air quality standard. Raw coal combustion (Pb, Zn, Cu, and Cr) was the primary source of heavy metals in PM₁ at the sub-urban site. The principal sources of heavy metals at the urban site were coal combustion (Pb, Zn, and Ni), industrial emissions (Ni, Cu), road and soil dust (Mn and Cr), and traffic emissions (Cu and Zn). The heavy metal values obtained were compared to the WHO air quality criteria and the USEPA regulatory guideline. It is important to note that the National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQS) only has an exposure limit for Pb. Note that Mn and Zn recommended values were not seen in the literature.

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BIOAEROSOL PROFILING AT TWO CONTRASTING LOCATIONS IN THE NORTH-WESTERN HIMALAYAN REGION: IMPLICATIONS ON CLIMATE AND HUMAN HEALTH

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Keywords: BIOAEROSOLS, BACTERIAL AND FUNGAL DIVERSITY, NORTH-WESTERN HIMALAYAN REGION (NWHR), CLIMATE, HUMAN HEALTH

INTRODUCTION

Bioaerosols are cosmopolitan in the earth's atmosphere, whereas, majority of them are present in the lower atmosphere (Bowers et al. 2013). Microorganisms present in air have long been associated with aerosols. The so called bio-aerosols contain bacteria, fungi, pollens, viruses, algae, protists (Tang et al. 2022). Bioaerosols like bacteria, fungi, plant materials and their associated cell wall material are capable of causing allergies or respiratory problems (Beggs et al. 2017). Bioaerosols significantly influence the atmospheric system and hydrological cycle by acting as a cloud condensation nuclei as well as ice nuclei and have direct implications on the human health and agricultural productivity (Frohlich Nowoisky et al. 2016). Airborne microbial diversity is still unexplored as compared to soil and water. The diversity of fungi in air is not well known. The reason behind poor understanding of microbial diversity remains in the fact that microbial diversity cannot be fully characterised by using culture based techniques as well as direct microscopy but, with recent advances in this field characterization using high-throughput sequencing can be done which gives unprecedented insight in the diversity of microbes (Despres et al. 2012).

METHODS

Aerosol sampling was done in Jammu (Sainik Colony) in November- December 2019 and March 2020 by using MOUDI II 120R sampler and in Jammu (Greater Kailash) and Katra in January-February, 2021 and June-July- 2021 using and Handy Total Suspended Particulate (TSP) sampler. Aerosol samples were stored at 4 °C until further processing. Direct DNA extraction from aerosol loaded filters was performed followed by high throughput Next Generation Sequencing for bioaerosol diversity.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The analysis of amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) showed dominance of phylum Ascomycota, Basidiomycota and Mucoromycota with dominant fungal species *Schizophyllum commune*, *Aspergillus penicilloides* and *Mycosphaerella tassiana*. While in case of bacteria, the dominance of phylum Proteobacteria, Firmicutes and Actinobacteria was observed with prominent species viz. *Tremblaya princeps*, *Erwinia dispersa* and *Erwinia soli*. The characteristics of bacterial and fungal communities varied in different seasons over the Himalayas while archae were rare. The observed higher bacterial and fungal diversity in winters can be attributed to lower Planetary Boundary Layer

(PBL) however multiple factors govern the concentration and composition of bioaerosols in the atmosphere. A negative correlation was seen with temperature and concentration of bioaerosols. The species level assessment in this pilot study showed ice nucleating and disease causing bioaerosols over the NWHR.

CONCLUSIONS

The bioaerosol profiling presented in this work will help in understanding the role and contribution of bioaerosols in modulating climate and understanding their implications on human health and overall ecosystem over the NWHR. The data generated in this study will serve as a valuable resource for future studies, facilitating the development of targeted strategies for bioaerosol monitoring, risk assessment, and mitigation in this ecologically sensitive region.

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MODELLING OF HEALTH RISKS EXPOSURE IN INDIAN CITIES DUE TO CRITERIA AIR POLLUTANTS

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Abstract

Both indoor and outdoor air pollution in 2016 caused an estimated 7 million deaths or one in nine deaths globally. Better understanding of the relationship between ambient concentration of criteria air pollutants and health risk holds the key for exploration of suitable mitigation measures. Key metropolitan cities in India including Kolkata, Pune, Chennai, Ahmadabad, Hyderabad and Bangalore reported health risk values for the categories of respiratory mortality, cardio-vascular mortality, total mortality, respiratory morbidity (COPD hospital admission) and Cardio-vascular morbidity (hospital admission) in the range of 5042-10757; 4305-8672; 3262-5713; 74638-183324; 90173-147408, respectively. In the present study, we assessed health risk values of the above categories for 57 Indian cities, attributable by criteria air pollutants (SO₂, NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}) have been examined by following the WHO-specified approach similar to that of AirQ+ model. Population data were obtained from respective official websites of civic bodies by considering the average incremental growth rate. The results indicate that Delhi (having ~ 27 million populations), among all the cities considered in the study, exhibits the highest health risk values of 32033, 35579, 24938, 780439 and 547384 for the above-mentioned categories. At least 15 out of 57 cities indicate low-to-moderate values of health risks for population ranging from 0.1 to 1.5 million. The number of health risks is found proportional to ambient concentration of criteria pollutants as well as population size. More details about the model and results will be presented.

Keywords: *AirQ+ Model, Air pollution; Exposure; Health risks, Mortality, Morbidity*

HEALTH BURDEN ASSOCIATED WITH AMBIENT PARTICULATE MATTER EXPOSURE IN INDIA: A STUDY FROM GBD-2019 DATASET

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Keywords: *Particulate matter, Health burden, India, Respiratory diseases*

INTRODUCTION

Particulate matter (PM) of various size fractions imposes intense deterioration in the ambient air quality and public health in India(Chatterjee et al., 2023). Aerosols of various fine and coarse fractions can be exerted into the ambient environment through various natural and anthropogenic sources; however, anthropogenic contribution deteriorates the air quality intensely. Subsequently, the prevalence of aerosols imposes a severe public health burden across the country that can exacerbate morbidity and mortality. This study aims to delineate the health burden of respiratory-related diseases estimated by GBD-2019 possibly caused by Ambient particulate matter in India from 2010 to 2019.

METHODS

For delineating the possible health burden caused by PM prevalence in India, we utilized *Global burden of diseases (GBD-2019)* data to obtain further insights. *GBD-2019* provides a publicly accessible database for obtaining the burden of 369 different diseases in 205 countries mapped to 87 risk factors(Vos et al., 2020). The estimate is provided in terms of multiple quantities such as mortality, DALY, YLL and YLD whereas each quantity of estimate is categorized by sex and 23 age categories as well. We used the number of deaths as an estimate parameter of the health burden caused by two respiratory diseases COPD and LRTI through PM exposure.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

COPD, a respiratory illness caused primarily by smoking and exposure to PM and toxic gases that subsequently impact morbidity and mortality. Acute and Chronic exposure to PM leads to COPD exacerbation that is characterized by pulmonary inflammation, lung function impairment, and emphysematous changes. Exposure to PM is one of the primary risk factors that is associated with LRTI. The DALY of global LRTI burden through PM2.5 exposure on children under the age of 14 and adults aged more than 70 was estimated to be 41 years per 1000 populations(Asri et al., 2021).

Figure 1.23 Number of Deaths caused by COPD and LRTI through PM exposure in India from 2010-2019.

Altogether COPD and LRTI caused 10.5 lakh deaths in India in 2019 in which exposure to PM alone was responsible for 3.75 lakh deaths. TM_{copd} increased by 33% in 2019 when compared to 2010. Whereas in $TM_{copd/pm}$ a similar trend was identified but with a 70% increase from 2010 to 2019 (Fig. 1.1). Moreover, the percentage contribution to TM_{copd} by $TM_{copd/pm}$ increased from 27.4% to 36.5%. Whereas TM_{lrti} declined considerably by 21.6% in 2019 in comparison with 2010. Yet, $TM_{lrti/pm}$ caused more number of deaths in 2019 when compared to 2010 with the highest number of deaths in 2014. When segregated into different age groups people aged more than 50 were at higher risk of having

COPD, whereas concerning LRTI in addition to the age of >50, children of age less than four were also found to be at high risk (Fig. 1.2).

Figure 1.24 $TM_{lrti/pm}$ in different age groups in India from 2010 to 2019

Abbreviations: COPD, Chronic Obstructive Respiratory Diseases; LRTI, Lower Respiratory Tract Infections; TM_{copd} , Total number of deaths by the cause of COPD; $TM_{copd/pm}$, Total Number of deaths by the cause of COPD attributed to the risk factor ambient PM pollution; TM_{lrti} , Total number of deaths by the cause of LRTI; $TM_{lrti/pm}$, Total Number of deaths by the cause of LRTI attributed to the risk factor ambient PM pollution.

CONCLUSIONS

We utilized the GBD-2019 dataset to delineate the health burden of COPD and LRTI through ambient particulate matter exposure. PM attributed mortality by COPD and LRTI exhibited a significant increase in India in the study period which can further intensify the health risk. Various implications we arrived at may help understand the severity of PM exposure and emphasize the formation of effective strategies required in air quality management.

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CHARACTERIZATION OF AMBIENT BIOLOGICAL AEROSOLS OVER DIBRUGARH

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Keywords: PARTICULATE MATTER, BIOAEROSOL, SEM-EDX.

INTRODUCTION

Bioaerosols are essential components of ambient particulate matter (PM) with a significant impact on ecosystem growth, evolution, and dynamics, and play an important role in the interactions between the atmosphere, biosphere, climate, and public health (Després *et al.*, 2012). It accounts for approximately 20-40% of atmospheric aerosols (Jaenicke, 2005) and has an impact on the Earth's energy budget in both direct and indirect ways. Pollen grains act as cloud condensation nuclei locally, affecting cloud formation. Decaying vegetation, marine plankton, proteins, and fungi can all behave as efficient ice nuclei (Scheel *et al.*, 2016). Bioaerosols affect both indoor and outdoor air quality. Those microorganisms spread infectious diseases like allergies, asthma, cancer, and respiratory disorders in humans (Kim *et al.*, 2018). Northeast India, one of the major biodiversity hotspots of the world, has been explored for biological aerosol through a campaign mode observation (Pathak *et al.*, 2022). Based on microscopic technique, 4-20% pollens, 1-24% animal debris, 1-17% fungal spores and culturable microbial populations in terms of colony forming unit (CFU) count of 20.83–632.45 CFU/m³. Further, 184 OTUs (operational taxonomic units) of bacterial count with 28,028 abundance count consisting of 7 major phylum, 6 classes, 10 orders, 15 families, 13 genera, and 8 species were observed through a DNA-based metagenomic approach. The present study uses a spectroscopic technique to characterise Bioaerosols over Dibrugarh (27.4°N, 94.6°E, 111 a.m.s.l), a semi-urban location in the upper Brahmaputra valley of Assam.

METHODS

The samples are collected at Dibrugarh University, Dibrugarh using a high-volume sampler on a quartz fibre filter during pre-monsoon, 2022. The filter paper was desiccated for 24 hours and weighed before and after sampling by a microbalance with sensitivity ± 0.001 mg. Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectrometer (EDX), INCAx Sight microanalysis system (Oxford Instruments, Model 7582), hyphenated with a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) (JEOL JSM 6390 LV) have been used to understand the elemental and morphological characteristics of the PM.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The total mass concentrations of PM collected on the quartz fibre filter ranged from 85.37-185.19 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ during pre-monsoon season. SEM-EDX analysis revealed the presence of both biological and non-biological aerosols having Carbon, Oxygen, Magnesium, Silicon, Sodium, Aluminium, and Potassium as the major elements in the samples. Some hazardous elements like Chromium, Copper, Zinc, Iron, and Titanium were also identified. The biological aerosols were classified based on the clustering rule: $(\text{C}+\text{O}) > 75\%$ and $1\% < \text{P}; \text{K}; \text{Cl} < 10\%$ (Matthias-Maser and Jaenicke, 1994). The different types of biological aerosols such as animal debris (a, f), different types of pollens (b, e), microorganisms (c, d), and fungi (g, h) (Figure 1) have been identified. The high Si value in the spectrums is mainly attributed to the characteristics of the filter paper and the high concentration of dust aerosols. The region rich in tea gardens (~22%), huge forest cover (~12%), and vast agricultural land mass (~43%) (Subba *et al.*, 2023) makes it vulnerable to biological aerosols.

Figure 1. SEM-EDX spectrum analysis of different types of bioaerosols present in aerosol samples collected over Dibrugarh during pre-monsoon season. Identified bioaerosols include animal debris (a, and f), different types of pollen (b, and e), microorganisms (c, and d), fungi (g, and h).

CONCLUSIONS

The region is semi-urban, and the observed level of PM concentration is quite alarming for the site. The SEM-EDX analysis of aerosol samples collected during pre-monsoon over Dibrugarh reveals the presence of primary bioaerosols like animal debris, pollens and fungi. The region being mostly vegetated serves as a good source of primary bioaerosols, which can have a significant impact on aerosol-cloud interaction.

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RISK ASSESSMENT FROM PM₁ ASSOCIATED BIOLOGICAL AND CHEMICAL COMPONENTS IN AMBIENT AIR OF INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN

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Keywords: Risk Assessment; Bioaerosol; Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon (PAHs); Metals.

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution is the fourth-highest global risk factor for early mortality (*State of Global Air*, 2020). The PM₁, associated with air pollution, is related to different respiratory and cardiovascular health issues, carcinogenicity, and mutagenicity in the exposed population (Jarvis et al., 2018). Due to very small size, PM₁ reaches deep inside the alveolar region and enters systemic circulation, causing toxicity (Gupta et al., 2023). The PM-bound components (like Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), metals, along with viable bioaerosols (bacteria, fungi), etc.) pose severe health hazards, especially in sensitive populations. This study aims to investigate the synergistic health risk from different viable and chemical fractions of PM₁ in the IGP region.

METHODS

The PM₁ sampling was done on Quartz and Teflon filters for metals and PAHs analysis inside IIT Kanpur. For bioaerosol analysis, three different agar media were used for capturing Gram-positive Bacteria (GPB): Mannitol Salt Agar, Gram-negative bacteria (GNB): MacConkey Agar, and Fungi: Sabouraud-Chloramphenicol Agar (Gupta et al., 2021). The sampling was carried out from November 2017 to October 2018, three times a week on quartz filters and once a week on Teflon filters. Also, the bioaerosol sampling was done in tandem with the quartz sampling, three times a week. Both the samplers were developed in-house at IIT Kanpur. The metals were analysed in Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometer, and the PAHs were investigated via High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (Gupta et al., 2023).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The average concentration of PAHs in terms of Benzo[a]Pyrene was found to be $115.2 \pm 150.4 \text{ ng/m}^3$. The estimated Incremental Lifetime Cancer Risk (ILCR) from USEPA PAHs was $3.6 * 10^{-5}$ and $2.1 * 10^{-5}$, for adults and children, respectively. However, if we extrapolate this to a larger matrix of PAHs present in ambient air by considering a factor of 6.67 (Gupta et al., 2023), the ILCR was $>10^{-4}$, suggesting severe health risks. Among carcinogenic metals, only Cr and Pb were detected in significant amounts. The cancer risk due to Cr(VI) (taking Cr(VI)/Cr = 0.39) was high ($>10^{-4}$), while for Pb, it was negligible ($<10^{-7}$) for both adults and children. Thus, synergistic cancer risk from these chemical components was very high in IGP ($>10^{-4}$). The non-cancerous risk from bioaerosols and metals was calculated through the hazard quotient. The hazard quotient values in Table 1 show serious health risks from Cr(VI) for children. Although health risk due to bioaerosols in terms of number concentration was non-serious, its detailed qualitative assessment can shed information on respiratory allergies and infections.

Table 1. Non-carcinogenic risk assessment from PM₁-bound metals and bioaerosols

Hazard Quotient	Pb	Cr(VI)	Bacteria	Fungi
Adult	$4.5 * 10^{-2}$	0.819	0.529	0.32
Child	$8.8 * 10^{-2}$	1.833		

Figure 1. Cancerous risk from PM₁-bound components

CONCLUSIONS

The study shows major carcinogenic risks from PM-bound components ($>10^{-4}$) in IGP. The metals, especially Cr(VI), contribute heavily to PM toxicity for both cancerous and non-cancerous risk assessment. As a result, the present investigation amply demonstrated the necessity of lowering Cr emission sources in the Central IGP region. In the case of PAHs, roughly half of the assessed PAHs were shown to be carcinogenic. The ILCR values for USEPA PAHs were discovered to be of the order of 10^{-5} , whereas the estimated risk owing to all environmental PAHs was of the order of 10^{-4} , which is extremely high. For bioaerosols, the health hazard was not significant, as the IIT Kanpur campus is exceptionally clean, and there aren't any open sites where bioaerosols might breed (such as open drains, dumping grounds, or other anthropogenic sources of bioaerosols). More bioaerosol studies from different occupational and non-occupational environments can give a much better picture of bioaerosol pollution in this region, as the macroenvironment of the site heavily influences its concentration.

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DISPARITY IN AMBIENT AIR POLLUTION EXPOSURE AMONG INDIAN SUB-POPULATIONS

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Keywords: Disparity, Atkinson Index, Health burden, Environmental justice.

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution is the largest environmental risk factor globally.¹ The exposure to fine particulate matter (an aerodynamic diameter of $<2.5 \mu\text{m}$) is attributed to 0.67 million (95% UI: 0.55-0.79) premature deaths in India.² The population-weighted mean exposure is one of the key determinants of health burden estimates,³ which is strongly dependent on the geographic distribution of the population sub-groups. Evolving studies from the developed countries (US and China) have captured the spatial variation of this phenomenon where marginalized sub-groups are turned to be more exposed as compared to their privileged counterparts.^{4,5} However, a few studies have also estimated the temporal variation and shown that various source contributions of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ have differential impacts leading to disparity among the sub-groups.^{6,7} In India, the exposure levels vary spatially depending upon the proximity of the pollution sources, topography, and climatology.⁸ For long-term exposure, the sub-groups who are exposed to higher exposure levels, may develop a larger health burden. To our knowledge, the scenario of exposure disparity and its spatio-temporal variations have never been studied before in the developing countries, including India, which is a socially diverse country. Addressing this gap is extremely necessary to identify the vulnerable sub-groups and the hotspot regions of larger disparity, and to feed the policymakers to prioritize the key emission sources for better air quality, alleviating the environmental injustice and health inequality among the population sub-groups across Indian states.

METHODS

Datasets: Exposure data: Air pollution estimates were satellite-derived annual average $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations for 2015-16 and 2019-21. We relied on satellite retrieval as India's in-situ measurements were not adequate to have a national representation. We used 23 climatological, sociodemographic, and land cover data as inputs in the random forest (RF) model to predict the aerosol optical depth (AOD) and from there, the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration at $1 \times 1 \text{ km}$ resolution.⁹ Our predicted estimate showed a very strong correlation with the ground-based measurements ($R^2=0.95$ and RMSE of $9.06 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). **Demographic information:** Demographic data were the population estimates from the National Family Health Survey (NFHS) by gender, wealth, education, ethnicity, and types of cooking fuel usage in the households.

Estimation of Population-Weighted (PW) Mean Exposure : Population-weighted mean exposure (PWME) was calculated for different sub-populations combining the socio-demographic and exposure data for both urban and rural regions for two NFHS rounds,

$$E_{ij} = \frac{\sum_1^n C_i \times P_i \times SW_i}{\sum_1^n P_i \times SW_i}$$

Where E_{ij} is the PWME of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ for sub-population i in state j , C_i is the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration for sub-group i in each cluster, P_{ij} is the survey population of sub-group i , SW_i is the assigned sample-weights for every cluster divided by 1 million, and n is the number of cluster in that state.

Equation metrics to estimate exposure disparity (Atkinson Index): We integrated the demographic information for each sub-group with the exposure estimates. Lastly, we quantified the exposure disparity using the AI metrics.⁵

$$\text{AI} = 1 - \exp(-f_i)$$

f_i represents the population fraction of sub-group i in a state, E_{ij} represents the PWME of each sub-group i in the state j , E_{state} indicates the PWME of that state considering the entire population.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

We quantified the exposure disparity using the Atkinson Index among the sub-populations across Indian states, stratified by gender, wealth, education, ethnicity, and cooking fuel types. We classified the AIs into quantile values (first to fifth) and found the spatial heterogeneity in exposure inequality in the urban and rural regions (Fig. 1). Among the sub-population categories, we found higher disparity across the wealth and ethnic sub-groups, and households using different types of cooking fuel. A significant disparity was observed discretely in the states of the central and southern peninsula, and NE region. We did not find higher disparity in IGP states, possibly due to large population density, concentrated survey clusters, and homogeneous mixing for the sub-groups within the clusters. On the other hand, a larger disparity was observed in other parts of India where population density is comparatively lesser and distribution is spread across different levels of sub-group categories. This could be one possible reason for getting wider exposure distribution in the rural regions than to urban counterparts; and larger exposure disparity in other parts of India than to IGP states. From NFHS-4 to -5, we found that exposure disparity has increased among the sub-groups stratified by education, ethnicity, and households using various types of cooking fuel. In general, the disparity has increased in the central and southern states; however, a significant increment in environmental inequality was observed in IGP and western Indian states as well (gender and education sub-groups).

CONCLUSIONS

Our study provides the first national scale analysis on air pollution exposure disparity among Indian sub-populations, stratified by gender, wealth, education, ethnicity, and cooking-fuel types in the households. We further estimate the urban-rural disparity at two timestamps following the NFHS rounds. We found that the disproportionate impact of air pollution exposure is different in India as compared to the developed countries (US). The increasing AI metrics in recent years indicates that the relative difference has grown although there was an absolute reduction in pollution concentration. Targeting locally important sources of PM_{2.5} for mitigation could alleviate the exposure inequality. Overall, our findings suggest that continued improvements in air quality, sub-groups' lifestyle, and the healthcare system to eliminate societal barriers may reduce the PM_{2.5} exposure disparities; which require additional deprived-class oriented policies and interventions to counter the underlying causes of environmental injustice to ensure India could achieve health equity and avoid large health burden in the near future.

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BIOAEROSOL: THE NEXT PANDEMIC? WHAT WE NEED TO PROTECT OURSELVES

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Keywords: Bioaerosol, Sources, Impact on human health.

INTRODUCTION

Bioaerosols are airborne particles of biological origin, such as bacteria, fungi, viruses, pollen, and their fragments. They can be found in both indoor and outdoor environments. Bioaerosols can be generated by a variety of sources, including: Human activities (Coughing, sneezing, talking, and breathing), Natural processes (Wind, rain, and other weather events can also release bioaerosols from soil, plants, and water). Some industrial processes (composting and waste treatment, can also release bioaerosols into the air) can all release bioaerosols into the air.

Bioaerosols can have a variety of impacts on human health, the environment, and materials. They can cause respiratory infections, allergies, and other health problems. They can also contribute to the formation of clouds and fog in the form of cloud condensation nuclei

METHODS

Biosampler was used for sample collection to be analysed for bioaerosol concentration in ambient air.

Samples collected

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Our site was dominated by gram –ve bacterial at a particular period of year. They are of particular important as they can induce strong inflammatory response and symptoms like fever, headache, coughing and respiratory distress.

CONCLUSIONS

A detailed study on this topic would provide a robust database for bioaerosol concentration in an urban coastal location which is Bhubaneswar. This data would be helpful to the governing body to create a standard guideline for bioaerosol concentration in ambient air.

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ESTIMATING DRY PARTICLE SIZES OF SALIVA DROPLETS USING SESSILE DROP TECHNIQUE FOR UNDERSTANDING THE SPREADING OF AIRBORNE DISEASES

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Keywords: Sessile drop, size, dry particle, nucleation model, hollow particle

INTRODUCTION

The alarming spread of covid-19 pandemic and its severe consequences have brought in a considerable need to understand and control airborne aerosol transmissions. Comprehensive modelling (Anand et al., 2022) approach of the droplet dynamics from the stage of release of infected droplets by a patient (through cough or sneeze) to their deposition inside the lung of a bystander strongly points to the role of the size of the virus laden particle. An important question in this regard is the shrinkage ratio of a droplet to its final residue. There is a large uncertainty in this size ratio varying from 16%-43% (e.g. Lieber et al., 2021) due to the different approaches followed in their determination. In view of its importance, herein we examine the shrinkage ratio of solution droplets containing NaCl and Glucose as solutes as well as human saliva. Controlled experiments based on “Sessile Drop-on-Super-Hydrophobic Surface (SDHSS)” approach is used to study evaporation and residue formation. Simultaneously, we model the shrinkage process using “droplet evaporation-solute diffusion-nucleation” models and compare with measurements.

METHODS

Experimental: The SDHSS drying approach involves placing droplets over a Super-Hydrophobic (SH) surface and examining their shrinkage over time under defined environment (Bamboriya and Tirumkudulu, 2023). The hydrophobic surface keeps the deposited drops almost spherical due to high contact angle and their evaporation is not affected by surface properties. Superhydrophobic (SH) glass surface was prepared by using a commercial spray (Glaco). A 5mL bottle sprayer was used to generate sessile micro-droplets (mostly 20 μm to 150 μm) of different suspensions on the SH surface and observed under 10X magnification of a microscope objective. Their drying under ambient conditions was recorded and the shrinkage ratio (final diameter/initial diameter) was estimated by using ImageJ[®] software. Along with human saliva, solutions of 0.8% w/v NaCl and 0.8% w/v Glucose (sugar) were subjected to sessile droplet drying and their shrinkage ratio (*SR*) was estimated. The reported *SR* and the associated standard error is obtained by averaging over of large number independent measurements.

Modeling: A mathematical model has been developed to predict the size of a dry particle formed from an airborne, evaporating solution drop. The model consists of solving mass and heat transfer equation for the evaporating drop coupled with equations for solute diffusion within the shrinking drop and solute precipitation from nucleation theory. Both prescribed critical supersaturation (Bandyopadhyay et al., 2015) and a more complex nucleation-cluster growth models have been applied and compared. Due to liquid evaporation, the supersaturation increases to a level at which solid crust is formed suddenly and the shrinkage ceases beyond this point. The *SR* is estimated as the ratio of the size of the crust to the original droplet size. Calculation have been made for NaCl and Glucose at initial concentration of 8 kg/m^3 and also for saliva assuming NaCl of 6.3 kg/m^3 . The molecular weight and equilibrium solubility are the crucial factors governing the shrinkage ratio.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Fig.1(a) illustrates modelling results for the rise in solute supersaturation ratio *S* (black and red lines) as the droplet shrinks (blue line) due to evaporation, for the case of NaCl. A sudden drop in the increasing *S* is due to the onset of solute nucleation along with crust formation, which does not shrink further. The model assumes this to be the dry particle size. This size is very close to that predicted by the prescribed critical supersaturation model. A shrinkage ratio of 0.27 is predicted for NaCl while values of 0.215 and 0.245 are obtained for Glucose and Saliva, respectively (Fig.1b). The experimental *SR* value (Fig.1b) for NaCl and Glucose are 0.28 (± 0.015) and 0.21 (± 0.02) respectively, which are remarkably close to the theoretical values. The avg. *SR* value for human saliva obtained from experiments was 0.22 (± 0.05) (Fig.1b) which is very close to the measurements

of Lieber et al. (2021) and Stiti et al. (2022), who used levitation devices to perform droplet drying. The model predicted value of 0.245 for saliva agrees reasonably well with the experimental value within error margin, although not as close as the other two cases. The SR values were also independent of initial diameters. Fig.1b also shows the compacted solute particle SRs calculated by using their solid densities: 0.156 for NaCl, 0.173 for Glucose and 0.144 for Saliva. The fact that the obtained SR are significantly larger than these values indicate that residue particles are likely to be hollow having far lower effective densities. These findings have parallels with the modelling study of Ozler et al., 2023.

Figure 1: (a) Diffusion modelling of a supersaturated solution (b) Comparison of experimental and theoretical SR values for NaCl, Glucose and Human saliva droplets

CONCLUSION

The study clearly demonstrates the usefulness of sessile drop technique to study residue formation from evaporating drops. The results strongly point to the formation of hollow residue particles having significantly lower effective densities as compared to compact NaCl. This will render the aerodynamic diameters lower by a factor of 2 or more having the twin effect of increasing their airborne residence time and deeper penetration into the lung. These findings have crucial implications to mechanistic models aiming to predict the risk of transmission of respiratory diseases in indoor spaces.

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THE IMPACT ASSESSING OF INDOOR BIOAEROSOLS ON HUMAN HEALTH: A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY

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Keywords- Bioaerosols; Indoor air Pollution; Environmental monitoring; Microbial analysis.

Indoor air is an important part of human health because people spend most of their lives in the environment. Among the many factors that affect indoor air, bioaerosols are receiving more attention due to their potential impact on human health. This research article presents a comprehensive study to evaluate the effects of indoor bioaerosols on human health in various indoor environments. This study used a multidisciplinary approach combining environmental monitoring, microbial analysis, and health assessment to provide a better understanding of the impacts of indoor bioaerosols in relation to human health.

Key points of this study include characterization of indoor bioaerosol, microbial diversity, and identification of potential health-related exposure through ingestion. To achieve this goal, a variety of indoor environments, including homes, workplaces, schools, and healthcare facilities, were investigated, accounting for different bioaerosol sources and conditions with the right layering.

The results of this study show a significant relationship between indoor bioaerosol exposure and adverse health conditions. Respiratory diseases, allergies, and possible links to infectious diseases are clearly identified health risks. Additionally, the study evaluated the effectiveness of different indoor air control strategies, such as ventilation, air filtration, and ventilation, in reducing the risk of bioaerosols.

This comprehensive research paper highlights the important role of indoor air quality control in reducing bioaerosol risk. Pay attention to people's health. The results presented here are intended to inform public health recommendations, design and care, and regulatory policies to reduce health risks. This study reveals the interactions between the indoor environment and human health, highlighting the importance of taking an integrated approach to improving the environment, indoor air, and ensuring people's health and comfort in various indoor spaces.

QUANTIFICATION OF AGE-SPECIFIC AEROSOL DEPOSITION IN THE HUMAN RESPIRATORY TRACT

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Keywords: Particulate Matter, tracheobronchial, Pulmonary, Indo-Gangetic Basin, Lobar

Introduction

Air pollution has become a global concern, and PM is considered a very significant air pollutant. The major physical traits of PM include size, mass, and number concentration. Based on size, PM is classified into coarse ($\leq 10 \mu\text{m}$), fine ($\leq 2.5 \mu\text{m}$), and ultrafine ($\leq 0.1 \mu\text{m}$) particles. Mass measurements are considered for coarse and fine PM (Kumar et al. 2007) while number concentration is used for ultrafine PM measurements. In humans, PM enters the airways through the nose or mouth. Once entered, PM will get deposited by direct contact in multiple regions of the lungs viz. head, tracheobronchial (TB), and pulmonary regions. In developing countries like India, PM Levels often exceed the legal standards, particularly in urban areas, and are highly associated with increased mortality and morbidity (Balakrishnan et al. 2013). Therefore, a study on the health risk of PM over a region like Agra is very pertinent (Gupta et al. 2020).

Method

The human health risk due to particulate matter was calculated using a new version of the previously used MPPD v3.04, namely MPPD. In the present study, Particulate matter i.e., PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and PM₁ was collected using Polltech dust samplers on the roof of the Technical College, Dayalbagh Educational Institute, Dayalbagh, Agra using filter paper as collecting surface.

Result and Discussion

The average PM values recorded during the study period are PM₁₀: 130.10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, PM_{2.5}: 76.10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and, PM₁: 28.10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The value of PM is quite higher than the standard set by WHO, USEPA, and NAAQS. The average of the recorded values of PM during the study period is considered for the deposition and clearance calculations in MPPD. The deposition fractions of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁ in each age category are presented in Table 1. For the given airway morphometry and PM properties, 89–99% of inhaled PM₁₀ is deposited in the human airways followed by PM_{2.5} (61–77%) and PM₁ (32–49%). The total deposition fraction is found to be highest for PM₁₀ followed by PM_{2.5}, and PM₁.

Table 1 -Total and regional deposition fraction of PM in different age categories.

Age	PM ₁				PM _{2.5}				PM ₁₀			
	Total	Head	TB	P	Total	Head	TB	P	Total	Head	TB	P
3months	0.44	0.22	0.09	0.18	0.66	0.23	0.12	0.3	0.93	0.51	0.42	0.01
28 months	0.40	0.25	0.03	0.12	0.63	0.31	0.6	0.25	0.89	0.6	0.22	0.06
3 Year	0.43	0.25	0.03	0.15	0.61	0.28	0.05	0.28	0.92	0.60	0.26	0.07
8 Year	0.50	0.25	0.04	0.21	0.73	0.27	0.06	0.40	0.95	0.63	0.30	0.04
9 Year	0.49	0.25	0.04	0.12	0.73	0.27	0.06	0.39	0.96	0.63	0.30	0.02
14 Year	0.40	0.20	0.04	0.16	0.66	0.26	0.56	0.33	0.95	0.68	0.21	0.06
18 Year	0.32	0.12	0.04	0.16	0.75	0.41	0.5	0.27	0.99	0.95	0.03	0.02
21 Year	0.33	0.12	0.03	0.18	0.77	0.41	0.05	0.30	0.99	0.95	0.04	0.01

The Size-segregated deposition of lobar fractions in infants, children, and adult categories has been also studied. All three PM sizes show high deposition fractions in the left lower lobe and right lower lobe while the least is observed in the right middle lobe.

The deposition mass per area visualization also plays an important role in knowing about the effect of PM on the human lungs. The calculated deposited mass visualization and deposited mass per area

visualization of human airways of different age categories with their airway geometry has been also calculated.

Conclusion

The mass concentration of PM_{10} , $PM_{2.5}$, and PM_1 has been found to be many times higher than recommended values set by WHO, USEPA, and, NAAQS. This age-specific model allows quantification of the total deposition fraction, total deposited mass and deposited mass per unit area, regional deposition fraction, lobe-wise deposition, and clearance during the post-exposure period. Total deposition of PM_{10} , $PM_{2.5}$, and PM_1 is high in children (8- and 9-year age group), followed by adults and infants. The deposits in the head and alveolars (except in adults) are dominated by PM_{10} . Fine particles ($PM_{2.5}$, and PM_1) are highly deposited in the pulmonary regions. Lobar deposition analysis showed that the lower lobes experience maximum deposition than the upper and middle lobes. Total lobe deposition is higher in the right lung than in the left lung. A 3-month-old will not spend 100% of their time indoors, even strapped to the chest or riding in a stroller, they receive all sorts of stimuli outside that they don't get indoors. This stimulation helps build the synaptic connections between cells in a baby's brain which are crucial to cognitive development. Since they spent some time outdoor, it is important to also calculate the deposition in the respiratory tract of a 3-month-old.

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CARBONACEOUS AEROSOLS

LIGHT ABSORPTION CHARACTERISTICS OF METHANOL-SOLUBLE AND WATER-SOLUBLE CARBONACEOUS FRACTIONS IN THE ATMOSPHERIC AEROSOLS

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Keywords: CARBONACEOUS AEROSOLS; ORGANIC CARBON; ABSORPTION COEFFICIENTS; ABSORPTION ANGSTROM EXPONENT

INTRODUCTION

Carbonaceous aerosols, which significantly impact the Earth's climate system are categorized as organic carbon (OC) and black carbon (BC), with BC being a powerful light absorber. Some OC, known as brown carbon (BrC), also absorbs light, and understanding its absorption is vital for climate analysis. Various methods exist to measure BrC, including molecular analysis, particle characterization, and optical techniques. Commonly used method for optical measurement of BrC is achieved through water or organic solvent extraction followed by BrC absorption measurement in the extracts using UV-visible spectroscopy. This method allows for the assessment of BrC absorbance without interference from BC. Typically, water along with methanol solvent has been extensively used to report BrC optical absorption properties. The choice of solvent is important and can lead to differences in values of absorption coefficients. Although water has low OC extraction efficiency, the absorption of light by water-soluble organic carbon (WSOC) has been considered as a proxy for BrC optical characteristics in many studies. However, methanol is known to extract more OC than water, ranging from 85% to 98% (Chen and Bond, 2010 and Liu et al., 2013). Measurements of the optical characteristics of MSOC and WSOC simultaneously can reveal vital information on their similarities and applicability. The present study focuses on Mumbai, examining the light-absorbing capabilities of WSOC and MSOC, comparing their properties to gain insights into BrC behavior in this urban area.

METHODS

In this study, particulate matter with a diameter less than 2.5 μm ($\text{PM}_{2.5}$) was collected in an urban area of Mumbai, India, known for its dense population and industrial activity. The sampling site was situated approximately 15 kilometres from the city centre, bounded by harbours and a national highway, and surrounded by industries including refineries, a large fertilizer complex, and a thermal power plant. Sampling was conducted twice a week for 24 hours each, from September 2017 to May 2018, totalling 62 samples. The collected $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ samples were analysed for WSOC and MSOC. Filter papers were split into two halves, one extracted with deionized water and the other with methanol solvent. These extracts were subsequently filtered, and organic carbon concentrations were determined. Light absorption properties of the extracts were assessed using a UV-visible spectrophotometer across a range of wavelengths. The absorption coefficients for MSOC and WSOC, factoring in the volume of solvent used, air volume over the filter area, and optical path length were determined as per the methodology prescribed in Liu et al., 2013. The concentration of the MSOC and WSOC along with the estimated absorption coefficients were used for determining the mass absorption cross-section. The angstrom absorption exponent (AAE) was estimated using the negative log-log slope of the absorption spectrum.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

During the sampling period in Mumbai, $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations ranged from 7 to 106 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, with an average of $56 \pm 24 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. MSOC consistently made up a larger portion of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ compared to WSOC, with average concentrations of $16 \pm 8 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and $13 \pm 6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, respectively. MSOC and WSOC concentrations showed a positive correlation throughout the sampling period, and the highest concentrations of both were observed during the winter season, coinciding with increased $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ levels. The absorption coefficients of MSOC and WSOC decreased with increasing wavelength, with MSOC

consistently exhibiting higher values than WSOC. This trend aligned with observations from other geographic locations. Daily variation in absorption coefficients at 365 nm plotted in figure 1(a) shows that MSOC had higher coefficients, approximately 1.57 times that of WSOC, indicating that methanol was more effective in extracting light-absorbing organic carbon. The study also explored the relationship between MSOC, WSOC, and brown carbon absorption coefficients. The brown carbon absorption coefficients were obtained from previous study (Rathod and Sahu, 2022). MSOC demonstrated a stronger correlation with brown carbon absorption coefficients ($R^2 = 0.62$) compared to WSOC ($R^2 = 0.38$) as shown in the figure 1(b). It emphasises the importance of MSOC in approximating brown carbon in the atmosphere. The AAE was calculated for MSOC and WSOC, with MSOC AAE ranging from 4.4 to 6.9 and WSOC AAE ranging from 4.5 to 8.6, suggesting strong wavelength dependency for WSOC. However, AAE values showed little seasonal variation, indicating consistent organic carbon sources at the sampling site. The mean MAC values (at 365 nm) for MSOC were found to be $1.41 \pm 0.76 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and for WSOC it was $1.03 \pm 0.39 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for the sampling period.

Figure 1. a) Variation of absorption coefficients for methanol and water-soluble organic carbon aerosols observed during the sampling period. b) The correlation graph of brown carbon absorption coefficients with methanol soluble organic carbon and water-soluble organic carbon at the sampling location.

CONCLUSIONS

The study contributes valuable insights into the optical properties of WSOC and MSOC in an urban context. The comparison of the optical characteristics of WSOC and MSOC, as well as their correlation with brown carbon, indicates that MSOC is a more accurate representation of atmospheric brown carbon.

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**SEASONAL VARIATION OF AEROSOL OPTICAL DEPTH OVER INDIA UNDER
FUTURISTIC CLIMATE SCENARIOS: AN IMPLICATION OF CARBONACEOUS AEROSOLS**

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Keywords: Aerosol Optical Depth, Carbonaceous Aerosols, Organic Carbon, Black Carbon, GEOS-Chem

INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols, including carbonaceous particles, have profound implications for human health, climate, and air quality in India, a nation experiencing rapid urbanization and population growth (Gunthe et al., 2021; Shekar Reddy & Venkataraman, 2000). These aerosols influence parameters like visibility, precipitation patterns, and air quality, with rising concentrations of sulfate, Black Carbon (BC), Organic Carbon (OC), dust, and Sea Salt (SS) particles over the Indian subcontinent (David et al., 2018). Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD), a key measure of particle concentration, has shown an increasing trend, particularly in densely populated regions like the Indo Gangetic Plain (IGP), impacting climate with rising temperatures and altered monsoon patterns (Cowan & Cai, 2011). These aerosols also pose health risks, contributing to respiratory and cardiovascular diseases (Yang et al., 2019). In light of India's commitment to reducing carbon emissions, this study examines the future trends in carbonaceous aerosols under Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs), focusing on RCP4.5 and RCP8.5. It reveals both current trends and future scenarios, emphasizing the urgency of emission reduction strategies to combat air pollution and improve air quality in India.

METHODS

This study employs version 12.2.1 of the GEOS-Chem 3-D global model, driven by 6-hourly assimilated meteorological data from NASA's Modern Era Retrospective Reanalysis2 (MERRA2). The simulation domain was nested over Asia (11°S-55°N, 60°-150°E), with a horizontal resolution of 0.5° × 0.625° and 47 vertical layers down to 0.01 hPa. Aerosol components encompass black carbon (BC), organic carbon (OC), sulfate-nitrate-ammonium, dust, and sea salt, simulated using standard GEOS-Chem methods. Simulations involve emissions from 2010 and future decades (2010-2100) under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios, driven by 2010 MERRA-2 meteorology. Anthropogenic emissions, including carbon monoxide, non-methane VOCs, sulfur dioxide, NO_x, ammonia, BC, and OC, are categorized into ten activities, with monthly scaling factors enhancing accuracy. Observations for model validation include AOD data from AERONET stations, MODIS measurements from Aqua and Terra satellites, and MERIS data from Envisat, converted to model resolution for assessing aerosol concentration simulations.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Under the RCP4.5 scenario, the AOD increases at a rate of 6.91% AOD per decade until the year 2030 and then there is a decrease of -8.76% AOD per decade. For the RCP8.5 scenario, on the other hand an increase of 8.72% AOD per decade through 2050 and a further decrease of -3.52% AOD per decade from 2050 to the end of the century is observed. The maximum AOD is observed over Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) in both scenarios. Under RCP8.5, 2020-2080 is the period with high AOD, mostly contributed by IGP and East India (EI). A gradual increase in AOD over Central India and some parts of South India and West India from 2030 is noticed, but the reduction in this region is also very much evident from 2090 until the end of the century. Similar to RCP8.5, high AOD is observed over IGP and EI until 2050 in RCP4.5, however a much higher reduction by the end of the century is evident in this scenario.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, these findings underscore the feasibility of future reductions in AOD levels. Although projected future changes in AOD due to carbonaceous aerosols under RCP scenarios provide us with important guidance for mitigation efforts, such projections are subject to uncertainty. However, realizing these potential demands stringent measures to be implemented, either to attain the objective out right or to effectively mitigate its impacts.

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SOURCE CHARACTERISTICS OF WATER-SOLUBLE ORGANIC AEROSOLS OVER SOUTH ASIA

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Keywords: AGED AEROSOLS, OXIDATION, DIRECT EMISSIONS, SPATIAL VARIATION.

INTRODUCTION

Water soluble organic carbon (WSOC) can act as cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) and influence cloud formation. Higher levels of WSOC can enhance the availability of CCN, affecting cloud droplet formation and cloud properties. This, in turn, impacts the reflection and absorption of solar radiation by the clouds, altering shortwave cloud forcing. It can also impact cloud properties indirectly through interactions with other aerosols or by modifying the atmospheric stability and moisture content. These indirect effects can influence cloud formation, cloud lifetime, and cloud radiative properties, leading to changes in shortwave cloud forcing. Even though, there are studies on the concentrations of WSOC over various geographical locations in South Asia, a comprehensive picture is not yet evolved. Considering the importance of WSOC, the spatial variation and source characteristics over south Asia is depicted in this article. To get a clear picture, the data of carbonaceous aerosols (Organic Carbon (OC), Elemental Carbon (EC), Secondary OC (SOC), WSOC from the extensive observations carried out over the region combined with that reported in the literature.

METHODS

We have used the Total Organic Carbon analyser (TOC-LCPH, Shimadzu, Japan) that employs the principle of catalytic combustion oxidation at 680°C for measuring the WSOC concentration (Aswini *et al.*, 2018). The data reported by other investigators in this study have also used the same technique for WSOC measurement following similar protocol. The three different ratios are used to delineate different source processes; OC/EC for source identification (Cachier *et al.*, 1989), WSOC/OC for long-range atmospheric transport (ageing) and WSOC/SOC to understand the primary and secondary contribution of WSOC (Boreddy *et al.*, 2018).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The spatial variability of WSOC for distinct sectors over South Asia during winter period is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Spatial variability of WSOC for distinct sectors over South Asia during winter period. The analysis revealed that, over south Asian region during winter, pre-monsoon and post-monsoon all locations were found to have WSOC/SOC greater than unity with WSOC/OC > 0.4 (Table 1). Similarly, during monsoon season, both Himalaya and IGP shown the same trend. Over these locations, wide range of water-soluble compounds released by biomass burning contributes directly to the WSOC fraction or undergo further atmospheric processing, such as oxidation or aging, leading to the formation of additional WSOC. WSOC/OC (organic carbon) ratio and the correlation between the WSOC and secondary organic carbon (SOC) are used for assessing the importance of secondary sources. Variability in the characteristics

of WSOC over different sectors over south Asia based on the average concentrations and ratios (OC/EC, WSOC/SOC and WSOC/OC) during different seasons were extensively analysed.

Table 1. The sector wise average of OC/EC, WSOC/OC and WSOC/SOC values during different seasons.

Ratio	Season	Himalaya	IGP	North-West	South Peninsula	Marine
OC/EC		5.67±1.24	6.36±2.60	6.29±1.48	3.19±1.78	3.30±1.62
WSOC/OC	Winter	0.57±0.10	0.47±0.14	0.44±0.21	0.49±0.13	0.72±0.15
WSOC/SOC		1.98±0.85	1.08±0.52	1.73	0.99±0.37	3.35±2.12
OC/EC		4.0±1.34	3.45±1.0	6.03±1.52	5.31±1.18	
WSOC/OC	pre-Monsoon	0.48±0.23	0.54±0.15	0.43±0.08	0.44±0.09	
WSOC/SOC		1.52±0.93	1.40±0.72	1.06±0.12	1.03±0.41	
OC/EC		5.23±2.50	4.35±1.78	9.03±2.1	4.74±0.61	
WSOC/OC	Monsoon	0.63±0.03	0.63±0.17	0.28±0.15	0.46±0.01	
WSOC/SOC		1.13±0.40	1.30±0.68	0.24	0.85±0.20	
OC/EC		4.29±1.02	6.20±3.05	5.84	4.56±1.30	
WSOC/OC	post-Monsoon	0.70±0.11	0.57±0.13	0.36	0.51±0.21	
WSOC/SOC		1.39±0.54	1.60±0.38		1.11±0.84	

CONCLUSIONS

The present investigation based on the extensive analysis of the data set reported over South Asia, revealed that, the primary OC that have undergone substantial chemical processing as a result of long-range transport have a significant influence on WSOC formation over south Asia, especially in IGP outflow regions such as southern peninsular and adjacent marine regions. Overall, oxidation and ageing of primary organic aerosols emitted from biomass burning was found to serve as an important source of WSOC over south Asia.

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SOURCES AND FORMATION PATHWAYS OF WATER-SOLUBLE ORGANIC AEROSOLS OVER WESTERN GHATS INDUCED BY TWO DISTINCT AIR MASSES

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 Keywords: CARBONACEOUS AEROSOLS, ANTHROPOGENIC SOURCES, BIOGENIC SOURCES, PHOTOCHEMICAL PROCESSING.

INTRODUCTION

The Western Ghats, a series of foothills that range along the west coast of peninsular India, is one of the eight biodiversity hotspots in the world. It is a home to an astonishing array of flora and fauna, many of which are endemic. Based on recent observations made over the Western Ghats, there is a need to investigate the chemistry of particulate matter, especially the molecular level characterization of water-soluble organic aerosols (WSOA). The goal of the present study is to assess the molecular fingerprints, sources and formation pathways of WSOA in the submicron particles (PM_{1.1}) at Ponmudi, a tropical high altitude remote hill station at the southern part of the Western Ghats.

METHODS

Aerosol chemical characterization involves two steps viz, collection of particulate samples using appropriate sampling procedures and chemical analysis of the collected samples. Submicron particles were collected using a SIBATA high volume (Model HV-1000R) air sampler. A total of 23 PM_{1.1} samples and field blanks were collected on pre-combusted quartz fiber filter at ISRO facility in Ponmudi (8.8°N, 77.1°E, 960 m a.s.l.) from January 31 to March 21, 2020 and February 19 to April 10, 2021. The sampling duration for each sample was about 2 to 3 days. Organic carbon (OC) and elemental carbon (EC) fraction of the carbonaceous aerosols is measured using OC-EC analyzer. A non-oxidizing stage and an oxidizing stage is used for the detection of OC and EC, respectively. Water-soluble OC (WSOC) is analyzed using total organic carbon (TOC) analyzer. Detailed instrumentation and methodology of the analysis of OC, EC and WSOC is described in Aswini *et al.* (2018). A gas chromatograph (GC) equipped with flame ionization detector (FID) is used for the analysis of water-soluble organic compounds, including dicarboxylic acids, oxocarboxylic acids and α-dicarbonyls. The methodology adapted for the GC-FID analysis of samples is presented in Hegde *et al.* (2022). Five days air mass back trajectories (BTs) at 100 m a.g.l. are computed using the Hybrid Single-Particle Lagrangian Integrated Trajectory (HYSPPLIT) model.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

According to the BTs (Figure 1), the samples collected at Ponmudi are categorized in to two kinds of samples. We found 11 samples controlled by mixed air masses (continental + marine), whereas 12 samples are mainly influenced by marine air masses. Oxalic acid (C₂) is the most abundant compound in samples of both air masses, followed by malonic (C₃), succinic (C₄), azelaic (C₉) and phthalic (Ph) acid in marine air mass samples and terephthalic (tPh), C₄, glutaric (C₅) and Ph in mixed air mass samples (Figure 1). Glyoxylic acid (ωC₂) is the most abundant oxocarboxylic acid in both the mixed and marine air mass samples. The ratio of C₃ to C₄, which is an indicator of photochemical processing (Kawamura and Ikushima, 1993), ranges from 0.61-1.9 (avg. 1.1) in marine air mass sample and 0.17-1.1 (avg. 0.49) in mixed air mass sample. This result signifies that marine air mass samples are more photochemically processed than mixed air mass samples.

Figure 1. Schematic showing different type of air masses and composition of water-soluble organic compounds in PM_{1.1} samples at the observation site.

The correlations of C₂ with C₃, C₃ with C₄ and C₂ with C₉ are positive and significant in marine air mass samples ($r = 0.59, 0.79$ and 0.83 , respectively), whereas the correlations are insignificant in mixed air mass samples. Moreover, C₂ presented significant positive correlations with Ph ($r = 0.83$) and benzoic acid ($r = 0.67$) in mixed air mass sample. This indicates that water-soluble organic aerosols had a stronger influence from anthropogenic sources in mixed air mass samples, whereas in marine air mass sample, they are mainly biogenic in nature. This is further supported by the diagnostic mass ratio of Ph/C₉, which varied from 0.11-0.92 (avg. 0.51) and 1.1-5.0 (avg. 3.1), respectively, in marine and mixed air mass samples. The correlation analysis between C₂ acid abundance in total measured water-soluble organic compounds and the ratios with its precursor compounds suggest that oxalic acid is largely formed via the photochemical oxidation of organic precursors during atmospheric transport.

CONCLUSION

The molecular fingerprints of water-soluble organic aerosols revealed the abundance of oxalic acid in both the mixed and marine air mass aerosol samples, followed by terephthalic acid in mixed air mass sample, and malonic or succinic acid in marine air mass sample. The ratios of malonic to succinic acid and phthalic to azelaic acid, along with the correlations with the organic molecular marker compounds, indicates that the water-soluble organic aerosols originated from anthropogenic sources in mixed air mass sample and biogenic sources in marine air mass sample. Moreover, aerosols collected under the influence of marine air masses exhibited higher levels of photochemical processing compared to those obtained under the influence of mixed air masses. We conclude that the development of water-soluble organic aerosol over the Western Ghats is driven by the input of anthropogenic and biogenic precursors, as well as photochemical processing during atmospheric transport.

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GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION OF BLACK CARBON FROM SATELLITE RETRIEVAL

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Keywords: SATELLITE RETRIEVAL, BLACK CARBON, BIOMASS BURNING.

INTRODUCTION

The radiation budget of the Earth is strongly affected by light-absorbing black carbon (BC) aerosols. Multiple experiments and models, all examining the climate warming potential of BC, necessitates accurate quantification and seasonal source characterization of BC on regional and global scales (IPCC, 2021). A novel method of measuring and classifying BC across distinct geographic regions worldwide is the synchronization of satellite-based radiation measurements with ground-based point measurements. However, satellite retrieval of BC over land is complicated by their complex optical properties arising out of highly heterogeneous sources and transformation processes. Several new algorithms have been developed for aerosol retrieval over land, but retrievals of BC from satellite-based radiation measurements have been few. This study presents the global distribution of BC based on satellite-based retrievals from Thermal And Near infrared Sensor for carbon Observation–Cloud and Aerosol Imager-2 (TANSO-CAI-2) observations made from the Greenhouse gases Observing Satellite-2 (GOSAT-2).

METHODS

The retrieval technique is based on fine-mode aerosol optical depth (AOD) estimates at multiple pixels, along with estimation of the volume mixing ratio of BC in fine-mode particles. Using the relation of surface reflectance and observed reflection passing through the aerosol layer at multiple pixels, the AOD and aerosol absorption properties are retrieved simultaneously. The multi-wavelength and multi-pixel (MWPM) method adapted for the retrieval is a combination of an optimal method based on Bayesian estimation and smoothing constraint to horizontal aerosol distribution to solve the problem. Several a priori values around the true states are considered to simultaneously retrieve fine-mode and coarse-mode AODs, soot volume fraction in fine-mode aerosols, and surface reflectance over heterogeneous surfaces over multi-wavelengths and multiple pixels. To evaluate and validate the spatiotemporal distribution of BC from satellite retrieval, near-surface BC mass concentrations measured across the Aerosol Radiative Forcing over India NETwork (ARFINET) of aerosol observatories are used. The results depicted RMSE < 1 and absolute difference below 2 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ for > 60 % of simultaneous satellite and ground-based observations, exhibiting good associations for December, January, and February (R of approximately 0.73) and March, April, and May (R approx. 0.76).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The global spatiotemporal variation of BC from satellite retrievals shows several typical hotspots throughout the year. They vary in magnitude, including many regions of South America, Africa, India, and China, with several of them coinciding with biomass burning activities. Significantly enhanced values of BC are also found for western Canada and the USA, over Europe, and Russia because of large fires occurring mainly during April–August. As revealed from the global map of fire radiative power (FRP)s, the fire activity increases in March over Southeast Asia, northeastern China, and some parts of southern and south-eastern China. This pattern continues through May. For northern latitudes, the fire season begins in April–May. During the summer (JJA) season, the large-scale outbreak of forest fires occurs in the boreal forests of North America and Russia. In central Siberia, forest fires occur in April or at the beginning of May in southern areas and in June in northern areas (above 60° N latitude), with peak fire activity occurring in July. The fire activities over these regions contribute substantially to the aerosol emissions and inject higher amounts (percent) of plumes from forest and woody fires into the free

troposphere. In southern Africa, peak burning activity mainly takes place during July–September. However, the rainforest in central Africa, being the largest biomass burning region, shows a large increase in the magnitude of BC during both DJF and JJA, during which the biomass burning activities are also prominent. It is particularly interesting that some oceanic regions near the coast of western Africa also show higher values of BC during DJF and JJA. Some offshore fires are also seen to be contributing to the BC load on the west coast of Africa. These observations clearly indicate that the spatio-temporal variation in BC across the globe is mostly coincident with the regions of intense biomass burning activities, whereas BC over some regions of southern Asia and China do not collocate with the biomass burning regions.

Figure 1. Global map satellite retrieved monthly BC ($0.25 \times 0.25^\circ$) during March – June, 2019..

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, satellite retrieval of BC is demonstrated to be an effective means for monitoring BC loading resulting from vehicular, industrial, and biomass burning.

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ASSESSING CARBONACEOUS AEROSOLS FROM ON-ROAD VEHICLES: INFLUENCE OF DIVERSE DRIVING CONDITIONS AND FLEET COMPOSITIONS

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Keywords: Carbonaceous aerosols, light absorption, on-road vehicles, emission factors

INTRODUCTION

Emissions from on-road vehicles are a significant and increasing source of carbonaceous aerosols. This can be attributed to rapid economic growth and the ongoing urbanization trend, which has led to an exponential rise in global transport demand, particularly in developing economies, like India. The expanding vehicle population is a major driver of congestion and air pollution, posing human health and climate risks in urban areas. Aerosols have a direct impact on the balance of atmospheric radiation, resulting in reduced and changes in the lifespan of clouds (Liu et. al., 2016). While organic carbon (OC) scatters light and contributes to atmospheric cooling, black carbon (BC) and certain light-absorbing organic carbon, referred to as brown carbon (BrC), induce atmospheric warming (Che et. al., 2019). Chemical and optical properties of aerosols from vehicular emissions are not yet fully understood, especially in Indian context. The primary objectives of the study include: (1) to characterise the carbon profile and light absorption properties of aerosols from on-road vehicles, (2) to investigate the impact of varying fleet composition and driving conditions, and (3) to estimate emission factors (EF) of carbonaceous aerosols from different vehicular fleets.

METHODS

Aerosol measurements were carried out using roadway tunnel and roadside measurements. Two roadway tunnels (Freeway Tunnel: FT and Kamshet-I Tunnel: KT) and two kerbsides (LBS road and Mulund Toll Plaza: MTP in Mumbai) were selected based on their distinct traffic characteristics such as speed (based on Modified Indian Driving Cycle), type of roads, vehicle types (LDV: light duty vehicles, HDV: heavy duty vehicles) and fuel composition (petrol, diesel and CNG vehicles). A very small fraction of electric vehicles was also observed in the fleet at LBS road and at MTP. Portable real-time and gravimetric instruments were used to capture emissions from high-speed (50-60 km.hr⁻¹) urban traffic (at FT: all LDV fleet), low speed (15-35 km.hr⁻¹) creeping traffic (at LBS road: 5% HDDVs and rest LDV fleet) and idling (<15 km.hr⁻¹) traffic (at MTP: 8% HDDVs and rest LDV fleet) in Mumbai city, and high-speed (70-90 km.hr⁻¹) inter-city traffic (at KT on Mumbai-Pune expressway: 20% HDDV and 80% LDV), covering both peak (07:00–11:59 AM) and off-peak (12:00–05:00 PM) traffic hours. Simultaneous measurements were also carried out at an urban background (during the roadside measurements) location in Powai, Mumbai.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Carbonaceous aerosols accounted for up to half of the total PM_{2.5} mass concentration across all four measured vehicular fleets, highest being in the fleet with highest HDV fraction (at KT). Around 60% of OC was comprised of high volatile organic carbon (HVOC: OC1 and OC2) in the LDV dominated fleets at FT and LBS road, while the low volatile organic carbon (LVOC: OC3 and OC4) dominated (~75% of total OC) in the mixed fleet with higher heavy duty diesel vehicle fleet at KT and MTP. In case of the EC fractions, EC1 dominated at FT, followed by EC2 and EC3. At KT it was EC2 that dominated the EC concentrations followed by EC3 and EC1 (80% of the EC was Soot-EC), mainly driven by the diesel powered HDVs. Similar EC profiles was observed at LBS road and MTP which had small yet significant

HDV and super-emitter (SE) fraction. The highest OC/EC ratio was observed at FT (1.58 ± 0.6) and lowest at KT (0.6 ± 0.2). Lower water-soluble OC (WSOC) was found lowest in the higher HDV fleets indicating the hydrophobic nature of soot aerosols. These differences in the carbon profile indicated the influence of vehicle and fuel composition in the fleets. Light absorption coefficients were observed to be 1.4 to 2.6 times higher in the fleets with higher HDVs. The methanol-soluble (MS) BrC were significantly higher than the water-soluble (WS) BrC and a strong association was observed between the LVOC and MS-BrC ($r^2=0.76$), suggesting strong influence of LVOCs in the absorbing characteristics of the aerosols. The emission factors from different fleets are given below in Table 1.

Table 1: Estimated emission factors derived from different vehicular fleets

Pollutants (veh⁻¹.Km⁻¹)	Idling traffic 10% HDV 16% SE (Toll plaza)	Low-speed traffic 5% HDV 14% SE (LBS road)	High speed all LDV fleet 12% SE (FT)	High speed 20% HDV fleet 22% SE (KT)
PM _{2.5}	54 ± 18	28 ± 12	44.2 ± 26.9	314 ± 65
OC	18.5 ± 6.2	11.3 ± 9.6	12.6 ± 5.1	56.2 ± 13.8
EC	13.2 ± 8.4	6.5 ± 3.8	9.8 ± 3.7	108.6 ± 21.5
WSOC	7.7 ± 2.9	5.2 ± 4.1	7.1 ± 2.6	29.4 ± 11.6

SE: Super-emitters (high emitting vehicles that can be poorly maintained, old, heavily loaded vehicles or all of them)

CONCLUSIONS

Our study finds that while the near road emission levels are inevitably higher than background locations due to the significant contribution from the on-road vehicles, the emission profiles vary significantly depending on the vehicle and fuel composition. Higher HDV and SE fraction in the fleet contributed to three times higher EC concentrations. They also emitted higher light absorbing aerosols as compared to the LDVs. These findings can help in making informed policy decisions towards urban vehicle emission control and monitoring by focussing on targeted vehicles that are polluting disproportionately more than rest of the vehicles.

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SOURCES OF FINE CARBONACEOUS AEROSOLS OVER A SEMI-ARID URBAN CITY OF WESTERN INDIA USING DUAL CARBON ISOTOPES

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Keywords: Carbonaceous aerosol, Radiocarbon, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, Aging, Transport

INTRODUCTION

Rapid urbanization of many regions has led to a significant increase in air pollution levels all over the globe. Among different pollutants, carbonaceous aerosols (CA) are the major one and they emit from the incomplete combustion of biomass and fossil fuel sources. Study of CA is very important because it can affect the human health, Earth's radiation budget, hydrological cycle, ocean biogeochemistry etc (Bond et al., 2013; Liu et al., 2020). This study was conducted over Ahmedabad, a rapidly growing urban city situated in the semi-arid region of western India, an under-studied region. The sampling period covers post-monsoon, winter, spring, and summer seasons. During winter, the airmasses from highly polluted Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) are transported to the Arabian Sea through the sampling region. Similarly, clean airmasses from the Arabian sea is flown through the sampling region during summer. Chemical (organic carbon (OC), elemental carbon (EC), water-soluble OC, and organic speciation using HR-ToF-AMS), optical (black carbon (BC) and water-soluble brown carbon, BrC), and isotopic (^{13}C and ^{14}C) measurements were conducted on the samples collected during these seasons, and the results are briefly discussed in this abstract.

METHODS

The 24-hour averaged $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ samples were collected at the roof of the main building of Physical Research Laboratory Ahmedabad, and the mass concentrations were calculated gravimetrically. The sampling was conducted from Nov 2020 to Jun 2021 which were classified in to post-monsoon (Nov), winter (Dec-Jan), spring (Feb-Mar) and summer (Apr-Jun). The EC and OC concentrations were measured using EC-OC analyser, WSOC using a TOC-TN analyser, major ions using ion chromatography, organic speciation using HR-ToF-AMS, and carbon isotopes using isotope ratio mass spectrometer and accelerator mass spectrometer. More details regarding the measurements can be seen in Devaprasad et al. (2023). Simultaneously, the ambient BC concentration was measured using a multi-wavelength aethalometer connected through $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ cutoff cyclotron. The radiocarbon measurement in total carbon (TC) is reported as $f_{\text{bio_TC}}$, where $f_{\text{bio_TC}}$ value of 1 means 100 % of CA from biomass burning (BB)/ biogenic source and $f_{\text{bio_TC}}$ value of zero means 100 % contribution from fossil sources.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Figure. 1 shows the time series of various particulate matter components across all the seasons. The highest $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration, observed on November 14th, was attributed to emissions from firecrackers during the Diwali festival, coinciding with an enrichment in the carbon isotope $\delta^{13}\text{C}$. To quantify the organic matter (OM) concentration, we multiplied OC concentration by the OM/OC ratio obtained from aerosol water-extracts analysed with HR-ToF AMS. The combined contribution of OM and EC collectively referred to as CA (OM+EC), exhibited seasonal variations, contributing $42 \pm 10\%$, $53 \pm 11\%$, $55 \pm 12\%$, and $29 \pm 6\%$ to the total $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ mass during post-monsoon, winter, spring, and summer seasons. The lower contribution of CA (%) in post-monsoon is likely due to higher emissions of ions and metals from burning firecrackers during Diwali. Further, ^{14}C analysis suggests that $\sim 64\%$ of CA during the post-monsoon and winter seasons were from BB/biogenic sources, and this fraction progressively reduced as summer approached. Examination of the OC-EC regression line slopes revealed consistent primary sources of CA during both winter and summer, while the intercept indicated a higher contribution of secondary organic aerosols (SOA) during the winter season (34%) compared to summer (16%). Further analysis involving various chemical and isotopic measurements, such as WSOC/OC, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, and OM/OC,

demonstrated that CA during the winter season had undergone oxidation and aging processes, likely originating from long-range transport. The air mass back trajectory indicates these air masses were originating from the heavily polluted north western Indo-Gangetic plain during winter. Post-monsoon has shown enriched $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ compared to all other season, which is attributed to specific types of biomass burning and its memory effect during Diwali. Additionally, a robust positive correlation ($R^2=0.76$, $n=26$) was established between $f_{\text{bio_TC}}$ and $\text{BC}_{370/950}$, indicating similar sources for both elemental EC and TC over Ahmedabad.

Figure 1. Shows the stacked bar plot of the mass concentrations of organic matter (OM), WSIS, EC, and others. The total length of the bars represents $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration, and the light green bar indicates the WSOM. The figure also shows the f_{bio} and stable carbon isotopic ratio ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$).

CONCLUSIONS

OM is the major contributor to the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ in all the seasons and winter have significant additional CA from the upwind regions. Around 64 % of CA during post-monsoon and winter originated from BB/biogenic sources, and their contribution kept decreasing till summer. Chemical and isotopic measurements revealed the presence of aged CA during winter, likely from long-range transport. Most enriched $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ was found in post-monsoon, which is attributed to burning of specific type of biomass during Diwali. A strong positive correlation was found between radiocarbon-derived $f_{\text{bio_TC}}$ and $\text{BC}_{370/950}$, indicating similar sources for EC and TC. Such studies are very important to quantify the different sources and the formation mechanisms of air pollutants and it will help in the planning of effective mitigation policies.

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THE SMOG-INDIA_{COALESCE} EMISSIONS INVENTORY

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Keywords: emission calculator, data management system, high geospatial resolution

INTRODUCTION

Emissions inventories underlie policies and agreements towards the reduction of emissions of environmentally damaging pollutants could include governmental regulatory regimes, for example, to meet air pollution standards or intergovernmental agreements to meet environmental or climate targets. Such emission reduction could include those by public entities or private enterprises including energy companies, industry or emissions trading firms. To complement global inventories e.g. the updated CEDS (McDuffie et al. 2020) database, we need national emission inventories to better capture regional activities and practices, which may be peculiar to specific regions and vary across regions, especially those which occur in the informal economy. Further high spatio-temporal resolution of emission releases is essential to capture air pollution and climate impacts. The Speciated Multipollutant Generator (SMoG-India_{COALESCE}) emission inventory has been developed under the National Carbonaceous Programme’s network on Carbonaceous Aerosol Emissions Source Apportionment and Climate Impacts (COALESCE).

METHODS

The SMOG-India_{COALESCE} emission inventory management combines a database management system, an emission calculator module embedded with robust sectoral methodologies and a query-based web-interface for visualization. Input data (such as activity data, emission factors) of a particular in specified formats into are stored in a database management system (DBMS), which converts these data into similar formats for archival and easy access. An emissions calculator performs the required calculations using the underlying methodology in the Python programming language. The results are fed back into the DBMS and output is extracted and displayed using a geographical information system (GIS) through a graphical user interface (GUI) as a standalone computer software enabling query-based use (Figure 1).

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The schematic of the SMOG-India_{COALESCE} emission inventory management system (Figure 1) illustrates different elements of the inventory and an example of data visualization.

Figure 1: Schematic of the SMOG-India_{COALESCE} Emissions Inventory

The emissions inventory estimates emissions from India at the country, state and district administrative levels, as well as at the 5km x 5km gridded level. Species include greenhouse gases (CO₂, N₂O), air pollutants and their precursor gases, some of which are short-lived climate pollutants (black carbon BC,

organic carbon OC, sulphur dioxide SO₂, and ozone precursors including NO_x and volatile organic gases (NMVOC). India level annual emissions for the 2019 base year (Figure 2) show emission totals of 10.6 Tgy⁻¹ primary PM_{2.5}, 1.1 Tgy⁻¹ of black carbon or BC and 3.1 Tgy⁻¹ of organic carbon or OC.

Figure 2: Annual India Emissions of PM_{2.5}, BC and OC for the base year 2019.

The distribution of emissions among different emitting sectors, shows that between formal sectors (thermal power, transport and industry) and informal sectors (residential, agriculture and brick production) the distributions of emissions (formal:informal%) for primary PM_{2.5} is 40:60%, BC is 35:65% and OC is 8:92%. This suggests that aerosol emissions in the Indian region are strongly influenced by informal sector emissions. The paper will further analyse emissions across pollutants and spatial scales of source contributions to species of air pollution and climate relevance.

CONCLUSIONS

The SMOG-India_{COALESCE} emissions inventory is a step towards accurate estimation of the magnitude and sectoral split of emissions, crucial to underpin effective air pollution and climate mitigation strategies. Especially for air pollution mitigation, the high spatial resolution of the inventory provides information for possibly different control strategies at multiple administrative scales across India.

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CHARACTERISTICS, TEMPORAL VARIATION, AND SOURCE IDENTIFICATION OF FINE CARBONACEOUS AEROSOLS OVER INDO-GANGETIC PLAIN IN INDIA

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Keywords: Carbonaceous Aerosols, Indo-Gangetic Plain, Organic Carbon, Black Carbon, Cluster Analysis, Backward Trajectories.

INTRODUCTION

Of all the air pollutants, Carbonaceous aerosols (CAs) consisting of Organic Carbon (OC) and Black Carbon (BC), constitute up to ~10-70% of the PM_{2.5} in the urban atmosphere (Bhowmik et al. 2021). The Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP) is home to the world's most smog-plagued cities. In this study, the mass concentration trends of carbonaceous aerosols (CAs), including organic carbon (OC), black carbon (BC), their long-range transport and role of meteorology, were examined over a 3-year period (January 2019–December 2021) in five (5) highly polluted IGP cities in India: Delhi, Hisar, Kanpur, Muzaffarpur, and Kolkata.

METHODS

Hourly dataset for CAs was extracted from Modern-Era Retrospective analysis for Research and Application, Version 2 (MERRA-2). The hourly meteorological data (relative Humidity (%), wind speed (ms⁻¹), ambient temperature (°C)) and data of other pollutants like PM_{2.5}, NO₂, SO₂, O₃ (µgm⁻³) and CO (mgm⁻³) were extracted from the Central Pollution Control Board's website. The hourly dataset was reduced to daily average for correlation analysis with CAs. Microsoft Excel application and R programming language (Openair Package) were used for statistical data analyses. The 5-day backward trajectories were created using Hybrid Single Particle Lagrangian Integrated Trajectory (HYSPLIT) model to study the transport pathways and cluster analysis was performed to group trajectories based on geographic origins.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The monthly mean OC and BC concentrations over IGP varied from 3.49 to 48.74 µgm⁻³ and 0.94 to 10.05 µgm⁻³, respectively, in different months. For all locations, the seasonal trend for both CAs was: Winter (DJF) > Post-Monsoon (ON) > Summer (MAM) > Monsoon (JJAS). The annual average for OC and BC over the study area ranged between 9.38 to 19.61 µgm⁻³ and 2.36 to 4.26 µgm⁻³, respectively. The OC/BC ratio varied between 3.56 and 6.84, with an average of 4.25 ± 0.19 for the study locations. Muzaffarpur saw highest OC/BC mean across all seasons, and the minimum was for Hisar. Seasonally, maximum OC/BC ratio was observed in post-monsoon season for Hisar, Delhi, and Kanpur whereas for Muzaffarpur and Kolkata, the maximum ratios were observed in summer season. When compared annually, the ratio was consistent for Hisar, Delhi, and Kanpur, while maximum variations were seen for Kolkata and Muzaffarpur.

When correlated, OC and BC depicted a strong positive correlation (>0.95) for all locations. A negative correlation was observed for CAs and the meteorological parameters (RH, WS, and AT) and low to moderate correlation with the gaseous pollutants. The contribution of CAs to PM_{2.5} load varied from ~13% in Hisar for 2019 to ~41% in Kolkata for 2021. The concentrations of CAs were observed to increase for all the years despite a decrease in PM_{2.5} concentrations in the year 2020. The highest contribution of CAs was observed for Kolkata (62.5 % in September 2020) and minimum observed for Hisar (5.38% in May 2019). Cluster and CWT analysis highlighted dominance of local contributions from IGP and lower Himalayas (Nepal, Uttarakhand and Himachal Pradesh), long-range transportation of aerosols from Tibet, the Arabian Sea, the Bay of Bengal and from the Sindh and the Punjab regions of Pakistan.

Figure 1. Raincloud plot representing (a) OC, (b) BC, and (c) OC/BC monthly means dispersion across all locations for three years.

Figure 2. (a.) Season-wise clustering of 5-day air mass backward trajectories and (b.) Season-wise CWT analysis results for OC for Delhi.

CONCLUSIONS

- For all locations, the highest monthly mean concentrations for CAs were observed in either November, December, or January.
- Muzaffarpur reported the highest while Hisar reported the minimum CAs concentrations throughout.
- Though in 2020, PM_{2.5} concentrations decreased due to COVID-19 imposed restrictions, upward trend of CAs continued to increase, indicating independent sources of PM_{2.5} and CAs in IGP.
- The average OC/BC ratio was >4, specifying biomass and fossil fuel burning as potential emission sources.
- BC and OC negatively correlated with the meteorological parameters (RH, WS, and AT) and low to moderately with the gaseous (air) pollutants.
- The highest contribution of CAs to PM_{2.5} load was noted for Kolkata throughout the study period.
- Cluster analysis and CWT plots revealed that IGP was the major contributor to CAs for all locations in the winter season. While long-range transport from Tibet, Pakistan, Myanmar, the Arabian Sea and the Bay of Bengal were observed for most locations for monsoon season.

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**HIGH-RESOLUTION AEROSOL EMISSIONS FROM CROP RESIDUE BURNING: A
COMPONENT OF SMOG-India^{COALECE}**

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Keywords: Carbonaceous aerosols, emissions inventory, crop residue burning

INTRODUCTION

Emissions from crop residue burning in India have come to the fore in the last decade because of their contribution to poor air quality episodes in northern India. They emit large amounts of carbonaceous aerosols and are especially significant during the post-harvest periods. A recent study showed, using field-surveys and multivariate regression models, that crop-burning is practiced across the country (Kapoor et al., 2023) not just in the northern-parts. In this study, we estimate high-resolution spatiotemporal emissions from the source for efficient application to climate, weather, and air-quality modelling.

METHODS

Emissions are calculated by multiplying the activity, or the amount of residue burned on-field, with the emission factors, or the mass of pollutants emitted per unit dry weight of residue. The district-wise activity information from a previous study (Kapoor et al., 2023) was multiplied with crop-type specific (rice, wheat, cereals, and other crops) emission factors adapted from previous compilation (Andreae, 2019) to calculate emissions. The district-specific emissions were then redistributed to days of the year using district-specific seasonal crop production information, harvest periods from surveys (taken from Kapoor et al., 2023), and the satellite derived fire counts (MODIS MOD14A1 product). Further, the daily- and district-specific emissions were redistributed to $0.05^\circ \times 0.05^\circ$ grids using the satellite derived (MODIS MCD12Q1 product) cropland information as a proxy. Therefore, we obtain an emissions inventory with high-resolution spatial and temporal information over the Indian domain.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The total emissions from PM_{2.5}, BC, and OC are estimated to be 927 Gg/year, 334 Gg/year, and 57 Gg/year. These emissions are dominated by the burning of (% OC emissions in parenthesis) rice (30%), wheat (32%), and sugarcane (11%) residues (Table 1). Large emissions are observed in the northern (rice, wheat, and sugarcane) and the central/western (wheat, sugarcane, and oilseeds). Significant burning is also observed in southern India (primarily of rice, sugarcane and cotton) (Figure 1D). Moreover, we observe substantial emissions from the burning of crops like oilseeds, cotton, and banana in western and southern India, which has not been reported previously. These emissions may not be substantial at the country level but are likely to be crucial at more regional scales.

Table 1. Emissions (Gg/year) from crop residue burning from different crop residues and post-harvest periods.

	Total	Oct-Nov	Apr-May	Feb-Mar	Rice	Wheat	Sugarcane
PM _{2.5}	927	238	341	195	340	252	90
OC	334	74	136	69	99	106	36
BC	57	11	16	16	10	9	12

The aerosols are emitted primarily during the post-harvest periods of kharif (Oct-Nov), rabi (Apr-May), and the late-kharif (Feb-Mar) harvest periods, contributing to 22%, 41%, and 21% of the yearly emissions, respectively (Figure 1B). Interestingly, most of the burning in post-kharif period is from rice residue burning in the north-western region. Meanwhile, most of the other crops - including wheat, oilseeds, and some sugarcane – is burned during the rabi period (April-May) (Figure 1C&D). Additionally, other crops like sugarcane and cotton, are also burned during the late-kharif Feb-March period in some parts.

Figure 1: High-resolution spatiotemporal OC emissions from crop residue burning in India, (A) gridded emissions at $0.05^\circ \times 0.05^\circ$ resolution, and daily emissions for (B) India, and (C) & (D) for select states.

CONCLUSIONS

Accurate estimation of crop residue burning is crucial to understanding their impacts on air-quality and climate. The present study reports high-resolution emissions from crop residue burning in India using ground-verified activity data and updated emission factors. We find that while the emissions of rice residue burning are extensively studied, emissions are also significant in other periods, from other crops, and other areas.

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OPTICAL PROPERTIES OF PM_{2.5} FROM LIGHT-DUTY GOODS AND HEAVY-DUTY VEHICLES IN INDIAN ON-ROAD CONDITIONS

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Keywords: On-road vehicular emissions, Black carbon, Mass absorption cross-section.

INTRODUCTION

On-road transport sector is one of the important sectors that contributes in urban air pollution and affects climate change and human health. Diesel powered vehicles are dominant fuel consuming vehicles in Indian on-road fleet which are responsible for particulate emissions (Pandey and Venkataraman, (2014)). Tailpipe emissions of diesel vehicles consist of carbonaceous aerosol including particulate matter and light absorbing carbon. Mass emission and its composition from vehicle tailpipe depend on many factors such as type of fuel, vehicle technology, maintenance and driving characteristics. Jaiprakash and Habib, (2017) suggested that the tailpipe emissions from laboratory (chassis dynamometer) and model studies are significantly different from emissions measured through on-road measurement. Aerosol absorption and scattering properties such as mass absorption cross-section (MAC) and mass scattering coefficients (MSC) play an important role in regional climate assessment. Therefore, in presents study, the real-world mass absorption cross-section and mass scattering coefficient from exhaust emissions of light-duty (goods) and heavy-duty vehicles (Trucks and tractors) will be presented in Indian on-road conditions.

METHODS

On-road measurement of emissions from light motor vehicles (LMV)-goods, tractors and trucks were performed in real world conditions in Nalanda district in Bihar using versatile source sampling system (VS3). In VS3, a fraction of exhaust entering through an isokinetic particle sampling probe into a dilution tunnel designed for homogenous mixing, negligible wall losses and complete aerosol quenching. A turbulent and instantaneous mixing of exhaust with 40-60 times zero air inside the dilution tunnel exhibits the dilution process that happens in the atmosphere. Portability, low power requirement and continuous clean air supply are other important attributes of VS3 for its on-field use. The emission measurements were conducted on rural roads and highways with load and no-load conditions on a 15-20 km mixed traffic route daily followed by the driver. PM mass was collected on different filter substrate for gravimetric and chemical analysis. The particle absorption and scattering were measure with 7-wavelength aethalometer (AE33) and Nephelometer (IN102) respectively. The carbonaceous fraction of PM_{2.5} was determined on Quartz filter using Thermal optical reflectance analyser.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

BC and EC concentration in the vehicle exhaust were found in the range of 5000-40000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for the tractors, LMV-goods and trucks. A correlation plot was made for BC and EC concentration as shown in figure 1 and found a good correlation between them with R^2 value of 0.97. Mass absorption cross-section ($\text{m}^2/\text{gPM}_{2.5}$) was presented in a box plot as shown in figure 2 for tractor, LMV-goods and truck. MAC value was found higher for tractor (1.4-10.4) and truck (4.4-8.3) as compare to LMV-goods (0.8-5.3) due to having lower concentration of BC for LMV-goods. Variation of MAC for tractor, LMV-goods and truck of different emission norms on rural roads and highways with load and no-load condition of vehicles will be discussed in the paper. Mass scattering coefficients will also be discussed in the paper for the same vehicle categories.

Figure 1. Correlation plot for black carbon and elemental carbon concentration in exhaust for all set of experiments of tractor, LMV-goods and truck vehicles.

Figure 2. Mass absorption cross-section for tractor, LMV-goods and truck for all set of experiments.

CONCLUSIONS

The mass concentration of EC determined from TOR method have shown good correlation with BC obtained from aethalometer (Figure 1). The mass absorption cross section of particles emitted from truck and tractor were higher than those from LMV-goods (Figure 2). A strong dependence of MACs on vehicle age has been observed. The finding from this study has implications in climate assessment and framing the policies for on-road use of vehicles for improving local air quality.

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DECADAL TREND OF BLACK CARBON AEROSOLS AT A SEMI-URBAN LOCATION IN THE CENTRAL IGP

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Keywords: Black Carbon, IGP, Aethalometer, Trend, Aerosols.

INTRODUCTION

Black carbon (BC), also known as soot, is a component of fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) and is primarily produced through incomplete combustion of fossil fuels, biomass, and other organic matter. It has negative impact on both human health and the climate (Bond et al., 2013). BC concentrations can vary over time and space due to a variety of factors, including emissions sources, meteorological conditions, and local environmental factors. Several studies have investigated BC variation over the Indo-Gangetic Plain (IGP), with a focus on understanding its sources, distribution, and impacts on air quality and climate (Tiwari et al., 2016; Vaishya et al., 2017). The present study highlights the BC variation and its trend using long-term ground-based observations over the Gorakhpur region, located in the central IGP.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

Black Carbon (BC) concentrations were measured using an Aethalometer AE33 (Drinovec et al., 2015) model (Magee Scientific, USA). The Aethalometer AE33 is a widely used instrument for real-time measurement of BC concentrations based on the principle of filter-based optical absorption. It measures the differential attenuation of light through a clean and a particle laden filter. This measurement of absorption of light is simultaneously done at seven wavelengths. BC mass concentration is then calculated from the absorption coefficient by multiplying it with a wavelength specific mass absorption cross-section (Weingartner et al., 2003).

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The present study focuses on the temporal variations of Black Carbon (BC) concentrations at Central IGP region in Gorakhpur station over a span of 10 years, from 2013 to 2022. Boxplots representing the annual distribution of BC concentrations reveal a significant decreasing trend in BC levels, with a rate of $0.67 \pm 0.21 \mu\text{g m}^{-3} \text{yr}^{-1}$ (Figure 1). This decline suggests a positive improvement in air quality and a potential reduction in BC emissions in the region.

Fig 1. Annual trend of BC concentrations in the central IGP. Black dot represents the annual mean concentration, end lines and middle line of box represents the 25th and 75th percentile and median, and the whiskers represent the standard deviation.

Manoj et al. (2019) observed decreasing trend in BC of $0.242 \pm 0.053 \mu\text{g m}^{-3} \text{yr}^{-1}$ over India during 2007 – 2016. In central IGP (Varanasi) indicate the increase in BC trend of $0.9 \mu\text{g m}^{-3} \text{yr}^{-1}$ for period of 2009 – 2013 (Srivastava et al., 2019). Our study utilizes BC data from 2013 to 2022, as no other trend analyses have covered the IGP region during this period.

Fire radiative power (FRP) data from MODIS and absorption aerosol index (AAI) data from OMI was analysed to find out if the reasons of decrease in BC concentrations over the years. It is seen, in Figure 2, that FRP and AAI, both, show an increasing trend of 1.089 W yr^{-1} and 0.024 yr^{-1} , respectively. This indicates that there might be a potential decrease in BC emissions from fossil fuel sources and increase in BC from biomass-burning sources resulting in a net decrease in BC concentrations over the years over the central IGP.

Fig 2. Annual trend of a) Fire radiative power (FRP) by MODIS; and b) AAI from OMI. The black dot represents the annual mean, end lines and middle line of box represents the 25th and 75th percentile and median, and the whiskers shows the standard deviation.

The declining trend in BC concentrations may stem from stricter regulations on industrial and vehicular emissions, increased public awareness, and advancements in technology favouring cleaner energy sources. Regulatory interventions and a shift towards renewable energy and cleaner fuels likely contribute to improved air quality, leading to lower BC levels.

CONCLUSIONS

This study presents a comprehensive analysis of the decadal trends in BC concentrations at Gorakhpur, in the central IGP. The findings indicate a consistent decrease in BC levels, both annually and across all seasons. The decline can be attributed to a combination of factors, including regulatory measures, and technological advancements. There is also a potential increase in BC emissions from biomass-burning sources. These results underscore the importance of continued efforts to reduce BC emissions and improve air quality in the region.

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VERSATILE SOURCE SAMPLING SYSTEM (VS3): TRACKING ON-FIELD RESIDENTIAL COOKING ACTIVITY EMISSIONS IN INDIA.

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Keywords: Aerosol monitoring, Combustion sources measurement, Portable sampling trains, Dilution system,

INTRODUCTION

Source emission estimates hold immense significance as they provide critical insights into the environmental and societal impacts of various human activities. These estimates are pivotal for assessing the environmental consequences of traditional cookstoves, industries, transportation, and agriculture, enabling regulators to identify major pollution sources and formulate effective strategies for improving air quality. Among all the major emission sources, residential solid biomass fuel use was found to contribute 40-45% of total PM_{2.5} emissions in India (Pandey et al. 2014). The previous estimate for cooking activity is mostly available from lab-based emission factors. Moreover, to have a precise emission estimate it is essential to capture the on-field emissions rather than in lab under controlled conditions. The on-field data collection gives a more precise estimate as it also captures the variable factors affecting the combustion characteristics. This accuracy is crucial for reducing uncertainties in emission inventories and ensuring that they truly reflect the environmental impact of various activities. The VS3 was designed with various types of inlets to capture area, line, and point source in India. The system was then evaluated to assure isokinetic sampling and minimal particle losses. It was used to capture emission from residential cooking activity in Haryana and Bihar.

METHODS

A portable versatile source sampling system (Figure 1) has been designed, fabricated, and evaluated with synthetic and combustion aerosols to measure emissions of different particulate and gaseous pollutants from stationary (residential/open biomass burning/brick kiln/small- or large-scale industries) and mobile (light and heavy-duty vehicles) sources. A dilution tunnel to operate at a lower dilution factor for residential cookstoves was also designed and evaluated in the present study. It can be operated to dilute the aerosol samples by a factor of 20-40.

The sampler was taken into field and the emissions were captured during the real-time cooking process. A total of 84 emissions measurements were conducted in Haryana and Bihar that includes various single fuel and mix-fuel use, open and semi-closed kitchens, and various cooking processes. The samples collected on filter papers were later analysed for gravimetric and chemical analysis. The emission factors were calculated using carbon balance method.

Figure 1: VS3 On-field set up capturing emission from traditional cookstoves.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The present study estimated (Habib et al. 2023) national solid biomass fuel consumption for 2019 was 291 (186-394) MT y⁻¹, which comprises 45% fuelwood (130 (77-182) MT y⁻¹), 18% crop residue (52.4 (36-68)

MT y⁻¹), and 37% dung cake (109 (73-144) MT y⁻¹). The national total LPG consumption estimated for 2019 was at 19.5 (13-26) MT y⁻¹. The emission factors have been updated using the present study values as well as the other field studies conducted in India. The emission factor of dung cake was found ~1.6 times higher than burning fuelwood highlighting higher contribution from dung cake (Figure 2a). The national PM_{2.5} emission estimate (Ggy⁻¹) for base year 2019 was 4263 having 50% contribution from dung cake use in cooking activity. The PM_{2.5} emissions has been spatially distributed at 5km x 5km grid Figure 2b.

Figure 2: (a) The emission estimate for base year 2019 from residential cooking activity; (b) PM_{2.5} emissions (Ggy⁻¹) spatially distributed at 5km × 5km grid.

The paper will discuss the national emission estimates for PM_{2.5}, black carbon BC, organic carbon OC, as well as sulfur dioxide (SO₂), greenhouse gases (CO₂, N₂O), and ozone precursors (NO_x, CO, CH₄, NMVOC or nonmethane volatile organic compounds) in detail.

CONCLUSIONS

The emission factors used for estimating the emissions from cooking activities are derived mostly from single fuel use assuming either fuelwood or dung cake is predominantly used for cooking activities. However, it was found that households use mix-fuel mostly rather single fuel for cooking and thus secondary fuel use emissions needs to be included in the emission estimation. The secondary fuel use does alter the emission characteristics depending on the type of fuel dominantly feeded while cooking.

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CONSTRAINING ESTIMATES OF BLACK CARBON (BC) EMISSIONS FROM OPEN BIOMASS BURNING USING LAGRANGIAN DISPERSION MODELLING

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Keywords: Aerosols modelling, black carbon, open biomass burning, FLEXPART

INTRODUCTION

Biomass burning is an essential component of biogeochemical cycles that influence climate, air quality and ocean productivity. Accurate estimation of trace gas and aerosol emissions from biomass combustion is critical for future air quality assessment and forecasting climate change. To constrain BC emission fluxes from agricultural waste burning and forest fires, we used fire products from MODIS Terra and Aqua satellites over India, as well as ground-based observations of BC and a Lagrangian transport model (FLEXPART). The simulated BC concentration using various inventories over an urban and a rural location in India, when compared against in-situ observations, were found to underestimate BC concentration. Other researchers' using spectral analyses and OC to BC ratios have shown that biomass-burning sources contribute significantly to BC in India. However, it still needs to be determined whether the biomass burning activity contributing BC concentrations at a given location is due to domestic indoor biomass burning or open biomass burning such as agriculture waste burning and forest fires.

METHODS

For our hypothesis, we estimated the contribution of the fire occurrences to the stations (receptor) where the observations are made. This was determined by integrating fire occurrences data from NASA's MODIS Spectroradiometer and Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite (VIIRS), as well as the S-R relation (also called potential emission sensitivity; PES) derived using the FLEXPART model. The combined SR relationship, alongside fire occurrence counts, encapsulated comprehensive details about particle trajectories and the proportion of particles arriving at the observation site from fire clusters within the Indian subcontinent. To estimate modeled black carbon (BC) concentrations, we multiplied the footprint PES values by emission fluxes obtained from various inventories for each grid point and subsequently integrated these values across the entire output grid.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Fig. 1 displays PES values for the surface to 100m layer for 2 days during the year 2014. One of the receptor sites, Ahmedabad, is denoted by a white star, and the red dots indicate fire hotspots identified by MODIS satellite (MODIS Collection 6 Hotspot) for 10 days backward for those 2 days. Fig. 2 shows the comparison of observed daily mean BC concentration and modelled BC concentration estimated using the ECLIPSE inventory for Ahmedabad for the year 2014. Also, the BC concentration estimated using the ECLIPSE inventory, only including the contribution from open biomass burning sources like agricultural burning, waste and flaring, is also shown. ECLIPSE inventory significantly underestimates the observed BC concentrations.

When a trajectory intersects with fire hot-spots, it is designated as influenced by open fires, with each intersecting fire being assigned a "weight" based on PES values at location of that fire event. Weighted fire counts (WFC) are calculated based on the assigned weights and all the days are ranked based on WFC values. Rank 1 represents the day when measurements over Ahmedabad are expected to have minimal influence of fires detected as hot-spots and the rank 365 represents the day when the measurements over Ahmedabad are expected to have maximum contribution from the

fire hot-spots. If the fires as detected in fire hot-spots was the most significant factor then one would expect a monotonically increasing BC concentration as a function of the rank but as one can see in Fig. 3, observed BC concentrations (brick red bars) are not increasing monotonically and rather follow a pattern similar to modelled BC concentrations (orange bars) excluding open fire sources.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

CONCLUSIONS

The modelled BC concentrations using the latest emission inventory are significantly lower than the observed black carbon aerosols particularly during winter and spring at the two locations. We find that the cause of underprediction of BC concentrations at Ahmedabad is unlikely to be the open biomass burning source like agriculture waste burning and forest fires.

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